

Nature and Dynamics of Health Culture: A Sociological Examination on the Changing Health Seeking Behavior and Medical Pluralism of the Rural Population in South Karnataka, India

Thesis Submitted to Srinivas University, Mangalore (India) in Partial Fulfillment for the Award of the Degree of **Doctor of Letters (D.Litt) in Sociology**

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Sept 2018

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DECLARATION

I **Dr. D.C Nanjunda** do hereby certify that the thesis entitled "*Nature and Dynamics of Health Culture: A Sociological Examination on the Changing Health Seeking Behavior and Medical Pluralism of the Rural Population in South Karnataka India*" is a record of original and independent post doctoral work and it has been carried out by me during the year 2011-2016 in the Centre for Social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy Centre, Mysore University and submitting it to the Srinivas University, Mangalore for the possible award of Degree of Doctor of Letters (D.Litt) in **Sociology** .

I further certify that this thesis has not been submitted by me for the award of any other degree or diploma of this or any other university and this research study is exclusively carried out by me for the possible award of Doctor of Letters in Sociology.

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This is to Certify that this thesis entitled “Nature and Dynamics of Health Culture: A Sociological Examination on the Changing Health Seeking Behavior and Medical Pluralism of the Rural Population in South Karnataka India’ is submitted by Dr. D C Nanjunda for the fulfilment of the requirements of D.Litt Degree in Sociology from Srinivas University, Mangalore. This study is an independent work done by Dr. D.C NANJUNDA in Centre for Study of Social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy (CSSEIP) University of Mysore-06 and this thesis has not been submitted for any degree / diploma / fellowship or any other similar title earlier to any University.

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Preface

Culture creates an inimitable example of beliefs and perceptions as to what “health” or “illness” actually means. In turn, this pattern of beliefs impudence how symptoms are recognized, to what they are attributed, and how they are interpreted, and this affects how and when health services are sought. The health seeking behavior of rural populations is very complex because it is influenced by a large number of factors among the most critical of these are issues of awareness.

Studies have suggested that the lack of optimal-utilization of modern health services by rural peoples is due to a variety of socio-cultural reasons. Some services are inappropriately used, whereas others, such as preventive healthcare, are under-utilized due to lack of awareness. Further, overcoming difficulties in communication that prevent one to interact with external changing forces is vital. Despite modern preventive and curative medicine, the healthcare delivery services in several rural areas are still poor and largely unscientific. Within the current comprehensive health intervention services there has been no attempt to understand health culture as a sub-culture complex. But this is precisely the perspective necessary to develop a model of a culturally suited health care delivery system specifically designed for the rural people of the country. It is said that established rurals’ health behavior should not be under estimated citing them as illiterate or superstitious . Even today major sections of the rural respondents are not ready to accept modern health system. Experts have lamented the dearth of micro-level data among such rural populations and have suggested that an effective solution to the health related problems of rural society must situate the problem within the larger contexts of changing health culture. It is said that cultural differences among rural people seeking health care as related to social structures and relationships and the degree of skepticism about professional medical care. Delay in seeking care was found among individuals belonging to cultural groups characterized by ethnic exclusivity, traditional family authority, and high skepticism about medicine. More recently, level of acculturation has been shown to account for differences in the use of health services within ethnic groups after controlling for age, gender, health status, and insurance coverage. This study is a Sociological Examination on the Changing Health Seeking Behavior and Medical Pluralism of the Rural Population in the Selected Districts of Karnataka state, I Thank Mysore University, and CSSEIP Centre, ICMR(New Delhi) and all my friends for their consistent support.

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Guidance

Thesis prepared with the guidance of the following scholars

1. Dr. Steven Wind, Department of Anthropology(formerly), University of Arizona-USA
2. Prof (Retd). M. Annapurna, Social Anthropologist, University of Mysore, Mysore –India
3. Dr. Sunitha V Ganiger, Department of Sociology, Tumkur University, Karnataka India
4. Prof. Douglas D Anderson, Department of Anthropology, Brown University, USA
5. Prof.(Retd).M. Muthurayappa, Medical Sociologist , ISEC, Bangalore India
6. Prof. Srinivasa Mani, Medical Anthropologist, Rock Slippery University-USA
7. Dr. M.C. Smith Asst. Professor, Dept. of Community Medicine, JSS Medical College, Mysore -India

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

1. Dr. Steven Wind, former faculty, Department of Anthropology, University of Arizona-USA for his lifelong academic help
2. Prof. Douglas D Anderson, Department of Anthropology, Brown University, USA for his priceless support
3. Prof.V.G. Talwar, the former Vice Chancellor, University of Mysore for his unforgotten help and support
4. Prof. K.S. Rangappa, Former Vice Chancellor, University of Mysore, Mysore for providing support and aid
5. Prof. Srinivasa Mani, Medical Anthropologist, Rock Slippery University-USA for his comment on the draft of the thesis
6. Prof. Muzafer H Assadi, Dept of Political Sciences , Mysore University for his assistance
7. Prof. Ananthan, the former Vice Chancellor, RCU, Belgaum for his academic support
8. Prof. M. Annapurna, Department of Anthropology, University of Mysore, for her timely support
9. Prof. Alic Patric, Professor of Sociology (Rtd.), Auckland, New Zealand for providing valuable recommendations
10. Dr. K.C. Srivatsa, Ayurvedic Doctor, Dist. health office, Mysore for his medical advise
11. Prof.(Retd).R. Muthu rayappa, Sociologist, Bangalore for his supportive role
12. Dr. J.K Guptha, Professor (Rtd) of Community Medicine, Mumbai for his assistance in data collection.
13. Dr, Anderson, Research Officer, Centre for Public Health, UK for his timely help
14. Dr.Lancy D souza, Asso. Prof, Maharaja college Mysore University for his support and Dr. P. N. Venugopal, AnS I, Kolkata for his statistical aid
15. Research faculties and the non -teaching staff of Centre for Study of Social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy(CSSEIP) , University of Mysore- Mysore for their never ending and valuable support throughout the study

Thanks for your kind help.....

Smt. Devajana Parvathi Chinnappa my adored parents, Mrs. S. Jyothi Lakshmi my beloved wife and my daughter D.N. Deeksha

Director and Staff of ICMR, New Delhi for their funding support (PDF);

Authors, editors and the publishers, of various journals, books, periodicals and the reports

The village people who participated in my research study and

The teaching and non teaching staff of University of Mysore, Prof. Lancy d Souza, Prof. Rama swamy, Sri Appaji gowda for their logistic support. Directors and the social workers of the various health research centers and the NGOs across the country, Dr. John Rose, Post Doctoral Fellow, University of New England, Dr. (Mrs.) Harsha Rao, Indian Institute of Advanced Studies -Simla, Dr. Ramkrishane Gowda, Dr. Srivthasa, Institute of Social Science, New Delhi, Anil Kumar (typist), Dr. V.N. Mahadeviah, Ms.Lepakshi, Raji, Harish M. Basker, D.C. Sujatha, Mahesha (Monish D T P centre), and Srikantha and others

More than that, I would like to express gratitude to all who played a vital role directly and indirectly in completing my research work in time with the grace of the God. All of you made it possible for me to arrive at this last stage of my attempt. Thank You from my heart-of-hearts.

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Thesis Structure and Reading Guidelines

A. **Introductory chapter** briefly explains the importance of the topic, and gives a very detailed introduction and background

B. The **Second chapter** deals about, methodology, objectives, methodology, conceptual framework of the study, limitations of the study

C. The **Third chapter** provides a review of the literature related to the study. The related studies are classified into four groups namely,

1. Studies relating to health status, consisting of studies related to the socio economic and other factors that determine the health status of rural people,
2. Studies relating to health culture, health behavior
3. Studies relating to medical pluralism, consisting of different systems of medicine
4. Other related health studies focusing rural health issues.

D. The **Fourth chapter** deals about health culture, health behavior and medical pluralism in the rural context.

D. The **Fifth chapter** discusses about theoretical perspectives on sociology of health illness. It provides an over view about various health belief models, approaches and theories including lexicalizations and other factors affecting on rural health culture

F. The **Sixth chapter is on** health Scenario in Karnataka state -India

G. The **Seventh chapter** deals about result and discussion. It is the major chapter of the study and has been divided into four sub chapters;

- i): Social, Economic, Demographic factors of the respondents
- (II) General Health status, practice of the respondents
- (III) Health concept, culture, medical pluralism and health behavior towards various illness/diseases
- V) Relationship between various social determinants and the health behavior
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H. The **Eight chapter** gives a picture of summary and conclusion

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j. **Tenth chapter** deals about Bibliography

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ABSTRACT

Health Culture creates an inimitable example of beliefs and perceptions as to what is “health” or “illness” actually means. In turn, this pattern of beliefs influencing how symptoms are recognized, to what they are attributed, and how they are interpreted, and this affects how and when health services are sought. The health seeking behavior of rural population is very complex because it is influenced by a large number of internal and external factors. Among the most critical of these are issues of health awareness. Lack of optimal-utilization of modern health services by rural people is due to a variety of socio-cultural reasons. Despite modern preventive and curative medicine, the healthcare delivery services in the several rural areas are still poor and largely an unscientific. Within the current comprehensive health intervention services there have been no attempt to understand health culture as a sub-culture complex. The aim of the study is to reveal the nature and dynamics of health culture (care practices) and changing health seeking behavior and medical pluralism of the rural population and to explore how these are determined by their unique and changing socio cultural background in the selected rural districts of South Karnataka, India. Also the current research study was to understand how different forces and approaches to health culture are determined in the larger and changing available modern medicines in the rural areas.

Various studies have proved that established rurals’ health behavior should not be underestimated just citing them as illiterate or superstitious (Helmance, 2001; Hardon, 2001). Even today major sections of the rural respondents are not ready to accept the modern health system. Because of stiff resistance within and out, many rural targeted health programmes have not been succeeded. Medical Anthropologists/sociologists felt the modern health programmes, do not have any space to respect peoples inherited health culture, emotions and spiritual meaning associated with health and diseases. It is believed that respondent’s health behaviour depends on the particular culture, particular geographical area and the particular eco-system. Here general culture and eco-system plays a vital role on respondent’s health seeking behaviour and in opting particular type of health care approach. Moreover it is found that health seeking behaviour varies according to the type of illness, causation of illness, gender and age of the patient. It is found that perception of illness and sickness directly affects on health seeking behaviour and health care seeking behaviour of any particular community.

It is found that there is much extreme diversity in the demographic behaviour of the rural people. Further, ethically, socially, economically, culturally rural people are having different perception on various developmental issues. Hence, it is found that health behaviour is much controlled by the social traditions and family based frame of mind rather than social and economic status. In certain rural parts, both traditional and modern medical health behaviour continuous to be antagonistic to each other as opined by Singh (2008). This is why rural people have pharmacopeia of their own and notion about various types of illness/disease they face normally in their life.

Disparities in health care issue were also found between people in different social classes and ethnicities within the same rural society, even though in the medical profession they put more importance in “health behaviours” such as alcohol, smoking, gutka, diet, and exercise. There is a big data supporting the wrapping up that these behaviors effect on health more drastically than other issues. Sociologists think that it is more obliging to look at health and illness through a broader lens. Delay in seeking care was found among individuals belonging to cultural groups characterized by ethnic exclusivity, traditional family authority, and high skepticism about medicine. Sociologists agree that alcohol consumption, smoking, diet, and exercise are some important issues, but they also see the significance of analysing the socio-cultural factors that influence these patterns. Sociologists also look at the effects of dynamic process on health and illness. Experts also looking at things such as environmental pollution, accidents at work, and stress-related diseases playing big roles among rural people in the globalized world (Gordon, 2009).

It is found that broad and specific geographical pattern of health behaviour can be seen across the villages and in some cases similar health culture also can be seen across the villages irrespective of caste/social groups. Also one of the great strength of rural health culture is the involvement of blood relatives/friends /and others in therapy management. Kins, friends, and other villagers will also help in the therapy management and has grate sociological significance. We found that this social support network in the treatment process including sharing, suggestions and counseling to the patents will boost the morality of the concerned patient. If the patient suffers from any pain normally the whole group shares the agony. Hence, healing process will be a type of a shared experience in rural parts. In this case rehabilitation of the patient will not be a problem at all. Also we noticed that the overall impact of various economic development processes, modern developments causes some positive or some negative effect on the rural health.

Continuous migration has done sever changes in the health culture of the rural folk(Joshi ,2004) .

We found before people seek medical help they try to interpret the illness / diseases symptoms themselves and often consult other people to get more clarity. Any common illnesses if they will be examined not because of their seriousness but because of their frequency which disturb their life. The five possible triggers that rural people normally seek medical aid includes “1- occurrence of an interpersonal crisis 2- perceived interference with social and personal relations 3- perceived interference with & physical activity 4- sanctioning by other people 5- illness nations about how long certain complaints should last usually”. These models are the parts of the approach that people use to build socio-medical culture over the period of time in the rural settings as we found. They give meaning to illness and health, will answer for the questions about personal responsibility about health and most importantly his/her illness explanations. It can help to explore why some patients’ will follow a doctors directions and others pay no attention to them totally. A patients’ clarification or understanding of their illness can be much broader than a physician's and this dynamic has become a major criticism of modern medical practice since it normally excludes the "social, psychological and experiential dimensions of illness"(Punamaki, Raija-Leena, 1995).

This study has conducted in the selected villages of Karnataka state-South India using survey, focus group etc data collection technique. This study found that established rural health behavior should not be underestimated citing them as illiterate or superstitious and that rural health behavior, depends on particular health culture, geographical area etc. It is found that health seeking behavior of the rural people varies according to the type of illness, causation of illness, gender and age of the person affected by a particular disease and illness. People feel each disorder has a different cultural meaning. Also this study has found that developmental issues, lack health infrastructure, lack of social network, illiteracy, health policy problems are some of the reasons for the health inequalities among rural people. It is also felt that lack of cultural specific health programmes is the main problems because of which we are not respecting the inherited health culture, emotions and spiritual meanings associated with health and disease of the rural people. We suggest that an effective solution to the health related problems of rural society must situate the problem within the larger contexts of changing health culture situations. Also this is precisely the perspective necessary to develop a model of a culturally suited health care delivery system specifically designed for the rural

people of the country. As India is a diverse country with large social inequalities combined with rapid economic and inclusive growth, research on rural health inequalities has a particular policy implications. We recommend that studies on rural health inequalities in the prospect must focus on evaluations of policy and required health programs, and on under privileged health outcomes and populations.

(Nanjudna)

List of Abbreviations

ANC: Ante Natal Clinic/Care
ARI: Acute Respiratory Infection
ARC: AIDS Related Complex
ARV: Anti Retro Viral (drugs)
CHW: Community Health Worker
CMR: Child Mortality Rate
CSO : Central Statistical Office
DHC : District Health Care
FHH: Female Headed Household
FP : Family Planning
GDP : Gross Domestic Product
GNP: Gross National Product
HFA : Health for All
HIV : Human Immunodeficiency Virus
HMIS: Health Management Information System
HosMIS: Hospital Management Information System
HSR Health System Research or Health Sector Reform
LCMS: Living Conditions Monitoring Survey
MCH: Mother and Child Health care/clinic
MoH: Ministry of Health
NGO: Non governmental Organization
NHSP : National Health Strategy Plan
PHC: Primary Health Care
PMR :Perinatal Mortality Rate
PNC : Post Natal Care
RHC: Rural Health Centre
STD: Sexually Transmitted Disease
TB: Tuberculosis
TB: A Traditional Birth Attendant
TFR Total Fertility Rate
U5MR: Under-5 Mortality Rate
UNICEF: United Nations Children's Fund
IMR Infant Mortality Rate

ISM : Indian System of Medicine
TM: Traditional medicine
MCH: Mother and Child Health care/clinic
MHH : Male Headed Household
MMR : Maternal Mortality Ratio
MO : Medical Officer
MoH : Ministry of Health
MWH: Maternity Waiting Home
PHC: Primary Health Centre
SC : Sub Centre
NGO: Non Governmental Organization
NHS: National Health Strategy
O & G : Obstetrics &Gynecology
OR: Odds Ratio
TFR: Total Fertility Rate
U5MR: Under-5 Mortality Rate
WHO: World Health Organization

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Health, illness and the cure are realities in everybody's life across the societies. Therapy, practices and results normally evolve over the period of time within the socio-cultural contexts. Health is not only a stable state of physical and natural well being but also in a true sense it involved the various other complex issues. As it is widely known fact that, health is one of the imperative indicators shimmering the excellence of human life since time immemorial. It provides different insights about health culture, behaviour, traditions; customs in the health care system. Through the personal experiences patients' and the doctors/ native healers will also add on to the knowledge of society's health belief system continuously over the period of time. All cultures consist of vital information's about how disease occurs, what makes illness and how to choose suitable healing approaches. This would be a health culture of each and every community. In each health culture there will be different concepts, ideology philosophy and thinking and planning in handling various diseases and illness appropriately Experts have given a term called "cultural diseases" because some diseases are created partially because of "cultural" definition of the given "situation" . Regarding the social construction of disease and illness has an argument for analyzing 'behavior determinants of the health of individuals at the societal level'. People feel each disorder has a different cultural meaning. Also it is found that developmental issues, lack health infrastructure, lack of social network, illiteracy, health policy problems are some of the reasons for the health inequalities among rural people. It is concluded that lack of cultural specific health programmes is the main problems because of which we are not respecting the inherited health culture, emotions and spiritual meanings associated with health and disease of the rural people.

Introduction

“All systems of medical belief of practice are empirically self confirming. People everywhere live until they finally die and they only die once, while in the process of living they undergo various, physical and mental disease or illness episodes. In brief, a lot of people will recover from their health problems no matter what the healers they met, say or do, and they will mostly would like to give credit to their recovery to what was done” (Leslie, 1986 : 79).

In 1998, the World Health Assembly made new commitments to ‘Health for All Policy’ for the 21st century. The commitment included in part: “We commit ourselves to strengthening, adapting and reforming as appropriate our health systems including essential public health functions and services in order to ensure universal access to health services that are based on scientific evidence of good quality and within affordable limits, and that are sustainable for the future. We will continue to develop health systems to respond to the current and anticipated health conditions, socio-economic circumstances and the needs of people, communities and countries concerned to appropriately manage public and private actions, and investments in health” (WHO,1998).

In all human society irrespective of its simplicity and complexity and no matter how small or big, no matter how advanced or traditional there exists some sort of simple or complex health issues. The world health assembly in 1977 started a movement for health and wellbeing for all by the year 2000 A.D. India was also committed to achieving “Health for all to her citizen”. The National health policy accepted by the honorable Indian parliament in 1983 states health care as the main device for achieving sustainable development of the community. It is a known factor that the development of any society depends on the healthy people only. Without the good health even we cannot think appropriately and act properly and expect the society to keep moving smoothly. It is a known fact that without proper health we cannot expect the proper social inclusion of any community in any way.

Health is not only a stable state of physical and natural well being but also in a true sense it involved the various other complex issues. As it is widely known fact that, health is one of the imperative indicators shimmering the excellence of human life since time immemorial. Healthy community is very vital because it can set the destiny of the any society or country. Also healthy human resources lead to have any type of development or any kind of achievement. Health is a very vital integrated component of an individual/a community. Sometime collapse of health may even lead

an individual towards an early death. Also unhealthy community may be a hinder for the holistic growth and development of any society. Poor health status of any community may isolate that community from the mainstream of the society(Kerketta, 2008).

Health is one of the prime concerns of mankind, since his emergences on the earth. Health is a pre-requisite for human development and is essentially concerned with the wellbeing of the common man. Health is not only related to medical care but an integrated development of an entire human society. Normally the context in which an individual lives it is of very vital and significant for his/her health status and quality of life. There are some external determinants which can decide the health status of any person including social environment, hospitals, doctors or technologies. Also it significantly depends on some internal factors including his /her health culture, behavior, level of education, health practices, etc. Quality of health care, health orientation and social protection of the health of a population affects the entire developmental status of any nation.

Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (2008) states “Health has received less philosophical attention than disease, and this essay will correspondingly have less to say about it. The conceptual terrain in the case of health is a little more complex than that of disease; one way of thinking about health says that it is just the absence of disease, so if disease is biological malfunction or abnormality, it follows that a healthy person is someone whose biological systems are all in the order. But another way of looking at health insists that it is not just the absence of disease but the presence of something more; a positive state”.

Health is a part and parcel of any organism. Historically post-renaissance (**Post Renaissance** is the era followed by the High Renaissance(an art) has been a period of enlightenment. It is the phase in the progress of human civilization when the substance was systematically separated from the mind and answers to the everyday world phenomena were required in the dominion of nature. All aspects of knowledge were uniformly affected by this new ideological outline. “Mainly in medical sciences, body (anatomical and physiological dimension) of man was separated from the mind. Thus in this Cartesian model (Deisenberg ,1977), health was taken to means as a disease free physical state. Joshi said “Though, immense achievements were made in the fields of diagnosis, chemo therapy and surgery its philosophical orientation coercively divorced Biology from Psychology and Socio-cultural environment. The Man was treated as an object mere assemblage of body systems- a machine”. (Joshi, 1990).

Health finds dissimilar meanings from the various perspectives. The biomedical approach which dominated the medical consideration till the end of the nineteenth century was based on the “germ theory of diseases”, which views health as an “absence of diseases only”. This concept approximately neglects the impact of the environmental, psychological and the other socio-cultural issues which are very crucial in the health management. The ecological perspective opines health as a vibrant balance between the man and the environment. The psychological approach views that the health is not only connected to the physical body but also to the mind and particularly to the outlook of a person. The socio-cultural approach recognizes health as an artifact of the social and the community structure (Advani and Akram, 2007).

Experts felt that Health can be more precisely viewed as an index of human adaptation to ‘micro-ecological niche’. Even though the western system of medicine has many advantages over the traditional, it has not totally been accepted by the majority rural Indian masses till today. It is because of their unique health behavior consistently influencing by their inherited culture, tradition, beliefs, values, norms and practice etc. All these play a very vital role in shaping health behavior of that community in a given society. Invariably it keeps shaping the perception and the attitude towards onset and curing of different health problems in a given community over the period of time to form a ‘definite health culture’. Finally it determines to select a particular type of treatment to treat the particular type of health problem in the future.

Sociologists felt that every community (may be urban/tribal /rural) normally develops their own health needs and curing approaches after motivating by their changing socio-economic conditions. In this process, the health of the rural community as a subsystem will be mainly infused with the above attributes of the entire social system. Experts felt cultural response of the community to the health problems confronted by it determines the way in which individual members perceive different habits of dealing with the various health problems.

Rajasekharan, (2008) views that; health is an important indicator of economic development of any country also. The increasing health status of the people reflects the socio economic development of the country and is shaped by a variety of factors such as level of income, education level, life style, health consciousness, personal hygiene, sanitation facility, housing facility, and access to health care services etc. It is widely accepted that poor health status of low income countries is the product of poor nutritional level, lack of drinking water supply, improper sanitation facility, housing

conditions etc. These conditions invite deficiency diseases which are dominating mortality and morbidity pattern in those countries. The relationship between poverty and poor health is indisputable. It is clear that, poor health leads to loss of income, as well result in extra expenditure. The betterment of health status of people can bestow through health care service systems. It is recognized that health systems contribute towards several outcomes that are socially desirable and therefore health being a necessity indeed is a fundamental right of the people.

Since time immemorial health-seeking behavior of the rural population is greatly governed by the cultural values, beliefs and traditions. However now it is open for the gradual change because of continuous interventions of the different kinds of external agencies in the rural part. Further, in the changes of patterns of health seeking behavior of the rural people, one also can notice incredible fresh ideology which has occurred with respect to philosophy, knowledge, and practices of indigenous systems such as Ayurveda, Homeopathy, Allopathic, etc in rural settings. However, it becomes important to work on problems of rural's health because it differs from one area to another area owing to their remote geographical setting, historical milieu processes of social change and the cultural diffusion (Bulliyya,2009). Geographical isolation and limited interactions with other communities have become an obstacle to know the degree of prevalence of various communicable and non communicable diseases including HIV and STD among rural area and the community's response (Arlappa, 1999; Bose, 2006; Kerketta, 2008).

Pattanayak (2012) opines health is a significant pointer of the general growth and development of any society. Health can never be denied in a progressive society. However irony is that a marginalized section of the society does not encompass its equitable place in the health profile of the society. He further opines "having a large number of malnourished people, having precarious premature mortality situation, not having proper access to modern health facilities owing to a host of reasons, and as a natural consequence majority rural people suffers from ill-health" (Pattanayak (2012). Various studies have established the possible connection between the health status and the GDP growth of any country. Further, it has also been recognized that the contribution of a healthy person for the economy will be always higher when compare to those who suffer from ill-health' (Pattanayaka, 2012; Wheeler, 1980; Deolalikar and Behrman, 2002).

Reddy (2013), opined

“Health and disease are multidimensional aspects of mans’ biology and culture. There have been numerous bio-social modifications set in a man in the past, and example being sickle cell anemia, hypoxia and other disorders. But cultural ways of humans seem to have reduced fitness in relation to modernity and technology. Human culture and genetic processes seems to be not cohesive as biological process is slow while cultural development is first in action. These consequences as a situation of imbalance between the two and occur more disease than being healthy. And this demands more medicine and this we are at the feeble and desperate state of affairs” (Reddy, 2013).

Today public health issue has become a part and parcel of every state in fact it is a matter of national importance. The Universal declaration of human rights says every human being has the right for the health and well being. WHO also states that health is a fundamental right of every human being without health one even can’t think, act etc. Generally right to health means, Right to good food and shelter, good environment, appropriate and quality health care etc., Even Indian constitution and various court verdicts have upheld health rights is a part of fundamental rights. The concept of health is more related to the basic social regimentation of the community.

Health is a vital component in every social development programmes. Today every government is intended to bring many new health programmes. Quality health care has become a key indicator of social inclusion. Providing health care to the disadvantaged sections of the society has become a challenged task before any government, rather than just medical care. Generally quality health care system depends on existing strong politico-economy of the state. Today health sector is a potential of having long term marketing investment. It is found that quality health care service largely influenced by the socio-economic and other situational factors in the rural part. Poverty, illiteracy, under development are some of the reasons for huge health inequalities in India. Uneven distribution of modern medical facilities, lack of effective prevention measure, development behavior of certain communities, the absence of strong political will, bureaucratic negligence, poor medical infrastructure, malnutrition, transport system, peoples ignorance are some of the hurdles in the way of “Health for all” .

The importance of good health of the people cannot be minimized as it has been considered as one of the important components of human capital. Good health is an indication of strong mind. Due to its vital importance, health economics are

attracting researchers and policy makers more rapidly in recent decades. It is well said in the theory of human capital that people should invest themselves in terms of education, health and skill development programmes. Health is a major segment of human capital. If the quality of human capital is not good, physical capital and natural resources cannot be utilized properly and growth can neither be sustainable nor be qualitative.

Life expectancy at birth, infant mortality rate, fertility rate, crude birth rate of the rural community are perhaps the best measures of real human development of any nation. It is because in a developing country $\frac{3}{4}$ of the total populations lives in rural areas only. These indicators of health are determined by the numerous factors such as per capita income, nutrition, housing, sanitation, safe drinking water, social infrastructure, health and medical care services provided by Government, geographical climate, employment status, and incidence of poverty and so on (Dadibhavi and Bagalkoti, 1994). However, in developing countries like India, due to the poor financial accessibility it is hard to spend much money by the rural people on health. Hence, Government intervention is necessary for making strong human capital and sustained economic growth in the rural part as they are strongly and positively interrelated to each other (Siddu, 2009; Murthy and Revankar, 2011).

The issue of rural health has drawn increasing attention both at the national and international level today. Criticism has been focused on poor health infrastructure and its impact on physical, mental, social, moral and spiritual health of the rural folks. Since 1990, the WHO is emphasizing on improving the health status of the rural people across the developing countries stressing promotion of the scientific usage of traditional medicine. Also some health scientists are focusing on how community evaluates the risk associated with poor health infrastructure on the future generations and the cultural barriers in using modern medical health care facilities and how to overcome this problem soon.

In April 2002, WHO and WONCA (Rural health initiative from the major 20 development countries) organized a chief WHO–WONCA unique seminar on Rural Health issues. This seminar focused the ‘huge challenges for improving the health of rural people and remote areas and started a detailed action plan: ;*The Global Initiative on Rural Health*;. The ‘Health for All’ vision for rural people is more probable to be achieved through combined intensive hard work of international and national bodies working together with doctors, nurses, NGOs and other health workers especially in rural areas across the globe’ (Roger Strasser, 2003).

The poor rural health condition has drawn increasing international attention and condemnation since 1970s. During the same period many international Non Government Organisations (NGOs) and other agencies have begun to speak out against poor health infrastructure in the rural parts in developing countries. The issue of rural health has generated renewed interest because of the new economic policies formulated in line with the structural adjustment programmes. Developing countries have adopted a strategy to help them to integrate into the global health market economy. Hence, the long neglected topic of public health issue has suddenly attracted worldwide interest as a subject of research and analysis, particularly regarding the supply and demand sides of the health commodities. This interest among economists and social scientists began during a transition period in which the incidence of death due to presence of modern health care had been declining for decades among the developed countries and increasing among the developing countries including India. This pattern may be a kind of optimism that signals the spread of rapid usage of the science and technology in public health sectors that endorse the protection of valuable human life. Science and technology today is saving millions of life suffering from various diseases and illness across the globe(Balgir ,2001).

Health has physical, mental and social dimensions. Physical health implies the concept of perfect and general functioning of the entire body. Mental dimension includes peace and self control of the mind whereas social dimension includes the delivery of different social functions as a member of the given society. The healthy person must possess all these three elements for his normal growth and development. Health is responsible of both an individual and the community. Experts felt individual and the community should go hand in hand for de-medicalized health. Meaningful participation of the community will lead to have accessible and affordable public health care to everyone. Since health affects both cognitively and productively it is opined that acquiring good health is a most necessary prerequisite for human development (Akram, 2007).

Article 21 of the Constitution of India also identifies health as an integral aspect of human life. Further, Article 47 (Part IV: Directive Principles of State Policy) says: The State shall regard the raising of the level of nutrition and the standard of living of its people and the improvement of public health as among its primary duties and, in particular, the State shall endeavour to bring about prohibition of the consumption except for medicinal purposes of intoxicating drinks and of drugs which are injurious to health (Desai , 2007).

1.a CONCEPT OF HEALTH

Health is an important phase of human life. Health and wellbeing are matter to all strata of the society. Health has a much larger domain which affects all aspects of human existence. The entire life structure will be based on it only. In the ancient time people all over the world were generally indifferent to the all round development of a human being. Of course attention was paid to their physical development through physical exercise, hard discipline and self-control and there were no space for mental health.

The development of good health is conditioned both by heredity and environment. Healthy community is the future asset or capital for the development of the any society. If the society burdened by ill health people it would be a kind of overburden and it may be a curse for the any society for that matter. Poverty, illiteracy and population explosion including cultural and traditional background are some of the vital and major pushing factors for the poor health status of the rural community in India. In the same way, it is revealed that public health problem is viewed as a major hurdle to the overall development of an Indian economy. It is also known that poor health actually minimizes the human capital accumulation, which is a prerequisite for the national development

1.b 'HEALTH' –THE SCIENTIFIC DEFINITION

WHO definition of health :- The present definition of health was originally created during framing a preamble to the aims and objectives of the world health organization in 1946.

According to the WHO definition

“Health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity”. In 1986, the WHO said that health is “a resource for everyday life, not the objective of living. Health is a positive concept emphasizing social and personal resources. As well as physical capacities”.

Further in an article in the Lancet (magazine) states that health is not a “State of complete Physical, Mental and Social well being”. Neither it is “merely the absence of disease or infirmity”. The article says the WHO definitions on health will not do in an era marked by the new understandings of diseases at molecular, individual, and societal levels” (Sources: The Lancet , Volume 373, Issue 9666, page 781, 7 March 2009).

It is further opined that there are various socio economic and socio demographic constructs like ethnicity, gender, class, caste, religion which effects while defining the term health. Neither health nor illness can be perfectly defined in isolation without knowing the socio economic background of the people and macro-micro level socio-political undercurrents of that community .

Further, health can be mainly classified into Two components 1. Physical health & 2. Mental health

1.Physical health:- It is defined that the physical health relates to anything regarding our whole body as a ‘physical entity. Physical health is very vital to keep ourselves active. In another word physical health means a good body health without having any deformities. Added, in another way we can say the physical health is nothing but the physical well being. More precisely the physical wellbeing can be achieved by cultivating all health related components with respect to his/her life style. Proper physical well being may be expected with the proper nutrition, proper body weight, vaccinations, and hygiene and away from the drug abuse etc. An individual having good physical healthy indulging in activities not in consonance with social norms will be normally seen as a mentally unhealthy.

2. **Mental health:-** In the literature, there are various definitions regarding mental health. Experts felt mental health refers to the absence of any type of mental illness. Some experts felt mental health includes peaceful mind, happiness in life, balanced thoughts, self actualization etc. Truly speaking mental health relates to once cognitive and emotional well being. According to WHO, mental health is----

“ A state of well-being in which the individual realizes his/her own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and able to make a contribution to his/her community”. It is opined that things shifts from individual to social when defining mental health and illness.

Dixit (2005) opined mental health and illness is understood in relation to Three vital backgrounds;

1. The bio medical;
2. Psychological ;
3. And the Psycho social

First International Conference on Health Promotion, Ottawa, (21 November 1986) has noted fundamental prerequisites for the good health are

- Food
- Income,
- Shelter,
- Education,
- Peace
- a stable eco-system,
- sustainable resources,
- social justice, and equity

WHO has identified five key elements to achieving health for all including (quoting)

- Reducing exclusion and social disparities in health (universal coverage reforms);
- Organizing health services around people's needs and expectations (service delivery reforms);
- Integrating health into all sectors (public policy reforms);
- Pursuing collaborative models of policy dialogue (leadership reforms); and
- Increasing stakeholder participation. (Source: WHO website)

Mahler (1980) says that "health is indispensable for a balanced development of the individual within the family and as a part of the community and nation".

Frazer (1990) has given five vital components in keeping good health (quoted).

1. Good physiological principles focusing quality;
2. Prevention care including immunization;
3. Early detection of diseases if any;
4. After care of sickness;
5. Good management of incurable sickness.

Webster (1969) opines that "the concept of well being conveys the state of being healthy or prosperous". According to him we can understand health from

1. Physical health refers to being healthy;
2. Mental health refers to being happy;
3. Social health refers to being prosperous.

Health is a substance of apprehension to all spear of the society. It is a high order to foresee a society which is free from the recurrent struggle against diseases. Science and technology have taken huge steps to manage epidemics and to augment longevity. "The achievement of the current medical system lies in the reality that it has been clever to run plentiful infectious and serious diseases and has shaped a hope

that one day there will be no disease at all. This is a remarkably narrow outlook of health that only stress on disease manages and healing characteristic of health” (Dalala and Ray, 2009). Health is a bigger sphere, which affects all spheres of the human survival. It is a wider sphere, which affects all aspects of human survival. It has wider implications for focusing social, economic and cultural life of a person and certainly cannot be completely understood within the limitations of the modern health care model/s. It is a generally recognized that health and disease is basically a social problem and well-being is still an added comprehensive aspects (Dalala and Ray, 2009).

1.c THEORIES ON HEALTH

Hahn and Kleinman (1983a) opines “constructs a medical theories on health is that it informs both patient and practitioner about how symptoms and conditions are distinguished, what courses they run in syndromes and why, how these conditions may be ameliorated, and how symptoms and their dynamics fit in a larger order of agency, power, and value”(Hahn and Kleinman 1983a:16). We have three basic theories namely;

1.Personalistic:- In this theory, it is believed that the diseases and illness cause due to the cosmological or supernatural powers. Some time local black magician or a sorcerer will be treated as a person having unique powers to control or to create some diseases and illness originally obtained from the deity or spirits through various means. In some culture, it is believed that the mistakes or faults done by an individual intentionally will get some punishments by the evil forces. Further, if anyone failed in observing the moral or spiritual norms will get severe punishment in the form disease or illness by the evil forces. In the same way, if anyone failed in carrying out certain required health rituals also will be punished by a dead ancestor. Sometime breaching a religious taboo also attracts a punishment as widely believed in the various traditional societies. This theory is one of the strongest theories about the origin and causation for the various diseases and illness.

2.Naturalistic: - This is a second dominant theory in the field of illness and diseases. According to this theory health of a human being will be completely intervened with the ecology or the natural environment. A person must have a proper balance and co-ordination with the nature and if it is failed, illness or diseases results invariably. This naturalistic theory exists in both the modern and the traditional world and it has few popular approaches viz humeral, ritualistic and Ayurvedic ideologies. This theory mainly believes diseases or illness causes due to the hot and cold imbalances inside a

body. Basically this approach rooted in the concept of the proper intake of the food and water according to the nature seasons without fail. This approach views a strong association of health with the environment. It opines if human being goes with the environment there will be no problem.

3.Vitalistic:- In this approach it is believed that disease or illness may cause due to the unknown power full energies. In this theory believed that each and every human body is the home for certain vital powers/energies. Health status will be good if the energy flows smoothly within a person's body. If the flow of energy stops or interrupts, person may get various health problems or even death. Proper and on time treatment is required to bring back the normal flow of energy for good health.

1.d HEALTH SYSTEM : -

Stephens and Harpham (1992) opines

“Heath outcomes are not influenced by the ecological factors but also by the input of health services by the characteristics of the population and by the socio-economic conditions in which they live”.

It is known that Often **health system** has been defined with a reductionist viewpoint, for example plummeting it to **healthcare system**. In a lot of publications, for example, both language are used interchangeably. a number of authors have developed point of view to get bigger notion of health systems, represent ting supplementary magnitude that should be considered:

- Health systems should not be spoken in terms of their mechanism only, but also of their interrelationships;
- Health systems should comprise not only the institutional or supply side of the health system, but also the inhabitants;
- Health systems must be seen in terms of their goals, which comprise not only health development, but also equity, receptiveness to lawful expectations, respect of self-respect, and fair financing, among others;

Health system includes the sum of health institutions, education, policies and programmes, and various efforts to remove disparities etc. The word “system” composed various formal and informal activities towards various health issues in the society. The health system is an established system to provide the quality and necessary different health care systems through resources, knowledge and technology to the patients' and needy in the society. Preventive, curative and rehabilitative care is the three major pillars or components of any health system. However, there is no

single ideal pattern of the health system. Health system basically has a normal or some time different patterns across the multicultural societies. Health services are one of the main factors influencing the health status of any population. Sometime various political forces play a dominant role in shaping the good or bad health system in any society. Health systems have to also be defined in terms of their functions, including the direct provision of services, whether they are medical or public health services, but also "other enabling functions, such as stewardship, financing, and resource generation, including what is almost certainly the most multifaceted of all challenges, the health workforce.(various resources)

There are three health care systems (sector) available

1.The Popular Sector

1. It is basically non-professional and lay;
2. Disease/illness will be diagnosed based on experiences and lay beliefs ;
3. Health care behavior / activities start here;
4. Healing will be without professional consultation;
5. Self medicating is a most vital part here;
6. Female head of the family takes an actual decision;
7. Both the patients and the healer thinks/shares parallel assumptions about disease/illness;
8. Set of blind beliefs exists about prevention measures.

2.The Folk Sector

1. Healers are specialized in faith / sacred / or both;
2. It is not a part of the formal medical system;
3. Mostly low cost and culturally specific;
4. Holistic approach;
5. More focus on supernatural / cosmology causation ;
6. Healers are not well trained;
7. Patients use informal network;
8. Family role is vital in identifying and treatment option.

3. Professional Sector

1. Western biomedical system;
2. Trained professionals;
3. Scientifically proven;
4. Mostly monopoly of knowledge and techniques;
5. Control over the field of specialists;
6. Endorse common interest;
7. More ethical; 8) Based on organized knowledge and power

Curtsey (from various sources)

Health is also associated with Wellness, Illness, Sickness and Disease. All these aspects are very vital when studying health behavior and health culture of any community.

Local Health Care System: Internal Structure

Fig 1

Source: Anthropology of Health, Illness and Medicine: Original Author is Greatly Acknowledged

1.e CONCEPT ABOUT WELLNESS and ILLNESS

1.WELLNESS :The University of East Carolina defines **wellness** as “ The integration of mind, body and spirit. Optimal wellness allows us to achieve our goals and find meaning and purpose in our lives. Wellness combines seven dimensions of well-being into a quality way of living. Overall, wellness is the ability to live life to the fullest and to maximize personal potential in a variety of ways. Wellness involves continually learning and making changes to enhance your state of general health. When we balance the physical, intellectual, emotional, social, occupational, spiritual and environmental aspects of life, we achieve true wellness”. (Sources: University of East Carolina (2007),USA).

According to **Med lexicon’s Medical dictionary**, wellness is “ A philosophy of life and personal hygiene that views health as not merely the absence of illness but the full realization of one’s physical and mental potential, as achieved through positive attitudes, fitness training a diet low in fat and high in fiber and the avoidance of unhealthful practices (smoking drug and alcohol abuse, over eating)” Sources: NHS (UK), NIH (USA), Medical News Today). The term wellness is very broad domain and good health can give good wellness only. Wellness is a holistic concept comprising various health components.

In true since wellness relates more to an abstract noun. Wellness is the kind of potential usage his/her fullest capacity in achieving various life goals. The term wellness has multi dimensional and multifaceted meaning. Wellness leads good the physical and mental health. Wellness may increase the cognitive capacity of the human beings so that he/she can think properly, act appropriately etc. Moreover, the need for self determination, self efficacy or autonomy also comes from the wellness only. Due to the wellness both physical and social environment of the human beings also will be glowing. Expert’s opined wellness is more a social experiences and the practical knowledge regarding the conformity and deviance and the social aspects of wellness form the base for an informal system of good health care also.

2.ILLNESS: In general, the **illness** is a kind of feeling of ‘not being normal and healthy’. Experts felt illness might be due to the disease or due to a psychological disorder etc. Illness is a state of poor health. The concept of illness may be varying from culture to culture. There are two schools who have given two vital explanations about the state of illness.

- In naturalistic explanation: Illness causes due to an impersonal and mechanistic reason/s that can be cured by the medical science.
- In personality description (second school of thought): Here people will believe illness is due to the effect of the super natural power or forces. Here curing will be normally through the channel of traditional medicines only.

The concept of illness even differs from the person to person or community to community. For example:- person 'X' may feel unhealthy because of perception of having a disease though he/she is not actually. Hence illness is more a subjective state. Normally it occurs independently of or in connection with a disease. An illness also can be referred as an experience of a patient during ill health stage. An Illness has few broader dimensions including the socio-culture, socio-economic, emotional history, personality etc. We can say an illness exist where diseases will be normally absent and the vice versa. Normally an illness will be away from the biological reality. Medicine can cure the disease but not an illness. Since an illness is more pertaining to the mind, it cannot be easily diagnosed unlike a disease (from various sources). Also different societies accept illness in a different way owing to its cultural history.

Dari Fali (2006) writes :

“Illness is culturally distinct in all the societies; it is one more universal found in medical system. From a cultural point of view, illness is rather a dissimilar thing. It is the social detection that a person is unable to perform his normal roles sufficiently and that something must be done about the situation. Illness is a cultural concept. Human diseases turn out to be socially important only when they are identified as illness, a physiological malfunctioning that is seen to threaten the individual and his society”.

Analyses of the representative “causes” of the illness listed in the world’s ethno medical accounts according Forest George (1991:18-19) are as follows **(extracted)**

- i. “Angry deities who punish wrong deeds, for example those who violates taboos;
- ii. Ancestors & Ghosts who feel they have been soon forgotten or otherwise not recognized;
- iii. Sorcerers or witches, working for hire or for personal reasons;
- iv. Spirit possession or intrusion of an object into the body;
- v. Loss of the basic body equilibrium, usually because of the entry of excessive heat or cold in the body.
- vi. The evil eye” **(sources are greatly acknowledged)**

Kochar (1980) has listed Four important categories of illness behavior

1. Normal performance of one's ascribed roles;
2. Patient will gradually lose competence to do normal work and slip in to sick role;
3. Actual involving the sick role;
4. Leaving in the sick role. **(source extracted)**

Kannuri, (2005) writes :

“Health and illness are two opposite concepts, one defined as the lack of the other. It can be said that these two concepts lie on two opposite poles of the range. Health in universal is understood as nonexistence of illness. Illness is a socio-culturally defined exit from health and it can be differentiated from disease, which is a biomedical group. Experts concern would be more towards illness rather than disease since illness is a prejudiced occurrence related the social and cultural factors, where as disease is an objective occurrence defined merely in bio-medical terms by modern health professionals. The reply to illness – illness behaviour – is the way in which symptoms are perceived, evaluated and acted upon. This may vary from one individual to another. Though, this behavior is also really prejudiced by the culture, of which the sick person is a member” (Kannuri, 2005)

Wellin (1977) has given the most acceptable concept on illness. According to him illness is not necessarily a biomedical phenomenon. Truly speaking it is a spectrum of social, cultural, psychological and finally a bio-medical entity. However it holds good when the patient and its neighborhood social group recognizes it so. Further Joshi (1990) opines “that every society whether developed or under developed will normally constructs set of history ideas, beliefs, behavior, norms, values based on their experience encountering with illness issues”. Based on this point illness experiences not necessarily be an individual, impersonal, logical and objective; however it is a total sum of shared social experiences and subjective which is culturally and geographically specific.

Further Mahajan (1990) felt each and every society especially rural and tribal develops various relief channels to encounter an ill health. This is what we call as the social and cultural domain of illness of a given society at any point of time. This domain has two dependent variables. The first one is the affected person, his family members and his neighborhood etc. The second dependent variable would be popular or professional health facilitators and their role. The social and cultural specific

entities are placed in particular institutional set-ups (Joshi and Mahajan, 1990; Welling, 1977).

Thribhuwan (1998) has opined about illness including ;

- a. Illness is a social sanction;
- b. Illness is a deviance;
- c. Illness is due to failure of social system performance;
- d. Illness is social conflict;
- e. Illness is due to disturbance of the cultural order;
- f. Illness is sum of cosmological effect

Dalal and Ray (2009) opines 'Illness is a social occasion and understanding of the symptoms is a combined endeavor. There is an immense deal of prejudice in the explanation of the symptoms and social beliefs, potential and status provides the base for symptoms explanation. The social edifice of the disease and its symptoms may not essentially equivalent to those of the medical professional. Patients' and their families get significant treatment related decisions based on the understanding of the disease/illness. This event also becomes the source to choose which method of action to follow to get well soon' In rural set up people believe illness is due to supernatural power, angry deities trouble form the ghosts, ancestors, etc. According to Tribhuven (1998) 'generally rural folk believes the illness is a kind of social sanction and has the perception that illness is a punishment for doing wrong deeds in the life'. This kind of attribution is an early form of social control in a more regular way and the development of the human society (Hallowell, 1963). Further, Persons and Fox (1952) have opined that illness can also be seen as a form of deviance in its own right. They opined that that a high rate of illness occurrence is a kind of dysfunctional for any kind of social system. Lieban & Richard (1973) have written that illness is an indication of the performance of any social system Camaroff (1981) and Foster (1976) have opined rural people believe illness is a type of curse due to the disturbance of cultural order and every society has its own explanations and reasons for illness (Polar, 1968; Cromble, 1969) .

Normally a certain social group shares some common basic concepts about the health and illness. Lewis (1993) said 'illness pertains to those corresponding choose to identify as underside called abnormal, the experience and meaning of perceived disease" (Lewis,1993). Also it is found that an indigenous concept and beliefs on health are completely associated and may be more precisely we can say it is intertwined with the various dimensions and angles of the illness itself. Also diversity

in contingent and other strong social factors play a vital role in shaping the simpler or complex health seeking behavior among the rural folk, including the proper selection of a treatment.

Some cultural groups in the rural India will treat an illness and a disease due to the bad karma(fast deed)/ bad luck etc. Some culture will believe specific illness and disease is a type of curse due to the bad effect of the different planets. Recovery from any illness involves certain rituals and symbolism performed by the conceptual indigenous practitioners /Vaidya. Even though an illness is a social aspect and the healer/s will pose it as a social sanction on the patient. However certain health psychologist's opined disease is also a kind of mental phenomena and how it is interpreted or taken at the personnel level will be finally termed as 'illness'. Hence disease, illness and sickness are interrelated and these are the completely cultural dependent issues.

Adam (1953) has found rural people would like to divide illness into Two main identifiable classes ;

(a) those illness which can be cured by the local traditional healers;

(b) those illness which can only be curable through A modern scientific medicine.

Das (2004) opined 'disease and illness are basically individual and biological reply normally directed and framed for the most part of the cultural ideas learned in the way of being socialized' (Das,2004). It is found both health and illness are the antagonistic concepts. One will not exist without another. Illness is socio-cultural aspects and disease is truly a biological entity. Illness is largely a subjective issue for that matter. Kannuri (2009) opines "the response to illness behavior is the way in which symptoms are perceived, evaluated and acted upon"

1.f CONCEPT ABOUT SICKNESS AND DISEASE

Dubois (1959) wrote "disease is a condition of the organism that seriously obtrudes against these adaptive requirements and causes partial or complete disablement and physical and behavioral dysfunction". Ackerchnecht (1946) writes "disease and it's treatment are only in the abstract purely biological processes, but the fact is that a person gets diseased and what kind of treatment he receives includes diet and the rest depends on social and cultural factors".

1.What is a Disease?: In a more scientific term a disease is normally associated with a bacterial or viral cause and more simply we can say disease may harm our physical or mental health. The Disease will have specific sings and symptoms. The

disease can be diagnosed only by the medical experts. Apart from bacteria or virus some other things like chemicals, genetics, external environment, and weak immunity may cause diseases to the human being. The disease may cause a type of threat to our life. The disease can be more specifically defined an abnormality causing due to the various external and internal pathogenesis, biology, genetics etc pertaining to the human organ system. It is a biomedical perception. One of the lacunas in this definition is that it does not focus anything about the social or psychological dimension/s of the disease. More importantly it nullifies the significance of the cultural context in which the term “diseases” derived its meaning.

Diseases are classified under Two headings;

1. Organic and 2.Functional

2. Organic Diseases

- a. Causes identifiable physical damages;
- b. Causes by multiple sources

3. Functional Diseases

- 1. Has no organic base;
 - a. Mostly biological / psychological in nature;
 - b. Not clearly identifiable.

However, it is found that different social agencies have different perceptions towards the cause of the diseases and they try to treat disease/s in its own way. Some time it depends on the people’s perception of the pathogenic agent or force responsible for the cause or context in which condition of ill- health occurred and the degrees of disruption and a patient’s relationship with the pathogenic agents. Since Indian rural society is a very unique having distinct culture and traditional concept about an illness and disease will get changes from community to community. It is found that in a multicultural rural society different caste groups are having a different perception towards the onset of various illnesses and diseases. Each caste and community has its own way of dealing with disease and illness in fact. Even though disease and illness have their own scientific meaning, it depends largely on the social and cultural life style of a particular community and the socio- cultural- economic dimensions of any society led to focus on their changing health behavior due to the various external interventions.

Recently some researchers have tried to visualize the rural health issue from the social transformation perspectives. Expert felt rural health issue needs to be studied from both clinical and cultural perspective. The role of medicine and other treatment options has required an urgent study from the different dimensions and approaches focusing Indian rural society (Akram, 2008). In summary, we can say the disease is a malfunction of the biological entity and an illness is malfunctioning of a psycho-social process.

Rivers (1944) has given a model defining three types of worldviews associated belief systems, and three other modes of behavior related to disease.

Rivers Model Explaining Beliefs and Behavioral Traits Related to Disease.

Tab-1

Worldview	Belief about Disease	Practices or behavior treating the disease
Magical	Disease is believed due to the magical human manipulation of forces	Sorcery or counter sorcery
Religious	Diseases believed due to the supernatural-per natural force.	Appeals to, or propitiation of supernatural-per natural forces.
Naturalistic	Disease is believed due to th natural processes to cause and effect relations of natural Phenomena	Naturalistic treatment of specific illness or injury

Sources: River (1941)

The Disease Illness Approach

Fig 2

Sources: Adopted from : Allan young (1982) ‘the Anthropology of Illness and Sickness’, Annual Review of Anthropology, 11:257-85

1.g HEALTH, ILLNESS AND the CULTURE

Cultural views of ‘health and illness’ are vital in understating the health culture and health behaviour of any society. As we are aware an additional key notion of the medical anthropology is that of ethno-centralism and it is a vital concept to study about the health culture of the any social group. It refers to assuming our own culture as the best in the world when compare to the other. “Medical anthropologists have done remarkable work in diverse cultures across the globe and their perspectives on disease and illness by looking at the biological and the ecological aspects of disease, the cultural perspectives, and the ways in which cultures approach prevention and treatment” (Hyder and Morrow,2005).

Further, the Sociologists have suggested for the better comprehend of the cultural context of health and illness, it is indispensable to effort with quite basic and vital concepts. First, the concepts of emic (insider) and outsider (etic) notion are helpful for investigating nay health culture. When we are seeing things from our point of view and when we are trying to understand the views of someone else’s is a very vital issue. It is found that much cultural co-relation about an illness and the target organs in the body exists in various cultural realms. Good and Good (1981) opined heart is a most vital organ in both Chinese and Iranian culture. Both these cultures

have the same attitude and opinion about various heart diseases. Topley (1976) mentions incompatibility of horoscopes between mother and child may be a prime reason for Childs' illness as believed in the Chinese culture.

Some of the cultural reasons for causing illness and diseases (as widely believed in rural society)

a. Body Balances: In the group of body balances, the perception of hot and cold is one of the most persistent. Hot and cold attitudes are the basic element of what is referred as 'humeral medicine'. When an illness has been identified, the system is used to endeavor to reinstate body balance of the patient.

b. Emotional: Some of the illness problem causes due to the emotional origin of a patient. It is widely believed in many cultures and customs. Some facts like distress, sadness, fear, anxiety, and stress are seen as causing a particular type of illnesses in human beings.

c. Supernatural: The supernatural entity is another frequently viewed source of illness. Evil eye, spirit possession causes illness as believed in some society.

d. Food : It is believed that food can be a key reason for an illness in the hot and cold belief system. It is opined that some time flawed food, rotten food, dirty foods, uncooked foods, using wrongly combined food may cause harm to the body.

e. Vectors or Organisms: in some culture vectors or organisms are blame for the illness. The Bio medicine system actually approves it. Some native culture also believes this concept blindly.

g. Weather: Change of seasons also some believed to be causing illness in some culture. (too dry, warm, cold, wet,) can be blamed for causing illness.

g. Angry of deity: Angry deities believed to be causing illness in some culture.

i. Sexual: In some culture children's illnesses were sometime blamed because an illegal sexual relationship of any parent of the child with the outsiders.

j. Heredity : Some culture strongly believes in this concept for an early death of human being

(Source:, Culture, Behavior, and Health, 2005 by Adnan Ali Hyder and Richard H. Morrow web book)

Types of Insider Culture Explanations of Diseases Causation

Tab-2

<p>A. Body Balances</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Temperature: hot, cold • Energy • Blood: Loss of blood; properties of blood reflect imbalance; • Pollution from menstrual blood • Dislocation: Fallen fontanel • Organs; Swollen stomach; heart; uterus; liver; umbilicus; • Others • Incompatibility of Horoscopes <p>B. Emotional</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fright • Sorrow • Envy • Stress • foods <p>C. Weather</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Winds • Change of weather • Seasonal misbalance <p>D. Vectors or Organisms</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Worms • Flies • Parasites • Germs 	<p>E. Supernatural</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bewitching • Demons • Spirit possession • Evil eye • offending God or gods • Soul Loss <p>F. Food</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Properties; Hot, cold, heavy(rich), light • Spoiled foods • Dirty foods • Sweets • Raw foods • Combining the “wrong” foods (incompatible) • Mud <p>G. Sexual</p> <p>Sex with forbidden person</p> <p>H. Heredity</p> <p>I. Old Age</p>
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Source: Adnan Ali Hyder And Richard H. Morrow, from the book *Culture, Behavior, and Health*, 2005

1.g DEFINING SICKNESS:

Bhasin, (2007) writes “Sickness is a process for socializing disease and illness. In “pluralistic” medical systems, a single set of signs can designate more than one sickness and social forces help to determine which people get which sicknesses. Symbols of healing are simultaneously symbols of power. Specific views of social order are embedded in medical beliefs, where they are often encoded in etiologies and beliefs about the sources of healing power” (Bhasin, 2007).

Sickness is commonly referred to the physical illness or a disease. Normally sickness will be more depend on the type of illness alone or vice versa. Some time it is opined that sickness causes due to disease. Sickness has both cultural and the social dimensions including how it influences on the patients’ to react to his/her health conditions. Medical experts felt sickness is a biological entity and affecting different parts of an organism indirectly. Sometime epidemiologist’s refer sickness is more an extended form of an illness. Even some of the medical experts felt both sicknesses and an illness are like two faces of a single coin. Medical Anthropologists felt boundary between a disease and the sickness is a culturally specific. Medical experts felt that criterion which separates diseases from the sickness is some deviation from a biological norm.

Sickness is a kind of social sanction on the patient imposed by the society due to the health problem. Normally they may have to perform the different role in the society because of an ill status. Sometime generally he/she will be exempted from the certain social responsibilities. Sickness may reduce the ability of a patient from leading a normal life. Attaching to these concepts there are two vital concepts

1. Curing;
2. Healing

Curing purely relates to a biomedical concept and the healing refers to the biomedical concepts but it focuses the patient’s point of view. Different cultures have different notions about the healing. Gestler (1984) opined healing has two vital roles;

1. To Control sickness;
2. Providing framework or implications of a patient’s experience of sickness

Certain medical sociologist felt even though the sickness is basically an individual or personal issue or phenomenon it will be largely influenced by the surrounding different social groups having different cultural background. These groups will play a vital role in shaping the specific type of health beliefs or behavior into that sickness.

This would be a kind of interpersonal behavior, care, sympathy etc towards the sick person (Gestler, 1984; Ahmed, 2005).

Parson (1964) has given some sick role notions;

1. Since the sick person cannot do any socially assigned role he/she cannot be expected to perform any social performance too.
2. The Sick person cannot help being ill, and cannot get well by an act of decision or will.
3. In the same way the sick person also should try to come out of sickness soon.
4. The Sick person must be provided all possible social and medical care to come out of the sickness soon.

Hann (1995) opines that “if the meaning of sickness varies widely from one culture to another, what then culture has in common that might be called sickness?” He further ascertained that sick people behavior will be depending on the manner in which patients are being treated by their respective family members. In supplementing Kleiman (1988) write “ sickness or illness refer to how the sick person and the members of the family or wider social network perceive, live with, and respond to symptoms and disability”. Certain experts have opined that the sick person has to try to come out from sickness soon to perform his/her normal duty. Otherwise the patient may be stigmatized. All this may lead towards weakening the society. Hence, sometime society may use different forms to control on the behavior of the sick person. Here medical Doctors are having a vital role to certify whether a person is ill or healthy. However there is a general critique about empowering the Doctors to certify who is a sick person? And who is not?

According to the some medical ecologists sickness may be an organic or an inorganic or socio-cultural and sometime absence of clear clinical symptoms. Truly speaking sickness has a negative item effecting by and large on the society in different way. It is a kind of loss in terms of both individually and collectively. The sick person will show deviance which requires certain control on it. It is generally believed that sick persons are a problematic entity in the society. Up to a certain extent a sick person is eligible for the societal sympathy. The sick person should not expect only sympathetic behavior from the society for the long time. In the same way sick person also should try to come out of the sick role as soon as possible. The sick person should not show the character of dependency throughout the course of his/her sickness.

Kochar has listed four important categories related to sickness

1. Normal performs of once ascribes roles;
2. Patient will gradually loose competence to do normal work slip into sick role;
3. Actual involving sick role;
4. Leaving sick role

Prolonged dependency of the stickpersons on others will be a threat to the very basic nature of any society. Medical sociologists opined that the sick person should not feel incapable, otherwise this attitude also affects on the other fellow members of that society in due course of time. It may threaten the smooth functioning of the society too in the long run. Meanwhile the society also must be very careful about the familiarity of sickness. This would be the duty of the Doctor to declare he/she is really sick or not or just acting so and how much time he/she requires to come over from being sick. The sick role has both rights and obligations. The Sick role needs to be legitimized by the experts. It would be the duty of medical institutions to approve sick role at the best interest of the society (**from various resources**) .

1.h.WHAT IS WELL BEING?

Well being is commonly called as happiness in the life. Today the term wellbeing is redefining like 1.subjective well being, 2.normal, 3.positive, 4.effect, 5.satisfaction etc

The majority of the experts have been explained that wellbeing as life satisfaction. Diener (1984) has given 3 points about well being including;

- a. It is a subjective;
- b. It demands positive measures;
- c. Well being is a long term process

Today behavioral scientists are focusing on feelings of well-being rather than feeling of emotions (Suh and Oishi, 1997). Well-being is not a unilateral aspect rather it is a multifaceted. It is heavily depend on an individual subjective experience. It is embedded in individual feelings about his/her current situation or conscious experiences. Myers and Diener (1995) have defined wellbeing is a positive effect and the absence of negative effect. Vande, Water and others (1997) said it is a positive domain of mental health. Shmotkin and Lomrang (1998) have opined well being is an essential positive outlook of human being. Sharma and Yadav (2005) have opined different culture/society understood the term 'well being 'differently over the period of time. Corsini (1999) defines well being includes overall satisfaction, self esteem

and happiness etc. Kapur (2001) have opined cultural difference is vital in the conceptualization of the term well being. Lagipa (1990) opined social support can effect physical and psychological well being, positively and negatively on the patients’.

It is normal notion that the good health is often commensurate with the general well-being of a person. Ray and Dalal (2004) opines that “the concern is not with curing i.e., treating and preventing organic malfunctioning, but with healing the person, i.e., regenerating a sense of well being and fitness to meet life challenges”. Experts have opined that both mental and physical health is a vital part of the well-being. It is also found that wellbeing has more psychological dimension rather than the physical aspects. Well-being is a vital domain which affects all aspects of the human existence. Also it’s a more complex to be handled by the medical care institutions only. The state has also a vital role here. Hence, it is felt that there is a need of more standardized indicators to measure the wellbeing of a population (Roy and Dalal 2004).

1.i What is Pain:-Even though pain is a personal experience, obviously its’ a social phenomenon. It may seize the freedom of a person. Pain may expel him/her from rest of the world. It may even go up to the level of loosing person’s identity, courage, peace, attitude, work efficiency and confidence. Conjointly pain would be a hurdle in the way of contributing like economic contribution, cognitive contribution etc to a given society. Each person may perceive pain in a more or less different way. Each person will define the term pain according to his/her social, cultural and cognitive background. No one can experience the pain of others and vice-verca. Pain management depends on gender, class caste etc. Exports felt each person face pain based on the subjective and individual character; because an impact which pain leaves will be totally different from person to person. Also sometime pain can be socially regenerative. Person full of pain due to various reasons will get a kind of sympathy, help and advice from the society describing, justifying, analyzing, reasons for the pain. Cultural concepts on pain are totally different across the societies. Different social groups will define the term pain in different patterns. Different social groups perceive pain based on their health culture and the behaviour as felt by the experts.

The State of Ill- Health : A Conceptual

Fig 3

Others (insects, snakes etc.)

Source: Robin D Tribhuwan (1998), Medical World of the Tribes, (Discovery publisher, New Delhi)

1.j THEORETICAL PERSPECTIVES ON HEALTH AND ILLNESS

There are few noted theoretical perspectives on health and illness. Some of them are

1.Structural Functionalism: According to this perspective illness is a form of deviance whereas medicine is an institution of social control. Further this theory says different social facts affects on the health seeking behavior/culture of a person. This theory says sick persons should be exempt from the normal social roles. Next, sick persons should not be held responsible for his/her illness. Also the sick person should try his/her level best to come out of his health problem and the sick person should get suitable medical help. However, this theory has little criticism. Some people can pose pretend sickness to keep themselves away from their routine normal social responsibility. For some of the problems, like smoking, drinking etc people are personally responsible for any health problem out of their bad habits. Mentally ill patients' and terminally ill patients are sometime branded as excluded. Because they need long time to recover from illness/health problem or some time they may not even.

2.Conflict Theory: This theory basically stresses upon political dynamics of social arrangements. Engles (1990) says health and illness are related to an unequal social arrangements. According to Navarro (1998) said the State intervenes in public health issue just to promote capitalist goals only. Hence, he said the State also may be responsible for occupational and environmental illness. Graham (1978) said, gender differences at home causes low or high mortality or morbidity problem in developing societies.

3.Symbolic interactions theory: This theory focuses on social interaction and the subjective interpretation and understanding of its meaning of an individual. According to this theory disease relates to physical aspect and illness is an experience by the patient. Patient will look alternative to cope up with the health situation.

4.Critical race theory: According to this theory all knowledge is related to the power and wealth. Hence medical knowledge is Eurocentric. Some time the outcomes of the medical knowledge would be unfair and predictable.

5.Feminist theory: This theory focus on the gender relation to health. According to this theory women view and her health problems must be the centrally focused. This theory focuses on family responsibility, work responsibility (outside home if any) and domestic violence and its effect on the women's health.

In the same way there are five vital sociological approaches to study health and illness. They are

- Political economy
- Marxist approach
- Parsonian sociology of health
- Foucault's sociology of health
- Feminist approaches

1.k SOCIAL DETERMINANTS OF HEALTH

“what really moves the health of whole societies, adding to or subtracting from the sum of total health, may be factors which account for only a very small part of the individual variation in health and so escape detection” (Wilkinson:1996;16)

As we are aware socioeconomic and cultural issues have long been considering influencing factors on individual's health. These factors includes an individual-level (e.g. individual socioeconomic status, sex, caste, class) and neighborhood-level dimensions (culture, community, demography composition, social and physical environment) operating both separately and through various interactions. Current spatial research has found that in rural communities, economics, caste and class status are the furthestmost fundamental factors influencing on their health status. On the other hand, rural communities also face supplementary problems connected with access, and utilization of quality health care (Beard and others ,2009).

Public Health Agency of Canada has given 12 Social and Economic Determinates of Health

- (1) Income and Social Status;
- (2) Social Support Networks ;
- (3) Education and Literacy ;
- (4) Employment/Working Conditions;
- (5) Social Environments;
- (6) Physical Environments;
- (7) Personal Health Practices and Coping Skills;
- (8) Healthy Child Development ;
- (9) Biology and Genetic Endowment;
- 10) Health Services;
- (11) Gender (12)Culture

(Source: Public Health Agency of Canada: www.publichealth.gc.ca)

The World Health Organization (2008) views that the following health determinants has a pivotal role in determining the better health and standard of living of the people in general. The major health determinants are as follows;

(Sources: official website of WHO) Quoted

- Income and social status – higher income and social status are linked to the better health. The greater the gap between the rich and poor, the greater the differences in health.
- Education – low education levels are linked with poor health, more stress and lower self-confidence.
- Physical environment – safe water and clean air, healthy workplaces, safe houses, communities and roads all contribute to good health. Employment and working conditions – people in employment are healthier, particularly those who have more control over their working condition.
- Social support networks – greater support from families, friends and communities is linked to better health. Culture – customs and traditions, and the beliefs of the family and community all affects on health.
- Genetics – inheritance plays a part in determining life span, healthiness and the likelihood of developing certain illnesses. Personal behavior and coping skills – balanced eating, keeping active, smoking, drinking, stresses and challenges all affects on health.
- Health services – access and use of services that prevent and treat disease influences health. (Sources: official website of WHO)

Since India can be divided into urban /rural, and tribal India, social determinants affect differently on different sections of the society. Rural people are the most vulnerable to the different kinds of health problems. In this care their social and economic conditions normally will be very poor. Some time they have to live in a most remote area. Their income, educational level and occupation type will also play a vital role while determining their health problem.

Dahlgren And Whitehead's Model Highlights Some of The Main Factors Determining the Health of the Regional and the Local Populations (Cannon, 2008).

Fig 4

Source: Dahlgren and Whitehead (1991) cited in Leeds NHS Primary Care Trust

Not only biological factor, health is more determined by both social and cultural environments. Various studies have established this link about this (Beard and others, 2009; Menon,2000). Some of the social variables like income or poverty, occupation, educational status social network etc plays a vital role in determining the health behavior of any community. It is very crucial indicator of the health status of any community. Throughout the life course, social determinants influence on health at multiple levels on every human being. For example, the income of a person influences the health at different levels. This influence may co-occur and interact with each other to produce good/bad health status of an individual. Further, various social facts differently and independently influences on the health of an individual at different stages of life. It is found that socio-economic variables influencing health is quite widespread across the different geographical and cultural specific societies and for a variety range of health outcomes. Each socio-economic facts affects on health behavior of a person through different mechanisms.

Medical sociologists have opined that various social factors affects on population starting from onset of a disease and opting a treatment to cure that problem. In the first instances, individual's risky health behavior, low hygiene, low quality food etc may play a vital role in the onset of various diseases. Next, during the development of any disease/illness issues like social determinants, different types of medicinal systems (Ayurvedic / self treatment) , accesses to the quality treatment,

adoption or rejection of the modern medical system, coping behavior and other vital issues play a vital role in choosing a particular type of health care .

1.INCOME AND HEALTH : The Income level of a family may determine the level of the poverty (may be relative or absolute) . Since the link of income with health is quite complex it is not so easy to reveal the connection with reference to the rural people. Some time income may be seasonal. Also health status depends on individual income or total household income. Income also depends on employment itself. Income also depends on salary, pension, social security, household size, taxes structure saving pattern etc. Low income always associates with the low accessibility to the quality and on time health care among various social groups. The associate ship between the lower income and mortality and the morbidity rate in any family will be normally higher. It is found that those individuals of having good health can also improve their total income. In the same way ill health is a potent cause for job loss and decreases in the regular income. Once the fall of the regular income starts, it not only affects on that individual but also on the other family members.

Obviously good income enables any individual to buy various health related items like, nutritious food, good hospitals, health insurance etc. It gives somewhat good mental health too. Good income releases the individuals from poverty related and other stress. In the same way savings and other wealth also ensures good health of an individual. Because income is a kind of flow of resource where as assets and other forms of wealth can be used to maintain the better health at any point of time. Certain experts have shown that people with high income live longer when compare to the people of having low income. The Infant mortality rate will be lower in the high income groups whereas it will be higher in the low income group. High income people are more likely to report having met a physician regularly where as low income group people are not (Bir,2010) so regular .

All these findings show that marginal income or low income level tends to be more strongly associated with reduced probability of poor health than increase probability of strong health. Certain study reports have concluded that rich people are spending high on health care. In addition some poor people do not have a tendency to spend on their health despite decent income. However, not all research shows an independent effect of income inequality on health because there is less agreement about whether income inequality causes health and social problems independently (Beard and others, 2009; Menon,2000).

2. EDUCATION AND HEALTH

Education level has a close link with health over the period of time. Studies (Tipping and Segall, 1995) have shown that the level of education directly or indirectly impacts on health of an individual or social group. It is proved that the low educational attainment influences in risky health behavior. Education is a casual variable in improving the health status of any individual at any time. It is found that the higher level of education is associated with a healthy lifestyle too. Also it is established that good linkage between the level of schooling and the healthy lifestyle.

Health specialists felt there is a need to have deep probe among

- a. Normal impact of education on health;
- b. Interaction between the level of education and the inherited health features
- c. Level of schooling and the improved health literacy.

Educationists felt that importance of providing pre-school education will greatly increase the health prospects of the children as well as the family members. Generally it is found that both physical and mental health will be better amongst the good educated people and these people will spend less on the health when compared to the others. Also it is found that the low level of education is strongly associated with the poor psychological functions. Studies show that the low level of education is associated with the poor biological conditions, bad habits and unscientific health practices etc. Interestingly good educated people though they have had bad habits previously but they gave up because in the best interest of their future health (Menon, 2000; Orubuloye, 2003).

Since education is also a major determinant factor in the health care system, less educated people have a shorter life expectancy than the higher educated one in certain cases. Also the high rate of crimes and violence can be seen more among the low educated people. More education obviously leads to have a higher income. This high income helps in accessing high quality health care, good food, lifestyle etc. It is found that good education provides individuals to make better health related decisions related to himself and on behalf of the other family members. Next, it is found that in rural areas the level of education may not impact on the health separately from other vital variable factors. Income and occupation also have a good linkage with the education and finally all these factors influence on health. Finally education is a vital tool for increasing the healthy life style of any individual. Due to the better education,

family members can practice good health behavior and the low health expenditure (Tipping and Segall, 1995).

Health Behavior and Health Education

Fig 5

Sources: Glanz, K., Rimer, B.K. & Lewis, F.M. (2002). *Health Behavior and Health Education. Theory, Research and Practice*. San Fransisco: Wiley & Sons.

3.POVERTY:- It is widely known fact that poverty is a key role in determining the health status of any community. It may be urban, rural or tribal. It is found that poverty ultimately results in unhygienic housing, frequent exposure to various ill health, low medical care, poor nutrition, increased risk of health behaviour, poor sanitation, low level of hygienic etc. Poverty leaves an ultimate impact on the health culture of any community particularly vulnerable and the poor population in any given society. WHO (1999) felt poor health status might be a good parameter to measure poverty and visa -versa. Experts felt an increasing health expenditure by the Govt. will not improve the health status of the community unless the reducing the level of poverty. We cannot expect any good improvement in the health status of the population with so-much of the poverty problem in the rural parts of the country.

Poverty is a multidimensional aspect. It affects on good food, shelter, unemployment and the low income that all work together and effects on an individual's health. Due to this an individual will be at risk of getting depression, anxiety or any type of chronic disease. Due to the poverty poor people may not visit a doctor unless it is a serious disease seeking emergency care. Normally he/she will try with the local traditional or self medication. Sometime due to the poverty, patients' will buy the medicines over the counter (From the medical shops without prescription). Recent human development report (2011) opines that poverty and health influences each other directly and indirectly. Sociologists felt poor people often describe illness and disease is because of the fate, hunger, pain, fear, anger etc. Poverty not only affects the adults; it also affects severely on the health status of the children and the aged people in any given society. Due to the poverty poor people visit only government hospitals where there will be no modern health care facilities and the highly specialized physicians to diagnose the health problem in the early stage itself and giving curing options.

Due to the poverty people cannot visit private practitioners or good hospitals where one can get a high quality health care. Experts felt due to the poverty sometime children could not attend schooling. Hence, children and the parents cannot get any awareness about simple day to day health related practices/education. Poverty not only effects on the physical health but also affects on the mental health. Poverty related stress may even provoke to commit any crimes. This poverty related stress also effects on the development behavior of the community.

4.OCCUPATIONAL STATUS

Rather than income, occupational status of an individual or family is more reliable and the static criteria to measure the socio-economic status with reference to the health. Occupational status has a closer link with an easy access to the good health. Good occupational status or at-least the decent occupational status leads to have a more quality healthy life. It is found that an occupational status has a closer link with an access to the good health status. Flow of income may be some time fluctuates, whereas a good occupation generally promises more reliable and regular income flow. Hence, they can take the right decision regarding their suitable health care planning one time. Sometime, ill health may be a major reason for the downward occupational mobility. Studies have also proved that casual effect of occupational status on health behavior. Some time a health disorder may be a constraint for the upward occupational mobility of any person (Twumasi, 1988).

Sociologists have focused on objective and subjective indicators of the health and the occupational status. People with the higher occupational status are less likely to be exposed to the various occupational disorders generally. Also higher occupational status gives more peaceful mental health. Since employment status is more strongly associated with the health income experts felt it plays a vital role to access more economic resources. This may help an individual for the upward social mobility. Also it is observed that an unscientific health practices and an unhealthy habits can be seen more among the unemployed people often. This association has been found among the younger adults, older adults and people with various disabilities. However, some of the studies have observed that income and health are independently associated. Even after the good employment status the health problem/s of the higher income group are still increasing today. This might be due to an effect of material factors on health culture (Olujimi, 2006).

5.SOCIAL SUPPORT, SOCIAL NETWORK AND HEALTH

Various types of social connections, networks etc play the most vital role as a major social determinant of the health care or health status of a person or a group. Social supports not only gives material recourses but also they provide love, emotions and attachments. Social support is a type of health assistance that people will normally receive through their various social networks. Social network provides vital information's about healthy life style, better health management or hospital care. Certain studies have shown that good social network; result in a positive impact on both the physical and mental health. Social networks predict the risk of all cause and the cause specific health disorders. The Social network also has a history in providing better mental health care to the people. Social network and social support have also helped in surviving from various major illnesses (Szarz, 2007 ; Olujimi, 2006).).

Certain epidemiologists felt social connections may help in avoiding the onset of various infectious diseases. It is also found that association between social supports and gene environment interactions. Social networking and support may together use as social capital, whereas members of the community can make use of social capital system for betterment of their health needs. Studies (Wishwakarma,1993 ; Szarz, 2007), have also proved that there is a close association among social capital, health outcomes and communities socio-economic characteristics. It is also shown that withdrawn from the social network resulted in some type of mental agony among the members. Modern social network system in rural areas has proven useful in providing culture specific health care planning by the local NGOs. Like this through social networks and support rural people will get instrumental support, emotional

support and informational support to solve their both short term and long term health problems. On the other hand good social network can also be a negative impact on the variety of health outcomes. Sometimes people may use their social network for bad health behavior (ex. drug users etc).

In a changing rural society association between various socio-economic characteristics and health is a point of interest for the decades. It is found that education, poverty and income are the three major indicators of the healthy society. However, each of the indicator acts through different mechanisms on health issues in a society. Socio-economic characters in health are wide spread, distinctive, dynamic across multicultural societies and for a diverse range of health issues. Also through this variables, we can enhance our knowledge in understanding how biological pathways for some health disorders shaped by the local culture. Understanding contribution of social and cultural factors for good health gives a new edge to get an idea on mechanisms by which these variables play a key role about onset of various diseases and its progression and people's response to it. Socio-economic variables influence health at different level throughout the life course. These variables interact with both inherited and behavioral features to leave an impact on the health status of any community.

Bullseye Model of Social Determinants of Health Fig 6

1. Broader socio culture environment
2. Civil society
3. Intimate sources and economic realm

(Sources: A. Aiddiqui, M. Bobak and C.Hertzaman (2009) 'The Social Epidemiology of Population Health During the time of Transition from Communism in Central and Eastern Europe' in an edited book of S.J. Babones ;Policy Press-UK)

Effects of Housing and Neighborhoods on Health

Tab 3

Attributes	Direct effects	Indirect effects
	Individual/ household Neighborhood Level	Area/ Level
Physical / Material attributes	Damp, Cold, Mould, Heat, Homelessness	Indicator of Social and Economics Status
		Services and facilities; Features of the natural and built environments
Social/ Meaningful Attributes	Rent / Mortgage Arrears and In / Security of tenure	Household and area culture and behaviors.
	Feeling of ‘ home’ Social status Ontological security	Reach ability of services and community safety facilities
		Neighborliness

Souse: Adopted from World Health Organization (Europe), 2004

1.1 OTHER DETERMINANTS OF HEALTH

1.Gender : Involvement of women in health education, policy and interventions is an important determinant of her successful participation . This proves that gender stereotypes need to be examined seriously as they place in the way of the improvements in health that are known to be effectual. Gender discrimination in health services needs an affective address.

2.Political : It also affects in many ways on health. It is very essential to reveal the impact health care policy on people more efficiently. Also the researchers need to have an improved comprehend about the politics of health policy decision making, political forces, including voters, interest groups, Govt. health policy, insurance policy etc

3.Environmental: Environment mainly affects our health. Hazardous substances found in the air, soil and water cause health problems. Also agricultural and industrial activities, mining operation can cause health issues.

4.Nutritional : Peoples actions activity stage will influence their daily nutritional requirement. Different people need a different nutritional requirement. Lack of nutrition may cause many sever health problems

5. Media : Social and mass media can also play a role in bringing both positive and negative consequence on health wellbeing .Media influences the relationship between health policy and community

6.Philosophical: It involves the health ethics, medical ethics, processes, and people who are in need of protection of health care. For the nearly everyone the philosophy of healthcare is best proved as an inefaceable constituent of human social structures.

7.Vocational: This include rehabilitation for the people with various disabilities

(sources: from various sources)

1.m ETHNO MEDICINE IN RURAL CONTEXT

According to the WHO

Ethno medicine is "the sum total of knowledge, skills and practices on holistic healthcare, which is recognized and accepted by the community for its role in the maintenance of health and the treatment of diseases. Traditional medicine is based on theory, beliefs and experiences that are indigenous to the different cultures, and that is developed and handed down from generation to generation". (WHO, 1996).

The history of ethno-medicine system can be traced even in Vedas period. Ethno-medicine is commonly called as indigenous healing/ folk medicine/ faith healing, or magico- religious healing system. In 1968, Hughes applied the term as "those beliefs and practices relating to disease which are products of indigenous cultural development and are not explicitly derived from the conceptual framework of modern medicine" (Rubel and Hass, 1996).

Thribhuwan, (1998) writes

"Ethno medicine is conceptually defined as a culturally ordered interrelationship of medical symbols and meanings that are associated with the community notions of illness ideology body image and the entire set of preventive, primitive, curative and destructive health rituals and or therapeutic actions performed by the participants actors in various healing contexts into a symbolic system, there by representing the cultural whole" (Thribhuwan, 1998) .

Even though the definitions for ethno medical system is very narrow later on the meaning of the term was further extended to include all medical system, including biomedicine, viewed within the framework for their respective culture (Hughes,1990, Rhodes, 1990, Vijayendra and Bhat,2004).

The WHO again defines traditional medicine as:

"the health practices, approaches, knowledge and beliefs incorporating plant, animal and mineral-based medicines, spiritual therapies, manual techniques and exercises, applied singularly or in combination to treat, diagnose and prevent illnesses or maintain well-being."

(Sources; Fact sheet no. 134: Traditional medicine". World Health Organization. 2008)

Hughes (1968) has explained ethno medicine is to refer to those "beliefs and practices connecting to diseases that are products of indigenous cultural conceptions and are not unambiguously resulting from the theoretical construction of modern medicine". Ethno medical method is to regulate how an exact group of people perceives and deals with their health and illness. This method thus includes the study of health beliefs, healing techniques and practitioners and the relationship of these with culture and society in which they are found. The insider's viewpoint on ethno medical issues aids the sociologists to look at the rural peoples notion of health and disease (Kannaury, 2005).

Ethno-medicines are normally called as folk medicine/ popular medicine. Ethno medicine includes essential basic details about various diseases (onset and symptoms) different types of healing techniques / therapies, experience of indigenous healers etc.... Basically "ethno-medicine can be divided into sacred and secular sub sectors". Also it is opined that an in-depth scientific understanding about the mechanism of ethno-medicine will help to understand the interface between traditional medicine and modern medical system. It has a root in both religious eg; Shamanism) and empirical,(Hebraism) (Das,2004)

Dalal, (2007) writes ;

"Traditional healing is holistic, and aims at the overall well-being of the person. It takes body, self and society within a framework of dynamic equilibrium. The holistic approach takes into consideration the values, passions, beliefs, social interaction, and spiritual orientation of a person in their healing practices" (Dalal, 2007).

In 1924 W.H.R Rivers (British physician) first developed an idea of the indigenous medical system and he opined 'it should be viewed as prevailing causation beliefs with respect to any type of disease or illness'. Gradually medical anthropologists and sociologists started to study the indigenes medical system existing in various social groups focusing rural/tribal parts. Now a day's ethno -medicine has become as a study of non-western medicine and its significance in solving local health

problems. Basically ethno medicine covers mechanical, chemical and magic-religious procedures. It demonstrate an empirical therapeutic knowledge including Trephination, Bone setting, Obstetrics including Caesarian, Laparotomy, Uvulectomy, Comparative anatomy, Cantery, Inoculation, Poultices, Inhalation, Laxatives, Ointments and Cupping etc. (Acker Knecht,1942; Simmons,1955; Langhlin,1963 Huard,1969, Kar, 2004). Today even world bodies like UNISCO and WHO and others are promoting traditional knowledge more widely in both developing and developed countries.

According WHO (1998), more than 85% of the global population depending on traditional systems of medicines, (mostly plant-based), to meet their primary health care requirements. The National Health Policy of 1983 envisages incorporation of Indian Systems of Medicine and homoeopathy with the modern system of medicine (Annual Report, AYUSH, 2000-01). However it is found that traditional medicine has been completely integrated into the mainstream of health systems in China, North and South Korea and Thailand.

Recently world health organization (WHO) has revised earlier definitions and opined traditional medicine as

“The health practices, approaches, knowledge and beliefs incorporating plant animal and mineral- based medicines, spiritual therapies, manual techniques and exercises therapies, manual techniques and exercises, applied singularly or in combination to treat, diagnose and prevent illnesses or maintain well being” (WHO, 1999).

Even today more than 85% of the Indian rural population depends on various traditional medicines for their health care needs. However, experts and even WHO have cautioned that direct intake of traditional medicine may affect on the health and standardization of such medicine and ensuring safety is the need of the hour.

In Indian rural settings following are the some of the common medicinal system and they are :-

1. Ayurveda,
2. Unani
3. Sidda
4. Accu-puncher
5. Chinese Medicine
6. Tibetan Medicine, etc...

All these different types of medicine may have common base or different, sometime may be overlapping also. Sometime traditional medicine like Ayurvedic, Sidda may found along with western medicine. However, the basic principle and healing technique will be different. Sociologists have opined that traditional medicine may be invariably influenced by the established medical systems prevalent in the same society. Experts felt today's modern medicine is also based on the extracts of the plants and animal that had been long used in the formal traditional medicine/s. Experts felt a detailed study about TM (traditional medicine) also helps to find out why the majority of rural people are not showing trust to adopt or interest in modern medical health care facilities. Today it is widely known fact that TM is practiced mostly by the poverty ridden sections of the society only. In the same way T.M is becoming more popular in the western societies because of large scale side effects due to the modern medicines. Hence one can say more than 50% of the population across the globe solely depends on traditional medicine.

WHO in the year 2000 again opined ;

“Holism is a key element of all systems of traditional medicine. Therefore, when reviewing the literature on traditional medicine (both herbal medicines and traditional procedure-based therapies), the theories and concepts of the individual practice of traditional medicine, as well as the cultural background of those involved, must be taken into account”(WHO, 2000)

Some of the problems inherent in studying ethno medical issues are highlighted by Fabrega(1987) include;

1. What is ill vs what is not ill;
2. The role of sick person;
3. Interpretation of illness by social groups;
4. Interpretation of illness symptoms;
5. Institution used for treatment;
6. Organizations and quality of the medical system.

(Source: Robin D Tribhuwan (1998), Medical world of the Tribes, (Discovery Publisher), New Delhi

Ethno Medicine(EM) has Five Elements

1. Ethnology: It particular deals about how diseases/illness will be classified in a cross cultural scenario;
2. Diagnosis / Divination: Diagnosis is to identify the disease after proper examining the patient;

3. Divination: Predicting future course of action through cosmological entities;
4. Cultural bound syndrome: Specific social psychological syndrome of a specific illness in a given culture.

It is found that EM has Five Divisions.

1. Classification of disease/ illness
2. Etiological categories
3. Selection of therapy
4. Selection of the specialists
5. Ritual heading

(Sources: Foster,1981;Fabregr, 1977)

It is found that 80% of the modern medicines are basically from the plants which are traditionally using as herbal cures (Farnsworth, 1990). Keeping these information in mind, WHO in 1977 gave an official gratitude to the traditional medicines and recommended the involvement of customary healers with the national health care programmes (Maiti,2005). However, it has been focused on the standardization/ safety of the traditional medicine and its real efficacy. Over the last few years medical anthropologists are working towards the traditional medicine and its social relations and its side effects (Wardram, 2000; Barns, 2005). Several studies have also found the absence of the proper scientific evidences with respect to Ayurvedic and another type of traditional medicines focusing its side effects (Namarari et al, 2010; Desilva, 2011; Lamberts, 2013; Adam, 2011). Even today the traditional medicines are used across the globe (Kim, 2009; Sujatha, 2011). The issue is to focus on an approved protocol to study the traditional medicine and its efficacy. Experts felt Govt. and NGOs should not try to promote traditional medicine blindly and there is an urgent need to integrate traditional medicine with the modern biomedical health system after its proper standardization as a safety need (Bode, 2013).

ETHNOMEDICAL PATHWAY : A CONCEPTUAL MODEL

Fig 7

Source: Robin D Tribhuwan (1998), Medical world of the Tribes, (Discovery Publisher, New Delhi).

Studies on ethno-medicine have a long history. However, scientific studies on ethno medicine have started recently. Earlier studies were stressing only on the role of Witch-craft, Sorcerer, Spirit, Deity, Shaman's, focusing health belief of rural communities. Modern studies on ethno-medicine have been most helpful in distinguishing between the social aspects of an illness from the biological aspects. Experts felt studies on ethno-medical approach will be useful in scientific understanding of the treatment patterns followed by the indigenous practitioners. Ethno-medicine specialists follow culturally meaningful reality of patient's health behavior and go after traditional concepts to cure the various health problem.

Now we shall see some common reasons for certain illness and ethno-medicinal beliefs among rural people.

1.Influence of Evil Spirit: rural people believe generally this world is full of good/bad spirits including trees, air, water, light etc. If someone failed in respecting the evil spirits they may have to face the punishment in the form of disease or illness. All these problems are caused due to the evil spirit as believed by the most of the rural folks. For this kind of problem the traditional practitioners first identify the main spirit responsible through divination. After the proper diagnosis or identification she/he performs suitable magico-religious measures and administers holy threads, holy water etc to the patient. Sometime a healer uses the products of different animals (hair/teeth/skin), plants, herbs, etc to cure the patient. In this treatment most interesting fact is that before doing any treatment usually local healers take an appropriate personal care and protection to safeguard him from the reverse effects of the spirits. However, treatment pattern differs culture to culture and society to society having some common basic notions.

2.Influence of Evil Eyes': Generally in rural areas it is believed that some individuals would have certain evil powers. When such a person watches others instinctively other people may get diarrhea, fever, vomiting like problems. Normally it is believed that children are more affected due to the evil eyes'. In such cases, generally the folk healers use holy water with magical hymens etc.

3.Effect of Angry Deity:- In every society, each household worships a particular male or female/divine being/deity. If any household member failed in worshipping the deity regularly any member in that household will be having any health problem/s due to that angry deity. In such cases any one member or all household members may have to face the consequences. Generally in this circumstance, the family members invite a priest or a faith healer who has some divine powers to perform an appropriate

religious rituals at home or sometime in the nearby village temple. In the ritual process, household members should offer different things in cash or kinds so that deity will be satisfied.

4. Curse for the Sin :- Some of the infectious diseases like T.B , Leprosy, Chicken pox are believed to be caused due to the curse by the deities for a sin or an intentional mistake committed by an individual in the life. People also believe some time these problems may cause due the mistakes done in the previous birth also. For these problems folk healers normally administer certain liquid medicine prepared out of plants. Also he performs particular health rituals offering various items to the angry deities/spirits. Sometime healer asks the patient to rub with the juice extracted from the plant leaves on the affected body parts.

5. Sorcery or Black magic :- Generally rural folk believe certain disorder like Epilepsy Paralyse, Chest pain, are caused by the 'magical powers'. The inconvenience or pain or trauma will be unbearable on the part of the patients'. Some time the affected patient may have to face severe mental disorder due to trauma. Rural people believe all this will be happening due to sorcery or black magic etc. For this kind of problem healers follows established magico-religious spiritual curative treatments. Also in some cases the patients will be asked to eat magically treated food items or some certain holy things to keep always in the pocket or in the house or under the bed etc. Sometime patients should recite chants taught by the healer. The basic notion of this treatment is to neutralize the power which caused disorder to the patient through magico-religious approach. Sometime healer may beat the patients with the plant sticks.

6. Influence of the Village Deity:- Each village in the rural areas in India will have a particular type of male/female deity. It is generally believed that If deity got angry the whole village may have to face the health consequence including the mass death due to the communicable diseases, drought, etc. In this case all villagers collectively will worship the village deity, with different offerings. Also holy water and thread will be fixed to the main door of the each and every household in that village. In addition, all village people should observe certain norms and the regular rituals for a few days. Sometime holy threads will be placed at the main entrance of the village. Subsequently any evil forces cannot enter into the main village. Normally to avoid such problems each and every village will celebrate the festival /fair in the name of the 'village deity' once in a year without fail (Sonowal and Barua, 2011).

Bhasin (2007) also noted that the key belief in spirits as causing sickness, emanating from evil eyes, sorcery, witches, has also been reported from the various studies conducted in multi-caste villages in India (Harper,1969; Babb, 1975) and in rural areas of Rajasthan and other parts of the Karnataka (Carstairs, 1985; Lambert, 1992). Further cross cultural studies and observations related studies also done from other tribal groups of north India (Bhasin, 1997, 2002, 2003, 2004).

Response to any disease and illness is more or less cultural and geographically specific. It will be largely shaped by the nature of health culture of the particular society. Societal belief in any particular type of treatment or the therapy will be largely depending on existing health behavior. As Jaggi (1973) said even today in many villages in India people will practice same old medical systems as did Two thousand years ago (Jaggi , 1973).

In ethno medicinal system ritual and ritual healing play a vital role.

1.n HEALTH RITUALS

Ritual is a sum of established sets of activities and procedures performing throughout the healing process. It may include verbal behavior such as songs, chants, actions, prayers etc. Rituals will be performed in a defined place or in the context of a particular patient. Rituals have a number of socio-cultural functions they are :-

1. It's a symbolic mode of communication;
2. It reveals hidden meaning of symbols;
3. It helps to reconstruct the social order;
4. It helps to find out a solution for unresolved or mystical problems;
5. It helps to reach an expected outcome;
6. It helps to share socio-cultural meanings;
7. Rituals help for cohesion and transition.

(Source: Medical World of the Tribals. R.D.Thribhawan, (1998), Discovery Publisher, New delhi).

However, noted Anthropologists through their studies found rituals have number of socio-cultural functions as follows;

- Gluckman (1970) has opined 'Rituals encourage cohesion'
- Kartzp (1981) has felt ' rituals enhance individual and group autonomy'

- Munn (1973) found ‘ritual actions express and communicate shared socio-cultural meanings which are symbolically transacted through the medium of ritual action’
- Firth Raymond (1973) states that ‘rituals function as symbolic modes of communication’
- Geertz: (1970) said ‘ritual is an undivided part of health culture’
- Douglas 1975) found ‘ritual acts endow culturally important cosmological conceptions

(Source: Robin D Tribhuwan (1998), Medical world of the Tribes, (Discovery Publisher, New Delhi)

There is a widespread disagreement among the sociologists and medical anthropologists about ritual concepts. They feel the rituals should be applied to all cultural set of health behaviors. Rituals vary according to the social class/caste/religion etc in the rural parts. Turner (1988) has opined that ritual symbol is the last and the tiny unit of any health behavior. Normally the ritual process will be conducted to achieve the desired end within a given cultural/religious framework. Rituals help to understand the process of the social life as a consistent and meaningful event. Sometime rituals are strongly influenced by the socio-cultural domain of the rural health culture.

Ritual Healing: - Ritual healing is a kind of process performed by the medical practitioners as a part of an appropriate therapy. Ritual healing is a process to satisfy the spiritual, ancestral, cosmological entities etc. In a traditional setting, beliefs in rituals are more crucial than any therapeutic actions. All traditional healing methods (herbal/magic etc) will be culturally influenced by an established ritual action/s. It is widely believe ritual healing will be performed due to ---

1. To reconstruct the cultural order;
2. To satisfy or settlement with the cosmological powers;
3. To worship the angry deity/pathogens;
4. To balance bodily equilibrium;
5. To diagnose organic causes of illness
6. To remove the evil effect
7. To thank the healer

(Source: Robin, Peter & Preeti Medico-Ethno History of Kathkaris & Thakuras, TRC Bulletin Vol. 14. No.3, 1992)

1.0 COMMON HEALING SYSTEM IN RURAL AREAS;

1.Spiritual healing: Spiritual healing is a kind of healing system passing energy to the patients' body through the mediation or prayer which is a most common trend in rural parts. It is a kind of holistic medical system focusing uniformly on the body, mind and spirit at a time.

2.Pranic healing:- It is an ancient science of healing therapy. It is a more or less a kind of spiritual healing through the soul actualization and reaching the God or realization of self actualization. It also focuses on to increase the natural healing power or immunity of the body.

3.Humoral: It normally refers to the elements of the blood and other fluids of the human body. It is widely believed that the humeral imbalance brings diseases or illness in the human body. Equilibrium of humeral substances is an essential to keep healthy. Humeral theory has dated back (375BC). Even today various modern medicines depend on these theories only.

Elements of Humors:-

Tab-4

Elements	Colour	Season	character
Phlegm	Yellow	Winter (water)	Rational
Blood	Red	Spring (air)	Courage hope
Gall	Black	Autumn	irritable
Choler (bile)	yellow	Winter	Unemotoild

Critiques of Ethno medicine:- Most ethno-medical practices are being criticized for various reasons. Some of them felt the cosmological power or ritual healing is just a hoax (tricky) only. Shamans are playing on psychology of the patient's. Also critics' say an ethno-medicine cannot directly applied without knowing the possible biological reasons for the disease/illness. Because of the therapeutic skills some healers, have been mastered in curing specific types of health disorders. Some time they charge more money from their clients. They enjoy some special positions and informal powers in the medical world of the villages because of their healing reputations. In some cases ethno-medicines even can influence on the modern medicine in certain aspects. Hence, it is the need of the hour to have more scientific studies on the relationship among the modern medicines and the other existing ethno-medical systems. Various instances have been examined about the problems involved in

introducing the modern medical system in the villages because of the heavy influx of ethnic medicines.

1.1 TRADITIONAL HEALERS:

Dala (2007) writes “in most of the folk practices healers are mediators between the physical and the metaphysical. One can regularly find healers who are recognized for their ability to host a deity or spirit and under whose spell they acquire supernatural powers to manage the minds of their visitors and to heal them” (Dala ,2007).

Role of the medicine man or the traditional healers’ in administrating or practicing ethno-medicine will be more vital in rural parts. Even though the traditional healers are scientifically untrained, they would normally have more knowledge about the local’s concept on disease, illness and people’s social psychology etc . Hence, some time they will have more successful healing rates. Also these healers are more informal, approachable and easily accessible and patients friendly. However, in modern medical world the patient - doctors relationship is quite formal, hierarchical and also it is more depersonalized. Qualifications to be a traditional healers or quacks need some sort of formal or informal training or strong family background. In some cases, more than Two years of apprenticeship may be required. In a village side every therapist will be specialized in handling different types of illness and diseases. Women healer also can be seen who is specialized in solving women related disease in the rural areas. A religious leader like a priest, quack etc, also plays a significant role as faith healers in handling various health issues. People believe the supernatural authority is bestowed upon him by a cult or organization. Rural folk normally have a faith in the religious leaders who receives healing power/s directly from the cosmological sources according to the local people(Joshi, 2000).

In many societies religious leader performs healing rights (faith healing) sometime as a family advisor also (Hoebel, 1958). Experts are opined that the faith healings largely depends on the subject of the healing technique. Healers’ here normally focus on the weak psychology of the patient. Healers will try to convince the patients’ that his/her illness has caused due to the supernatural/deity power only. Hence, only supernatural powers can cure or heal the illness through the healers only. Traditional healers have got a holy position in the mindset of the village people. Usually traditional healers will be respected by everyone in the village. He/she will be honored on many occasions. Normally people do not want to cross his words/advise. Traditional healing normally would be a familial healing and its secret will not be

leaked to anyone outside of his/her family. In most of the cases this job would be like a family occupation passing from generations.

Joshi (1986) has classified traditional healers found in the rural areas in the following Five categories;

1. Diviner or Thantri / Vaidya;
2. Astrologer, Priest and the Healer;
3. Pulse specialists and Herbalists;
4. Midwife / Gyneic specialists

In rural parts people choose the healer based on the following particulars;

1. Caste background of the healer;
2. Cost he/she charges per case;
3. Friendly behavior of the healer;
4. The personal attention he takes towards patients ;
5. His/her past experience;
6. Success rate of the healer

A lot of Anthropologists and Medical sociologists have written largely on traditional healers (Lewis, 1971; Parrot, 1970; Joshi, 2000). The majority of the writings are on the psycho-social role of the healers because they are specializing in psycho-pathological treatment. Experts have opined that traditional healers sometime manipulate current social symbols they can repair the broken social ties from the patient's point of view. Some time in a rural multi cultural society, caste of the patients and the caste of the healer also play a vital role in the broader social context. Some time patients belonging to the upper caste may ignore the healing skills of the Vidya belonging to the lower caste. (Sources; Turner, 1967)

TYPES OF HEALERS COMMONLY FOUND IN RURAL SETTINGS

TAB-5

(Source: Adnan Ali Hyder And Richard H. Morrow, from the book *Culture, Behavior, and Health*,2005)

<p>1.Indigenous</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Midwives • Shamans • Curers • Spiritualists • Witches • Sorcerers • Priests • Diviners • Herbalists • Bonesetters • Massagers 	<p>2.Other Medical Systems</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chinese medical system • Practitioners • Chemists/herbalists • Acupuncturists • Ayurvedic practitioners • Taoist priests • Pluralistic • Injectionists • Indigenous health workers • Western-trained-birth attendants
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THE CHOICE OF HEALER IN RELATION TO VARIOUS EXPLANATORY VARIABLES

FIG 8

(Sources: Kroger, 1983)

RITUAL PROCESS ASSOCIATED WITH TRADITIONAL HEALERS TO COLLECT MEDICINAL PLANTS

FIG 10

Source: Robin D Tribhuwan (1998), Medical world of the Tribes, (Discovery publisher, New Delhi)

THE CHOICE OF HEALER IN RELATION TO VARIOUS POSSIBLE EXPLANATORY VARIABLES (After Kroger, 1983)

TAB 6

	Subject characteristics	Disorder characteristics	Service characteristics
Explanatory variables	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age • Sex • Marital status & position in household • Ethnicity • Formal education • Occupation • Resources (land, cash, etc) • Interaction with family, • Community, etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chronic or acute • Severe or trivial • Etiological model • Expected benefits from treatment • Psychosomatic vs somatic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessibility • Appeal (opinions and attitudes towards traditional and modern healers) • Acceptability • Quality • Communication • Cost

Source: Rapid Assessment of Health seeking behaviour in relation to STD SEF/PRS/STD (GPA/WHO June1995 (draft protocol)

1.q CULTURAL COMPETENCE AND RURAL HEALTH CARE

Cultural competence in health care describes a health care system that is accessible and respects the beliefs, attitudes and cultural life-styles of professionals and of patients. It is a sad truth that, the quality of rural health care received varies greatly depending on class, caste and socioeconomic group, or place of residence (especially if it is rural). Cultural awareness and synthesis of learning are on-going requirements for the delivery of optimum patient-centered rural health care. In the social environment and health logic model access to “health promotion, disease and injury prevention, and health care serves as an intermediate indicator along a pathway linking resources in the social environment to health outcomes. An important component of access to care for culturally diverse rural populations is the cultural competence of healthcare systems” (Anderson , 2003).

Cultural competence is an essential to the healthcare quality, because the goal of culturally competent care is to promise the stipulation of suitable services and decrease the occurrence of medical errors due to from misunderstandings caused by

differences in verbal communication or culture or tradition etc . Cultural competence has possible for improving the competence of care by plummeting needless investigative testing or unsuitable use of services. as long as culturally competent services has the latent to get better health outcomes, augment the competence of clinical and support staff, and result in greater client satisfaction with services especially in rural areas. Workforce diversity in the healthcare setting is seen as a means of providing pertinent and effectual services. Workforce variety programs go further than hiring practices to comprise organizational strategies for diagnosing barriers that put off employees from completely participating and achieving triumph. Achieving assortment at all levels of the healthcare organization can pressure the way the organization serves the wants of clients of a variety of cultural and linguistic backgrounds and circumstances (Anderson, and others, 2003).

As we are aware India is more a culturally diverse society and more health inequalities have been acknowledged. Cultural competence is a 'health care system that is reachable and compliments the viewpoint, attitudes and cultural life-style of professionals and the patients' in any given society. It is a more pathetic to note that the quality of rural health care already is too low in many rural parts of the country because of various social and economic background of the rural community. Any researcher must have the solid cultural background to study the health issues of any community. It is a well known truth that an existing social and cultural consciousness and fusion of knowledge are very essential and required requirements for providing the best possible patient-centered quality rural health care. "In the social surroundings and health, logic model access to health promotion, disease and injury prevention, and health care servies as an transitional pointer along a pathway connecting capital in the social atmosphere to health outcomes"(Anderson,2003).

Experts opined that significant constituent of quality health care for culturally varied rural populations of the country is the cultural framed healthcare systems only. This is essential to the healthcare quality, because the objective of culturally competent care is to guarantee the stipulation of suitable services and to decrease the occurrence of possible various direct and indirect mistakes (may be a small or huge) occurring from misunderstandings caused by differences in exact understanding the health cutler and health behavior of the rural people so that more success full programme (Anderson,2003).

Various experts have suggested to have quantify cultural competence in health care including

- Official concepts ;
- Replica of programmes ;
- Laws, system, and principles;
- Valid Performance ;
- Criteria for Evaluative

(Sources: U.S. Department of Health and Human Service (2004)

Anderson (2003) again writes

“Workforce diversity in the healthcare setting is seen as a means of providing relevant and effective services. Workforce assortment programs go beyond hiring practices to include organizational strategies for identifying barriers that prevent employees from completely participating and achieving success. Achieving variety at all levels of the healthcare organization can influence the way the organization serves the requirements of clients of a variety of cultural and linguistic backgrounds”

Achieving associate ships across the multi cultural and vulnerable rural health sector in a methodical and continued means is a significant code for mounting valid, useful and significant cultural proficiency/competence. Facts can be recognized and acted in a long-standing organized approach rather than through intermittent unplanned policies and programs focusing rural parts. Field experiences increase the profit of additional health plan to improve the health culture. More over cultural competence play a significant role to pass up errors and allows to increase more success rate to implement more quality health care programmes across the rural societies (Anderson , 2003).

It is well know truth that solid and appropriate cultural competence of various medical and health worker professionals can have more prospective for developing the efficiency of care by reducing unnecessary medical procedures or unsuitable use of health care services which also can avoid medicalisation. Reducing medicalisation is also a major contribution from cultural competences of healthcare system. Further it is noted that services of having cultural frameworks have the possibility to have progressed and improvised health outcomes. Also it augments the competence of various medical and non medical staff, NGOs health workers in providing competent and quality health care system. Also it plays a vital role in providing patient friendly, client focused health care services especially in a multi-cultural rural area.

CHAPTER II
RESEARCH DESIGN AND
METHODOLOGY

It is obvious from the objectives of the study presented above that the present sociological study is concerned with the analysis of the rural's health behavior from the different perspectives. Neither a descriptive nor diagnostic technique was followed. A blend of both diagnostic - exploratory in nature model has been used in this study. This study used both qualitative and quantitative approaches. Both these methods were useful to find out in depth understanding of the problem and its quantification. The methodology had Five major components; 1. Survey 2. Community Norms Study 3. Institutional Ethnography (NGOs /PHCs /Bureaucratic Perspective); 4. Content Analysis ; Case Studies. Data have been collected from Five sources: 1 .Household Members 2. Other Community Members. 3. NGOs 4 PHCs and the health officials. 5. Traditional Healers. Study has been done in the rural parts Karnataka-South India. Although this research was meant to investigate the perspectives of multiple stakeholders, a number of data collection methods were used to generate data directly from the selected samples (households). Data have been analyzed using statistical software's

2.a CONCEPTUAL CLARITY OF THE CURRENT STUDY

Health is one of the vital indicators reflecting the quality of human life. Today the majority of rural people is suffering from various communicable and non communicable diseases. The health seeking behavior of rural population is very complex because it is influenced by a large number of factors. It is stated there is a positive correlation between the health status of rural people and their social, economical and cultural background.

Studies have suggested that the lack of optimal utilization of modern health services by rural peoples is due to a variety of socio-cultural reasons. Some services are inappropriately used, and preventive health care, are under-utilized due to the lack of awareness.

Experts have lamented the dearth of micro-level data among such rural populations and have suggested that an effective solution to the health related problems of rural society must situate the problem within the larger contexts of health culture and preventive strategies of the households. Even though rural society is small and simple but has its own inherited health beliefs and practices concerning various health disorders/illness. In the same way each and every culture has discovered its own local system of health seeking and health care seeking behavior and pluralistic therapy in their health culture to encounter with various diseases/illness. It gradually leads to the formation of new health culture. This health culture will constitute viz social, cosmological, spiritual, natural and super natural beliefs towards the onset of various diseases/illness and different system of medicine to care it. Any rural health culture normally would consist of three major health components.

1. Illness ideology;
2. Body symbolism and;
3. Ritual healing.

This health culture is a part of the sub culture within a totality of the population. Hence, in more precise term we can say health culture can be termed as learned health behavior to separate it from the aspect of health behavior caused by various biological stimulation. This health culture will be a wider complex of the knowledge including roles, norms, values ideologies, practice, rituals, etiology, local healers etc. These factors together responsible for having a particular type of health seeking or health care seeking behavior in a given situation.

Over the period of time due to the interventions of various external agencies and the changing socio-economic status, rural people are adopting certain changes in their health culture transforming their health status. Due to the globalization/NGO interventions health culture in a rural society is under tremendous changes where the majority of them is gradually shifting from the traditional to the modern medical health care system. However rest of them is in dilemma as indicated by some studies (Bhardwaj and Paul ,1986).

As the health status changes, perception and behavior in encountering with the different health problems will also get changed (Banerji, 1986; Aann,1992). People usually develop their health needs generated and stimulated by their changing level of socio-economic condition, seeking some alternative way-out and actions to face various health crises within the given environmental condition (Parsons, 1963). This is the most common among particular social groups in rural societies. Now a day's medical pluralism is also a very vital compliance of the rural health culture following availability of different types of medical systems and its success and failure. Today the medical pluralism is playing a vital role in shaping specific health behavior of any community. Therefore this current medico-sociological study is of critical, comprehensive, multi dimensional, multi frontal and suggestive in nature.

Further, western sociologists opined the major reason behind persisting of the poor rural healthcare in India is due to the strong prevalence of the caste and the class system. Higher caste people consider good health status as a menace to maintain the differences among the social classes, especially in the rural parts of the country. And this higher caste people expect better social dealings, respectable places in the society and an improvement in their health standards (Steven, 1990). This aspect of the enquiry has some vital importance in the present study because it facilitates a medico-sociological probe into the working of a social system and the functional and un-functional aspects of various social institutions and sub systems focusing the health culture and behavior of the rural people.

Age old traditional norms and the values regarding the various health issues are still prevailing in many rural parts of the country. The traditional medicinal system is the most common health care aspect even today in most of the rural parts. Next, an analysis of the rural health care problems demands a deeper medico-sociological insight into the problem. Hence, the major theoretical objective of this proposed research study is to find out the social and cultural factors responsible for the issues relating to the changing illness ideology and the role of medical pluralism. This kind of analysis leads to an understanding of conflict between the traditional and modern

medicines in multi cultural societies and why some rural people are reluctant towards using the modern medicinal system even today.

Further, overcoming various difficulties in communication skill that prevent one to interact with external changing forces is vital. Despite the modern preventive and curative medicine, the healthcare delivery services in several rural parts in Karnataka state (India) are still poor and the low quality and largely unscientific. Within the current comprehensive health intervention services, there has been no attempt to understand the health culture as a sub-culture complex. But this is precisely the perspective necessity to develop a model of culturally suited health care delivery system specifically designed for the rural people of the country. This study is also touching these facts.

Anthropologists have revealed that the development of the health culture of the rural mass should be examined as an undividable part of the entire way of the life focusing the rural health behavior and the well-being in the changing scenario. Today there are various forces percolated from the larger socio-economic and directed through the attribute to the historical, social and political dimension of the developmental pattern of their health culture in the given settings.

The aim of the current research study is to understand how different forces and approaches affects the health culture which is determined in the larger and changing socio-economic conditions of the rural people. This study is largely based on the geographically and culturally specific data situating with a new understanding and interpretations about the factors responsible for the changing the health behavior of rural population's within a context of changing socio-cultural norms and this study further aims to reveal how communities social and economic resources can be specifically mobilized for remediation campaigns towards improving the health status of the rural people.

2.b GENERAL OBJECTIVE:

To study the nature and dynamics of health culture and changing health seeking behavior of the rural population and to explore how these are determined by their unique socio-cultural background in the selected rural districts of South Karnataka, India

2.c SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES:

1. To study the changing social, economical, cultural, political, health and demographic profile of the studied rural population ;
2. To understand the changing illness ideology of the rural people and to find out the existing perception, health seeking behavior and culturally bounded attitudes about onset of certain common diseases and use of different systems of medicines(Traditional, Ayurvedic, Homeopathy, Allopathic etc) to cure it;
3. To analyze the dimension of rational, non rational, fatalistic and non fatalistic pattern in understanding their behavior for causes and treatment of illness/disease;
4. To reveal the factors accounting for the accessibility to, availability of and affordability for new health care institutions and services and to compare the variability in acceptance of new health schemes on account of rural's unique socio-economic and cultural background;
5. Suggestion to develop culturally compatible and acceptable new health intervention strategies for the rural community.

2.d. THEORETICAL POSTULATES:

1. Any domain of social life (including ethno-medicine) is built on a framework of implicit meanings ;
- 2 That these meanings are not restrained to a single sphere/area of social life but the same pervade the whole social system (Sources: Schneider,1976;Turner,1972;Tribhuwan ,1998).

2.e RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

It is obvious from the objectives of the study presented above that the present sociological study is concerned with the analysis of the rural's health behavior from the different perspectives. A deeper sociological insights into the problem demand much more concentration on the various social issues and the related problems concerning changing the health culture of the rural folk in the recent times. Neither a

descriptive nor diagnostic technique was followed. A blend of both diagnostic - exploratory in nature model has been used in this study.

The first step was to select the samples for the actual study. Since the present study was a multi dimensional covering different perspective and the nature of the rural health culture, the number of households having all such characteristic features which fulfills the objectives of the study was quite large. And it was not theoretically possible to cover all these samples in the studied villages. Hence, the Census method of data collection was adopted in this case. Therefore the researcher decided to choose representative samples, having all essential features in a relative proportion. A careful attention was given to an adequacy of the size of the samples for the study.

This entire study has been divided into two parts. First part deals with the demographic aspects like family, size, family income, education, and occupations-etc. The second part deals with subjective issues like the impact of socio economic aspects, concepts, practices, attitudes, perceptions on health and illness, health behaviour, rituals, cultural barriers etc.

A. AREA UNDER STUDY

This study had been conducted in the following Four districts (rural) of Southern Karnataka –India based on the recent RCH and Health and Family welfare survey report

1. Chamrajanagar Districts
2. Hassan Districts
3. Kodagu Districts
4. Kolar Districts

B. ABOUT THE STUDIED DISTRICTS *

1. Chamarajanagara is the southernmost rural district in the state of Karnataka. As per 2011 census Chamarajanagar district has a population of 1,020,962 and population density of 200 inhabitants per square kilometer (520 /sq mi) and population growth rate over the decade 2001-2011 was 5.75%. District has a sex ratio of 989 females for every 1000 males, and a literacy rate of 61.12%.

2. Hassan is a southern district in Karnataka state. As per 2011 census Hassan district has a population of 1,776,221, The district has a population density of 261 inhabitants per square kilometer (680 /sq mi). Its population growth rate over the decade 2001-2011 was 3.17%. Hassan has a sex ratio of 1005 females for every 1000 males, and a

literacy rate of 75.89%. Hassan District is administratively divided into eight taluka and tourism and agriculture is the main income sources.

3.Kodagu also known by **Coorg**, Kodagu has a population of 554,762. The district has a population density of 135 inhabitants per square kilometer (350 /sq mi) with population growth rate of 1.13%. Kodagu has a sex ratio of 1019 females for every 1000 males and a literacy rate of 82.52%.Kodagu is a rural region and economy based on agriculture, plantations and tourism. Kodagu District is administratively divided into Three taluka

4.Kolar district is a district in Karnataka state of India. The major sources of employment are agriculture, dairy and sericulture, floriculture with a population density of 384 inhabitants per square kilo metre (990 /sq mi) and population growth rate is 11.04%. Kolar has a sex ratio of 976 females for every 1000 males, and a literacy rate of 74.33%. (* Wikipedia resources) All these districts have poor performemnce in RCH study

C.SAMPLING DESIGN

Multistage stratified random sampling technique was adopted for the selection of the villages from the Four districts for the current study. In first stage, Four (4) rural blocks were selected from each studied Four rural districts i.e 1 Hassan, 2.Kolar, 3.Chamrajanagar and 4.Kodagu districts on the basis of good, average and poor performance in RCH (Reproductive And Child Health Survey-2010) as per achievement of indicators during the previous assessment year and following discussions with the district health officials. In the second stage, in each district 4 sub-centers (one each from the different PHC jurisdiction areas of the identified blocks) were randomly selected from the each Four blocks. Likewise 16 sub-centers were selected out of the total 93 sub-centers in all Four studied districts of the state.

In the third stage from each of the 16 selected sub-center areas, one sub-center headquarter (HQ) village and one non-HQ village were also randomly selected. Likewise 16 villages comprising 8 HQ and 8 non-HQ were identified out of total 50 villages in the identified sub-center areas from all the Four districts. From the each village a total of 50-60 (depending) household samples have been selected for the current survey. Totally 16 villages, 800 households were selected for the current study. Further Five reputed NGOs working for the rural health care and for the case study purpose 25 local healers were also included based on the purposeful sampling technique for an in-depth study. Few PHCs and sub centers were also consulted.

While finalizing the village's for the data collection, the literacy rate, development index, population composition, political influence, fundamental facilities, health infrastructure, nature of adjoining areas, and distance from the nearby city etc had also been noticed. Since the samples of the study were heterogeneous and complex in social structure, samples had been carefully drawn. Above sampling technique was adopted so as to obtain an overall picture of community's health behavior and health culture presuming a definite distribution exist within the different blocks of the district, with respect to the performance of public health being better in some areas as compared to other relatively underserved areas.

To successfully address my research objectives I have collected required data from Five sources: **1 .Household Members 2.Other Community Members. 3. NGOs 4 PHCs and the health officials. 5. Traditional Healers.** Although this research was meant to investigate the perspectives of multiple stakeholders, a number

of data collection methods were used to generate data directly from the selected samples (households). These efforts had been guided as much as possible by the participatory methodologies developed by an international rural welfare NGOs to eliciting useful data.

Secondary data were collected from the related resources. Further Indices for socio-economic status, environmental status and the health status are constructed according to the general formula used by the United Nations Development Program (UNDP). These indices are used to find the relation between health status and the role, of socio-economic factors. Before the study, an informal consent was taken from the respondents.

D. PHASES OF THE RESEARCH STUDY

This study had been conducted in three phases for an intensive analysis;

1. In the first phase an extensive secondary materials were collected on the topic from the various resources;
2. In the second phase quantitative primary data were collected through a household survey;
3. In the third phase data collected through focus group study from the community (other than the studied samples)

E. RESEARCH COMPONENTS

This study used both qualitative and qualitative approaches. Both these methods were useful to find out in depth understanding of the problem and its quantification. Sutton (2006) and others have given a rationale for conducting this kind mixed research. 1. Participant enrichment, 2. Instrument fidelity 3. Treatment integrity and, 4. Significant enhancements.

The methodology had Five major components;

1. Survey;
2. Community Norms Study ;
3. Institutional Ethnography (NGOs /PHCs /Bureaucratic Perspective);
4. Content Analysis ;
5. Case Studies

F.SAMPLING FRMEWORK/STRUCTURE

SL. No	District	Village Name	Sampling
01.	Chamaraja Nagara	Dodda Kandonor	47 HH
		Dodaveagge	52 HH
		Ankanahalli	39 HH
		Telnauru	61 HH
02.	Hassan	Danthalli	54HH
		Cowdahalli	45 HH
		Harohhali	51 HH
		Harehalli	55 HH
03.	Kodagu	Kallahalli	47 HH
		Kanooru	53 HH
		Nalknadu	51 HH
		Vatekolli	49 HH
04	Kolar	Begli Hosahalli	50 HH
		Chokkahalli	59HH
		Karahalli	46HH
		Obenahalli	55HH
			HH Sample: 800

*HH Households

Tab 7

All these villages have poor performemnce in RCH study(2012)

1.HOUSEHOLD SURVEY

The household survey had been found to be most effective tool for investigating the health phenomenon in all its facets. A survey was conducted among carefully chosen samples of 800 households from the Four districts. Thissurvey had been carried out with the scheduled questionnaires (194) covering the following subject matters (in brief). Respondents were asked to just describe the symptoms in his/her own words (lay perception) and later on classified with the help of a Physician. Here disease/illness had been just used as references for revealing specific health seeking behavior /health care seeking behavior of the respondent's covering---

1 What is health? Reasons for ill health, age, education, income and occupation, caste and its role on health status of a community etc;

2, Cultural concept of health, illness, health behavior, socialization, local healers etc ;

3 Household decision making process on health and illness, common health problems in the area and reasons, cultural perception etc;

5 Mortality, undernourishment, immunizations mental health, western medicine legal provisions, role of PHC, medicalisation health policy and programmes etc.

2. COMMUNITY NORMS STUDY

Part of this study had involved community norms regarding various health issues. Hence, subjects including local community leaders, teachers, advocates, politicians, college students, and other elite's of the society have been interviewed. They have been drawn from the communities –at-large in which studied samples lives. The first session was conducted to elicit community perceptions about health, illness and medical pluralism and opinion about the common health problems according to gender and age. The second part of the community norms study had few discussion sessions to cover the breadth of topics including the relative advantages and disadvantages of various medical systems, medicalisation, rural health problems, cultural barriers, the role of education, Govt. schemes, NGOs role etc. All focus group interviews have been recorded and analyzed using appropriate advanced software's.

3. INSTITUTIONAL ETHNOGRAPHY

This is to understand the rural health scenario from the perspective of local NGOs. This included discussion of organizations philosophy towards rural health, reasons for poor health infrastructure, changing health culture, the structural constraints and success and failure of the group/s had experienced with its interventions etc. A checklist of around 25 major focus areas of the study problem was prepared after pre-testing the schedule for this purpose.

4. CASE STUDIES

The portion of this component however had consisted of visiting selected 25 local healers to conduct an in-depth interview. Next, I use participant observation technique to better understanding of health practice of the samples/healers. Interviews were semi structured and utilized an interview guide addressing the themes of research objectives.

G. SECONDARY DATA SOURCES

Secondary Data were collected from

1. Records maintained in the village directories;
2. Records maintained by various health agencies;

3. Census records for demographic information;
4. Study reports, articles, books Govt. documents, health survey reports et

H.TOOLS FOR DATA COLLECTION

The following tool were used to collect data

- 1.Survey;
2. Interview ;
3. Participant observations;
4. Focus group ;
5. Case Study

II.INSTRUMENTS

The following instruments were structured for the collection of both Quantitative and Qualitative data.

1. Respondets (sampling) Level Schedule;
2. Indigenous /local healers Schedule;
3. Community Schedule (focus group);
- 4.NGO Schedule;
- 5.Govt. Health Official Schedule

J.RECORDING OF DATA

Data had been recorded using various modern devises

K.ANALYSIS OF DATA

The quantitative data have been analyzed using **Minitab and SPSS** software. The thematically indexed discourse from various interviews, case studies and focus groups had been converted into an extended set of dummy variables and entered into the *minitab* database. It is the most useful because, it would allow the perceptions of the different groups supplying various data (community, household members, NGO staff etc) to be compared to be compared along a spectrum of variables utilizing ANOV method and was tested for the hypotheses related with the research objectives.

The qualitative data generated from the interviews, case studies and focus groups had been thematically coded in the *NUD*IST* database software and had been indexed to identify dominant themes and to link those themes with the specific

research questions. The actual data which could not be predicted with certainty include the concept/s of health behaviors, risks involved in health culture, health concept, community perception on various health policies and the programmes implemented by both the Government and NGOs an index tree had been prepared to delineate relationship between themes (Qualitative Research and Solution, 1999).

Also descriptive statistics, including standard deviation (SD), frequency and percentage were used to analyze the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents. Chi-square had been used to examine the association between non-parametric variables. ANOVA was used to test the relationships between parametric and non-dichotomous categorical variables wherever required. Somewhere the logistic regression method used to find the relationship between the dependent variables and some predisposed independent variables wherever required. In addition, random co-efficient modeling allowing for clustering within the families for assessing impact of interventions of various external agencies on health culture also been used. For coding system and to classify the disease/illness the following reference system had been used

1. Metlab Demographic Surveillance System
2. International Classification of Diseases Health Related Problems (WHO, 2004)

L.STATISTICAL METHODS APPLIED

Following statistical methods were employed in the present study

a.Descriptive statistics: it is the discipline of quantitatively describing the main features of a collection of information, or the quantitative description itself. Descriptive statistics aims to summarize a sample, rather than using the data to learn about the population that the sample of data is thought to represent.

b.Frequencies

Frequency is the number of occurrences of a repeating event per unit time. It is also referred to as temporal frequency, which emphasizes the contrast to spatial frequency and angular frequency. The period is the duration of one cycle in a repeating event, so the period is the reciprocal of the frequency.

c.Percentages

A percentage is a number or ratio expressed as a fraction of 100. It is often denoted using the percent sign, "%", or the abbreviation "pct." For example, 45% (read as "forty-five percent") is equal to 45/100, or 0.45. A related system which

expresses a number as a fraction of 1,000 uses the terms "per mil" and "millage". Percentages are used to express how large or small one quantity is relative to another quantity. The first quantity usually represents a part of, or a change in, the second quantity. (sources: from various sources)

d. Chi-square test

chi-square test or χ^2 test, is any statistical hypothesis test in which the sampling distribution of the test statistic is a chi-squared distribution when the null hypothesis is true. Also considered a chi-squared test is a test in which is *asymptotically* true, meaning that the sampling distribution (if the null hypothesis is true) can be made to approximate a chi-squared distribution as closely as desired by making the sample size large enough (Krishnaappa, 2013).

e. Crosstabs Procedure (Contingency Coefficient Analysis)

The Crosstabs procedure forms two-way and multi-way tables and provides a variety of tests and measures of association for two-way tables. Crosstabs' statistics and measures of association are computed for two-way tables only. If you specify a row, a column, and a layer factor (control variable), the Crosstabs procedure forms one panel of associated statistics and measures for each value of the layer factor (or a combination of values for two or more control variables). For example, if GENDER is a low factor for a table of MARRIED (yes/ no) against LIFE (is life exciting, routine, or dull), the results for a two-way table for the females are computed separately from those for the males and printed as panels following one another.

Note: Since this study deals with medical pluralism and the health seeking behavior more emphasis have been given to the qualitative data collection, micro analysis – taking family or a couple as a unit, then gone to other social units. These methods will give us a better “emic” view of the health seeking behavior and other aspects connected with the ethno medical scene in the studied samples. These include diagnosis and nosology (classification), etiology and therapeutic procedures etc. Emphasize is also given to variations in health seeking behavior within a village or a given rural population.

M. OPERATIONALIZATION OF VARIABLES

a. Dependent Variables

Here the health-seeking behavior has been considered as a dependent variable. The description of health seeking behavior in this study is an action, in which the respondents take to deal with the first illness/sickness that can be recognized by

disease within the previous six months. In the questionnaire illness and sickness and the concept of good health, selection of therapies have been separately dealt. Each of these issues is connected with its own method of handling respectively. There are many alternatives for people to choose the health services that are divided into four categories: 1. Traditional 2. Western 3. Folk 4 others

b. Independent variables

The socio-economic, demographic, and illness treatment variables have been considered as an independent variables which can possibly be affected on health seeking behavior of any person;

- Age
- Sex
- Marital Status (Married/ Unmarried)
- Education
- Income
- Occupation'
- Social network etc

c. Illness Treatment Variables

Illness treatment variables have been focused on these Three issues

1. Reason for Choosing Illness Treatment

This variable refers to the first main reason for choosing a type of treatment when dealing with first illness that can be identified from the disease;

- Belief including self-treatment/traditional healers etc
- Economic reason including Govt. hospital/untrained physician/cost
- Quality of service including quality of the hospital/treatment /doctor

2. Degree of Severity including mild sickness, severe sickness, get well by do not take, sick from deformities not infected, treat specific diseases etc.

3. Decision-Making for Illness Treatment

This variable refers to the situation that the person makes the decision for treatment when dealing with first sickness which can be identified by disease. There are three categories: did not participate in making decision, making own decision, and join with others.

N.GENERAL PARAMETERS EXAMINED;

1. Local concepts of health and illness (cultural definition of ill health)- what is being healthy and being sick;
 2. Classification of illness from the native point of view (humoral imbalance, superhuman causation, immoral behavior, punishment for deeds done in the previous generation, natural causation, caused by bacteria and vectors, fate, etc.);
 3. Local knowledge about various diseases (that are common in the area) and their causation;
 4. Indigenous healing practices and indigenous practitioners and their operation;
 5. Beliefs about the effects of various foods on the human body- including classification of foods as "hot" and "cold"
 6. Foods consumed by various age and sex categories and their assumed effects;
 7. Nutrition during pregnancy and after the birth of a child;
 8. Sickness according to the age and gender of the patients;
 10. The beliefs of the natives about the effectiveness of folk medicine and modern medicine;
 11. Patterns of interaction between folk healers and modern medical practitioners;
 13. What kinds of training are possible for the indigenous practitioners (local midwives, folk healers, etc.) so that modern medical ideas and practices can be introduced in culturally acceptable ways?
 14. What are local beliefs and health care practices that are in vogue that can be utilized in promoting good health?
 15. What are cultural barriers and facilitators for the introduction of modern health care supplies and services?
 16. Government efforts and reaching these populations with respect to health care;
- ETC**

O.DE-LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

It is assumed that the present study has some following limitations;

- Inadequacy and insufficiency of available data. The present data available may not only insufficient but also inadequate in providing a more or less accurate description of the health seeking behavior/culture because;

- It was restricted to the only few selected villages in each district;

Respondents' opinion may be or may not be completely true or false;

- As a result the generalizations arrived at by using the available data may not applicable to all the social categories or villages of the state;
- Other problems were associated with the theoretical content derived by applying divergent prospective (I, e marxist, and socialist, postmodern) to the study and analysis of the situation of changing rural health culture at the micro and macro level;
- Possible methodological error.

P.NEED FOR THE CURRENT STUDY

Today the majority of rural people are suffering from various communicable and non communicable diseases. It is stated there is a positive correlation between the health status of the rural people and their social, economical and cultural health practises. Over the last few decades, various Indian governments have developed few policies to achieve long term goals to provide a compressive health care programme for the rural people, and have increasingly emphasized the more immediate need to provide essential basic primary health care and scientific management of rural the rural population's traditional system.

The first one is sociology and medicine which focuses the contribution of sociological knowledge to the diagnosis and treatment options to cure disease/illness. Next, sociology of medicine focusing on the sociological study of the medical profession. An in-depth study of health culture of any rural folk will help in understanding the complete knowledge of etiology, onset of health, disease, healing etc.

As far as an organic linkage with the rural health is concerned, there is no basic service for a comprehensive health intervention attempt to understand the rural health culture as a sub culture complex in developing a model of culturally suited health care delivery system especially for the rural people of the country. Very little work, however, has entailed an in-depth analytical study of comparative emic perspectives of different factors influencing rural people's health behavior in Karnataka-India. This current research has built on recent social science efforts to contribute to filling that gap in the present understanding of impacts of various changing internal and external factors influencing the existing health culture and in shaping health seeking behavior of rural people in the selected villages of Karnataka.

Further, this study will help in the long term improvement of the health behavior of the targeted population and research findings will certainly helpful in developing a culturally compatible and acceptable developmental intervention strategy at the grass root level for both the Government and NGOs.

The data may be directly relevant to the three major user groups;

- a) Government, International Agencies and NGOs working for rural health issues;
- b) Agencies involved in health -oriented programmes like nutritional health care and immunization programme;
- c) Agencies and institutions mainly focusing on the universalisation of health care, NRHM, public health development and other executive agencies.

Q.SOCIOLOGICAL SIGNIFICANCES OF THE PRESENT STUDY

The explicit study of health in sociology (Medical Sociology) has a long history. Sociologists have long pointed out the implication of prevailing socio-economic conditions on the health seeking behavior of the rural folk. It is well known fact that culture is inseparable from the human behavior. Generally Sociologist/Anthropologist's views health culture as an attribute of the social life of human beings. Medicine and society are the centrally focused concepts in medical Sociology/medical Anthropology. Since cultural is an integrated functional unit of a society, Sociologists/Anthropologist's tries to find out how health problem is interlocked with the local culture issues. Sociologists who are working on health development programmes have produced adequate theories and research methodologies dealing with the processes of change in the health seeking behavior of the rural people that are vitally important in framing new theories and health policies.

Further, it can be noted that due to the influence of changing socio-economic pattern, political issues, awareness, particular health culture will get framed and reframed continuously. To reveal the psycho-sociological compliant of health culture first we need to take into account of the overall culture of the community. It is known fact that certain cultural practices it-self creates certain health disorders. Certain cultural practices of the community will get either by the diffusion or may be the own local innovation. Social science in general and Sociology in particular play a vital role in understanding of both qualitative and quantitative changes in the various domains of health culture of the rural people. This empirical study will come out with the new and unique findings and contributes to the theoretical understanding prevalent in the concerned domains of the subject to fill the research gaps.

An in-depth sociological study has acquired a greater relevance to the present day health problem emphasizing on how community evaluates the risks in different adopted and acquired health behaviors and the therapies preferred (including medical pluralism) and why some rural people have been reluctant to use the modern medicines. It is also most important to know an extent to which how people are responding to the different health policies and programmes of both Government and NGOs. Differences in the changing attitude and outlooks regarding various health /illness disorders in rural societies are very important for any medical sociologists.

CHAPTER III
REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Research is a continuing process and it doesn't stop anywhere unless we conclude for the time being. Knowledge on health issue is growing rapidly today. Scholars, researchers will go on adding knowledge through their research findings for the centuries. Hence, the researcher has to survey the available literatures pertaining to his/ her topic and he/she must keep himself updated in his or her studied field of research. A review of literature is devoted for making a brief review of previous studies on the problem and significant previous findings on the topic under study. At present this review provides a summary of the current state of knowledge in the area of investigation, to understand the concepts relating to the present study on health dynamics of the rural people. Review of literature enlightens us about an appropriate methodologies, research designs, and techniques analysis etc used by the various researchers. It also explores the research gaps exist and how this present chapter is an attempt to fill that gap will be highlighted in this section. A review of available literature on health issues provides an understanding of the problem confronting the topic as a whole. Much has been written on the health issues from a different perspective but only a few from the sociological point of view. The review of existing literatures on the health culture and health behavior reveals that an extensive research is required to fill up some of the gaps related to changing different perspectives of the rural health problem. It is found that there is a rising socio-economic inequality between rural and urban population. Essential inequality in health care reimbursement between rural and urban is augmented by the fast but uneven economic expansion that rural India has witnessed in the last few years. This review of the literature related to the study provides 1. Studies relating to health status, consisting of studies related to the socio economic and other factors that determine the health status of rural people,. 2. Studies relating to health culture, health behavior 3. Studies relating to medical pluralism, consisting of different systems of medicine 4. Other related health studies focusing rural health issues.

Review of Literature

Rural health has been an interesting concept in sociology and medical anthropology since last few decades. Plenty of research work has been done on the health culture and health behavior of the rural people across the globe. However, in Karnataka very few studies have been done on this topic. For the first time noted Medical anthropologists Rever (1924), has done land marking work on the concept of health and illness of native people. Clements (1932) has done work on the basic concept of disease focusing black magic, sorcery, spirit intrusion etc in rural areas.

Ackerknecht (1942) has opined primitive medicines cannot be ignored as it composed of only Herbals, Chants, worship and beliefs. Moreover, we should not focus on the forms but we have to consider the place of a medicine occupied in the life of the rural or tribal people and how they will conceptualize illness. Karna (1976) has found normally rural people think diseases and illness causes due to combination of both external (supernatural) and internal conditions (Humeral) of the body. However, people rather than internal conditions strongly believe an external condition which is being influenced by the various supernatural powers in causing various types of disease/ illness. He further ascertained that people are showing gradual interest in accepting the modern medicine with many doubts!

Camaroff (1981) and Fortes (1976) have opined illness may be a type of disturbance of the human normal relationship with the nature as widely believed in much rural society. Also illness may be an issue of violation of normal and natural cultural order. Each and every community will have its own expatiations for the causing several illness/diseases. Response to this illness will be normalcy related to the structure and maintenance of a given social system. Medical phenomena may be an indication for the performance of the any social system.

Cockcroft.et.al (2004) has opined today the traditional healing system have been pushed to the marginal position and could not establish as the major health care system in most of the developing countries. Weaver and Miskevies (2004) have opined accessibility to the quality health care will depend on the physical and social resources in any rural areas. Taylor (2003) has opined that people with the low socio-economic status should be provided subsidized health care facilities first. Young and Garro (1982) have opined expenditure for the transport to access a good medical care also be a burden on the poor people. Mackiam (2003) has opined that “If we desire to shift the debate into new and supplementary fruitful arenas, this review reaches the conclusion that we need to develop a tool for understanding how populations engage

with health systems, rather than using health seeking behavior as a tool for describing how individuals engage with services”.

Murdock (1980) opines that the basic definition of illness and its effect on the health in the rural culture will be generally based on the broader concept of natural and super natural causation. Further, he said the concept of the natural causation among the rural people will be somewhat near to the modern medical theory including the theories of micro-organisms, psychological issue etc. In case of supernatural concept, diseases normally cause due to the intrusion of the various supernatural powers. This concept is non-significant to the modern scientific theories.

Mbiti (1987) and Ewruhdiakpor (2008) have opined majority of the rural people believe state of normal health exists due to the perfect co-ordination and the relationship between man and the environment. Authors have opined in African cosmology, spirits play a vital role in maintaining order of the society as widely believed. Due to the various reasons sometime spirits may get disturbed by the man and hence this is the reason why health related problems occur. Further, they have opined in African health culture, it is widely believed that all human beings should have a good relationship with the God/s and the spirits. Otherwise different health problems may occur either to an individual or to an entire village which would be a drastic.

Mechanic (1989) has opined that rural health behavior depends on how one experience and expresses his/her illness issue to others. Also he said it is necessary to reconsider about what illness is actually meant in a society and the changing relationship among different kinds of healers, medical systems and the patients’.

Whitaker (2003) opines Basic beliefs about health in majority cases derive from an approach to the personal management of the body that is not just reactive but also proactive. Author has examined a multifaceted field of health factors in relation to historical processes and a system of medical pluralism. He felt fast demographic and social changes over the past century have done an accommodation of very old medical beliefs to more new-fangled germ-oriented principles. A lasting belief in the permeability of the body leads to an emphasis on moderation in personal conduct to stop debilitation, whether by atmospheric insults, microbial infection, or modern-day miasmas such as pollution or additives in food. Author felt the idea of health itself is analyzed to show how biomedicine varies across societies and how historical processes have shaped modern cultural patterns and led to generational continuities

and differences in beliefs and behaviors. This information may also improve connections between patients and health care providers

Parsons and Fox (1952) have opined people believe illness is more as a type of deviance. Authors have opined that people believe illness causes due to violating various social norms mainly a type of punishment by the God. Hence, nature exercises natural control over reducing the rate of illness whenever required as opined by the rural people. They also firmly believe at-least theoretically about the closer relationship between illness ideology and the social control as believed by the rural folks. Also they have written extensively about human behavior in the diverse medical background and in addition, they opined that high rate of traditional health seeking behavior causes a big problem to the rural society in the long run.

Manning and Fabrega (1973) and Press (1978) and have found in their studies that factors like religion, caste and class structure, current social system play a role in determining the health behavior of a rural community. Further, they felt this issue contrasts sharply with the closeness of bio-medicine. They writes “discontinuous from an ordinary social process and is disobliging to substitute systems”.

Glick (1967) has opined healing practices in case of non-western cultural always go with the religious or caste aspects. Mechanical therapy will have a certain sort of magico-religious elements. He opined rural people always think there are certain secrete factors involved in the etiology of an illness and they believe it is due to an affect of the supernatural powers and causes due to their ‘fate only’. Further he opined, healing techniques of the rural and tribal society will be normally based on the magic-religion means. Rural people visit PHC’s if there is no solution in their local traditional medicines and people only use the modern medicine if health problems are really serious and disturbing their normal routine work.

Landy (1977) found that interface between the ecosystem and socio-cultural system which is regional specific play a vital role in shaping the local health culture. People’s perception of illness and their therapeutic practices and preferences depends on the type of severity and social relations with the medicine. Also he states that rural people’s concepts about various preventive measures are closely linked to the other aspects of their daily social life.

Martinson (2011) opined A patient’s option between the pluralities of health services is incomplete to the point of being deemed as completely forbidden as opposed to structurally limited. Due to such radical structural constraints, some experts have argued medical pluralism to be an illusion in that all medicinal practices, in a

contemporary capitalist society, are just varying manifestations of the homogenous leading industrialist medicine.

Seymour –smith (1986) noted that symbols of healing are the symbols of the power. By analyzing the ‘semantic networks around illness terms within these two traditions, the authors have shown that the inner experience of symptoms and signs is well connected to the outer and the shared psychosocial factors, facilitating cultural and medical reply that optimize circumstances for normalcy’. Evans-pitchard (1937) has provided the common philosophy for explaining the health misfortunes. He described the health beliefs and practices using a conceptual framework targeting other aspects of the social structures and social relations to be studied first among the developing societies. Frank (1963) has described the factors that can play a vital role in changing the health behavior focusing various social factors. He also stressed on the faith healing, psychotherapy and curing ceremonies that can affect the health status of the patients’. Minocha (1974) argues that there are numerous links between the medicine and the society. She says sociologists in India have neglected sociology of medicine as a field of study. She demonstrated Sanskritisation, Universalisation, Parochialisation and stigma are useful to describe component of medicine like other social elements.

Next numbers of studies have examined the traditional medicines and their connections to the other system of medicine each with a distinct prospective and have shown that how social transformation has led to have different health behavior (Bala, 1991; Langford, 2004; Naraindas, 2004). Next, Das, (2003) have opined that patients’ anxiety regarding the suitable treatment to get control over the body again need to be stressed. More awareness among the rural community about the healthy life style has brought some sort of drastic change in case of health care seeking behavior. People are now more interested about the healthy life through practicing self care today.

Opler (1963) in his finding opined rural community normally believe problems such as diseases illness, drought etc all are cause due to the evil spirits, angry deities’ and the displeased ancestors. Village people think if any one of them breaches the taboo or failed in observing morals, the deity may permit evil powers to enter into the villages to teach a lesson. To overcome this problem, villagers will perform various rituals to satisfy the various deities. Also he opined folk minded people are very slow in accepting the new medicines because it would differ from their own culture and would be brand new phenomena to their perception.

Hassan (1967), in his findings has found Two types of socio-cultural factors affecting the health of rural community. He writes

1. Certain beliefs, values, practices, customs, taboos will help the rural community in spreading or controlling certain diseases. It is true that in some cases rural people are unknowingly protecting themselves from the various diseases.

2. There are certain socio-cultural factors which indirectly affects the health behavior of the rural community. A physician practicing modern medicine in a village should mind and respect all these cultural facts. Otherwise he/she cannot be a successful doctor in a village setting. Modern doctors should treat the village patients' through the local culture and traditions as much as possible.

Kakar (1977) has opined in case of Indian villages, normally people's concept about diseases and illness evolves from the history of a family, village, influence of the indigenous healers, the position of the elderly people and the ecological settings. All these factors play a vital role in shaping given health culture in the society.

Khatua (2001) based on his study has classified illness in to these categories as widely believed in rural parts;

1. Illness by the super natural power;
2. Illness by the magical route;
3. Illness due to breaching taboos;
4. Illness due to the ecological change;
5. Illness by the pathogenic;
6. Illness by other means

George (1981) has consolidated through his study about course of illness among the rural people

- Angry deities punishing human beings for doing wrong;
- Angry ancestors for being forgetting them;
- Spirit possession or evil eye on the human body;
- Loosing balance of the body fluids because of heavy heat and cold food/climate

Hallowell (1963) has opined that occurrence of illness due to misconduct by the human being may be a kind of social control by the nature and the vital aim of the people's concept about etiology and healing is a type of sanction and support moral and social systems. Even today in many non-western societies people will feel illness as a consequence of the sin which is a major social sanction (Tribhuwan ,1999; Polgar ,1968 ;Crombie,1969).

Mechanic (1978) has given Ten decision points which determine illness behavior in rural settings.

1. Primary symptoms of illness
2. Individual's experience of system security
3. How illness is disturbing the patients'
4. Frequency of systems
5. How patient is coping with the illness
6. How patient perceives illness focusing his/her cultural background
7. Denial of illness
8. Illness disrupts needs
9. Alternative interpretation about his/her illness problem
10. Decision making about choosing a suitable treatment option.

Murdock (1980) and Shweder (1987) have found that explanation for illness in rural society will be basically bounded by psycho-social and spiritual rather than biological. Sometime in the rural societies people believe illness is due to the various social, cultural and psychological factors but surprisingly they will go for the western medicine for treatment!. Rural people strongly believe about cosmological forces causing various disease/illness for the variety of reasons. The cognitive domain of a patient will play a vital role in believing causes for health and illness and choosing a specific form of health care system in time to cure any health problems.

Swain (1994) has examined the perceptions of illness and diseases prevailing among the different social groups in rural India. He said social and cultural factors of the family like caste, class gender are the most vital factors in shaping the health culture and health behavior of the rural and tribal people. This is happening because illiteracy, isolation, remoteness, lack of unfaith on the modern medicine etc.

Singh (1994) has opined following factors strongly influence on health and illness including in rural part including

1. Natural element forces

2. Social and economic conditions
3. Dietary pattern
4. Psychological factors
5. Success of traditional medicines
6. Medical pluralism
7. Role of external agencies etc

He concludes that the traditional medical system should be scientifically upgraded so that rural people can accept the modern medicine.

Tribhuvan (2004) has written rural community widely believes disease and illness is due to the malfunctioning of the psycho-social process. Rural people strongly believe in spirits, cosmology and their role within the routine social system causing illness and diseases. Hence, rural people strongly believe in the ritual healings for the correctional process. However, in recent times some sections of the rural community believing micro organisms causing various health problems for a variety of reasons. This is a notable change among the rural people. Also he states that techniques used by the traditional healers need in-depth scientific study.

Brody (1987) & Sacks (1993) have opined the patients' illness narrations played a significant role from the clinical point of view. Any type of healer (traditional/western) should spend more time with the patient to listen his/her illness story and his version of the health problem. This kind of narration may be helpful for the doctors in diagnosing the problem accurately as soon as possible and the proper treatment also. Sometime due to the communication problems, doctors could not diagnose the health problem accurately. Also insufficient/incorrect illness narrations of the patients' may generally create some sort of misunderstanding between the physician and patient including treatment pattern also.

Lars- Christer Hyden (1997) has given five vital uses from the illness narrations. They are;

1. Formation of a world of illness from the patients' personal illness story
2. Will be helpful in complete understanding of the illness concept of the patient
3. Will be helpful to having a personal life history due to illness
4. Will be helpful to learn strategies to heal the malady

Toombs (1988) found due to illness, patients' may lose his/her functionality. It causes an imperative impact on the patient day to day life. He may feel a breakdown of his/her relationship with the rest of the world. At this moment illness narratives will be helpful to reconstruct the events that the patient had gone through due to an illness. The author debates that every medical system composed of several beliefs and the practices associated with the some hidden logics. Bury (1991), opines chronic illness will be a kind of distraction in anybody's normal life. Chronic illness may leave significant impact changing patient's relationships with the outside world. Moreover, it may alter the current status or identifying an individual in the society in a different way. Narrating once own illness experience would be a vital issue in medical sociology for an in-depth study about the health culture of the rural people.

Schneider (1976) has opined that few hidden symbols and meanings associated with an illness experience to restore the health of a patient in the true sense has been constructed from the beliefs, experiences, performances and culturally held perceptions in case of rural settings. Adams (1955) in one of his study in a Guatemalan Indian village has cited an interesting example. He found in that village, people were used to believe when a person lose blood that person will lose his resistance power gradually. Hence, sometime doctors who were collecting blood for the lab testing purpose may not succeed in their effort in many rural hospitals. This also delays the diagnosing process substantially.

Frake, (1961) has opined in his article about division of illness has said basically folk people will divide illness into Two identifiable classes;

1. Illness which can be cured by the local traditional healer
2. Illness that can be cured only by the modern medicine

Mrinal (1994) has analyzed the magic-religious beliefs and practices in rural part. He said various healing practices are diminishing because of 'acculturation'. However, he felt the health culture of the rural people is also getting changed. External agencies are playing a decisive role in bringing such changes in rural parts. Also he opined that the NGOs can make a vital role in the changing health culture and behavior of the rural people. However, NGOs should take rural people to their confidence first. And there should be no harm to their basic social and cultural beliefs on health and illness. All programmes must be socially and culturally specific and it is the need of the hour.

Studies conducted by Rizvi (1991) Bhattacharya (1995) Das (1986), Basu (1995) Mhapatra (etd.) (1990) Khan (1986) Sinha (1996) have written some classic papers on the concept of disease, healing, and the health behavior of the rural people by

conducting the field work in various rural settings across the country. They have cited various reasons for the causes of diseases and illness as widely believed among the rural folks including;

1. Humeral Imbalance
2. Angry deity
3. Agony of super natural powers
4. Pathogeneses
5. Failed in observing moral and ethics in life
6. Breaching taboos
7. Not celebrating festivals
8. Not observing usual code of conduct
9. Others

Lewis (1958) has written “some advantages in learning about the beliefs and practices of the rural community are the insight they give into the world view of the people as concepts of disease causation are part of societies total world view”. He asserted that rurals’ unique theory of etiology, healing techniques, role of shaman (local healer) needs to be studied as how it affects on the health behavior of the common rural folk.

Kopparty (1994) has written about the social stratification and healthcare in a rural community from the sociological perspective. He opined that the social stratification has more influence on the type of health behavior, health action and the morbidity pattern etc. This study has found that social stratification has a critical role in understanding the health practice and health behavior of the rural community. Hassan (1979) has opined different sociological factors like caste; class etc affecting the rural health culture and behavior needs be properly addressed. Also he opined that the health behavior and the health culture of the rural people must be studied only ‘before and after introducing the western health care system’. This result need some sort of comparison and based on that result only new and innovative health policies can be framed for the rural health development in the country.

Sermsri (1999) writes in rural areas “sometime people would like to combine treatment pattern , taking herbal medicine in conjunction with the western pharmaceutical drugs”. Oska & Nankorn (1996) have opined people in rural Thailand will opt the self medication in the majority cases. Before approaching the modern

health care people use “weight & see” technique here. Herbal medicine will be used more in case of self medication in the rural parts of the Thailand. Akin and Hutchinson (1999) writes in Srilanka even the poor people normally don’t choose the traditional health care because of the low quality and low cost. Rather, they would like to visit quality hospitals irrespective of distance/cost factors to get a quality health care treatment. Author calls it as ‘bypassing in health care facility choice’. Holcomb (1996) opines in certain cases medical pluralism ‘exists as a relationship to both individual spirituality and group identity in rural areas’. Hahn and Kleinman (1983) have opined that ‘modern medicinal system itself participates equally in culturally based epistemological structure and hence does not essentially challenge the ‘exotic’.

Elliott-Schmidt and Strong (1997) write

“Attitudes to health and illness may vary between rural and urban dwellers. Issues that may relate to the provision of health services to rural dwellers are raised for consideration. The reply of urban dwellers to illness or disability has often been linked to uneasiness caused by pain or cosmetic attractiveness, while for rural dwellers the answer to illness or disability is often related to the degree to which the illness or disability affects productivity. Often the rural resident will postpone seeking medical or associated services until it is economically or socially convenient” (Elliott-Schmidt R, and Strong J.,1997).

Frake (1961, has given five facts about diagnose and treatment for disease/illness.(quoted)

1. ‘Normally people use cognitive structure to have a specific health behavior;
2. People will be disagreeing while diagnosing or identifying a problem based on actual symptoms;
3. People will try to avoid the name of the illness to be published because of fear of future stigmatization ;
4. There is a relationship between organizing sick behavior and other phenomenological domains;
5. People may use sickness as a medium for pursuing other interests’.

Frankenberg and Young (1990) opined that sickness is a total sum of the behavioral and biological signs for socially recognizable meanings to the world. Sickness is a kind of symptom of etiology for legitimizes outcomes. Further, they said illness is a way of socializing disease and sickens. It helps the healer to adopt a

suitable approach to solve the health problem. Further, they said each sickness has its' own consequences on the life of an individual and the society as well.

Taussig (1980) has critically opined that due to the serious illness a patient may turn into a philosopher. Serious illness may disturb the everyday life of a patient. The Author has also opined the doctors should not separate the health issue from the values, norms, and ethics of the patients' life. All health issues are socially co-exists. He has criticized how the medical knowledge has been a means of social control and the human body has become an experimental entity for testing new medicines. Also he said the modern doctors have become the agents for the rich people who control the social order and the wealth.

Debabar (1989) found that the rapid social transformation including social and economic changes among the rural people is playing a vital role in the changing health behavior and culture of the rural masses. Basu (1998) has opined that various cultural factors practicing by the low socio-economic groups in the rural parts play a vital role in changing their health culture. He also felt process of sanskritization is also a main responsible factor in this phenomenon. Menon (2000) has opined that utilization rate of the modern health services among the rural people is low because of the ignorance, lack of awareness, health illiteracy, low level of participation etc. People for that reason are not even interested to get free western health care available in the local PHC/SC. It seems village people have taken the health issue for granted and not considered health is a vital subject in their life course.

Guptha (2008) has found that today traditional healers are totally out of the scene in some villages . Actually, villagers simultaneously follow medical pluralism techniques. Institutional interventions operating in the form of PHCs, Aanganwadi centres. CHCs (community health centers) and some schemes like Janani Suraksha Yojna (for safe baby delivery), Mobile hospitals and presence of more private doctors are more popular among the rural people today. Nevertheless, some of the pertinent doubts which arise out of this conclusion relates to the sincerity and commitment on the part of PHCs and CHCs, its resourcefulness as well as availability of modern facility in these hospitals without having any problems for the local people on time. The paper suggests an integration of indigenous and the modern health care system for an effective healthcare management mechanism in rural pars of the country.

Bose and Desai (1983) have given pathetic health conditions of rural community. Poor socio-economic conditions, lack of awareness, poor sanitation, and

absence of potable water, lack of medical education and health resources, cultural taboo, and minimum interface of external agencies poor modern medical infrastructure are some of the reasons for poor health outcomes of the rural community. Also they say it is a great task to bring rural folk into the domain of modern medicine.

Hitchcock and Minturn (1963) have conducted a study in Maharashtra villages. They found that village folk are more focusing on hot and cold concept of food relating to their health or illness. People normally will classify the certain food item as cold and some are hot. In general people are of the opinion that food hot in nature causes more health problems. Hence, the rural people have the seasonal dietary from a century. Ramachandran (2000) and Kate (2000) have found some interstate variations focusing tribal and rural health in India. They have given some notion that the rural people are more or less ignorant about genetic disorders. Besides rural people are having the general and geographical specific health problems in the country. He felt more health awareness programmes and the low cost health care system for the rural people is required urgently.

Tribhuvan (1933) has opined ritual healing is historically and culturally framed procedure as a part of the health seeking behavior through which a patient 'had to pass through' to get healed. This ritual healing composed of therapies like herbal, magico-ritual, chanting, spraying holy water etc. Specific types of ritual healings will be performed depending on the communities' perception about the origin and cause of illness with due respect to the socio-cultural process of the healing settings. He felt 'scientifically it is found that any healing techniques which will be performed to heal the patient normally would contain shared meanings which are symbolically converted through the medium of ritual performance'.

Further it is revealed that social reinforcement focusing traditional belief also a vital role in choosing a variety of medical care. In rural areas illness viewed through social phenomena. It is opined that today rural people are showing, much interest in choosing more than one type of medicinal system to cure any type of health problems. Some people will not even bother about the cost factors. It is also opined that Govt. and, NGOs should try to provide the modern health care facility to the rural people through the local culture.

Lamba and Metha (1990) have written the impact of any medicine on illness depends on ;

1. Degree and concealed potentialities of causing illness;

2. Various reasons for illness ;
3. Biological and social disorders due to the onset of definite kind of illness.

Djurfeldt and Lindberg (1978) have opined Maternal and child health care is very poor in rural settings and poor nutrition causes more damages to the health of the rural people. Rural health behavior is less depending on ecology. Today rural people prefer to have any rapidly healing medicinal system. Only during the serious stage people will follow the allopathic medicinal system. Next, Kroeger (1983) and Twumasi (1987) have opined illness cases due to disturbance with the spiritual environment headed by the sorceress, evil spirits etc., as believed by the large rural masses. Normally people may not get health problems accidentally; rather it causes due the cosmological powers. Basically, rural people believe, virus, bacteria etc., are the secondary causes of illness. The authors have written that it is the general question of the rural people like microorganisms one or two individuals in a village should suffer from sickness /disease and why some time all masses will suffer at a same time?.

Joshi (2012) has found that the high mortality among rural females during childbirth, and high child death rate is due to purely cultural reasons. Also some time deaths are occurring due to even from preventable diseases, like Malaria, Jaundice and Diarrhea, etc. Rural people are in a sorry state of affairs with respect to the availability and effectiveness of the modern health care facilities. Besides poor geographical accessibility, access, affordability and low education and lower awareness levels, corruption among the Govt. Health functionaries, together with mismanagement and inadequate coordination between different parts of the health care delivery system, are largely responsible for the miserable state of health of rural masses today. He opined that in a vacuum the any health programmes cannot achieve the target. This calls for the formulation and implementation of health schemes in relation to other development measures focusing rural people.

Ruger (2010) has given an approach that health care facility must be balanced regarding health decision making between internal factors (patient) and external factors (social determinants). It is very vital to give maximum and different health care options to the patient to take a final and appropriate decision to cure his/her health problems. Matsuokr and Aigaetal (2009) have found some barriers like physical, cognitive, formal organizational playing a vital role in shaping the health seeking behavior in case of rural masses. Next, Mackam (2003) has opined that focus must be in the result of interaction among the patient, society and the health care system focusing rural areas. It is also found that household decision will play a vital

role in getting the best health care available in that area. However this would be partially influenced by the various social determinants' too.

Zborowski (1953) in his writing has explored how different cultural groups feel about 'pain'. Some cultural groups accepted 'pain' as a normal illness process. Whereas some felt it is an unacceptable phenomenon and they may go for any type of clinical solution. Another given example is that in Poland women accepts pain during delivery as a normal one. However, in US women during delivery may ask for pain killers. He concludes that not all cultural groups may tolerate different pain or show interest in using pain killer medicines. Poliakoff (1993) has opined that some people will be ready to face any pain. In Hindu tradition people think pain is a physical aspect and it is due to the sin committed in the previous birth. Chinese people have some reservations in using any type of pain killers. The Author has concluded that response to the pain will be largely depending on the emotions and cultural background of a particular social group.

Wilkinson (2001) has conducted few studies in Cambodia and found that (quoted);

1. HSB depends on socio-economic, psycho- social and economic problem;
2. People are not so much aware about modern medicine;
3. Traditional perspective about illness and disease still exists in large;
4. People some time wait for the natural healing of illness;
5. The local traditional healer has a decisive role;
6. Generally home remedy /self medication would be the first choice.

Khun and Maderson (2007) have opined that some time choosing a specific type of healthcare will depend on the degree of severity of disease/ illness in rural parts. Also it depends on cost for the treatment and faith on the healer, and patient's previous experiences with that of a particular healer. However, for women health problem, people normally prefer home remedies. It is a kind of gender bias mostly common in the rural parts. Yanegisawa and Mey (2004) have opined that in rural parts, for all types of health problems home remedies would be the first choice. Some time self medications including 'over the counter medicine' also increasing today in rural parts. This would be due to the changing socio-cultural reason and some time may be just to 'take a chance'.

Coton (2008) opined that mental health problem is not at all considered in the rural parts an issue. Even people are not much aware about the various mental health issues suffering in their everyday life. Even today people normally use traditional and

religious (faith healing) health care system to deal with the various types of mental problems. He has suggested to opening mental health clinics in the rural areas. Singh and Palak (2012) made an attempt to explore the linkages between the larger issues of socio-economic, political and ecological factors with the accessibility, affordability and availability of health services to understand the maternal and child health problems among rural women. The authors write ‘given the complex intertwining among so many issues involved in rural health care, the entire gamut of rural health issues poses challenges for the social scientists as well as health workers especially in the context of mainstream development process’. This paper concluded with a retrospective note that rural health issues have to be examined within the context of an interdisciplinary perspective so as to make it more viable from theoretical as well as practical points of view.

Iwelunmor (2013) opines work done using application of the PEN-3 cultural model (PEN-3 cultural model is a theoretical framework that centralize ‘culture’ in the study of health) has a good result for the developing society. Author felt this model also place culture at the core of development, implementation, and evaluation of health interventions to address health behaviors through a cultural lens. Few experts felt very culture has something positive, something unique, and some-thing negative for nay health issues. Together, these factors are essential to eliminating inequities in health among margins and improving the mission of public health behavior .

Kshatriya and Kapoor (2005) write “Over the past fifty years important development has been achieved in the circumstance of economic, social and demographic attributes of India. Nonetheless, there still exists a strong inter-regional demographic discrepancy. Varied social and cultural distinctiveness of Indian population are main causal factors to such a diverse demographic situation in addition a lot of others. Furthermore, inequalities maintain to continue in the sphere of health care delivery system. The health programme requires special concentration in the framework of rural communities of India because of their settlements in difficult areas and conditions. Health, nutrition and medico-generic troubles of diverse rural social groups inhabiting extensively varying geo-climatic conditions present a formidable challenge for effective health care delivery. Correspondingly, the ordinary beliefs, customs and practices connected with health and disease are familiarly associated with the treatment of disease” (Kshatriya and Kapoor , 2005).

Parson (1951) has opined that illness as deviance and rurals’ sick role is connected to structuralism and functionalism issues of the society. The sick role behavior is to be studied with respect to changing socio economic factors due to globalization and its

effect on rural health culture . Singh (2007) has opined concept of health or illness even though it's culturally bounded it largely intertwined with the other developmental process of the society. He says since rurals'/ tribal's are not more aware of their body composition they largely relay on the cosmological powers. Hence, some time new medical technology comprehended to the rural people because of structural hurdles in the new technology is to be accepted by the policy makers.

Sultan (2011) has written about faith healing. She said people widely believe faith healing system that will play a vital role in curing and preventing disease with the divine blessing of the creator [God] psychologically. Spirituality and religion is the base core of this system. People think faith healers can speak directly with the various cosmological powers in the curing session/rituals. The theory underlying in this type of healing is 'healing of soul through the body and mind'. Next, Melinowski (1948) has given a major contribution to understand the health seeking behavior of individuals. He opined that people will get medical or non-medical treatment based on their social and cultural background. He wrote 'Individuals may have control over their illness in more than one frame of references in understanding illness & its curing'. Albrecht, (2011) opined if the formal medical system failed in curing their illness or if rural people don't have faith on the formal medical institutions naturally people will go for the traditional medical institutions to get treatment. Here strong faith, confidence and self belief works a lot in choosing a particular type of health care system.

Mechanic's (1978) general theory incorporates ten decision points which determine illness behavior: **(quoted)**

- 1) "deviant signs and symptoms;
- 2) The individual's perception of symptom severity;
- 3) Disruption of the individual's daily life as caused by the illness;
- 4) Frequency of symptoms and their persistence;
- 5) Individual's tolerance of symptoms;
- 6) Individual's knowledge and cultural assumptions of the illness;
- 7) Denial of illness as a result of basic needs;
- 8) Whether or not response to the illness disrupts needs;
- 9) Alternative interpretations" **(quoted)**

Ahmed (2000) opined that medical pluralism exist in a single cultural system. Availability of more than one type of the healing system (homecare to modern /western) at the door steps have become a common phenomenon in the rural society

today. Severity of the health problem and duration of illness also counts a lot while choosing a specific type of treatment. Attitude of the medical care provider and satisfaction of the patients' also a vital role in the success and failure of any type of formal medical care system today.

Scheff (1966) has worked on 'negotiation of medical works and identify'. He opines medicalization is quite rampant in each every stage of health care system. Modern doctors are playing with innocent rural people by exploit them like anything to gain monetary benefits. Paul (1955) has opined that rural community will expose to the outside world mainly in Two contexts. 1. When external agencies (like NGOs and other) will get into the village with the aim of creating awareness about health care and 2. when the rural people migrate to the urban or semi urban areas for variety of reasons. Only through these two channels rural people will get more information's about various health issues and the modern treatment for the various health problems.

Goyal (1990) has raised certain questions about community participation in rural health care . He argues policy makers should have previous idea about what kind of community participation is needed in universalizing the primary health care focusing rural folk?. Also he opined study is needed to find out why various programmes brought to the rural masses have not succeeded invoking their interest in the modern healthcare. And what kind of other efforts required to get more rural participation in the various health care plans.

Fuch (1964) has made some classic studies in certain central Indian villages'. He opined the local healers have created an influence on the rural community in such a way that people will strongly believe the healers and their supernatural powers and their vast experience. He found that the local healers use certain techniques like finger pulling, measuring with grass-stalks to diagnose different types of diseases. Latter on healers identify the deity responsible for an illness/disease and asks the patients' to offer required offerings in the form of cash/kind to satisfy the deity/sprits. Also healer use some techniques and manipulation to denote inquiry about the future events in the case of a patient.

Giri (2012) highlights the role of culture, tradition and indigenous knowledge in the management of health and nutrition among the rural people. The author is of the view that absence of comprehensive and well-structured modern health management institutions are the major issues for the poor health status. Next, he opened not only old age definitions of health and disease, but traditional beliefs regarding pregnancy, birth, health ceremony, child caring and nurturing, taking care of old age people, the

subject of death etc counts a lot with respect to the health culture of the rural people. Next, the author also noticed the gender disparity in all aspects contributing to poor health status of women in many rural parts of the country today. Finally, the paper underlines some suggestions to translate the goals of the National Health Mission into action for qualitative improvement in health and nutritional status of rural folk soon.

Lessa and Uogt (1965) have given certain explanations about the power of a Shamans' and Priests' in healing scenario in various rural social settings. Shamans' claim they have got supernatural powers through deviation, whereas the Priests' claim they have got supernatural power 'through codified and standardized knowledge'. Also authors have opined traditional healers and faith healers play a vital role in diagnosing early health problems and Govt. should utilize their service.

Duggal (1994) has found in rural parts, people have certain believes about the hereditary problems

- Hereditary problems cause due to the side effects of modern medicines and various types of pollutions;
- Only traditional medicine has a solution for hereditary problems
- It is the fate of the patient;
- Hereditary diseases are purely communicable ;
- hereditary problems causes due to cosmology/ spirits effect;
- Causes due to internal damages

Joshi (2012) has examined an issue of breast feeding as a necessary precondition for the improvement in the health status of infants. He found various independent variables such as caste, religion, community, age at marriage, age of delivery, class, occupation and income in case of rural parts. The author has observed that because of canopy faith, tradition, and high level of illiteracy health status of infants in rural parts is under crisis today. In many families new mothers do not allow for breastfeeding for the first three days after the birth because they perceive new or first breast milk is not fit for the infants. This paper also examines the effects of the adoption of an early feeding of the supplement foods for the infants in the future. The author has concluded that ignorance regarding the breastfeeding and urgency in feeding supplementary food items are some of the vital reasons for the high infant mortality rate in the rural areas.

Sinha and Banerjee (2004) wrote;

“one may infer that magic, which craft , and sorcery are rooted in traditional customary ideas whereby societies categories and order the universe around them as such, they not only intertwined with every aspect of society, through and language but

also provide coherent and systematic means to influence the world in which man lives. For the anthropologists such belief systems provide essential and non-western standing of the structured aspects of customary thoughts”.

Bourguignon (1995) has opined the magical practice is a most vital element in the healing technique among the traditional healers dealing with diseases and illness of rural masses. In a very complex situation, traditional healers would use ‘combinations of magic, worship and mystical arts etc., to cure various health problems. In some cases, rather than adopting the magical healing, healers’ will go for a psychological healing tool’. The author opines that sometime it is highly impossible to logically view the rurals’, concepts etc. about disease and illness and reasons for the cause

Mukherji and Somayajulu (2004) have opined rural people need more aware of health education and they felt stress must be on

- Focusing concept about self hygiene;
- Household ecology;
- Proper local health education ;
- Using safe food and water;
- Usage of over the counter medicines;
- Quality service at PHCs/SCs;
- Overcome the barriers in accessing modern medicine

Malathi G. Nayak (2012) and others writes

“Sociologists have established that the spread of diseases is heavily prejudiced by the socioeconomic status of individuals, ethnic traditions or beliefs, and additional cultural factors. The pervasiveness and response to different diseases varies by culture. Sociologists agree that alcohol consumption, smoking, diet, and exercise are central issues, but they also see the importance of analyzing the cultural factors that affect these patterns. Social factors play a significant role in developing health and illness”.

Sujatha (2003) has written extensively about the medical lore (wisdom) of the village folks. She has opined that medical lore has been emerged as a part of people’s experience. It has both epistemological and ontological features. The core part of the medical lore has a vital connection between the health concepts and practices. She felt various health practice itself constructs medical knowledge in the society over a

period of time. Also a continuous practice creates novelties in the therapeutic pluralism. Rurals' medical lore is not a static, rather it is a dynamic. Over the period of time, important medial features will continue adding to the knowledge.

Trawick (1992) has opined that the medical pluralism is like without having any dichotomy. She has done an extensive study on Ayurvedic, Sidda, Unani, Trans healing etc., having a strong history of the Indian medical system. The author has distinguished these medical systems based on the basic concepts about illness, gender, curing, ritual healing system, death etc. Also she found that some common unique elements in Shiva and Sidda type of health system about the concept of death and the feminine ideal. Next, Dugger (1994) has opined that underutilization of modern health care facilities by the rural people is very common now a days. Because, various modern health agencies are not paying the required amount of attention towards the rural health problems including inconvenient locations and the time, failing to understand the rural ideology about modern health care services and the bias about the health care providers etc. He also further opined that modern health agencies have failed in understanding how rural social and economic factors are playing a vital role in accepting the modern health system.

Beals (1976) has found that rural people will accept the biomedical system if they have a strong personal network and exposure to various positions. Normally people show much interest in getting the cheapest medical system. Some time people show mush interest to get a treatment from the multiple medical systems simultaneously. Also people are not showing much interest to spend on the health needs of the aged people and women because of the various socio-cultural reasons. In rural parts more interest will be given to the health needs of the male members in the majority hosueholds

Cosminsky (1980) has found that the pluralistic medicine includes simultaneous usage of self remedies, indigenous drugs, visiting private ayurvedic/homeopathy/ naturopathy doctors etc. the Author has opined that the pluralistic health care system needs emphasis on how various components from the different medical systems are incorporated. Pfleiderer (1984) in his study has found that there will be some sort of continuing conflict between the parents' (father and mother) about choosing a particular type of medical care for their ill child if any. It would be a more problematic among the parents belonging to a different caste especially in rural parts. In this case, decision on choosing an appropriate health care system depends on the family history, tradition and modern outlook etc of the each parent. Bernstein (2001) wrote "health-care decision-making shows that members of

the community outlook a range of medical traditions as break up and non-competitive spear where the limitations are very thin and are continuously being negotiated and re-negotiated through dialogues”.

Karnyski, (2009) has examined an intersection of the ethno medical health care practices comparing with the allopathic health care system. She has concluded that people always would, like to take a chance with using more than one type of medicine for any specific types of diseases to get fast curing. Hence, more expenditure and the pain can be avoided in the future. Sundal (2009) has done work on the Karimojong community. She has opined that the social, political, and economic marginalization of Karamoja has shaped the poor distribution of the healthcare resources and the local concept of health and illness is vital in choosing modern/traditional health system.

Bith (2004) in his work has stressed on how village people in Sdaov village, (Cambodia) manage with health-seeking behaviors of AIDS patients’ with an importance of the cultural construction of AIDS. The author has shown how foreign aid impacts on the medical pluralism and health decision-making of the rural people. Also it focused on the types of socio-economic dilemma that put off the community from managing their personal lives. Johannessen, et.al (2006) have opined that the co-existence of the diverse therapeutic medicine should not be conceptualized as a separate and an autonomous socio-cultural system. It should be ‘viewed as networks that are formed at dissimilar levels and across different levels. The editor has doubted whether it is suitable to talk about the medical pluralism when a biomedical form of praxis is included into the native understandings of the person’.

Aggarwal (2001) has conducted a study on rural health infrastructure and found women patients’ don’t like to visit PHC’s because of non availability of female staff in PHCs in the rural part. Also he found in some villages PHCs/ ANMs (Auxiliary Nurse Midwife) are over burdened. In addition, he said if a Doctor is absent some time a pharmacist will prescribe some medicines where rural people afraid to use such medicines. Johl and Sharma (2008) has opined that the usage of the modern medicines by the rural people normally depend on various issues like the distance factors, personal attention by the health staff, availability of the free medicine in the hospitals, availability of the lady staff, keeping the personal health problems secrete, convenient time etc., If they satisfied with all these issues then they show interest to use modern health care modestly in the future too.

Guptha (1999) in his study has revealed that in rural areas, distance factor from the home to the hospitals plays a vital role. He also mentioned that rude behavior of

the medical staff, long waiting hours, overcrowding at the hospitals also counts a lot. If the laboratory facility is not available, people will visit private hospitals only. Though, the Government is spending a lot on improvement of the primary health care still rural hospitals are facing infrastructure, manpower, shortage of medicines like problems even today.

Outwater, et. al (2001) has opined that the traditional healers have mixed opinions about their knowledge and accepting the modern medicines. In majority cases traditional healers are not ready to get the modern training in diagnosing different kinds of diseases. In addition Govt. should insist training mandatory so that it will help in enhancing their scientific service to the underserved especially in rural areas. Yamasaki-Nakagawa et.al (2001) has found that in Nepal, women were more likely than men to visit the local healers for their health problems. Author felt more study is required to reveal why rural people choose the local healers or untrained/under trained allopathic doctors rather than the trained modern doctors in many cases. Evans and Lambert (1997) have opined rather than stressing on the health behavior, the health improvement scheme for the rural folk must be focused on reflecting actual decision making process in opting a treatment for any illness/disease. Also the authors have opined more community awareness is required about the modern medicine to fortify them for the better health outcomes rather than trying to change the health behavior of the individuals.

Further he opined local concepts about disease and illness are offers as orderly and a systematic as they are complex.

Corner and Norman (1996) have developed some noted social cognition model to predict the perceived pattern of health seeking and promoting behavior focusing demographic, cultural, history, and other cognitive factors. They conclude that there is a dearth need of understanding rural people's health perception through their ecological settings first. However, their models' have been criticized based on the various grounds and it is found that its applicability is not practically possible and need some more factual information's. Akram (2008) has opined that the health behavior is a part of social construction. Health orientation is neither fixed nor an inherent by birth. Usually human beings will born with an undirected health seeking behaviour which being gradually shaped by the various social experiences in a given direction. "Unlike what is perceived our health behavior and health culture does not unfold automatically from within" he felt.

Kleinman (1980:1981:1982) has rejected the popular biomedical model and gave his own interpretations. He says disease might be due to the dysfunctions of the organ system. Illness may include but not limited to a disease. It is simply a socially disvalued state of a particular person (patient). Regarding sickness, he has opined it may include both the disease and / or illness. Further, the author has explained how illness relates to psychosocial experiences. In addition he felt researcher's needs to concentrate on efficiency of medical pluralism/types of healings & more focus must be on illness narratives of the patient. Moreover, he has explained in details about the therapeutic interventions for each and every patient and its management. In addition through his other work he has given the finest concept about how healing is different from curing and how it differs from the culture to culture in the rural settings. He has given some vital notes also on 'somatic illness network' also.

Marriot (1955) in his classical study found the traditional medical system is not an impervious to the influence of modern medicine. Despite, the increasing modern medical care even in the under developing rural areas with consequent reduction in the prevalence of various types of diseases, traditional health care system still dominates in the rural area and play a vital role in influencing health decision of a community. He further asserted that while implementing the modern medicine a politico – economic issues and its inter-relationship with the human health should be focused.

Kakar (1972) has analyzed in his article about the village medical institutions and the role of a western doctor. He was primarily concerned about the relationship between village folks and the modern doctors. He opined expectations of the village patients' will be quite different and a western doctors can't fulfill some time and will just ignore and it negatively affects on the patient health behaviour or health culture.

Turner (1966) has found that illness is generally viewed focusing cleavage in the social solidarity. Normally the rural people think illness and diseases causes due to the breaching taboo and angry deity. Healing techniques adopted by the local healers will be largely based on the social ties. In the majority rural settings, beliefs and healing practices will be culturally and geographically specific. Hence, health related beliefs and practices are invariably related to the socio-cultural sphere of the rural life.

Chan (2011) has opined even today the educated rural people are mostly interested in using the evidenced based traditional medicines. It is not because of prioritizing over another. It is a workable co-existence among various system of medicines and dealing with in terms of norms, values, experience and preferences. In

some rural areas, even today more than one type of medicinal systems available in a parallel mode from the centuries. More important is that the cultural values that navigate the proper distinction among various medical systems to examine and optimize the health behavior of a rural patient. Lash (2002) has suggested that to understand the complexities of a particular health decision or action and how people weighing up the options, we should focus on reflexive communities (i.e. reflection of the social status of an individual or group in taking a specific way of behavior/decision making).

Polar (1962) in his study has concluded since etiology is outside of its socio-cultural domain perception on the onset of diseases will be a kind of reflection of the patients' experience being a core member of the society. Edmund Leach (1968) opined that ritual is a common ingredient in the health-culture of every society and 'it is a symbolic message that changes the meaning embedded to accomplish given tasks in the healing process'. Ward et.al (1996) opined from his study that the health seeking behavior is a kind of sequence of the healing procedure with the patients' to cure his/her health problems. Treatment options normally depend on the type of illness, severity, health beliefs of the patient, accessibility to the pluralistic therapy and their success rate etc.

Ackernecht (1971), was the pioneer in the study of ethno medicine and he has identified vital aspects and has described ethno medicine;

1. "Not only one, there are various ethno-medicine/primitive medicines exists ;
2. There is no such or much difference between various medical systems and their elements;
3. The degree of synchronization of various elements of medicine into the whole and of the 4.whole medicine into a specific cultural pattern varies significantly".

Barth (2002) has given Three divisions regarding disease knowledge of the rural /tribal people including;

1. Cosmology
2. Rituals
3. Religious tradition.

He also highlighted the role of ethno-psychology, human morality, super natural powers and their effects on health beliefs of rural people.

Kapferer (1996) opined that curing ceremonies are “Socially reconstituting and re-originating process”. Traditional healers actually try to restore the patient’s relationship to the meta-physical and social words which is a root cause of illness as they believe. Pramukh (2009) has explained better approaches of medical anthropology to study the folk medicine viz;

1. A cultural complex of material objects, tools, rituals, methods;
2. The network of relations among various social structures;

Author felt these approaches also help us to understand why certain social groups accepts the modern medicines and why other rejects?

Das (2009) has opined that the non-medical factors will influence more rather than the medical factors on the health issue in any rural settings. This non-medical factor primarily comes from the social, cultural and physical aspects relating to the certain social groups of the society. Hence, the researchers have to focus on using drugs, smoking, usage of alcohol, festivals, and fairs by the rural people and its consequences on their health. And stress is also required on why few people accept the modern medicine and how they defend it. Also he opined that attention is required on the different factors including, social norms, opinion on the modern health care system, stress, and tension etc., affecting rurals health behavior.

Kannuri (2005) has focused on the culture deterrents of health. He felt culture is the final factor affecting community’s perception on health and disease. He found that socio-religious medical reactions to any specific type of illness usually changes over the period of time in any society because of the various internal and external factors. Hence, some time people found to have a common health belief for the various health disorders. Also he felt “the reply to an illness behavior is the way in which symptoms are perceived, escalated and actual upon”. Next, Parson (1951) has opined a traditional medical system has a social shape and have a poor vital components ;

1. Adaptation;
2. Goal –orientation ;
3. Integration;
4. Latency

He has opined beliefs, values and attitudes relating to sickness/ illness/ disease of the rural social groups must be examined from the total context of the current social organizations.

Ikels (2002) has opined that culture not only play a vital role in shaping treatment patterns for illness in the rural settings. There are some vital issues like illness recognition, perception, and severity of illness etc. Also culture guides for the suitable healing approaches for the specific health problems. Some time the culture will recognize some health problems as a very serious issue and some of them are not. In some cases, culture may identify the serious problem as normal or usual one. Vijayalakshmi. &Swamy (2013) writes “social networks along the lines of caste, kinship or regional ties, though at times viewed as detrimental to health behavior play on the positive side, a crucial role in reducing the element of isolation in an alien atmosphere by allowing homogeneity in a health culture to grow. The first type of network includes all blood relatives; the second considers co-villagers and neighbors”

Nancymun (1973) found that “ritual is a common medium of social interactions which becomes a vehicle for framing messages through iconic symbols (acts, words, chants and other things) that convert the load of importance of complex socio-cultural meanings embedded in and generated by the ongoing process of social existence into common currency. In other words, shared socio-cultural meanings constituted, which are symbolically transacted through the medium of ritual action”. Medhiano and Hassan (2002) have found that introducing western medicine may be a reason for the emergence of medical pluralism. In some village, people use both the traditional and modern type of medicine to cure different types of diseases/illness. Some time people will themselves choose a particular type of therapy for their different health problems. In certain cases both the local healers and the patients; are being well aware about various biological & non-biological substances as medicines to cure various health problems.

Lisabourke and Others (2004) have opined that rural health is a complex web of social relations, cultural history and socio-political networks. Practitioners who work in the rural setting should take care about the confidentiality of their patients’. Normally rural people do not want to leak their health problems to others. Also practitioners should aware of cultural safety (i .e. the primary understanding of other culture) and cultural competence while working in rural settings .

Nova Scotia Department of Health, (2005) has opined regarding cultural competence. “Cultural competence is very vital in any community health care system. Experts have opined it is very helpful in working in diverse cultural settings

It reduces disparities in health services and increases detection of culture- specific diseases

It addresses inequitable access to primary health care

It impacts the health status of culturally diverse communities” (quoted)

Anthropological writings on traditional healers have largely concentrated upon role on Shamans in rural health care system. Some of the experts like Metzger and Williams (1963) ; Margetts (1965) ; Handelman, (1967); Lebra, (1969); Tenzal, (1970); Boyes(1964) ; Turner (1967); Toralemon (1985) and Joshi (2004) have focused on the ‘psychosocial dimensions of Shaman’s role in curing illness on the part of the patients’. They opined Shamans’ usually follow psycho-pathological treatment for the patients’. Extensive use of projective techniques and personalized consultations has been the major focal of attention in all above mentioned field studies. Some authors have meticulously analyzed the Shaman’s abilities in manipulating the existing social symbols to restore the broken social ties of the rural patients’.

Padhi (2012) has done work on the various health issues with the Tribes from the Korapat District of Odisha from the human rights perspective. It highlights an infrastructural profile and the social and cultural practices to deal with poor health status. It underlines how a poor infrastructural arrangement attributes to the poor health status of the Tribes of Odisha in general and rural people of the neighboring areas in particular. Also, an attempt made in this paper to map out impact of poor health conditions in the health empowerment process. The paper concludes with a positive note that the question of health and disease can be meaningfully addressed provided integration of the traditional and modern health institutions and practices.

Kurian and Tribhuwan (1990) have pointed from their study that some rural people would normally prefer the baby delivery at home only. It is because people believe home would be the perfect place to conduct certain rituals immediately after delivery. Also all these health rituals have deeper cultural meanings and impacts on the health of both the mother and child in the future. However, authors have doubted that this may negatively affect both on new mother and an infant in the long run with respect to health.

Carpa (1991) has narrated that Shamanistic idea of illness is based on the concept that every human being is a part & parcel of the certain cultural order. It is found that diseases or illness causes whenever there is a disturbance with the cosmic order. Hence, ‘curing illness means restoring the good harmony with the spirit world again’. He also opined that ‘shamans will not treat a patient based on his/her conscious rather an entire social-unconscious shared by the universe’. The main

objective behind the ritual healing is to satisfy and surrender to the cosmic powers. Dauglas (1975) has written every human being will have both social body experiences and physical body experiences. However, physical experiences of the body always changes by various social categories. Throughout the life course of an individual, there will be an exchange of meanings, exchange of perceptions and other consciousness between these two types of bodily experiences. Further, this author has explained about the relationship between symbols and its meanings associated with the communities' perception or expression about illness theory and body image. He also said a different healing technique in various contexts represent the cultural whole.

Chilivumbo (1977) wrote

“diagnosis and therapeutic measures acquiring meanings through subjective perceptions and the defined symbolic world view in which irrationalities assume meanings. Illness experience is shaped by cultural symbols and meanings in a defined cultural context or situation”

Tribhuvan (1998), Sten and Mazonde (1999) have opined health seeking behavior has no place in the modern medical text books. The modern doctors should aware of the health seeking behavior of the both urban and rural patients' for an effective treatment under the context of medical pluralism.

Outwater, et-al (2001) has found few vital facts about the traditional healers and their knowledge about the modern health techniques. He opined today traditional healers use more inputs from the modern medicines. Also the author felt traditional healers should be given enough scientific training to handle simple health problems of the rural people. Because, people have more faith on the healers who are not trained enough than the trained doctors due to the various cultural reasons. Murdock (1980) has felt illness perceptions of the various societies' can be obtained based on their opinion about the natural and super natural causation of various health issues. Normand and Bennet (1996) study has found that people who can have control on their health can have more knowledge on promoting self-health behavior normally. He felt today due an explosion of various modern media' people are aware more about their health needs.

It is found that rural medicinal system will be based on magico-logical theme believing that cause itself leads to a cure. Even though it books hard it has been practiced over the generations. This traditional system of healing techniques practiced across the rural societies and it has become a part of their health culture. Further

health problems of a community can be considered as functions of the entire ecological system. Clements (1937) has given a wide destruction of five basic concepts of discourse

- a. Sources,
- b. Bereave of tobacco,
- c. Object intrusion
- d. Spirit intrusion and soul loss,

Macphail and Campbell (2001) have studied how individual's medical knowledge in social and cultural contexts develops. They opined that there is a slight conflict between the modern and local medical knowledge over the period of time. People strongly believe the modern medical technology has originated basically from the traditional system only. Campbell and Mzaidume (2001) have opined people's participation in health related projects may increase more positive health care seeking behavior among them'. Also health projects will give more therapeutic options to the people. The author also found high rates of various infectious diseases in the rural areas is due to the poor socio economic status, health illiteracy, unhygienic conditions etc.

Bedri (2001) has opined women have limited opportunity in accessing good health care facilities in the rural areas because of their vulnerable position. The significant higher fertility rate among the rural people is mainly due to the high infant and child mortality rate facing by the rural population. They also showed that simple awareness about the infant and child mortality influences the real family size of those who recognize the current level of infant and child mortality as the same or worse than before. Radley (1994) ; Dalal and Ray (2005) have opined health and sickness are often limited in natural terms, referring to the bodily conditions, as assessed by the medical professionals. This distinctive expert-oriented approach fails in delivering the health care services. In the first instance, rural patients' will approach the health professionals only when they find their illness symptoms threatening and understand that they need some urgent medical attention. Thus, it seems significant to understand the health and illness issues from the patients' viewpoint especially in the rural settings.

Shaika (2004) has opined that the health seeking behaviors of the rural people in the developing societies are changing today. This is because of the changing physical, socio economic, cultural and political scenario due to the globalization. He opined that the utilization of any type of health care system normally depend on the socio-

demographic factors, existing social structure, gender discrimination and ecology. He writes 'health policy making should be supplementary to the pluralistic health care system'. More focus should be given to the socially excluded people through an inter-sectoral collaboration.

Martorell (1999) **has** opined that malnutrition and childhood mortality became a serious problem among the rural community in many south Asian countries. It is found that the rurals's social-cultural background, health seeking behavior and dynamics of the health culture play a significant determinants indicating the health status of the rural community in a multi cultural society like India. Because of a unique heath seeking beliefs and behavior, malnutrition and the childhood mortality issues are more common in the rural areas.

Joshi (2004) opines that health beliefs among the people changes according to the different geographical areas. Broad and specific geographical pattern of medical knowledge can be seen across the villages in India. In some cases similar health cultures also can be seen across the villages. Also one of the great strength of the Indian rural medical system is involvement of the group in therapy. Kins, Affine and other villagers will help in the therapy management. This social support network in the treatment process including sharing previous experiences, suggestions and the counseling will boost the morality of the concerned patient. If the patient suffers from any pain normally an entire village group shares the agony. Hence, the healing process is a type of shared experience in the village culture. In this case rehabilitation of the patient is not a problem at all. The overall impact of the various economic development processes, modern developments are also caucusing effect on the rural health. Continuous migration also has done sever damages to the natural humanity to the rural folk.

Gaidas (2005) opined that the health seeking behavior differs in both men and women. Men belonging to the different socio-economic background and ethnicity normally may have to suffer with the various health inequalities. He opined that heterogeneous sample is required to reveal the factors which place a vital role regarding the health decision making among rural men.

Deepa (2005) has opined that Ayurvedic and Homeopathy should be treated as a complementary rather alternative to the western medicinal system. In US it will be considered as a food supplement. Since the more medical pluralism is available today in the rural areas, people some time may get confusing over accepting an appropriate health care system.

Panikar and Soman (1984) have opined existing rural institutional frame work needs some more reforms for the effective implementation the inter-sectoral action programme for the successful rural participation. Arson and Sun (2004) concluded that education, occupation, income has close connections with the specific health behavior of the rural people. People in good occupation and income status normally will have the better health status. They go for the modern health care facility and will have more preventive programmes. Jose (1990) opined that the rural people believe the medical pluralism has more advantages than the western medical system because of the cost and accessibility factors.

Nakkeeran (2001) has opined that integration of the traditional medical system and its mainstreaming is very essential today. Today the western medicinal system has dominated the rest of the health care system also. He further opined the traditional medicine needs an accurate standardization for the safety reason.

Banerji (1979) opined that the Britishers' were using the western medicine (when India was under colonies) to strengthen the supporting groups and to weaken the oppressed groups. Colonial system brought many regulations so that only few sections of the society could access to the western medical system during that time.

Minocha (1980) has opined that people always look for the quality, availability, accessibility of the good medical care provided by the different health care systems even though they may not aware of cost and benefits of all these system. The author says both the medical and non-medical interventions are required to improve the health behavior of the rural people. And it is the need of the hour also. Duggal (1994) has opined pluralistic medical system focus more on prevention and promotional aspects and has no curative issues. He also opined that curative message is quite needy for the rural folk.

Weyers (2010) opined that the exact role of social determinants in the health care seeking behavior is not completely cleared yet. The Health beliefs sometime more closely relates to the both psychology and sociological issues with the broad influences of the socio-economic conditions. Also various social networks play a vital role in framing the vital behavior determinants. Moreover, the neighborhood environment also largely influences on the people with reference to their health behavior and the health culture. Krishna (2004) and Noponen and Kantor (2004) have opined that poverty and the health are closely related in every society. Poverty effects on the health in many ways. The authors have found that heavy cost for the quality health care might be one of the reasons for the poor health status in the rural parts.

Russel (2004) also shown that the health risks are the major threat to the poor people today. Wagstaff (2002) Dahlgren and Whitehead (1992) have opined that poverty and other issues effects on the health status including the poor lifestyle, social exclusion, malnutrition, mental problems etc.,

Alam (2000) has suggested having more in-depth studies on the health inequalities among the various social groups in the rural areas. He felt this why the rural people are quite indifferent regarding their health culture. Adam, Beek and Van Loon (2000) have opined we should not only focus on why some people are not showing an interest in having the good health care seeking behavior. Also we should stress on how their behavior turns into one of the high risk factors for their future health.

Aver at. al (2001) found using/waiting for the different therapeutic models may delay the actual required treatment. People need a good health education so that patients' may approach the suitable medical aid soon after the onset of any disease/illness.

Manhart el al (2000) have opined an inappropriate treatment must be avoided which cause due to the over using the modern medicine without having any valid prescriptions.

Goldman and Hevueline (2000) say the health care seeking behavior differs from the disease to disease. People show a less seriousness towards some common infectious diseases and they show fairly different behavior towards the more serious disease/illness. People think if any health problem could not solve by a local healer that problem must be a serious one and they will look for a better option.

Lubanga el. al (1997) found that the rural young mothers need to be trained in diagnosing some early symptoms of the child health problems. Beals (1980) has found that the uniqueness of the certain disease is like cause and mode of action. These "fixed-strategy" mechanically insist to a particular type of treatment. In the rural parts self or home remedy typically would be the first step in suitable medical care depending primarily on medicinal plants (Kolay, 2011). Wallman and Baker (1996) has found autonomy; social network and informal channels play a vital role in the choosing appropriate medical treatment with respect to women in rural parts. Qadeer, (1990) and Priya (1990) have opined normally common people have been neglected while framing the new health policies. Health policies will be framed in Delhi and same would be implemented across the country uniformly without knowing the pulse of the people. It is why in most of the time policies won't yield any good result. The

authors felt Govt. should first find the health needs of the people than should frame the new policies.

Kurane (2011) opines that even after the five decades of designed development, rural and tribal health development poses a challenge to the policy makers, administrators and the social workers. There must be something incorrect either with the direction of achieving development, functioning of the health development agenda, or with the tribal /rural themselves. There is a need to examine the failure of the health welfare model of growth and development as applied to rural and tribal India. She felt the health development programmes should have a qualitative aspect of human development. Tribals and rurals should be psychologically provoked to accept the new skill, new programmes, new approaches, and life style towards the health care seeking behavior. The Government, social scientists, social workers, social activists should take an urgent step to organize the activities.

Singh (1994) has examined an interplay of various factors influencing health of the rural communities. He has listed;

1. Socio economic status ;
2. Dietary habits;
3. Psycho-social issue ;
4. Health culture ;
5. Mortality and morbidity ;
6. Genetic disorders ;
7. Health delivery system ;8. Medical pluralism etc.

Singh (1994) further writes in an informal sense, everyone is a “healer ” because self-treatment is always the first consideration in dealing with a perceived health problem. Yet, in all cultures, some people are being recognized as having special abilities in diagnosing and treating various health problems and cross-cultural evidences indicates some common criteria of the successful traditional healers.

Alderman, Hoddinott, and Kinsey (2003) have opined there were a number of forces percolated from the larger socio-economic environment and directed through an attribute of historical, social and political dimension of the developmental pattern of rural’s health culture in the given settings. Good health required a balanced diet. Fewer than Five children need a good nutritional diet which is scanty in many rural settings in the country and this causes mortality and morbidity among the rural under five children. Moyon (2004) has stated in her paper that in tribal / rural community

ethno-medicine will be the first option. Later on they go for the western medical system whenever the child health issue is concerned. Women health normally will be depending on the socio-economic status, educational level of her family. They also opined that rural health care system must be

1. Easily accessible to the people;
2. Must be affordable;
3. Must be culturally viable;
4. Must be low cost also.

Suchman (1965) has given how an individual takes a decision about use/not to use health care in rural settings.

1. Symptom experience including pain;
2. Assumption of a sick role;
3. Medical care contact ;
4. Dependent patient role;
5. Inner strength and of the patient to recover from illness
6. Family history

Young and Carrot (1988) have given four criteria based on which a rural patients choose any type of treatment.

1. Severity of the illness;
2. Availability of home remedy ;
3. Success or failure of home remedy ;
4. The Cost and availability of health care system.

However ,Weller and others (1997) have written some criteria based on which the rural patients' choose any type of treatment.

1. Seriousness of illness,
2. Cost factors
3. Past experience with the same illness

House et. al (1988) and Stone et. al (1999) have opined due to the some cultural reason, some people don't seek more social support with respect to their health needs. Patients use different approaches of cure in complementary and

supplementary manner. Today the healers do not adhere to a single specialty. The authors have suggested a better understanding the influence of traditional, cultural and health beliefs needs an additional and culturally suitable and successful health provisions focusing rural mass. Uchida et. al (2008) has explored the relationship between emotional support and the good physical health and well being. Leven et. al (1984); Ajzen and Fishbein (1980) have proved that the socio-cultural factors will play a vital role in shaping the psychological domains such as illness, cognitions, attitude, behavior etc., of the rural patients'. Bird et-al (2000) has opined more studies are required to find out of the effect of the rural social structures and the institutions on the various established health and illness issues of a common man. Next, various rural institutes invariably causes more effects on the established health culture and health behavior of the rural community.

Skylab Sahu (2013) has written mainly rural women lack health care access in comparison to men in developing states of Africa, India and even in underdeveloped pockets of developed states like USA. Women lack access to the health care due to economic constraints, geographical barriers and formal and informal social responsibility. She has also indicated that the prevalence of stigma in the health care system has emerged as a greater barrier in accessing the quality health care. Women oriented unavailability of health care and the persisting denial of the quality treatment has become a shocking phenomenon across the country.

Smith and Ross, (2006) has opined health empowerment is an input for excellence of life. Health dignity, good governance, pro-poor growth, project effectiveness, and improvised service need to be focused on rural areas for the best health outcome. Health empowerment has dissimilar meanings in the diverse socio-cultural and political contexts, and cannot be translated easily into all languages. Looking at narrow terms, some issues including mental strength, good physical health, self-power, self-reliance, living standard, choice, a life of dignity, harmony with one's values, capable of hostility for one's rights, autonomy, health decision making etc., should be greatly focused in the health policies (Smith and Ross, 2006).

Nichter (1996) has written "Biomedical disease symptoms are encomium passed within the humeral conceptual framework. A cutting of metaphors occurs. Popular health culture in India is biological an assemblage of assorted conceptual and martial reassures". Morrow (2001) has opined the role of social capital in sustainable health development among the rural poor is vital. Favlk and Kilpatrick (2000) have

proved that how social interceptions, different strata would be vital in providing the required primary health care among the traditional societies. Poliakoff (1993) has opined health culture will be a vital issue in an emotional response to the pain and it varies across the societies. Uskul and Hynie (2007) have opined that ill-health has a close association with the traditional health rituals. Generally rural people think if they failed to perform certain obligatory rituals it may lead to have more disease /illnesses. Cesario et.al (2004) and Surerman et. al (2006) have opined if the health communications are culturally relevant, then it may influence more on the health care seeking behavior. Oyserman and Lee (2008); Oyserman and Sorensen (2009) have opined ‘culturally matched health message increases the persuasiveness in seeking the suitable health care behavior among the rural people’.

Kolay (2011) has opined that “despite the penetration of bio-medicine concept in remote areas, traditional ideas of disease and therapies still prevails. The total commitment of the believers in the traditional systems persists and so does the belief of the patient in the healer, regardless of the result. The traditional health culture has generally been accrued of erecting barrier to the use the bio-medicine and bifurcation between the traditional and modern medicine systems still obtain in anthropological literature”. Good (1977) has found that new notion of the ‘semantic illness network’. It is a collection of words, situations, symptoms and narrations which are associated with an illness and gives it meaning for the sufferer in rural parts. Blumenhagen (1981) has described the semantic illness network to explain how BP Problem was perceived by the American patients.

Roseman (1988) opines that healing action actually lies in between Two established facts;

1. Musical or different ritual performances and its effect and
2. Binding emotion on cosmology, illness, etiology etc.

The Author has opined these two play a vital role on the psychology of the patients’

Richard (1973) has opined that healers will normally use the chemo therapy, mechanical and magico-religious to cure the patient’s health problems. Either of this therapy may compose of certain prayer/ chants, action etc. In some cases healers may use the decoction prepared out of the medicinal plants to cure various illness. Sometime this may lead to have more side effects rather than curing the health problems.

Joshi (2004) has found that the health belief changes from the different geographical areas. Broader and specific geographical pattern of medical knowledge can be seen across the villages. In some cases similar health culture also can be seen in same villages. One of the greatest strength of the rural medical system is involvement the Kins, friends, relatives and other local villagers in the therapy management. This social support network in the treatment process including sharing, suggestions and the informal counseling to the patient will boost the morality of the patient. If a patient suffers from any pain, normally the whole village shares the agony. Hence, the healing process is a type of shared experience especially in the rural parts. In this case, rehabilitation of the patient will not be a problem. The author has also opined the overall impact of various economic development processes and modernization programmes are also causing an effect on the rural health scenario. The continuous migration also has done severe damages to the natural immunity of the rural folks.

As Balgir (2003) says rurals are rooted with the several superstitious beliefs. They believe that the prayers and offerings can give more relief to their health problems. This kind of beliefs separates them from using the modern treatment and medicine. Some services are inappropriately used, whereas others, such as preventive health programmes, are under-utilized because of the unacceptability of the modern medicines. Guite and Acharya (2006) have shown the acceptance of a particular health care system among the rural people mostly depends on its availability and accessibility. The Unacceptability of the modern health care system is due to an easy acceptability of the traditional health care services over the period of time.

A range of health improvement programmes have some direct and indirect effects on the health status of a rural community. Even if a child gets any type of health problem usually parents' will not be very serious. In the majority cases, they simply pass few days until naturally it gets cured!. In the rural settings, people don't go for any type of treatment until and unless it gets worse. It clearly shows that the decision at the household level will be taken in the latter stage. By that time, a disease will reach to an advanced stage and it will be very complicated to cure. Next, the household decision about the treatment will be largely governed by the local traditions, customs and other related issues. Rural people will take a decision to choose an appropriate medical care system after passing through the various complicated traditional process at the household. Experts found that gender discrepancy has become the most vital component in getting or not to getting the proper and on-time treatment in case of women. Usually mother-in law or husband

will take a final decision at the household level in rural parts. In the majority rural settings, malnutrition among the children and young mothers also due to the various cultural health believes.

Rural areas in general are market by the poor implementation of various health facilities. The Government has implemented many rural specific health programmes. However, high concentration of infectious diseases, absence of an effective health education, and lack of fundamental facilities are adversely affecting on the rural health scenario today. Even today there is no good road facility for many remote villages across the country. Due to this factor, new medical technology has not yet reached to many villages even today. Rural health today has two important dimensions:

1. Some of the communicable diseases which are most commonly prevalent among the rurals including Malaria, Cholera, Diarrhea, Malnutrition, etc., require good health education with an effective grass root level interventions and providing hygienic environment;
2. Some of the non-communicable diseases including mental illness, neurological problems, requires good psychiatric social work. Also there is a dearth need to have some special programme for alcoholism, smoking and drug addictions in the rural parts.

Chaudhuri (2004) opines in rural settings health and treatment normally reflects the community's solidarity. He writes if something happens to someone in the village like any health problem the rest of the village will come forward to observe certain norms. In certain cases the whole community will take the responsibility of the patient in curing his/her health problem. This social solidarity through the social network will also play an indirect role in educating other people to be cautious about any health problems. The author also highlights that social scientists have done an enormous work on the rural health culture and commented about their blind health beliefs but they have not gone into the in-depth study on the basic forces behind that types of beliefs. Further, he opines the current traditional method available to the rural people needs more scientific study. There is a dearth need to encourage and support the traditional healing system to the tune of modern medical coverage. The Traditional healers should be trained at least in the field of identifying diseases at an earlier stage where burden on the patient can be substantially reduced.

Ben (1997) opines the

“low health status is a characteristic of any transitional society, which enfolds multi-class-based social structure, and complexes of traditional and pre-capitalist production relation operating under the rein of the dominant ideology and mode of exploitation”. This also holds true in respect of Indian society wherein, multi-class social structures exist and a complex of traditional and pre-capitalist production relations are operates in an articulated capitalist mode production and exploitation”.

Basu and others (1994) have conducted a study on perception on health and health seeking behavior of the certain rural population and tribes in Karnataka. They opined that the health status in terms of the health behavior is quite poor. Malnutrition, standard of living, lack of health education, cultural log, absence of mass media, poor health infrastructure are some of the reason why rural people have poor health behavior. Also the rural people have a perception that the modern medicine is the last option because of poverty, health illiteracy etc., As well, the author has opined distance factors, economic conditions, lack of facilities, behavior of the staff (PHC) are some of the reasons why people are not showing interest to visit the modern medical health care centers. Next, Tandon (1994) has noted the different dietary patterns among the rural and tribal people as a mode of excellent health care technique. Due to the changing dietary pattern he felt rural people need a more nutritional awareness programme. Because of socio-cultural reasons and the fear of the cultural sanctions, people will not use some food items in the rural areas. Also, it may lead to have some serious health issues among the new mothers, infants, aged etc.

Akbar (2002), has concluded that folk healing issues in certain villages of Pakistan depends on the nature of illness. People will use different kinds of treatment options based on the severity and probable future problems. Sometime an entire village takes part in the final decision in selecting (unofficially) a particular type of medical care for the patient. In some cases, the local healers will suggest the patients’ to go for the modern medicine if they can’t cure the problem.

Mitra et.al (1998) found if any health problem occurs to women it would affect an entire family. It affects wellbeing and functioning of the family too. Usually in the rural parts head of the household will take a decision to get her treatment or not. In rural parts, women cannot take her own decision to get any type of treatment in the majorly cases. Some time mother –in-law also takes a final decision in the household.

However recent studies Bode (2013) have been focused on the standardization/safety of the traditional medicine and its real efficacy. Over the last few years medical anthropologists are working towards different traditional medicines, its side effects

and its effects on social relationships (Wardram, 2000; Barner, 2005 ; Lambest, 2012; Adam, 2011). Experts felt proper scientific evidences with respect to the traditional medicines and its exact mechanism in the healing process is not revealed properly yet (Narahari et. al, 2010; Desilva, 2011). Even today, large numbers of people are using ethno medicine rapidly and unscientifically across the globe (Kiw, 2009; Sujatha, 2011) without bothering its side effects and result. Also, there is no standard protocol to study the tradition medicine and its efficacy. Few authors also raised some objections without having any scientific evidence, Govt. NGOs should not try to promote the traditional medicines and there is an urgent need to integrate the tradition medicines with the modern bio medical health care (Bode, 2013).

Waitzkin (2001) opines that health inequalities among certain societies are due to the various economical and political reasons. No doubt, the social class and castes are underpinning why large scale health disparity exists today in the rural societies. Moreover, the political, economical and developmental issues cause more impact on the rural life. These powerful agencies evaluate the people based on their income, occupation, educational background etc., while allocating health resources. Not only these forces, medical institutions, pharmaceuticals companies are also responsible in creating the health disparities among the different classes in many ways.

NCAER report about AYUSH (Ayurveda, Yoga, Unani, Sidda and Homeopathy) in 1990 has stated 8% of the health problems are being cured by the AYUSH only in rural India. The same report clearly says that in rural India major sections of the people depending on the indigenous medicines even today for their health needs. Next, Nagla, (2007) has conducted a study regarding attitude and belief towards the traditional medicines and the medical care system in two dissimilar settings, i.e., urban and rural, in Haryana. She also analyzed what sort of knowledge people having towards diseases and illness and how they are combating with these health problems effectively is to be stressed. The ‘results shows advice from the science and the health professionals tend to be filtered through an existing health beliefs and practices, and through the prevailing social relationships’.

It is generally opined that the social and cultural factors play the major role in deciding the health aspects of a girl child in the rural settings. Among the rural communities, it is the male child who is expected to assume the dominant role in all traditional activities including the festivals and other religious occasions, which results an automatic discrimination of the girl children in every social aspects. It manifests itself in a number of ways, which documented in detail in some gender related studies. Adverse sex ratio, female infanticide, lower nutritional status, difficult

household tasks to the girl children are some of the indicators which amply supports the factors discriminating about the health issues of the girl children in India.

Douabedian (1981) & Anderson (1995) have done some noted work about the evaluation of the various rural health schemes implemented by the various health service providers like Government and other NGOs at all the levels including person, community, and the social groups etc. They found many loopholes (structural, administration, functioning, etc) in various Govt. sponsored health programmes. They opined participation of the beneficiaries is very vital in the success of the any health programmes in the country.

Jain, Tiwari and Sharma (2002) have observed that poor living standard and an unhygienic condition are the vital factors responsible for the frequent out breaking of various communicable diseases in the rural areas. Also they opined due to the usage of more pesticides, and chemical fertilizers cause more health hazard among the rural people. Mother & child healthcare practices in the rural parts of the country are also pathetic. However, in certain cases, the young educated rural generations are showing more interest towards the modern healthcare. Discrimination against women in health care normally exists in the rural parts and it is often studied only as a part of the overall pattern of discrimination against women. As womens' health is concerned, these authors have opined 'what has been observed is that most of the parameters are often defined in such a manner that discrimination is not even apparent'. Studies have revealed that in rural areas women are engaged in running the households, cooking, collection of water, fuel ,fodder, agricultural work, and looking after the children etc., Such invisibles activities invariably effects on the health of a women especial in rural parts (Sinha, 2000).

Benzeval and Judge (2001) have found that chronic poverty affects more on the health than livelihood issue. Next, Burtey and Boulton (2000) have opined germ theory and genetic study may helpful in understanding health behavior and illness issues scientifically. Stacey (1988) has opined any health care system in a society can't be studied by keeping other inevitable aspects of the society from the ambit of the study. Any medical system, health culture, health behavior normally represents the contemporary value and the social structure of the any society.

Gulati (1996) has done some study on precise and imperative socio-economic, cultural and demographic factors of the choice and use of contraceptive methods in different socio-economic settings in rural parts of Kerala and Uttar Pradesh states. This study found that contraceptive using rates were drastically lesser amongst the

rural Muslims compared to the rural Hindus and other religious sections despite controlling all the important predictors of contraceptive user behavior. Also, the author felt different health policies and the decreasing infant and child mortality rate has played a vital role in the elevated usage of the various contraceptive methods in the rural areas.

Meesan et.al (2003) opined encountering with the high cost of the health system by the poor people is called 'iatrogenic poverty'. Poverty ridden people also show the poor health status and may use only low quality health care services which may cause some sort of side effects in the long run to those people. Schrijvers et. al (1999) opined the lower socio-economic status may be one of the vital reasons for the higher health risks. Phellas (2010) has opined the sociological studies have crossed its traditional boundary and has to focus now on the issues like conflict among the different health care providers, euthanasia, medicalization, health inequalities, and trauma and feminization issues etc., focusing the rural areas. All these factors play a vital role in generalizing the health care behavior of the rural people. The author opined the nature of the personal-professional relationships between the patients' and the doctors' also counts a lot in rural settings today.

Stenstorm and Andresson (2000) felt people who don't have a strong belief and faith in the modern preventive health education may run into having risky health behavior. Hjelm et. al (1999) has opined in rural parts the patients' of having different diseases will normally focus on the self medication/home remedy first. Next, it is felt that the rurals' health seeking and health care seeking behavior depend largely on the cultural history of the family. Also the strong belief of the family elders about the origin of diseases/ illness counts a lot in choosing the specific types of treatment.

Choubey (2000); Paudry (2000); Sharma (1999) have opined more medico-anthropological related studies on rural and tribal health problems focusing utilization of modern medical facilities, nutritional status, mortality, mobility, family welfare services etc required today. Authors have found that rurals' are facing more new health problems because of their changing socio-cultural issues due to the globalization. They are still hanging between the traditional and modern health practices. The authors have opined more scientific studies are required focusing family welfare behavior of the rural and tribal people in the changing social context.. the Government and NGOs need to create more awareness among the rural people without intervening in their cultural world.

Bhat (2011) says the real challenge would be improving coverage of MCH (mother and child) services in rural parts of the country where the knowledge level is apparently low. Pertinently, the female literacy level is also low in the majority rural regions of the country which are found to be strongly related to the utilization of MCH services and, demographic and health indicators in general. Another important challenge would be the greater inclusiveness of socio-economically deprived and backward groups such as SCs, STs, OBCS, illiterate and the poor into MCH programmes.

Helman (2001) has opined that the rural health system consists of multi level prospective and he has classified there are 3 overlapping sectors of health care and can be identified:-

1. Popular sector.
2. The folk sector &
3. Professional sector.

Hardon(2001) has opined normally illness will be self treated in the first stage. If it is doesn't work then patients would go for other higher level of medicine? He has given two patterns of health seeking behavior.

1. Simultaneous resort and
2. Hierarchical resort.

He found that severity of illness will play a vital role in fixing specific health seeking behavior.

Freund & Maguire (1995) have opined patients' will always not follow the prescription of A doctor. Some the patients' may follow the prescription partially or fully or just ignore or even he/she may reject the prescription at all. Based on the others advices in the village some time he/she may go for a second opinion.

Shrestha & Ittiravivongs (1994) have opined age, gender, education, the family and distance factor will not associated with the utilization of the modern healthcare facilities. Occupation, income, knowledge & attitude towards western healing system will play a role in opting the modern health care utilization. Having a good occupation and income people normally use the modern medicine and will have modern health beliefs irrespective of their social background in the rural parts.

Jain and Visaria (1988) et.al opined despite marvelous development focusing preventive and curative medicine, the child healthcare delivery services among several

rural communities are still poor and unscientific. It is found that poverty; illiteracy, malnutrition, scarcity of potable water, sanitary conditions, poor mother child health services, problems in covering national health and nutritional services, etc. are some of the vital causative factors for the prevalence of severe childhood mortality and morbidity in the rural parts of the country.

Santhat (1999) has opined based on the illness symptoms people changes treatment pattern and the consultation places and the author has defined it as 'switching pattern of the health seeking behavior'. This will be largely influenced by the socio economic and the family history of the patients'. Lyttleton (1996) has opined some time the modern medicine would be the first choice for the majority rural folks because of the growing health awareness. However, they will seek the health care from other medical systems depending on the nature of the health problem.

Zhangfan (2003) opined the income level of the people more affects on the health seeking behavior of the people. Middle income people often go to the hospitals but some time higher income people visit folk medicines in the rural parts surprisingly. However, high income people rely on the Gov't. hospital only than private some time. Hence he felt it would be quite complicated to analyze it in the developing societies.

Alderman, Hoogeveen, and Rossi. (2005) **have** opined that the poor health outcome of the rural community and their children need to be read within in the context of the rapid urbanization, poor health infrastructure, treatment cost etc. However, in a multicultural society like India rural childhood mortality cannot be analyzed in a context of the vacuum. Instead, they need to be looked in the light of larger socio economic changes experienced by the rural community over the period of time due to interventions of various external agencies.

Millman (2011) has opined some issues like the cultural competency and cultural sensitivity have become the vital points to be discussed in the medical field today. He further opined that the medical sociology or anthropology is vital in understanding the problems of the rural health care system and the role of the cross cultural issues in understanding various faces of rural health and illness.

Hand (1985) opined that among minorities, dissatisfaction emerges from the various economic and linguistic reasons including the problem in accustoming biomedical health care system with their traditional health care system.

Coe (1997) has opined that the western medical system does not respect lay beliefs' about health and illness. Hence, there will be some sort of the dissatisfaction

among the patients'. The western doctors will not show interest to listen their belief and the narrations before giving any treatment and they simply treat the patients' like a material.

Bhatia (1984) felt today various Governments have implemented numerous programmes to improve the nutritional status of the pre-school children through various innovative schemes. Huge money spent to raise the nutritional level of the children. Still country experiences severe under nutrition and rural child mortality issue. The health experts opined that lack of good primary health care, perceived and personal risks, lack of awareness have led to failing various health improvement programmes in the rural settings of the country.

Wing (1998) has opined that in cross cultural society integration of both the bio medicine and folk system are necessary for the holistic health care especially in focusing the rural areas. Farmer (1992) has pointed out that in many developing societies, the modern health care system would be very costly also do not effectively address the social aspects of 'illness'. This is because of the various socio-cultural problems and withering social relationships today.

Micozzi (2002) has pointed that basically the modern medicine considers 'body and mind' as separate entities whereas there will be no such distinction in case of the traditional medicinal system. Alternative health care system is more holistic in nature and it is parallel to the folk medical system. Hence it is more popular in the rural area.

Inhorn (2006) has opined that in the name of the modern public health, today the biomedicine system has entered into all facets of the society. It has narrow down the vital parameters of the general health. Welch (2003) has opined that during the medical examination a relationship exists between the doctor and the patient. However, in the modern health care, doctor will play a final role and the patient will be just a receiver. In this point the doctor will keep a distance away from the patient because of his/her position, power and the medical knowledge unlike the folk healing system. Whereas in the folk healing system, there will be an intimacy between the healer and patients'.

Kakar (1983) has opined the usage of the traditional medicine has cultural conception. Illness is completely intertwined in the societal role and if the medical care could not meet the social needs and emotions of the patients it may likely to get failed gradually. Hence any medical health care system should provide a holistic care to the patient.

A Study conducted by Stephen and others (2012) have found that that undoubtedly Janani Suraksha Yojana (JSY) programme is reducing the prenatal and neonatal mortality especially in the rural parts of the country. On the other hand, its real effect on the rate of maternal mortality still not clear in the rural community of the country. With the increasing medical facilities for the baby delivery and we should also watch the increased workload on the health personnel's. Moreover, the Govt. need to think the monetary and political obligations towards JSY and it should be more consistent in its approach. Consequently, the Govt. should think in creating an appropriate evaluation and the monitoring mechanism across the country for the data gathering, as a part of the national health information system. This will facilitate a definite evaluation on the regular and consistent base whether JSY has succeeded in reducing the numbers of neonatal and maternal deaths in the rural parts of the country or not (Stephen and others, 2010).

Few studies found that the JSY has unarguably resulted in growing numbers of hospital based deliveries, and is very helpful for the rural poor women to access the quality public health facilities at the door steps without having much problem. Perhaps for the first time, it has challenged to the public health system, forcing the providers and the system to deliver a quality service for the safe childbirth. This has been made possible by the proportionate increases in the infrastructure and the human resources provided through the NRHM inputs. Notwithstanding these successes, still we need some more to be done on the various other health schemes (Teenashu, 2008).

Few studies have also proved that the human resources and other infrastructure are not sufficient to provide effective and quality services of JSY especially in rural areas. Experts found "Some issues require instant attention, such as the removal of the exclusionary criteria for home and institutional deliveries which limit this privilege for the poorest SC/ST women, effectively putting it out of their easy reach. Next, the most vital is the reorganization of the payments and addressing issues of leakage ensuring out of pocket cost on women need to be stopped. One way to do this would be the public distribution of current policy decision that user fees should not apply to the mothers and newborns" (Vaishali (2009) ; Rajaratnam . et.al (2010).

Few studies have proved while there are no shortcuts to reducing maternal mortality in rural parts. Recommendations out of the various studies can be implemented right away and some others require long term scheduling and instigation. However it takes much time to yield any good result. There is a need to have more awareness programme amongst rural young mothers. PHC should be covered with all modern facility and man power. New e- media, traditional media can also be used to

in this regard. Also all procedure to access the facility needs to be simplified. It may trigger up in case of health seeking behavior. Also long term measures may comprise the “1.development of additional facilities including an amplified number of trained of skilled birth attendants; 2.enabling facility based newborn care across facilities, 3.developing new optimal health personnel policies, and 4. Creating a prototype of differential financing across facilities” (MacDonald ,2009).

Next, studies have found that safe motherhood requires to be revisited in a circumstance where quality health care for the antenatal women, post partum mother and newborns need some more institutional care. Also ASHA worker needs more scientific training and their perks and remuneration needs to be increased. Hence ASHA worker may get more motivation in implementing the JSY scheme. As we know JSY is a foundation to tackle maternal mortality in rural parts, however, it needs more improvement in its administration at the ground level. This entire programme must be sustained, and accelerated in each and every nook and corner of the country with some modifications. Moreover need based accomplishment is also desired. Then only goals for the reduction of maternal mortality through JSY may get some good result (Deb, 2008;MacDonald 2009; Sudeep,2008).

D’souza (1993) opined to avoid expenditure and multiple trips to urban areas for the treatment people will go for traditional health care system in the rural parts. Izhar (1989) opined now-a-days urban people also depend on alternative medicines for many reasons. Asraf (1982), writes untrained allopathic doctors are the more dangerous than the traditional healers. Planning commission in one of its report (2000) has opined traditional healers have both geographical and cultural ethos. Illness is completely intertwined in the social roles and if the medical care could not meet the social needs and emotions of the patients, it fails in providing holistic care to the patients’.

Winkelman (2009) has opined that practice of healing techniques to heal any disease or illness is the fundamental part of any medical system. However, the traditional healing system has intertwined in the socio-economic sphere understanding the health culture. Whereas, the modern medical system does not consider this issue. Dressler (2001) writes that there is a dearth need to examine how the bio-medical model was distributed within the various strata of the society and how social, cultural and economic factors are affecting in practicing biomedical health care system. This would yield some results in finding why rural people are not showing interest in modern health care facility.

Farmer (1992) conducted his AIDS illness study in Haiti and he found that complex socio cultural, historical context of AIDS problems and its connection to the modern medicine. Treating AIDS patients has a lot of socio cultural issues in any society. Wijzen and Tanner, (2001) opined the traditional medical system has continued in society's social cultural complex through extremely entrenched processes. It is a set of concepts of health, illness and sickness that reflects certain values, traditions and beliefs based on the community's normal way of life. Cohin(2000), has opined social support helps the patient to recover fast and better rehabilitation. This is a kind of psychological effect on the part of the patient. Some time good social network will help the patients to have preventive measures in the future .

Mithra et. al, (1998) showed how environment, socio-economic factors and cultural issues plays a vital role in the health of the pregnant and nursing mothers. Editors have opined the rural health problems and health practices are directly related to their current socio-economic status. People's belief in dietary patterns also one of the main responsible factors causing infant and childhood mortality in the rural parts. Women's health is largely bounded by the cultural factors in rural areas. Also they found in the majority cases the head of the household will take the responsibility and the final decision regarding treatment options for the female members of the household. Moyon (2004) has opined in some rural parts people depend on the allopathic system for the health care service. Folk medicine also will be used along with other type of medicines. The author felt people don't like to take any chance with the modern medicine.

Bottorff et-al (1998); Dibble et. al. (1997) rurals' response to any health disasters depends on the few vital socio-economic parameters like occupation, income caste and class. Kohli and Dala (1998) writes in rural society issues like the Karma, God, Fate and Deed etc like concepts will play a very decisive role in shaping the specific health culture and health behavior. Rural people strongly believe humeral imbalance also causes due to the cosmological powers. Next, Lav et-al (1989) said some people will think the super natural power is the key responsible for causing any disease or illness and have more perceived power in case of recovery also. Westbrook et. al (1994) opined local health concepts about the reasons for causing disease would be vital in framing the cultural specific health policies especially for the rural people. Radford (1998) showed that "disabilities create space-time constraints on individuals, which limit where and how they experience place. Further, this study has shown that

that connotation is endorsed to illness within the constraints and opportunities experienced at home, neighborhood and workspaces etc. “,

Lewis (1958) opine that researchers “too has noted that the advantage in learning about the indigenous beliefs and practices of the community is the insight that one can get regarding the world view of the people as concepts of disease causation are part of a society’s total world view, which is also reflected in other spheres such as agriculture politics, and interpersonal relations” etc. Sharma (1979) has conducted a study on nutritional status of the rural and tribal people of Orissa state. He found that malnutrition, infertility, mortality, and morbidity have some close connections to the food culture of the rural society. Also he opines food pattern is a kind of reflection of their health culture. He felt malnutrition and other types of the problems are mainly due to an inadequate intake of the certain food items. Also he said due to the ecological destruction food scarcity is gradually increasing today in rural parts of the country.

Barry and Yuill (2002) have opined that today people are showing much interest in using alternative medicines. It might be due to an effect of post- modern industrial society. It shows peoples option is open to the therapeutic pluralism. Rural people are showing much interest in the medical system which gives them some quick result. Due to the non confidence and high cost, rural people are rejecting the western medicine or showing a delay in getting the suitable modern treatment on time which also cause more expensive in the future. Niranjan and Rao (1996) have worked about what extent the socio-economic characteristics influences the use of mother and child care services in Andhra Pradesh. The Authors have opined that the respondent’s education level is positively associated with using the mother and child care services in the rural areas. The religion is found to be an important issue in the utilization of various health care services. It is also revealed that utilization of the services were also found to be very poor among the people belonging to the lower castes in the rural areas.

Sharma (1996) in his study has explored about health belief of the rural minorities and the interpretations depend on,

1. Income and social status;
2. Urban-rural residence;
3. Education and occupation;
4. Ecological factors;
5. Social network and isolation

Addalkha and Graver (2000) have opined that in the past changing rural society people showing more interest in practicing the different health behavior similar to various exploratory models propounded by the various experts. Today people are selective in choosing the therapeutic pluralism for their health needs. The authors felt the social representations of illness episodes should be mainly studied from the sick persons' point of view for generalizing the issue. Kumar (1999) in his study has examined the reproductive health care of women should be studied from the prospective of political, economical and material background of a household. He also opined that reproductive health is also depending on the gender relations within the household structure and composition in rural societies. He further wrote illness perception and behavior of the rural people depending on the previous hospital experiences, behavior of the hospital staff, the cost of the medicine, duration for healing etc.

The quality of the health service largely depends on the health infrastructure and its proper functioning. In the rural areas, infrastructures at all the levels are under question. Medical officers and health officers posted in rural areas are practically cannot work in rural areas due to the lack of various basic conveniences. In the remote villages, availability of hospital facility is very poor. Rurals have to walk a few kilometers to visit a government hospital sometime. Hence it is important that the authorities should open more Primary Health Centers (PHCs) or sub-centers in these remote villages with quality medical facilities; otherwise the health needs of the rural community will remain as unmet

Babu & Soundari (2013) and Crewell and Santow (2002) have found new cultural, behavioral and ideological aspects in case rural life is emerging due to this, rapid change in the health behavior also can be seen among the rural folk. These changes have occurred at both micro and macro level. The expert felt due to these changes new theories on the health culture are emerging now-a- days in medial sociology. Further, the authors have written that the rural health care behavior is in 'transition' today. The pre- transitional disease and class inequalities among them still persist today. Also rurals' are today focusing more on an improvised life styles and life conditions.

In a paper Madhu nagla (2003) writes a healthy person will adjust him/her self to any kind of adverse situation. Villagers think both physical and mental health is vital. For being healthy people must have proper food on time and good sleep as believed by the rural people. Also she writes village people think those who are out of any worries, difficulties etc will also be healthy. Further the author says village folk

think blessing of the God, good deeds in the previous birth, life without any sin are very vital in maintaining good health in the present life. Author also classifies health behavior of rural folk in to

1. Fatalistic ;
2. Non –fatalistic ;
3. Rationalist;
4. Non- rationalistic.

Lorber and Moore (2000) have found that rural life style have been largely influencing by the urban culture now-a-days. People are hanging in-between modern and the traditional health care system today. They are not in the position to accept modern health care completely or leaving behind traditional health care system. Their concept of disease and illness, prevention and treatment option is also changing rapidly today. He also opined any new health care service must be complemented with the local health culture. Leslie (1988) has admired the medical pluralism plays a vital role in framing the quality health programme for the rural people. The Medical pluralism he felt ‘must be a part of the primary healthcare in developing societies’. Villagers normally would have a lot of knowledge on the different healthcare systems and we have to make use of it in constructing the valid medical comprehensions. Also due to the social and cultural networks people transmits the health knowledge from on the region to the other. Kashyap (1991) opined the cultural concepts about differently disabled people are determinant about how family perceives the disability and takes steps for the curative and rehabilitation purpose in a given household. He opined since the disabled people are economically unproductive, households will not show any interest in their health care needs. Rather, many in rural parts, people are only interested in getting the different benefits in the name of the disabled member from the Govt.

Kruske and Basclary, (2004) have opined people belonging to the lower caste and class normally use traditional medicine for their health care needs in rural part. **The** authors felt using traditional medicine without standardization **is** quite dangerous to the health. Also he felt exploitation of the traditional healer and the commercialization of traditional medicines is quite unethical. Landy (1990) points out cultural sentiments need to be considered separately while dealing with effects of emotions and beliefs on the health issues. Further, he said different socio-cultural issues may not be helpful in having good physical health. Like that few illness cases may not be directly related to the biological, however potentially harmful.

Gautam, Raman and Kumar (2002) have given an interesting statistics and they found in rural parts 83% use Indian system of medicine 14% of people use Homoeopathy and 4% uses Unani and Sidda system. They suggested in the rural areas Govt. should allot more trained Ayurvedic doctors. Charterjee and Saha (2000) have found that utilization of available health services by the rural /tribal people is a big issue today. Health communication and awareness programme must be an integral part of any health interventions especially in rural areas. Ngoma (2003) has opined today even for mental problems, rural people depend more on traditional healers even today. Rural people normally neglect their mental health problems. Also the author felt mental health problem is least bothered in rural part where Govt. needs to concentrate more on this issue by opening more mental health centers.

Goldberg and Huxley (1992) have opined that from the centuries, people from the south Asia are accessing to the different pathways with various types of faith healing system. Some time parallel to each other also. Novareo(1980) has opined modern bio-medical approach is completely depends on the disease etiology only. It de-recognizes social feature causing disease as a second factor. The modern doctors have no emotional attachment towards the health culture and behavior of the rural patients. The physicians simply treating rural patients like material objects as felt by the author.

Chhotry (2003) has opined the cultural beliefs about hot and cold concept of food are very vital as pseudo-scientific belief about the onset of various disease and illness in rural parts. People believe there must be an equal balance between the hot and cold food consumption and normally, diseases /illness cause due to the humeral imbalances. People also believe disease and illness causes due to the bad blood and bad blood causes due to the consuming contaminated food as believed by the most of the rural people

Tripathi and Punitha (2005) have opined the cultural beliefs play a vital role in coping with the severe health disorders. Each culture has its own beliefs and the response to illness. Individual's background and experience will be a vital issue in any illness response. In Indian rural society, the metaphysical beliefs will play a dominant role with respect to the health seeking and the health care seeking behavior. Krause (2001) has opined "social support is the best defined operationally as a measure of social embeddedness (eg. Indicators assessing the frequency of contact with others), received support (e.g; measure of amount of tangible help actually provided by the social network members) and perceived support (e.g; subjective evaluation and supportive exchanges" (Krause, 2001).

Gould (1957) has opined that normally village people would like to use the western medicine only for the some life threatening diseases like Jaundice, Typhoid etc. due to the urbanization today village folk use the modern medicine to cure some diseases also. It doesn't mean that village folks have changed their healthcare options. Unless a valid and strong reason, rural people normally will not shift the medical care system from traditional to the other type of established health care system. Khare (1996) has distinguished with respect to the practice, ideology and cultural dichotomy among the various medical systems. He advised to use the concept of 'practiced medicine' to get the insights of the rural people about their health problems and the treatment plan. He expressed doubts about influence of both traditional and modern medicine on the changing rural health culture. He opined the western doctors and the traditional healers are using one others knowledge often without each other's notice. He felt the modern doctors practicing in the rural areas need to communicate with their patients' through the local culture, tradition and the languages for the more success.

Nanjunda (2011) has opined the modern sociological studies have largely neglected the lifestyle disorders of the village folk. Author has felt due to the migration, rapid urbanization and the changing dietary nature of the rural people, health status of the rural people has largely changed now a days. Khare (1981) has conducted a study in some villages in U.P. and has found that now-a-days villagers are moderately using the both modern and traditional medicines system for their health care needs. Hence, the village folk have a lot of faith and confidence in the pluralistic therapies in identifying and classifying the different diseases/illness.

Gangadharan and Shankar (2006) opined that in contemporary society like India traditional medicine has a wide relevance in the public health scenario. It is the time to understand how age old traditional knowledge has interviewed in the day to day culture of the rural people. Further, they suggests without having the basic theory of traditional knowledge of the rural people we cannot avoid these people from using the traditional medicines easily. Basch (1999) has opined there must be a lot of provision for economic upliftment of the rural community. If the poverty level reduced, naturally health status will be improved. If the quality of the life enhanced, then demand for modern health care facility will be reduced

Balsubramanian and others (1995) have felt effective health education can be given through the local Panchayats, weakly market centers, dormitories, art groups fairs etc. there are some evidences of using rural youths, local and religious leader in various

health care initiative programmes for the rural people. NGOs can play a vital role in convincing people for modern health care usage.

Bagdi and Soman (2005), have argued that the public health system must be upgraded in rural parts of the country. Govt. and NGOs should take culturally sensitive programmes to create awareness about health education among the rural people. There must be a comprehensive programme for community health development. Also scope for the involvement of the local folk is highly required. Leslie (1980) opined 'ideal of modern medical practice is to restrict or eliminate irregular practices, while incorporating local medical systems into larger structures that are ultimately linked to the worldwide system of medicine'. An alternative frame work views the medical system as pluralistic structures in which cosmopolitan medicine compels with numerous alternative therapies. Ken (1996) opined traditional medicine will be an alternative to the western medicine in developing societies. In addition, he felt rurals' health-seeking behaviour is exaggerated by their beliefs, knowledge and attitudes concerning the effectiveness of health care services and the success of curability of their illness.

And Paul (1986) has opined choosing a therapist or healing system by the rural people is a complex procedure and people focus on the cost factor, distance, success rate, etc. Rather than the different health programmes, orientation to preventive health care will play a vital part. Janes (1999) opined catastrophic expenditure on health can be avoided by expanding the traditional medicine system. Due to the catastrophic expenditure (spending more than 40% of their total income just for health care) majority of the people are suffering from an economic burden. Introducing generic medicines may be a good move as opined by the author.

Bhardwaz and Paul (1986) have opined choosing a healer or healing system by the rural people is a complex process and people focus on the cost factor, distance, success rate etc. Rather than the severity of the health problem, orientation to preventive health care will play a vital role. Pedersen and Barufattic (1985) have opined that framing of a bio-socio-cultural model is required for the qualitative improvement of rural health behavior in developing societies. A modest blend of both modern and traditional medicine is required.

Zaman (1983) has opined that re-orientation of the traditional healer for the emergency primary health care is required. Since rural people will strongly believe the traditional healers, Govt. should think in the direction to get their experience in introducing the modern medicine in the rural parts of the country.

Good (1994), has opined that since diseases is a natural one, it is better to consider health issue is outside of the culture. Rationality plays a vital role as a direct reaction to the dominance of the role of ecology and environment on different health and illness issues in rural parts. Contemporary social realities and dynamics of health and illness depend on the cultural context and the healing process with reference to the cross-cultural examples.

Worthington and Gogne (2011) have written that the belief and culture and its impact on the patients have a great outcome. They opined some beliefs have strongly impacts on the individuals positively. In the someway some beliefs can negatively impact on the mental and physical well being of a person. Sometime the cultural bound norms may play a vital role on individuals displaying psychiatric and somatic symptoms. Culture and religion will be very vital factors in identifying and treatment process for any health disorders in case of rural parts. The Family members, their experience and background should not be undervalued while treating the patients to recover from an illness.

Michealraja (2011)feltover the years, displacement and rapid acculturation has led to the dramatic changes in t socio-cultural and value systems of the rural people. Referable to the poor health infrastructure, high degrees of poverty and ignorance, rural residential areas are extremely vulnerable to the various health troubles. Over the centuries, the rural people developed their own medical system based on herbs and other items gathered from nature and treated locally. They have also their own system of diagnosis and curing. But those skills as well as the natural resources are fast disappearing today. Moreover, the traditional systems cannot treat or prevent many diseases that modern medicine can.

Swathi (2011) has opinedaccess to the quality health care is a problem for the physically challenged people in the rural areas. It is due to their unemployment status and other stigma. People with the physical disability generally experience greater risks of poor health and higher medical expenditure. They require the frequent medical interventions and it may require longer stay in the hospitals some time. Thus provisions for the free medical care or health insurance are of the utmost necessity for the differently challenged people today. Thus, prevention, restoration and correction of disability as well as the reclamation of these individuals are intrinsically linked to the reform of the public health schemes in rural India. Preparation of effective health care services for the differently abled persons will improve their economic and social productivity and secure family and societal concord.

Chan (2011) has opined, even today some highly educated rural people have interested to practice evidence based traditional medicines over the modern. It is not because of prioritizing one over another. It is because of workable co-existence among various system of medicines and dealing with norms, values, experience and preferences. In some rural areas even today more than one type of medicine has been working in parallel for many years. More important is the cultural values which navigate the proper distinction among various medical schemes in order to examine and optimize health behave.

Next, Leslie (1988) has opined that “All systems of medical belief and practice are empirically self confirming, people everywhere live until than finally die, and they any die once, while in the process of living they undergo various, physical, mental health illness, episodes. In short, a lot of people will recover from their health problems no matter what the healers may say or do, and they will mostly would like to give credit, to their recovery (skill) to what was done” (Leslie 1988:).

Srider (2005) has opined some of the tribe/ rural folk feels illness is an intermediate point between the life and the death. Rural people largely believe illness is due to the misunderstanding between the human beings and the nature. Sometime people believe illness also causes due to the curse of the fellowman /neighbor /friends one who cannot tolerate the progress/growth of another individual. They felt proper respect should be given to the cosmic, supernatural and ancestral beings through ritual healing regularly. Also rurals’ believe that the death is due to the result of an angry of sorcery or the evil spirit controlled by the God.

Kakar (1983) has opined that the cosmopolitan medicine is a most favored medicine for the rural people. He opined that the different elements of the western medicine should be incorporated into the traditional medicine system so that rapid improvement in the health care seeking behavior can be expected in case of rural people.

Sujatha (2003) asserted that village people are more focusing on the body system rather than the body functions. She says people from the semi city areas will consider a particular disease to any specific organ of the human body; not an entire physical body. People opines the sickness or disease causes due to the “certain tendencies and attributes” of the body system as felt by the villagers. Further, she opined that the villagers basically classify the disease and illness which causes due to bad blood inside the body.

Petzor (1996) has opined psychological problems among the rurals are quite common and he found some of the common psychological problems;

- a. Social disorder tension (occupation, finance, family issue etc.);
- b. Psycho neurotic disorders (depression, anxiety etc) ;
- c. Functional psychotic disorders;
- d. Problem with alcohol, smoking , drug etc;
- e. Psychological issues with infertility legal issues sterility, disability etc;
- f. Choric, acute and terminal illness (sources R.K Das, 2005)

Robert and Des et. al (1995) have worked about the psychological disorders among the rural folks. They felt acute poverty, male authority, economic dependence, domestic assault, depression; sexual abuse will cause more problems among women and her health requirements must be addressed more cultural rather than medically. Jena(2005) in his article has stressed the need for the positive behavior changes at all the levels. He felt care must focus on the dietary and life style of the rural community. Likewise, there must be some control on the price of food items and regular supply pure drinking water to the rural expanse. Hence, more than 70% of water born disease can be controlled. More growing of vegetables must be encouraged. Also he stressed the need of organic agriculture for the benefit of both the people and to the land.

Arvind (2009) has opined that the poor health status of the rural people largely due to the failure of monsoon, drought, agriculture failure, etc. He also watched people using more pesticides, insecticides, etc. and this also responsible for having more health related problems among the rural people. Besides, using chemical manure, modern agriculture technology causes more environment related health problems among the rural farmers. He suggest the government should promote an organic agricultural among in rural areas.

Foucault (1975) has opined the modern medical system in the west as emerged as an out-shoot of capitalist environment and gradually the medical profession got a part of dehumanization in the industrial world. Because of the dehumanization elements the rural/tribal people are not showing much interest in getting the western medical care in the majority cases.

Naveena and Nusrath (2013) opines the food security also cause a lot of health issues for the in case of poor rural people. As per the study conducted, global per capita food production has increased substantially for the past several decades in rural areas only. Due to the shortage of the required quality of food items rural people have

social and economic and health problems. Also nutritious foods required to meet their dietary need and food preferences for an active and healthy life. If not it may leads to have more health problems. However, the same report says due to the shortage of food items, rurals are prone to the different types of the diseases.

Tipping, and Segal (1995) has opined sometime people shows more tendency to meet the traditional healers before visiting any formal health care centers (PHC). In some instances, people would show interest to visit PHCs if advised by the traditional healers. Their study has shown that the various socioeconomic factors like age, societal status, education; gender plays a critical role in opting or not to opting the formal health care schemes.

Orubuloye (1999) has opined for some minor health problems rural people basically choose traditional healers only. They don't visit PHC at all. In the most cases, people visit PHCs for the health problem if it is not successfully cured by the local medical system. In an absence of such examples, people will think twice to visit the modern doctors. Some time advice given by the family members, village elders' the friend's, the patient may visit a hospital for the proper treatment. The author has also opined the gender is a recurring theme in the rural health care issue. Tipping & Segall (1995) have pined that the health seeking behavior should be considered from an individual's perception of their societal and cultural environment point of opinion. Besides, they have advised that studies must be centered on how people choose a different medical system to catch their diseases healed. They said Govt and NGO should try to create awareness so that people have to alter their lifestyle to get proper modern medical attention on time.

Singh (2005) has opined that the lack of speedy healing and the absence of trained healers are the primary facts for not opting an Indian system of medication by the majority of rural people today. He said rural people now days are showing more interest about the possible side effects of the medical pluralism.

Ramachandra and Shastri (1983) have conducted a study in Karnataka and opined that that different socio-economic group will choose the different healing systems. People will bother about the overhead cost of the treatment and distance factor is not a determinant factor for the quality health care system. Thiruvankataswamy (1988) opined people belonging to the lower economic group will choose the low quality health service in the rural parts than in urban parts. Vijayalakshmi and Swamy (2013) writes 'though political contacts yield in terms of providing access to basic health amenities or ownership of land, to the rural poor, they

do hamper the long-term interests of the rural families. Since the political aim of using these households during the election time are more impelling than any social or human interest, such favors tend to bind the beneficiaries to the benefactors forever with no actual fear on the division of the latter for the poor rural inhabitants to have upward mobility' (Vijayalakshmi &Swamy, 2013).

Further, Izhar (1989) opined the health behavior of the patients will get change based on the acceptance of a specific health care system. He opined people will choose a traditional system first and then the western medicine for their any health problem. He felt the western medicine has interrelated factors to the local medical systems. Mathew (1979) has conducted a study in Tamil Nadu and found the social and religious factors effects on health behavior and health culture of the rural family. People's opinions about the causal agents of disease/illness are a mark in choosing a particular healing/medical care arrangement. He felt various types of healers and agencies are closely intertwined in the social system of the rural people from the centuries .

Brijesh and Siddiqui (1994) have opined today utilization pattern of the health services is changing among the rural people. The Traditional medicine has become more popular even among the urban people now. Regional disparities in healthcare still continue in rural India. Low cost insurance model is the need of the hour for the rural people.

Ray (2004) and Radhakrishnan (2004) et. al opined inequality, poverty and inferior complex are some of the critical reasons why the rural people are not expressing interest in the innovative health care facility. Today the plight of the rural people has become much worse because of new economic reforms and globalization. As well, they have been largely affected because of FDI in health sector, privatization of health sectors, special economic zones and so on. All these causes a bunch of health associated troubles and ultimately because of the health problem they cannot produce the fruits of the exploitation and in the end they will be socially excluded.

Sodani (2003) has noted that rural people are also spending more on the wellness subjects like urban people. Now-a-days even traditional medicines are bit costly because of its widest use. Also he noted people will go to the modern hospitals when their disease gets worse and hence the total health expenditure will automatically increase. Sometime to save money, people directly buy the medicines from the medical shops (over the counter). All these play a vital role in choosing or not choosing any particular type of medical care.

Mandelbaum (1981) has opined while dealing with illness rural people sometime think about “trans natural curing”. Based on Indian experience he has given two notions about this;

1. Pragmatic &
2. Transcendental complex.

Next, the author felt the accordion to pragmatic view people give more concentration to solve the personal problems which causes due to illness. The transcendental view says about the long-term welfare of a community i.e., lifelong health education.

Egunjobi (1983) found factors like the number of cases cured by the hospital, suggestions extended by the friends and relatives, duration took to solve the problem, cost factor , transport system, behavior of the hospital staffs, availability of the free medicines also plays a significant role in choosing the formal health care system by the rural people. Aregbeyian (1982) has found poverty, ignorance, satisfaction with the quality of service are the major factors why rural people will wish to look for the traditional health care seeking behavior.

Macphail and Campbell (2001) have explored the societal, normative context, knowledge; attitude will take on a role in negotiating and constructing the health seeking behavior from the childhood to death. They opined in rural society’s individuals’ relationship between the health knowledge and health seeking behavior is quite poor.

Lash (2000) opined that understand the complexities involved in people’s health seeking behavior required “Reflexive Communities”. Through this people’s way of behaving, thinking and reaching final decisions can be better studied. Also it helps to find out how people take an appropriate decision using information and knowledge regarding the proper health care / treatment for their short term and long term health care needs.

Campbell and Mzaidume (2001) has noted that a drastic change/shift is needed in the health promotion activity focusing rural people today. Rather than the traditional educational approaches, better to have the modern media based health development approach with the help of local healers to create awareness about the modern health care facilities among the rural people. Health promotion activity should be a societal behavior. Further, they opined that the health seeking behavior should not be an individualistic; it must be a wider community based one.

Gonzales (1996) has found that in some community, symptoms are detected with the bio- medicine system, while the reason of illness will be dealt through a folk specialist. Cosminsky (1977) further he says ‘traditional theories of illness etiology are frequently multi factorial and multilevel (i.e. instantaneous and eventual levels of causation) which permits the use of diverse treatment resources for underlying factors and levels’. Further, as reported by Cosminsky (1980) for “Guatemalan plantation, pluralistic behavior among the tribal population group is realistic, often based on trial and error, apparent effectiveness, ambiguity of illness causation and expectation of speedy recovery”. (Kolay, 2011).

Alphonse and Valeau (2009) have opined the traditional medicines basically originated to cater the needs of the local people. Hence, blend of the local and modern medicine may get good results in case of rural health culture. Vanhollen (2003) has opined in rural areas the lower caste people are being discriminated badly. Caste and class also play a vital role in accessing the good health care system even in PHCs. Sadgopal (2009) has opined that 36% of the child delivers in the rural parts of the country will be performed by the traditional birth attendants only. They need some sort of training. Peters and Muraleedharnan (2008) have opined that the recent studies have shown that the number of untrained local healers have increased in Ayurveda /Sidda and Unani system of medicine in rural area. More fake doctors can be seen here

Tabuti et al; (2006) have opined the Govt. of Africa, Latin America etc., have shown interest to include the traditional health practice in the primary health care programme. Hence, the Govt. of India has to tackle decision to integrate the local medicinal system with the modern one for her primary health care needs focusing the rural people.

Beck and Loon (2000) have opined while studying about individual decision regarding the health seeking behavior we should also focus how people evaluate the risks involved in the particular types of illness(if not treated properly what happens next ?) and selected health care system to cure that illness. The Culture, also may be an underpin between the modern or traditional health care system. They also opined study should focus on particular health seeking behavior and their translation into risks.

Tripathy (2012) dealt with the existing disparity between tribal and non-tribal populations in health services in the state of Madhya Pradesh. Based on the secondary data, the paper covers the issues of infant and child mortality, malnutrition, death of the girl child, maternal care and health and expenditure to deal with all these issues. It

also examines the recent initiatives taken by the Government of Madhya Pradesh from gram panchayat level to improve the health status of marginalized focusing STs and SCs. It proposes to have efficient health care delivery mechanisms, including curbing loopholes in the delivery system, controlling, sensitizing health service providers at the block and Panchayats levels etc., Hence, not only the health disparity also the overall health status of the rural community can be improved he felt.

Thanni (2003); Udosen et. al (2005); Nwan kwo and Katcha (2005) have also found that a lot of variations in the knowledge, experience, treatment style, quality, success rates can be seen among the traditional healers practicing in the same areas . This matters a lot while choosing the particular type of a healer by the rural people for their health needs. Next, Naylor and Chen (2010) opined that the western medicinal system is today looking for an integrated approach whereas Jayasundara (2010) has opined the western medicine is an empirical based and the traditional medicine is a theoretical one. A blending of both may get good results for an inclusive health care.

Ventura (2000) has opined the western medicine normally attempt to separate actual health problem by relating its symptoms to a particular location of the body. It has no space for the patient's emotional needs. Gandhi et. al (2003) opined in the modern medical system the side effects is overlooked where rural people are more concerned in that issue today. Hamburg and Collins (2010) have opined today the medical systems have been personalized i.e. healing and treatment has been shifted to an individual need. Shastri (2007) has opined Ayurvedic medicines require the functional standardization for the safety reason. It is better to administer after the standardization because of the safety is concern. Today most of the rural people are using the raw medicinal plants without having ideas about its possible side effects. Patvardhan and Mashelkar (2009) have opined the modern medicines are basically getting the clinical inputs from the traditional medical system only.

Wolnsky (2005) opined today the drug companies along with the new drugs they are creating new diseases also! Meulbeld (2008) opined the traditional medicine system required an inter scientific sensitivity for the safety reason. Shankar (2004) has opined today in rural India the local healers are striving hard to retain their clients and autonomy in the changing health cultural scenario and it is due to the high influence of the growing medical pluralism. Valiathan(2009) has opined the concept of hot and cold food system is a much debated issue between the medicine and culture in the rural regions. Hot and cold concept shapes the health behavior largely as believed by the most of the health experts.

Habib and Raina (2005) has opined 'relationship between culture and medicine will decrease the scope for the various medical systems other than the western which is than incorrectly referred to be out of culture'. Bodeker and Burford (2007) opined the medical pluralism is an integrative medicine and has become a part and parcel of the public health programme across the world. Priya and Satyamala (2007) have opined women have been severely excluded from the various medical institutions. In rural parts, other household member will take the health decision on behalf of women.

Priya and Shwetha (2010) have opined even today people from the rural area are mainly depend on home remedies, folk healers and AYUSH for their immediate health care needs . Nagda (1992) has found in rural areas the local healers have dominated in curing certain diseases. Traditional healing becomes a family business for them. They will not reveal the curing secret to anyone. They are doing this work from the generations in the rural parts.

Alavi, (2007) has opined today the Unani system is more popular among the non-Muslim communities especially in the rural areas. Mueller (2001) and others have experimentally shown recovery from illness is possible from the spiritual prayer too. They have shown that addressing the spiritual needs of the patient might be useful to the any healer to cure his/her patient rapidly. Though the author's results had statistical significance it may not be applicable to all patients-experts opined. Vore et. al, (1999) in their study has found that Syphilis and Chancroids are common STDs found among rural people. They also say other types of STDs are being gradually increased among the villagers because of the various social and cultural reasons. Narayan (1994) has found that an awareness about HIV/ AIDS among the most of rural people are relatively absent because of the health illiteracy and only few rural educated youth have some awareness about AIDS/STD. Still they are showing interest towards unsafe sex when they visit city for various other reason. His study found little percentage of the rural folk has just come to know about AIDS through T.V/ NGOs etc.

Rao (1996) has concluded that nutrition problem is more prevalent in most of the rural areas. It is because of their unique socio-economic back ground. Due to the low economy they are not afforded to buy any good food items regularly. Also their age old belief towards different food has caused malnutrition problem. Singh (1995) has revealed a poor dietary pattern of the rural people is vital in causing the malnutrition problem among infants and the new mothers. Failed agriculture system, frequent drought has led to have more food shortage problem in rural areas.

Rahaman (2008) and Bedri (2001) opined women's health status should be focused carefully in rural area. It is because of more prevalence of gender disparity there. They need social capital and formal institutional support to have more improvised health seeking behavior. In the developing societies since women are being limited to only household work a strong social network support is required to access the modern health care system for women. Narayan Stress (1999) opined an appropriate community based health policy is required focusing the geographical and cultural specific issues. Also proper focus should be given regarding various problems in case formal and informal health institutions in delivering quality health care. Moreover there should be a focus on how informal health institutions are keep changing in their values and norms and the operating procedure. They opined the proper mechanism is required to include the marginalized sections and women into the network of the quality formal and inclusive health care system in rural parts.

Lash and Urry (1994) opined for an understanding health seeking behavior of an individual we should focus on his/her source of health information. We should also concentrate on the cognitive process of the people, including unspoken words, emotions and feelings, suppositions and interpretations to find out why and how people pickup a particular character of the health care organization. Also, he said the rational cognitive process and affective-emotional process involved in the health decision making process. Rahman (2000) opines in the rural society, women cannot directly access to any formal or informal health care institutions. Because it depend on the household characteristic feature, cultural background, social forces etc. Also there should be a enough number of lady health care providers in the formal healthcare institutions like Govt. hospitals. Health education must be focusd on husband and mother –in –law in rural settings.

Williamson (200) found that health promotion activities must have a strong focus on individual behavior. Further, focus is required to remove health discrepancy and health inequalities in the society including more opportunities for inclusive health care to all. Health policy must contain a lot of scope for enhancing more involvement of community in the health seeking process. The study also needs to be focused on how poverty and other issues play a vital role in excluding marginalized group away from the modern health care services intentionally. Bhopal (1980) in his study found cultural background and sensitivity towards medicine play a role in getting modern health care treatment by the patient. People who are accustomed to the traditional healing system may not be interested in getting formal health care service because of

cultural sensitivity. Hence he suggested modern doctor must be culturally sensitive while dealing with the rural patients.

Singh (2008) has given some points to improve health care system in rural/tribal settings.

1. Modern medical system should combine with the traditional medicine;
2. Geographically & cultural specific health policies are required;
3. More focus must to control communicable disease;
4. Train the local people to handle the endemics ;
5. More health awareness channels needs to be created in rural areas.

Merton (1976) has used the new concept 'sociological ambivalence' focusing how a western doctor/traditional healer should be. He felt more than a medical practitioner; a doctor should be a good friend, guide and philosopher to the patient. Doctors should not to act as a learned person. Also he said patients' must have a strong faith in the Doctors and they should treat the doctors as a friend. The author felt patients also have some sociological functions. Patients' should appear to deserve to get some treatment and social sympathy. Also he opined there should be a good understanding between doctors and the patients' throughout the treatment course.

Mackian (2003), has written "what seems to be missing in the current literature review regarding health culture and health seeking behavior is the sense of how the process of health seeking behaviour continues, overtimes space and the health system is more complex race and cannot be understood as something intrinsic to the individual/ community and there social background". Bannerji (1982) has analyzed in his article that there is a great disparity regarding the health services between rural and urban people even though rural people are proven to have infectious diseases frequently. The Government is not interested in introducing modern medicine using a cultural approach in rural parts. The author has asserted that there must be a great co-ordination is required between the trained physician working in the rural settings and traditional healers.

Even though works have been undertaken on the different facets of the health problem like socio economic causes, they are not so comprehensive. Some of the studies (Mackian, 2003) have been done at local level and some at the regional level only. Since health dynamics is highly a complex issue, researchers have got only little success in analyzing the problem from an insider's point of view. From the statistical point of view many works have been focused only on the general aspects of the health

culture and health behavior of the rural people. A lot of research work has yet to be conducted on various issues like insider's view, community perceptions on the issue, psycho-social analysis of the healers, community views on the risks of ethno medicine, and social and cultural factors that are deeply embedded with the rural health problems.

If we go through the current existing literatures regarding different prospective of rural health dynamics it seems to be having a few major drawbacks

- 1) Lack of empirical research on rural health culture;
- 2) Needs still better utilization of the field data from the Indian rural perspective;
- 3) Lack of proper understanding of the problem through sociological point of view ;
- 4) A lot of emphasis only to general aspects of the health behavior and ;
- 5) No much work on rural health culture and health behavior since 1985 onwards in India

Regarding rural health manpower Somashekaraiah, Rangegowda and O.D.Heggade (2011) write 'There should be forecasting of manpower needs depending upon the requirements at least ten years in advance keeping in view the difficulties in developing personnel for the health sector. Manpower planning should be based on the proper mix of different categories of health workers. Also Training programmes for health manpower should be formulated to make them need based, task oriented and relevant to the conditions of the country. They should be directed towards making the manpower relevant to the needs of the health services so as to cover the rural people and the underserved urban poor Somashekaraiah, Rangegowda and Heggade (2011). The health manpower planning process should not concentrate on the personnel and training resources of the public sector only but also take into account the private sector and charitable sector'

Balse and Naik (2011) writes the Government health care centers are having problems like shortage of resources. The complexity to access the health care in rural areas is additional compounded by an insufficient numbers of health care people. In the view of the poor health care infrastructure available in the rural areas, there is a requirement to the fresh review the rural environment 'to appraise the deprived functioning of the value delivery system in the health care arena. The difference between the rural and urban health care management services is mounting at disturbing rate which, when seen and compared, leaves the spectator surprised and worried.

The review of existing literatures on the health culture and health behavior reveals that an extensive research is required to fill up some of the gaps related to changing different perspectives of the rural health problem. It is found that there is a rising socio-economic inequality between rural and urban population. Essential inequality in health care reimbursement between rural and urban is augmented by the fast but uneven economic expansion that rural India has witnessed in the last few years. The high occurrence of illness cuts into the financial plan of rural people in two dissimilar ways i.e.

1. Rural people need to use up big amount of money for treatment of diseases and at the same time
2. They are not in a state of affairs to go for faster income production to meet unusual and an unexpected health care expenditure. The health culture and traditional bound health behavior are effecting like anything on the rural people.

Research gaps

All these studies shows about few research gaps. At the outset the overall review process says no data is found about how socio-culture and attitudes reproduce the essential world view and values of a health culture, such as how we relate to nature, other people, time, being, society versus community, adults versus elders and independence versus dependence, rural or urban. Also no data found that how illness behavior determines, who is susceptible to illness and who agrees to become a patient and who will certify that focusing rural areas. Since because it is only about one third of the ill will see a physician in rural parts. no data found that how to decide about how one will behave as a patient and what it means to be ill to him/her, Who and what affects final decisions about a patient's needed treatment and who makes the decisions at family level/community level in rural parts. We must also focus on the special meaning of medicines and how and why diet issues requires particular attention in the rural parts it seems. Also we need to have data about how physical pain and psychological suffering varies from culture to culture some time religion to religion and affects the attitudes and effectiveness of care-givers as much as of the patients. Religious beliefs and attitudes about health and illness, which have many cultural variations, are particularly pertinent to hospital-based treatment needs some more clarifications. through new research. Linguistic and cultural interpreters can be necessary; they are more obtainable than realized, though there are differences in their use. We need more data the effect of medical pluralism under globalization . This study will fill all these research gaps

CHAPTER IV
HEALTH CULTURE, HEALTH
BEHAVIOR AND MEDICAL
PLURALISM

Like there are many more definitions about the term culture. Culture is a core concept in Sociology. It is used in various ways by the specialists in Sociology. It is opined that that the cultural is a social heritage, spectrum of civilization which is transmitted through the tradition over the period of time. Systemic investigation of rural health culture has gained a vital consideration in medical sociology. Studies have been conducted to get the core concept of rurals' healing behavior and the systematic reveal of their ethno-medical system. Studies have been focusing on cultural perception, cultural labialization, culture experience and cultural communication about illness ideology and therapeutic behavior of the rural folk for various health issues. However, socially constructed medical roles in enhancing particular health behavior and cross societal similarities and changing patterns in such behavior also been noted by the certain studies. It is also revealed that medical pluralism and health seeking behavior of a one family in a village some time may be followed by the rest of the village . This kind of diffusion may have similarities and variables with respect to health seeking behavior of the people of the neighboring village also. Sometime, lifestyle of the particular person, how seriously he considers his health problem and frequency of occurrence of the particular health problem play a significant role in shaping his relation to the medicine. Experts have explained how cultural factors lead to perpetuating many health problems among the social disadvantaged groups especially marginalized sections in the rural India. They found socio cultural factors including the dominant caste system, inferiority complex among the margins, ethnic and gender discrimination is responsible for the perpetuation of various health discriminations and heath behaviour.

Health culture and Health behaviour

"it is very unlucky that the bulk of the social scientists, who have worked in the field of health culture of the rural populations in India, have been overenthusiastic in discussing the superstitions, health beliefs, and practices of these people, and that they have not paid adequate attention to the powerful social, economic, and political forces which had been instrumental in causing the delay and degeneration of their health culture" Fali (2006)

Health has been defined as a condition of dwelling in one's own pleasure-self i.e *Svasmin Tisthatiti Svastha*. In addition, a total description of a healthy state of the body or health has been furnished by Ayurvedic seer Susruta. According to him, "a person having balanced temperaments (*Vatta, Pitta and Kapha*), having thirteen fires as well as seven (Dhatus) component elements, continuous outflow of residuals and whose soul, mind and organs are happy is called healthy". In other words, a person should be healthy including physically, mentally as well as spiritually (Jha,2007).

What is Culture:

Culture: Culture is a core part of any human civilization, without culture we cannot assume this human society. We cannot study human behavior without knowing his/her cultural background . In more general definition we can say Culture is a total sum of tradition, customs, values, beliefs, behavior ideas, rituals institutions etc.

Paul, (1955) write

"If you wish to help a community improve its health, you must learn to think like the people of that community. Before asking a group of people to assume new health habits, it is wise to ascertain the existing habits, how these habits are linked to one another, what functions they perform, and what they mean to those who practice them" (Paul, 1955).

According to Keesing (1958) the basic assumptions of culture are ;

1. Its' elements originating through innovation spread through diffusion.
2. It can be studied as a regional phenomenon
3. Cultural tends to be patterned
4. A cultural is subject to change
5. Culture is nothing but symbolic.

Basically the health culture is comprehensive including attitude and traditions of a society which have evolved in endeavoring to administer its common predicament, an

element of which apprehension the incidence of illness and diseases and require for medical treatment (Enos and Sultan, 1977). By assessing the uniqueness of culture of a society, we can comprehend the health care system. Nagla (2007) opines “First, most of the beliefs and customs are cultural when they are quite commonly shared by the people of the society”. We have a popular of cultural traits with health beliefs and customs shared by a huge number of people; and we have abundant sub-cultures, large groups of people who share somewhat diverse health beliefs and customs (Nagla, 2007).

Like there are many more definitions about the term culture. It is opined that that the cultural is a social heritage, spectrum of civilization which is transmitted through the tradition over the period of time. Sociologists have opined like other cultural elements, health culture also undergoes change over a period of time. Cultural diffusion, cultural innovation and external interventions are the major tools in the changing health culture of a community (Sahu, 1979).

Culture is a core concept in Sociology. It is used in various ways by the specialists in Sociology. The only problem with this concept is that there is very little agreement about how to define the term culture universally. The scientific use of the term culture corresponding to the original meaning of the culture which is derived from the Latin words COLETRE (to cultivate and instruct) and CULTUS (cultivation and training). In its broadest sense culture is a cultivated behavior i.e, man’s learned or socially transmitted behavior (Srivatsava, 1992)

The general sociological meaning of the term ‘culture’ includes;

1. ‘That complex whole which includes knowledge, belief , art, morals, law, custom, and any other capabilities and habits acquired by man as a member of society’ (Tylor, 1871).
2. ‘All the historically created designs for living explicit and implicit, rational, irrational and non-rational, which exist at any given time as potential guides for the behavior of men’(Kluckhohn and Kelly, 1945)
3. ‘The mass of learned and transmitted motor reactions, habits, techniques, ideas and values and the behavior they induce’ (Kroeber, 1948)
4. ‘The man made part of the environment’ (Herskovits, 1955)

Fali (2006) has given the overall impact of culture on diseases including :

- “Culture patterns diseases ;

- Culture produces personality types, especially vulnerable to certain kinds of illnesses;
- Culture may perpetuate malfunctioning by rewarding it in certain prestigious roles;
- Culture may produce psychiatric disorders ;
- Culture may impose certain diseases through proper sanctions and structure on acceptable behavior;
- Cultures may produce psychosomatic disorders”

(Sources: M. Dari Fali (2006) ‘A Study of Health Culture of Lambdas’ : Web published Ph.D Thesis , University of Hyderabad –India)

3.a HEALTH CULTURE

In a broader definition given by the WHO ‘health culture means a set of cultural beliefs about health and illness that forms. Health culture is the basis for the health seeking and health promoting behavior, the institutional arrangements within which that behavior occurs and the impacts of socio-economic, political and physical context for their beliefs and institutions’. Some of the western anthropologists in their writings have opined even though western medicines are having a high rate of success it has not been accepted by the majority Indian rural people because of their unique and historical health culture. However, some of the western epidemiologists have proved that how rural people can be convinced to adopt the western medical system without affecting their inherited health culture and belief. Cultural response to the different health problems forms an interacting subsystem within the overall general cultural system. Health culture is an invariable determining factor of ‘communities’ understanding of health and illness.

Fali (2006) writes “The notion of health culture refers to a sub culture within a totality of population. It includes a vast complex that means socio-cultural aspects of health, the beliefs and practices relating to health and disease, health seeking and health care seeking behavior, the diagnosis and treatment methods, the healers, concepts and organization of medical system etc. Each society irrespective of degree of social organization, and design of culture, has its own sub-culture called health culture, because it is the beliefs and practices these people share to conceptualize the health and disease and produce the appropriate cultural methods to remove the pain and suffering. Health culture stress on the nature of illness as it is conceived by the people , their own methods and criteria of classification of disease, the causes and

cures, types of therapists that search for to lessen illness and their skills and social roles, defensive measures, ethno-medicine, traditional healers survival of western medicine in rural part, and finally the ethno-psychiatry” (Fali ,2006) .

(Sources: Dari Fali, (2006) ‘A Study of Health Culture of Lambdas’: Web published Ph.D Thesis , University of Hyderabad –India).

According to some of the medical sociologist’s health culture may be explained as an acquired health behavior to separate it from the domain of health seeking behavior due to the physiological stimulations. Sometime acquired health behavior may pass from generation to generations. It is learned that the health culture of one society may get transmitted to another society. Banerji (1982) has opined “health culture and health behavior is a sub cultural complex of the whole way of life style of the community” ‘further he redefined that sub cultural complex includes both subjective and objective environments an external interventions in the action of an internal environment of human beings in a given context’. It may include both material and non-material culture of the community at any given point of time.

Kannuri (2005) has opined the socio-religious medical reactions to the different illness and disease in numerous forms including the beliefs, customs, and tradition established, conducted and approved constitute the ‘health culture’.

Experts have opined Today health culture is keep changing gradually because

1. Changing in health concept
2. Changes in health emphasis
3. Interventions of external agencies on health issues

Health culture is the core concept of Medical Sociology or Medical Anthropology and it may significantly helpful in deepening our insights into the vital inter-relationship between culture and health. However some sort of variations amongst Sociologists, can be looked upon health culture in the recent time.

We have two approaches to study the health culture;

- 1.Realistic and 2. Idealist approaches.

The realistic approach looks upon health culture as an attribute of the social life of man. The realistic approach understood the health culture as an attribute of social life of mankind. According to this view health culture is inseparable from the real human behavior in society and it is a standardized social procedure. However, experts felt individual differences and variations within the concept and perception of health

culture need scientific consideration without fail. Regarding idealistic view the health culture is conventional understanding of health behavior of the community towards specific diseases or illness. This approach opines particular health behavior of a particular community passes through the generations as a social heritage (Sinha and other, 2002).

Nagda,(2007) writes “Every culture, irrespective of its simplicity and complexity has its possess beliefs and practices concerning disease and evolves its own system of medicine in order to care for diseases in its own way. Rural people practice different type of diagnosis and treatments during illness /disease. In rurals, intrusion of super-natural agency is predominantly strong in circumstance of health and disease. The different deities and spirits are associated with different types of disease. Rural communities have specific Gods and Goddess for treatment of diseases, calamities, treatment of diseases of cattle, snake-bite, dog-bite and so on. All these deities have their own respective sphere and fields” (Nagda, 2007).

Health culture is a very wider concept as it includes various health problems, occurrence, medicine, healing, beliefs, norms values side effects, habits, rituals all these issues works in a given set of system which together known as health culture. Again Banerji defined ‘health culture means the health behavior of the people in the context of the availability and accessibility of health institutions and health care facilities and their cultural meaning and cultural perceptions on several health problems existing in a given socio-economic condition’ (Banerji, 1982).

It is generally opined disease is not merely a bio-physical event. It cannot be cut off from the main socio-cultural setting. The discernment of the disease and its cure assumes dissimilar magnitude in diverse societies. Cultural patterns and characteristic ways of living give substances to the process in which disease is apparent, uttered and reacted. To some degree, the cultural framework defined what circumstances are documented to evaluate and identify the illness situations (Mechanic, 1978). ‘Communication of individuals, disease and society is decisive for the entirety perceptive of health and disease phenomena’. An interactional part of the issue has changed the medical science in contemporary times. Though, the biological brake down is greatly accountable for the disease yet its’ interface with the socio-cultural environment cannot be overlooked (Nagla, 2007).

The complete way of life of any community including social, economic and religions conditions forms a vital section of issues along with the biological and environment factors shapes the nature, intensity, occurrence, frequencies and

distribution of the various health problems in any given society. Further, the holistic cultural reply of the community for various types of health disorders confronted by it specifies the way. Each community member perceives various ways of handling different health disorders. It is found that the “total health behavior of a community is largely founded by an existing health culture and all these different elements together constitute an interacting sub-system within the entire cultural system” (Sahu, 1991).

Benerji (1981) opines that “interaction between certain aspects of the way of life of a community - its culture - and the environment, in the widest sense of the term determines the state of health and disease in a community”. It means that the culture of a community determines its health culture - that is the cultural meaning of the health problems of the community, and the means the community adopts to deal with.

Coffey(2014) in her article writes regarding why latrines socially unacceptable? “Firstly, many people think that having such a latrine near the house would be ritually polluting. Second, because cleaning feces is associated with “untouchables” (the lowest group in the caste system), emptying latrine pits when they are full is an important concern to potential latrine owners. But these groups have changed their concept today. Muslims in rural India are often an exception to this rule. Ideas about ritual purity and pollution have different cultural meanings for Muslims, and they are more likely to build and use the kinds of simple, affordable latrines that save lives in the rest of the developing world”. It means how culture is associated with the concept of toilet

It is popularly believed that health culture has its own existence and has no boundary too. Health culture is completely independent and more precisely an autonomous component of a society. No external force can easily intervene in it, and health culture has its own norms and value orientation in a chronological order. Further, we can say health culture is also one form of socialization which helps a person in cultivating his/her own perception on diseases, illness, sickness and health practices; during the different stages of his/her development. Naturally an individual will develop own health behavior with the due influence of his/her surroundings, ecology, and daily experiences.

This health behavior of a particular person will keep on developing from the childhood until his/her death to form a particular health culture. All organic needs of a human being will act as stimulating agencies and helps to acquire or to frame an individual health behavior for the life. Health culture is not an impersonal one. It is an

objective and shared like other social experiences. It is deemed that communities' health behavior largely influences by a cultural specific issues in a particular institutional settings. Truly speaking health culture has an existence of its own. More precisely it is an autonomous and independent entity. During the process of socialization health culture will be an integrated part of an individual and it helps in shaping once own health seeking behavior or action in due course of his/her life time.

Bir (2002) opined, “ In fact, the organic needs that operate the internal environment or system of an individual such as needs for food, sex, protection etc are the sources of stimulus force or motivation for an independent action of the system of health culture”. Whereas Hassan (1967) opined “The level of satisfaction of these needs takes place in accordance with the values of health culture acquired by man as a member of the community or society” .

Truly speaking the health culture is an integral part of an entire culture of any community. Geertz (1973) has opined that each and every community will think their health behavior is ‘simultaneously models of /and models for reality’. Each and every health culture of the community will consist of norms and practice for “translating signs into symptoms for thinking sytmatologies to etiologies and interventions and for using the evidence provided by interment to confirm translations and legitimize outcome” (Comrof, 1982; Lock, 1982; Nichter, 1980; Mishra,2006).

In rural parts, life styles, dietary pattern, social norms are deeply rooted in their tradition and culture. Chaterjy (1993) felt that ‘there are more pronounced in the remote villages where outside influences are quite minimal’. Hence, it is found difficult to introduce the western medicine in majority Indian villages. This is how the socio-cultural issues influence on the health behavior of the community. Since the rural part is a multi-cultural society and some time different religion also effects on each other's health beliefs.

The important point made is that cultural influence on health has been taking place since history, and there are some common roots in the problems that society faces in a given period of their histories. Rural people are struggling as a result of a common legacy of authoritarianism and various exploitations in the name tradition and customs, which had been modified through a basic process of social, economic and cultural change over the period of time. Societal norms on health issues are the most vital while assessing the effect of general culture on health and illness of a particular community.

There are some studies to show that changing the new socio-economic process will also influence on the pattern of the existing health culture and health seeking behavior in the rural areas. When changes happen in the health culture, health behavior will also get changed. Thereby health status of that particular community will also get changes gradually. Hence, perception and attitude of the community towards different health problems will get new shape and frame in due course of time. Finally, it leads to the formation of new health behavior when they face such health disorders in the future (Banerji, 1986; Chaterjy, 1993). When the health culture is strongly influenced by external agencies (level of education, migration, role media. etc) in a particular geographical area, people in that area will also develop new health behavior. This adopted new health behavior will resolve the various health problems within the given ecological settings without much effort (Parson 1963). This type of forced change in the health behavior of a particular community sometime will be explicit and some time will be implicit also.

The concept of health culture differs in different societies and largely depends on cultural practices. Some of the studies have shown that the health culture concept in rural parts are largely influenced duly by the generation of gaps. The concept of health and illness normally develops out of the experiences in a particular culture or communities, for particular social groups in particular sets of circumstances. Experts opined 'health problem is how to articulate a standard, or divergent standards for the beginning of a moral and ethical reflection on cultural health practices that takes into account but does not privilege our own cultural presuppositions'. Some time in rural part interpretation of the health issues concept is largely based on the cast factors (Bhardwaj and Paul, 1986; Mishra,2006).

Kanuri (2005) writes

“Culture determines to a large degree not only the kind and incidence of disease/illness but also the way people perceive, explain and treat diseases as well as the mode in which they react to the delivery of modern medicine. Thus, culture is an unchanging determining feature of a community understands of health and illness. The socio-religious medical reply to illness in different forms-including the belief forms recognized, conducts approved – make the actual health culture. As a division of this health culture, members of each community tend to construct a specific belief frame relating to several illnesses /diseases recognized by them”

Further, he opines the symptom identification, assessment and health decisions connected to recovery of health recuperation are disposed by belief frames connecting

to disease caution, multiply, diagnosis, and curing. Understanding the role of health culture should be examined as a sub cultural complex of the whole way of life. Rural health cultural will normally have a lot of dimensions including changing social, economical, political and historical etc. Rurals' health culture is a part of their social system as well an adaptive system. Understanding their health beliefs always should be within the boundary of holism which is illuminated by their local medical system. Anthropologists felt health culture is a product of actions adopted by the pool of people over the period of time. It is argued that rural health culture should not be underscored as just superstitious.

Thankar (2011) opined that that “rural people are typically subjugated, deselected and susceptible to a range of diseases including malnutrition, morbidity and mortality etc. All these problems are due to poverty, illiteracy, ignorance of the causes of the disease, hostile environment, poor sanitation etc”. Examining of health culture of these communities belonging to the poorest and vulnerable strata of society is tremendously required and indispensable to resolve their access to diverse health services obtainable in the current social set up. It would be significant input for the growth and development of a community thus to social and economic development of the country.

Rural people who live in remote areas are more prone to have various diseases because of insufficient access to quality health care facilities due to lack of communication and required health facilities. Many rural focused health programmes have not been successful because of lack of local cultural components in the programme. The biggest problem is lack of space for emotions, practice beliefs, proactive behavior associated with various types of diseases/illness. It is opined that culturally accepted and culturally meaningful health programme for the rural area is very essential today.

Within the context of health culture, health has been considered less as an abstract state and more as a means to an end which can be expressed in functional terms as a resource which permits people to lead an individually, socially and economically productive life. Health is a resource for everyday life, not an object of living. It is a positive concept emphasizing social and personal resources as well as physical capabilities (Goel, 2002).

This issue is not only country like India even in US is the same. NRHA in web says ‘the hurdles faced by health care providers and patients in rural areas are vastly dissimilar than those in urban areas. Rural Americans face a sole mixture of issues

that make disparities an discrimination in health care not found in urban areas. Economic factors, cultural and social differences, lack of education , lack of gratitude by legislators and the sheer separation of living in remote rural areas all conspire to impede rural Americans in their fight to lead a normal, healthy life’.

3.b HEALTH SEEKING BEHAVIOR:

Shaikh (2008) writes

“The notion of studying health seeking behaviours has evolved with the course of time and has eventually become a tool for understanding how people utilize with health care systems in their respective socio-cultural, economic and demographic conditions. All these behaviors can be divided at various institutional levels: family, community, health care services and the state”.

It is opined that health behavior of a community is closely related how they are going to perceive actual meaning of diseases or illness to them in the time and space Banerji (1982) has stated “ it is the document of the complex whole including social-cultural perception and meaning of various health/illness problems and history of its nature of curing pattern of an individual/communities in the context of available, accessible and affordable health care institutions is named as health behavior”. As we are aware people across the globe have general and specific behaviors related to health and illness that originates from their various cultural forces and individual experiences and the historical perceptions. It is a well known fact that health seeking behavior refers to the series of corrective proceedings that patients /individuals carry out to rectify apparent ill health.

Mackian (2003) writes

“Basically health behavior is initiated with indication, description, upon which an approach for treatment action is planned. Health seeking behavior more generally drawing out of the factor which enable or prevent people from making healthy choices in either their life style behavior or their treatment plan”.

Health seeking behaviors clearly differ for the same individual or communities when they face different illnesses/disease situation. Health seeking behavior is not an individualistic. It is more deeply rooted in communities’ inherited health culture itself. Health behavior is more a dynamic, an interactive and a collective and it is a cultural specific. A number of social-origination models have been developed to study the health behavior patterns (Konnar and Norman, 1996). Medical Anthropologists have opined that in order to understand how people choose their health behavior we need to

understand the underlying, unrevealed, unconscious feelings, emotions and assumptions as much as possible. A number of studies (Shaikh,2008;Kulkarni and others, 2013) have shown health seeking behavior vary depending on the factors such as age, gender, occupation, autonomy, habitat, education, economic status, severity of illness, availability of physical infrastructure, type and cadre of health provider, etc.

Health behavior is a type of social behavior mainly influenced by various socio-cultural issues. Understanding a disease/illness is not a medical subject rather, it is mainly relying on the common and shared information of the concerned community. Customs traditions, social practices etc will add to the total pool of community's knowledge about health and illnesses. These social aspects of health, shapes the strong base for recognizable systems of health care in any given society (Dalal and Ray,2009). Health behavior also includes health beliefs which specify specific beliefs which promotes individual to adopt certain health behavior. Normally healthy behavior will be in the context of socially, politically and culturally surrounded environment of any individual. Health seeking behavior is a process of responding to illness or seeking proper treatment. It involves many steps and cannot be explained by a single model of health seeking behavior in a multicultural society. However it is known fact that health seeking behavior can be positively understood in terms of an individual's perception of their given socio-cultural environment (Mackian, 2003) .

Medical epidemiologists have opined like other cultural elements, health behavior also undergoing many changes over a period of time. Cultural diffusion, cultural infusion, cultural innovation and other external interventions are the major tools in changing the health behavior of any community. Anthropologists felt 'cultural response to the different health seeking behavior forms an interacting subsystem within the overall health system'. The study of health behavior of a community would be very vital in understanding the concept of health and illness of that particular society. As experts felt today health seeking behavior is undergoing a vital change in many rural parts because mainly,

1. Changes in the health and illness concept;
2. New emphasis on the curing system

Various studies have proved that the health behavior is not only depending on inherited social and cultural tradition of a community. Also it is depending on expositing an individual to the different situations, the material human and social capital of a community and the different health care system available locally. Further,

it is found that individual's health seeking behavior depends largely on his/her engagement with the local environment or structures which surrounds them. Till now only few studies have been done on the issues how the local structural issues impacts on the health seeking behavior conceptualizing it as a socio-cultural phenomena rather than an issues residing in a particular individual (Mackian, 2002). Generally it is believed that an existing health system (tradition/ modern) has more influence on the current health seeking behavior especially in the rural parts. As the health culture become a part and parcel of any community, it will become the basic stimulating force adopting suitable health seeking behavior to encounter any type of new health disorders (Menon, 2000; Panikar and Soman, 1984).

Change in the health seeking behavior is because health itself represents a separate area marked by the diversity of new health beliefs and practices. Studies which highlights the 'end point'- i.e. utilization of the formal system, or health care seeking behavior); and those which put emphasis on the 'process' i.e illness response, or health seeking behavior) (Kroeger,1983; Gester, 1984). Das (2005) has opined medical anthropologists so far have given most findings with regard to illness, though sickness, connecting disease and /or illness is their actual field of study. In their final analysis medical sociologists have opined 'there is a substantial interdependence and interpenetration between the sphere of individuals and their existing or changing health culture'. Das(2005) opines when illness is classified as the course through which troublesome behavioral and biological symptoms continues, cultural manifestations imitate the human capacity to widen the health behavior patterns in the milieu of each and every ecological slot.

Hyder and Morro (2005) have opined health behavior has some common notions like (quoted)

- It is shared ideas, meanings, and values about health and illness;
- It is socially and culturally learned, not genetically transmitted;
- Patterns of behavior that are guided by these shared ideas, meanings, and values;
- frequently exists at an unconscious level;
- continuously being modified through "lived experiences"

Menon (2002) writes rural health issue is a complex one. A lot of visible and invisible factors have been associated with the people's health behavior and culture. He says local cultural norms regarding the health aspects play an essential role in

framing various rural health policies. Researcher should concentrate on the local economic situation, geography and gradual changing of the society, and loosing bonds among the family members etc. Also researchers should try to get culturally and geographically specific data while analyzing the health behavior and culture. Experts opined that rather than focusing on his/ her general health better focus on the health seeking behavior.

Since 1960s researches have started to work on developing models to assist or to predict the health seeking behavior. Few experts have suggested two document approaches to study the health seeking behavior of the pople.

1. Pathway model
2. Determinate model.

In case of pathway model focus will be given for steps involved regarding how people take actions when they fell ill. In case of determinate model focus will be on different factors involved while taking such action which leads to the final decision about a particular type of healing treatment plan. Experts opined that health behavior cannot be classified in many domains like, social, cultural, political or biogenic, etc. Health behavior is also a part of medical science to complete understanding of knowledge, attitude, value, norms and actions in reply to symptoms of illness/ disease. It is found that Individuals response to any diseases/ illness will be largely based on Two vital factors.

1. Psychological perception of an affected individual;
2. Severity of the disease and action to solves that disease/illness

Health Seeking Behavior (HSB) generally focused on illness perception and health beliefs. Also it would be vital to study the Health Seeking Behavior, from the community point of view. It is also opined that while studying HSB we need to focus on the patients' decision making within a given social and the cultural context. Sometime HSB will be more depending on the health education receiving through various formal and informal channels. A few experts have opined that studying HSB should be beyond the traditional factors and should cover the therapeutic pluralism which is available in that particular geographical area. Greenly and Annear (2010) have opined that the social and institutional factors play a complex role in shaping HSB of any individual. Also HSB needs to be studied from various circumstances including households, ecology, community and the medical system. In addition they opined HSB would be the result of both external and internal factors including propels' attitudes, daily custom, decision concerning health maintenance, food habits and food serving practices etc. Shaikh **(2008) writes** "the concept of studying health

seeking behaviors has evolved with the course of time and has in the end become a tool for sympathetic how people employ the health care systems in their respective socio-cultural, economic and demographic circumstances. All these behaviours actually define social position of health and provide a better considerate of the disease process. It is therefore vital to study the impacts of all the determinants, such as ethnicity, education of the mother, gender of child, lifestyles, or economics of a community’.

Conceptual Model Studying Health Seeking Behavior (Modified From Anderson)

Adopted from Syeed Masud Ahmed (2005),

Fig. 11

Sources:

1.Andersen (1995) Revising the behavioral model and access to medical care :Does it matter?, *Journal of health and social behavior* ,36 2.Syeed Masud Ahmed (2005), *Exploring Heath Seeking Behavior of Disadvantaged Population in Rural Bangladesh*, Karolinska University press Sweden

3.c Gender Inequalities and the Health Seeking Behavior:-

Gender refers to “the array of socially constructed roles and relationships, personality traits, attitudes, behaviours, values, relative power and influence that society ascribes to the two sexes on a differential basis. Gender is relational—gender roles and characteristics do not exist in isolation, but are defined in relation to one another and through the relationships between women and men, girls and boys” (Health Canada. Health Canada's gender-based analysis policy; 2000)

It is found that the gender inequality is a common phenomenon in all the societies across the globe. In developing countries, because of the vulnerability position she is being discriminated in accessing the quality health care service. This is severely impacting negatively on women's health. Men are more accessible to the different health care system when compared to a woman in rural areas. Also a male can go for the quality medical care when compare to a women more easily. All these because, men have more control on the resources than a women in general. Also women have to overcome various social, economic, cultural barriers to get any kind of quality medical treatment in the rural parts. Society is giving more importance to the health of a male member. In developing societies especially in the rural areas, the head of the house hold (husband or mother in law) will take a final decision about any health care issues of a woman in that household. This is where the real problem lies. Society shows less importance to the women's' health issue due to the gender bias.

Nash and Gilbert (1992) have given obstacles which women facing in getting the quality health care in rural parts.

1. Institutional barriers;
2. Socio-economic barriers;
3. Cultural issues;
4. Educational barriers

Tanner and Vlassoff (1998) have given three important risk factors why women are being discriminated in getting proper health care.

1. Personal factors;
2. Social and reproductive activities;
3. Economic/productive activities

However, reproductive health care is an exception which is highly medicalized today. Bias about women health has lead abstain from accessing the quality health service. There is a need to have a gender sensitive health programmes focusing women in rural, parts. Women involved in various invisible activities like

cooking, childcare, maintains etc will be treated as an unpaid/ unnoticed jobs. Also women have less access to the economic resources in the family. For every health problems, women have to be depended on men to meet the cost. However, in some cases, women cannot demand preventive health care also (ex. AIDS/STD etc) Negotiations for safe sex are often difficult also. Absence of safe sex also leads in having STD related diseases among women. Not only family, some time various health institutions also discriminating women in quality health care seeking.

3.d HEALTH CARE SEEKING BEHAVIOR:

Health care seeking behavior is quite differing from the Health Seeking Behavior. Health care seeking behavior is an aspect of a general behavior. In Health *care* seeking behavior, people diverge in their readiness to look for the professional help from the various healthcare services. Some will go willingly for the treatment as a precaution; other will go if they get any illness/diseases or some time when ill health gets more serious. It is found that the models of health care seeking behavior are multifaceted and vibrant. People do not look for one type of health care resources and differ in their health behaviors according to the type of disease/illness. The health *care* seeking behavior is also influenced by an inherited belief of causation of certain diseases/illness (UNICEF, 2009). The health care maintaining behaviour involves a good deal of the creativity, as it requires the divergent and convergent use of an alternative survival skills. Next, the divergent skills include a range of adaptive responses or treatment methods for the similar disease.

Health care seeking behavior has two vital issues;

- 1) Barriers between the patient and the health services
- 2.) Identification of pathway to the regular health care system

Since the rural society is more a multicultural, the health seeking behavior differs from the caste to caste and class to class. People belonging to the twice born caste will observe a dual type of health seeking behavior. Religion is also greatly impacting on determining the type of health care seeking behavior in the rural scenario. If required, the Hindu patients' will visit a Muslim quack whereas the Muslim patients' will visit a Hindu quack. The Nomadic quacks also found significant in curing various ailments in the rural parts. Sometime the rural people will also visit a tribal healer for curing. In rural settings, various social groups play a vital role. Some time lower caste people will not visit the quacks t belonging to a higher caste. In the same way, people belonging to a higher caste will not visit a quack belonging to the lower caste.

Analyzing the effects of the caste system in India in the context of health, Oliver (2005) adds that the compartmentalization of groups of people on the basis of a caste hierarchy with a well-defined traditional occupational role for each of the caste group has resulted in health inequalities in rural parts. The upper class took more advantages of education, urbanisation and industrialization. Among the lower caste groups, because of their economic dependency upon the upper caste groups, health problems are more prevalent among the weaker sections of the society because of low social economic profile.

Mackiam also (2003) has opined

“Using the lens of social capital to view and study health seeking care behaviour and its relationship with health systems development. Social capital may have effects at two levels on the health of populations. Firstly, it has been shown to have a direct effect on the health of communities’. Secondly, the act of participation in networks or community centered projects has been demonstrated to have an indirect effect on the health seeking behaviour of participant”

Jena (2005) writes it is learned that every human being is an inventive social creature, well trained with an ample option of adaptive responses to the varying health situation. Some of them are phylo-genetically premeditated and created by learning. He further opines a broad variety of social responses, like co-operation and interpersonal message also come into play while adopting the suitable healthcare seeking behavior. From a border viewpoint, these responses will help to keep up the well-being of an individual, protecting themselves against any diseases/illness (Jena , 2005).

It is generally felt that following issues needs to be focused while studying health care behavior;

- Redefining the health and illness from the rural sociological point of view;
- Need a new sociological explanation and evaluation of the relationship among gender, class and ill health;
- Cultural definitions of health, illness and medicine ;
- Cultural definitions of healthy life style;
- Sociological thinking to assess person experiences and understanding different medical practices;
- Appraise the impact of chronic illness on the concept of self identify and social identity;

- Studying the long term impact of the particular health behavior on the health culture;
- Studying the specific impact of a particular health behavior on the society (in the long term);
- Role of local medicinal system and its validity ;
- Why people are not interested in the western medicine ;
- The role of the local healers and his/her cultural space

Ethno-medicine will be largely shaped by the different socio- cultural, biological and ecological factors. It is found that the values, beliefs, practice, duly associated with health and illness in the rural world is not just connected to the treatment of the individual rather than individual will be taken as an integral identity of an entire socio-medical system. In various rural societies, we can witness for a wealth of folk medicines to cure the various diseases. (Das, 2004) opines largely patients’ as a part of the culture, usually develops “social institutions, etiological hypothesis and healing techniques to encounter the social, cultural and other dislocations caused by an illness induced disability”.

Sociologists endeavored to focus a light on the various aspects of health care issues in rural India. According to them, several economic and social factors due the various globalization issues are responsible for the prevalence of the large-scale health issues among the underprivileged sections of the rural society. Poverty is the important cause too. Also an old traditions and social customs do supplement for the prevalence of various health problems.

Breaking Down Determinants of Health care Seeking Behavior **Tab-8**

Category	Determinant	Details	Sphere
Cultural	Status of Women	Elements of Patriarchy	Cultural property
Social	Age and Sex		
Socio-Economic	Households Resources	Education Level Maternal occupation Marital Status Economic Status	Informal
Economic	Cost of care	Treatment, Travel, Time	Physical
	Type and severity of illness	--	---
Geographical	Distance and physical access	--	Infrastructure

Organization	Perceived quality	Standard of drugs, Standard of Equipment, competence of staff, Attitudes of Staff Interpersonal process	Technical, Staffing Interpersonal formal
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Source: Sara Mackiam (2003:4): A Review Of Health Seeking Behavior: Problem and Prospects (University of Manchester)

Hypothetical Pathway Linking Socio Economic Time Preference and Prospective and Health Care Related Behavior (Jean Adams , 2009)

Fig12

Source; Jean Adams , 2009 the Role of Time Frequency of perspective in Socio culture Inequalities in Health related Behavior in a Edited Volume of S.J Babones ; Policy press:

Zola (1973)found that communities’ reaction to the symptoms was dependent upon their cultural values / beliefs concerning the various health issues. That is their perception of what is 'normal'. Therefore, the choice to seek the proper medical help was either promoted or delayed by the various social factors. Zola`s (1973) model has identified Five diverse types of occurrence which `triggered' the judgment to seek the medical care, incidents which intimidate people`s philosophy of customariness”.

Zolas Help-Seeking Model (Zola, 1973)

Fig 13

Sources: Zola,I. (1973),Pathways to the Doctor : From Person to Patient, *Social Sciences and Medicine* Vol. 7:677-89

Nagda (2009) opined in fact social capital play a vital and tremendously helpful with special reference to the health seeking behavior ‘because it shifting the focus from individuals to social groups, and the social embedded ness of the actions of individuals’ Nagda (2009). In relation to the individuals’ health there is mounting proof that good social capital definitely affects on the quality of health care. Further, Nagda (2009) opines “the point to stress is that this sort of benefit is an attribute of social structures, and therefore cannot be read off the individual alone as most health seeking behavior studies attempt to do”. In addition, there is also a lot of proof to derive a conclusion that active peoples participation in various health programmes will give a turning point in case health seeking behaviour (Brown and Ashman, 1996). Next, Campbell and Mzaidume (2001) have also opined “the very act of involvement in a health promotional community project also means health-related knowledge, traditionally the preserve of experts, is placed in the hands of common people”.

3.e MEDICAL PLURALISM

Field (1977) writes “A society may, and often does, have more than one medical system, and they may well overlap each other, but it may be argued that the totality of such systems constitutes the medical system of that Society...” (Field, 1977)

Prakash (2000) opines “Medical Pluralism is an adaptation of more than one medical system or simultaneous integration of orthodox medicine with complementary and alternative medicine (CAM)” (Prakash, 2000)

Mazumdar (2007) opines the pluralistic medicine is very common in each and every society in the globe. The dissimilarity only existed in the formal recognition of such coexistent of different healing system of medicine, along with the western system of medicine (Minocha, 1980). Medical pluralism is normally recognized as two types 1. Intra –system and 2. Inter Systems. “Pluralism within a system in terms of types of service providers and types of medicine usage can be termed as intra system pluralism; while inter-systems pluralism refers to differential resources across multiple systems” (Mazumdar, 2007). It is found that as the layman’s viewpoint, a pluralistic option of medicine consists of main complexities in terms of cause of disease & illness, existing health behavior and depending on that preference of medical practices from different systems.

Around the world different rural communities will use different medical systems to cure different infectious and non-infectious diseases. Depending on the diseases and illness, rural people will normally practice magic, worship, usage of plants and animals products representing traditional healing and other medical systems like Ayurvedic, Homoeopathy, Allopathic, Unani, Sidda, Chinees, and Tibetan etc to cure various illness/disease. All these invariably represent the medical pluralism. However, this medical pluralism will be based on the ecology, cosmology and other belief systems. Local healers classify some diseases causing due to the failure or malfunctioning of the different organs. Even though it looks vague and unscientific, this classification will help the indigenous practitioners to diagnose the problem properly and to find out the actual cause of diseases or illness. Rural local healers will not use any single healing technique. They use verity of healing techniques at a time or in a different therapeutics stage representing the medical pluralism. Preference for practitioners from their own cultural milieu is more important to the patients’ than the accessibility and quality of good medical care provided by the different systems. (Minocha, 2011).

As McGrath (1999) writes,

“Pluralistic systems persist to be explained in terms of opposites: ethno- and biomedical, non-western and western, native and european, traditional and modern, local and cosmopolitan, indigenous and introduced, alternative and scientific, natural and allopathic, and so forth” (McGrath, 1999).

In rural settings, choosing an appropriate medical system and specially having strong faith on folk medicine are basically depending on the theory of causation of illness and disease. It may vary from witchcraft to the breakdown of the body systems. As we are aware when culture differ, the healing practices will also get vary. Selecting a type of healing technique or more than one type of healing pattern within a given culture is a kind of response by the population over the period of time to cure disease/illness. This therapeutic option is a more common phenomenon across the society and co-existence within another type of alternatives (various) medical practices and ideology. This different treatment options will have a different origin and have different success rates also. However, people will go for such type of treatment having a more effective rate despite practitioners use toxic elements knowingly/unknowingly.

Medical pluralism is a part and parcel of any socially stratified and culturally diverged natured rural society. Since numerous medical care system is available in the rural society, sometime these medical systems (pluralistic therapy) may have to compete to each other over the success rate. Also due to influence of changing health culture, the under lying notion in each medical system will also get changed. Individual practitioners will adopt an appropriate technique/s in administering each therapy. While administering more than one therapy to a single patient co-operation and co-existence required between various medicinal systems. Sometime biomedical systems dominate over an indigenous medical system or vice versa. Hence, the medical pluralism sometime referred as a blend of tradition and modern medicine within the existing complex factors like political, eco-nominal, social and cultural hegemony in rural parts. Also some time experts feel the true reality of medical pluralism in quite myth too (Elling, 1981).

It is a well known fact that medical pluralism is culture dependent rather than cultural independent. Medical pluralism is a kind of social system because medical pluralism will arise and construct within a broader frame work of social, cultural and political context. Every medical system will have its own anthology, theory, and epistemology. Every medical system plays a vital role in fulfilling various needs of

the patient/s. It is found that dichotomization/ contra position is crucial among the various medical care systems. Medical sociologists argue that there are no specific bounders among various therapeutic measures. It is also proved by some studies that there will be an association/ interactions between the folk healers and the modern medical practitioners when they are practicing in the same village or in the same socio-economic context. It shows various medical system may be local or global they have their own method in sharing or transmitting vital information's about diagnose and curing elements presence in each other's system (Basu, 1992; Bhardwaj and Paul, 1986).

As health behavior is becoming too complex today there is quite high level medical pluralism in both tradition and advanced societies. In any medical system normally there will be a sign of pluralistic therapy as well as some-cultural elements. It shows any medical system cannot be out of influence of the current socio-cultural system. Also both the traditional and advanced medicinal system will have more similarities rather than differences. Today preventive health care is most common. It invariably affects forms, content and context of the any medical/health care system.

Medical sociologists felt availability and accessibility of various medical systems in a given setting will be useful in changing culture based attitude on illness, diseases and sickness among rural people. Also variety of medical systems will be useful in decreeing prevalence of both infectious and non-infectious diseases in rural areas. Probably this would be very useful in introducing modern medicines and making culturally acceptable for the rural folk. Since various medical systems available in the same society the vital question arises about its legitimization and allowing them to co-exist in any given settings. Hence both pragmatic and pseudo political views helps to explain the phenomena of medical pluralism in a deferent setting. In greater cases, it is found that if the folk medicine failed to cure the particular health problems then only rural people would like to consult a bio-medical health provider for the solution. In larger cases patients' are reluctant to use the tablets or tonics prescribed by the modern doctors (Mazumdar, 2007).

Cranelon -Malamuel (1991) writes

“In case of therapeutic pluralism, both trained and untrained practitioner gives patients with an array of diseases and illness concept and healing alterative that can be used not only to get resource like prestige, power etc. But also to negotiate to social relation and define cultural identify “

The hierarchical principle of high and lower caste is not only within the social groups. Also it exists with that of medical pluralism in the rural settings. Normally lower caste people will visit the traditional healer who has also belonged to the lowest caste. As Guptha (1990) said the ‘caste-class classification is normally congruent with the medical pluralism hierarchy with special reference to rural society.’ Today the broad verity of healing techniques belonging to the different medical systems co-exists along with the traditional medicine especially in a rural society. This is an established fact that in some cases traditional healers will treat the patients’ based on the certain diagnostic techniques available in the modern medicines. It is happening purely because of medical pluralism only.

Due to the globalization rural society is past changing today. Because of new social, political and economic scenario including interventions of other powerful external agencies some section of the rural people are showing more interest in Ayurvedic and Homeopathy rather than Folk medicine or Allopathic. It is also because of side effects and cost factor in case of bio medicine. Lack of publicity, understanding, and validation of the pluralistic medical system is need of the hour. This is a vital draw back in implementing the culture specific health care programme in the rural areas.

Medical pluralism cannot be overlooked from both clients and providers perception and today a hierarchical range of systems within the band of pluralism is extensively manifestable. Also sometime people felt different ISMs (Indian System of Medicine) is biased with allopathic system in urban areas. The more worrying factor is that some of the sidelined healing system like Unani, Sidda, and the Naturopathy etc have become a last resort for the patients’ in case the given problems is not solved in the modern health care system. Only Two popular medical systems viz; Ayurvedic and Homeopathy are most in demand in the rural parts today. Further, they have stated even though allopathic medicine has more emphasized, promotion of different medical systems should also be focused by the State too. Sujatha (2010) has opined that “negotiations among various types medical co-existing therapeutic system and between patients and practitioners in terms of forms of legitimating is vital in the long run of any Indian system of medicine”.

Source: Adapted from William C. Cockerham (2006). Health lifestyle Theory and the Convergence of Agency and Structure, Journal of Health and Social Behaviour, 46(March) 51-6

3.f Health Culture, Health Behavior and Medical Pluralism in the Rural Context

The sociological investigation of the problem on the rural health culture and behavior involves an analysis of social, cultural, economic and political aspects of the issue. The health culture and behavior has been a constant theme in Medical sociology. It is argued by a critical concern with the neoclassical approach to study health behavior and culture. Two main areas of research have been cited by the sociologist’s interest:

1. The family context of health culture and
2. Socialization and health behavior.

One of the leading themes of Medical Sociology has been conceptualization of health behavior and its cultural meanings. The growing numbers of publications of sociology on health behavior issue in the underdeveloped countries has raised a renewed interest in the family context of health culture. Central to some of the notable work has been “how health behavior among the marginalized sections is constrained by hierarchies based on age, caste, gender, that result in its typically rural, flexible and personalized character, rather than a widespread form of medicalizations”.

To some extent different medical system can co-exist as separate arenas in the same geo-graphical areas. There is a persistent belief, which finds its origin in the neoclassical approach, that medical pluralism is the best antidote to rapid medicalizations at least with special reference to the rural part. This notion suggests that availability of a different medical system decreases health expenditure on the family. Next, articulation of gender, age and kinship of the patients play an instrumental aspect in opting particular type medical system.

Culture will not only determine the health behaviour towards any type of diseases or illness rather culture play a vital role in revealing how people perceive, explain and treat the various illness and diseases in a given context. Hence it is generally found that culture determines communities’ understanding of health and illness, because of this, a community develops specific belief, towards several health problems including causation, spread, diagnose etc. Health culture, health behavior and medical pluralism in the rural context play an ultimate role in determining the health status of the rural people. Health culture and health behavior are like two faces of a coin, one cannot exist without another. Notwithstanding exposition of health culture in case of rural context has been attributed by some of its determinant factors. In rural settings, availability and accessibility of different health care systems are the vital components in shaping the rurals’ health culture. The co-existence of various health care agencies became the outcome of social changes including the socio-political development. With such health institutions and the service rural people have inter-oriented themselves in fulfilling their required health needs (Deepa, 2005).

Though the process of socialization is common, the health culture became an internal aspect of any individuals’ life, and it becomes the health behavior in accordance with the value of norms in due course of time. Hence the health culture is a stimulating force to have required health behavior (Bir, 2001). In the majority cases

the cultural attitudes towards the health- belief system is largely boosted by the changing socio-economic conditions. However, rural health culture has undergone tremendous changes due to the various new technologies, varying social needs and influence of a variety of pressure groups. Various studies have shown that while the society making a decision about the sick person his/her age, income, occupation, religion etc will be taken into consideration. Also health behavior is found to be a complex phenomenon ranging from the psychological, biological to economics etc (Bir, 2001; Nagla, 2007).

Different beliefs and practices indirectly reveal causation of diseases/illness as they provide the framework for perceiving reasons and expecting healing treatment. Various studies have proved that rurals' health behavior is found to exist along with the western and it is a vital effect of such association is delay in getting proper medical treatment on time. Apart from the socio-economic factors there are some other vital issues is shaping rurals' health culture and behavior. They are the village elders, religious leaders, faith healers and the locally influential people these people influences on others to continue age-old beliefs, traditions and attitudes towards opting any type of treatment. Religious leaders and their faith healing techniques also has become a part and parcel of the rurals' health behavior. Because these healer also influences a lot in accepting or rejecting modern medicine on rural folk (Mazumdar, 2007 ; Malamuel,1991).

Cultural factors like ethnicity, religion, gender also produce differential health behavior in case of rural people. Certain Anthropologists have introduced different health models in order to understand rurals' health behavior including the etiology of diseases, symptoms constructed, response, communication, and management. Some studies have also focused how rural people differentiates between diseases and illness based on their cultural experiences. Rurals' perception of severity of the diseases, previous experience and faith in the success of a particular type of healing technique will play an imperative role in seeking a suitable initial choice. In remote rural parts, people are wise enough to differentiate different diseases which can be cured only by the western doctors or the local healers. It is also found that in some rural parts modern medicine is being used to cure the various health problems only because the new referral system (Duggal, 1994 ; Bhardwaj, 2010).

In rural India the health seeking behavior is more depend on the people's perception abbot illness or disease and available health services. Health seeking behavior is taking pragmatic decision to deal with the health problems within the available resources. Income, occupation and the level of education also play a vital

role in selecting an appropriate treatment. Higher income groups in the rural area will normally approach for a good health care whereas low income groups will look for subsidized health care or would like to visit only the government hospitals where poor health infrastructure exists including some sort of negligence by the health staff because of poor background of the patients'. Sometime in rural areas the distance factor also counts a lot. The structural and functional changes in the rural societies are taking place over the period of time. Hence the new health culture and behavior are spontaneously brought in and some being induced in the context of several upcoming new health institutions.

Ackerknecht (1942) has opined (quoted) ,

1. Rather than one type of traditional medicine there is an existence of various types of traditional medicines in rural settings;
2. The differences between various traditional medicines are very small variations in their "elements" than various existing medical system which is basically shared by their given general cultural types;
3. The degree of unification of various elements of medicine into a whole and of the whole medicine into an existing health cultural pattern differs significantly.

Over the last decades, awareness has increased regarding usage of medical pluralism and role of modern medicine among rural people. Even today variety of healing treatments exists alongside the western medicine in rural areas. However, in the fast changing rural society due to the globalization local medical system has been under the tremendous influence of the other different medical systems. The medical system in rural India consists of a variety of practices including, magic, faith healing, herbal etc. Both orthodox and non-orthodox therapeutic pluralism has been widely available today in the rural parts. Also orthodox and non-orthodox medicine reflects the changing political economy of the rural areas. Experts felt demand for the pluralistic therapeutic is increasing in rural areas due to the changing concept regarding health and illness. Due an external influence, usage of more than one type of medical care for the same health problem is gradually increasing.

In rural area patients are showing interest for the therapeutic pluralism because;

1. Those who suffered from the side effects of allopathic medications;
2. Those who would like to avoid excessive medications;
3. Those who want to avoid surgery (Bhardwaj, 2010)

In rural areas, usually patients' evaluate the therapies in terms of the cost benefit analysis with reference to the various types of health care system. Here cost means not the money rather, the long term impact of the particular type of therapy on health and duration required for healing. It is found that today in rural areas people are very careful regarding standardization of the traditional medicines and more aware about the various side effects with the help of various social networks. It is found that some of the sidelined medical system likes Unani, Sidda also getting popularity in rural areas today. It is because of its low cost and absence of side effects. Today the medical pluralism in rural areas opens up for the new possibilities of gaining insight into the interplay of social, economic, political and cultural domains of the health behaviour. Efficiency of treatment determined differently by the various actors and class of people when several system of medicine available the same area. Pluralism is not just a therapy but substantive definitions of what constitute a disease and how efficiently rather how fast it can cure (David,1989).

Ibata (2004) has opined that

“The interchange of people and goods with ambient culture has configured the multicolored medical knowledge and healing practice on its own right in each different geo-graphical and cultural context” .

“the Indian medicine system is also embedded in the beliefs of a wide section of the population and continues to be an integral and important part of their lives and for some, it is also a way of life” (MoHFW, 2002).

It is found that selecting a type of therapy in rural traditional health system has a bigger impact than curing a disease. As Turner (1966) points out that as a rural health culture believes ‘beginning of any health disorder is a direct result of an impact on the social solidarity’. In this moment selecting a right medical system to heal the problem will play a vital role in cementing the existing ‘social ties’. Experts opined that medical pluralism has various dimensions and dynamics including philosophy, ideology, of various levels of diversity within the caste, class, religion etc. Traditional healers basically use this philosophy in their treatment to preserve their role and status within the wider society/culture. The only holistic concept of health culture provides a structural insight about rurals' changing health seeking behavior today.

Shanker and Geetha (2012) write

“the culture of community determines the health behavior of the community in general and individual members in particular. The health behavior of the individual is closely linked to the way he or she perceives various health problems; what they actually

mean to him or her, on the one hand, and on the other his or her access to various relevant institutions”. .

It is also opined that option for the multiple system of relief was basic to the human in the broader need and cannot be analyzed as a cultural obduracy neither ignorance on the part of the people of the rural area. It is not just because of the absence of the proper allopathic facilities nor the general ignorance of the rural people. Guptha argued that the ‘co-existence of traditional and modern medicine had hence to be seen not as dichotomies but as overlapping instrumentals’ (Guptha, 1988; Sujatha, 2012).

Medical sociologists have opined that the modern world should not ignore the entire traditional medical system including the diagnosis and healing techniques prevalent among the rural people. Hence expert felt any study should focus how various medical aspects influenced by various social and cultural issues and how the given socio-cultural issues influenced by the different medical aspects. Further, certain studies have found that both the indigenous and modern medicines have certain common platforms and hence it is better to study the rural health culture from the context of both differences and similarities within these two medical systems. Expert said it is the time to find out the cultural factors affecting in accepting the traditional medicine and cultural issues as inhibiting factors in non-accepting modern medical care by the majority of the rural people (Sheer and Abraham ,1996).

Syed (2000) has opined private hospitals will provide better quality health services because they will run normally on ‘users’ fees. Since there will be no user fees in the Govt. hospitals. Sometime this would be the main reason why village people may not show interest in visiting Govt. hospitals. Because they feel free healthcare might not be a quality one. He said rude behavior of the staff, unavailability of the required specialists and free medicines etc., also some of the reasons why the village people will not show interest visiting Govt. hospitals today.

Phillips (1990), opined studies across the globe has found that the young members in household will not seek immediate treatment for any kind of health problems when compare to the elderly population. This might be due to the over confidence, ignorance, negligence etc., However, in the rural families usually younger’s will be more cared rather than older people for any kind of medical treatment. Waldron (1994) pined normally life expectancy of the women will be more when compared to men. However, women face higher rates of chronic diseases in the rural parts because

of gender discrimination. Even though men face less risk of being ill they die more quickly when illness strikes. It is because of three factors.

1. Life style,
2. Use of the healthcare, &
3. Genetics

Hotchkiss et, al (1998) in their study have found that the household health care expenditure increases because of the growing risky healthy behaviour. Urban people expect more health care needs than the rural people. Urban people use the private health care because of the more health consciousness. Rural people use the traditional medicines mainly because of the cost factor. Though the herbal medicines are the most popular in the urban settings, it will be more expensive one. Hence, urban people now a day's visits rural area for the traditional health care which is free from the various side effects. Bhatia & Cleland (2001) have opined that the level of education plays a vital role in determining the health care seeking behavior and the types of service they normally opt. As the level of education and income increase people will choose the private health care for the quality service.

Kanungsukkasem (1991) have found based on acute or chronic health conditions, rural patients' will plan their choice of treatment. Sometime the patients' will contact a large number of doctors to enhance their multiple choices of treatments focusing the cost factors and the duration for the healing. For the severe health problems or in case of emergency, rural people finally visit the hospitals only. He said for the minor problems people use mostly home remedies in the rural areas.

Balse and Naik (2011) have opined that the need of the sound health begins from the womb. Consequences of poor health conditions have a direct bearing on all aspects of the life. It may be education, employment, occupation etc., In the rural parts due the ill health or due to the lack of the proper treatment poor students are being deprived form the school education. It is an irredeemable throughout one's life. Moreover, the health of an individual normally effects on the total income of the family and the financial status of that family will get affected because of any health problems. Therefore, the health needs to be considered as an important component of the progress and development of any society. Early detection of any health problem and its immediate arrest have an overwhelming importance in keeping the society healthy and consolidating nation's manpower resources.

Chaudhuri (2004) opines in rural settings health and treatment normally reflects the community solidarity. He writes if something happens to a person in the village rest of the village will be ready to observe certain health norms. Choosing a healing therapy will be sometime at the community level. In certain cases, an entire community will take the responsibility of the patient until he/she get cured. This social solidarity through the social network will also play an indirect role in educating other people to be more cautious about any health issues. He also highlights that the social scientists have done enormous work on the rural health culture and commented about their various blind health beliefs but they have not focused on an in-depth study on the various basic forces behind that belief. Further, he opines the current traditional method available to the rural people needs more scientific study. There is a dearth need to encourage and support the traditional healing system tune to the modern medical coverage. Traditional healers should be trained at least in the field of identifying diseases exactly in the earlier stage where burden on the patient can be substantially reduced.

A number of studies have done on rural and tribal health problem, invading utilization of the modern medical facilities, nutritional status, mortality, nobility, family welfare service etc. They found that Indian rural people are facing poor health stress. They are still hanging between the traditional and modern health practices. Still studies required to find out the changing health behavior of the rural and tribal people due to the Globalization and other forces. Govt. and the NGOs need to create more awareness among the rural people without encroaching their social and cultural world (Choubey, 2000; Pandry, 2000; Sharma, 1999).

The medical system of any society will be normally composed of different medical sub -systems found in a co-operative or competitive mode. One patient and the multiple health providers like Ayurveda , Unani, Sidda, Western doctors etc are the vital features of any medical pluralism. This issue plays a vital role in the health seeking behavior focusing medical pluralism in a given society. Usually complex societies include all types of medical systems in a parallel and sometime overlapping manner. Medical pluralism in a society sometime based on the hierarchical relation, socio-political and economical control etc. In a pluralistic health care system, the very basic interpretation of illness may get changed over the period of time. Usually patients' do not essentially mind the illness details and healing approaches coming from the different health care system as a contradictory one. Salvador (2009) writes *“the real issue is that usually the deceased person and different healers consider various underling medical logics doesn't necessarily undermine treatment”*.

Studies have proved that the acceptability of traditional or western medical system by any community mainly depends on the cultural, social, economical, political and moral values of the society. If a patient got a bad treatment at the government hospital he/she shares that experience with the others people. Hence people may reluctant to visit any Govt. hospital in the future. If a patient satisfied with quality of the service including duration took to solve the health problem he /she may like to encourage others to visit the same hospitals (Choubey, 2000; Pandry, 2000;). This is a reason why it is not so easy to introduce the western medical system in the rural areas where traditional systems strongly exist for a long time. People will normally compare various medical systems available at the door steps with respect to the quality, cost, duration to heal, degree of efficacy etc. Of course, all these factors differ from context to context an culture to culture. Rural people normally expect medicine/s should solve their health problem quickly. They just only bother about immediate consequences. Hence, now Sociologists are focusing phenomenology and the political economy exist within the current medical pluralism and the social relation the rural health care management. A perfect understanding of medical pluralism in diverse cultural settings is need of the hour.

CHAPTER-V
Sociology of Health and Illness

Culture is a shared concept of the specific social groups. The concept of health, hygiene, illness, well being, and sickness are the fundamental issues present in all types of culture. This is a vital concept and an instrument to conduct any health studies among the rural population as patients' belonging to different social groups and the culture. These people express a unique health behavior and the medical pluralism. People's construction of illness is a focal point in sociology. The Influence of religious belief and social network on the health culture is a vital issue studying health and illness from the sociological point of view. Every culture has its exact clarification and justifications for all types of ill health. Culture provides people with ways of thinking that are "concurrently models of and models of actuality". Further, wide differences in delaying the healthcare seeking process across the culture can be seen. It may due to the existence of traditional knowledge and belief about the disease, over confidence, ignorance, strong faith in the medical technology etc. various other socio-cultural factors counts a lot here. Some time based on the different health priorities people will develop their health seeking behavior or health care seeking behavior. In addition, people will consult the doctors on any other health workers issue when health disturbs their normal routine life which as a lot of sociological significance

Health and illness are universal concepts in all advanced/traditional societies. Each community organizes itself through experience, through different means, through different elements and finally will develop different approaches to fight against various illness and diseases. In this way each and every society develops specific medical institutions called health care system in a relevant social context. This health care system will have origin, symptoms, development, process and curing of various diseases/illness. This system will have different symbols expressed through the means of practices, interactions and institutions.

Sociology of Health and Illness

Sociology brings two different perspectives of analysis in the study of health and illness:

1. At the first instance it focused to 'make sense of illness', by applying various sociological perspectives both to a scrutiny of the understanding of illness, and to the social structuring of health and disease. Further, sociology makes an imperative input to multi-disciplinary and multi faceted assessment into issues of interest to health care providers and helps in the development of new and appropriate health policies;

2. At a second level, sociological enquiry can give more options in understanding of the effect of wider social and cultural phenomenon upon the health of an individual or the community and various social groups including social inequalities, health culture, behavior, change, knowledge, medicalizations and power.

Sujatha (2010) opines “Marriott’s universalisation has vital role in studying rural health cutler.. Not only the origin but also the continuance, maintenance and promotion of the classical medical traditions seemed to have been associated with the inputs coming from folk systems. On the other hand, parochialisation is the reverse of universalisation. It is the process of ‘Localization’ of and “limitation upon the scope of intelligibility, or deprivation of literary form, of reduction to less systematic and less reflective dimensions” (Marriott 1955, 205-6). The transfer from the great to the little tradition involves a series of transformations by which the original material is adapted to the local context. The processes of universalisation and parochialisation are, according to Marriott, continual and also cyclical. While the concepts universalisation and parochialisation help in understanding the link between the great and little traditions, they do not suggest anything about how exactly these processes take place. In the context of indigenous medical traditions, health behavior, culture etc some cues from our field data can throw some light on this hitherto dark area”

Health is an elusive concept. We have numerous definitions to define the term health. Good health can be some time positive or sometime negative or more precisely absence of any kind of health related problems like physical or mental. Herzlich (1973) said “health is to feel well, in good form, happy content, with a good appetite, sleeping well wanting to be up and doing; it is to feel well and strong; that’s what good health is”. Parson (1951) defines health is a good status of the physical body which can perform any task. He said ‘healthy person can do any social role which is a normal part of his/her societal responsibility. Health disorder may reduce the capacity

of the human being'. We can also opine the cultural setting of any given society regarding, 'perception, preference, evaluation and satisfaction about 'health' is more vital while generalizing term' (Nagala, 2007). The health of any society is intimately related to its value, system, philosophical and political and ecological organizations (Singh et, al. 2008). Moreover health is subjective in its basic nature.

Mishra, (2010) writes “ Sociological research deconstructs such discourses and highlights their implications on the notion of agency of the patient, meanings of informed consent, patient participation in different cultural contexts and notions of health and illness as doing. Health becomes an everyday moral duty” (Mishra, 2010).

The sociology of health and illness has a long history. Over the last 100 years many concepts, theories, findings have been explored for the better understanding of health behavior of human beings and the role of the society. the majority theories and approaches relating to the health and illness have been originally propounded by the western sociologists only. Even today researchers in the developing countries are heavily depending on the western theories to explain health culture and behavior of the rural community. In the developing countries social class, caste, gender etc play a vital role in accessing suitable healthcare facilities. More than these the underlying social, political and economic forces are also counting a lot. It is found that sociology of health and illness significantly helps us in better understanding of people's concepts about onset of various diseases and its cure in a cross cultural framework.

Right from the history, Sociologists are attempting to find out how social and cultural factors influences understanding of illness and diseases, people's responses to illness and its relevance in the healthcare policies. Sociologists are also probing how social, economic, and cultural factors impacting about choosing a different health seeking behaviors. the medical sociologists and anthropologists have given a wide range of findings on health and illness based on the various empirical studies conducted in the different rural settings across the globe. Particularly sociologists have written more on the sick role, the social construction of health and illness, influence of the local culture and tradition in defining and treating diseases and how health and illness concept may affect on the different segment of the given society.

Albrecht (2000) writes “An massive body of work in the sociology of health and illness is not so patently realistic but is intention on understanding what it means to be sick, to have a chronic illness or disability, to be a woman, to experience fertility and menopause, to be poor, a member of a minority group and in need of health care and social services” (Albrecht et, al. 2000; Bird et, al.2000).

Since community perceptions' on health and illness varies from culture to culture sociologists have given various theories and approaches to study about health and illness over the period of time using longitudinal studies. Truly speaking the very basic concept of sociology of health and illness is to enlighten about the social origin and influence on the onset and choosing suitable medical care of any diseases or illness and the role of different components of the society relating to that issue. Sociology of health and illness also explains how different social groups have come up with the specific diseases over the period of time and what other culture can learn from their experiences. Also concept of health and illness of the society is based on the cognitive orientation of a particular social group and cure will also follow the same cultural logic.

The health care system is also a part of general culture. There will be no much difference between socio-cultural experiences and an episode of illness with respect to a particular social group. Each and every individual through his/her personal episode of illness will keep on adding his/her prospective to the society's health culture. We cannot neglect health and illness episode of any lay person. Health culture will develop according to the social, economical, legal and political development etc. of the society. In this matter, various medical institutions and the systems will also play a vital role in the maintaining of the "state of health" (Langdon & Wikinson , 2010; Kleinman, 1980; Langdon and Wilk, 2010).

Health care system normally will have Two components.

1. Social component;
2. Cultural component

Social Component: In case of social elements it consists of different health care institutions, healers, health culture, health behavior etc., It also includes the traditional medicinal system like folks system, faith healers, quacks herbalists etc., Apart from these we can also witness for the growth of other medical system like Unani, Sidda, Tibetan and Chinese medicinal system side by side. Also we can see the concentration of different specialists practicing different therapeutic models based on the different health cultures and care. Each and every social group will have their own reservations, perceptions in accepting or acknowledging or rejecting these type of medical system/s. This acceptance or rejection will be largely based on the socio-economic background, caste, family history, religion etc. Hence we cannot isolate all these vital factors while studying the health culture of a community from a sociological point of view.

Cultural Component: The cultural system of health will help us in gaining the different knowledge and cognitions to identify, perceive and explain disease/illness. Each and every culture will have their own concept about symptoms, classifications about various types of diseases/illness. However, they are not a universal. Every health culture gives etiological theories about multiple causes for diseases and illness. Certain health culture theories provide us the historical concept behind traditional preventive and curative knowledge of the lay man. Some theories enlighten us about the various reasons for using more than one type of medical system (medical pluralism) and how the medical pluralism shapes communities' health behavior and the health culture in due course of time .

Truly speaking the health care system has been just a conceptual model to understand society's different health culture and behavior. This will help us to understand the different sets of elements and experiences involved in the health culture and behavior. Since the health care system is a cultural system, sociology will also help us in understanding the medical pluralism operating concurrently in the different social groups and cultural response to various health problems.

Further Sociology of Health and Illness focus on

1. What should be the actual theories of health and illness?
2. How theory should be constructed focusing health and illness;
3. How health theories changes from culture and culture;
4. How the body, mind and spirit careered each other;
5. Connections between theory of health and theory of healing;
6. What is meant by healing and who is the actual healer;
7. Relationship between medicine and society
8. How health culture and health seeking behavior changing over the period of time;
9. How quality health care \ can be delivered to all
10. Why people reject/accepts modern medicines

Sociology of health and illness specifically also deals with

- Various medical and healing agencies ;
- Social role;
- Symbols, power and the healing;
- Structure, process and outcome

Sociology of health and illness basically deals about the inter relationship between 'health and society' and 'medicine and society'. Study about health and illness in the society is not a new phenomena. From the time immemorial, people are doing official or unofficial research study about the societal reactions and responsible towards health and illness issue. Even during the Egyptian period also there were some interested people doing research on medicine and its connection with the society. Essentially, there is a clear cut differentiation between the medical sociology and sociology of health and illness. In medical sociology focus will be concerning health and illness delimited by a range of social institutions. Nevertheless in case of sociology of health and illness researchers by and large studies concerning a) various social and cultural factors causing diseases and illness, b) health seeking behavior, c) health care seeking behavior and d) inherited health culture of the society.

It also focuses how health culture and behavior varies based on the socio-economic status of a community. Sociological concept about illness gives a fair idea how an external determinants causes health problems to an individual and how he/she responds to it in a given social context. It is a well known truth that the influence of socio-cultural factors varies across the globe. Normally these social factors demonstrated through various discourses on important diseases /illness and its outbreak in a specific geographical area. Basically experts' focus on the issues comprising society and medicine, socioeconomic setup, general cultural issues which are geographically specific while studying the specific health culture of a community. Sometime a common disease may affect the larger population whereas a major disease may affect the smaller population only. Medical anthropologists basically studies about these discrepancies.

It is found that basically sociology of health and illness study takes place in Three vital domains. They are-

1. Conceptualization of health and illness of a particular society or culture;
2. Measurement and distribution of the health and illness;
3. Reason behind choosing a particular type of healing approach

As we are aware, different culture responds differently to the different illness/diseases. Based on this factor it would be worth to study focusing how an illness affects the social regulations or controls over the period of time. Measuring and distribution of various diseases/ illness will help how community is using various existing health services. It also helps to get patients' perception about his/her illness

and reason for that. Sociologists are trying to study the various data to analyze the distributional pattern of certain disease and illness in a given society.

Since the history, thousands of people had been dying due to the outbreak of various endemics which led to think about the necessity of having a good public health strategy. It is found that the earlier concept of good health was only among the elite sections (rich people) of the society. Slowly concepts and significance about good health and reason for disease/illness among other people were also starting to develop. People started to have a notion that good health leads to have a good social status in the society. Gradually marginalized sections of the society started showing interest towards sanitation and precautions in their personal life to keep healthy.

As new medical health care facilities discovering health status of the any community across the world has started considerably improving. The gradual changes in the socio economic status of the people also led to have the quality medical care. Diagnose and treatment pattern also started to affect positively on the health care seeking behavior of the community. Now rural people are showing more interest to adopt modern health care facilities. This change in the health culture of the community causes the issue of health and illness within the given societal life to be highly volatile in definition. Hence, studying health and illness from the sociological point of view continuously need an updating excursive.

Wilkinson (1996) has opined societies having a poor health status, will tolerate the high inequality in every aspects. Differences in the health practices between various social groups would be more vital for sociological analyzations. Even in the same society, disparities in health status and health behavior can be seen among different social classes/castes. The wide income gap, material deprivation and psychological issues invariably effects on the health and illness of an individual/community in a society. Wide gap between rich and poor people results in the low social cohesion which finally affects on the health of all the members. It is found that vital differences in case of mortality and morbidity rate continuously increasing between low income groups and the elites of the society. However, the research is on the way to find out how poverty and deprivation effects on the general health issue and behavior among the members of less advanced societies.

Health seeking and health care seeking behavior of an entire family will be largely influenced by the social and cultural factors. Poor income means the poor health. Finally it leads to have various effects on the family causing numerous health problems. Income and health are closely related to life expectancy of any community.

High income inequality also leads to have a big gap in the health disparity between different social groups. This health disparity is due to the material deprivation, socio-psychological effects etc.,. Due to the social exclusion (class and cast) certain sections of the society may not get an equal health benefits. Various social, cultural, developmental and psychological factors finally leaves an impact on the health condition of an individual irrespective of his/her class and caste etc.,. Moreover it is found that social capital like education, housing, social networks also places an imperative factors causing health and illness (Crision , 2007 ; Wilkinson, 1996 ; Marmot ,2004).

Few Sociological studies also revealed how different social process and functions affects on health status of different social groups. In addition it helps to reveal how different social groups are experiencing health and illness. Supplementary it reveals layman's health beliefs, and illness behavior. Many studies have proved that layman's health beliefs vary according to social and cultural background. How a layman experiences, describes, justifies health and illness would be a vital point in understanding general conceptions of health and illness of the people. However, certain medical sociologists have opined there will be a big difference in case of general societal opinion than an individualistic opinion about the socio-cultural aspects of health and illness. Because individualistic determinants for health and illness cannot be simply generalized or add up to become the general social determinants s in a border way(Crimson, 2007; Marmot ,2004).

SOCIAL CONSTRUCTION OF ILLNESS

Bhasin (2007) writes “every culture has its particular explanations for illness. Frake (1961) during his research among Subanum of Mindanao, explained an illness as a vehicle for pursuing other interests. He wrote “illness is fundamentally semantic or meaningful and..... all clinical practice is inherently interpretive.....”.

According to Good (1977) “semantic illness network is the network of words, situations, symptoms and feelings which are associated with an illness and give it meaning for the sufferer”

Health, illness and the cure are realities in everybody's life across the societies. Therapy, practices and results normally evolve over the period of time within the socio-cultural contexts. It provides different insights about health culture, behaviour, traditions; customs inv the medical health care system. Through the personal experiences patients' and the doctors/ native healers will also add on to the knowledge of society's health belief system continuously over the period of time. All cultures

consists of vital information's about how disease occurs, what makes illness and how to choose suitable healing approaches. This would be a health culture of each and every community. In each health culture there will be different concepts, ideology philosophy and thinking and planning in handling various diseases and illness appropriately (Bhasin 2008). Obeyesakere (1976) has given a term called "cultural diseases" because some diseases are created partially because of "cultural" definition of the given "situation". Regarding the social construction of disease and illness Rose (1992) has evolved an argument for analyzing 'behavior determinants of the health of individuals at the societal level'. Rose writes "concerning the social distribution and determinants of disease and illness cut across the view of disease as an autonomous individual affliction. It focus that new disease and the discloser to the range of possible risk factors are a result of the norms of any given society". Hence, it is opined that beliefs held by the community/individual within a society about onset of the disease and curing is critical always.

It is generally opined that illness has three domains:

1. Illness as Sanction (punishment for doing wrong)
2. Illness as Deviance(a form of social control)
3. Illness as an Indicator of Social System Performance (indicative of the performance of an existing social system)

It is well known truth that health and illness is a 'socially constructed concept'. Each and every society will interpret the term 'health and illness' differently in its own way. This would be depending largely on the history, culture, religion, gender role etc. of that society. Moreover, it depend who has the final authority to apply the label called 'illness' within a given society. Also, it depends on the context or the circumstances in which illness occurs. Truly speaking social construction of illness means how society shapes illness behavior of an individual in which he/she normally live. Here one question arises what does really construct an illness?

Steven (2001) writes "clearest example of illness as a socially and culturally shaped through a similarity of eastern medicine system and description of illness versus western medicinal system and description of illness".

Illness has three historical origins:

1. Few illness notions are originally rooted with the historical and cultural meanings;
2. Most of all illness is socially constructed at the empirical level;
3. The true medical concept about illness is mostly framed by the vested interest

Social construction of illness depend on how people differentiate between illness and the disease. Social construction of illness has developed through an interaction in a social context. Meaning and the experience of illness will be largely framed by the historical and existing social system. Scholars say illness is not 'given' rather actually conferred by dominating social groups in a given society. They say society will confer illness as a part of the control/sanction (short term). Scholars who support 'symbolic interactionism' felt illness is an experiences within the framework of daily social interactions of an individual.

Sociologists are showing interest to work on how 'symptoms' or 'symbols' are being labeled or identified as an 'illness'. It is also interesting to look what an accepted as "Illness or what is not accepted as not an 'illness' and what are the factors which play a vital role in differentiating illness from any biological framework. However, few scholars also say an argument over illness and it's societal construction approach as something 'Mixed' i.e. Illness has both medical and social deviance. Some time illness varies or may not have independent factors of effect on patient and health care system. Illness has also the cultural symbolic domain. Some illness has been labeled as stigma, while some illness may not be stigmatized in the society. For example AIDS will be severally stigmatized where as Polio not some time. Illness stigmatization varies society to society based on the type, duration and severity etc. It may have less noticed in the urban society whereas may be a more serious in case of the rural society. Some time due to the stigmatization people may not come forward to take the suitable medical care as all.

It is the known fact that sociologists are studying 'patient perspective of illness' since 1950 onwards. Strauss (1975) has opined that since patients' will spend only few days 'with illness (if it is a minor problem) patient's personal experience/narrations may not the same as the illness experiences of a patient having long term health problems' Hence, it is necessary to focus on the 'patients life's before illness, during the stage of illness and after the illness medially cured'. This helps us in the social construction of an illness based on the patients' experience in a given society. Also it helps us to know how the different components of the society helped him/her to come out of illness stage soon. During the stage of illness patients' will be normally worried about their personal and the social relationship and other day to day activities which could not be performed well. Sometime during the stage of illness, patients will review their previous life and in some cases it may create new illness identification (ex. patients under dialysis) also.

Banks and Prior (2001) have opined in this situation patients' will create their own illness ideology based social context and their own illness narrations and parameters to measure their illness notions.

Truly speaking sociological study of health and illness mainly focus on two perspectives:

1. Sociological analysis of different societal factors causing health and illness;
2. Social structure and how different segments of a society responsible for the current illness and how a patient responds to it.

Studying health and illness from the societal perspective will yield some diverse dimensions and discourses. This would be completely different when examining health from an individualistic prospective because the social determinants and individual determinates are quite different. Social, cultural and economic conditions are some of the strongest determinants while studying illness in rural society.

SOCIOLOGICAL APPROACHS: Sociological theories of health and illness are relatively based on the 'humeral imbalance'. Certain sociologists argue illness causes due to the problems in the social relationships. Also they argue that an illness causes due to the broken relationship between human beings and the eco-system. Indian system of medicine is based on the same belief that the human body is made-up of three basic substances called 'spirit, phlem and bile'. Chinese's medicine is also based on the belief that the body is made-up of five elements including 'water, metal, earth, fire, and wood'. In addition, the Greek system of medicine opines that the human body has Four different forces. Expert says any imbalance among these basic elements would cause illness and disease among the human beings. Certain sociologist's proposed their theories about illness and diseases based on the natural and super natural causations. Theories of natural causation focus on disturbance of health as a physiological consequences including infection, germs, mental trauma (Murdock ,1980).

There are three vital theoretical modules to get into the in-depth understanding of health and illness from the perspective of Medical Anthropology.

1. Epidemiological approach ;
2. Interpretive ;
3. Critical Medical Anthropology

1.Epidemiological Approach: In case of epidemiological approach, normally researchers studies health and illness from the prospective of social and cultural

factors. The core part of this theory deals how ecology and environment affect causing various health problems in the society. In this approach, normally focus would be on various risk factors which cause diseases and illness and how it relates to the environment. This theory also propounds the relationship between urbanization and the new public health problems. According to these theory, social interactions, food habit, and household ecology also play a vital role in causing various health disorders. This theory adds urbanization and migration invariably causes new social pattern of health problems in the society.

This approach further divided into Three more divisions;

a. Retrospective approach: it conducts reasons for various diseases and illness which are occurred already.

b. Prospective approach informs us whether the diseases occur or not? More precisely we can say prospective approach gives an idea of possibility about future occurrence of some diseases. Epidemiological approach will not avoid the occurrence of any diseases but gives a hint in advance.

2. Interpretive Approach : Basically this approach studies diseases/ illness from the micro prospective. Interpretive prospective further elaborates how specific the cultural factors cause disease/ illness. It also focus how the health behavior and health culture evolved over the period of time in a given society/community. This study would be useful in analyzing the health behavior and the health culture of the small communities.

3. Critical Medical Anthropology here the researcher would focus on how economics and political issues of the society play significantly in the development or underdevelopment of various human health issues. Economics and politics are the major factors in the development/underdevelopment of the human health. Also this approach deals about various social problems and effects of the media on the prevailing health care system in the given society. This theory further focused how the dominant western biomedicine discriminates poor and powerless in the society with respect to health. This approach also sheds light on the pseudo-medicalism, medical exploitations, cost of treatment, Doctor's behavior, medicalizations process etc. This approach strongly believes in the notion that political and economical structure of the society basically responsible in establishing good/ bad health status of a community. Finally this approach criticizes the western health care system for being de-humanized. This theory also strongly criticizes about 'over medicalizations'.

Experts felt health expenditure, resources, health policies all come under the domain of economic factors causing health disorders in a society. The Social and developmental policies, political will, political stability, decision, participation etc also affect on human health culture and behavior. Social exclusion is also a major factor in accessing well quality health care facilities to the marginalized sections of the society. Because of Social exclusion certain sections of the society is away from the health rights even today.

Theories about Origin of Diseases and Illness

There are various theories about the origin, cause and cure of diseases and illness. Also theories explain how the particular health behavior and health culture evolved in the society. Theories about diseases and illness mainly divided into two groups they are:- 1. Personalistic 2. Naturalistic . 3.Folk Concept

1.Personalistic theories argues illness or disease causes due to the supernatural powers including the spirits, sorceries, souls, witches etc. According to this theory illness causes due to the moral or spiritual violation by human beings. Violated social and religions taboos also cause illness as believed in many traditional cultures. This theory further believed that illness is a type of sanction by the super natural powers due to the immorality or breaching taboos in the life. This theory also opines failure to carry out certain rituals may also end up with illness. According to this theory recovery can be had by worshipping deity through ritual or through a trained healer. This theory also explains about sick role in the society and society can help him/her to come out of sick as spoons as possible. Also it explains the space of the sick person in the society and effect of sick role issue on the stability, continuity and cohesion of the society.

2.According to the **Naturalistic theory** illness causes due to an impersonal terms. This theory assumes illness causes due to the disturbance of the cultural order of human beings with his/her surrounding eco-system. This theory says the harmony between human beings and the eco-environment should be properly maintained without which it causes severe harm to the health of a person. Humeral concept is a vital concept of naturalistic theory. Proper balance of various human systems would be a vital component for being healthy. According to this theory Indian system of medicine is also based on the naturalistic theory. In India '*Prana*'(vital energy) concept exists since time immemorial, *Prana* is essential in keeping the human being alive. If the vital energy is disturbed human being may get sickness .

Folk Concept: - This is one of the ancient concepts of explaining causes of illness and cure which is prevalent in many parts of India and other Asian continents. The Folk concept's on illness and diseases ranges from the social world to the supernatural world. These symbols have the cultural significance in explaining the health behavior and health culture. The Folk concept presumes illness and disease may cause due to evil eyes, imbalance of body fluids, hot and cold diet, sorcery, violation of taboos, improper behavior also. It also opined an individual failed in performing rituals regularly may get various health problems. The Folk concept has a lot of symbolic meanings. This theory also explains how human body normally functions (humeral), and how it causes symptoms and the meaning of illness and its moral, social and cultural significance. Also it thrives to explain about illness within the individualistic perspective.

THEORETICAL PROSPECTIVE OF HEALTH AND ILLNESS

1.Marxist Theory of health and illness:- This theory says society is basically made out of social, political, legal and economical entities. This theory relates to the health phenomena in capitalist society. This theory mainly focuses on the relationship between political and economic activity of the society with health issue. This theory specifically examines how economical activity leads to the origin and treatment pattern for various illness/disease and how capitalist society leads health disparity among its members. Production in the society has involved various social relations and network. This production leads to the development of division of labour and class. The inner core of Marxist prospective reveals how the capitalist's economic system affects on the human health in a given society. As usually, production costs various health disorders for the laborers including injuries. Also various industries cause's different pollutions which leads to have a variety of health problems in the society. Production creates different classes. Owners of the production units/factories will get more income and wealth when compare to the laborers. The living standard of the owner's increases and the same of the laborers will get decreases. Laborers are more prone to disease/ illness in the capitalist society. This also greatly creates the health disparities between owners and the laborers because of social and economic exclusion. Due to the accumulation of wealth with owners group, laborers may end up with low quality health care, food, catastrophic health expenditure etc.

2.Functionalist perspective: It is widely focused on the sick role and its related behaviors. This theory categorically says 'illness absolutely a social phenomenon rather than a biological entity'. This perspective defines illness is an 'unmotivated deviance'. This prospective opines keeping healthy of any community is very essential

for the normal function of the any society. If the people are unhealthy, society cannot move smoothly. Sickness is a kind of short-term sanction on the patient. The sick person has their own role to perform in society. Not only the patient, have those who take care of the patients' also had some key role to play. Both the patient and the caretaker have obligatory rights and the mandatory responsibilities towards society.

Further, this perspective says society is linked to both social and biological settings and made up of many integrated parts with respect the health culture. This perspective opines in the society everyone should try to keep themselves healthy. Normally one should not wish to have any kind of illness/diseases. Ill person can be exempted from discharging his/her normal societal responsibility during the period of illness. This must be endorsed by the trained medical specialists for the authenticity. In addition, it says due to the sick, a person cannot perform his /her assigned function/s. Due to this, both sick person and the society will get suffer with their respective normal functioning. Society should help the patient to come out of his/her health problems soon. Also through the various social networks and other means, patients should try to come out of the illness back to the normalcy to perform his/her normal role and duty in the society. Hence, sometime society has the power to use different approaches to control the sick behavior. Here physicians are having a vital role to certify whether a person is ill or healthy and how fast he can come out of his/her illness. However, there is a critic about leaving complete power to the Doctors to decide who is a sick? And who is not a sick?

3.Conflict Prospective :- According to this prospective capitalism is the main cause for comodifying health. This prospective opines people having money power, masculine power, and the people belonging to the dominant caste and the elites can only access to the modern health care system and sometime they will control the entire health care system in the society. Rest of the people will be away from the different health benefits. This creates a big gap naming health disparities between “haves” and “have nots”. Class and caste conflict, ethnicity, racism and gender also create the health disparities in rural societies. Poor people because of the poor hygiene, food, and shelter are more likely to face various disease/illness. It gradually creates conflicts between the elites and the poor for accessing the good health care. In this conflict, the Doctors will get more benefits. However, this theory does not say anything about new discoveries in the medical sciences that would not have been possible without the economic support of the whole society. Finally we can say this theory looks in how health issues fit in to the different forces in society.

4.Foucauldian Theory : -

This theory completely focuses on the current medical discourse in the management of diseases and illness. This theory believes it may be traditional or western medicine. However; they have both power and control on the wider structure of the society. This theory also explains the role of the modern process on the health culture and health behavior of marginalized sections of the society

5. Feminist theory : -

This theory is about the role of gender in the definition and treatment for diseases. This theory also explains how the male dominant society controls women from getting the suitable treatment for her various health issues. This theory explains how women being discriminated in the societal health care system because of her vulnerability position.

In addition, some time patients' may go even up to getting the self medication. All this process may commonly form as 'lay-referred'. This issue is very vital in understanding the layman concept about illness and treatment from the socio-psychological prospective. Sociologists further asserted that in a society unaccepted behavior will be labeled as deviant and finally it will be labeled with that particular individual showing unaccepted behavior. This label brings changes in the image of that individual. For example if a person is mentally ill assumptions about him among his fellowmen will be quite different so that the patient will be labeled which is a one form of social stigma. the Doctor- patient interaction can be better understood through this approaches about the subjective illness experience of the patient.

From the long back the sociologists are trying to get an interpretive understanding of health and illness. Sociological studies about advanced societies cannot be studied unlike the physical world. Hence, sociologists found an interpretative understanding is required very much. This interpretative approach can be connected to the health and illness issue. Interpretative approach specifically focuses on to precisely define the term 'ill-health', and how the society perceives illness. This interpretative approach also focus on the relationship among the 'physician and patient', 'patient and patient' and the 'physician and physician'. Hence sociologists have used the symbolic interaction and the social construction module.

Symbolic Interactionism: In a given society normal communication will be taken place through the exchange of symbols. This approach studies about the different symbols using by the patients to express their illness status. Meanings will be basically reflected through the symbols which is the basics of any language. This

approach specially spotlights on a variety of languages through which illness will be expressed by the patients' to the others. Also this module explains how the language/symbols will be used in the different ritual healing process. People can understand others situation or can explain their own situation through the language communication to others. This modules stress about an appropriate usage of the language communication (symbolic). Also it says one can understand the individual's sufferings interpreting their signal and symptoms without going through an in-depth study about his/her health problems. Further, it also explains experience of an ill person, role of the doctor, expectation from the patient etc. Also this theory presumes that diseases and illness is not just what matters rather it's a kind of social accomplishment. An expert physician can read the patient through the signs and symptoms of the patient without asking to narrate the patient's illness history .

Social Constructionist Approach:- This approach feels the knowledge and facts about health and illness in a society will be produced through the social interactions and how society analyze and interprets the facts. Facts sometime will be created because of an uninterrupted communication among the people. This perspective focuses how an individual fees about his/her physical body and the health disorder/s. This notion finally leads to an individualistic prospective on health and illness and finally society will re-construct his/her illness experience based on the individual's facts. It means that the disease will be intercepted form the prospective of illness experience. This theory generalizes all facts and knowledge about illness are culturally evolved and constructed by the society.

Further, this approach focus on how culture evaluates risk associated with the disease/illness. This approach does not divide watertight compartment between social and scientific knowledge of health and illness. It felt whatever knowledge is currently available is mainly socially constructed through various ideas and beliefs from different individuals and social groups. This theory further opines health and illness is a result of cultural construction. Illness experience will evolve how we perceive about our physical body. This emotional and intellectual notice about our physical body will help in assessing health seeking behavior of a community as opined by the sociologists. This approach will be highly useful in studying how the health culture evolved in a given setting over the period of time and space in a society. Also it helps to assess how the community perceives death and dying (Crimson,2007).

All the theories significantly focus on

- How and why illness or disease does occur?

- How a patient should face illness?
- What is the consequence of the illness on the society ?
- What is expected behavior of a sick person?
- What are the basic criteria to a choose particular type of theory of his consequences.
- How should healing take place?
- Why does health disparity occurs in the society?
- What is the role of modern medicine ?

(**Sources:** Murdock , 1980; Ackerknecht, 1971)

It seems all these theories of health and illness might have been evolved focusing the geographically and culturally specific case studies. It seems all these theories originated in a given context of the patients' experience during their illness period. Since all types of illness are more or less cultural context, the core cultural values will allow the patient in defining the seriousness of the illness and selection of appropriate therapy. However, the locally developed traditional concepts about health, disease, illness and curing therapy may or may not relate to any major existing sociological theories on health and illness. There is some criticism as well as drawbacks also regarding these theoretical approaches.

Paradigms: Health is an interest of research in sociology and anthropology, over the period of time few paradigms evolved focusing health and illness issue. The popular health 'Paradigms' is based upon the medical model which is symptoms oriented.

1.Wellness model: According to this module, health issue has become the materialistic part and dependency on the part of the health consumer. A number of experts have criticizing this model as medical institutions are part of capitalist development. Rather than focusing on the patients, today's medical institutions are simply focusing an extracting the patients. The Doctors are becoming money making machines today.

Under the wellness model health is much more vital. Teague (1987) says the wellness model promotes vitality for beyond what is recognized as feasible in the traditional medical system. Tager (1982) says wellness model uses a life style approach that focuses on teachable context "when people are willing to listen and act on the messages their bodies are sending them". It is found that immunizations, health education, nutrition etc are the part of wellness model.

2.Paradigms of Alternative Medicine (CAM): Today various complementary and alternative (CAM) medicines are available in the market. This paradigm says there

must be an establishment procedure on both health care providers of consumers in the usage of this medicine and peoples must be properly educated.

Taiaryn (2002) has given four paradigms of health and illness in association with different medical systems;

1. Body paradigm;
2. Mind-body paradigm;
3. Body energy paradigm;
4. Body-spirit paradigm

All these sub-paradigm focuses stress, social supports, life style, cosmology entities etc.

3.Health Education Paradigms: Jensen (1997) has given two sub paradigms in health education.

1. Moralistic paradigm
2. Democratic health education

a.Moralistic paradigm dominated by the western school of thoughts regarding the role of health education programme. It is argued that the moralistic and totalitarian paradigm may actually be a hurdle in developing the context specific health education at the school levels.

b.Democratic health paradigm, health education will be provided in a more liberal way including action competence and holism. These two paradigms opines health and environment should be taught to the students at a same time to acquire firsthand knowledge regarding various health problems.

4.Disease Specific Paradigms:- This paradigms has two sub paradigms;

1. Malnutrition paradigm
2. Infections disease paradigm.

a.Malnutrition paradigm: It argues the absence of nutritious food is the main cause for various health problems. This paradigm focuses the development of an infrastructure for the delivery of quality medical services (and good food) in rural areas.

b.Infectious Disease (ID) Paradigm :It opines various ID's are the main determinants of mortality, morbidity and malnutrition etc. It also opines an unhygienic ecology is the main reason for spreading ID's in the society.

5.Holistic Health Paradigm:- This paradigm opines disease can be avoided with the proper prevention measures. This paradigm stresses on various issues like life styles, individual responsibility, and community accountability, the role of public health care

for the effective and inclusive health care system. it also opines health can be improved even without urbanization and industrialist ion process.

Lay Concepts on Health and Illness:

Bhasin (2007) writes,

“ In the western world people usually do not make a distinction between illness and disease. Disease is an objectively measurable category suggesting the condition of the body. By definition, perceptions of illness are highly culture related while disease is usually not. To a great extent, research in medical anthropology , makes use of pragmatic orientation, but a powerful alternative also prevails, focusing on negotiation of meaning as key to understanding social life”.

It is found that the lay concepts of health and illness are basically different conceptual models used by every person of the society to keep him/her healthy and narration episode of the illness. Sociologists have found that lay concepts of health and illness is basically culturally constructed, vague, and have no strong theoretical background because lay concepts of health and illness normally depends on the theory of humeral, cosmological, Ayurveda sidda, unani, biomedicine etc. In the western part of the globe people considers physical body is a kind of machine which requires tuned up regularly. They also think health as a normal mode of the physical body and diseases or illness is a kind of technical problem in the machine. In Indian society lay person would believe health is a kind of equilibrium status with social, cosmological and physical world. Any breakdown with any one of this would lead diseases or illness. For example if a person gets chest pain people will think it might be due to worrying factors. However in the western world people think it might be some problem with the heart. Experts felt this kind of cultural differences in analyzing the symptoms is normal and causing delay in getting the proper and timely required medical care. Lay concepts in the traditional society on diseases or illness will include only an immediate and the casual cause associated with the symptoms. People also casually think in evaluating the seriousness of the health problem and the possible remedies.

Sociologists found lay concepts on health and illness will be based on various variables like.

1. Cultural history of the society;
2. History of health culture;
3. Socio-economic determinants of the community;
4. Medical pluralisms and its success and;

5. Political – economy of the society ;

According to the self regulations model, illness has few vital representations and they are

- a. Diagnosis of illness;
- b. Symptom of illness;
- c. Believed to have caused the illness;
- d. Effects of illness;
- e. Duration of illness;
- f. And treatment for illness

Some of the studies conducted by both the sociologists and epidemiologists among the rural people having poor socio-economic background have revealed that if a person unable to do his duty then only he/she need medical help. Lay concepts of diseases and illness may be classified into various types based on its origin including;

1. From the individual world.
2. From the super natural world.
3. From the natural world.

In rural parts of India, origin of illness relates to the social world (breaching taboo etc). Some illness attributes to the individual world (life style problem) etc. It is quite pathetic that lay person will not connect his illness or diseases to the biological or psychological issue. The Lay concept also includes the origin of illness may be due to the heat or cold factors, unhygienic conditions, eating contaminated food (by evil eye, sorcerer etc) etc. the Lay concepts have different symbolic meanings that have the cultural and psychological dimensions. Sometime lay person suffering from illness will show his/her problem through his physical body. Normally it will be due to the pain and bad feeling that he/she is not performing his social role because of illness properly. Symptoms in the lay concepts have the cultural meanings that will largely based on the fact that how the particular community perceive health, illness etc. Sometime lay concepts also overlap with many biomedical health models.

Normally indigenous practitioners will read the mind of the patients' through their physical symptoms. Within the given culture and in far with the lay concept finally the practitioners treat the patient. This entire process will create a strong faith on the part of the patient so that it may positively affect on the psychology of the patient during healing stage. The real success of the traditional healers will be based on the fact that how he/she interprets the symbolic meaning/lay concepts expressing by the patients

having different dimensions. In many cases the traditional healers may not diagnose the problem accurately and it will be just through the symbolic meanings only. In the same way the traditional healers may be over looked the patient because of social or emotional stresses the patient is experiencing. Hence, it is suggested that the trained doctors working in the rural settings should have little knowledge about the lay concept of illness if not the patient may be overlooked or ignored. The Lay concept about health and illness has been ignored largely in the medical textbooks or by the modern medical institutions. Proper emphasis must be given on this issue to understand the health culture of a given community (Gale Encyclopedia of Public Health).

In Indian scenario rural people will have more emphasis on Karma (Deed), Fate, God, evil forces etc. Here people also connect there health issues to these kinds of beliefs. People will strongly believe according to the deed/karma, God will reward or punish. Punishment may be a kind of severe disease/illness. Study show that people who believe illness due to God's effect will perceive more control over their cause of the illness. This shows perceived causality varies across the culture. Some of the culture focus on collectivism which shows ill health may leads to failure in fulfilling certain social obligations (Liyeage, 2010).

Some studies show that patients' will be more concerned about the different burdens on the family due to illness, feeling bad because of not fulfilling social responsibilities properly. They also more worried about the socially engaged emotions rather than the socially disengaged emotions. In this way isolation from the social network (individualism) are moving with the social groups have a lot of consequences in case of emotional responses to illness. It would be very vital to narrate the beliefs about the causes and effects of various health disorders are constructed and reply to it. It is found that in advanced societies usually beliefs and concepts over health and illness will be largely connected to an integral part of the physical and social word. In traditional societies the metaphysical beliefs about health and illness dominates normally. Sociologist's opined the culturally shaped medical advice should be very necessary in providing advanced healthcare systems for rural people. Through the culturally framed theories, the modern medical system should understand lay men's' concept and response to illness in rural scenario and it may play a better tool in providing the good medical care facilities (Uskul and Hynie, 2007; Kitayama et. al, 2006; Kohli and Dhalal, 1998).

Kshathriya (1988) has written "it may be worthwhile to state that at least one component of health is universally seen among the tribal societies and that is

committing or omitting certain acts in other words a breach of trust is thought to bring upon some kind of affliction on the individual or a family as a whole. Measles, tuberculosis diarrhea, cholera are some diseases where individual's action may cause some concern to the family, clan or the village". In the majority cases, people normally do not consider the health status relating to the hygienic or pathogenic rather people connects their illness problem to the supernatural powers many a times. People believe there are some benevolent and malevolent supernatural powers. Benevolent means which do good things to the human being and the later is harm to the mankind. People beliefs continuous worshipping benevolent powers brings good deeds to the family

Among rural people incapacitation/absence from the work is the general index of an illness. Even though the basic concept of the illness changes from caste to caste a person will be declared as a diseased if he/ she could not perform day to day work. They expect a healthy person should work normally without having any problem. Consequently, sometime if people have mild fever, head ache, BP, depression, giddiness etc, will not be considered as a part of disease/ illness because these symptoms will not hamper their normal routine day to day work. Usually peoples don't bother for these simple health issues. Hence, sociologist has concluded that in rural areas illness is more related to functional rather than clinical or biological.

Delton's(1970) Model As To How People Perceive IllnessClinically

Clinically Ill	D		C
	B		A
Clinically Ill			

Tab 9

Category - A: People think that they are not ill both culturally and clinically

Category - B: People think that they are not culturally ill but are clinically ill

Category - C: People think that they are culturally ill but not clinically

Category - D: People think that they are ill both culturally and clinically

Sociological Studies of Lay Health Beliefs

(Sources: Public Health Text Book (online), Public Health Action Support Team CIC), Crinson, 2007

Constructs	Indicators
<p>1. Health as functional capacity (Blaxter:1982)</p> <p>This broad notion would also include the notions of ‘health as the absence of disease’ (as not ill) as well as ‘health despite disease’ (Blaxter:1990). Largely a working class conception, but also held by the elderly, particularly those in poor health, were less likely to define health in terms of illness.</p>	<p>a. The ability to fulfil social & work roles as main criterion of healthiness – never having a day’s illness’ was found to be used as a (positive) moral characteristic of individuals.</p> <p>b. Conceiving health as coping or overcoming disease / misfortune. Related to this is the idea of health as ‘reserve’.</p> <p>c. Cornwall (1984) in her study of a working class community in Bethnal Green, found that the way people thought about their health was a kind of ‘cheerful stoicism’ even when physically ill.</p>
<p>2. Health as emotional well-being (MacInnes & Milburn:1994)</p> <p>Closely linked to health as energy vitality (Blaxter:1990). D’Houtaud & Field(1986) saw this as essentially a middle class concept.</p>	<p>a. Positive approach to life, do not ‘worry all the time’.</p> <p>b. Illness as resulting from negative attitudes – ‘moaners’.</p> <p>c. A holistic and multidimensional view of health and illness.</p>
<p>3. Health as reflecting lifestyle, including a moral</p> <p>Closely linked to health as ‘healthy’ behavior, the ‘healthy life’ (Blaxter:1990).</p>	<p>a. Healthy behavior as not smoking. Good diet, exercising, and not drinking alcohol to excess.</p> <p>b. Moral evaluations of individuals, role of ‘bad habits’ in causative explanations.</p>
<p>4. The notion of ‘candidacy’</p> <p>Utilised in lay explanations of relative risk of disease and efficacy of preventive health behaviours. Constructed from appearance or circumstances surrounding an event i.e the onset of illness. Can support or challenge biomedical aetiology (Davison, Davey Smith & Frankel:1991)</p>	<p>a. Identification of those who become ill / ‘disease candidates’, retrospectively and / or predictively i.e ‘he was fit, skinny and young. The last person you would expect to have a heart attack’.</p> <p>b. Teleological explanations of illness- ‘there was a meaning/purpose in their becoming ill’.</p>
<p>5. Conceptual duality of health</p>	<p>a. Illness as external, arising from a</p>

Tab 10 Stacey (1988)	Endogenous health / exogenous illness (Herzlich:1973)	conflict between the individual and society – lifestyle in its widest sense. b. Health as coming from within; requiring a struggle against ‘ unhealthy lifestyles’
writes "Ordinary people develop	6.Theorizing the body as physical capital or the ‘commodification of the body’ (Bourdieu:1977). Working class having an instrumental relation to body; Middle class seeing the body as a ‘personal project’	a. Working class ideology: body as a ‘means to an end’ / as machine, which may require servicing from medical experts to run efficiently. b. Middle class ideology: body as under personal control, choices can be made about ‘appropriate lifestyle’.

p explanatory theories to account for their material, social and bodily circumstances. These they apply to themselves as individuals, but in developing them they draw on all sorts of knowledge and wisdom some of it derived from their own experience, some of it handed on by word of mouth, other parts of it derived from highly trained practitioners. Thus say explanations go beyond common sense, in that explanations beyond the immediately obvious are included”

It may be any society people will not accept the new things easily. Like that, changes in the age old health practice and customs will not be easily changed having a history of thousand years. Accepting new element/s into their health culture will be largely depend on how the new elements fit into their values, norms and concepts which are already a major part of that particular society. As the culture changes, the health behavior also tend to change similar to those which is characterized by the society at large. As the basic social characteristics of any society, over the period of time, the health seeking behavior also will get change in the larger context. Unless we study the history of medicine and society focusing rural areas, we cannot explain how and when the changing social facts effects on the changing health seeking behavior of a lay person. Further, it is also significant to focus on the doctor- patient relationship in the rural settings as perceived by the many sociologists. They have opined their relationship may get affected by the sub-culture of medicine including the type of disease and socio-economic background of both the doctors and the patient’ (Ahluwalia, 1967; Joshi, 2004).

Solavadar opined

“ Culture does not work in a mechanic and deterministic way, but provides people with more than one way in which somatic and behavioral dysfunctions can be transformed into socially accepted sickness. Sociological proved that patients are

flexible when it comes to explaining and treating disease. Explanatory models are accommodating, do not prohibit each other and are arranged into hierarchies. Disease explanations are negotiated in medical settings and move along with the medical systems that are consulted and the treatments that are applied. Multiple therapeutic uses and not disease precise patterns of resort seem to the norm”... (Solavadar, 2009).

As defined by the experts basically diseases and illness are completely culture specific. It means both the patient and the healer normally will have knowledge on current diseases and illness through an interpretive actions. It includes the biology, cultural practice etc., It is found that faith and practice of the health culture refers as much to the religion and certain studies have proved that the usage of the modern medicine depend on the socio-cultural background, ethno-medicine, political and moral values of a lay person. Based on this factor the lay person may deny to visit the hospital in the future if he is not satisfied with the quality of the service including the duration took to solve the health problem and other issues (Anderson, 2003, Minocha, 1980).

It is not so easy to introduce the western medicine system in the area where the traditional system exists from a long time. People will normally compare among the various medical systems available at the door steps with respect to the quality, history, cost, duration to healing, degree of efficacy etc. Rural people always expect medicines taken by them should solve their health problem as soon as possible which is next to an impossible in reality. They just bother about an immediate consequences. Murdock (1980) has given 3 types of supernatural causation as believed by a lay person.

1. Mystical causation;
2. Theory of animistic causation; 3 And magical causation;

In s mystical theory it is believed that illness causes due to an impersonal relationship between human beings and the surrounding eco system. Next, the animistic theory says illness causes due to the soul, ghost, spirit, etc. Finally magical illness focus on the changes in the health behavior is due to black magic employs by the trained local healers in different names.

Mechnic (1978) has given Ten decision points which determine illness behavior as believed by a lay person;

1. Primary symptoms of illness
2. Individuals experience of system security

3. How illness in distributing the patients
4. Frequency of symptoms
5. How patient is coping with the illness
6. How patient perceives illness focusing his /her cultural background
7. Denial of illness
8. Illness disrupts needs
9. Alternative interpretation about his/her illness problem
10. Decision making about choosing available treatment option

Parsons (1951) gave a key gift in identifying the mechanism of the sick role in terms of what was predictable from the point of patient. Mechanic (1962) has made a contribution in considering what does it mean to be ill and how the lay person does experience and express illness based on his socio-cultural background. He opined faith is the social attachment that makes diagnosis and treatment easy on the part of the lay person and the new health policy needs to be in this direction

Good (1994), has opined since diseases is a natural one it is better to consider the health issue is outside of the lay mans' culture. Rationality plays a vital role as a direct reaction to the dominance of the role of ecology and environment on different health and illness issue. Contemporary social realities and dynamics of health and illness depend on lay men's cultural context and healing process with reference to the cross-cultural examples.

Udry (2001) writes

“Sociologists are very diverse in their theoretical orientations. Some of us work within paradigms that are incompatible with paradigms used by other sociologists, even though we suppose we are working in the same domain – in this case, the study of gender....Paradigms with different perspectives are not necessarily mutually exclusive. I can live with the critics' paradigm. But can they live with mine”? (Udry, 2001: 616)

Worthington and Gogne (2011) have written belief and culture and its impact on patients' outcome. They opined some beliefs have strong impacts on the lay men positively. In the same way some beliefs can negatively impact on the mental and physical well being of a lay men. Sometime cultural bound norms may play a vital role where an individual displaying psychiatric and somatic symptoms. Culture and religion will be the vital factors in identifying and treatment process of any health disorders. Family members and their experiences and background should not be underpinned in analyzing the lay men's perception.

Health related aspects including smoking, alcohol, Junk food, lack of physical activity etc also affects on health. Sociologists are now trying to find out how the cultural factors affecting these food patterns. Next, they are also looking how modern industrial revolution, pollution etc are affecting on the health behavior and culture of the rural people and they are focusing on how the low cost health insurances, old age health problems, pension schemes etc. affecting health behavior among the old aged people in rural settings. Now-a-days youngsters are more prone to various deadly diseases. Sociologists are also looking these issues very seriously in a laymen's perspective focusing youngsters changing life style in the recent times. It is noted that the lay men belonging to the different culture will represent illness and treatment collectively and are unequally distributed in this point.

Zola (1973) has opined that the response to any type of illness by a patient will be mainly depending on how he/she perceives/ belief concerning health and illness. In the next stage, he/she seeks assistance from the various social components (including, friends, relatives, people who suffered from the same health problems previously....etc) to get a proper outlet to come out from the current health problem. Also the medical anthropologists feared during this entire process of the health seeking assistances makes the delay in getting the proper treatment on time. Zola (1973) found that the communities' reaction to symptoms is depends on their cultural values / beliefs concerning health. That is, their perception of what is 'normal'. Therefore, the choice to seek the proper medical help was either promoted or delayed by the various social factors. Zola's (1973) model has identified five different types of occurrence which 'triggered' the judgment to seek the medical care incidents which intimidate people's philosophy of the customariness".

LABELING AND STIGMA

This concept has evolved from an interactional sociological perspective. Basically it focus on the symbolic meaning of health and illness and the societal acceptance. Since 1960 this labeling has been used in the former medical practice as a sociological construction to draw attention that the sick role has both the social and physical dimensions. Stigma follows the labeling process. Since the medical practices do not exist without the social platform the stigma will left a negative image on the patient after he/she is being labeled. It causes a lot of damage on the social life of the patient (ex. AIDS/TB) also. Some time it permanently spoils the identity of the person in the society. Due to the labeling a person will get the social disgrace in which he/she may be socially excluded in due course of time. Due to the stigma, patient and some time his/her family members may not fully participate in the various social

processes. Stigma not only affects on the concerned patient rather it affects on the rest of the family members also. Some time expert calls it as '*courtesy stigma*'. Because of this, the family has to suffer with the feeling of guilt consciousness along with the patient in the society. Family members some time cannot move freely in the society or some time they will be underpinned in the social network. Hence, some time the entire family members have to be away from the various social roles and functions. In case of mental illness, it would be more pathetic both to the patient and to his/her family members.

Lamert's (1967) has done some remarkable work on this issue. He opines that labeling on the sick person may change his/her behavior in relation with the given 'label'. Also he opines the labeling has both primary and secondary deviances. In case of the primary deviance the deviant leaves only the slighter affects on the social and physical status of a person. However, the secondary deviance affects on the social role of a person. It may also positively or negatively effect on the public identification or the societal approval of the patient concerned. Beeker's (1963) has opined the social groups basically create deviance. He felt the deviance has nothing to do with the behavior of a patient; rather it is a reaction between the concerned patient and who reply to it. Deviant is one to whom the label effectively applied. The labeled deviating behavior involves the value judgment. Also he felt the labeling must focus less on the deviant act and more on the social reactions to that particular behavior. Generally the primary deviance represents an illness experience only. The secondary deviance involves the diagnosis process of the doctors who finally label the patient as a legitimately ill or disease free. Also disease label affects on the public image of the concerned patient. Labeling will help in diagnosing the real cause for the disease/illness. It helps whether a patient is biological diseased or just an ill person due to the some psychological issues.

Basically the stigmatization exists because of social reason/sanction. Also few studies have shown that stigma over few illness/disease may get over after some time .Also the stigma also some time limits accessibility to treatment on the part of the patient. Conrad and Barker (1988) have worked about 'contested illnesses. These contested illnesses have a definite cultural level scope or significance. In this case, illness may be purely because of a strong medical reason. But it may not be medically legitimized as claimed/ing by the patient. This type of situation may create a kind of conflict between the medical knowledge of a lay perception focusing the cultural legitimization of symptoms and agony. In this case some time doctor's and the community may question the mental stability of the patient. This would be kind of

culturally visible and medically invisible. Sometime it questions the authenticity of the existing medical technology in labeling a patient (Seambler, 1989; Mathews, 1979).

Fault-lines in sociology of health and illness

Sociology of health and illness has more than 100 years of history. Sociological studies have provided new concepts, theories and other discoveries regarding health and illness from the cross cultural perspective. However even today certain issues are unanswered, existence a gap between findings and practice etc;

1. Whatever knowledge and findings have been done in sociology of health and illness are of the western scholars. All of them have been scientifically trained in the industrial societies. Whatever studies done by them in less developed societies are duly conducted by the western scholars only. This is the major problem of external validity and scope for generalization with special reference to the developing societies like India.

2. The most vital fault-lines in the sociology of health and illness is health disparities in many developing countries. Even though health behavior depends on culture, gender, class, caste and race that have been more exaggerated among developed, developing and poor countries. Different politico-economy structures in all societies also a kind of responsible for the existing health inequalities/over medicalizations. Powerful health institutions and drug the companies have succeeded in exploiting the poor and marginalized people

3. Sociologists have conducted research on health and illness by the using outsider and insider perspective (emic/etic perspective). Sometime researchers had to bow to the drug companies because they pay medical sociologists, medical colleges, scientists and other vested interested agencies a huge amount of money. Hence we cannot expect any reliable results given by the sociologist's is an objective one. Whatever studies have done till now, all are short term in nature. However, longitudinal studies are very rare regarding the health culture is concerned in India . (Albrecht, 2011)

The main question here that what kind of data sociologists gathered to give any final conclusion. Still controversies are going about using the qualitative and quantitative studies in medical sociology. Sociology of health and illness normally not depend on numbers but it depends on a deep understanding of the theoretical perspective. Experts felt conducting sociological studies in the rural area needs structural centered

and meaning centered approaches. Without understanding the local culture, the sociologists cannot conduct an objective studies in any developing societies.

SOCIOLOGY OF HEALTH BEHAVIOR

“Many health problems have their roots in various aspects of community life and cannot be influenced by health interventions alone. Non-medical interventions are also very vital and for optional result, a reasonable co-ordination of both is essential” (Pratiba, 2001).

Today health and illness has attracted wide attentions of medical professionals, Sociologists, policy makers etc. It's because of three important reasons;

1. Gradual change in the health concept of the community;
2. Gradual change in the emphasis;
3. Medical pluralism;
4. Changing healthcare utilizations

Culture is a fundamental aspect of human civilization made out of traditions, beliefs, values, norms etc. Earlier health behavior was classified under other category of social behavior. However, today health behavior is in different domino because of wider health beliefs, significances and practices across the society and its role. Since, health traditions vary across the societies, we cannot generalize about health behavior. Hence sociologists felt to have a new model having both scientific and cultural elements for the study. Understanding disease means, understanding the biology of health. There is a close relationship between biology and the society. Various social and cultural factors influence both illness and the biology of health. Even though illness is a psychological issue, it is duly bounded by social, psychological and cultural issues. Some of psycho-social disorders will have social pathological and social disorder dimensions. Hence, experts have opined to have a strong social rehabilitation programme for the patients' who are facing any terminal illness. Behavioral problem of the children, exclusion of aged people from the health circle, psycho-social rehabilitation of differently challenged people will have larger dimensions of social prospective (Kantidas, 2009). Sociologists have long been interested why different people believe differently with respect to their health. Also they have been interested how the health behavior will be influenced by the various internal and external factors.

There are two different approaches to study health behaviors.

A.Healthcare seeking behavior: Utilization of the system:

According to this approach various socio-economic issues like age, sex, occupation, income education play vital role including various geographical and organizational indicators in the onset of various illness/disease. This approach also enlightens us why people show or not showing interest in using or not using any particular type of medical care. It may be the traditional/ modern. This approach also enlightens us how different barriers keep the patients' away from getting the required medical services.

B. Health care seeking behavior: The process of illness response

This provides information about how remedial action will be indicated as response to illness. It also reveals how people take the decision in choosing required healing pattern/healer. It helps us to predict the possible affirmative / preventive activity with respect to the various health problems of the people. It also reveals how emotional, cognitive, demographic factors play a vital role in choosing or not choosing suitable medical care in time.

Further, wide differences in delaying the healthcare seeking process across the culture can be seen. It may due to the existence of traditional knowledge and belief about the disease, over confidence, ignorance, strong faith in the medical technology etc. various other socio-cultural factors counts a lot here. Some time based on the different health priorities people will develop their health seeking behavior or health care seeking behavior. In addition, people will consult the doctors on any other health workers issue when health disturbs their normal routine life.

Facione (2000) has opined gender also play a vital role in the health care needs. In rural areas the majority cases women are vulnerable about their health needs. They would give preference just to fulfill responsibilities as a family member. Her health requirements always will be least bothered. This might be the reason why some time women shows delay in seeking the required medical care on time in most of the developing societies. Further, in some cases gender issues also would be the vital regarding relationship between the patients' and the doctors. In the rural areas, women patients don't like to be examined by male doctors. Lady Doctors will be very few in rural hospitals. It may be one of the reasons in delaying the health care seeking process (Bottorf et. al, 1998).

Factors influencing treatment seeking behavior as opined by the epidemiologists are

1. Type/nature of illness;
2. Type of healing pattern and its accessibility;

3. Individual and collective experiences and opinion about the pattern of treatment;
4. Faith in the age old treatment pattern (Source: Priya, 2012) .

The pattern of the healthcare system and health institutions varies from society to society. The changes involved in this process will be largely depending on the changing cultural value and norms in the society. Different medical institutions have developed in societies over a period of time. In this process they had to undergo various changes according changing social needs, influence of medical technology and because other social institutions. In the same way a lot of changes in the healing process, approach and ideology regarding diseases and illness can also be seen today. Hence, it is very vital to understand the people's concept regarding emerging health problems, changing health behavior towards new diseases, hygiene, medical technology, medicalizations, medical pluralism etc. Sociologists are studying rurals' health seeking and health seeking behavior care and healing approaches as a total way of life of people. It helps in two different ways.

1. It helps to get a complete picture about the health culture, medicinal systems and its efficacy;
2. To avoid the hurdles in introducing the western medicine in developing societies. (Sources: Madhunagla (2007)

Sociologists have found that more studies are required on three vital concept viz;

- a. Cultural concept on personal hygiene, cleanliness
- b. Food habits
- c. Nutritional status in relation to its culture.

Also the sociologists felt studies are required to find out up to what extent, beliefs and practices are playing a crucial role in health seeking behavior of the people belonging to different class and caste?. Because different caste and class people will have different health culture, attitude, health decision, expenditure pattern etc reflecting the maintenance of normal health system of any society. Even though, preventive medicine is available for the various diseases, the use of such services will be largely influenced by the people's concept on health, illness and concept on etiology of diseases etc (Nagda, (2007).

Sociologists have long back developed many models to scientifically study health culture, health behavior and behavioral change. Some of the theoretical module has been developed after having prolonged research study in a multicultural society.

a.Health Belief Model : - This is a very influential theoretical module and it explains regarding four elements which play a vital role in the health seeking behavior process namely;

1. Apparent vulnerability to the illness;
2. Apparent severity of the illness;
3. Use of prevention behavior ;
4. Possible barriers to that behavior

This module is more significant in understanding community's response to the illness. And this says normally people will focus on these three issues;

1. Chances of getting any particular diseases;
2. Severity of the diseases;
3. Severity and its relation to their existing belief.

These three basic elements of this theory are very vital in understanding the sick role behavior in a multi cultural society. If the disease is more severe, people will take more prevention and curative measures. One drawback of this theory is that it does not focus on the ecology and socio-demographic impacts on lay men's health decision. This theory reveals the severity of the illness will be the prime factor in choosing the different healing approaches. Also people will be worried about the cost and time required for curing. Treatments which cost less will be the first choice in most of the cases.

The Health Belief Model

Fig 15

Sources: Derek Rutter and Lyn Quine (2002), Social Cognition Models and Changing health behavior,. In the book 'Changing Health Behavior Intervention and Research with Social Cognition Model's: Open University Press : UK

B. Theory of Reasoned Action : - This theory is propounded by Ajzen and Fishbein in 1972. This theory basically is to predict the patients' specific health behavior in a given time & space. This theory further says behavior may be a total sum of the specific intention, beliefs, attitude, outcome and norms. This theory also highlights how measurement of an intention plays a vital role in choosing a specific health behavior

Source: Fishbein, M., & Ajzen, I. (1975), Belief, Attitude, Intention, and Behavior: An Introduction to Theory and Research. Ontario: Addison-Wesley Pub.

Kroeger's Model for Reasoned Action (1983)

Fig 16

Source: Kroeger, A. (1983) Anthropological And Socio-Medical Health Care Research In Developing Countries. Social Science & Medicine, (17):147-161

C. Theory of Planned Behavior,

According to this theory behavioral intention involves----

1. Attitudes towards behavior which is determined by the belief
2. Subjective norms are approval of once behavior and personnel motivation
3. Perceived behavior will be determent by access to the resources needed
4. Socio-demographic factors affecting above determinants

Source: Conner, M. & Sparks, P. (1995) The Theory of Planned Behavior and Health Behaviors, in Predicting Health Behaviour (Conner, M. & Norman, P. eds.). Buckingham: Open University Press.

Theory of Reasoned Action/Planned Behavior

(Extracted)

	Constructs	Description
1	Environmental	Factors outside the person
2	Situation	One's perception of the environment
3	Behavioral Capability	One's knowledge and skills to perform a behavior
4	Expectations	One's anticipation of the outcomes of a behavior
5	Expectancies	How good or bad one evaluates the outcomes to be
6	Self-control	Regulation of one's own behavior
7	Observational Learning	Acquiring a new behavior by watching someone else perform it and observing the outcomes—a.k.a. modeling
8	Reinforcements	Responses to a person's behavior that affect how likely it is that the behavior will reoccur
9	Self-efficacy	One's confidence in one's own ability to perform a behavior
10	Emotional Coping Responses	Strategies used by someone to deal with emotionally challenging thoughts, events, or experiences
11	Reciprocal Determinism	Dynamic interaction of the person, the behavior, and his/her environment

Tab 11

+This is a widely used behavioral forecast theory which represents a social-psychological loom to consider and predicting the determinants of health-behavior

Sources: Colleen A. Redding, Health Behavior Models, The International Electronic Journal of Health Education, 2000; 3 (Special Issue): 180-193<http://www.iejhe.siu.edu>

D. Diffusion of Health Innovations Model : - According to this theory diffusion of health education plays a vital role in changing the health behavior of an individual. Here also how information passes through specific channels amongst the societal members will be a vital issue .This theory says information on the health behavior will have following steps;

1. Identification of the health problem;
2. Possible selection of the problem;
3. Development of specific strategy to cure the problem;

4. Marketing of the innovative strategies;
5. Disseminating new ideas;
6. Consequences of the new ideas

This theory also highlights that the success of the health communications will be based on the effective rate of the diffusion and how easily it will be communicated to the other members. Sometime it depend on the cost, time and energy etc., Adaptation of this idea might give good result in rural India for example.

1. Selling iodized salt;
2. Contraceptive injections etc

Even though mass media plays a vital role in spreading health education, interpersonal relationship also counts a lot.

E. PRECEDE Model : -

This theory is propounded by Green and Others (1980)

When expanding the term **PRECEDE** it stands--

P – Stands for Predisposing

R – Stands for Reinforcing

E – Stands for Enabling

C – Stands for Causes

E – Stands for Educational

D – Stands for Diagnosis and

E – Stands for Evaluation

In general this theory primarily focused on the entire community rather than the individuals. This theory also focuses on the effectiveness of interventions and targets for the further interventions/improvement. This model normally works through seven phases;

1. Social diagnosis
2. Epidemiologic diagnosis
3. Behavioral and non-behavioral causes of health problem
4. Activities to identify pre disposing and enabling factors with that of concerned health behavior
5. Choosing the specific health interventions
6. Administration and implementation of the specific health programmes
7. Evaluation

F. Trans Theoretical Model :-

This model currently has four elements;

1. Different stages of the changing health behavior;
2. Balancing health decision;
3. Self efficiency;
4. Elements of change

According to this theory sometime patients' normally will not take any sudden decision about their health problems for the first few days. After that, the patient may take a positive health behavior and seriously think about the health problem or even just ignore it again. In the second stage, the patient will take some decision balancing the cost and benefits in opting a suitable health care. In case of self efficiency, either patient may dare to have a new health behavior or to continue the same unhealthy behavior for few a more days .

G. Precaution Adoption Process Model

This model has Five stages;

- Unaware
- Unengaged
- Undecided or decided not to act
- Undecided to act
- Acting-and-Maintenance

The transtheoretical model assesses an individual's readiness to act on a new healthier behavior

Sources : Derek Rutter and Lyn Quine (2002), Social Cognition Models and Changing health behaviors. In the book 'Changing Health Behavior Intervention and Research with Social Cognitive Model', UK;Open University Press.

H. Explanatory Model: This theory propounded by Kleinman in 1980. This theory focused on an interrelationship between the patients' and the doctor. Also this theory focus on individual interactions and the faith he/she has on the Doctors, and faith in a given set of medical systems etc.

This model depends on an individual experiences with the actual health status or health information's

This theory has four elements;

- Etiologic ;
- Time and mode of onset of symptoms ;
- Patho- physiology ;
- Course of sickness;
- Treatment

I, Meaning Centered Approach : - This theory highlights the patients perspective, cultural influences, behavioral expression etc., towards the specific health disorder. This theory strongly opines illness is a psycho dynamic aspect. This theory also highlights diffusion of health behavior from culture to culture.

Meaning-Centered Approach to Clinical Practice	
	<p><u>Primary Principles</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Groups vary in the specificity of their medical complaints● Groups vary in their style of medical complaining● Group vary in the nature of their anxiety about the Meaning of symptoms● Groups vary in their focus on organ systems● Groups vary in their response to therapeutic strategies● Human illness is fundamentally somatic or meaningful● Clinical practice is inherently interpretive Actions● Practitioners must Elicit patients requests, questions, etc● Elicit and decode patients semantic networks● Distinguish disease and illness and develop plans for Managing problems● Elicit explanatory models of patients and families● Analyze conflict with biomedical models, and negotiate alternatives

Source: B.J.Good and M.J.D.Good,(1981) The meaning of symptoms: A Cultural Hermeneutic Model of Clinical Practice, in I. Eisenberg and A. Kleinman,(edt) ‘The Relevance of Social Science for Medicine’, Dordrecht: Kluwer Academic Publishers

J. Health Care Utilization Model: (The socio-behavioral model)

(Adopted from Andersen & Newman, 1973)

The model was specifically developed to investigate the use of biomedical health care in developing societies

This model focus on ;

- Predisposing factors
- Enabling factors
- Need factors
- Health service use

Fig 19

Source: Andersen, R. & Neuman, J.F. (1973) Societal And Individual Determinants Of Medical Care Utilization In the United States . *Health and SocietyQuarterly*, (51):95-124

K. Rosenstock’s Health Belief Model (adapted from Wolinsky, 1988)

This theory believes

- 1) An individual will seek preventive health care if they think they may get an illness/disease soon
- 2) A person will not seek treatment or prevention if he/she think it is not a serious health issue
- 3) An individual will not take an action unless the treatment or prevention is perceived as having greater benefits than costs;
4. An Individual may get more information about the health through his/her social network

Fig 20

Source: David P. Rebhan (2007), Health Care Utilization: Understanding and applying theories and models of health care seeking behavior .website extract

L. The “Four As” Model : - This is the most popular model to study health behavior and to find out the barriers in seeking appropriate medical care.

It has four elements

- * Availability : - It refers to different health care systems including, clinics, hospitals, drug store etc.,
- * Accessibility : - It may include different transport system.
- * Affordability : - It includes treatment cost.
- * Acceptability : - It includes social and cultural dimension of the potential health care system.

Good’s Pathway model Model,

This model focus on the significance of ‘significant others’ and the decision-making process. (Significant others’ are part of the ‘therapy managing group’)

Fig 21

(The arrow indicates that people move from one sector to another)

Source: Good, C.M. (1987) Etno-medical Systems in Africa. New York: The Guilford Press.

M .Ethnographic Decision- Making Model.

It is intended to predict the exact health seeking behavior of an individual focusing ground reality. The methodology they use in order to identify key factors involved in therapy choice .This model study about involving in-depth enquiry regarding the perceives of the severity of illness and capacity or absence of required economic resources to bear the possible cost. Having some hypothesis this model reveals how family takes an appropriate decision regarding medical care.

R. Fear Models:-

This a. **Fear drive model** deals about the level of 'fear' associates with the changing health behavior. This theory says the concept of 'fear' can be used as an agent for change in the health seeking behavior.

b. Fear Model: Recruiter (2001) has developed this model. In this model the influence of fear on perceived threat is identified. This theory assumes due to fear, patient or normal people will look for genuine new health information's to control their fears, anxiety etc.

Expanded Health Belief Model Combined with Fear Drive Model & Fear Model

Fig 22

Sources: Recruiter (2001)

Framework on Women's ISM Therapeutic Behaviour
Intermediate

Fig 22(a)

Background

Therapeutic

Having prior exposure to Non-Allopathic Treatment

Source: Papiya Mazumdar and Sumit Mazumdar (2007). Traditional Medicine in Contemporary India: *Medical Pluralism* by Urban Females, Paper presented at 2nd Indian Anthropological Congress, Human Development: Evolution and Vision, organized by Indian National Confederation and Academy of Anthropologists (INCAA), Pune University.

I. Spontaneous Processing Model: -

This theory focused on an unpredictable nature, component and process in the particular health decision making. This model has focused on the individuals and the centrality of cognitive process (Mackain, 2003).

J. Self Care Model ;

Self care is a “processes by which people function on their own beliefs in the health promotion prevention and in the disease detection process” (Levin,1981; Adams et, al. 2003).

It involves the self diagnosis and the curing including;

- Using expired medicines
- Buying medicines over the counter
- Using home remedies
- Faith healing
- Meeting only undertrained local healer.

K. Social Cognition Model: - This model depends on Two important assumptions.;

1. Normally health is influenced by a very particular /specific inherited behavior
2. Any health behavior is modifiable at given time and space.

This theory further opines that individuals normally take a rational decision by weighing the pros and cons of a particular and intended health behavior. Also this theory says health behavior will keep changing as new information available. Also this model reveals how different demographic variables and psychological characteristics affect on health beliefs.

Diffusion of Innovation Theory/model

Instead of stressing completely on personnel decision-makers or social structures, the Diffusion of Innovation (DoI) theory focus its stress on novelty as an manager of behaviour change, with innovation defined as ‘an idea, practice, or object perceived as new’ (Rogers 2003: 12).

Predicting Health Behaviour with Social Cognition Models

Social Cognition Models tries to forecast the health behaviour through a diversity of means, and are predicated on two assumptions 1.central to classic 2. New health promotions: This model says health is influenced by 1.behaviour; 2.behaviour is modifiable (Conner and Norman, 1996b).

Information

Fig 23

Sources: Sheeran, P and Abraham, C (1996) The Health Belief Model. In M Conner and P Norman (eds) Predicting Health Behaviours: research and practice with social cognition models Open University Press, Buckingham. 23-61

F. Community Organization Theory ;

This theory believes an active participation of the community solving the health and other social problems. It focus on the community empowerment, and its participation in framing the new health policies

Z. Social Environment and Health Model.

This theory profound that the social environment is associated with disease and the mortality risk which is an independent of other individual risk factors. This theory further saysthe social disorganization, urban environment, social change, and social control also play a vital role in the health seeking behavior .

The Guide to Community Preventive Services’s Social Environment and Health Model.

Health Determinants

Fig 24

Source: L. M. Anderson, S. C. Scrimshaw, M. T. Fullilove, et al., “The Community Guide’s Model for Linking the Social Environment to Health,” 2003, *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 24(3S), p. 13.

There are several other theories to explain health seeking behavior including

A. Multi Attribute Utility Theory : - This theory basically predicts given health behavior of an individual based on evaluating the consequences associated with following or not following a given customer behavior.

B. Ecological Model of Health Behavior:-

This model deals about three vital factors;

1. Multiple factors influencing on the health behavior
2. Different ecological factors effecting on the behavior interaction

This model says multilevel interventions will be an effective in changing the specific health behavior.

C. Self Efficacy Theory:- According to this theory there are two determinants of the health behavior namely;

1. Perceived self efficacy;
2. Outcome expectancies.

Both determinants have positive and negative impacts of performing the health behavior.

D. Protection Motivation Theory:- Rogers (1983) has developed this theory to reveal how people react to the health threat communications (like rumors. media etc). Also this theory deals about the protection and motivations of the people to protect oneself against any kind of illness or diseases. In addition, this theory deals about how the different factors influencing on the people in taking the preventive measures to save themselves from the possible health problems.

E. Social Learning Theory:- According to this theory three factors are responsible for the health behavior of an individual .

- a. Personal factors;
- b. Environmental factors;
- c. Self efficacy

Also it focused on the capability and reinforcement capacity of the patients'

G. Organizational Change Theory:-

It specifically deals about the success of the health policies and programmes implementing by the various formal organizations. It also deals about the

organizational strategies to improve the community health through the various health policies.

H. Diffusion of Innovations theory: -

It deals about how new ideas and the concepts on health issues spreads across the society through the various formal and informal channels.

It is found that a lot of discussions are running over on these theories and the established models to study the health seeking behavior including its weakens and strong points. Each and every theory and, the model have their own strong and drawbacks in understanding the health behavior in a given setting. Some theories will result in giving the potential symptom of illness/disease (how and why people believe so) defined as an illness or sickness behavior. All these theories and models have their own way of generalizing the general health behavior within the theoretical frame work. However, we should note that unlike theories /model actual health seeking behavior will be differ in the ground reality.

Since all theories are framed by the western experts some time it may not applicable to the Indian settings. We have to use it as a ready reference only.

Apart of the model and theories some the researchers have given some noteworthy findings through their studies. Suchman (1965) has given how an individual takes a decision about use/not to use the health care system based on

1. Symptom experience including pain;
2. Assumption of a sick role;
3. Medical care contact;
4. Dependent patient role
5. Inner stanch and the patient to recover from illness.

Yound and Gorro(2001) has given Four criteria's while opting the suitable health seeking behavior by a person

1. Severity of the illness;
2. Availability of home remedy ;
3. Success or failure of home remedy;
4. The cost and availability of health care system.

Weller and others (1997) have found the health seeking behavior depends on

1. Seriousness of illness;
2. Cost factors;

3. Past experience with the same illness

Priya, (2012) said the nature of illness has been in line of action based on the perceived role and the actors.

1. Natural healing
2. Human effort through (healer/doctors/ ritual)
3. Role of the spirit world
4. The fate/ good or destiny etc.. (sources: Priya, 2012)

Susanna Hausmann-Muela and others have worked on to illustrate how the health-seeking processes are integrated in the processes of vulnerability. They have given a sketch

Fig 25

Source: Susanna Hausmann-Muela and others (2003), Health-seeking Behaviour and the Health System Response, DCPD Working Paper No. 14.

SOCIOLOGY OF MEDICINE IN INDIA

Like economy, religion and politics the health and illness is a part and parcel of the any society. In sociology, the relationship among magic, religion and medicines have been discussed deeply. The Indian sociologists have done in-depth study of the social character of health and sickness. Truly speaking the field of medicine comprise a number of individuals interacting with each other influenced by the local health culture and the society. In this way the concept of health, illness and medicine will be largely influenced by the particular type of culture mainly. Hence health and illness should be studied in a holistic way from the lens of the socio-cultural factors. Each and every individual will develop the health seeking behavior or health care seeking behavior over the period of time. Sometime the health seeking behavior may be similar or different. In this background the Indian sociologists have tried to study the social dimension of health and illness and response to the society.

In Indian society people's concept about health and illness varies from culture to culture, caste to caste, class to class and one geographical area to another. In rural areas people will normally presume illness may be due to an angry deity or cosmological effects because of sins and crimes committed in the past or present life. Sometime people in the rural parts will connect their health problems due to the sin of their previous life. For example if a person suffering from the blood related problems, largely people think that person might have killed a holy cow in the past life. Also sometime rural people think diseases/illness are normally due to the some internal factors i.e. three humors (tri-dosha) of the human body. I e. Air, Bile and Phlegm (vaatha/pittha/ khafa).

Sociological studies conducted in many rural parts of the country have generalized that rural people normally classify diseases or illness into two categories, they are

1. An Illness which can be cured by the local healers (folk medicine)
2. An Illness which can be cured only by the western medicine.

This classification will be based on the previous experience of the patient or advice given by the family or village elders from time to time. Car (1955) has conducted some noted studies in rural Rajasthan and narrated about peoples beliefs on health and illness. People were really against the western theories of etiology and the curing techniques because of the strong belief in local health culture. Though India is a heterogeneous society, there are certain elements which are common in all types of

cultures. This is because of exchange of certain elements over the period of time between the different cultures because of Sanskritisation and Universalisation (Srinvasa,1952). Sociologists have shown how the cultural elements transfer from one society to another. Sometime due to an uneven spread of culture, certain traditions and customs can be seen across the society and sometime only in certain specific geographical areas. This is also applicable to the health culture.

Normally in the rural areas, diagnose of any health disorder will take place initially at the family level. Before visiting the healer people in the rural parts usually practice certain home treatments. The elder people in a particular family will extend their opinion, suggestions and the possible healing treatment for any illness or diseases. Also they will cross-check with other experienced people of the village or friends or relatives through their own social network. In many parts of the rural area, healing approach or theory will be largely decided based on the collective opinion (Tribhuvan, 1988). If the home remedy failed then the patient will visit the local healer/doctors to solve the health problem. In rural areas, we can see some local specialists who are well experienced in curing certain disorders. These local healers use different system of medicines to cure the health problem. Sometime this would be monopolized by some families belonging to the higher caste.

Certain studies conducted in the rural areas have provided some valuable notions about the illness ideology of the Indian rural folk. Sometime illness will be handled in a non-magical and non-religious way because diagnosing and the curing of the various illness differs from culture to culture. People would believe the shamans or priests only can interpreter the supernatural phenomena causing health issues. Sometime rationale for choosing a particular type of treatment/healer will be based on the suggestions given by some other people who were a victim for the same problem. Also they guide the suitable healer, he/she had approached previously to cure that health problem. Thus the patient's perceptions about the origin and cause of illness and healing take its meaningful course towards the specific healer in a given situation in rural parts. Shaman's ideology is that whatever illness causes due to the spiritual reason, should be handled in spiritually way only. After conducting many diagnostic rituals, healer always administer medicines to their patients' to make healing meaningful and to rise the comfort level of the patient at best (Basen,1992;Chopra, 1984).

There are two major division of curing techniques in traditional Indian medicine system;

1. One who diagnose and use appropriate theory based on the magical power or supernatural power
2. One who respects and honors the patients' self diagnosis and suggests suitable therapeutic measures.

It is found that entire set of ritual performances including the chants, songs, pooja, gestures, etc. have a lot of underlying scientific meanings. Only the healers would know about these meanings and can interpret these meanings. Whatever meanings involve in a healing procedure is embedded in a symbolic system and it represents the cultural order of that community in a given geographical area. Whatever ritual performance takes place with preventive, curative and promotive for the betterment of the health status in any cultural settings will be normally and clinically meaningful reality. The main aim behind any ritual performance and healing techniques would be to identify the origin, and the reasons for the health disorder. Further, the rituals would be conducted to honor or to compromise with cosmic powers or spirits or pathogenic agents to restore the disturbed cultural order. Since people perceive illness is an indication of impurity of mind and soul, people would think mind and soul should get purified through the various ritual healings.

Even today established contrasts and conflicts exist between the local and the western medical system in rural settings. Experts opined rural India needs medicinal system having the best understanding of social life of the Indian villages. Also it is found that in rural settings doctor and his treatment approach must be suitable to the cultural background of the patient. Introducing any new medical system should be in a position to meet the cultural expectations of the rural patients'. Since the Indian villagers are more conservative in nature emerging medical pluralism needs to focus on social organization and the institutions in the rural settings.

RELIGION, CASTE AND THE MEDICINE

Chaudhuri (2012) write

‘It is rightly recognized that health is not the restricted sphere of medical science, because each and every health culture, irrespective of its simplicity and complexity, has its own beliefs and practices relating to diseases. No culture works in a worthless fashion in its treatment of diseases’.

Every culture evolves its own classification and structure of medicine in order to treat diseases in its own way. Thus, treatment of the disease may differ among various social groups. To comprehend the health and health-related problems in an accurate viewpoint, it is extremely significant to think about the socio-cultural factors surrounding the health issues. This is an extra relevant factor in the rural areas too. Studies conducted on sociology of health and illness in India has used an existing social structure as the basic unit for the reference. Caste and class will play specific roles and in rural areas some time people belonging to the higher caste will be the power centric and even they can control the money and health. Even though the western medical system has an edge over the traditional one, its success depends on how good it gets a reliable space “between the realm of outsider and the inner realm of kinship” (Morriot, 1955; Kakar,1990).

Caste and religion have a close similar/dissimilar associations in using specific/different kind of medical system in rural settings. Also few studies have shown religion has no connection with using a specific type of medicinal system. Sujatha (2003) in her study has opined usage of Unani system is quite universal in Kerala, while people belongs to another religion in UP & other states are sparingly use Unani in all walks of life. Sidda system is relatively rare among the Muslims and Christens’ where it is quite common in case of low caste Hindus especially among the tribal people (Kakar, 1990). Faith healing is a common phenomenon with the Hindu’s and Muslims and it is most uncommon among the Christens. Hence it raises some important question regarding the relationship between different religious background and the usages of a specific type of medicine available in the society. Ayurvedic is an oldest system of medicine in our society and it is more prevalent among all the religion. Uberoi (2002) has opined in some part of the world people would like to differentiate between religion and the medicine based on the procedures involved in

curing sessions. Otherwise any identification of any type of medical system would lead to the communal issue (Sujatha,2002).

Burton (2008) has opined that the relationship between the caste and medicine especially in the post industrial society is a significant sociological issue. Certain castes in rural areas have dominated on the traditional medicines. It has become a family business today. Also it is found that certain traditional healers would like to extend the treatment only for the patients' belonging to his/her caste only. Sujatha (2003) felt in British regime traditional medicinal system was an important tool for the caste mobilization. Abraham (2010) felt caste comparison and caste based treatment have been plagued in the traditional medicine system in the rural parts of the country today. It is also found, because of the caste and class conflicts and the medicalizations, the socially excluded communities are suffering a lot in the rural parts of the country.

Sociologists from the long back are showing interest in studying various segmentation of the society and emerging medicinal system. Also the sociologists are doing some comparative studies about the medical pluralism using by the various castes and ethnicity people as a strong indicator/parameter in evaluating the health inequalities in rural aprts. Sujatha (2005) has found each and every caste in India has its own health culture, tradition, ritual, diet in a given society. **Also** it is noted in a multi caste society the health culture and health seeking behaviors varies significantly under the changing social system due to the various external factors. The lower caste people mostly prefer only the traditional medical care for any health problems while the higher caste people will opt the quality medicines. There economic conditions also play a vital role too.

In rural areas each and every caste has its own healer some time the caste factor of a local healer would be a significant issue too. The caste based medical skills also an important issue for the debate today. Though the female traditional healers available in the every society, they are not getting enough importance. Lee and Bery (2005) have opined religious/caste based offers will play a vital role in meaning positive and mental health in the area of onset of a disease, cure and general well-being. Next, Raghulam et. al, (2002) and Razali et. al, (2002) have opined some religion and caste based health practices will be used as both the psycho-biological and cultural healing practices. Further Winkelman (2002); West(2000); Koching and

Comen(2002) and Seligner (2005) have opined some healing practice's taking place in religious places like Masque's, (dargahs) and the Churches' will be a type of recovery oriented approach to come out of the mental trauma. Also Statsny and Lehmann (2007) and Minkowitrz and Dhanda (2006) have opined that religious practices for healing will help the patients' to come out of his/her illness and guide others to recovery as soon as possible. Hence the caste and religion have a very close association with health and illness issue in rural areas.

Medical Knowledge and Power: A Sociological Concept

Crinson (2007) writes

“Power is essentially relational rather than something that is possessed by individual doctors or the medical profession as a part of social group”.

As we know the development of the medical knowledge has a long history. The Bio-medical science help us to reveal the cause and effect with special reference to the health and illness issue. The scientific understanding health and illness can only be applied through the material practice. The Medical knowledge evolved as an organizational system of formal health care system in this globe. This formal health care system through the material practice has become socially embedded gradually. The Medical knowledge, education and power are the core part of the modern healthcare system (Crinsons, 2007). Earlier, experts were used to define the term medical knowledge as ‘Medical Cosmologies’. This itself shows the medicine has a close relationship with the society or it is a part and parcel of the society. The evolution of medical knowledge has its own root within the societal domain. The medical knowledge composed of both the science and social sphere. Before industrialization, the doctors were used to judge the sick person based on the personal attributes of the patients’. Institutional (hospital) based medicinal system has developed in association with the continuing phase of the social change. The Medical knowledge evolved along with the industrialization, urbanization, capitalist society etc. Along with this, the doctor- patient balance of power begun to change. The Medical knowledge ahs gradually started to pass from the patient to the doctors.

New medical discoveries and the improvised treatment started to emerge. Foucault (1973)coin the term “Clinical Gaze” for this. Also he showed the importance of the social relationship of the medical knowledge between the physicians' and patients'. Power is a kind of an approach or discursive practice which

is the core part of an emerging social system. Power exists at all the levels which controls the different segments of the society including the health. In the case of medicine, power is nothing but scientific knowledge associated with modern medical health care systems including hospitals, physicians, medicines etc. Since any health care system needs to work within the society this often referred as biomedical discourses. Power and knowledge are the most vital for both development of new health care system and its sustainability in the society.

Armstrong's (1983), opine "any new health policies, schemes or programmes are just a kind of medical power channelizing through the supervision of a communities health seeking behavior". Further, Crinson (2007) has felt all health polices basically would have some vested interests. Hence, sociologists felt this is the time to negotiate with the medical knowledge and power for maximizing health status of a layman.

Bhasin (2006) has opined underestimating the traditional medical system may not promote the biomedical therapy in rural areas all of a sudden. We cannot just overlook the efficacy of the traditional medicine because just because it is being used by the people over the centuries. Rapid expansion and promotion of the medical system and knowledge could not affect the popularity and avoid in using the traditional medicine. She opined experts should work on reducing the complexities and problems involved in using the bio-medical system. Normally rural folk does not want any new medicinal system to be encroached into their traditional health culture. Any new medical system should commensurate with their socio- cultural systems. We must have an understanding of diverse culture and the traditions in the current medicinal system and health culture.

MEDICALIZATION:- It is nothing but an expansion of the medical jurisdiction in the areas normally thought non-medical (Szasz, 2007). Defining the term medicalization is quite complex because we cannot clearly separate the medical issue from the non-medical domain focusing the societal perspective. Because there are so many factors which effecting separately on both the medical and non medical domains including the power, knowledge, professional objectives, political economy, socio-cultural issues, patients' interest etc. Illich (1976) has opined 'day by day more and more segmentation of human life has been brought into the bio-medical influence'.

The concept of medicalization reflects both interactions and the Marxist approach focusing health and illness. It is an extended part of the social domain of medicine.

It is opined that the medicalization has undermined the people's ability to take care of their own health and medicalization has a dual role to play like;

1. It discloses and eradicates the diseases 2. It negotiates the diseases into sickness.

Parson (1964) has opined establishing what is medical and non-medical will be the base for the medicalization and is the result of the functional connection between curing the diseases and the normal functions performed by the sick role. Sickness according to Parson is 'a social fact between physician and the patient corresponding to their wider social roles' (Parson, 1964).

Zola (1978) has opined that the medicine acts 'as a tool to control the society and medicine is a vital agency or force in medicalizing society'. Medicine has become legitimate control over the people's health. Sometime the medicine expands its influence unnecessarily even on the healthier individuals too. Friedson (1998) opines 'political aspects acts as a powerful process in the society taking forward the expansion of medicalization process rapidly'. Illich (1976) has observed 'new medicine is basically a capital oriented forming the basis of the modern society and which is narrowing down the definition of the health and illness'. Medicalization has its roots in the sick role. It is driven largely by the social control aspirations having implications on the day to day life of an individual. Medicalization is a kind of social construction. Indeed, not only medicine, however, sociology of medicine also produces medicalization though;

- a. It produces knowledge about the medicine
- b. Indirectly expands the nature of the medicalization.

Kennedy and Kennedy (2010) opined social construction is the core part to reveal the role of medicine in the medicalization of the society. The social construction process moves through a sociological frame of reference naturally. Indirectly, sociological components of the medicine will play a vital role in the various stages of the social constructions of medicalization.

Today the medicalization has expanded to cover bio-technology, consumers and the insurance sector also. At present the commercial domain of medicine is fast expanding. Now a day's every human problem is being considered as a medical

problem and are trying to solve it medically only. Sociologists are now focusing on how a disease normally develops, considers medically valid and treat the patients' accordingly. Some of the natural phenomena which are common in the human life are also being labeled as medically valid for some type of treatment! Sometime problems among the human relations will also be treated medially! Also complicated social problems are being treated medically today! It seems that it has become a tradition human problems are being treated scientifically rather than addressing the real underlying socio-culture or other cause for the actual problem. On the other hand, it is found that the medicalization play a vital role in providing an advanced and the scientific health care system. Some Sociologist's have opined some time the false lay knowledge about the illness/disease may decrease the relationship between the Doctors and the patients' and there by the medicalization expands in the society rapidly. The process of medicalization is of vital issue to be debated in the new health care sector focusing the rural folks.

Kinds of Medical Knowledge and Accounts (Allan Young:1982)

Fig 26

SOURCES: Adopted from Allan young (1982) the Anthropologies of Illness and Sickness Annual, Review of Anthropology, (11):257-85.

Analytic Framework Used To Evaluate The Effectiveness Of Healthcare System Interventions To Increase Cultural Competence.

Fig 27

Sources: Laurie M. Anderson and others , Culturally Competent Healthcare Systems A Systematic Review, Am. J Prev Med 2003;24(3S)

Globalizations and Health

The Globalization has spread its tentacles' everywhere. It has not even left the health sector. As globalization intensifies, new medical technologies and new disease are emerging which is a major challenge to the health care system today. It has led to the new paradigm called 'Development of Diseases'. Due to the socio economic development process, day-by-day various types' of the disease are emerging, mainly due to the changes in ecology, environment, changing life style etc. In this context, we also should note that transferring the western bio-medicines care system in the non western traditional area is a vital change due to the rapid globalization, privatization and liberalizations focusing rural people. Hence, today we can witness for the rapid medical pluralism in each and every culture as new drugs are being developed and new diseases are also emerging simultaneously.

It is also noted that globalization is the major responsible factor in creating awareness about the medical education and more improved health behavior in any society. Today people are largely using over the counter medicine (without prescription by the doctor) as a part of self medication. Biologist's opined that today new drug resistant diseases are emerging like mushrooms. Because of knowledge explosion in medical science, the lay concept about health and illness is also changing rapidly. Both formal and informal medical care institutions are rapidly emerging in the society. Today people can choose any medical caring system to prevent any type of health problems.

A lot of changes have also occurred in the basic theory of illness ideology and sick role because of the availability of speedy healing techniques/treatments. The significance of the "sick role" has also been diluted because of globalizations. The Globalization has affected even on the concept of traditional or folk medicine today. Today the public health communication has been effective due to the availability of new and upcoming formal and informal health channels. However, because of globalization the western bio-medicine acting as a system of social control. A report says today the western part of the globe turning to use the non-biomedical healing system rather than modern medicines! .

CHAPTER VI

**RURAL HEALTH SCENARIO IN
KARNATAKA**

Basically India and is a land of villages. Karnataka is also a more or less rural dominant area. Since the independence, Government of India has implemented several programmes to improve the health conditions of the rural people. However, growing regional and gender disparities have become a big challenge for the rural health sector. Now-a-days. In rural Karnataka people are facing both communicable and non-communicable health disorders. Availability quality primary health care has still become a distant dream in many rural parts. HIV is also fast spreading in the rural areas of the Karnataka state like anything. Life expectancy has increased up to 65 years in Karnataka. The infant mortality rate is around 85 for every 1000 live births today. The maternal mortality rate is around 445 for every 1,00,000 live births. However, the report says more than 70% of all deaths are causing only due to the communicable diseases in the rural parts in the state. Poverty, illiteracy, unhygienic health conditions, malnutrition, scarcity for potable water, drought etc., are some of the reasons why the rural are the worst victims for the various health disorders even today in Karnataka. Recent study on accessing to the quality healthcare facilities shows that rural areas stay drastically underdeveloped in terms of the health infrastructure in rural Karnataka: About half the people in India and over three-fifths of those who live in the rural areas need to travel around 4-6 km to reach PHC/SC. Rural areas in Karnataka general are marked by the poor implementation of the basic health facilities. Governments have implemented many rural specific health programmes. Still situation has not improved yet. High concentration of infectious diseases, absence of effective health education, lack of fundamental facilities, problems in the implementation are adversely affecting the rural parts in the state today. this portion deals about Rural Health Scenario In Karnataka

Rural Health in Karnataka

Strasser, (2010) writes

“In all developing countries, accessibility to rural and remote communities is exaggerated by the physical topography, with mountains, deserts and jungles creating difficulties for transportation, at times complicated by varying climatic conditions. As a result, in some areas, at least some of the time, there is no means of transportation, and evacuation of critically ill or injured patients is impossible. The standard and quality of communications between diverse rural and remote areas and between those communities and the urban centers is also very variable”(Strasser, 2010).

Rural areas in general are marked by the poor implementation of health facilities. Various Governments have implemented many rural specific health programmes. High concentration of infectious diseases, absence of effective health education, lack of fundamental facilities, problems in the implementation are adversely affecting the rurals' health today. Even today there is no good road facility to reach many remote villages across the country. Due to this factor, new medical technologies have not yet reached to the many villages in the country. Rural's health today has two important dimensions;

1. Some of the communicable diseases which are most commonly prevalent among the rurals including Malaria, Cholera, Diarrhea, Malnutrition, etc. require good health education , grass root level interventions and hygienic environment.

2. Some of the non-communicable diseases including Metal illness, Neurological problems, Kidney and Heart problems etc require some special programmes .

According to Aman Gupta, “India is the second most populous country in the world and with a healthcare infrastructure that is over-burdened with ever increasing population, a set of challenges that are unique to India has raised.” He further writes as below:

- “India faces the twin epidemic of continuing/emerging infectious diseases as well as chronic degenerative diseases;
- The former is related to the poor implementation of the public health programs, and the latter to demographic transition with increase life expectancy;
- Economic deprivation in a larger segment of the population results in the poor access to the health care.

- Poor educational status leads to the non-utilisation of scanty health services and increasing avoidable risk factors.
- India faces high burden of disease because of the lack of environmental sanitation and safe drinking water, under-nutrition, poor living conditions, and limited access to preventive and curative health services.
- Lack of education, gender inequality and explosive growth of population contribute to the increasing burden of disease.
- Expenditure on health by the Government continues to be low. It is not viewed as an investment but rather as a dead loss.
- States under financial constraints cut expenditure on health.
- Growth in national income by itself is not enough, if the benefits do not manifest themselves in the form of more food, better access to health and education.”(quoted)

Recent study on accessing to the quality healthcare facilities shows that rural areas stay drastically underdeveloped in terms of the health infrastructure in India : About half the people in India and over three-fifths of those who live in the rural areas need to travel around 4-6 km to reach PHC/SC. Availability of healthcare services is skewed towards the urban centers with these inhabitants, who make up only 28% of the country's population, enjoying access to 66% of India's available hospital beds, while the residual 72%, who live in the rural areas, have access to just one-third of the beds (Sources : IMS Institute for Healthcare Informatics/Economic Times Daily June 22/2013).

Basically India is a land of villages. Since the independence, Government of India has implemented several programmes to improve the health conditions of the rural people. However, growing regional and gender disparities have become a big challenge for the rural health sector. Now-a-days Indian rural people are facing both communicable and non-communicable health disorders. Availability quality primary health care has still become a distant dream in many rural parts. HIV/AIDS also fast spreading in the rural areas. Life expectancy has increased up to 65 years. The infant mortality rate is around 85 for every 1000 live births today. The maternal mortality rate is around 445 for every 1,00,000 live births. However, the report says more than 70% of all deaths are causing only due to the communicable diseases in the rural parts. Poverty, illiteracy, unhygienic health conditions, malnutrition, scarcity for potable water, drought etc., are some of the reasons why the rural people are the worst victims for the various health disorders.

Normally people having the low economic profile like rural folks are becoming more victims for the various new epidemics. As it is a known factor that the major section of the rural society is either small land holders or the marginal land holders having very limited resources. Obviously their socio-economic status would be very low and they cannot spend the required money on good food. Also they cannot spend much on the good health care facilities

We can divide healthcare in India into two divisions.

1. High quality medical care in urban India.
2. Low health infrastructure in rural India.

The Report says more than 73% of the rural people are not having the modern curative and preventive health care facilities. It is found that only 24.6% of the Doctors are serving in the rural areas. Big disparity in the presence of the government hospitals between rural and urban part of the country can be seen even today. For the period 1905 to 2000 the life expectancy at birth was be 60.36 years for males and 63.39 for females in rural part. In 1991 the sex ratio was 920 females for one thousand males in rural part. Maternal and child health programme has been improved in the rural areas significantly. Immunization programme in rural areas also in good progress. Some of the programmes like up gradation of the primary health centre/ sub centers are on the way. Today almost all PHC's centers are working 24x7. Strong measures have been taken to control the various endemic diseases in rural areas. Regular free health checkups are being done.

However reasonable disparity in case of rural health can be seen today and it is because of

1. Lack of cultural specific rural health policies ;
2. Low expenditure on the health sector in budget;
3. Absence of the rural infrastructure ;

Also the Govt. has brought a vital programmed titled National Programme for Prevention and Control of Cancer, Diabetes, Cardiovascular Diseases and Stroke (NPCDCS). Through this programme; It is anticipated to achieve the behavioural change in the community to adopt the healthy life styles including dietary style, improved physical activity and the condensed intake of tobacco and alcohol resulting in the general decrease in the risk factors of the common Non-Communicable Diseases (NCDs) in the community (source: India Development Gateway)

There are numerous health care issues with respect to the rural area like;

1. Poor socio economic issues
2. Malnutrition,
3. Frequent outbreak of communicable disease,
4. Failure of family planning rate
5. High infant mortality rate;
6. Lack of sanitation and hygienic environment;
7. Shortage of safe drinking water ;
8. Cultural beliefs about diseases ;
9. Poor health infrastructure

Poor Socio economic Issues: As we are aware, the socioeconomic and cultural issues have long been considering an influencing factor in case of rural health care issue. These factors include individual-level (e.g. individual socioeconomic status, sex, caste, class etc) and neighborhood-level dimensions (culture, community, demography composition, social and physical environment etc) operating both separately and through various interactions. Low income and social status, traditional health culture, low social support network, stumpy education and the literacy level, employment/working conditions, poor social environments, unhygienic physical environments, poor personal health practices etc are some of the poor socio economic issues causing various health problems among the rural community.

Malnutrition:- It is found that 47% of the rural children are facing the severe malnutrition problem. It is even greater than few African countries. Due to the malnutrition social and cognitive development will impaired among the rural children. Today childhood mortality has become a serious problem in the case of rural children. It is found that their social-cultural background, health, behavior and health culture dynamics plays a significant role as the vital determinants in the health status of a particular community. A good health required a balanced diet. Under Five children need a good nutritional diet which is scanty in many rural settings in the country and this causes mortality and morbidity problems among rural the population. Hence, under nutrition and childhood mortality has become common in the rural areas. WHO report (1985) has found that 57% of death of fewer than Five children in the developing countries are accompanied by the under-nutrition and thereby low weight for their age.

Infant mortality rate and under Five mortality rates are the finest indicators of health and quality of life of any given community. It is found that Nearly Thirty (30) lakh rural children in India die before the age of Five due to the various health problems. However, the reports show that various child health indicators of the country have shown considerable improved and infant mortality has declined from 78 to 57 deaths per 1000 live births and under-five mortality has decreased from 109 to 74 deaths per 1000 live births. However, under-five mortality levels among the rural children are still shockingly high (at 97 deaths per 1000 live births) (Health survey Report, 2010). Experts have opined that poverty, illiteracy, malnutrition, scarcity of potable water, sanitary conditions, poor mother child health services, problems in covering national health and nutritional services, etc. have been found most vital causative factors in the prevalence of the sever childhood mortality and the morbidity amongst the rural communities in the country. Despite the marvelous development focusing preventive and curative medicine, the child healthcare delivery services in the several rural areas are still poor and unscientific and needed to be further strengthened in order to achieve the goal of health for all in the country.

Anthropologists have revealed that the development of the health culture of the rural environment should be examined as a sub cultural complex of the entire way of life. There are a number of forces percolated from the larger socio-economic environment and directed through the attribute of historical, social and political dimension to the development of the pattern of their health culture in the given rural settings.

Current health issues in the rural areas in Karnataka.

A.Outbreak of Communicable Diseases: Rural people are more prone to have many communicable diseases like Malaria, Jaundice, T.B , Cholera, etc. In many parts of rural partS of the Karnataka state Diarrhea is the prime cause of early child hood mortality. The Report says more than seven thousand rural people are dying because of various communicable diseases in a year across the country. Malaria and Jaundice have become common in the rural parts. Because of the poor sanitation and an unhygienic environment, thousand of deaths occurring in the rural parts. (Rural Health Survey Report, 2010).

B.High Infant Mortality Rate: It is found that 0.7 Million rural children die each year before turning one year. Under Five Mortality and infant mortality are also become a big issues in the rural health care scenario. Poverty, low income illiteracy is destructing much in case of mortality issue. Due to the strong cultural beliefs the rural

people are not showing much interest in immunization. It is found that diarrhea and respiratory infections also responsible causing high infant mortality rate in rural parts.

Poor Sanitation: Even today considerable number of rural households has no proper toilet facilities. Report says only 21% of Indian rural families use closed toilet whereas 79% of the population is still using open spaces. Also poor drainage system, inherited attitude towards sanitation issue, dispose of the solid and liquid waste and Open air defecation also spreads various infections among the rural people (HDI, 2005).

Shortage of Safe Drinking Water : This has caused a serious problem in rural areas. Some time people have to walk a few miles to get safe potable water. Usage of contaminated water has also caused various infectious diseases in the rural areas. The Ground water level has also decreased due to the repeated failure monsoon. Presence of arsenic and fluoride content in the ground water also a kind of threat to the rural health.

Poor Health Infrastructure: Modern healthcare facilities and hospitals have been concentrated only in the urban areas. Most of the villages even today do not have enough number of primary health care centers are the sub centers(SC). The majority of rural hospitals are lacking sufficient numbers of the doctors, paramedical staffs and the required infrastructure. Some of the hospitals in the rural areas don't have even the proper building.

Failure of Family Planning Issues: Due to the various social and cultural beliefs, family planning programmes have failed in the rural areas and the poor contraceptive materials also become a problem. Still the rural folks are using traditional type of family planning which has mixed result. Strong cultural issues are one of the reasons too.

It is reported that the crude death rate has been slowly decreasing in rural part of the country. Survey has found that the following diseases are most common reason for the death in case of rural people (in ascending order)

- a. Cholera
- b. Jaundice
- c. Malaria
- d. Typhoid
- e. Dengue
- f. Snake bite g. Infections

Death also happening due to the non-communicable diseases including in rural areas :-

- a. Heart problems (blockage of veins);
- b. Acute lungs problem (due to smoking);
- c. Liver damage(due to alcohol);
- d. Kidney problem (due to the modern life style);
- e. Oral cancer(due to using tobacco, jarala, beeda)

Also death is occurring in rural area due to:-

- a. Severe injury
- b. Poisoning (snake bite etc)
- c. Unknown disease
- d. Parasitic diseases(due to using patricides)

(Source: National Health Servy, 2010).

INCIDENCE OF VARIOUS CHRONIC DISEASE PER 1000 (GENDER WISE)

	RURAL		URBAN	
	MALE	FEMALE	MALE	FEM ALE
ALL INDIA	451	448	443	455
KARNATAKA	372	697	354	408

Source-CCR-IFCU Project on Aging and Development tab 12

REPETEAD INCIDENCE OF CETIAN HEALHT ISSUES IN KARNATAKA

(in %)

ILLNESS	URBAN MALE	URBAN FEMALE	RURAL MALE	RURAL FEMALE
B.P	31	25	14	16
Diabetes	26	22	6	11
Eyesight	16	10	22	25
Heart diseases	13	4	14	18
Dental	11	11	46	32
Arthritis	8	16	16	27
Asthma	5	5	22	10

Source-CCR-IFCU Project on Aging and Development tab 13

MATERNAL HEALTH STATUS IN BACKWARD REGIONS (In %)

Health Issues	South Karnataka	Coastal/ Malnad Karnataka	Mumbai Karnataka	Hyderabad Karnataka	State
1. Mothers registered in the first trimester when they were pregnant with last time birth/ still birth	82.7	88.2	65.5	59.5	74.0
2. Mothers who had at least 3 Ante-natal care visits during the last Pregnancy	93.5	93.8	74.5	66.3	82.0
3. Mother who got TT injection when they were Pregnant with their last time birth/ still birth	95.1	96.6	85.1	72.2	87.3
4. Institutional birth	77.9	85.0	60.4	44.9	67.1
5. Delivery at home assisted by a doctor/nurse/LHV/ ANM	14.9	14.1	26.0	15.8	17.9
6. Mother who received post-natal care within 48 hours of delivery of their last child	71.8	83.5	62.0	51.2	67.1

Source: District Household Level Survey III, IIPS, Mumbai, 2007-08. Tab 14

MORTALITY, MORBIDITY AND DISABILITY ISSUES IN RURAL PARTs

Mortality: It was reported to be 65 per 1000 live births in 1994 and the material mortality ratio was estimated at 415 per 1,00,000 live births in the year 2000. Further, children under 5 who are dying from Diarrhea was around 5,40,000, from acute Lungs problem was around 3,20,000, from Cholera was around 3,20,000 and from Malaria around 3,40,00 deaths have been occurring per year in rural areas (Health Survey 2010). Further, it is reported that from the heart related diseases 1.58 Lakh, from the Traffic accident 675 and from the work related accidents 143 deaths have been reported in the year 2000 in a rural health survey.

Morbidity:- Mortality and morbidity rate are the best indicators of the health status of any community. Morbidity focuses on the death of the people due to the various problems after a certain years. It is reported that (HFW report 2010) due to Leprosy 1,60,000 (in the year 2000), due to T.B 2,27,000 (1999), due to Malaria 1,27,000 (1999), deaths have been reported across the rural part of the country. After implementing the DOTS programme, TB problem has been declining in the rural parts

gradually. The prevalence rate of Leprosy also decreased due to the limited success of the multi drug therapy in the rural parts.

Also 0.80 million deaths are occurring in the rural areas because of water born diseases in the year. This report also says Typhoid, Cholera, Malaria animal bites are common in rural area causing 0.60 million deaths every year. It's about one thousand accident related deaths occur in rural India because of absence of emergency health care. In case of safe motherhood it is found that only 26% of rural pregnant women had an antenatal checkup. Further, snakebite, mishandling insecticides, etc also causes death in rural areas. Also rurals' are facing oral problems, respiratory infections, addictions and gynec problems and exact facts are not available (HFW report 2010).

Disability:- It is reported that in rural areas around 7571 physical disability cases 2110 visual durability 1900, hearing problems 1650 speech and 1041 locomotors cases have been reported for every 1,00,000 population in 2004 in rural parts. Also it is found that 3.3 million people have become blind due to unnoticed cataract. More than 37% of rural are suffering from various mental illness problems (From various health survey reports). Health issues facing by the rural people are many and diverse. It varies from fever to acute respiratory tract infection and sometime from cholera to cancer. Postpartum illness also causes maternal mortality in the rural parts. Next, rural people In India are having the strong traditional belief towards health and illness which is a big hurdle. Some rural people are still practicing the traditional healing approach with other type of established medical system because of their unique social, economical and cultural background. All these are also responsible for the onset of the various communicable and non-communicable diseases in the rural areas.

Demographic, Socio-economic and the Health Profile of Rural Karnataka As Compared to India

Indicator	Karnataka	India
Total population (In crore) (Census 2011)	6.11	121.01
Decadal Growth (%) (Census 2011)	15.67	17.64
Infant Mortality rate (SRS 2010)	38	47
Maternal Mortality Rate (SRS 2007-09)	178	212
Total Fertility Rate (SRS 2010)	2.0	2.5
Crude Birth Rate (SRS 2010)	19.2	22.1

Crude Death Rate (SRS 2010)	7.1	7.2
Natural growth Rate (SRS 2010)	12.1	14.9
Sex Ratio (Census 2011)	968	940
Child Sex Ratio (Census 2011)	943	914
Schedule Caste population (in crore) (Census 2001)	0.85	16.6
Schedule Tribe population (in crore) (Census 2001)	0.34	8.4
Total Literacy Rate (%) (Census 2011)	75.60	74.04
Male Literacy Rate (%) (Census 2011)	82.85	82.14
Female Literacy Rate (%) (Census 2011)	68.13	65.46

(Source: RHS Bulletin, March 2011, M/O Health & F.W., GOI) tab 15

Reporting Infectious Diseases in Rural Areas in Karnataka (Annual base)

Indicator	Percentage
Typhoid	14.67
Jaundice	12.7
Cholera	15.8
Dioharria	17.8
Malaria	23..0
Viral fever	19.2
Dengue	7.1
Plague	3.1
Other s	26.8

(Source: RHS Bulletin, M/O Health & F.W., GOI: March 2011) **Tab 16**

Reporting of Other Type of Health Problems in Rural Area in Karnataka (Annual base)

Diseases	Percentage
Injures	34.5
Heart and Kidney problems	13.6
Cancers	7.9
Abortions	11.8
Mental problems	9.5
Snake and other bites	21.6
From Chemical manures	16.8
Skin related	11.8
Bone and liver related	17.8

(Source: RHS Bulletin, March 2011, M/O Health & F.W., GOI) **Tab 17**

Beard (2009) has opined that the ‘socioeconomic and cultural factors have long been thought to influence an individual's health. He has suggested a framework for characterizing these factors that comprises individual-level (e.g. individual socioeconomic status, sex, race) and neighborhood-level dimensions (population composition, social environment, physical environment) operating both independently and through interaction’. Recent spatial research suggests that among the rural communities, socioeconomic disadvantage and indigenous status are two of the greatest underlying influences on the health status. However, rural communities also facing additional challenges associated with access to, and utilization of the quality health care (Beard , 2009).

Strasser (2010) has opined that ‘with the concentration of poverty, low health status and high burden of disease in rural areas, there is a need to focus specifically on improving the health of people in rural and remote areas, particularly if the urban drift is to be reversed. The WHO the International Development Programme has highlighted this, with the specific objectives for the policies and action which promotes the sustainable livelihoods with facilitating people to access to land, resources, markets, better education, health and opportunities in case of rural people easily’. These objectives seek to contribute to lowering the child and maternal mortality, and to improve the basic health care for all, including the quality reproductive services. Achievement of this is linked to the protection and the better management of the natural and physical environment (Strasser,2010).

District wise Health Status (HSI) Indices of Karnataka, 2010

Region	District	HII		HSI	
		Value	Rank	Value	Rank
North	Bagalkot	0.76	25	0.89	25
	Belgaum	0.71	29	1.13	3
	Bellary	1.24	11	1.02	10
	Bidar	0.86	22	0.90	23
	Bijapur	0.74	27	0.89	28
	Dharwad	1.22	12	0.87	29
	Gadag	1.22	13	0.89	24
	Gulbarga	0.74	28	0.89	27
	Haveri	1.03	17	0.89	26
	Koppal	0.85	23	0.91	22
	Raichur	0.75	26	0.95	17
	Uttara Kannada	0.96	20	0.94	18

South	Bangalore	3.68	1	1.12	5
	Bangalore Rural	1.95	2	1.08	7
	Chamarajanagar	0.96	19	0.96	14
	Chikkaballapura	1.88	4	1.09	6
	Chikmagalur	1.30	10	0.92	20
	Chitradurga	0.94	21	1.00	12
	Dakshina Kannada	1.39	8	1.14	1
	Davanagere	1.18	14	1.03	9
	Hassan	1.45	7	0.96	15
	Kodagu	1.93	3	0.92	19
	Kolar	1.18	15	0.95	16
	Mandya	1.33	9	0.92	21
	Mysore	1.49	6	0.98	13
	Ramanagara	1.10	16	1.05	8
	Shimoga	0.98	18	1.12	4
	Tumkur	0.79	24	1.02	11
Udupi	1.51	5	1.13	2	
All	North	0.86		0.92	
	South	1.14		1.02	
	Karnataka	1		1	
CV	North	22.3		8.0	
	South	45.2		7.6	
	Karnataka	47.2		9.0	

(Source: Karnataka at a Glance,2010)

TAB 18

Primary Health Centers (PHCs) in Rural Areas

In India, Primary Health Centers (PHCs) are the keystone of rural healthcare. PHCs play a vital role as the first level of contact and a connection between individuals and the health system, bringing health care delivery as close as possible to where people live and work. In addition, these PHCs are charged with providing promotive, preventive, curative and rehabilitative care in urban rural and rural areas. Even though there are numerous reasons for a meager performance of PHCs, almost all of them stem from weak stewardship of the sector, which produces a poor incentive framework. Primary healthcare is indispensable health care based on sensible, scientifically sound and socially suitable methods and technology made generally reachable to individuals in the community through their full involvement and at a cost the community and country can afford to sustain at every stage of their advancement in the spirit of self-reliance and self-determination.

Normally in India, a PHC covers a population of 20,000 in hilly, rural, or difficult areas and a population of 30,000 in plains areas with 4-6 indoor/observation beds. It acts as a referral unit for 6 sub-centers and refers out cases to Community Health Centers (CHCs) (30 bed hospitals) and higher order public hospitals located at the sub-district and district level. Primary Health Centers (PHCs) form the backbone of the public health system in rural India. The Mudaliar Committee (1955), Jungalwalla Committee (1965), Karthar Singh Committee(1973), the Shrivatsva Committee (1975), and the Bajaj committee (1986) have also highlighted the importance of up gradation of PHCs. Despite criticism they have faced concerning excellence of care and poor infrastructure, they continue to be the major primary care provider for the majority of India's population who reside in rural areas.

The Primary Health Centers (PHC) are not immune from issues such as the incapability to notice diseases early due to lack of multi-disciplinary medical expertise and a laboratory and other amenities and insufficient quantities of general medicines. Further, rural patients usually do not visit PHCs in the early stages of their diseases. Therefore, healthcare providers (if at all present) are forced to focus only on seriously ill patients due to the heavy work load. Poverty and a low level of literacy are the basic causes for the poor health behavior among tribes. The absence of responsibility and accountability stems from the fact that there is no formal feedback mechanism and incentive to treat tribes as clients. Rural Patients often find fault in the rude and abrupt behavior of health workers that discriminate against women and minorities from scheduled castes or tribes. The lack of accountability leads to absentee doctors, as it is hard to get qualified doctors to rural areas). Unresponsive ANMs, inconvenient opening times and little or no community participation are some of the other problems faced by the PHCs in rural areas.

Opening of essential primary health centers (PHCs) in rural dominant districts was an integral part of various rural development programmes implemented since 1947. The Bhore Committee Report recommended opening PHCs to cover only a population of 10000 and that each should have 6 specialist doctors, other required staff, and 75 beds. However, each PHC complex in the rural blocks consists of 6 beds, 1 medical officer, 2 midwives and 1 ancillary person. Different governments have taken suitable measurements to upgrade the PHCs based upon various experts' committee reports. Recent national health policy has laid stress on a people-centered primary health care approach. Nevertheless, the ICMR report has exposed the fact that

more than 80 percent of the population has no access to any form of health care. However, curative services, people's awareness about the functioning of PHCs, preventive activities, and the attitude of the health staffs need to be properly evaluated through different research approaches.

In Karnataka state, the PHCs were started only in the Ad hoc plan years after the Third Five Year Plan by opening 34 PHCs with 55 Sub-Centres. During the Fourth Five Year Plan, 24 additional PHCs with 66 Sub-centres were opened. Thus, at the end of the Fourth Five Year Plan there were 236 PHCs and 141 Sub-Centres in the state. The total strength of the PHCs in the state at this time is 2,164. More than half of the PHCs are working in rural areas, with a small number (246) working in the rural-dominant parts of the State.

It is found that factors like rude behavior of the staff, distance factors, transport problems, long waiting time, and the non availability of lady physicians are some of the other reasons why rural beneficiaries do not show interest in visiting PHCs. These findings are corroborated with another study conducted in Karnataka on PHCs which concluded that the non availability of adequate man power, finance and equipment were some of the prime reasons why rural people have negative perceptions about the PHCs.

Rural PHC are also facing the problems including lack of proper accommodation, lack of amenities in PHCs , poor quality buildings , transport problem, an inadequate supply of both medicines and equipment, and bureaucratic practice in transferring physicians and p.m staff. Regarding the process of medical care, the frequent transfer of doctors and health staff, lack of their dedication, indifferent attitude towards people, lethargy, doctors lack of interest to work in the the rural areas, and insufficient or untimely supply of medicines are observable in the rural PHCs. Regarding the outcome of service in rural areas of Karnataka, there is a lack of aftercare services, lack of attention towards the prevention of diseases before their actual attack, and lack of follow up methods .

Selecting a PHC to seek the health care and treatment depends upon several criteria in the rural parts. Most often, there are several reasons why the beneficiary families do not visit the Primary Health Centers in their jurisdictions. The common causes for the low level of the choice of PHCs for health care treatment are the lack of knowledge among the beneficiary families about PHCs, lack of funds at PHCs to

provide efficient service, and the repeated absence of doctors at the centers. When all these factors come together, people prefer to go to the private hospitals instead of PHCs. In this study, it was discovered that the policymakers, PHC users, communities, and even NGOs are not fully aware of the various problems. Both the communities and NGOs lack access to relevant information on the required health services, and they are not involved in the monitoring service. Furthermore, the local government bodies responsible for the health services are not accountable to communities (Srinivasa,2001).

The functioning of PHCs in rural areas as well as urban areas is not free from the impediments. Several impediments on the path of the functioning of PHCs such as illiteracy of the people, lack of response from beneficiaries, lack of fund from the government, lack of staff at PHCs and lack of interest on the part of people occupying authority positions was observed at the time of the fieldwork. The overall performance of PHCs is greatly affected by these impediments. They also affect the attitude of the people towards accepting the services of PHCs. However, all PHCs are not having the same degree of these impediments. Therefore, it is essential to identify the specific impediments confronted by each PHC in Urban areas.

PHC is the primary contact point between village community and the Medical Officer. The PHCs were expected to offer an integrated curative and preventive health care to the rural population with stressing on the preventive and promotive aspects of the health care.

(Sources: Part of this portion is based on the article published by the same research scholar in *Online J Health Allied Scs.* 2011; 10(2):3)

Community Health Centers (CHCs) in Rural Areas

We have the three tier health care systems namely, the Sub-Centre (SC) for a population of 3000-5000, the Primary Health Centre (PHC) for 20000 to 30000 people and the Community Health Centre (CHC) as the referral centers for every four PHCs covering a population of 80,000 to 1.2 lakh. From 6th Five year plan onwards, the government took a major decision to increase the total number of CHC's across the country. CHCs play an imperative responsibility as the second level of contact and a connection between individuals and the health system, bringing the health care delivery where people live and work (Nanjunda,2011). Further these CHCs are charged with providing advanced promotive, preventive, curative and rehabilitative care as well. Various health experts suggested that an integrating and intensification of the rural PHCs and CHCs through the proper standard and the functional linkages.

According to the recent norm, Community Health Centre (CHC) for every One lakh of population or one out of four P.H.Cs. to be established to provide the quality health care to the rural areas in India **(Roy,1985)**. The main function of the CHCs are care of routine and emergency cases in the surgery and the care of the routine and emergency cases in medicine. It is a 24X 7 service. As per minimum norms, a CHC is mandatory to be manned by four medical specialists i.e. Surgeon, Physician, Gynecologist and Pediatrician with a logistic support by 21 paramedical and other staff at any cost. The basic reason CHC's have been shaped to avoid congestion in the local district hospitals and to make available a high quality and easily accessible health care service to the rural people. CHC's would consist of 4 specialized Doctors, 20 to 30 beds for indoor patients, a small operation theatre and a lab including paramedical staff. CHC's covers a population of 85,000 to 1.25 Lakh. Sometime in the hill area it covers a population of 70,000 to 90,000 (Chaudhry and others 2006; Singh,2008).

It is found that the functioning of CHC's including the large coverage of the geographical area and population which is practically impossible. Now a days preponderance of the CHC's is facing insufficient medical and paramedical staffs especially in the rural areas. Availability of the required specialists in CHC's has also become a vital problem. All most all CHC's in the rural areas are lacking the required fundamental facilities. Some CHC's even don't have an adequate power and water supply. More than 70% of CHC's are running either with one specialized or without

any specialist doctors. Hence, CHC's are not in the position to act as an effective referral center in rural parts. The Majority of CHC doesn't have enough stock of medicines and sometime even they give outdated medicines to the patients. More than that absenteeism of the Doctors and other staff has become a big problem in case of CHC's. Both the medical and paramedical staffs of the CHC's are not visiting the CHC's regularly. They visit CHCs if they have some free time only! Still they receive a huge Govt. salary and are taking undue advantages. They have a nexus with the highest authority and are escaping without being punished (sources: various reports).

Selected Health Indicators in Karnataka and India

Sl. No.	Items	Karnataka	India
I. Status			
1	Life Expectancy at Birth	65.3	63.5
2	Infant Mortality Rate	41.0	50.0
3	Under Five Mortality Rate	54.7	74.3
4	Percentage of persons not expected to survive beyond the Age of 40 years	14.6	17.7
5	Percentage of Women Adult Population with BMI <18.5	35.5	33.0
6	Percentage of Men Adult Population with BMI <18.5	33.9	34.2
7	Percentage of Women with Anaemia	51.5	55.3
8	Percentage of Children (0-5 years) with Anaemia	70.4	69.5
9	Death Rate	7.2	7.3
10	Public Expenditure on Health as a percentage to GSDP	0.87	2.02
11	Per capita Public Expenditure on Health	233	1014
12	Per capita Private Expenditure on Health	597	1639
13	Public Expenditure on Health as a percentage to total Health Expenditure	71.9	58.3
14	Private Expenditure on Health as a percentage to total Health Expenditure	28.1	41.7
II. Infrastructure Facilities per 10 lakh Population			
1	Public Health Centres (PHCs)	38	21
2	Sub Centres	140	129
3	Community Health Centres (CHCs)	6	4
4	Rural Hospitals	8	6
5	Urban Hospitals	8	3
6	Total Hospitals	16	10
7	Total Beds	1096	476
8	No. of Doctors at PHCs	48	21
9	No. of Health Assistants at PHCs	34	31
10	No. of Health Workers at PHCs	203	188

Source: India Human Development Report, part 2(2010) TAB 19

Bird view of Rural Health care Services in Karnataka TAB 20

Sl.no	Availability of Man power Resources in Rural Health Centers	Percentage
1	Sub Centers	24.6
2	PHCs	66.8
3	Resident ANM	54.2
4	Male Health Workers	6.9
5	Female Health Workers	62.5
6	Availability of Additional ANM's	37.5
7	Deficit of ANM's	53.9
8	24x7 Delivery Services	37.5
9	Trained ANM	95.9
10	Estimated Expenditure on Primary Health Center	83.3
11	Availability of Total specialists	8.9
12	AYSUH facility	10.0
13	Total Number of Primary Health Centers	250
14	Availability of Surgeons	10.0
15	Availability of General specialists	25.0
16	Gynecics	4.0
17	Pediatrics	25.0
18	Doctors in sub centers	25.0
19	Anesthesia	1.0
20	General facility	8.0

Sources: NRHM Report, 2009

Health Indices Services in Rural Karnataka

<u>Particulars</u>	Total	Urban	Rural
Infant Mortality Rate	53	36	58
Birth Rate	22.8	18.5	24.4
Death Rate	7.4	5.9	8
Total Fertility Rate	2.7	2.1	3
Pure Drinking Water	89	96	86
Sanitation	28	18	52
Under weight Children	40.4	30.1	43.7
Adult Education	66	80.3	59.4
Immunization	43.5	52.6	38.6
AWL Treatment	50.7	73.8	42.8

Sources: N FWS-3, SRS (2009)

Tab 21

Malnutrition Picture in Rural Areas

Underdevelopment among below 3years old children	1998-99	2008-06
Wasted among below 3years old children	45.50	38.40
Under weight among below 3years old children	15.50	19.10
BMI Ratio among 15-24 aged women	47.0	45.9
BMI Ratio among 25-49	-	44.1
15-49 aged women BMI >18.5	-	30.7
15-24 aged men BMI <18.5	36.2	35.6
25-49 aged men BMI <18.5	-	47.3
15-49 aged men BMI <18.5	-	20.9

(Sources: N FWS -3 Report (2009)

Tab 22

Unlike in urban area the rural communities have a different culture. Rural communities will have a particular sense of health behavioral norms. The Social roles and functions among the rural people are supported by the historical and the religious practices. Poverty, low health status and high burden of diseases are rampant in the rural areas. The WHO in its programme has specifically advised to the developing countries to focus more on the sustainable developing including regeneration of agricultural activities, natural resources, quality health care, etc. Achievement in these issues might lead towards the better management of the natural and physical environment. The good health is a way out of poverty. The Good health status may contribute in producing economic assets. The poor health may also decrease the productive capacity of the rural people. The rates of avoidable deaths in rural areas are higher than in cities. It is found that the work injuries are more in case of rural areas and people will normally ignore the consequence of these injuries which may some time lead in losing an organ finally. In rural areas good medical healthcare has become a nightmare even today. in many rural parts of the country, poor transport system and other underdeveloped medical infrastructure also causes delays in sifting the patients to the nearby hospitals. Sometime it would be impossible to evacuate the patients because of the remoteness and bad communication system in the rural areas. Gram vaani (an NGO) has stated in its bulletin ahs found that

- Rural Health centers are critically short of trained health medi-cal person
- 8% primary health centers do not have doctors
- 39% PHCs do not have lab Technicians
- 18% PHCs do not have a pharmacist

The Rural health infrastructures have been neglected since a long time in India. Various Governments also are giving low priorities for the rural health issues. Even after introducing NRHM programme situation has not completely improved. Reduction of funding for the rural development in India in the budget also can be seen. Also the rural areas are facing the shortage of the doctors and other paramedical staff. In some parts of the rural areas, untrained doctors and under trained doctors are practicing which is a great threat to the rural folks. In addition, studies have found that lifestyle related diseases and illness are more common in the rural areas today. Their low economic status also creates more stress on these communities. The absence of mental health facilities has also been increased the severity of the problem. More over smoking, alcohol, low nutrition's foods also some of the reasons for the poor health status in rural India. The WHO has also advised to the developing countries to decentralize the health issues and strengthen health surveillance system especially in the rural areas. Also emerging technologies can be used in serving the needs of rural people. Moreover there is a need of having area specific innovative health education programme as a part of preventive measures. There is a requirement of new programmes and the guidelines to create awareness on the health issues even at school levels, health NGO's, health workers for a co-ordinated activities. However, recently brought Janani suraksha scheme is very useful to the rural people in case mother and child health care.

Decentralization of Health Governance

Bheenaveni (2007) writes " the possible realm of influence of the Panchayats extends over a significant proportion of public health issues. The Gram Sabha, where empowered has the potential to act as a community level accountability mechanism to ensure that the functions of the village Panchayat in the area of public health and family welfare, actually respond to people's needs" (Bheenaveni, 2007).

India is presently undergoing for two types of developed paradigms having the potential to considerably get better the health for its people. The first is the mounting identification of drawbacks' in the public delivery of health care services is in catastrophe. And the second is India's massive hard work to reinforce the rural health care through the decentralization to local governments Panchayats Raj Institutions (PRI) . It is argued that these two presumably separate trends can converge to generate real reform in the health sector in India through the potential for increased

accountability that local government can provide (Aiyar, Samji, and Hammer, 2006). The real concept is that decentralization brings governments closer to people thus allowing them to act in response additional efficiently to the local health needs and preferences. Studies on the rural decentralization even argued that the decentralization is a misnomer in Karnataka. In the health sector, decentralization has been clearly played a vital role in the chain of service delivery under the National Rural Health Mission (NRHM).

Indian health care delivery system has a long history which can be traced back to the British era. It looks very sound on paper in terms of policy formulations and health programme planning. But a careful evaluation of impact of these policies and programmes shows that the results are far from the satisfactory. Indian health system is ranked 118 among 191 WHO member countries on overall health performance. The key issues are availability, access, affordability, quality, equity and efficiency. Health is a priority goal in its own right, as well as a central input into economic development and poverty reduction. India's health system is at crossroads today. The third wave of health care is upon us. The first wave was the government run healthcare delivery model. The influx of private players defined the second. Now a discerning and interconnected nation demands a new incarnation, that will transform the very ground rules of healthcare & that will catalyze its participants to engage with a billion plus people across the length and breadth of our diverse nation.

As we aware rural population having inadequate access to health care. poor placements of medial and Para medical doctors in rural districts are also under question. The maternal and child mortality rates in Karnataka are also under the scanner. All these play a role in the diminishing rural health care service in many rural parts of Karnataka. It is found that at least six to seven deliveries take place without the supervision of any doctors at many general hospitals in the state every day . Some time one sub centers should cater to around three- five villages at a time. Proper documents of the patients are also a bigger problem due to man power.

Thus efforts at rural decentralization (73rd amendment) have been undertaken within the context of strengthening accountability in governance structures. "Moreover, proximity encourages better monitoring and enforcement. In the specific context of the health sector, a decentralized institutional structure that emphasizes a bottom up, participatory approach can indeed help to redress some of the key failings

in the sector such as absenteeism and corruption by strengthening accountability through NRHM programme” Samji, and Hammer(2006). Experts felt there is a need of having more research study to find out capacities of panchayatraj institutions to manage the grass root health system in Karnataka state and to find out does the degree of decentralization under the NRHM correlate strongly with perceived decision space of Health officials and PRI members at the District level and below (Aiyar, Samji, and Hammer(2006).

The PRIs are seen critical to the planning, implementation, and monitoring of the NRHM. The success of NRHM significantly depends on the well functioning Gram, Block and District level Panchayats. A village health committee is an integral part of every Panchayat. The PRIs through village health committees can create a link between the Gram Panchayat and the community for various health needs. The village health committee is expected to prepare a village health plan and maintain the village level data supervised by the Gram Panchayat. Engaging the Gram Panchayat and other smaller groups in the planning and monitoring of the Village Health Plan enforces transparency and accountability within the programme (Development Issues in Rural Karnataka website article).Guptha(2007) writes “Linking of the health sector with the Panchayati Raj system is a multifaceted chain procedure involving frequent stakeholders. Our knowledge in this context so far is mixed. The PRIs have often been subjugated by the local elite, obstructed by the politician sat the state level, and have mostly been seen as advisory rather than decision making. Allocated financial resources, often inadequate, are usually governed by tied budget lines, leaving little flexibility at the local level to meet the precise needs of the local populations. However, based onrecently Union health budget, a new budget line was introduced which provides elasticity to the GPs in the use of at least a part of the health budget according to the local needs (pattern offunding in the recently launched (NRHM)” (NCAER website).

Analytical Framework : Delivery and Monitoring of Public Health Services at the Local Level in Karnataka

Fig 28

Sources; Sekher, T.V, Shashanka Bhide and Md. Nazrul Islam (2004), Panchayati Raj Institutions and Public Health in Karnataka Draft Project Report, *Institute for Social and Economic Change*, Bangalore.

Health Programmes in various Five Year Plans

Five- year plans	Components and levels of services rendered
First Plan (1951-56)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Setting up of antenatal and postnatal clinics by NGOs • Licensing of private nursing homes for maternal and child health services • The government of India enter into an agreement with the UNICEF and the WHO to carry out a countrywide BCG programme. • Non-official organizations encouraged to establish and run tuberculosis institutions and governments to given them building and maintenance grants provided the institutions are on non-profit basis. • Voluntary organizations to be stimulated to set up, with state aid, after- care colonies at suitable places in association with tuberculosis institutions. • It should be possible adequately to provide drugs through a combination of private enterprise.
Second and Third plan (1956-61 and 1961-66)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governments subsidies and grants were given to states, local authorities. NGOs and scientific institutions for family planning clinics and research relating to demographic issues. • Maternity and child welfare services provided by welfare extension projects and by voluntary organizations. • A large number of voluntary organizations and social workers in anti- leprosy work to be associated in the leprosy programme.
Fourth and fifth plan (1969-74 and 1974-79)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NGOs to integrate family planning as part of their other health services that they extended to the community, distribution of contraceptives and education • In urban areas it was proposed that private practitioners provide advice, distribute supplies and undertake sterilizations. • Financial support from government to private practitioners and NGOs. • In order to create a sense of partnership with government efforts voluntary contributions to be encouraged in the malaria programme.
Sixth Plan (1980-84)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourage private medical professional and non-governmental agencies for increased investment. • Government offers organized, logistical, financial and technical support to voluntary agencies active in the health field • Financial assistance to be provided to voluntary organizations which provide medical care facilities at

	the village level through doctors employed on part-time basis
Seventh Plan (1985-90)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Voluntary organizations and local bodies encouraged to undertake responsibility for family welfare and primary healthcare services • NGOs involved in the extension education and motivation in fpp. • Scheme for assisting private nursing homes for family planning work continued. • Increased emphasis laid on MCH activities by supporting NGOs, village health committees, and women's organizations.
Eighth plan 1992-97) and Ninth plan (1997-2002)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourage private initiatives, private hospitals at secondary and tertiary level. • Role of NGOs, social marketing in RCH programmes • Some contracting out of primary level services
Tenth Plan (2002-07)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased involvement of voluntary and private organizations, self-help groups and social marketing organizations in improving access to healthcare. • Contracting in and out of clinical and non-clinical services.

Source : GOI (Various Years plans, Planning Commission Report)Tab 23

Public-Private Partnerships (PPP) Collaborations

As we are aware rural part fort of the country suffering a lot of troubles from underserviced an under developed medical delivery service due to the lack or under allocation of various resources, including money and labour and strong political will ever exploding the health care costs lack of specialty services, absence of required technology for the treatment of disease/illness and many such issues. Hence recently the Govt. planned about PPP scheme. A health services PPP can be defined as a long-term agreement (typically 15 to 30 years) between a public-sector authority and one or more private sector companies operating as a legal entity. 'The Government provides the strength of its purchasing power, outlines goals for an optimal health system, and empowers private enterprise to innovate, build, maintain and/or manage delivery of agreed-upon services over the term of the contract. The private sector receives payment for its services and assumes considerable financial, technical and operational risk while benefiting from the upside potential of shared cost savings'. This kind of arrangement has yielded much good result in the various parts of the country. Govt. of

India have taken initiation to for the establishment of Public-private partnerships(PPP) especially in the health sector including with the reputed NGOs in various five years plans (website extraction).

In Karnataka we these kind of tie-ups

a.Partners:Government of Karnataka and Apollo Hospitals Enterprises Ltd, Hyderabad Rajiv Gandhi Super Specialty Hospital, Raichur Apollo Hospital under the management contract are some of the good examples for PPP system.**Services:**350 bedded hospital. Free services to BPL patients, 40% beds for BPL (government reimburses the charges) and remaining patients treated under special rates.**b.Partners:**Government of Karnataka & Karuna Trust PPP arrangement .

Services:Contracting out adoption and management of PHCs and affiliated SCs in remote, rural, and tribal areas in the State.

Though, financial gain is not the only advantage of partnership, and in a lot of cases of partnership, other considerations offer the enticement. An ordinary one is the relocate of technical information between partners. This is often the case in partnerships between the public sector and NGOs, where both partners have information and skills that are helpful to the other are able to study from each other.Poor rural health condition has drawn increasing international attention and condemnation since 1970s. During the same period many international Non Government Organizations (NGOs) and other agencies have begun to speak out against deprived health infrastructure in rural parts of the developing countries. The issue of rural health has generated renewed interest because of the new economic policies formulated in line with the structural adjustment programmes. Developing countries have adopted a strategy to help them to integrate into the global health market economy. Hence, the long neglected topic of public health has suddenly attracted worldwide interest as a subject of research and analysis, particularly regarding the supply and demand sides of the problem. This interest among economists and social scientists began during a transition period in which the incidence of death due presence of modern health care had been declining for more decades among developed countries and increasing among developing countries including India. This pattern maybe a source of optimism that signals the spread of science and technology that have little use for public health and values that endorse the preservation and protection of valuable human life.

CHAPTER VII

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter deals about Result and Discussion

Section 1: Social, Economic, Demographic Factors of the Respondents

Sections II: General Health Status, Practice of the Respondents

Sections III : Specific Health Concept, Culture and Behavior

Section Iv: Relationship Between Social Determinants and Health Behavior

We think rurals' health culture and its impacts on health is insufficiently understood and studied in india (Nanjunda, 2016). It is established that some of the ways that culture has been considered in (rural) health, and states that culture is either used vaguely and broadly. For example, there is a rural culture, or hardly - certainly maybe interchangeably with ethnicity. It is known factor that although culture is a vibrant social concept, it has been adopted into a biomedical research paradigm as though it is fixed. Culture is often treated as something that can be addressed through cultural sensitivity/compatibility health education.

This study found that Culture determines to a large extent not only the type and frequency of disease/illness but also the way people perceive, explain and treat diseases as well as the manner in which they respond to the modern medicine. Thus, culture is an invariable determining factor of a community understands of health and illness. Every culture, regardless of its simplicity or complexity, has its own conception of health, illness and health seeking behaviour, which is referred to as 'health culture' – a component of the overall culture of the community. The socio-religious medical responses to illness in various forms-including the belief forms recognized, conducts approved – make the health culture. As a part of this health culture, members of each community tend to build up a specific concept relating to several illnesses /diseases recognized by them. The symptom recognition, assessment and health decisions associated to retrieval of health recuperation. It is suggested that culture is like an unaddressed 'elephant in the room' in the rural health care issue, that exploring and emerging soci-cultural differences and beliefs. Cultural differences are critical in truly understanding and addressing the rural health and health system challenges today.

SECTION:1

Age and Sex of the Respondents

Age in Years		Sex		Total	X ²	P
		Male	Female			
Between 25-30	f	135	34	169	7.312	0.000
	%	79.8	20.2			
30-45	f	352	156	508		
	%	69.2	30.8			
45-60	f	91	32	123		
	%	74.0	25.4			
Total	f	578	222	800		
	%	72.2	27.7	100.00		

Tab 24

Fig 28

In case of age wise distribution of the respondents, 79% of the male and 20% female respondents are belongs to the age group of 25 to 30. Next, 69% of male and 30% of female respondents belongs to the age group of 30 to 45. Finally 74% male and 25% of female respondents belongs to the age group of 45 to 60.

*The chi-square value of age and sex combinations of the respondents is found to be 7.312 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words age and sex combinations of the respondents have got a statistically significant influence over the health concept and allied issues of the respondents (gender wise).

Educational Qualifications of the Respondents

Level	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Primary	280	35.0	220.939	0.000
Higher Primary	188	23.5		
High School	77	9.6		
Illiterates	210	22.2		
College	28	3.5		
Neo literates	17	2.25		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 25

Fig 29

In case of educational qualifications, 35% of the respondents have studied up to the primary level whereas 23% have studied up to the higher primary level. Next, 9% have studied up to high school and 22% of them are illiterates and 3% of them have studied up to the college level whereas 2% are the neo literates.

*The chi-square value of educational qualifications of the respondents is found to be 220.939 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words level of educational qualifications of the respondents have got a statistically significant influence over the opinion of the respondents about the health culture, health behavior and allied issues

Occupational Status of the Respondents

Occupations	Frequency	%	χ^2	P
Agriculture	393	49.1	494.119	0.000
Factories	35	4.3		
Non form sector	160	20.0		
Unorganized sector	50	6.2		
Daily wage	102	12.7		
Government	9	1.1		
Private	2	0.25		
Others	1	.12		
Unemployed	48	6.0		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 26

Fig 30

Regarding occupational status of the respondents, it is found that 49.1% of them are working in agricultural sector while 4% of them are working in various factories and 20% of them are working in non-form sector. Next, 6% of them working in unorganized sector and 12% of them are working as daily wage laborers in cities. Further, it is found that 1% of them are Gov't servants ('D Class') and 0.25% of them are working in private sectors and 6% of them are unemployed.

*The chi-square value of occupational status of the respondents is found to be 494.119 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words occupational status has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior and allied issues of the respondents.

Monthly Income of the Respondents (declared)

Income level (in Rs.)	Frequency	%	X ²	P
2,000-3,000	321	40.1	206.793	0.000
3,000-5,000	250	31.2		
5,000-7,500	123	15.3		
7,500-10,000	84	10.5		
Above 10,000	22	2.75		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 27

Fig 31

In case of monthly income of the respondents more than 40% of them are earning between Rs. 2,000-3,000/ where as 31% of them are earning between Rs.3,000-5,000/. Also it is found that 15% of them are earning between Rs. 5,000-7,000, and 10% of them are earning Rs. 7,500-10,000/. Next, 2% of them are earning more than Rs.10,000/ per month. It is just a rage. It is little bit uncertain /untrue regarding claimed income is concerned.

*The chi-square value of monthly income of the respondents is found to be 206.793 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words monthly income of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health concept, healt care choice and allied issues of the respondents

Varna's of the Surveyed Respondents

Varna's	Frequency	%	χ^2	P
Brahmin	43	5.3	224.190	0.000
Kshtriya	243	30.1		
Vaishya	281	35.1		
Shudra	210	26.2		
Others	23	2.8		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 28

Fig 32

In case of Varna's it is found that 5.3% of them are Brahmin, while 30% of them are Kshtriya and 35% of them are Vishay. Next, 26% of them are Shudra and 2.8% of them belong to the other Varna's

*The chi-square value of Varna's of the surveyed respondents is found to be 224.190 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words there is a statistically significant difference among the different types of Varna's and it has influence over the health concept and allied issues of the respondents

Castes of the Surveyed Respondents

Castes	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Scheduled Caste	192	24.0	432.270	0.000
Lingayath	164	20.5		
Gowda	265	33.1		
Shetty	24	3.0		
Viswa karma	23	2.8		
Ganiga	12	1.5		
Besta	34	4.25		
Brahmin	31	3.8		
Kuruba	35	4.3		
S T	11	1.3		
Others	9	1.1		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 29

Fig 33

In case of caste classifications, 24% of the respondents belonging to Scheduled Caste and 20% of them are Lingayath while 33% of them are Gowda where as 3% of them are Shetty. Subsequently, 2% of them are Viswakarma and 1.5% of them belonging to Ganiga caste. It is also found that 4% of them are Besta, and 3% of them are Brahmin as well as 4% of them are Kuruba caste. We found 1% of them are ST and 1% of the respondents belonging to the other caste groups.

*The chi-square value of caste of the respondents is found to be 432.270 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words caste of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health concept, behavior and allied issues of the respondents.

Religion of the Respondents

Fig 34

In case of religion, 96% of the respondents are Hindus' where as 3% are Muslims' and 0.5% were Christians' and 0.125 belongs to the other converted religions.

*The chi-square value of religion of the respondents is found to be 879.257 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words, religion of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health concept, behavior and allied issues of the respondents.

Family Size of the Respondents

Family size	Frequency	%	X ²	P
4 Members	329	41.1	218.392	0.000
Members between 4-5	344	43.0		
Between 2-3	84	10.5		
Undivided	43	5.3		
Total	800	100		

Tab 30

Fig 35

It has been found that only 41% respondents belongs to the families having 4 members while 43% of the respondents belonging to families of having 4 to 5 members. It is more or less a middle size family in a rural area. Next, 10% of them belonging to the families consisting of 2-3 members. Fewer portions of the respondents (5.3%) belong to the families of having more than 10 members (undivided).

*The chi-square value of the family size of the respondents is found to be 218.392 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words family size of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health concept, expenditure, health behavior and allied issues of the respondents .

Dwelling Patterns of the Families

Fig 36

Regarding dwelling pattern, 28% of them are living in Pucca house types while 54% of them are living in Kaccha houses. Next, 13% of them are living in semi pucca houses whereas more than 2% of the respondents are staying in other types of houses.

*The chi-square value of dwelling pattern of the respondents is found to be 255.156 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words dwelling pattern of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health concept, health behavior and allied issues of the respondents.

Types of Latrines

Types	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Pucca sanitary	243	30.3	31.952	0.000
Pucca borehole	234	29.2		
Mixed scavenging	211	26.3		
Open field	112	14.0		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 31

Fig 37

Regarding types of latrine using 30% of them are using Pucca sanitary type where as 29% are using Pucca borehole type. Next, 26% are using mixed scavenging type where as 14% are still using open field.

*The chi-square value of types of latrine of the respondents is found to be 31.952 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words types of the latrine using by the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior and allied issues of the respondents.

Types of the Family

Types	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Nuclear family	693	86.6	489.744	0.000
Joint family	84	10.5		
Extended family	23	2.8		
Total	800	100		

Tab 32

Fig 38

Regarding types of families 86% are belongs to the nuclear family type and 10% are belonging to the joint family type where as 2% of them are belonging to an extended family.

*The chi-square value of types of the family of the respondents is found to be 489.744 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words types of the family of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health culture, behavior, and allied issues of the respondents

Types of Water -Drinking

Type s	Frequency	%	x2	p
Bore wells	245	30.6	286.704	0.000
Open Wells	162	20.2		
Either above	75	9.3		
Public taps	208	26.0		
Lake/ Pond	65	8.1		
Other	45	5.6		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 33

Fig 39

In case of usage of water for drinking 30% of them are depending on bore well (hand pumps) where as 20% of them are using water from the open wells. Next, 9% of them are using both bore well and wells water whereas 26% of the respondents are using public taps. Further, 8% of them using water from lake /pond and 5% of them are depending on other sources for drinking water.

*The chi-square value of type of water using by the respondents is found to be 286.704 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words type of water using by the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior and allied issues of the respondents .

Place of Birth and Migration Status of the Respondents

I Place of Birth	Families			
	f	%	X ²	p
Village	758	94.7	400.641	0.000
City	42	5.2		
Total	800	100		
II Status of Migration	Families			
	f	%	X ²	p
Same village	702	87.7	826.136	0.000
Moved from the other Villages	45	5.6		
Moved from the nearby Towns	20	2.5		
Moved from the other Districts	13	1.6		
Migrated from the other States	15	1.8		
No reply	5	0.6		
Total	800	100		

Tab 34

Regarding place of birth, 94% of the respondents have born and brought up in the same village where as 5% of them born in Cities and brought to the villages. Regarding status of migration, 87% of them are living in the same village since their born, where as 5% of them have come from the other villages and 2% of the respondents have come from the nearby towns. Next, 1% of them have come from other districts; where as 1% of the respondents are moved from the other States.

- The chi-square value of birth place of the respondents is found to be 400.641 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.
- In other words birth places of the respondents have got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior and allied issues of the respondents .

Migration

The chi-square value of migration status of the respondents is found to be 826.136 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

- In other words migration status of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior and allied issues of the respondents.

Expenditure Patterns of the Families (in Rs/Month)

Amount in Rs.	1000-2000		2000-3000		3000-4000		Above 5000		X ²	P
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
For Livelihood	233	72.5	120	44.1	29	23.5	12	14.2	221.529	0.000
For Health care	32	9.96	53	19.4	24	19.5	30	35.7		
Education	12	3.7	45	16.5	57	46.3	29	34.5		
Loan repayment	33	10.2	27	9.9	6	4.8	10	11.5		
Other	11	3.4	27	9.9	7	5.6	3	3.5		
Total	321	100.0	272	100.0	123	100.0	84	100/0		

Table 35

Fig 40

*The chi-square value of general pattern of expenditure of the respondents is found to be 221.529 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words general pattern of expenditure of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior and medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents

Table36 **Pattern of Social Expenditure of the Households in the last One Year**

Amount in Rs.	Rs. 5,000-10,000		10,000-30,000		40,000-60,000		Above 1,00000		X2	P
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Marriage	23	10.3	16	17.9	34	25.0	19	70.3	153.952	0.000
Birthday	45	20.2	16	17.6	-----	----	-----	---		
Death ceremony	5	2.2	24	26.8	97	71.3	8	29.0		
Festival	123	55.4	50	56.0	4	3.0	-----			
Other	26		6	5.3	1	0.7	-----			
No such cases	----	---		-----		-----	-----			
Total	222	100.0	112	100.0	136	100.0	27	100.0		

Fig 41

*The chi-square value of pattern of social expenditure of the respondents is found to be 153.952

and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant

* In other words general pattern of expenditure of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents

Break up Details of the Household Health Care Expenditure in the Preceding One Year

Amount in Rs.	2,000-5,000		5,000-15,000		20,000-40,000		Above 50,000		X ²	P
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
For Medicines	176	51.8	123	41.0	5	4.0	-----		73.085	0.000
Lab Testing	23	6.7	21	7.0	2	1.5	-----			
Surgery	43	12.6	100	33.3	101	80.1	30	88.2		
Consultation fees	36	10.5	34	11.3	----	---	-----			
Hospital charges	30	8.8	6	2.0	2	1.5	4	11.7		
Transportation	21	6.1	3	1.0	3	2.3	-----			
All the above	11	3.2	13	4.3	13	10.3	-----			
Total	340	100.0	300		126		34	100.0		

Tab 37

Fig 42

*The chi-square value of pattern of health care expenditure the respondents are found to be 73.085 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words health care expenditure of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues.

Ownership Details of the Land

Pattern	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Irrigated	187	23.3	155.027	0.000
Un-irrigated	248	31.0		
Dry land	113	14.1		
Land under non agricultural uses	34	4.2		
Grazing land	67	8.3		
Waste land	43	5.3		
No land	108	13.5		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 38

Fig 43

Regarding land ownership, 23% of the respondents own irrigated land where as 31% owns un irrigated lands. Next, 14% are owns dry land where as 4% owns some land but they are using it for non-agriculture purposes while 8% owns grazing land where as 5% owns waste land and 13% of them are the landless laborers among the studied samples.

*The chi-square value of the ownership of the land of the respondents are found to be 155.027 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant

* In other words ownership details of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, and allied issues of the respondents

Saving Patterns of the Respondents

Sources	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Bank	189	23.6	201.753	0.000
Post office	98	12.5		
Both	69	8.6		
Traditional	136	17.0		
No savings	297	37.1		
Other	11	1.37		
Total	800	100		

Tab 39

Fig 44

Regarding savings pattern, 23% of the respondents are saving money in the Banks while 12% of them are saving money in Post Offices and 8% are using both Bank and Post office to save money. Next, 17% are saving money in other traditional sources and 37% of them have no savings habits at all.

*The chi-square value of saving pattern of the respondents of the respondents is found to be 201.753 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words saving patterns of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health culture, behavior and allied issues of the respondents

Household Liabilities / Loans

Amount in Rs	5,000-10000		10,000-20,000		30,000-40,000		Above 40,000		X ²	P
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Category										
Bank loan	100	38.0	96	50.0	5	25.0	75	25.6	106.712	0.000
Mortgage	43	16.3	75	39.0	2	10.0	103	35.2		
Local money lenders	60	22.8	11	5.7	10	50.0	75	25.6		
All the above	20	7.6	6	3.1	1	5.0	14	4.7		
Other	40	15.2	4	2.0	2	10.0	25	8.5		
Total	263	100.0	192	100.0	20	100.0	292	10.0		

Tab 40

Fig 45

*The chi-square value of household liabilities of the respondents is found to be 106.712 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words household liabilities of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, and allied issues of the respondents

Disposal Patters of Solid and Liquid Wastages

Pattern	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Wherever suitable	78	9.7	239.960	0.000
In the premises of the house	116	14.5		
Separate Drainages	164	20.5		
Garbage blocks	356	44.5		
Disposing once in a weak	75	9.3		
Other type	11	1.3		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 41

Fig 46

Regarding disposal of the wastages, 9% of the respondents are disposing wastages wherever suitable while 14% of them disposing garbage's in the premises of the house where as 20% are disposing at the drainages. Further, it is found that 44% are using garbage blocks while 9% are disposing wastages once in a weak at the outskirts of the village.

*The chi-square value of disposal patters of solid and liquid wastages of the respondents is found to be 239.960 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words disposal patters of solid and liquid wastages respondents of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health concept, behavior, and allied issues of the respondents

Frequency of using Fruits and Vegetables

Frequency/week	Frequency	%	X ²	P
One serve or less	268	33.5	579.921	0.000
2-3 serve	23	2.8		
4-5 serve	14	1.7		
6 serves or more	1	0.1		
Only in occasions	494	61.7		
Total	800	100		

Tab 42

Fig 47

In case of using fruits and vegetables it is revealed that 33.5% of the respondents are using it twice/thrice a week where as 2.8% are using it frequently. Next only 1.7% of the respondents are using vegetables daily and 0.1 are using very rarely. It is found that 61.7% of them are using occasionally.

*The chi-square value of frequency of using vegetables and the fruits by the respondents is found to be 579.921 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words frequency of using vegetable and fruits by the respondents has the significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents

Food Style Pattern

Pattern	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Pure veg. only	349	43.6	137.772	0.000
Non veg. only	216	27.0		
Mixed	189	23.6		
Seasonal	46	5.7		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 48

Regarding food pattern of the respondents it is found that 43% of them are pure vegetarians where as 27% of the respondents are purely non-vegetarians. Further, 23 % them use both veg and non veg food items and 5% of them said that their food pattern would be seasonal.

The chi-square value of food patterns the respondents are found to be 137.772 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other wordspattern of food pattern the respondents is significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Prevalence of Addictions

Response	Frequency	%	χ^2	P
Smoking	189	36.1	190.298	0.000
Alcohol	201	25.1		
Both	43	5.3		
Beeda/ Jerda	17	2.1		
No such addictions	400	50.5		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 49

Fig 48

It is quite evident that 36% of them have smoking habits whereas 25% of them are alcoholic while 5% of them are having both the habits. Next 2% of the respondents are using Beeda/ Jerda and 50 % of the respondents don't have any addictions.

*The chi-square value of prevalence of addictions among the respondents is found to be 190.298 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words prevalence of addictions among the respondent's is significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents .

General Awareness about Health Effects of Addictions

Tab 50

Response	Frequency	%	X²	P
We aware the effects	206	25.7	209.462	0.000
We are not aware	129	16.1		
Partial idea	115	14.3		
Nothing will happen	156	19.5		
If any problem it can be curable	100	12.5		
We can't live without addictions	50	6.2		
Other	34	4.2		
No reply	10	1.2		
Total	800	100		

It is found that 25.7% of the respondents are aware of the consequence of the addictions while 16.1% of the respondents don't have any awareness about the health consequences of the addictions. Next, 14.3% of them have partial awareness where as 19.5% of them opined nothing will happen due to the addictions. Next, 12.5% felt problems if any from the addictions can be medically curable.

*The chi-square value of awareness about health effects of the addictions among the respondents is found to be 209.462 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words awareness about health effects due to addictions among the respondents is significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Do you hold any Health Insurance?**Tab 51**

Response	Frequency	%	X²	P
Yes	24	3.0	316.213	0.000
No	565	71.0		
Never heard	211	26.3		
Total	800	100		

In case of health insurance 3% of the respondents have different health insurances whereas 71% are out of any insurance coverage while 26% have even never heard about anyhealth insurance .

*The chi-square value of having the health insurance by the respondents is found to be 316.213and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words status of health insurance of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, and allied issues of the respondents.

Sources of Health Information's

Tab 52

Sources	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Through their educated children	213	26.6	50.808	0.000
Relatives and friends	100	12.5		
Folk media	111	13.8		
TV/ Radio/ News papers	131	16.3		
Health workers	66	8.25		
NGO camps	89	11.1		
No sources	90	11.2		
Total	800	100		

Fig 49

Regarding sources of health information 26.6% of the respondents are getting health education through their educated children while 12.5% are getting information through their relative and friends and 13% are getting through folk media only. Next, 16.3% of the respondents are getting it through various electronic medias while 8% of them are getting through health workers. Next 11% are getting information through NGOs and 11% are not getting any health information from any sources.

*The chi-square value of sources of health information's of the respondents is found to be 50.808 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words sources of health information's of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health culture, behavior, and allied issues of the respondents.

Preventative Measures

Tab 53

Measures	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Vaccinations/ Immunizations	56	7.0	239.253	0.000
Regular health checkups	125	15.6		
Celebrating festivals/ fairs/ worship	89	11.1		
Clean food / water/ shelter	342	42.7		
Good household ecology	176	22.7		
Nothing required	12	1.5		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 50

Regarding preventative measures to keep healthy, 7% of the respondents said it is only possible through vaccinations and 15.6% of them said through regular health checkups. Next, 11% of them said celebrating festivals and fairs are must where as 42.7% of them said clean food, water and shelter will keep us healthy.

*The chi-square value of the concept about preventive measure by the respondents is found to be 239.253 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words concept about preventive measure by the respondents is significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Are you Happy with your Current Health Status?

Tab 54

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Very Satisfied	45	5.6	231.407	0.000
Somewhat good	147	18.3		
Happy	246	30.7		
Unhappy	204	25.5		
Very bad	67	8.3		
Disparate	89	11.1		
Other	2	0.25		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 51

Regarding happiness with the current health status 5% of the respondents said they are very satisfied while 18% said somewhat ok. However, 30% of them said they are just happy with their health issues while 25% of them felt they are quite unhappy. Next, 8% of them said their health status is very bad while 11% are said they are very desperate with their current health status.

*The chi-square value of happiness with the current health status of the respondents is found to be 231.407 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words happiness with the current health status of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, and allied issues of the respondents.

Special Health Expenditure for the Children and the Aged Tab 55

Amount (In Rs. in a month))	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Les then 200	600	75.0	231.407	0.000
Between 200-300	112	14.0		
More than 300	41	5.1		
Nil	47	5.8		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 52

Regarding spending extra money for the health of the aged and the children it is found that 75% of the respondents are spending within Rs. 200/- per month while 14% of them are spending between Rs. 200 to 300/ where as 5% of the respondents are spending more than Rs. 300/- and more than 5.8% are not spending any money at all .

*The chi-square value of money spending specially for the children and the aged in a month by the respondents is found to be 231.407 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words money spending specially for the above purposes by the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, and allied issues of the respondents.

Factors affecting Women’s Health Issue

Tab 56

Factors	Frequency	%	X²	P
Socio cultural status of the family	237	29.6	408.796	0.000
Economic background	301	37.6		
Educational status of the in- laws/husband	218	27.2		
All the above	17	2.1		
Social network of the households	15	1.8		
Other	5	0.62		
Total	800	100.0		

Regarding factors affecting women’s health issues it is quite evident that 29% of them said it depends on socio cultural status of the family where as 37% of them opined economic background of the household play a vital role. Next, 27% of them viewed that educational level of the parents /in law or husbands is also an important issue affecting on the women’s health issue. Next, 2.% of them admitted all these factors are responsible with respect to the women’s health where as 1% opined it depends on social network of the households.

*The chi-square value of factors affecting women’s health as opined by the respondents is found to be 408.796 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words factors affecting women’s health as opined by the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, and allied issues of the respondents.

Fasting Practices of the Households

Tab 57

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Female members once in a week	176	22.0	145.303	0.000
Male members during festivals only	23	2.8		
All members only during festivals	287	35.8		
For aged members only(once in a week)	127	15.8		
No such customs at all	187	23.3		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 53

In case fasting practice, 22% of the respondents said only female members will observe fasting once in a week whereas 2.8% male members only during festivals. Next 35% of them said all members in the family observe fasting during festivals only. Subsequently, 15% of them said aged people in families will observe fasting while 23% of them said they don't have any such customs in their families.

*The chi-square value of the fasting practice by the respondents is found to 145.303 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words fasting practice by the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Healthy Foods as Viewed by the Respondents Tab 58

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Milk and milk products	121	15.1	40.046	0.000
Butter and Ghee	111	13.8		
Mutton , Egg and Fish	228	28.5		
Pulse and Cereals	88	11.5		
Fruits and Vegetables	145	18.1		
All the above	107	13.3		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 54

Regarding healthy foods as viewed by the respondents 15% of them opined milk and milk products whereas 13% of them said butter and ghee and 28% of them said mutton, egg, fish are the healthy food items. Next, 11% opined pulses and cereals and 18% of them fruits and vegetables are the healthy food items while 13% of them said all these foods are actually healthier.

*The chi-square value of the concept about healthy food items by the respondents is found to be 40.046 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words list of the healthy food items as opined by the respondents is statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents

Preseason's for the Contamination of Food items Tab 59

Sources	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Spirits and evil eyes'	113	14.6	178.078	0.000
eating outside	143	17.8		
Pathogenesis	345	43.6		
Preparing food outside	100	12.5		
Contamination of food items is a natural phenomenon	56	7.0		
All the above	43	5.3		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 55

Regarding contamination of food items 14% of the responders said it is because of spirits and evil eye while 17% it happens due to eating outside and 43.6% of them said it is because of pathogenesis. Further, 12.5% of them said if food prepared outside the home food will get contaminates while 7% of them opined contamination of food items is quite natural and we cont avoid it.

*The chi-square value of concept about contamination of food items the respondents is found to be 178.078 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words reasons about contamination of food items by the respondents is statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Concept about Pure and Impure Blood Tab 60

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Pure blood leads health and impure blood causes illness	134	16.7	129.242	0.000
Hot foods leads good blood and cold foods leads bad blood	132	16.5		
There is no such categorizations	200	25.3		
Good blood will get contaminated by evil eyes/cosmology	102	12.7		
It depends on consuming different food items	75	9.3		
Pathogenesis cause god blood into bad	148	18.5		
Other	9	1.2		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 56

*The chi-square value of concept about good and bad blood of the respondents is found to be 129.242 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words concept about good and bad blood by the respondents is statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Concept about Self Hygiene

Tab 61

Response s	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Taking bath daily is essential	104	13.0	76.368	0.000
Hand wash before eating is must	112	14.0		
Always better to drink boiled water	40	5.0		
Open field of toilet is dangers	202	25.2		
Household sanitation is not so vital	175	21.8		
hand wash after defecation has no relation to health	100	12.5		
Eating road side food items has no affects	157	19.6		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 57

*The chi-square value of concept about self hygiene and health Issue of the respondents are found to be 76.368 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words concept about self hygiene and health issue by the respondents is statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents

Food Discrimination among Family Members Tab 62

Reasons	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Males are the hard workers ;they need more food	209	26.1	129.423	0.000
Females work inside the house only ;they need less food	240	30.0		
Males need more energy because they are the bread winners	150	18.7		
Female may get obese if they eat more	77	9.6		
No such discrimination in the households	124	15.4		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 58

It is found that 26% of the respondent's opined males are the hard workers hence they need more food more whereas, 30% said females work inside the house only hence they should feed less. Next, 18% of the respondents felt male need more energy because they are the bread winner while 9% of the respondents said female may get obese if they eat more and 15% said no such norms in their households.

*The chi-square value of reason for serving different food among the respondent's family is found to be 129.423 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words of reasons for serving different food in the respondents family has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, and allied issues of the respondents.

Possible Social Determinants Affecting Health Status

Tab 63

Determents	Frequency	%	X²	P
Income	149	18.6	113.544	0.000
Occupation	213	26.6		
Educational level	201	25.1		
Poverty level	100	12.5		
Social network	25	3.1		
All the above	100	12.5		
Others	12	1.5		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 59

Regarding possible social determents affecting health status it is revealed that 18.6% them opined it is Income and 26.6% of them opined nature of Occupation play a vital role. Next, 25.1% said Educational level of the households whereas 12% said it is Poverty which acts as strongest social determinants. Further, 3% of them said Social network play a vital role and 12% opined all these factors affects as possible social determinants.

*The chi-square value of possible social determinants affecting health status as opined by the respondents is found to be 113.544 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words possible social determinants affecting health status as opined by the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Sources of Advice for Referral

Tab 64

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Elder family members	300	37.5	215.206	0.000
Friends/ relatives	154	19.2		
Different media	95	11.8		
Traditional healers	28	3.5		
Health workers	133	16.6		
Self	65	8.1		
Other sources	25	3.1		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 60

Regarding source of advice for referral, 37.5% of the respondents said elder family members, where 19.2% of them said friends or relatives while 11.8% of them said awareness through media are the source of advice for referral. Next, 3% of them said respondents said traditional healers while 16.6% of them said health workers whereas 8% of the respondents said self are the sources for referral.

*The chi-square value source of advice for referral of the respondents is found to be 215.206

and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words source of advice for referral by the respondents is statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents .

Beneficiaries of the Following Programme

Tab 65

Schemes	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Janani Suraksha Yojana	101	12.6	120.897	0.000
Sanitation Programme (SP)	121	15.1		
Yesheswini rural free health insurance	268	33.5		
Either of the above	189	23.6		
Others	78	9.7		
None	43	5.3		
Total	800	100		

Fig 61

*The chi-square value of beneficiaries of the various Govt. programmes of the respondents is found to be 120.897 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words beneficiaries of the various Govt. health programmes of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, and allied issues of the respondents.

Purpose of Visiting Health Workers Tab 66

Purpose	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Health education	187	23.3	150.291	0.000
Vaccination	96	12		
Natal care	194	24.2		
Counseling	76	9.5		
To distribute free medicines	178	22.2		
All the above	24	3.0		
No such health workers	45	5.6		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 62

*The chi-square value of purpose of visiting health workers as opined by the respondents is found to be 150.291 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words purpose of visiting health workers as opined by the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, and allied issues of the respondents.

Norm's for Diet Pattern

Tab 67

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
For the Patients' only	258	32.2	157.016	0.000
For Women only	225	28.1		
No such norms	73	9.0		
For the Childrens' only	211	26.3		
For the Aged only	33	4.1		
Total	800	100		

Fig 63

It is found that 32% of the respondents are observing diet pattern in case of patients whereas, 28% said of them are following diet norms for women only. Next, 26% of the respondents said diet norms will be only for the children, while 4% of them said diet norms is only for the aged in the family where as 28% of them said they are not observing any such norms in their respective families.

*The chi-square value of observed norms on the diet pattern of the respondents is found to be 157.016 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words norms on the diet pattern of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, and allied issues of the respondents .

Reasons for the Poor health Status Other than Poverty

Tab 68

Reasons	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Lack of awareness	89	11.1	195.856	0.000
Illiteracy	110	13.7		
Ignorance	200	25.0		
All the above	15	1.8		
Fate and Gods curse	200	25.0		
Not interested to spend on health	82	10.2		
Govt. policies and others	89	11.1		
No idea	15	1.8		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 64

In case of reasons for the poor health status other than Poverty related 11% of the respondents said it is due to lack of awareness, whereas 13% said it is due to illiteracy and 25% said it is due to ignorance while 25% felt it is due to fate and 10% felt it is due to ignorance

*The chi-square value reasons for poor health status of the rural people other than poverty related as opined by the respondents is found to be 195.856 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words reasons for poor health status other than poverty related as opined by the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, and allied issues of the respondents.

What is Health according to you?

Tab 69

Reasons	Frequency	%	X²	P
Health is a complete stat of physical, mental and social wellbeing	231	28.8	135.56	0.000
I believe health means looking after myself and taking things easy	110	13.7		
I believe health means giving up unhealthy habits	30	3.7		
Health is actively seeking out things that make me happy	15	1.8		
Health is thinking positively	90	11.2		
Health is taking charge of and responsibility for, my own life	245	30.6		
All the above	22	2.7		
No idea	57	7.1		
Total	800	100.0		

In case of people’s perception about health it is found that 28% said Health is a complete stat of physical, mental and social wellbeing whereas 13% believe health means looking after our self and taking things easy and 30% have opined that Health is taking charge of and responsibility of our own life

*The chi-square value about the concept/definition of health among the rural people as opined by the respondents is found to be 135.56 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words concept/definition of health among the studied people as opined by them has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, and allied issues of the respondents.

Characteristics of a Healthy Person

Tab 70

Concept	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Person without any disease/illness	300	37.5	239.553	0.000
Who can digest any food	107	13.3		
Who can tolerate hot/ cold whether	105	13.1		
Having a long life span	117	14.6		
One who always on work	80	10.0		
All the above	31	3.8		
Absence of worry/ tensions	40	5.0		
Don t know	10	1.2		
Total	800	100		

Fig 65

For the question of who is a healthy person 37% of the respondents said person without any disease /illness. Next, 13% of them said who can digest anything whereas 13% of them said who can tolerate hot/cold weather while 14% of them said who have the long life span can be considered as healthy people. Next, 10% of them said one who is on work always and 3% of them opined people who are having all these qualities should be considered as a healthy one.

*The chi-square value of characteristics of a healthy person as opined by the respondents found to be 239.553 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words of characteristics of a healthy person as opined by the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health culture, behavior, and allied issues of the respondents

Characteristics of and Unhealthy Person

Tab 71

Concept	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Who is suffering from an illness/ diseases always	345	43.1	242.469	0.000
Who can't work as usual and whose physical body will be pale/ week	76	9.5		
One who always depends on medicine	134	16.7		
Cannot fight against evil forces/ cosmology	116	14.5		
Who have a weak immune system	69	8.6		
Cannot withstand against pathogenesis	45	5.6		
All the above	15	1.8		
Total	800	100		

Fig 66

For the question who is unhealthy? it is found that 43% opined one who is suffering from illness/diseases always where as 9% of them opined who can't work as usual and whose physical body normally would be pale and week. Next, 16% of the respondents opined one who always depends on medicines and 16% of them said one who cannot fight against evil forces/cosmology while 8% felt who have weak immune system.

*The chi-square value of concept about Characteristics of an Unhealthy Person by the respondents is found to be 242.469 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words of concept about unhealthy by the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Why we should be Healthy?

Tab 72

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
It is need for our wellbeing	143	17.8	109.478	0.000
To earn our livelihood	106	13.2		
To discharge our duty effectively and promptly	167	20.8		
To keep the day moving without any problem	187	23.3		
To do our routine work effectively	110	13.2		
Not to depend on others	67	8.3		
No idea	20	2.5		
Total	800	100		

Fig 67

It is quite evident that 17% of the respondents opined healthy life is needed for our wellbeing whereas 13% said health is must to discharges our duty effectively and promptly while 20% of them said god health is must to earn our livelihood. Further 23% of them opined good health is must to keep the day moving without any problem whereas 13% said health is must to do our routine work effectively

*The chi-square value of reasons for being healthy as opined by the respondents is found to be 109.478 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words concept on health by the respondents is statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents .

What is Keeping Healthy

Tab 73

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Proper diet/ sleep/ absence of worry	121	15.1	100.471	0.000
Hygienic environment	159	19.8		
Proper health education	131	16.3		
Adopting prevention measures	174	21.7		
Celebrating festival/ worshipping god/ spirits etc	137	17.1		
All the above	28	3.5		
Other	50	6.2		
Total	800	100		

Fig 68

For keeping healthy 15% of the respondents opined proper diet and absence of worry is essential, while 19% of the respondents said hygienic environment is essential and 16% said proper health education is must for keeping healthy. Further, 21% said adopting preventive measures while 17% held worshipping god festival regularly, while 3% of them said all these reason play a vital role in keeping healthy.

*The chi-square value of concept of keeping healthy by the respondents is found to be 100.471 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words concept of keeping healthy by the respondents is statistically significant influence over the health behavior, health culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Do you think the following factors are risks for normal health status ?

Reasons	Low risk (%)	Moderate risk	High risk
Smoking and drinking	3.2	5.6	91.5
Junk food	40.2	36.3	23.5
Environment Pollution	49.3	20.3	30.2
Contaminate food and water	47.4	20.3	32.9
Stress	45.3	25.2	30.2
Obesity	57.4	23.1	20.2
Improper personal hygiene	56.6	24.3	20.0
Multiple sex partner	44.2	26.3	30.2
Ageing	5.2	3.6	91.3
Family problem	28.2	23.2	49.2
Type of occupation	40.3	28.9	31.0

Tab 74

Why Human beings would get Diseases?

Tab 75

Reasons	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Due to the effect of sprits/ angry deity/ cosmology etc	129	16.1	215.721	0.000
Absence of good food/ water/shelter	134	16.7		
Failure to perform health rituals	49	6.1		
Effect of Pathogens	323	40.3		
Due to unhygienic conditions	96	12.0		
All the above	39	4.8		
Others	30	3.7		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 69

Regarding reasons for causing various diseases 16% of them viewed it is due to the effect of sprits/ angry deity/cosmology power whereas 16% of them said it is due to an absence of good food/ water/shelter etc and 6% said alleged failure to perform health rituals. Next, 40% said it may be due to Pathogens /biological reasons while 12% said it is due to unhygienic conditions and 39% claimed all these factors .

*The chi-square value of concept about reasons causing various diseases of the respondents is found to be 215.721 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words concept about reasons for causing diseases of the respondents has significant influence over the health behavior, health culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Why Human beings would get 'Illness' Tab 76

Reasons	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Effect of Pathogeneses	213	26.6	232.637	0.000
Angry deity/ cosmology powers	164	20.5		
Failure to perform divine rites	78	9.7		
It is due to psychological reasons	199	24.8		
Due to an unhygienic conditions	60	7.5		
No differences between disease and illness	50	6.2		
All the above	20	2.5		
Illness can be traced by enemies	3	0.5		
Other	13	1.8		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 70

For the enquiry why human beings would get illness 26% of the respondents held the view that it is due to pathogens where as 20% said due to angry deity or cosmological power while 9% of them said it is because of failure to perform divine rites. Next, 24% of them opined illness is a status of psychological reasons whereas 8% of them said illness is due to unhygienic conditions. Next 6% opined no such differences between the disease and an illness in general

*The chi-square value of reasons causing illness as opined by the respondents is found to be 232.637 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words reasons causing illness of the respondents has significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Why Human being Would get 'Sickness' ?Tab 77

Reasons	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Sickness and illness are the same	366	45.0	434.508	0.000
Due to the cosmology/ spirits etc	09	1.1		
Medical or Biological	12	1.5		
Due to ill health	256	32.0		
Due to Psychological reasons	134	16.7		
No idea	23	2.3		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 71

Regarding reasons for sickness 45% of the respondents felt sickness and illness are one and the same whereas 1% said sickness causes due to cosmology/spirits while 1% held the view that it is due to the medical or biological reasons. Next, 32% held the view that sickness is due to ill health whereas 16% opined sickness is just a matter of psychological reason.

*The chi-square value of concept about sickness by the respondents is found to be 434.508 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words concept about sickness by the respondents has significant influence over the health behavior, health culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Differences between Sickness and Wellbeing Tab 78

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Sickness is ill health and wellbeing is another name of being healthy	321	40.1	141.228	0.000
Sickens is just not feeling well	211	26.3		
Wellbeing is general status of the health	98	12.2		
Sickens is an another name of illness	122	15.2		
No idea	48	6.0		
Total	800	100		

Fig 72

Regarding differences between sickness and wellbeing 40% of the respondents held the opinion sickness means ill health and wellbeing is another name of being healthy where as 26% held the view that sickens is just not feeling well while 12% opined wellbeing is general status of health. Further, 15% opined sickens is another name of illness and 6% did not understood.

*The chi-square value of differentiation between sickness and wellbeing as opined by the respondents is found to be 141.228 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words differentiation between sickness and wellbeing by the respondents has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents .

Do you think Sick Person have any Role to Play?Tab 79

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
We don't understand	321	40.1	141.228	0.000
Yes: they have	211	26.3		
No : they cant	98	12.2		
Sick people should try to come out of sickens soon	122	15.2		
Other	48	6.0		
Total	800	100		

Fig 73

Regarding the sick role 40% of the respondents did not understand the concept at all whereas, 26% of them opined sick person has certain role to play in the society. Further, 12% held the view that sick person cannot pay any role while 15% of them said sick person should try to get it cure and come of the ill health soon. Next, 6% gave some other reason.

*The chi-square value of concept about sick person's role of the respondents is found to be 141.228 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words concept about concept about sick person's role by the respondents is significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Any Health Care Discrimination between the Elderly and the Adult Members

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
No discrimination	89	11.1	114.866	0.000
Aged members will not be much cared	242	30.2		
Both aged and adults will be well taken care off	223	27.8		
Only adults will be well taken care off	200	25.0		
It is unnecessary to spend on aged people	46	5.8		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 80

Fig 74

It is found that 11% of the respondents opined there will be no discrimination between elderly and adult member in a family with respect to health issue whereas 30% of them opined aged will not be much cared. Further, 27% of them opined both aged and adults will be well taken care off while 25% said only adult members will be were taken care of

*The chi-square value of opinion about discrimination between elderly and adult health care choice of the respondents is found to be 114.866 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words opinion about discrimination between elderly and adult health care choice is statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

HOT and COLD Concepts of Food

Tab 81

	Food items	f	%	Sl.no	Food items	f	%	X ²	p
1	All vegetables are cold	115	23.1	1	All cereals are cold	129	42.4	141.804	0.000
2	Few vegetables are hot	167	33.6	2	Few cereals are hot	137	45.0		
3	All pulses are hot	122	24.5	3	Milk products mutton, chicken are hot	25	8.2		
4	Few pulses are cold	92	18.5	4	Other	13	4.2		
	Total	496	100		Total	304	100		

Fig 75

Fig 76

With regard to hot and cold concept of food items, 23% of the respondents' said all vegetables are cold while 33% of them said few vegetables are hot. Next 24% of them said all pulses are hot causing where as 18% are said few pulses are cold causing. Next, 42% said all cereals are cold, while 45% said few cereals are hot causing although 8% said milk products, mutton and chicken are the hot food items.

*The chi-square value of hot and cold concept of food items of the respondents is found to be 141.804 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words hot and cold concept of the food items by the respondents is statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

How HOT and COLD food Causes Health Problems

Tab 82

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Hot food causes humeral imbalances	256	32.0	238.071	0.000
Cold food causes humeral imbalances	143	17.8		
Hot and cold food will contaminate blood	131	16.3		
Hot and cold food causes metabolic related diseases	227	28.3		
Hot and cold food causes weak immunity	40	5.0		
No idea	3	0.4		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 77

In fact 32% of the respondents' felt hot food causes humeral imbalances while 17% of them said cold food causes humeral imbalances. Next 16% of them said hot and cold food will contaminate blood while 28% of them opined hot and cold food causes metabolic related diseases. Next, 5% of them opined hot and cold food causes weak immunity.

*The chi-square value of hot and cold concept of the respondents is found to be 238.071 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words of hot and cold concept in causing disease has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Concept about ‘Health Culture’

Tab 83

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Set of fixed principles to be followed during illness/ diseases	103	12.8	150.306	0.000
Age old procedure/tradition to follow when we get ill/ sick	119	14.8		
Set of rituals we need to perform during ill health	135	16.8		
Document of illness episodes/ narrations	88	11.0		
Other	34	4.2		
Don’t know	321	40.1		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 78

Regarding concept about health culture 12% of the respondents held the view it is a set of fixed principles to be followed during illness or diseases while 14% of them said it is age old procedures or traditions to follow when we get ill or sick. Next, 16% of them said that it is a set of rules we need to perform during illness while 11% of them said it is illness experience or illness episode while 40% said don't know what is actually health culture means.

*The chi-square value of concept about health culture by the respondents is found to be 150.306 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words concept about health culture by the respondents is significant influence over the health behavior, health culture and allied issues of the respondents

What is ‘Health Seeking Behavior’?

Tab 84

Response	Frequency	%	X²	P
Healing procedure starting from an illness/disease until its cure	213	26.6	136.177	0.000
Rules and regulations patients’ needs to follow during the stage of ill health	168	21.0		
It includes occurrence of diseases/ illness, severity, diagnose and medications etc	187	23.0		
Personal experiences of a patient when he/she had illness/disease and curing	121	15.1		
We don’t know	98	12.3		
Other	13	1.6		
Total	800	100.0		

Regarding health seeking behavior 26% of the respondents held it is about patients’ behavior starting from illness stage until its cure while 21% said health behavior means rules and regulations patients’ needs to follow during the stage of illness or disease while 23% of them said health behavior includes occurrence of diseases/ illness, etiology, diagnose and treatment etc while 15% of them opined personal experiences of a patient when he/she had illness/disease and curing.

*The chi-square value of concept about health seeking behavior of the respondents is found to be 136.177 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words concept about health seeking behavior by the respondents is significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents

Concept about Health care Seeking Behavior

Tab 85

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Doing specific measure to keep healthy in the future	146	18.2	97.424	0.000
Some sort of preventive measures	159	19.8		
Post curing measures	30	3.7		
Occurrence of disease /illness and its cure	123	15.3		
No idea	232	29.9		
Other	110	13.7		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 79

Regarding health care seeking behavior, 18% of the respondents felt health care seeking behavior means doing specific measure to keep healthy in the future where as 19% said it is some sort of preventive measures. Next 3% of them held, it is something about post curing measures while 15% opined it is about occurrence of disease /illness and its cure while 29% said no idea while 13% gave some other response.

*The chi-square value of concept about health care seeking behavior by the respondents is found to be 97.424 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words concept about health care seeking behavior by the respondents is significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

How would you take Decision when you get Sick?

Tab 86

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
As guided by the friends, relatives and village elders	221	27.6	138.185	0.000
At the capacity of my cognitive level	134	16.7		
Consulting family members	149	18.6		
Based on previous experiences	200	25.0		
From my own intuition	78	9.7		
No idea	18	2.2		
Total	800	100.0		

It is quite evident that 27% of the respondents said decision will be taken based on the self intuition whereas 16% of them opined decision will be taken at the capacity of once own cognitive level and 18% said decision will be taken consulting family members or friends where as 25% said decision will be taken based on the previous experiences if any while 9 % of them said decision will be taken as guided by the friends and others

*The chi-square value of decision of the respondents take normally during sickens is found to 138.185 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words decision of the respondents take normally during sickens has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Concept about Body Constitution

Tab 87

Pattern	Frequency	%	X ²	P
It is a boon of the God and the nature	252	31.5	79.067	0.000
It is pre-determined at the time of conception	100	12.6		
Disease and illness are due the malfunction of constitutional/internal factors	67	8.3		
Body composed of good blood, nerves and the organs only	89	11.1		
Hair, teeth and skin color are also attributed to the body constitution	90	11.2		
Body constitution is a pre disposition	100	12.5		
No idea	102	12.7		
Total	800	100		

Fig 80

Regarding body constitution 31% of the respondents said it is boon of the God/nature and 12% of them opined it is pre-determined at the time of conception. Next 8% of the respondents said disease and illness are due the malfunctioning of constitutional/internal factors whereas 11% said body composed of blood, nerves and organs only. Further, 11% of them said hair, teeth and skin color are also attributed to body constitution .

*The chi-square value of concept about body constitution of the respondents is found to be 79.067 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words concept about body constitution of respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Why certain Diseases are not Permanently Curable?

Tab 88

Responses	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Irreparable damages to the internal system	241	30.1	301.184	0.000
Dysfunction of the organs and nerves	321	40.1		
No such diseases in the world today	77	9.6		
Due to Spirits /evil eyes effects	63	7.8		
To check the population by the nature itself	31	3.8		
Failure of our health care system	34	4.2		
Other	33	4.1		
Total	800	100		

Fig 81

It is quite evident that 30% of the respondents opined it is due to an irreparable damage in side a human body while 40% of them said it is due to dysfunction of the organs and nerves in the body system whereas 9.6% opined no such diseases in the world which cannot be curable today. Next, 7% of them said it is due to sorcery /spirit effects whereas, 3% of them alleged this is due to check the population by the nature.

*The chi-square value of respondent’s responses is found to be 301.184 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words concept expressed by the respondents about curing certain disease is significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Concept about Treating an ILL Person

Tab 89

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Social isolation	67	8.3	364.072	0.000
Untouchable	43	5.3		
With sympathy	187	23.3		
Treat like others	243	30.3		
Depend on illness	33	4.1		
Support for speedy recovery	217	27.1		
All the above	5	0.6		
Other	5	0.6		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 82

Regarding concept about treating an ill person 8% of the respondents said ill people should be socially isolated while 5% of them said ill persons should be untouchables. Next, 23% of them said ill persons should be treated with sympathy where as 30% said we should treat them equally like others. Next 4% said it depends on type of illness where as 27% opined we should support ill people for the speedy recovery where as 0.6% admitted all these facts are true.

*The chi-square value of concept about treating an ill person by the respondents is found to be 364.072 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words concept about treating an ill person by the respondents is significant influence over the health behavior, health culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Who does Initial Diagnose of a Health Problem

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Family or village elders	221	27.6	154.643	0.000
Traditional healers	133	16.6		
Self diagnose	38	4.7		
Faith healers	36	4.5		
Health workers	100	12.5		
PHC doctors	218	26.8		
Drug sellers	24	3.0		
No reply	40	5.0		
Total	800	100.		

Tab 90

Fig 83

It is found that 27% of the respondents said family elders diagnose the health problem first where as 16% of them said traditional healers will diagnose the health problems while 4% of them said self diagnose. Next, 4% of them said faith healers will diagnose the health problem while 12.5% of them said local health workers will diagnose the health problem where as 26.8% said PHC doctors and 3% said drug seller will diagnose the health problem and 5% did not reply.

*The chi-square value of initial diagnose of the health problem as replied by the respondents is found to be 154.643 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words concept about diagnosing health problems of the respondents is significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Special Effort for keeping Healthy of the Family Members

Tab 91

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Good food, water and hygienic	137	17.1	268.074	0.000
No extra effort	289	36.1		
No such measures	308	38.5		
More precautions will be taken	56	7.0		
Left to the fate	10	1.2		
Total	800	100		

Fig 84

In case of special care for keeping healthy 17% of them said they concentrate only on good food, hygienic and preventive care while 36% said they are not doing much to keep healthy whereas 38.5% of them said they are not doing any special measures to keep healthy. Next, 7% said they will be taking more precautions while 1% of them said it is left to the fate.

The chi-square value of doing extra for keeping healthy of the family members as opined by the respondents is found to be 268.074 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words doing extra for keeping healthy of the family members of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, and allied issues of the respondents.

Common Epidemics Reported in the Village during the last One year

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Malaria	54	6.7	184.377	0.000
Cholera	135	16.8		
Typhoid	200	25.0		
All the above	32	4.0		
Dengue.	23	2.8		
Chikun guinea	67	8.3		
Jaundice	211	26.3		
Other communicable diseases	78	9.7		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 92

Fig 85

It is revealed that 6.7% of the respondents opined Malaria is frequently occurring since last one year while 16% of them said Cholera is the most common one. Next, 25% said Typhoid is occurring frequently and 4% of the respondents claimed all the above. Further, 2% of the respondents said Dengue is most common whereas 8% said Chicken gunya is frequently occurring in the studied village while 26% of them said Jaundice is most common in the studied village.

*The chi-square value of common epidemics found in the village is found to be 184.377 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words of common epidemics found in the village has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, and allied issues of the respondent.

Family Level Initiatives taken for the Health Problems

Measures	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Family elders will decide about treatment plan	231	28.8	112.337	0.000
Consulting senior village elders	137	17.1		
Worshipping deity	121	15.1		
Home remedy	200	25.0		
Other	75	9.5		
Visiting drug seller directly	36	4.4		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 93

Fig 86

Regarding initiatives taken for disease or illness at the family level it is found that 28% of the respondents will consult senior members of the village while 17% said family elders will decide about the treatment plan whereas 15% would like to worship deity. Next, 25% respondents will do home remedy first whereas 9.5 % other actions will be taken at the family level

*The chi-square value of initiative taken for disease/ illness at the family level of the respondents is found to be 112.337 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words initiative taken for disease/ illness at the family level of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Common Diseases Found Among the Children (8-12 Years Age)

Diseases	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Typhoid	76	9.5	28.674	0.000
Malaria	87	10.8		
Jaundice	132	16.5		
Cholera	99	12.3		
All the above	151	18.8		
Scabies	67	8.3		
Dioharia	110	13.7		
Seasonal	78	9.7		
Total	800	100		

Tab 94

Fig 87

Regarding common diseases found among the children (8-12 age group) in the area as opined by the respondents 9.5% of them said it is Typhoid, 10.8% of them said Malaria, 16% of them said Jaundice and 12% of them said Cholera. Further, 18% said all the above diseases are common while 13% of them said Dioharia are common in the studied area

*The chi-square value of common diseases found among the children as opined by the respondents is found to be 28.674 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words common diseases found among the children as opined by the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health status and allied issues of the respondents.

Common Diseases Found Among the Adolescents

Tab 95

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Typhoid	102	12.7	63.005	0.000
Malaria	86	10.7		
Jaundice	176	22.0		
Cholera	158	19.7		
All the above	67	8.3		
Injuries	89	11.1		
Diaoharia	56	7.0		
STD(not come across)	63	7.8		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 88

It is found that 12.7% of the respondents said it is Typhoid, 10.7% said Malaria, while 22% said Jaundice and 19.7% of them said Cholera whereas 8.3% said all these diseases found common among adolescents in the studied area. Next, 11% of them said Injuries while 7% of them said it is Diaohoria are most common among the adolescents in the studied area.

*The chi-square value of common diseases found among the adolescents as opined by the respondents is found to be 63.005 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words common diseases found among the adolescents as opined by the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, and allied issues of the respondents.

Common Diseases found among the Aged

Tab 96

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Heart problems	225	28.1	218.281	0.000
Liver disorders	145	18.1		
Lungs disorders	100	12.5		
Bone disorders	78	9.7		
Either above	80	10.0		
Life style disorders	109	13.6		
Injuries	43	5.3		
STD/AIDS	10	1.2		
Other	10	1.2		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 89

For this enquiry 28% of the respondents said Heart problem whereas 18% opined Liver disorder and 12% said Lungs disorder (due to excessive alcoholism and smoking addictions) are most common among the aged. Also 9% of them said Bone disorders whereas 10% of them opined all these problems are common in case of aged. Further, 13% of them said life style disorder is common among the aged whereas 1.2% of them said STD/AIDS is less common.

*The chi-square value of common diseases found among the aged as opined by the respondents is found to be 218.281 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words common diseases found among the aged as opined by the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, and allied issues of the respondents.

Recent Death in the Family (6-12 months) From any these ReasonTab 97

Fig 90

From communicable diseases like Jaundice Typhoid, Dengue etc 30% of respondents have lost their son/daughters while 25% of them have lost their husband/wife whereas 23% are lost their grandparents and 11% of them have lost their grand children as well as 24% are lost their other close blood relatives. From the mental illness, 6% of the respondents have lost their son/daughter, 8% of them are lost their husband/wife, 7% have lost their grandparents and 11% are lost their other close blood relatives. From accidents, 16% of respondents have lost their son/daughter, 8% of them have lost their husband/wife, 23% are lost their grandparents, 33 % have lost their grand children. Due to suicide, 23% of respondents have lost their son/daughter 8% of them are lost their husband/wife, 15% have lost their grandparents, 11 % have lost their grand children where as 13% have lost their other relatives.

*The chi-square value of death due to various listed reasons in the family of the respondents is found to be 45.712 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words death due to various listed reasons in the family of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, and allied issues of the respondents.

Types of Self-reported Health Problems during the Preceding 60 days

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Surgery related issues	23	2.8	450.465	0.000
Communicable diseases	79	9.8		
Eye and ENT diseases	26	3.2		
Gastrointestinal diseases	56	7.0		
Respiratory diseases	45	5.6		
Other problems	31	3.8		
Accidents	33	4.3		
No such Problem	507	63.3		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 98

Fig 91

It is quite evident that 2.8% of the respondents had surgery related issues while 9.8% of them had Communicable diseases and 3.2% of them had ENT problems. Next, 7% of them had had gastric related problems while 5.6% had respiratory problems and 3% had other type of health problems. Further, 5% had minor/major accidents while 63% did not have any such health problems.

*The chi-square value of types of self-reported diseases during the preceding 60 day by the respondents is found to be 450.465 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words types of self-reported diseases during the preceding 60 day by the respondents is statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents .

Respondents' Suffered From the Following Diseases in the Last One Year

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Typhoid	67	23.1	13.835	0.000
Malaria	54	18.6		
Jaundies	65	22.4		
Cholera	72	9.0		
Dengue	32	4.0		
Total	290	100.0		

Tab 99

Fig 92

It is found that 23% of the respondents have suffered from Typhoid while 18% of them have suffered from Malaria and 22% have them suffered from Jaundice whereas 9% of them are suffered from Cholera and 4% of them had Dengue.

The chi-square value of respondents' suffered from different diseases is found to be 13.835 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words respondents' suffered from various diseases has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondent,

Immunizations for the Children

Tab 100

Vaccines	BCG and DPT		Measles		Polio		Retro virus		Hepatitis		X ²	P
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Response											2855.532	0.000
Yes;	697	87.1	632	79	759	94.8	6	0.7	56	7		
No	65	8.1	160	20	31	3.8	790	98.7	700	87.5		
Don't know	38	4.7	8	1	10	1.2	4	0.5	44	5.5		
Total	800	100	800	100	800	100	800		800	100		

Fig 93

It is quite revealed that 87% of the respondents have immunized their children against BCG and DPT whereas 8% have not immunized their children. For Measles 79% of the parents immunized their children whereas 20% not immunized their children for Measles. Next, 94% of the respondents have immunized their children against Polio whereas 3% have not immunized.

*The chi-square value of type and rate of immunization of the children's of the respondents is found to be 2855.532 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words rate and type of immunization to the children's of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, and allied issues of the respondents

Mortality Indicators in the Studied Samples

Tab 101

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Natal mortality	9	30.0	1.619	0.805
Neo natal mortality	8	26.6		
Infant mortality	11	36.6		
Childhood mortality	5	16.0		
Maternal mortality	5	16.0		
Total	30	100.0		

Fig 94

Regarding mortality indicator in the studied samples it is revealed that 30% of the respondents have had Neonatal, while 36 % have had Infant mortality whereas 16% have had childhood mortality and 12% of the respondents have had maternal mortality problem.

*The chi-square value of mortality indicator in the studied samples is found to be 1.619 and P value is higher than 0.05 is found to be highly insignificant.

*In other words of mortality indicator in the studied samples has got statistically not significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Perception of the Causes for the Emergency of Disease /IllnessTab 102

Pattern	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Food Poison	221	27.6	133.458	0.000
Pathogenesis	146	18.2		
Sprits and Cosmology forces	148	18.5		
Medical reasons	201	25.1		
Other	34	4.2		
Don't know	50	6.2		
Total	800	100		

Fig 95

Regarding perception of the causes for the emergency of disease /illness it is found that 27% of the respondents opined emergency of disease /Illness causes due to differences in the food, water etc while 18.2% of them said evil eye and angry deity and 18.5% of them said it causes due to spirits and cosmology forces. Next, 25% of them said it cause due to medical reasons where as 4.2% gave some other reason and 6% of them said that they don't have any idea.

*The chi-square value of the perception of the causes for the emergency of diseases of the respondents is found to be 133.458 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words perception of the causes for the emergency of disease of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Types of Treatment for the following Health Common Problems Tab 103

Treatment pattern	Traditional		Home remedy		Modern		Self medication		X ²	P
	f	%	f	%	F	%	f	%		
Health Problems	f	%	f	%	F	%	f	%	65.019	0.000
Cough and cold	118	42.1	65	28.6	36	17.6	45	50.5		
Common fever	69	24.6	58	25.5	59	28.9	16	17.9		
Body ache	26	9.2	54	23.7	60	29.4	13	14.6		
Gastric and Vomiting	67	23.9	50	22.0	49	24.0	15	16.8		
Total	280	100.0	227	100.0	204	100.0	89	100.0		

Fig 96

It is found that 42% of the respondents would like to use traditional medicines while 28% would like to use home remedy whereas 17% use modern medicines for cough and cold. While 50% said they will use only self medications for cough and cold. For the common fever, 24% of them use traditional medicines, 25% use home remedies and 28% of them use modern medicines while 17% use self medications. For gastric 23% use traditional and 22% use home remedy.

.*The chi-square value of treatment patterns for the simple health problems of the respondent is found to be 65.019 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words of treatment patterns for the common health problems of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, and allied issues of the samples

Common Cusses for Anemia /Weakness

Tab 104

Responses	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Lack of medical care	67	8.3	360.426	0.000
It is a kind of diseases	209	26.1		
Lack of good nutrient foods	386	48.5		
Heredity factors	56	7.0		
Nature of the body constituents	32	4.0		
Evil eye/ spirit	20	2.5		
No idea	36	4.5		
Total	800	100		

Fig 97

In fact 8.3% of the respondents opined it is due to lack of medical care while 26% said it may be a kind of disease while 48.5% of the respondents said it is due to the lack of good nutrient foods while 7% of them said it is a heredity problem. Next 4% opined it is nature of the body constituent of that particular person where as 2% of them said it might be due to an evil eye /spirit effect.

*The chi-square value of concept about anemia or weakness of the respondents is found to be 360.426 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words concept about anemia or weakness has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents

Treatment pattern for Dog, Snake and Scorpion bite etc Tab 105

Pattern	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Home remedies	122	15.2	196.755	0.000
Traditional	218	27.2		
Faith healing	34	4.2		
Self medications	24	3.0		
Western	260	32.5		
Traditional and western	142	17.7		
Total	800	100		

Fig 98

It is quite evident that 15.2% of the respondents will use home remedies while 27% use traditional medicine where as 4.2% use faith healing. Next 3% of the respondents are using self medications whereas 32.5 % of them are using western medicines and 17% use traditional medications for western for Dog, Snake and Scorpion bite etc.

*The chi-square value of treatment behavior for animal biting by the respondents is found to be 196.755 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other wordstreatment behavior for animal biting among the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, and allied issues of the respondents.

Common Social behavior towards TB, Leprosy and Mental Illness Patents

Opinion	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Taboo	65	8.1	316.238	0.000
Isolation	76	9.5		
Ex-communication	133	16.6		
Deporting	23	2.8		
Don't know	43	5.3		
Other	45	5.6		
Treat commonly	415	51.8		
Total	800	100		

Tab 106

Fig 99

For common social behavior towards TB, Leprosy and Mental Illness 8% of the respondents said Taboo, while 9% of them said to isolate the patients from the society whereas 16% of them said to ex-communicate the patients. Next, 2.8% of them said to deport the patients' while 51.8% opined we have treated those patients commonly without any discrimination and 5.6% gave some other reasons .

*The chi-square value of common social behavior towards T B, leprosy etc by the respondents is found to be 316.238 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words common social behavior towards certain diseases by the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents .

Special care for the Differently Challenged Persons

Tab 107

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
No special care	3	8.1	10.382	0.065
Special food will be provided	10	27.0		
Emotional care	15	40.5		
Extra health care	6	16.2		
All the above	3	8.1		
Other	1	2.7		
Total	37	100.0		

Fig 100

It is found that 8% of the respondents had no special care for the differently challenged persons where as 27% of them said special food will be provided and 40.5% of them said more emotional care will be provided. While 16.2% of the respondents said extra health care will be provided and 8% of them said all the above

*The chi-square value of special care for the differently challenged persons by the respondents is found to be 10.382 and P value is higher than 0.05 is found to be highly insignificant.

* In other wordsspecial care for differently challenged person by the respondents has got a statistically no significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

The Meaning of Safe Sex

Tab 108

Pattern	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Sex with only one men/ women	345	43.1	95.575	0.000
Using contraceptives	209	26.1		
Sex after marriage only	30	3.7		
No sex outside marriage	116	14.5		
No reply	100	12.5		
Total	800	100		

Fig 101

It is revealed that 43% of the respondents said safe sex means having sex with only one men/women where as 26% of them said sex using contraceptives only. Next, 3.7% of them said sex only after marriage whereas 14% of the respondents said no sex outside marriage and 12.5% have not replied.

*The chi-square value of concept about safe sex of the respondents is found to be 95.575 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words meaning of safe sex for the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Usage of Contraceptives Tab 109

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Daily pill	29	3.6	95.575	0.00
IUD	58	7.2		
Sterilization	137	17.1		
Condom	92	11.5		
Implant	67	8.3		
Vasectomy	150	18.7		
Others'	67	8.3		
Not using any type	150	18.7		
No reply	50	6.2		
Total	800	100		

Fig 102

Regarding usage of contraceptives it is revealed that 3.6% of the respondents are using daily pill while 7% of them are using IUD and 17% are underwent sterilization. Next 11.5% are using condoms whereas 8.3% of them are using implant while 18% use vasectomy whereas 8% are using other methods. It is also found that 18% are not using any contraceptives whereas 6% did not reply.

*The chi-square value of type of contraceptives using by the respondents is found to be 95.575 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other wordstype of contraceptive using by the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents

Reasons for not Adopting Family Planning Method**Tab 110**

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Personnel reasons	25	16.6	11.892	0.064
It is against the custom	38	25.3		
Fear of operation	21	14.0		
Desire to have more children	14	9.3		
Not good for the future health	27	18.0		
Don't like planning method	14	9.3		
Other	11	7.3		
Total	150	100		

It revealed that 16% of the respondents said it is personnel while 25% said it's against the customs where as 14% said fear of operation. Next 9% said desire to have more children whereas 18% said it is not good for the future health. Further, 9% said they don't like any method , while 7% gave some other reason.

* The chi-square value of reasons for not adopting any family planning method of the respondents is found to be 11.892 and P value is higher than 0.05 is found to be highly insignificant.

*In other words reasons for not adopting family planning method of the respondents has got a statistically has no significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Special care During Menstrual time

Tab 111

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
No extra care	80	38.2	0.092	5.0
Special food	38	18.1		
Will take more rest	20	9.5		
Extra care	27	12.9		
More hygienic care	32	15.3		
Not replied	12	5.7		
Total	209	100.0		

Fig 103

It is found that during menstrual time 38.2% of the respondents don't take an extra care whereas 18% of them take special food during menstrual time. Next, 9.5% will take more rest. Further 12.9% of the respondents take extra care while 15.7% of them said measure for more hygienic will be preferred and 5.7% of the respondent did not reply.

The chi-square valuespecial care during menstrual time by the respondents is found to be 0.092 and P value is higher than 0.05 is found to be highly insignificant.

In other wordsspecial care during menstrual by the respondents has got statistically no significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Possible Reasons for Still birth and Miscarriage

Tab 112

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Heredity	87	10.8	206.589	0.000
Medical reason	234	29.2		
Effects of super natural powers	54	6.7		
Effects of conjugal marriage	116	14.5		
Don't know	286	35.7		
Other	23	2.8		
Total	800	100		

Fig 104

It revealed that 10% of the respondents' cited heredity is the main reason for still birth whereas 29.2% of them said it is due to the medical reason while 6.7% of them said it is due to the supernatural powers. Next, 14.5% of them said it might be due to the conjugal marriage where as 35.7% said they don't have idea and 2.8% of them gave some other reasons.

*The chi-square value of reasons for still birth/miscarriage of the respondents is found to be 206.589 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words reasons for still birth/miscarriage of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Methods Followed for Abortions

Tab 113

Types	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Traditional	44	5.0	117.732	0.000
Govt. PHC	260	32.5		
Village midwives	170	21.2		
Other	67	8.3		
Private hospitals	103	12.8		
Not replied	156	19.5		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 105

In case of methods followed in an emergency abortion it is revealed that 5% of the respondents use traditional methods whereas 32.5% use PHCs and 21.2% use village midwives. Further, 12% use private hospitals and 19% did not reply for the question

The chi-square value of methods followed in an emergency abortion of the respondents is found to be 117.732 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words methods followed in an emergency abortion of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Opinion about Traditional Methods of Abortion

Tab 114

Opinion	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Safe and secrete	260	32.5	336.879	0.000
Customary	23	2.8		
No side effects	34	4.2		
No faith in western termination	82	10.2		
Not replied	401	50.1		
Total	800	100		

Fig 106

It is revealed 32.5% of the respondents opined abortion with only traditional method is due to safe and secrete reason where as 2.8% said it is customary. Next, 4.2% said they chose traditional method because of absence of side effects while 10.2% said no faith in western type of termination whereas more than 50% did not reply.

*The chi-square value of reasons for preferring abortion with traditional method of the respondents is found to be 336.879 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words reasons for preferring abortion with traditional method of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

What Would Women do for Geniec Problems?

Tab 115

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Preference for natural healing	38	17.1	18.199	0.011
Visit traditional healers	21	9.4		
Visit private clinics only	49	22.0		
Visiting Govt. PHCs	20	9.0		
Home remedy	30	13.5		
Keep it secrete	10	4.5		
Meet lady health workers	27	12.1		
No such problems	27	12.1		
Total	222	100.0		

Fig 107

Regarding women health problems 17% of the respondents normally wait until it heals naturally while 9% said they visit traditional healers and 8% visits private clinics only. Next, 9% respondents would like to visit PHC where as 13.5% will do home remedy for any health problem. Next, 4.5% said they would like to keep it as a secrete while 12% gave other reason whereas 12 % of them said no such problems yet.

*The chi-square value of types of measure taken for geniec problems by the respondents are found to be 18.199 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words measures taken for the geniec problems by the respondents is statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Knowledge, Attitude and Treatment for Mental illness

Tab 116

Type	Frequency	%	X^2	P
Causes due to medical reasons	156	19.5	139.643	0.000
Cause due to fate/spirit	87	10.8		
Social isolation is the best	156	19.5		
No folk medicine; only western medicine can cure it	235	29.3		
Currently no medicine to treat mental illness	85	10.6		
All the above and emotion care is vital	56	7		
No idea	25	3.1		
Total	800	100		

Fig 108

It is revealed 19.5% of the respondents opined it causes due to medical reason whereas 10.8% of them said it causes due to fate or evil forces and 19.5% said mental patients need to be socially isolated and treat. Next, 29.3% of them said no folk medicine cannot cure mental illness and only western medicine should use to cure this illness. And 10% said no cure at all.

*The chi-square value knowledge, attitude and treatment for mental illness by the respondents is found to be 139.643 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words Knowledge, Attitude and Treatment for Mental illness by the respondents is statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondent.

Perception about STD Symptoms

Tab 117

Opinion	Frequency	%	X ²	P
White discharge	106	13.2	186.204	0.000
Gentile itching	100	12.5		
Paining of sex organs	125	15.1		
Bad smell of sex organs	107	13.3		
All the above	20	2.5		
Don' know	342	42.7		
Total	800	100		

Fig 109

Regarding perception about STD symptom, 13.2% of them respondents said white discharges while 12.5% of them said itching at gentiles where as 15% of them said paining of sex organs are the common system of STD. Next, 13% of them said bad smell of sex organs and 2.5% of them said all these are the symptoms whereas 42.7 % did not know anything about STD.

*The chi-square value of regarding perception about STD symptoms of the respondents is found to be 186.204 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words regarding perception about STD symptoms by the respondents is statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Heredity	67	8.3	37.026	0.000
Migration	149	18.6		
Breaching taboos	89	11.1		
Illicit sex	114	14.2		
Evil eyes	65	8.1		
Don't know	89	11.1		
Medical/ Biological	76	9.5		
Extra marital affairs and others	51	6.3		
Never heard	100	12.5		
Total	800	100		

Fig 110

Regarding reason for causing HIV/AIDS and STD 8% of the respondents said it is because of heredity while 18% said it is due to migration and 11% said it is because of breaching taboos. Next, 14% of them said it is due to having illicit sex whereas 8% said it is due to evil eyes and 9% said it is because of medical or biological reasons and 12.5% said they never heard about these health issues

*The chi-square value of concept about HIV/STD the respondents are found to be 37.026 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words reasons about sexual transmitted diseases by the respondents is statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Perception about AIDS/HIV Symptoms Tab 119

Symptoms	Frequency	%	X²	P
Weak, dizziness and Vomiting	17	2.1	244.171	0.000
Weak immune power/ pale/ tiredness	34	4.2		
Easily prone to other diseases	29	3.6		
Body pain/ can't do normal work	44	5.5		
All the above	39	4.8		
Don't know	615	76.8		
Other	22	2.7		
Total	800	100		

It is found that 2.1% of respondents opined weak, dizziness and vomiting are the common symptoms of HIV/AIDS. Next, 4.2% of them said weak immune power, pale and tiredness are the symptoms of HIV/AIDS while 3.6 % of them said patients easily prone to any type of diseases. Next, 5.5% opined regular body pain and problems in doing normal work whereas 4.8 % of them cited all the above symptoms where as majority (76.8%) of them did not know the exact symptoms while 2.7% of them gave other reasons.

*The chi-square value of perception about AIDS/HIV symptoms by the respondents is found to be 244.171 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words perception about AIDS/HIV symptoms in the respondents is significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Reasons for Diabetics and BP Problems

Tab 120

Reasons	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Heredity	56	7.0	200.576	0.000
Standard of living	121	15.1		
Humeral problem	45	5.6		
Diet issue	56	7.0		
Evil eyes /sorcery	89	11.1		
Age factors	300	37.5		
Biological /medical	112	14		
Don't know	21	2.6		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 111

Regarding reasons for Diabetics and BP 7% of the respondents opined it is because of heredity whereas 15% of them opined it is because of problems in standard of living and 5.6% of them said it is because of humeral problem. Next, of them 7% of them felt it is diet issue whereas 11% of them said it is due to evils eye or sorcery effect. Also 37.5% of them held it is because of age factor while 14% of them said it is due to the various biological reasons.

*The chi-square value of reasons for Diabetics and BP the of the respondents is found to be 200.576 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words reasons for Diabetics and BP by the respondents is statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Preference of Conducting Child Delivery

Tab 121

Response	Frequency	%	X²	P
Traditional midwife	45	5.6	434.072	0.000
Govt. PHCs	406	50.7		
Private hospitals	234	29.0		
NGO doctors	98	9.7		
No reply	10	1.2		
At home	7	.8		
Total	800	100		

Fig 112

Regarding preference of conducting child delivery 5.6% of the respondents prefer traditional midwife, whereas 50.7% prefer Govt. PHCs, while 29% prefers private hospitals. Next 9.7 % prefers NGO doctors and 1% people did not reply and 0.8 prefer at delivery at home.

*The chi-square value preference of conducting child delivery by the respondents is found to be 434.072 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words preference of conducting child delivery by the respondents is significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents .

Reasons for not Preferring Child Deliveries at Hospitals

Tab 122

Reasons	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Fear of pain/ operation	7	14.0	5.599	5.0
Cost factors	6	12.0		
No faith in the western treatment	7	14.0		
Prefer mid wife's only	16	32.0		
Distance factor	5	10.0		
Family traditions	6	12.0		
Other	3	6.0		
Total	50	100		

Fig 113

Regarding reasons for not having deliveries at hospitals 14% of the respondents held because of fear of pain/operation while 12 % of them said it's about cost factor whereas 14% said they don't have any faith in western treatment. Next 32% prefer mid wives while 10% respondent cited distance factor, whereas 12 % said age old traditions and 6% gave other reasons.

*The chi-square value reason for not having deliveries at hospitals by the respondents is found to be 5.599 and P value is higher than 0.05 is found to be highly insignificant.

* In other words reason for not having deliveries at hospitals by the respondents is insignificant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents .

Special Nutritional care During Pregnancy and after Tab 123

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Yes	341	42.6	229.519	0.000
No	402	50.2		
Up to certain extent	34	4.2		
Only during pregnancy period and not after	23	2.8		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 114

Regarding special nutritional care during pregnancy and after 42.6% of the respondents said they will offer special nutrition care to the pregnant and postpartum women whereas 50.2% of them said they are not using any such care and 4.2% of them said care will be taken up to certain period of pregnancy whereas 2.8% of them said only during pregnancy period and not after.

*The chi-square value of special nutritional care during pregnancy and after of the respondents is found to be 229.159 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words special care during pregnancy and after of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Factors Affecting Child Mortality and Morbidity Tab 124

Factors	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Medical reasons	108	13.5	55.863	0.000
Due to conjugal marriage	89	11.1		
Evil eye/sprits	161	20.1		
Heredity factors	155	19.3		
Lack of hygiene	161	20.1		
Absence of immunizations and others	70	8.7		
Don't know	56	7.0		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 115

It is revealed that 13.5% of the respondents said medical reason may be the prime causes for mortality or morbidity whereas 11% of them said it would be due to conjugal marriage. Next, 20% of them opined it is due to evil eye or spirit and 19% of them said it is due to heredity factors. Further, 20% of them said lack of hygiene and 8.7% of them felt it is happening due to the absence of immunizations where as 7% did not reply.

*The chi-square value of factors affecting child mortality and morbidity of the respondents is found to be 55.863 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant

* In other words of factors affecting child mortality and morbidity of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondent

Reasons for Death of Natal's and Neo-natal's Tab 125

Reasons	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Physiological problems	89	11.1	186.111	0.000
Fate/ deity curse/ evil sprits	124	15.5		
Lack of preventions	67	8.3		
Might be medical	298	37.2		
Household ecology	151	18.8		
Conjugal marriage	31	3.8		
No idea	40	5		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 116

Regarding death of natal's and neo-natal's 11% of the respondents said it might be due due to physiological problems whereas 15% of them said it is due to evil spirits. Next 8.3% of them said it is because of lack of prevention while 37.2% of them said due to medical reason and 18.8% of them said it might be due to bad household ecology whereas 3% of them opined it is due to conjugal marriage and 5% of them did not reply.

*The chi-square value for reasons for death of natal's and neo-natal's by the respondents is found to be 186.111 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words concept about reasons for death of natal's and neo-natal's by the respondents is significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Reasons for not feeding the Babies Immediately after the Birth

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Impurity of first milk	181	30.2	133.453	0.000
Age old customs	32	5.3		
Poor lactation	65	10.9		
Don't know its significance	80	13.3		
We feed babies	238	39.8		
Not replied	202	25.2		
Total	598	100.0		

Tab 126

Fig 117

Regarding reasons for not feeding babies immediately after the birth 30% of them held because of impurity of first milk whereas 5% said it is against the custom and 10% of them said it is due to poor lactation. Next 13% of them said they don't know the significance of the first milk while 39% of them said that they prefer to feed babies while 25.2% did not reply

*The chi-square value of reasons for not feeding babies immediately after the birth is found to be 133.453 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words reasons for not feeding babies immediately after the birth by the respondents is significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents

Time of Weaning of the Babies**Tab 127**

Duration	Frequency	%	X²	P
Between 3 and 4 months	229	28.6	131.052	0.000
Between 4 and 6 months	179	22.3		
Between 6 and 8 months	125	15.6		
Between 8 and 12 months	185	23.1		
Between 12 and 15 months	56	7.0		
No such norms	26	3.2		
Total	800	100.0		

About the time of weaning (feeding solid food) of the babies/children 28% of the respondents held it will be started between 3 and 4 months while 22% of them said it would be between 3 and 4 months and 15% of them said it would be between 6 and 8 months. Next, 23% said it would be between 8 and 12 months while 7% of them said it would- between 12 and 15 months while 3% sad no such norms.

*The chi-square value of weaning of the children by the respondents is found to be 131.052 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words weaning of the children by the respondents is significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Health Seeking Pattern for Natal, Neo natal and the Infants'

Tab 128

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Visiting faith healer or traditional healers	156	19.5	270.713	0.000
Home remedy	67	8.3		
Govt. PHC	307	38.3		
Private clinics	100	12.5		
Over the counter	46	5.7		
No special care	34	4.2		
As suggested by the elders of the family	37	4.6		
Consulting Health workers	21	2.6		
Other	32	4.0		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 118

It is revealed that 19.5% of the respondents would like to visit the faith healer, or traditional healers for Natal, Neo natal and Infants healthcare whereas 8.3% of them said they would do home remedy while 38.3% of them said Gov't PHC, will be contacted. Next 12.5% held they would visit private clinics only while 4.2% said no special care will be taken in case natal's and 4% opined decision will be taken as suggested by the elders of the family while 2% of the respondents said they would consult the health workers

*The chi-square value of health care pattern of natal, neo natal and infants of the respondents are found to be 270.713 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words health care pattern of the natal, neo natal and infants is statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents

Primary Requirements for Good health of the Children

Fig 129

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Nutritious food, clean water etc	145	18.1	181.315	0.000
Blessings of the Good/ fate	78	9.7		
Hygienic environment	180	22.5		
Regular vaccinations' and delivery at hospitals	94	11.7		
Rising with modern health care facilities	200	25.0		
Regular health checkups	60	7.5		
Other	29	3.6		
Don't know	14	1.7		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 119

Regarding primary requirements for good health of the children 18.1% of them said parents should provide nutritious food, clean water etc whereas 9.7% of the respondents said blessings of the God or fate is very essential. Next, 22.5% opined hygienic environment is must whereas 11.7% said regular vaccinations while 25% of them said rising children with the modern health care facilities. Next, 7% said regular health checkups are required and 3.6% gave some other response

*The chi-square value of primary requirements for good health of the children as felt by the samples is found to be 181.315 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words age primary requirements for good health of the children is significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Reasons for Not Immunizing the Children (if any)

Tab 130

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
It is against the custom	45	5.6	353.840	0.000
Neglect	78	9.7		
No idea	59	7.3		
Immunized	466	57.5		
Future side effects	78	9.7		
Cost factor s	42	5.2		
Not reply	32	4		
Total	800	100		

Fig 120

Regarding reasons for not immunizing their children 5.6% of the respondents held it is against customs while 9.7% said it is because of negligence. Next, 7.3% of them said no idea, where as 57.5 % have immunized their children while 9.7% of them felt immunizations cause future side effects. Next, 5.2% said it is because of the cost factors while 4% have not replied.

*The chi-square value reasons for not taking immunization for their children is found to be 353.840 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words reasons for not taking immunization for their children is significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Reasons for not taking Injections Tab 131

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Fear	45	5.6	288.186	0.000
Pain and side effects	70	8.7		
Cost factors	78	9.2		
We prefer Tablets only	166	20.7		
We prefer Injections	411	51.3		
Other	30	3.7		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 121

Regarding reasons for not preferring injections for any diseases 5.6% said fear while 8.7% of them said because of pain and side effects while 9.2% respondents said cost factor whereas 20.7% would, like to prefer tablets for any health problems while more than 51.3% prefer injections and 3.7% gave other reasons

*The chi-square value of reasons for not taking Injections for any diseases by the respondents is found to be 288.186 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words reasons for not taking Injections for any diseases by the respondents is statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Age Range of Sick Individuals who used Self-medication (at least one time)

Age range	Frequency	%	X ²	P
> 10(by care takers)	28	5.0	68.013	0.000
15-25	112	20.1		
25-35	168	30.2		
35-45	89	16.0		
45-55	103	18.5		
Above 55	56	10.0		
Total	556	100.0		

Tab 132

Fig 122

Regarding age range of sick individuals who used self-medication at least one time 20% of them belonging to the age group of 25-35 while 16% of them belong to the age group of 34-45 whereas 18% belonging to the age group of 45-55 whereas 10% of them are above the age of 55.

*The chi-square value age range of the sick individuals who used self-medication is found to be 68.013 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words age range sick individuals who used self-medication is significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Age of Sick Individuals who Sought care and Provider choice by Self-reported Symptoms (at least one time) Tab 133

Age range	Frequency	%	X ²	P
>10(by care takers)	4	0.9	172.760	0.000
15-25	15	3.3		
25-35	165	37.2		
35-45	157	35.4		
Above 45	102	23.0		
Total	443	100.0		

Fig 123

It is found that 0.9% belongs to the age group of below 10 years while 3% belongs to the age group of 15-25 where as 37% of them belongs to the age group of 25-35 while 35% of them between the age group of 35-45 and 23% of are above the age of 45.

*The chi-square value sick individuals who sought care and provider choice by self-reported symptoms is found to be 172.760 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words sick individuals who sought care and provider choice by self-reported symptoms has significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Duration Between falling Ill and getting Treatment

Duration	Frequency	%	X ²	P
We will visit right away	100	12.5	192.726	0.000
After 3or 4 days	321	40.1		
Wait and see technique	301	37.6		
When it get serious only	74	9.2		
Other	800	100.0		

Tab 134

Fig 124

Regarding the duration between onset of any disease and seeking proper treatment 12.5% of the respondents' claimed they would visit the doctor right away while 40% said after 2-3 days where as 37.6% said we follow 'wait and see' technique while 9.2% visits hospital only when it get serious .

*The chi-square value of duration between onset of any disease and seeking treatment by the respondents' is found to be 192.726 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words number of days usually respondents would like take to visit hospital/healer after fall ill has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents .

Cultural Attitude towards Hereditary Diseases

Tab 135

Factors	Frequency	%	X ²	P
It has no medicine at all	155	19.3	107.203	0.000
It is due to the side effects of modern medicines and pollutions	100	12.5		
Traditional medicine has a solution for hereditary diseases	143	17.8		
It is the fate of the patient	100	12.5		
Hereditary diseases are communicable	99	12.3		
Cosmology/ spirit effect	119	14.3		
Causes due to internal damages	78	9.2		
Don't know	6	0.75		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 125

Regarding cultural attitude(factors) towards hereditary diseases it is revealed that 19.3% of the respondents held it has no medicine at all while 12.5% it is due to the side effects of usage of the modern medicines. Next, 17.8% opined only traditional medicine has solutions for hereditary diseases. Next 12.5 % held the view that hereditary diseases are communicable and 9% held it causes due to sprits/evil eyes.

*The chi-square value regarding cultural attitude towards hereditary diseases of the respondents is found to be 107.203 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words concept regarding cultural attitude towards hereditary diseases is statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Concept about Congenital Deformities

Tab 136

Reasons	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Humeral imbalance	133	16.6	91.874	0.000
Superhuman causation or punishment for bad deed	145	18.1		
Due to internal damages	68	8.5		
Biological/ Medical	201	25.1		
Cause due to bad weather/food	202	25.2		
Conjugal marriage	46	5.7		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 126

For congenital deformities 16% of the respondents said it is because of humeral imbalance while 18% said congenital deformities happens due to the super human causations whereas 8% said it is because of internal damages. Next, 25% said it is because of medical reason while 25% of them said congenital deformities causes due to the bad weather/food where as 5% opined congenital deformities is because of conjugal marriage.

*The chi-square value concept about congenital deformities opined by the respondents is found to be 91.874 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words concept about congenital deformities is statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Concept about Communicable Diseases

Tab 137

Responses	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Which does not spread usually	69	8.6	170.861	0.000
Having spreading in nature	239	29.8		
Disease from which patients will die ultimately	67	8.3		
Long time Suffering	246	30.7		
No idea	57	7.1		
Depends on the disease	75	9.3		
No medicines for these disease	47	5.8		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 127

It is found that 8.6% of the respondents said communicable disease usually does not spread while 29.8% of the respondents said it spreads, whereas 8.3% of them said patients will die out of these disease and 30.7% of them said patients' will suffer for a long time from any type of communicable disease. Next 7% of them said no idea where as 9% said it depends on the types of the C. disease, whereas 5% said there is no medicine to cure this diseases.

*The chi-square value of concept about communicable diseaseof the respondents is found to be 170.861 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words concept about communicable diseaseof the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Concept about Non-Communicable Diseases Tab 138

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Having spreading in nature	89	11.1	229.815	0.000
It will not spread but some time it spreads	291	36.3		
Disease from which patients' dies ultimately	197	24.6		
Long time suffering	54	6.7		
No idea	82	10.2		
Depends on the types of the disease	80	10.0		
Can curable	7	0.87		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 128

Regarding Non-communicable disease 11% of the respondents opined it has spreading in nature while 36.3% of them said that it will not spread but some time it spreads and 24.6% of them said non-communicable disease means ultimate death. Next, 6.7 % of them said diseases long time suffering whereas 10% of them said no idea about these diseases.

*The chi-square value of concept about non-communicable diseases of the respondents is found to be 229.815 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words concept about non-communicable disease of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Reasons for Malnutrition, and Metabolic Disorders

Tab 139

Reasons	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Deity curse	95	11.8	138.977	0.000
Spirit or bad eye	89	11.1		
Heredity	109	13.6		
Physiology problems	290	36.0		
Due to pathogenic	109	13.7		
Bad weather/ contaminate food / water	78	9.7		
No idea	29	3.6		
Total	800	100		

Fig 129

It is revealed 11% of the respondents said malnutrition, and metabolic disorders causes due to deity curse while 11% of them said because of evil spirits while 13% said it is because of heredity, where as 36% opined it is due to the pathogeneses while 13% of them held it is due to the Physiology problems while 9% opined it might be because of bad weather, contaminate food /water and 3% said they don't have any idea.

*The chi-square value of knowledge about malnutrition, and metabolic disorders of the respondents is found to be 138.977 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words knowledge about malnutrition and metabolic disorders by the respondents is statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Reasons for Food poison, Lucko derma , Measles, Polio and Leprosy

Reasons	Food poison		Lucko derma		Measles		Polio		Leprosy		X ²	p
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Humeral imbalance	91	11.3	184	23	89	11.1	166	20.7	35	4.3	542.174	0.000
Superhuman causation	105	13.1	107	13.3	188	23.5	94	11.7	174	21.7		
Breaching taboo	103	12.8	89	11.1	75	9.3	90	11.2	150	18.7		
Pathogeneses	306	38.2	264	33	159	19.8	202	25.2	137	17.1		
Bad weather unhygienic food	157	19.6	126	15.7	269	33.6	230	28.7	185	23.1		
Other and don't know	38	4.7	30	3.7	20	2.5	18	2.2	119	14.8		
Total	800	100.0	800	100.0	800	100.0	800	100.0	800	100.0		

Tab 140

Fig 130

*The chi-square value of reasons for food poison, lucko derma , polio and leprosy as opined by the respondents is found to be 542.174 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words reasons for food poison , lucko derma , polio and leprosy as held by the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Pattern of Dental Hygiene Tab 141

Types	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Tooth pastes	321	40.1	209.135	0.000
Herbal sticks	167	20.8		
Home made	100	12.5		
Western type	54	6.75		
Either of the above	34	4.25		
Folk medicine	47	5.8		
Never visited dental clinic	77	9.6		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 131

For the dental hygiene it is revealed that 40% of the respondent uses toothpastes where as 20% use herbal sticks, and 12% use homemade items. Next, 6% use western type while 4% use any one of the mentioned. Next 5% said folk medicine, whereas 9% said they never visited dental clinic.

*The chi-square value for the pattern of dental hygiene of the respondents is found to be 209.135 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words pattern of dental hygiene is statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Treatment Pattern for Wounds and Injuries

Tab 142

Types	Frequency	%	X ²	P
With herbal plants	139	17.3	307.886	0.000
At hospitals only	400	50		
Home remedy	89	11.1		
Traditional healers	67	8.3		
Depends	49	6.1		
Natural healing	33	4.1		
Other	23	2.8		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 132

Regarding wounds and injuries 17% of them will be treated with herbals plants whereas majority of them said (50%) they would visit hospitals for treatment. Next, 11% of them said home remedy will be the best while 8% of them said traditional healers will be approached but 6% of them said treatment depends, on the severity of the diseases and 4% of the respondents said wait for natural healing and 2% of them gave other reasons.

*The chi-square value treatment pattern for wounds and injuries of the respondents is found to be 307.886 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words treatment pattern for wounds and injuriesof the samples is statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Classification on Knowledge Diseases and Illness **Tab 143**

Types	Typhoid		Malaria		Jaundice		Cholera		Mental Problems		X ²	P
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	F	%		
Disease	178	22.2	220	27.5	227	28.3	143	17.8	211	26.3	154.065	0.000
Illness	173	21.6	167	20.8	227	28.3	216	27	258	32.2		
May be either/	181	22.6	123	15.3	110	13.7	218	27.2	128	16		
Both disease and illness	168	21	140	17.5	114	14.2	112	14	132	16.5		
No idea	100	12.5	150	18.7	122	15.2	111	13.8	71	8.8		
Total	800	100	800	100	800	100	800	100	800	100		

Fig 133

*The chi-square value of diseases or illness classification knowledge of the respondents is found to be 154.065 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words diseases classification knowledge by the respondents is statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Classify the following Disease into Communicable & Non-communicable Diseases

Type	Communicable		Non-communicable		X ²	P
Disease	f	%		%		
Malaria	56	12.3	78	22.4	32.382	0.000
Typhoid	68	15.0	45	12.9		
Cholera	56	12.3	76	21.9		
Gastric	87	19.2	46	13.2		
Bone problems	35	7.7	23	6.6		
Heart problems	43	9.4	22	6.3		
Scabies	38	8.3	21	6.0		
Mental Illness	36	7.9	34	9.7		
Don know	34	7.5	21	6.0		
Total	453	100.0	347	100.0		

Tab 144

Fig 134

*The chi-square value of classification between communicable and non-communicable disease by the respondents is found to be 32.382 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words knowledge about communicable and non-communicable disease classifications of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents .

Reasons for Typhoid, Jaundice, Diarrhea, Cholera and Malaria Diseases

Reasons	Typhoid		Jaundice		Diarrhea		Cholera		Malaria		X ²	p
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Humeral imbalance	107	13.3	156	19.5	102	12.7	65	8.1	137	17.1	192.523	0.000
Superhuman causation	98	12.2	106	13.2	98	12.2	64	8	94	11.7		
Breaching taboo	83	10.3	88	11	98	12.2	87	10.8	88	11		
Pathogeneses/unhygienic	305	38.1	311	38.8	261	32.6	311	38.8	267	33.3		
Bad climate, water and food	201	25.1	107	13.3	239	29.8	270	33.7	195	24.3		
Others and don't know	6	0.7	32	4	2	0.2	3	0.3	19	2.3		
Total	800	100.0	800	100.0	800	100.0	800	100.0	800	100.0		

Tab 144

Fig 135

*The chi-square value of concept reasons for the onset of Typhoid, Jaundice, Diarrhea, Cholera and Malaria Diseases by the respondents is found to be 192.523 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words concept about Reasons for Typhoid, Jaundice, Diarrhea, Cholera and Malaria Diseases of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Selection of Treatment Pattern for Communicable Diseases

Diseases	Typhoid		Jaundice		Cholera		Malaria		X ²	P
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Medical system									479.920	0.000
Ayurvedic	112	14	215	26.8	106	13.2	67	8.3		
Traditional medicines	185	23.1	247	30.0	230	28.7	197	24.6		
Homeopathy	56	7.0	55	6.8	64	8.0	88	11.0		
Faith healers/ worshipping deity	57	7.1	43	5.3	12	1.5	41	5.1		
Home medication	34	4.2	32	4	22	2.7	20	2.5		
Allopathic	356	44.5	208	26.0	366	45.7	387	48.3		
Total	800	100.0	800	100.0	800	100.0	800	100.0		

Tab 145

Fig 136

*The chi-square value of treatment pattern for the selected communicable diseases by the respondents is found to be 479.920 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words concept about pattern of treatment for the certain communicable diseases of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Treatment Plan for the Selected Non communicable Diseases

Types/code	Nothing		Home remedy		Traditional		Over the counter		Govt. PHC		Ayurvedic		Faith healers		Both traditional and western	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Bone related	4	30.7	15	16.3	22	18.1	34	22.3	44	25.1	36	23.8	3	6.9	13	24.5
Gastritis	2	15.3	18	19.5	22	18.1	21	13.8	15	8.5	18	11.9	7	16.2	6	11.3
Respiratory disease	0		0		16	13.2	17	11.1	34	19.4	21	13.9	6	14.0	10	18.8
Pain/aches	4	30.7	17	18.4	12	9.9	27	17.7	33	18.8	28	18.5	9	20.0	11	20.7
ENT	0		19	20.6	28	23.1	25	16.4	38	21.7	29	19.2	9	20.0	10	18.8
Worm infection	3	23.0	23	25	21	17.3	28	18.4	11	6.2	19	12.5	9	20.0	3	5.6
Total	13	100.0	92	100.0	121	100	152	100.0	175	100.0	151	100.0	43	100.0	53	100.0

X^2 39.305 P 0.034

Tab 146

Fig 137

*The chi-square value of treatment plan for the selected non communicable diseases by the respondents is found to be 39.305 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words treatment plan for the selected non communicable by the respondents is significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Preventive Measures for Communicable Diseases

Measure	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Satisfying deity cosmology/natural powers	56	7.0	197.195	0.000
Health rituals and festivals	78	9.7		
Focusing self hygiene	132	16.5		
Maintaining hygienic conditions	254	31.7		
Proper health education	200	25.0		
Using safe food and water	67	8.3		
Don t know	13	1.6		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 147

Fig 138

Regarding preventive measure, 7% of the respondents held the view that communicable diseases can be avoided satisfying deity while 9.7% of them said by celebrating festivals regularly, 16.5% of them said more preventive measures is must while 31.7% of them said maintaining hygienic conditions, whereas 25 % of them alleged due to health education. Next, 8.3% of them said using safe food and water and 1% of them said they don't have any idea.

*The chi-square value of preventive measure for communicable disease as replied by the respondents is found to be 197.195 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words concept about preventive measure for communicable disease by the respondents is significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents

How Certain Diseases Affects On Human Body

Type	Morphology of the body		Physiology of the body		Anatomy of the body		Either Anatomy or Physiology		Morphology and Physiology		X ²	P
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%				
Disease											585.324	0.000
Cholera	89	14.4	107	19.2	87	14.5	67	10.4	45	10.6		
Typhoid	77	12.4	78	14.0	86	14.4	56	8.6	108	13.5		
Jaundice	86	13.9	76	13.6	134	22.4	78	12.1	198	24.7		
Malaria,	67	10.8	88	15.8	124	20.8	67	10.4	156	19.5		
TB,	182	22.7	108	19.4	98	16.4	89	13.8	78	18.4		
Mental illness	88	14.2	98	17.6	67	11.2	287	44.5	67	15.8		
Leprosy	211	34.1	245	30.0	204	25.5	156	19.5	148	18.5		
Total	800	100.0	800	100.0	800	100.0	800	100.0	800	100.0		

Tab 148

Fig 139

*The chi-square value of knowledge about disease and its affect on the body parts as replied by the respondents is found to be 585.324 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words concept about knowledge about disease and its affect on the body parts by the respondents is significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents

Cultural Concept of Health Rituals

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
It is a procedure to satisfy deities/spirits	123	15.2	43.413	0.000
Women cannot perform health rituals	105	13.1		
All village people has to observe norms and sanctity	81	10.1		
Higher caste people only has to perform rituals	161	20.1		
Low caste people are not supposed to perform rituals	87	10.8		
Evil forces will not entre in to villages after rites	67	8.3		
Health rituals are untrue/ fake/ un believable	176	22.0		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 149

Fig 140

It is revealed that 15.2% of the respondents opined it is a procedure to satisfy the health deities whereas 13% of them opined women cannot perform rites while 10 % of them opined during ritual rites all village people have to observe norms and sanctity. Next 20% of them opined higher caste people only has to do rites whereas 10% said lower caste people are not supposed to participate in any health rites while 8% opined evil forces will not entre in to villages after rites.

*The chi-square value of cultural norms on health rituals of the respondents is found to be 43.413 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words cultural concept of health rituals of the samples has significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Concept about Medical Pluralism

Concept	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Availability of more than one type of medicines	145	18.2	180.728	0.000
Using different medical systems at a time	102	12.7		
Availability of different medical care in a given place	95	11.8		
Different therapeutic treatments	58	7.2		
Don't know	400	50.0		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 150

Fig 141

It is evident that 18.2% of the respondents said medical pluralism means availability more than one type of medicine while 12.7% of them said using different medical systems at a time where as 11.8% of them said availability of different medical care system in a given place while 7% of them said different therapeutic treatment whereas majority of them(50%) said no idea about this

The chi-square value of concept about medical, pluralism of the respondents is found to be 180.728 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words of concept about medical, pluralism of the respondents statistically significant influence over the health behavior and medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Reasons for Using Different Medical Systems

Reasons	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Advised by the concerned healer	62	16.3	45.660	0.000
Just to take a chance	79	20.8		
Advised by the village/ family elders	103	27.1		
Previous good experiences	41	10.8		
Low cost and speedy recovery	78	20.5		
Hoping either one may cure the problem	16	4.2		
Total	379*	100.0		

*only 379 samples have used more than one type of medical system

Tab 151

Fig 138

Reasons for using different medical systems at a time it is found 16.3% of the respondents said as advised by the traditional healers and faith healers while, 20.8% of the respondents said that they are taking a chance and 27% of them said as advised by the village or family elders. Next 10.8% of them said previous good experiences is the reason why they prefer to use more than one type of medicinal system while 20.5% of them said as advised by the medical doctors and 4% said hoping either one may cure the problem.

*The chi-square value of reasons for using different medical systems at a time by the respondents is found to be 45.660 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words of reasons for using different medical systems at a time by the respondents has statistically significant influence over the health behavior and medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Pluralistic Treatment opted by the Suffered Respondents

Tab 152

Disease	Typhoid		Jaundice		Cholera		Malaria		Viral fever		X ²	P
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Ayurvedic - and Homeopathy	10	11.2	13	14.0	19	16.5	3	3.6	33	22.1	51.648	0.000
Ayurvedic-and Allopathic	18	20.2	19	20.4	24	21.0	13	15.8	41	27.5		
Folk medicine and Allopathic	13	14.6	24	25.8	17	14.7	25	30.4	24	16.1		
Homeopathy and Allopathic	19	21.3	15	16.1	27	23.4	18	22.0	19	12.7		
Sidda and Allopathic	14	15.7	17	18.2	19	16.5	21	25.6	26	17.4		
Allopathic and Unani	15	16.8	15	16.1	9	7.8	4	4.7	6	4.0		
Total	89	100.0	93	100.0	115	100.0	84	100.0	149	100.0		

The chi-square value for pluralistic treatment opted by the suffered respondents by the respondents is found to be 51.648 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words of pluralistic treatment opted by the suffered respondents has statistically significant influence over the health behavior and medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents

Fig 139

Opinion about Quality of Medical Pluralism Available

Opinion	Frequency	%	X ²	P
More options for the patients'	80	22.1	48.545	0.000
No such quality in certain medical systems	43	11.3		
Quality is satisfied in Homeopathy and Unani	80	21.1		
Sidda and Ayurvedic systems are the best	85	22.4		
Very costly/ chance of more side effects	50	13.1		
Folk medicines are very reliable	21	5.5		
No idea	20	5.2		
Total	379	100		

Tab 153

Fig 140

Regarding opinion about quality of medical pluralism available 22% of the respondents said more options for the patients is possible while 11% of them said no such quality in certain system of medical care. Next, of them 21% of them are happy with the Quality of the Homeopathy and Ayurvedic while 22.4% of them Sidda and Unani systems are the best while 5% of them said traditional medicines are only reliable whereas 5.2% of them said no idea at all.

*The chi-square value of opinion about quality of medical pluralism available by the respondents is found to be 48.545 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words opinion about quality of medical pluralism by the respondents has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Deaitls about Cooperation among Different Types of Healthcare Providers

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Cooperation is more	167	20.8	56.257	0.000
No such cooperation	197	24.6		
They are misguiding the patients	94	11.7		
More fake healers in the name of medical pluralism	87	10.8		
Professional rivalry is more	85	10.5		
Inside adjustments to get more money from the patients	64	8.0		
No idea	106	13.2		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 154

Fig 141

Regarding cooperation among different types of healthcare providers 20.8% of the respondents admitted cooperation is more among the different types of healthcare providers in the area while 24.6% of them said no such cooperation where as 11.7% of the respondents said different healers misguiding the patients. Next 10.8% said today more fake doctors in the name of medial pluralism.

*The chi-square value of opinion about cooperation among different types of healthcare providers by the respondents is found to be 56.257 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words opinion about cooperation among different types of healthcare providers by the respondents in the given area has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents

Opinion about Ethno medicine and the Health Care

Tab 155

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
It is reliable but disappearing day by day.	233	29.1	76.669	0.000
We have many other good medical systems	202	25.2		
Ethno medicine is our asset and only hope for the poor	50	6.25		
It is a part of our culture from time immemorial	148	18.5		
Time has changed we should use bio medicines not the traditional medicines	167	20.8		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 142

Regarding opinion about ethno medicine and their impact on health 29.1% of the respondents held that it is really good but disappearing day by day while 25.2% of them said it still exist we need to preserve ethno medicines whereas 6.2% of them said ethno medicine is our asset and only hope for the poor. Next 18.5% of them said it is a part of our culture 20% opined time has changed we should use bio medicines for quick heal.

*The chi-square value of opinion about ethno medicine and their impact on health the respondents is found to be 76.669 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words opinion about of opinion about ethno medicine and their impact has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents

Opinion on Traditional and Faith Healers

Tab 156

Opinion	Frequency	%	X ²	P
We completely and strongly respect the healers	167	20.8	122.618	0.000
They are the experts in healing any health problems	167	20.8		
Traditional healers are skilled and experienced	100	12.5		
We partly believe these healers	122	15.2		
Some healers are unskilled and not so useful	67	8.3		
Some disease can be curable only by these healers	20	2.5		
Healers need some sort of training	57	7.1		
No idea	50	6.2		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 143

*The chi-square value of opinion about faith healers and their impact on health by the respondents is found to be 122.618 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words opinion about of opinion about faith healers has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Perception about Impact of Supernatural/Cosmology on Health

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
It affects on the general health status	125	15.0	113.725	0.000
We believe it; but we cannot say more.	78	9.7		
Up to certain extent they effects on health	113	14.1		
It is responsible for specific diseases/illness and we should respect them	70	8.6		
We ignore because no proof for their existence	100	12.5		
We don't believe at all	314	39.2		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 157

Fig 144

Among the respondents 15% are partially believe in supernatural/cosmology and effects on human health while 9.7% of them said they believe but can't say more. Next 14% said up to the certain extent thee powers effects on the human health while 8.6% of them opined it is responsible for various diseases/illness and we should respect them while 12.5% of them opined to ignore such facts.

*The chi-square value of respondents believe on supernatural/cosmology etc and their impact on human health found to be 113.725 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words respondents believe on supernatural/cosmology etc and their impact on health has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Reasons for not Accepting the Modern Medicine for Health Problems

Reasons	Frequency	%	X ²	P
No faith in the modern medicine	39	10.8	48.270	0.000
More side effects	76	21.0		
Future effects on the general health	42	11.6		
Against our culture/ tradition	78	21.6		
Bad previous experiences	25	6.9		
Suggested by the friends/local healers	19	5.2		
Costly/ difficult to use	48	13.2		
Not adjustable to our body	34	9.4		
Total	361*	100		

*Only 361 people found not Accepting Modern Medicine

Tab 158

Fig 145

Regarding reasons for not accepting modern medical treatment for diseases 10.8% of the respondents said they don't have any faith in modern medicine while 21% of them said it has more side effects. Next, 11.6% said it may effects on health in the future whereas 21.6% said it is against our tradition and 6.9% of them said not because of bad previous experiences. Next, 5.2% said as suggested by the friends and local healers while 13% of them said it is costly while 9.4% said it does not suits to our body nature.

*The chi-square value of reasons for not accepting modern medical treatment for diseases/illness by the respondents is found to be 48.270 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words reasons for not accepting modern medical treatment for diseases/illness by the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior and medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Reasons for Accepting Only the Folk Medicines Tab 159

Responses	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Quick healing	49	13.5	91.057	0.000
Low cost and no side effects	94	26.0		
Easy to use and easily available	56	15.5		
Highly reliable	37	10.2		
All the above	34	9.4		
Using from the generations	42	11.6		
At par with our culture/tradition	24	6.6		
Just followed others	10	2.7		
No other options	13	3.6		
Total	361	100.0		

Fig 146

About reasons for accepting only traditional/folk medicine 13% of the respondents said it is because of quick healing while 26% of them said because of low cost and absence of any side effects, whereas 15.5% of them said it is easy to use and easily available. Next 10.2% of them said it is highly reliable whereas 11.6% said it is being used from the generations and 6.6% of them said it suits to our culture and traditions.

*The chi-square value of reasons for accepting only traditional/folk medicine by the respondents is found to be 91.057 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words reasons for accepting only traditional/folk medicine by the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior and medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Reasons for Visiting Traditional Healer/Faith Healers for Treatment

Reasons	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Reliable and low cost	45	12.3	53.525	0.000
tradition and custom	54	14.8		
Healers are very friendly/ the experts	67	18.4		
Easy to access and fast curing	47	12.9		
Just because of family pressure	35	9.6		
Healer knows our problems better	78	21.4		
Suggested by others	35	9.6		
Other	3	0.37		
Total	364	100.0		

Tab 160

Fig 147

Regarding reasons for visiting traditional healer/faith healers for treatment it is found that 12.3% of the respondents said because of low cost and reliable while 14.8% said it is family tradition while 18.4% said healers are very friendly. Next, 12.9% of them said easy to access, and fast curing whereas 9.6% of them said because of family pressure. Next, 21.4% of them said healers are the good experts and known to us from a long time while 9.6% of them said it is because as suggested by the friends and the relatives.

*The chi-square value of reasons for visiting traditional healer/faith healer for treatment by the respondents is found to be 53.525 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words reasons for visiting only traditional healer/faith healer for treatment by the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Reasons for Not-Visiting Traditional Healers /Faith Healers

Reasons	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Not capable/ irrational healing procedure	70	16.0	297.680	0.000
No confidence on traditional healers	300	68.0		
We just don't like	28	6.4		
Previous bad experience	28	6.4		
Suggested by the others	8	1.8		
Other	2	0.45		
Total	436*	100.0		

Only 436* samples are found not-visiting traditional healers

Tab 161

Fig 148

Regarding reasons for not-visiting to traditional healers /faith healers 16% of the respondents said traditional healers are not the real experts whereas 68% of them said no confidence on traditional healers while 6% of them said we don't like traditional healers. Next, 6% of them said because of previous bad experiences and 1% of the respondents said as suggested by the others.

*The chi-square value of reasons for not visiting traditional healer/faith healers for treatment by the respondents is found to be 297.680 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words reasons for not visiting traditional healer/faith healers for treatment by the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Reasons for Accepting Allopathic Treatment only for Specific Diseases

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Speedy recovery	180	41.0	181.636	0.000
Guarantee of cure	45	10.2		
No medicine in traditional system for some diseases	67	15.2		
More reliable and no side effects	21	4.7		
As suggested by the friends/ relatives	87	19.8		
Just followed others	36	8.2		
Other	3	0.68		
Total	439	100.0		

Tab 162

Fig 149

It is evident that 41% of the respondents said because of speedy recovery they opt allopathic treatment whereas 10.2% said allopathic has a guarantee of cure while 15.2% of them said no medicine in traditional system for some diseases. Next, 19% of them said as suggested by the friends/relatives whereas 4% said it is more reliable and no side effects. Next 8% of them said they opt allopathic treatment as suggested by the friends and the relatives.

*The chi-square value of reasons for accepting allopathic treatment only for specific diseases by the respondents is found to be 181.636 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words the chi-square value of reasons for accepting allopathic treatment only for specific diseases by the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior and medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Would You Take Precautions Once You Identified Any Health Problem/s

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Yes: of course	131	16.3	106.225	0.000
No such measures	135	16.8		
Only some time	168	21.0		
Partial precautions will be taken	201	25.1		
If it is feasible we will take	147	18.3		
Other	18	2.25		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 163

Fig 150

It is revealed that 16.3% of the respondents said they would take precautions as suggested by the Doctors/ traditional healers while 16.8% of the respondents said they don't take such precautions. Next, 21% of them said they take precautions only sometime while 25% of them take partial precautions while 18% of them opined precautions will be taken if it is feasible while 2% of them said they don't just bother.

*The chi-square value of concept about precautions once identified any health problems by the respondents is found to be 106.225 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

*In other words concept about precautions by the respondents once identified any health problems has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents

Section IV

Influences of Socio-Economic Status on Health Seeking Behavior

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Economic status effects very much	200	25.0	179.484	0.000
Social status does affects	201	25.1		
Caste plays an imperative role	195	24.3		
Gender counts s a lot	56	7.0		
Social network is a crucial issue	58	7.2		
Level of education is most vital	67	8.3		
All the above	23	2.8		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 164

Fig 151

It is revealed that 51% of the respondents admitted influences of social economic status whereas 24.3% of the respondents said caste plays a lot. Next, 7% felt gender counts a lot. Next, 7.2% felt social network is a crucial issue while 8.3% of them felt level of education is most vital.

*The chi-square value of respondent's opinion about influences of socio-economic status over health seeking behavior is found to be 179.484 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words of respondents opinion about influences of socio-economic status over health seeking behavior statistically significant influence over the health behavior and medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Percentage Distribution of Treatment Option by Caste, Religion and Age Characteristics

Characteristics	Subgroup	Treatment option								Total	X ²	p
		Folk medicine		Western		Home/Self medication		Ayurvedic/homeopathy				
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%			
Caste	SC/ST	93	45.1	44	21.3	37	17.8	32	15.5	206	11.595	0.03
	OBC	70	24.6	136	47.8	54	19.0	24	8.4	284		
	Others	61	19.6	180	63.3	49	17.2	20	6.4	310		
	Total									800		
Religion	Hindu	229	29.6	379	49.0	78	10.1	86	11.1	772	703.606	0.00
	Muslim	8	33.3	12	50.0	2	8.3	2	8.3	24		
	Others	1	25.0	2	50.0	0	----	1	25.0	4		
	Total									800		
Age	20-35	45	26.6	107	63.3	10	5.8	7	3.5	169	150.139	0.00
	30-45	123	24.2	345	68.0	30	5.9	10	1.9	508		
	45-65	43	35.0	66	53.6	6	4.8	8	5.2	123		
	Total									800		

Tab 165

Fig 152

*The chi-square value of respondent's treatments option based on caste, religion and age is found to be as mentioned above and P value of all is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

* In other words of respondent's opinion about treatment option based on caste, religion and age has statistical significance influence over the health behavior and medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Percentage Distribution of Factors Determining Treatment Patterns of the Respondents

Factors Determining Treatment Patterns of the Respondents Tab.3

Variables →	Determining Factors								X ²	P
	Income and Occupation		Education		Gender		Social networks			
Treatment Patterns	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Western	110	49.1	222	60.4	22	50.0	101	61.2	21.081	0.000
Folk medicine	14	6.25	45	12.2	6	13.6	10	6.0		
Ayurvedic	35	15.6	32	8.7	4	9.0	11	6.6		
Homeopathy	15	6.6	25	6.8	5	11.3	12	7.2		
Home remedy	14	6.2	11	2.9	2	4.5	8	4.8		
Sidda and Unani	24	10.7	9	2.4	3	6.8	11	6.6		
Other	22	9.8	23	9.1	2	4.5	12	5.7		
Total	224	100.0	367	100.0	44	100.0	165	100.0		

Tab 166

Fig 153

The chi-square value of distribution factors determining treatment patterns of the respondents about causing illness/diseases is found to be 36.823 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant

In other words distribution factors determining treatment patterns of the respondents causing illness/diseases has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Economic Group Wise Opinion about Causing Illness/Diseases

Category	Low		Middle class		High		Elites		X ²	P
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Cosmology	124	31.2	23	8.2	10	10.3	3	11.5	163.943	0.000
Pathogenic	47	11.8	127	45.3	46	47.4	16	61.5		
Unhygienic	59	14.8	60	21.4	21	21.6	3	11.5		
Lack of good food , water	78	19.6	30	10.7	11	11.3	2	7.6		
Humeral imbalance	89	22.4	40	14.2	9	9.2	2	7.6		
Total	397	100.0	280	100.0	97	100.0	26	100.0		

Tab 167

Fig 154

The chi-square value of Socio -economic group wise opinion about causing illness/diseases of the respondents is found to be 163.943 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant

In other words concept socio -economic group wise opinion about causing illness/diseases of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the concept of health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents

Caste wise Opinion about Causing Illness/Diseases

Category	SC and ST		OBC		Others		Converters		X ²	P
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Humeral	45	21.7	84	18.5	16	12.1	2	25.0	43.408	0.000
Pathogenic	47	22.7	189	41.7	37	28.0	2	25.0		
Super natural	38	18.3	74	16.3	33	25.0	2	25.0		
Unhygienic	41	19.8	58	12.8	16	12.1	1	12.5		
Either above	36	17.3	48	10.5	30	22.7	1	12.5		
Total	207	100.0	453	100.0	132	100.0	8	100.0		

Tab 168

Fig 155

The chi-square value of caste wise opinion of the respondents is found to be 43.408 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words caste wise of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents

Percentage Distribution of Treatment Factors by Health Seeking Behavior

	Treatment Patterns	Folk		Western		Self/Home		ISM		Total	X ²	P
		F	%	f	%	f	%	f	%			
											53.430	0.000
Reasons	Severity of the problem	28	14.7	146	76.8	6	3.1	10	5.2	190		
	Types of health issue	56	28.5	118	60.2	6	3.0	16	8.1	196		
	Cost factor	100	55.5	71	39.4	2	1.1	7	3.4	180		
	Quality care	59	34.0	100	57.4	4	2.2	11	6.3	174		
	Health beliefs	40	66.7	18	30.0	1	1.6	1	1.6	60		
	Total									800		
Decision making	Followed family tradition	110	48.2	58	25.4	5	2.1	55	24.1	228	7.028	0.000
	Own decision	89	28.3	192	61.1	6	1.9	27	8.5	314		
	Followed others	85	33.0	140	54.8	8	3.1	25	9.6	258		
	Total									800		

Tab 169

Fig 156

The chi-square value of percentage distribution of treatment factors by health seeking behavior of the respondents is as above mentioned and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words percentage distribution of treatment factors by health seeking behavior of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents

Co-relation between Educational level and the Treatment Option

Edu. Level	Illiterates		Primary		Higher primary		High school		College		X ²	p
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Folk medicine	45	26.0	29	20.5	21	13.4	26	17.4	38	20.9	76.943	0.000
Ayurvedic	34	19.6	43	30.4	31	19.8	30	20.1	32	17.6		
Western	19	10.9	27	19.1	43	27.5	40	26.8	78	43.0		
Homeopathy	32	18.4	19	13.4	33	21.1	21	14.0	19	10.4		
Sidda and Unani	43	24.8	23	16.3	28	17.9	32	21.4	14	7.7		
Total	173	100	141	100	156	100	149	100	181	100		

Tab 170

Fig 157

The chi-square value of co-relation between educational level and the treatment option of the respondents is 76.943 as above and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words co-relation between educational level and the treatment option of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the concept of health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Association between Gender and the Treatment - Options

		Treatment Seeking Options				X ²	p
Priority		Female		Male			
		f	%	f	%		
First choice	PHC	49	12.9	27	20.0	38.739	0.000
	Traditional	87	23.0	32	23.7		
	Faith healers	34	8.9	22	16.2		
	Home remedy	87	23.0	28	20.7		
	Either	34	8.9	23	17.0		
	Over the counter	87	23.0	3	2.2		
	Total		378	100	135		
Second choice	PHC	64	32	28	32.1	22.308	0.000
	Traditional	59	29.5	20	22.9		
	Faith healers	24	12	10	11.4		
	Home remedy	37	18.5	26	29.8		
	Over the counter	16	8	3	3.44		
Total		200	100	87	100		

Tab 171

Fig 158

The chi-square value of association between gender and the treatment - options of the respondents is as above mentioned and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words association between gender and the treatment - options of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the concept of health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents .

Different Occupational Status Groups and the System of Medicine Used

Type	Primary		Secondary		Tertiary		X ²	P
	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Folk medicine	51	16.7	54	18.6	17	8.2	117.982	0.000
Ayuevdic	56	18.3	31	10.6	35	17.0		
Western	43	14.0	56	19.3	94	45.8		
Self/home remedy	78	25.5	34	11.7	19	9.2		
Homeopathy	55	18.0	89	30.6	27	13.1		
Other	22	7.2	26	8.9	13	6.3		
Total	305	100.0	290	100.0	205	100.0		

Tab 172

Fig 159

The chi-square value of different occupational status groups and the system of medicine they used by the respondents is 117.987 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words co-relation about association between gender and the treatment - options of the has got a statistically significant influence over the concept of health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Effect of Other Determining Factors on Health Seeking Behavior Patterns of the Respondents

Factors	Determining Factors										x ²	P
	Social Support Networks		Social Environments		Physical Environments		Personal Health Practices		Quality of Health care Services			
Category	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Western	35	35	26	18.5	35	25.7	15	8.8	105	41.3	116.791	0.000
Folk medicine	28	28	53	37.8	36	26.4	74	43.5	47	18.5		
ISM	10	10	23	16.4	24	17.6	44	25.8	25	9.8		
Over the counter	10	10	25	17.8	15	11.0	12	7.0	45	17.7		
Home remedy	11	11	6	4.2	22	16.1	18	10.5	24	9.4		
Faith healer	4	4	4	2.8	2	1.4	4	2.3	4	1.5		
Other	2	2	3	2.1	2	1.4	3	1.7	2	0.7		
Total	100	100	140	100	136	100	170	100	254	100		

Tab 173

Fig 160

The chi-square value of effect of other determining factors on health seeking behavior patterns as opined by the respondents of is 116.791 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words effect of other determining factors on health seeking behavior patterns as opined by the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Economics Group wise Opinion about Medical Pluralism

Category	Low		Medium		High		Elites		X ²	P
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
It is more useful to the poor patients	203	51.1	90	32.1	25	25.7	8	30.7	71.120	0.000
More options to the patients	58	14.6	54	19.2	24	24.7	6	23.0		
Rate of success of healing will be more	78	19.6	67	23.9	10	10.3	5	19.2		
All the above	40	10.0	34	12.1	27	27.8	5	19.2		
May lead low quality	8	2.01	24	8.5	8	8.2	1	3.8		
Create more confusion to the patients	10	2.5	11	3.9	2	2.0	1	3.8		
Total	397	100.0	280	100.0	97	100.0	26	100.0		

Tab 174

Fig 161

The chi-square value of economic group wise opinion about medical pluralism of the respondents is found to be 71.120 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words economic group wise opinion about medical pluralism of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents .

Economics group-wise opinion about Indian system of Medicine

Category	Elites		Middle class		Lower middle class		Poor		X ²	P
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Reliable and safe	13	12.2	78	28.0	70	34.6	32	14.9	178.888	0.000
Guarantee healing/ easily accessible	11	10.3	43	15.4	63	31.1	57	26.6		
Low cost and affordable to the poor	9	8.4	100	35.9	44	21.7	75	35.0		
More side effects	27	25.4	30	10.7	10	4.9	30	14.0		
It is only for minor health problems	46	43.3	28	10.0	15	7.4	20	9.3		
Total	106	100	278	100	202	100	214	100		

Tab 175

Fig 162

The chi-square value of economics group wise opinion about Indian system of medicine of the respondents is found to be 178.888 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words economic group wise opinion about Indian system of medicine of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Economics group wise Opinion about of Modern Health care

Category	Low		Middle		High		Elites		X ²	P
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Reliable, safe, and easily available	25	6,2	54	19.2	32	33.0	13	52.0	164.328	0.000
More side effects ; only useful in emergency	132	33.2	89	31.8	13	13.4	8	30.8		
It is very costly; poor cant access	221	55.6	105	37.5	23	23.7	2	7.7		
Govt. should provide generic medicines at low cost	10	4.7	30	11.4	20	30,0	2	7.7		
All the above	9	2.2	2	0.7	9	9.2	1	,01		
Total	397	100.0	280	100.0	97	100.0	26	100.0		

Tab 176

The chi-square value of economic group wise opinion about Indian system of medicine of the respondents is found to be 164.328 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words economic group wise opinion about Indian system of medicine of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents.

Relationship between Preventive Measures and the Educational Status of the Respondents. Tab 177

Educational Status →	Illiterates		Primary		Higher primary and high school		College		Neo literates		X ²	p
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Good food/shelter	45	21.4	81	28.9	56	21.1	9	32.1	5	29.4	66.371	0.000
Good health practices and hygienic conditions	32	15.2	63	22.5	44	16.6	9	32.1	3	17.6		
Worshiping the deity blessings/divine rites etc	56	26.5	30	10.7	27	10.1	2	7.1	2	11.7		
Immunizations/quality health care	38	18.0	55	19.6	80	30.1	6	21.4	3	17.6		
Upgrading health education	25	12.0	48	17.1	47	17.7	1	3.5	3	17.6		
Other	14	6.7	3	1.0	11	4.1	1	3.5	1	5.8		
Total	210	100.0	280	100.0	265	100.0	28	100.0	17	100.0		

Fig 163

The chi-square value of relationship between preventive measures and educational status of the respondents is found to be 66.731 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words relationship b/n preventive measures and educational status of the respondents has got statistically significant influence over the concept of health behavior and medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents

Generations and Preferential System of Medical Care Tab 178

Type	First generations		Second generations		X ²	P
	f	%	f	%		
Folk medicine	47	15.3	24	13.1	19.791	0.00
Ayurvedic	53	17.2	25	13.7		
Western	85	27.6	78	42.8		
Self/ home remedy	40	13.0	10	5.4		
Homeopathy	30	9.7	19	10.4		
Other	22	7.1	26	14.2		
Total	307	100.0	182	100.0		

Fig 164

It is found that 15% of the first generation and 13% of the second generation respondents felt to use folk medicine whereas 17% first generation and 13.7% second generations would like to use Ayurvedic system. Next 27% of first generations and 42% of second generations would like to use western medicines while 13% of first generations and 5% of second generations would like to use self/ homemade medicines. Next 9% of first generations and 19% of second generations use homeopathy, 7% of first generations and 14% of second generations would like to use other type of medical care system.

The chi-square value of generations and preferential system of medical care used found to be 19.791 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words generations and preferential system of medical care used has statistically significant influence over the concept of health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Villagers Opinion about Private Clinics/Hospitals Tab 179

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Service is good but very costly	207	25.8	37.907	0.000
Doctors are good than PHC doctors and very friendly	133	16.6		
Distance factors and the health illiteracy are the barriers	126	15.7		
Staff are rude and unfriendly	76	9.5		
Govt. should improved PHCs	153	19.1		
More formalities and not for the poor	100	12.5		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 165

Opinion about private clinics/hospitals 25.8% of the respondents said service is very costly; cont affordable while 16% of them said Private Doctors are friendly than PHC doctors while 15.7% of them problems of Distance factors and the health illiteracy are the barriers. Next 9.5% of them said staffs are rude and unfriendly while 19.1% of them said Govt. should improve PHC/SC like private hospitals whereas 12.5% said private hospitals have more formalities and not for the poor.

The chi-square value of opinion about opinion about private hospitals by the respondents found to be 37.907 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words opinion about private hospitals has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Why Common People Cannot Access Modern Health Care Facility Today?

Reasons	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Poverty and health illiteracy	502	62.7	596.044	0.000
Cost and distance factors	104	13		
Lack of awareness	28	3.5		
Domination by the rich people	100	12.5		
Socio cultural factors	25	3.1		
Over medicalization	31	3.8		
All the above	10	1.2		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 180

Fig 166

Regarding failure in accessing modern health care facility 62% of the respondents opined modern medical care is too costly while 13% of them said poverty or illiteracy as hurdles in accessing modern health care facility. Next 3.5% said lack of awareness while 12.5% said western medicine is dominated by the rich people whereas 3% said due to social and cultural factors whereas 3.8% of them felt Doctors are very greedy while 1.2% of them admitted all these reasons

The chi-square value of opinion about accessing modern health care facility by the respondents is found to be 596.044 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words opinion about not accessing modern health care facility has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

The Longer the Period of Illness, Greater are the Chance of Searching for Meanings Related to the Original Cause of the Illness and Suitable Treatment (YES/NO)

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Yes	212	26.5	105.980	0.000
No	278	34.7		
May be	134	16.7		
Don't know	276	34.5		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 181

Fig 167

The chi-square value of opinion about longer the period of illness and original cause by the respondents is found to be 105.980 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words opinion about longer the period of illness and original cause has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Quality of a Best Allopathic Doctor Tab 182

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Should be culturally sensitive	143	17.8	78.097	0.000
Nice behavior/ friendly	212	26.5		
Should be available on time	200	25.0		
Should charge less	109	13.6		
Should be an expertise	58	7.2		
All the above	78	9.7		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 168

Regarding qualities of best allopathic doctor 17% of the respondents said he/she should be culturally sensitive, while 26% said doctors need friendly behavior and 25% of them said doctors should be easily available while 13% of them said doctor should charge less. Next 7% of them said should be an expertise in the field while 9% of them said all the above.

The chi-square value of opinion about qualities best allopathic doctor as opined by the respondents is found to be 78.097 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words opinion about qualities of an allopathic doctor has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

The Qualities of any Best Medicine should be

Tab 183

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Should be easy to use	221	27.6	78.839	0.000
Must have no side effects	105	13.4		
Should be bitter less and no pain	78	9.7		
Should have quick healing power	134	16.7		
Must be low cost and easily available	200	25.0		
All the above	62	7.7		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 169

Opinion regarding best medicine 27.6% of the respondents said that should be easy to use, 13.4% of them said there should be no side effects while 9.7% of them said that should be bitter less and painless, 16.7% of them said that should have quick healing power. Next, 25% of them said must be low cost and easily available and 7% of them said best medicine should have all these qualities

The chi-square value of opinion about qualities of a best medicine as opined by the respondents is found to be 78.839 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words opinion about qualities of the best medicine of the respondents has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Opinion about Medicalization

Tab 184

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Yes today it is very rampant	400	50,0	395.981	0.000
Community must aware of this development	107	13.3		
Poor may not access to modern health because of this	79	9.8		
Poor are being exploited by this	32	4.0		
Short route to earn more money by the Doctors	161	20.1		
Other	21	2.6		
Total	800	100.0		

Fig 170

Regarding concept about Medicalization 50% of the respondents admitted rampant Medicalization exists in the society today while 13.3% said up to certain extent Medicalization exists today whereas 9% expressed poor may not access to modern health because of this Next, 4% of the respondents felt poor are being exploited by this while 20% of them felt short route to earn more money by the Doctors

The chi-square value of concept about the Medicalization of the respondents is found to be 395.981 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words concept about Medicalization has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Affects of Caste on Health care in Rural Parts Tab 185

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Discrimination at PHC/SC because of caste factors	67	8.3	165.502	0.000
Discrimination by the traditional healers	66	8.2		
Health exclusion based on caste and class	157	19.6		
Discrimination by the health workers/ NGOs	154	19.2		
No such experience	262	32.7		
Don't know	94	11.7		
Total	800	100		

Fig 171

The chi-square value of opinion caste factor and healthcare choice found to be 165.502 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words opinion about caste factor and healthcare choice has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Respondent's Opinion about Primacy health centre/Sub centers

Opinion	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Long waiting hours	101	12.6	154.901	.000
Distance factor	57	7.12		
Absence of the Doctors	100	12.5		
No upgraded facilities	134	16.7		
No specialist Doctors	89	11.1		
Rude behavior of the staff	83	10.3		
No quality treatment	52	6.5		
Non availability of free medicines	60	7.5		
All the above	56	7.0		
No problems at PHCs	68	8.5		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 186

Fig 172

The chi-square value of respondent's opinion about PHC/SC found to be 154.901 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words of respondent's opinion about PHC/SC has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Purpose for Visiting Local PHC/SCs

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Free Vaccinations	66	8.25	158.183	0.000
Health education	38	4.75		
Neo-natal care	88	11.0		
Baby Delivery	168	21.0		
Accidents/ injures	100	12.5		
Either or all the above	55	6.87		
Treatment for minor diseases	34	4.25		
To get free medicines	156	19.5		
Treatment for major disease s	28	3.5		
Not visited yet	48	6.0		
Other	19	2.37		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 187

Fig 173

The chi-square value of purpose to visiting village PHC/SCs found to be 158.183 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words of respondent's opinion purpose to visiting village PHC/SC has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Are you Really Benefiting from he PHC/SCs

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Not to great extinct	200	25.0	39.633	0.000
A lot of bad experiences	133	16.2		
No quality treatment	55	6.7		
We need private hospitals	80	10.0		
Yes we are getting	110	13.5		
Not visited yet	218	27.2		
Other	4	0.5		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 188

Fig 174

For this enquiry 25% of them said not getting much help form the PHCs while 16% of them felt a lot of bad experiences while 6% of the respondents felt no quality treatment whereas 10% of them said we need more private hospitals in rural areas whereas 13.5% of them are getting good service and 27.2% of have not visited yet

The chi-square value of opinion about use of Govt. PHC for health problems found to be 39.633 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words opinion about the usage of Govt. PHCs by the respondents has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Are you accepting treatment at PHC with Willingness?

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Accepting with full confidence	300	37.5	71.832	0.000
Uncomfortable with PHC but half mindedly they are accepting	143	17.8		
Don like but only by the family pressure	78	9.7		
We have no options	173	21.6		
Private hospitals are better than Govt.	91	11.3		
No reply	15	1.8		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 189

Fig 175

Regarding accepting treatment at village PHCs 37% of the respondents are accepting with full confidence whereas 17% said they have accepted half mindedly while 9% of them said because of family pressure they are accepting allopathic medicines while 21.6% of the respondents said no option before them. Next, 11.3% said private hospital is better than Govt.PHC while, 1% did not reply .

The chi-square value of opinion accepting treatment at village PHC with willingness found to be 71.832 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words opinion willingness in accepting treatment at village PHCs has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Aware Functioning of Village Health and Sanitation committee

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Doing good	134	16.7	58.429	0.000
Somewhat OK	68	8.5		
Satisfactory	231	28.8		
Not satisfactory	89	11.1		
Not working at all	122	15.2		
No idea	156	19.5		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 190

Fig 176

Regarding functioning of village health and sanitation committee 16% of them said committee is doing good while 8% of them said committee is doing somewhat ok and 28% of them said committee work is satisfactory. Next, 11% of them were not satisfactory while 15% said not working at all and 19.5% were not aware of such committee in vial area

The chi-square value of opinion about functioning of village health and sanitation committee found to be 58.429 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words opinion about functioning of village health and sanitation committee has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Opinion about Govt. Effort for Quality Rural Health Care

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Lack of health infrastructure,	96	12.0	81.298	0.000
Lack of political will	154	19.2		
Bureaucratic disinterest	128	16.0		
Unnecessary delay and corruption	156	19.5		
Neglect about the rural poor	167	20.8		
Caste based politics	67	8.3		
Other	32	4.0		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 191

Fig 177

The chi-square value of opinion about opinion about Govt. effort found to be 81.298 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words opinion about opinion about Govt. Effort has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Opinion about Establishment of More Multi-Doctors Centers at Village Locations

Opinion	Frequency	%	χ^2	P
Good idea	351	43.8	310.027	0.000
Not a good idea	134	16.7		
May be a good idea but it spoils our traditional medicine system	267	33.3		
It may affects on our customs	40	5.0		
Other	8	1.0		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 192

Fig 178

Opinion about establishment of more multi-doctors centers at village locations 43.8% of the respondents said it is a good idea while 16.7% of them said not a good idea and 33.3% of them opined may be a good idea but it spoils our traditional medicinal system whereas 5% of them said it may affects on the rural culture whereas 1% gave other reasons.

The chi-square value of opinion about establishment of more multi-doctors centers at village locations found to be 310.027 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words opinion about establishment of more multi-doctors centers at village locations has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Cultural barriers in Introducing New Health Care system in Rural Areas

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Developmental behavior of the people	156	19.5	69.884	0.000
Beliefs on customs and traditions	229	28.6		
Ignorance about health care issues	95	11.8		
Negative opinion about western medicine system	145	18.1		
Health culture and health behavior	175	21.8		
Total	800	100		

Tab 193

Fig 179

Regarding cultural barriers in introducing new health care in rural area 19.5% of the respondents said developmental behavior of the rural people is the main barrier while 28.6% of them said age old beliefs and traditions where as 11.8% of them said general ignorance on health issues. Next, 18% of them felt negative opinion about western medicine system by the rural people is the main reason while 21.8 % of them said old health culture and health behavior are the factors are hindering in introducing new health care in rural area.

The chi-square value of factors hindering in introducing new health care in rural area as opined by the respondents is found to be 69.884 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words factors hindering in introducing new health care in rural as felt by the respondents area has significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Reasons for Changing Healthcare-Seeking Practices of the People over the Last 5 –10 years

Reasons	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Society is fast changing	100	12,5	50.230	0.000
More health awareness today	145	18.1		
Health care has become a personnel issue	100	12.5		
Growing medical pluralism	130	16.2		
Because of various Govt. programmes	110	13.7		
Improved economic status of the people	105	13.1		
Because of over Medicalizations	100	12.5		
No idea	30	3.7		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 194

Fig 180

The chi-square value opinion about changing healthcare-seeking practices of the people is found to be 50.230 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words opinion about changing healthcare-seeking practices of the people has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Perceptions' Of the Traditional Healers

Different Kinds of Local Healers Involved in the Study

Tab 195

Types		Sex		Total	X ²	P
		Male	Female			
Herbalists	f	6	4	10	10.203	0.037
	%	60.0	40.0			
Faith healers	f	7	5	12		
	%	58.3	41.6			
Bone setters	f	5	2	7		
	%	71.4	28.5			
Special healers	f	9	3	12		
	%	75.0	25.0			
Midwife	f	0	6	6		
	%	0	100.0			
Total	f	27	20	47		
	%	57.4	42.5	100.00		

Fig 181

Regarding composition of studied healers there were 60% male herbalists and 40% female herbalists. Regarding faith healers 58.3% were male and 41% were the female faith healers. Whereas in case of bone setters, 71% were male 28% were female. There were 75% special male healers and 25% female healers

The chi-square value of compositions of the studied different healers found to be 10.203 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words composition of studied different healers has statistically significant influence in seeking various perceptions of the healers for the current study.

Traditional Healers' Concept about causing Diseases/ illness

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Humeral imbalance	12	25.5	4.354	0.499
Cosmology/ evil eyes/ sorcery	5	10.6		
Immoral behavior	11	23.4		
Breaching taboo/ deity curse	7	14.8		
Pathogenic agents	9	19.1		
Didn't reply	3	6.3		
Total	47	100		

Tab 196

Fig 182

Regarding traditional healer's belief about factors causing various diseases 25% of them felt it is due to the humeral imbalance while 10% of them said it is due to the cosmology or evil eyes or sorcery. Next 23% of them said it might be caused due to the immoral behavior whereas 19% of them said it is due to breaching taboo or curse of a deity and 19% of them opined it is due to pathogenesis and 6.3% of them did not reply.

The chi-square value of concept about diseases and illness of the respondents is found to be 4.354 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words concept about Disease /Illness among the healers has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues.

Reasons for Performing Healing Rituals to Cure Disease /Illness

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
To neutralize the evil effects	10	21.2	2.725	0.909
To neutralize pathogenic agents	7	14.8		
Patching up/ recreating disrupted cultural order	7	14.8		
To cure the disease/ illness permanently	5	10.6		
Create humeral balance	5	10.6		
Rebalancing of the bodily equilibrium	6	12.7		
All the above	4	8.5		
No reply	3	6.3		
Total	47	100.0		

Tab 197

Fig 183

The chi-square value of by reasons for performing healing rituals to cure disease /Illness by respondents is found to be 2.725 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words reasons for performing healing rituals to cure disease /illness as felt by the respondents has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues.

Techniques involved in Diagnosing Disease and Illness?

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Based on experience/physical examinations/pulse etc	15	31.9	3.454	0.485
Based on patients' illness narrations'	10	21.2		
Studying etiology of the problems	6	12.7		
Intuitions/ boon of the God	5	10.6		
Professional secret	11	23.4		
Total	47	100		

Tab 198

Fig 184

Regarding diagnose techniques 31.9% of the healers will do based on their previous experience physical examinations, reading pulse etc while 21.2% of them, said based on patients' illness narrations while 12.7% of them said it is by studying etiology whereas 10.6% of them said by intuitions/ a boon of God, whereas 23% of tem said it is a professional secret.

The chi-square value of regarding diagnose techniques of the healers is found to be 3.454 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words diagnose techniques of the studied healers has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Components of Healing Techniques Tab 199

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Chanting/ magic/ holy water/ etc	13	27.6	1.514	0.959
Through various ritual's	9	19.1		
Worshiping deity/ sprites	7	14.8		
Either above	7	14.8		
Using herbal extracts	8	17.0		
Using mineral/ animal extracts	6	12.7		
Professional secrete	8	17.0		
Total	47	100.0		

Fig 185

Regarding healing techniques 27.6% of the healers said through chanting black magic/chanting/holy water etc while 19% of them said through various rituals. Next 14.8% of them said through worshiping deity or spirits where as 14.8% of them said either of the above. Next, 17 % of them said through administering herbal extracts while 12.7% of the healers use mineral/animal extracts whereas 17% of them said it is a professional secrete

The chi-square value regarding component of healing techniques of the healers is found to be 1.514 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words components of healing techniques have statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Opinion about Scientific Training for Traditional Healers

Tab 200

Type	Frequency	%	χ^2	P
We are ready to take training	5	10.6	6.742	0.150
We don't like any training	10	21.5		
We know everything; nothing new to learn	15	31.9		
It is against our family tradition	14	29.7		
Professional sanity will spoil	3	6.3		
Total	47	100.0		

Fig 186

Regarding Govt. sponsored scientific training for the healers to 10.6% of the healers are ready to take training where as 21.5% of the healers are not ready take training while 31.9% of the healers said nothing new to learn through training while 29.7% of them healers said it is against our tradition while 6.3% of them said professional sanctity will spoil because of the new training

The chi-square value of regarding scientific training for the respondents is found to be 6.742 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words scientific training for the healers has statistically significance influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Opinion about Western Medical system

Tab 201

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Against our culture and ethics	10	21.2	5.288	0.381
Traditional medicine is the best one	2	4.2		
More side effects in western medicine	13	27.6		
Heavy cost/ and unreliable	8	17.0		
No guarantee of healing	6	12.7		
We prefer western medicine in some cases only	8	17.0		
Total	47	100		

Fig 187

Regarding opinion about allopathic medical care 21.2% of them said it is against our culture and ethics while 4.2% of them said traditional medicine is the best one, where as 27.6% of them opined it has more side effects. Next, 17% of them felt western medicines is costly and unreliable while 12%of them said no guarantee in case of western medicine as 17 % of them said that they prefer allopathic medical care in certain some cases.

The chi-square value of regarding opinion about allopathic medical care of the healers is found to be 5.288 and P value is more than 0.5 is found to be highly insignificant.

In other words regarding opinion about allopathic medical care has no statistically significance over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

At Which Stage You Would Suggest the Patients' to Seek western Health Care Treatment **Tab 202**

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
If we can't heal it	13	27.6	4.167	0.384
When the patient is serious	9	19.0		
When it is out of our control	10	21.0		
Depends on the health problem	12	25.5		
We don't advise to get modern medicine in any case	3	6.3		
Total	47	100.0		

Fig 188

Regarding advise to get modern health care to the patients' 27.6% healers said if we can't heal it we advise to them to any hospitals, whereas 19% of the healers said when the patient get serious we advise to visit western type while 21% of them said when it goes out of our control we advise the patients to visit hospitals whereas 25.5% of them said it depends on the health problem and 6% of the healers said that they don't advise in any case to visit hospitals.

The chi-square value regarding advice to get modern health care to the patients by the healers is found to be 4.167 and P value is more than 0.05 is highly insignificant.

In other words advice to get modern health care to the patients by the healers has statistically insignificant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Concept about Safety of Folk Medicines (FM)

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
We never come across any safety issues yet	13	27.6	5.768	0.329
Indigenous medicines are really safe	10	21.2		
We are using it from the generations	11	23.4		
It is not a standardized medicine	4	8.5		
When compare to western it is safe	6	12.7		
No reply	3	6.3		
Total	47	100		

Tab 203

Fig 189

Regarding concept about safety of indigenous medicine 27.6% of the healers said they never come across such safety problems yet while 21.2 % of them opined indigenous medicines are relay safe 23.4% of them felt FM are using from the generations while 8.5% of the healers admitted it is not a standardized medicine where as 6.3% of them opined when compare to western medicine it is safe whereas 6% of them did not reply

The chi-square value for Concept about safety of folk Medicines (IM) by the respondents is found to be 5.768 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words Concept about safety of folk Medicines (IM) has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Opinion about Medical Pluralism

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Good for patients'/ more options	7	14.8	4.719	0.694
Healing chances are more	9	19.1		
Affordable and accessible	11	23.4		
Ayurvedic and homeopathy is good	5	10.6		
Some types of medicine are fake and dangerous	3	6.3		
Confusing for the patients	5	10.6		
All the above	4	8.5		
It is not a good phenomena	3	6.3		
Total	47	100		

Tab 204

Fig 190

Regarding opinion about medical pluralism 14% of the respondent said it is good for patients' in getting more options for treatment while 19% opined healing rates are more due to medical pluralism while 23.4% of them said it is affordable and accessible where as 10.6 % opined Ayurveda and Homeopathy are really good choice. Next 6.3% of them said some medicines are fake and dangerous while 10.6 % said medical pluralism leads to confusing to the patients' while 6% of them said it is not a good phenomenon.

The chi-square value for concept about medical pluralism by the respondents is found to be 4.719 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words Concept about medical pluralism has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Opinion about Degeneration of Traditional Medicines(TM)

Tab 205

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Domination of western medicines	13	27.6	15.598	0.004
People are not aware of its significance of TM	7	14.8		
Due to slow healing/ sometime no healing in TM	5	10.6		
Strong medical pluralism	11	23.0		
Absence of Government supports	5	10.6		
All the above	4	8.5		
Not degenerating	2	4.2		
Total	47	100		

Fig 191

Regarding degenerating of traditional medicinal system is 27.6% of the healers alleged it is due to domination of the western medicinal system while 14% of them said people are not aware of its significance whereas 10% of them held success rate is very slow in TM. Next, 23 % of them opined because of presence of strong medical pluralism while 10 % of them felt absence of government supports, where as 4 % of the healers defended it is not degenerating.

The chi-square of concept about degenerating of traditional medicine by the respondents is found to be 15.598 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words concept about degenerating of traditional medicine of the faith healers has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

What are the most common problems and Diseases you treat in the last Two years?

Code

Most common A+++	Common A++	Very frequent A*****	Rare A	Less common B
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Answer

Type	Ranking
Malaria	A+++
Cholera and Typhoid	A++
Dengue.	A
Jaundice	A*****
Gynec problems	A*****
Mental illness	B
Common fever	A+++
Cold and cough	A+++
Diharrioa	A++
Non communicable	A

Tab 206

According to the studied healers Malaria and Common fever are mostly common in the study area whereas Cholera, Typhoid and Diharrioa are just common. Also healers opined Jaundice Gynec problems **are** very frequent in the study areawhereas Dengue is rare and also they opined Mental illness is less common in the villages.

Faith Healers Opinion about Reasons for Causing Various Disease/Illness

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Humeral imbalance	2	11.1	2.195	0.700
Cosmology	2	11.1		
Immoral behavior	3	16.6		
Breaching taboo	4	22.2		
Pathogenesis	7	38.8		
Other	18	100		

Fig 192

For this enquiry 11% of the healers opined it is due to the humeral imbalance while 11% of them said it is due to the cosmology, whereas 16.6% of them said it is due to immoral behavior. Next, 22.2% said breaching taboo is the reason and 38.8% of them said it is due to the pathogenesis.

The chi-square value of opinion of the healers about causing various disease/illness is found to be 2.195 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words healers' opinion about causes for the various disease/illness has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the rural people.

Perceptions' of the Allopathic Doctors (PHC)

Common health Problems of Rurals' Visiting PHCs

Tab 207

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Injures	7	18.4	1.426	0.921
Minor problems	6	15.7		
For free medicines	7	18.4		
Delivery cases	8	21.0		
Vaccinations	6	18.4		
As referral	3	7.8		
Total	37	100.0		

Fig 193

Common health reasons for visiting PHC found that 18% people visit PHC for injury treatment while 15% of the people visit for minor health problems, whereas 18% of them visit PHC to get free medicines, and 21% of them felt for baby delivery cases. Further, 18% of the rural people visit nearby PHCs for free vaccinations and 7% of people visit for referral.

The chi-square value for Common reasons for visiting PHCs by the respondents is found to be 0.921 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words Common reasons for visiting PHCs have statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

Reasons for Not Visiting Rural People to PHCs

Tab 208

Reasons	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Lack of knowledge	5	13.5	4.743	0.448
People will visit PHCs when problems gets serious	13	35.1		
Socio cultural reasons	4	10.8		
They visit private clinics only	8	21.6		
Lack of facilities in PHCs	3	8.1		
People prefer traditional medicines only	4	10.8		
Total	37	100.0		

Fig 194

For this enquiry more than 13% of the PHC staff opined it is due to the lack of knowledge while 35% of them said usually people will visit PHCs when health problems gets serious only while 10.8% of them held the view that it is due to the socio-cultural reasons and 21% of them said today rurals’ visit private clinics only. Next, 8% of them held absence of good facilities at village PHC/SC and 10% of them viewed rurals prefer traditional medicines only.

The chi-square value of the opinion of the staffs about visiting rural people to the PHCs is found to be 4.743 and P value is higher than 0.05 is found to be highly insignificant.

In other words opinion of the staffs (PHC) about visiting rural people to the PHCs has no statistical significance.

Opinion about Traditional Medicine(TM)

Tab 209

Reasons	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Not safe and more side effects	10	27.0	2.337	0.674
Suites for the some minor health problems only	11	29.7		
Integration of both TM and western medicine has more advantages	6	16.2		
More research study is required in TM	4	10.8		
All the above	6	16.2		
Total	37	100.0		

Fig 195

Regarding opinion about traditional medicine 27% of the PHC staff said TM is not safe and has more side effects while 29% of them said TM is just for some minor health problems while 16% of them said integration of both TM and western medicine has more advantages in rural areas while 10% of them said more research is required while 16% of them accepted all these facts.

The chi-square value of opinion about traditional medicine by the respondents is found to be 2.337 and P value is less higher than 0.05 is found to be highly insignificant.

In other words opinion about traditional medicine has statistically not significant.

Opinion about Training for the Indigenous Practitioners

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Internship with the Doctors	12	34.2	3.513	0.476
Special resident training programme	9	23.6		
Training in PHCs	8	21.0		
All the above	5	13.1		
Other	3	7.8		
Total	37	100.0		

Tab 210

Fig 196

Regarding possible training for the indigenous practitioners 34% of them opined internship with the western doctors may be a good idea while 23.6% of them said special resident training programme is required for the traditional healers whereas 21% of them said training in nearby PHCs may be arranged while 13% of them supported all these ideas.

The chi-square value regarding possible training for the indigenous practitioners by the PHC staff is found to be 3.513 and P value is higher than 0.476 is found to be highly insignificant.

In other words possible training for the indigenous practitioners as opined by the PHC staff has statistically no significance.

Opinion about New Referral System between the Hospitals and the Traditional Healers

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Yes; it is must	11	28.9	4.542	0.103
No need	15	42.1		
Not a bad idea but need more authentication	8	21.0		
Some time it is required	3	7.8		
Total	37	100.0		

Tab 211

Fig 197

Regarding referral system between the hospital and the traditional healers 28% of the PHC staff said it is must, while 42% of them said no need whereas 21% of them opined it is not a bad idea but need more authentication and 7% of them said some time it is highly required.

The chi-square value for referral system between hospitals and the traditional healers as opined by the respondents is found to be 4.542 and P value is higher than 0.05 is found to be highly insignificant.

In other words referral system between the hospital and the traditional healers has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

COMMUNITY PERCEPTION

Community Opinion about Socio-Cultural Barriers in Introducing Modern Medicine

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Mindset of the rurals' has not changed yet	7	14.0	3.320	0.768
Old age health beliefs/ culture/ behavior	7	14.0		
Income and occupation also important	4	8.5		
Taboos in caste and religion	12	25.5		
Strong influence of customs and traditions	10	21.2		
New social network counts a lot	5	10.6		
Level of education counts a lot	5	10.2		
Total	50	100.0		

Tab 212

Fig 198

The chi-square value for community opinion about barriers in introducing modern medicine is found to be 3.320 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words community opinion about barriers in introducing modern medicine has no statistical significance.

Community Opinion about Rurals' Poor Health Status Tab 213

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Poor health infrastructure in the rural parts	9	18.0	0.433	0.994
Low level health education and participation	7	14.0		
Government ignorance and corruption	10	20.0		
Lack of fundamental facilities	9	18.0		
Poverty and illiteracy	8	16.0		
No idea	7	14.0		
Total	50	100.0		

Fig 199

Regarding reasons poor health status 18% of the community members said poor health infrastructure in rural parts is the main reason while 14% of them said it is due to low level of health education and participation while 20% opined Govt. ignorance and corruption while 18% of them said poor health status is because of strong existence of age old health beliefs /culture/ behavior whereas 16% of them opined poverty and illiteracy are the main reasons for poor health status of the rural population.

The chi-square value of the respondent's opinion about reasons poor health status in rural areas is found to be 0.433 and P value is higher than 0.05 is found to be highly insignificant

In other words community opinion about reasons poor health status in the rural areas has no statistical significance

Community Perception about the Western Medical System

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Establishment of more multi-doctor centers at rural locations	12	24.0	7.948	0.094
PHC must be provided with all facilities	21	42.0		
Govt, should provide support for medical pluralism	5	10.0		
Western Doctors should be cultural sensitive	5	10.0		
Modern health education through folk media is must	7	14.0		
Total	50	100		

Tab 214

Fig 200

Regarding western medical care for the rurals 24% of the community members opined establishment of more multi-doctor centers at central locations would be a good idea whereas 42% of them said PHC must be upgraded while 10 % said Govt, should provide support for the medical pluralism while 10% of them said western Doctors should be more cultural sensitive where as 14% said modern health education through folk media is a must.

The chi-square value of community opinion about western medical system for the rurals is found to be 7.948 and P value is higher than 0.05 is found to be highly insignificant.

In other words community opinion about western medical system for the rural has no statistically significant influence.

Category	Teachers		Advocates		Panchyathmembers		Doctors		Others		X ²	P
	f	%	f	%	f	%	F	%	f	%		
Traditional medicine is affordable and cultural sensitive but safety is in question	3	17.6	1	16.0	2	20.0	3	37.5	2	22.2	8.732	0.006
Local healers need training with the PHC staff	2	11.7	2	33.3	3	30.0	1	12.5	1	11.1		
Sidda and Unani system need more focus	3	17.6	1	0.1	3	30.0	2	24.5	2	22.2		
Traditional medicine must be integrated with the modern medicine	3	17.6	1	0.1	1	10.0	1	12.5	2	22.2		
Homeopathy and Ayurvveidc need more research for the standardization	5	29.4	1	0.1	1	10.0	1	12.5	1	11.1		
Other	1	5.8	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	11.1		
Total	17	100	6	100	10	100	8	100	9	100		

Fig 201

The chi-square value for communities’ opinion about Indian system of medicine for the rural is found to be 8.732 and P value is higher than 0.05 is found to be highly insignificant.

In other words communities’ opinion about Indian system of medicine has no statistically significance influence over the health issues of the rural population.

Community opinion about Medical Pluralism

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Good development and very helpful to the poor	12	24.0	3.161	0.531
Issues of side effects and untrained practitioners	13	26.0		
Quality and safety is a vital issue	13	26.0		
More options for the patients with affordability	7	14.0		
Govt and NGO work to preserve traditional medicines	5	10.0		
Total	50	100.0		

Tab 216

Fig 201

The chi-square value for communities opinion about Indian system of medicine for the rural is found to be 3.161 and P value more than 0,05 is found to be highly insignificant.

In other words community opinion about medical pluralism has nostatistically significant influence over rural health issues.

Reasons for Changing Medical Practice, Ideology and Treatment among Rurals

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Success rate of different system of medicines	13	26.0	3.369	0.643
Rapid medical pluralism at the door steps	11	22.0		
Awareness of side effects of all types of medicines	9	18.0		
Improvements in social economic status	6	12.0		
Effect of mass media	7	14.0		
Awareness about Medicalizations	4	8.0		
Total	50	100.0		

Tab 217

Fig 202

For this enquiry 26% of them opined it is because of success rate of different system of medicines where as 22% of them opined rapid medical pluralism is the main reason. Next, 18% of them said strong awareness of side effects of all types of medicines while 12% of them said improvements in social economic statuses is the vital reason. Next 14% of them opined it is due to the effect of mass media while 8% of them said it is due to over Medicalizations.

The chi-square value for community's opinion for changing health practice among the rurals' found to be 3.369 and P value is higher than 0.05 is found to be highly insignificant.

In other words community opinion about changing health practice due to medical pluralisms for the rurals has statistically insignificant influence on rurals health issue.

Community opinion about New Health Policies for Rural People

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Efforts should be made to devise new systems or patterns of institutions by which the access of rurals for modern health can be enhanced.	21	42.0	3.207	0.361
Provision for synthesis of Indian systems of medicine with western medicine	10	20.0		
Proper planning, implementing and monitoring of rural health programmes is required	9	18.0		
Must be a lot of scope for the decentralization of health care needs	10	20.0%		
Total	50	100.0		

Tab 218

Fig 203

Regarding community opinion about new health policies for the rural people 42% of them opined efforts should be made to devise new systems of institutions for accessing modern health care while 20% opined synthesis of Indian systems of medicine like with the rural system and modern medicine should be done whereas 18 % of them said all proper planning, implementing and monitoring of rural health programmes is must while 20% inclined towards decentralization.

The chi-square value for community opinion about new health policies for the rural people is found to be 3.207 and P value is higher than 0.05 is found to be highly insignificant.

In other words community opinion about new health policies for the rural people or the rural has statistically no significance over the rurals' health issue.

Opinion about NGOs working in the Villages

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
They are doing some good work	67	8.3	92.224	0.000
They are focusing only on health education	245	30.6		
There work is not so effective	201	25.1		
They are focusing only on rich people	87	10.8		
No idea	50	6.2		
No such NGOs	150	16.2		
Total	800	100.0		

Tab 219

Fig 204

Regarding functioning of local NGOs 8.3% of the respondents felt NGOs doing excellent while 30.6% of them said NGOs are not so effective while 25% of them it is somewhat ok. Next 10% of them said it is not bad while 6% of them opined they not aware about NGO work, while 16% of them felt no such NGOs in the area

The chi-square value of opinion about functioning NGO by the respondents is found to be 92.224 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly significant.

In other words functioning of NGO has statistically significant influence over the health behavior, medical pluralism and allied issues of the respondents.

NGO s Strategies for Rural Health Promotion

Response	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Collaboration with the local self help groups and PHCs	5	25.0	0.556	0.907
Action research and policy suggestions to the Govt.	4	20.0		
Act as an implementing agency	7	35.0		
Running mobile health units, awareness creation etc	4	20.0		
Total	20	100.0		

Tab 220

Fig 205

Regarding NGOs strategies for rural health promotion 25% of the NGOs are working in collaborating with the local self help groups and PHCs where as 20% of the NGOs are action research and policy suggestions to the Govt. while 35% of them acting as real implementing agency while 20% of them running mobile health units, awareness creation work etc

The chi-square value for NGO s strategies for rural health promotion for the rural people is found to be 0.556 and P value is less than 0.05 is found to be highly insignificant.

In other words NGO s strategies for rural health promotion has statistically no significant influence over rurals health issue.

DISCUSSION

“ The set of medicines composing various cultural practices, methods, traditions are embedded in a matrix of values, traditions, beliefs and pattern of ecological adaptation there provide the western maintain here it and avoiding ameliorating disease and injury in its members”(Landy,2001).

Health is one of the prime concerns of mankind, since his emergences on the earth. Health is a pre-requisite for human development and is essentially concerned with the well being of the common man. Health is not only related to the medical care but an integrated development of an entire human society. Normally the context in which an individual lives it is of very vital and significant for his/her health status and quality of life. There are some external determinants which can decide the health status of any person including socio-economic, social environment, hospitals, doctors or technologic. Also it significantly depends on some internal factors including his /her health culture, education, health practices, etc. Quality of health care, health orientation and social protection of the health of a population affects the entire developmental status of any nation. Studying the rural health issue is a complex one. There are various factors affecting the health seeking behaviour and medical pluralism among the rural population. It seems a lot of visible and invisible factors have been associated with their health behaviour.

Health is one of the vital indicators reflecting the quality of human life. Today the majority of the rural people are suffering with the various communicable and non communicable diseases. It is stated there is a positive correlation between the health status of rural people and their social, economical and cultural background. The plight of rurals' having many health issues drawn the increasing policy attention since 1960. Over the last few decades various Indian governments have planned long term goal of providing a compressive health care programme to the rural people, increasingly emphasized the more immediate need to provide essential basic primary health care and scientific management of the rural traditional system. Experts also conducted more studies on the culturally bounded health behaviour and its relations to the communicable diseases among the various rural settings. As for as organic linkage with the rural health intervention are concerned, there is no basic service for a comprehensive health care interventions attempt to understand health culture as a sub culture complex in developing a model of culturally suited health module programmes specially for the rural of the country having different origin.

Rationalism and Fatalism and Health

It is a well known truth that one comes across two types of beliefs towards the health practices at different cultural levels. First, primitive concept based mostly on predominance of the super natural theory or cosmological theory of causation of diseases and illness and seeking therapy by magico- religious means. Next at the folk cultural level there is 'folk system'. In this system respondents believe disease and illness causes because of both super natural and natural reasons. However, respondents believe more towards super natural causation and less belief towards natural reasons. Here respondents believe in the mixed type of therapy. Thus, respondents of "folk culture" have a fatalistic attitude towards their health status. Further, in traditional or indigenous medicine system (the third one) respondents believe more towards natural and very less about supernatural cause's theory of disease and illness. Finally in case of the modern medicine respondents completely recognize natural rather than supernatural causation of disease. They widely believe in the western theory of etiology and treatment. This view reflects the rationalist attitude towards causation of disease or illness and its cure (Nagla, 2007).

To reveal rationalistic or fatalistic view of the respondents about their health/ illness/health behavior etc the researcher has obtained data under the broad four categories.

1. Fatalistic;
2. Non-fatalistic;
3. Rationalistic and
4. Non-rationalistic.

The statements like good health is due to the blessings of the God/ Fate/ or for having good deeds in the past life were identified as 'fatalistic orientation'. The respondents opined about the causes of disease/illness by citing above reasons are kept in the category of fatalistic orientation, but others, who did not prefer them, are classified as non-fatalistic respondents. Like that, the researcher has divided respondents with another set of statements like health is predominantly depends hygienic/ nutritious food/vaccinations/preventive measure/ biological/heredity are some of them which reflect 'rationalistic orientation' This orientation is also interpreted in terms of rationalistic and non-rationalistic oriented respondents (as depicted in various Tables in the result section). It is very difficult to categorize respondents in two exclusive categories of rationalistic or non- rationalistic or

fatalistic or non-fatalistic due to some technical reasons. It is also found that people who are more rationalistic view has higher level of education, income, good occupation and good social network. They are more influenced by the various external agencies like NGOs/Health workers, TV, urban culture etc. Here place of birth and migration status counts a lot as we found (Nagla, 2007).

Fatalism and Health: It is found that Fatalism is a concept which combines belief in God, attributes of irrational practices such as superstitions or religious prescriptions etc. Here respondents strongly believe in case of relationship between disease and illness with the supernatural powers and here the respondents' normally visits temple to offer prayer. Also they offer cash/kind to the God expecting fast recovery. As various Tables in the result section clearly explains health behavior of the certain respondent's depicts a strong fatalism view in the onset and treatment for certain common health problems. Here people will always opt for folk/ traditional medicines and their health behavior and health seeking behavior reflect their age old health culture through which they passed.

Rationalism and Health: "Rationalism is a concept which tries to understand the things in terms of scientific perspective, logic or cause and effect relationships. Generally, it is believed that if an individual has a good health, it is attributed to his hereditary factor/ his fast good deed/good luck etc. Thus, good health is viewed in the rationalistic perspective as "good preventive care", "modern medicine and hygiene" and finally "medical/biological factors"(Nagla, 2007).

Throughout this study, age and gender of the respondents have played a vital role in developing and continuing lineage of health culture and the concept over the period of time. It is apparent that respondents in general gave higher preference to the fatalistic factors for some disease/illness rather than rationalistic factors for their good health as the total mean value of the factors which show the rationalistic dimension weighs more. It does mean that respondents are least preferring the rationalistic view. They have a rationalistic outlook about the origin and curing of disease/illness but their percentage is very low. Various Tables in the result section shows that respondents some time have both rationalistic and fatalistic view about their health seeking and health care seeking behavior based on various illnesses and diseases. And if we analyze each factor separately than hygienic/ nutritious food/vaccinations/preventive measure/ heredity were cited less whereas "traditional factors like supernatural/cosmological factors" have been cited more. However, percentage between these two categories is very meager with respect to the certain disease and very big in some diseases and vice versa. On further analysis, it is

interesting to note that a large number of respondents give higher prominence to the fatalistic factors for the causes of various disease/illness and give more stress on rationalistic view for choosing western medicine for same disease/illness (Nagla, 2007).

Also in the further analysis, it is interesting to note that a large number of respondents give higher weight age to fatalistic factors for choosing western medicine for some disease/illness and give more weightage rationalistic view for causing that disease /illness (for example Jaundice). Respondents think it causes due to the pathogeneses but need folk medicine for treatment).

It is really impossible to understand illness ideology and health behaviour of an individual without understanding the type of the culture he/she borne and brought up and how changing socio-economic factors are affecting on their health concept /culture over the period of time in a given setting. Regarding illness ideology, this study has found that it is mainly depend on the ways in which respondents have been recognized as an ill, approach that patients' uses to present his/her illness and the way/s that he /she is going to deal with an illness. It is revealed that inherited customs, norms which are associated with ill health are the vital issue of the health culture and we cannot completely study the 'health behaviour' in isolation. Some time illness ideology of the respondents goes beyond not only an ill individual, rather his/her family and the community level. This study has found that while focusing individual's response to an illness we need to also focus on the cultural and the societal attributes to his/her health behaviour (Pramuka, 2009).

We found that the level of education more significantly affects on the health status of any community. Today level of education is rapidly increasing in rural areas. This study has revealed that as the education level increases, awareness about health also increases. Regarding occupational status, majority of them are working in primary sector followed by the secondary and tertiary sector. This study has revealed that respondents having a good occupation can get more income and they can have more improvised health behaviour when compare to the others(Tab 26). We have proved that consistent income also plays a vital role in having a quality health life in case of rural areas. Also good occupational status has a closer link in accessing modern health care facilities. Further, this study has proven that better occupational status is lesser the exposure to various occupational related disorders.

This study has also found that occupational status has a closer association with the upward social mobility. Respondents having a lower occupational status show practicing bad habits including smoking, alcohol etc. These bad habits are more common among unemployed youths. This study again explored the level of income has close association with the good health practices. Low income always associated with the low accessibility for good health care. Because of the low income rural communities are not getting quality health care. Respondents having higher income will regularly visits the hospitals whereas the lower income respondents rarely visits hospitals, though their health problem some time would be quite serious.

This study has noted different health behaviors' amongst different Varna. Respondents belonging to Brahmin (higher) have shown more concern towards their health aspects. They perform various rituals regularly to keep-up good health status. They show more improvised health seeking and health care behavior. Respondents belonging to Kshatriya and Vaishya Varna didn't show good health practices in various occasions. Shudra community showed less significant health behaviour and health care seeking behaviour in this study(**Tab28**). Further, the caste has played a major role in practicing significant or less significant health care seeking behaviour. Respondents belonging to the higher caste have shown significant relationships with good personnel health and hygienic practices though their income level is very low. However, the higher caste respondents having a low income level have shown lesser significant health behaviour. This study has found that higher caste respondents having a moderate level of income have shown more concern towards quality health care, also they seek only the western medical care and normally visits good hospitals only. Respondents belonging to the lower caste have shown low accessibility to the healthcare despite having a good occupational income. Respondents belonging to the 'twice born castes' have shown significant interest towards health and hygienic issues. (Tab 29)

Religion has significantly influenced over the health culture. This study has found there is a significant difference on health culture among the various religions. Respondents belonging to Muslim have significant faith and beliefs on health rituals performed by the Hindu traditional healers/faith healers. Also Hindu patients' have shown a lot of faith on Muslim faith healers. In majority cases it is normal to get cure mental illness from the Muslim faith healers. It was quite interesting to note that Christen community is seeking help from both Muslim quacks and Hindu faith healers on case to case basis. (Tab 30)

Further, family structure and the family type also have shown significant differences over health seeking and the health care seeking behaviour. It is quite interesting to reveal members belonging to the nuclear family and extended family have shown more inclination towards the modern/western health care facilities because of good education and the awareness level. Members belonging to the Joint family have shown some sort of less inclination towards modern/western healthcare facility only. Joint family members have shown more faith towards traditional medicine and shows traditional health culture. This might be because joint family normally will be directed/headed by the elderly peopling who have strong faith on the traditional health care system (Tab 30).

Place of birth and the migration status have also shown some interesting relations. Respondents who moved from town/city to the village are also shown more improvised health behaviour because of more awareness level. Respondents who are born and brought up in the same village are having more belief in the traditional medical health care system. Respondents who born and brought-up in the urban areas and staying in the rural areas currently, are showing more improvised health culture and health behaviour (Tab.34).

Expenditure pattern of the respondent's for health issue has also shown some interesting notes. In certain cases catastrophic household expenditure (spending 40% of their total income only for the health issues) can also be seen here. Further, more than 20% of (in an average) the respondents are spending more than 25% of their total income for their different health expenditures in a year. Expenditure pattern also shows respondents are spending more money for health care only when compared to the other components of the life like education etc. This includes buying medicine, transport, hospital etc. This study has found that more than 35% respondents spend around 10-15% of their income for the health care. This is because all family members and other relatives accompany the patient whenever a patient needs to visit a doctor (indirect cost). Here Patient's family will bear the expenditure of the other relatives and the friends who accompanies the patient while visiting hospital/doctor. It is found that 11% of respondents are paying more than Rs. 5,000 / pm as a loan repayment which was taken for their health care needs (Table 35).

Regarding health expenditure is concerned; it also includes expenditure spent for the religious events to cure the sick person. Some respondents are spending more on the family members who are suffering from various chronic diseases like Heart/Kidney problem etc. Break-up details of household expenditure show certain respondents spending too much for the treatment of diseases caused due to the various

life style disorders. The majority of them have taken loan from the local money lenders or mortgagee their assets for their immediate health care needs by paying higher rate of interest. Even though the health expenditure as shown in the table is quite simple, it is a powerful and a more reliable indicator to show direct and indirect cost of the health care borne by the respondents(Tab 37).

This is quite interesting to note that though availability of the modern health care facilities in the rural area is very low, respondents are spending more money than urban people (as compared with various national survey) for the various health issues. This study also revealed that rural people normally visit the doctors when their health problems become more aggravated. Hence in the majority cases they may have to pay more money as a hospital expenditure. Longer the duration of illness increasing the health expenditure as we found. The overall expenditure of the studied households seeking good healthcare may be an important source of funds that can be used to improve the access and quality health care. These findings suggest that public health facilities in the rural areas are suffering from the various constructive problems and the patients' needs to purchase medicine in the open market always. The second vital issue of the health care expenditure is duration of illness episode. The longer the duration of sickness, leads more direct and indirect expenditure on the patients' parts.

The pattern of social expenditure shows respondents are spending a huge amount of money for marriage, birthday, festivals and for other rituals etc. However, when compared to their expenditure for marriage and birthday events, respondents are not spending much for their health needs it seems. This is also a reason why rural respondents are getting more loans for the higher rate of interest from the local money lenders. Also , we can say out of packet expenditure is more in some instances .

Different addictions have become a major problem among the studied respondents. More than 41 % of the studied samples are having different addictions like smoking /alcoholic etc. This study has shown proved that addiction is also causing health problems among the poor in villages. This also led them to have certain chronic diseases and spend more on that whereas 8% of the respondents also use Beda/Jerda which also resulted in having mouth and throat cancer among the respondents in the long run. Respondents who are habitual alcoholics are also suffering with liver and kidney related disorders. Though a reasonable number of respondents know the effect of addictions respondents are still addicted to it. Respondents are spending a considerable amount of money only for smoking or alcohol. Substantial part of their income is going to meet these expenditures only. These addictions not only cause health problems but also hampering their economic

status. The most pathetic thing is that more than 35% of the respondents are aware of the health effects due to addictions but they simply ignore it. In a few cases addictions have led them to have more chronic disease even among women and youths (Table 44).

Regarding source of health information in majority cases respondents are getting health information from their educated children. In the rural parts, folk media like (drama/street play etc...) also plays a vital role in creating more health awareness. Effect of media is also a crucial in giving awareness about preventive measures. Respondents are also getting health information through various other social medias too. Due to this impact we can witness for gradual changes in the health behaviour among the respondents. Also 16% of them said modern electronic media has become a most vital in spreading health information. Apart from these, health workers and NGO's have been more useful in spreading health information to the village people'(Tab 47).

This study sheds light on the different factors affecting women's health in the rural settings. However, more than 37% of them cited economic factors are most vital rather than the social factors affecting women's' health in the rural parts. Also interesting things this study has found that the educational status of mother in law /husband play a vital role in a family. If they are educated it invariably affects on the health status of the female members of that family. Hence this study recommends proper health awareness especially for the in-laws/husband of a particular family. It is found that various social networks of any household will be highly useful to get all sorts of health information(Tab 51).

Further, regarding awareness about contamination of the food items, notable percentage of the respondent's opined pathogenesis are the main sources in contaminating the food items. However, still some traditional beliefs exist like spirit and bad eye normally contaminates the food items and thereby it creates a lot of health problems. However, few respondents opined that food contamination is a natural phenomenon and it is seasonal. Regarding usage of fruits and vegetables in the menu it is found that just 33% of the respondents use vegetables twice or thrice in a week. Respondents are showing more interest to use mutton or chicken rather than vegetables(Tab 54).

Regarding the concept of pure and impurity of blood, respondents opined pure blood is a sign of good health and impure blood is a sign of illness. Respondents are connecting food items without knowing the biological reason behind blood formation.

They opined not only good food items leads to have a good blood but bad food habits leads to have bad blood too. They are of the opinion that '*fate or karma*' also a major reason in having good or bad blood in human beings. However, 18% of the respondent's opined pathogenesis is also some time converts good blood into a bad one among human beings. Respondent's classifications about good or bad blood may be due to their inherited cultural beliefs(Tab 55)

This study has found discrimination in serving food items between male and female members which is a common phenomenon among the rural households. Normally male members are being served more than the female members though females are engaged in more household work including cooking, taking care of the children, helping in the agricultural work, wood collection etc. still she is not getting enough share of the food in the family. This pattern of food dispositions is one of the vital determinants of quantity and quality of the households food usage in the rural parts and it is also significantly effects on their general health status. Here poverty and income level also plays a vital role(Tab 57)

Enquiring about possible social determinants affecting health; respondents opined occupational status is most vital followed by education level and income. Respondent's opined that a good level of education leads good occupation and income. Income reduces poverty level and leads to have more quality food, shelter, absence of worry and can access good medical care. Also they did not forget to mention blessing of \deity and good fathh is essential keeping ourselves healthy. (Tab58)

It is found that 61% of the respondents are rarely using fruits and vegetables. Respondents belonging to the middle income class use non-veg rather than veg items often. Probably this could be one of the reasons why more life style disorders are common among the certain respondents having a decent level of income. This study also found that considerable amount of money is being spent by the rural respondents just to buy non -veg items. Because of low-income 43% of respondents use some kinds of grains or pulses in their menu sparingly. It is noted that socio-economic variables affect the pattern of food style of the respondents. Good socio-economic leads to have a good food pattern. Caste is also a predominant factor playing here. We can observe case based food norms. Though vegetables are cheaply available in the villages it is quite surprising that respondents are not using it much. Probably respondents are not aware of the significance of fiber food items.

The disposal pattern of wastages also raised some vital issues. Because of the poor drainage system in the rural parts, it is found that people normally throw away both solid and liquid wastages wherever they find open spaces. It also leads to have endemic diseases. This kind of unscientific management of wastages is the major factor in causing different types of communicable diseases like Typhoid, Cholera and Dengue etc in the rural parts. Enquiries about various measures to keep healthy, the majority of them opined clean food and water are essential and also they felt clean ecology is very essential to keep healthy themselves. Still, they are not showing interest in keeping surroundings clean!. Meanwhile respondents believe celebrating festivals, worshipping deities and fairs play a vital role in maintaining good health. They also strongly believe blessing of the cosmology powers are essentials in case of health issues. Pleasing God /Goddesses also an important issue in having good health status of the rural people.

Household food norms play a vital role in studying the health culture of the rural people. Though people's socio-economic status is very poor, they normally use more non vegetarian food items. The food security of any household is a reflection of an entire socio-economic status of that household. This study has found more than 28% of the respondents said non-veg items are the healthiest food rather than fruits and vegetables because it gives more energy. Hence, they can do any kind of physical work. In a way it shows respondents are having more nutritious food items unknowingly. Though notable percentage of the respondents know the value of vegetarian food items, respondents would like to use non-veg food items more often irrespective of their income level.

The most vital finding of the study is a source of advice for 'referral'. It is found 37% samples opined that family elders are the key sources for referral whereas noted portion of the respondents are depending on friends and relatives for referral. Actually in the majority cases, family elder's would decide about the kind of treatment to be opted for the patient and its positive and negative consequences. Now a days due to the media interventions respondents are more aware of different diseases and their symptoms. It shows even in nuclear families, elders' have strong traditional control on deciding health seeking behavior of a household.

Regarding reasons for poor health status other than the poverty majority of them are opined 'general ignorance' about various health issues. Respondents are showing much interest in all issues except health care. People will even talk about politics throughout the day but hesitant to talk about health issues for a while!. It is found that the respondents are not generally interested to talk about their health issues

because of the cost factor. Respondents are more worrying on earning livelihood, financial problems, personnel issues, difficulties of the life and to sort out. They don't have enough time even to think about health issues it seems or just ignoring it. Also they opined lack of awareness, health illiteracy and other reasons causing health problems other than poverty especially in the rural parts.

Most stipulating issue is hot and cold concept of food items among the respondents. Respondents also believe hot and cold nature of the food normally leads to have a lot of health related problems in the daily life. Female members of the family have certain restrictions on food norms here. Respondents feel bad food habits leads to have different kinds of illness. People are not daring to use any new food items which are not being used in their tradition till date or not in their usual menu. There are various cultural beliefs about food items being given to postpartum women in the rural parts. Families those who have a good economic background will afford nutritious food to the new mothers, infants and to the children. Respondents in the majority cases use different food items according to the weather/session. Seasonality of food is common in the rural areas. During hot weather respondents use cold food items whereas during cold season respondents use food items causing heat. They believe it keeps humeral balance.

This study also found that different castes have different food culture. Usage of some food items is prohibited in some cases whereas some food item is allowed in some cases. Income level and occupational status has a close relationship with the food habits. Intra-family distribution of food compel women to eat less which causes more malnutrition among them and this is severely affected in case of new mothers having low income status. Norms of eating habits are also counts a lot in case of the rural health culture. Among certain castes, women usually take her meals in the same plate which had been used by her husband without washing it. She is not aware that this may also cause some health hazardous to her. It would be significant to study the manner of serving the food among the family members and practicing of drinking water also very important in understanding the health behaviour of a particular individual in the rural parts. It is widely believed that in the rural areas strong faith on the spirits and evil eyes and its close connections with that of food is quite significant. Respondents also believe certain domestic animals having super natural powers may contaminate the food items. Respondents believe such evil eye and the spirits brings more of illness/diseases.

In the rural areas, the elderly populations are being generally discriminated in various health care issues. It is found 30% of them admitted aged members will not be cared much whereas 27% have admitted that both aged and adults will take care of their health. Truly speaking aged people in many households is not getting enough healthcares. Family members are not showing much interest regarding health expenditures for the aged. Noted respondents have opined it would be unnecessary to spend on aged family members and they opined age-old health problems cannot be completely cured. Since the majority of the respondents are poor they are more concentrating on the bread winners rather than unproductive aged members. We found households even ready to get loan for the treatment (if any) for the adults but not for the aged once. Regarding HIV/AIDS awareness substantial numbers of the respondents are aware of this problem. Only a little percentage they know the exact symptoms of HIV. However, the majority of them don't know about mode of spreading. Enquiry about HIV also found that respondents are not ready to discuss about this openly. Regarding health insurance, more than 70% of them don't have any health insurance. In fact many of them are not even aware about that! It is also one of the reason why people spending from their pockets for any emergency health problem. Some of the respondents are having Govt. running low cost 'Yeshasvini' health insurance and other schemes.

Regarding the concept about body constitution, the majority of the respondents have opined human body is basically created by the God at the time of conception itself. Respondents believe there are certain tendencies in every human body that predisposes to certain kinds of illness. Respondents say hot food is proved to be the cause for heat related health disorders. The notion of the body system is an inevitable part of any characterization of disease by the villagers. Respondents believe the body system itself basically prone to the various diseases/illness by its nature. They felt certain diseases are seasonal and some of them are unseasonal. Respondents felt since it is quite natural that our body systems get diseases/illness hence pathogenesis has no role (Sujatha, 2003). Respondents opined that physical body is made up of several organs and nervous system having definite process and properties inter relating to each other. Hence, it seems that disease causation is an internal issue and whatever external factors responsible for causing various diseases has a close connection to the inside body particles located in the lymphatic system as felt by the villagers. Respondents have a strong belief that internal factors are more responsible for causing diseases.

This study also found that upper caste respondents try to relate their etiology in terms of wider known Gods and the respondents belonging to the lower caste try to connect their etiology to the lesser known Gods' or lesser known deities in the villages for being responsible for their illness. This might be because lower caste people some time cannot worship certain gods in the rural areas. Also it is found the health rituals of the respondents belonging to the lower caste will be very primitive. It is found the concept about the origin, cause of illness, disease classification; and etiological categories etc will revolve around the social, cosmological, spiritual, natural and supernatural belief of the respondents irrespective of the caste or the religion.

In certain cases respondents are much aware about the western medical system and have improvised health behaviour. Though their concept about origin and causes of diseases/ illness is traditional, certain changes in the health concept can be definitely noticed. This study has found that interpretation about various causing factors for any type of diseases/illness depends on people's perceptions on the pathogenic agents or the invisible forces causing that disease/s. Also context in which that health problem has occurred will also be taken into consideration carefully by the people. Moreover elderly persons in any family play a vital role in diagnosing and indentifying certain health problems. In case of women or children health, husband or the mother in law will decide about opting possible health care system in a household. Few respondents opined issue of severity of distribution of the patient's relationships with the other invisible/cosmological forces or even with the pathogenesis will play a vital role in causing various health problems to him/her. Hence, we opine the western theory of origin of diseases/illness has got only little importance among the studied Indian rural population.

Regarding the classification of illness or diseases, some interesting facts have been emerged. Respondents are completely unaware in classifying various health problems in to 'disease or illness'. Only 30% (in average) could classify Typhoid, Malaria, Jaundice, and Cholera as diseases, whereas substantial percentages of respondents have classified these diseases under illness category. They were of the opinion that patients' suffering from these health problems shows more physical symptoms rather than the clinical. We found some respondents sometime logically classify certain 'diseases into illness' and 'illness into diseases'. They are not in the position to cite an exact reason for their classification/s. Respondents are not in the position to find out any logic behind differentiating ' the illness from a disease'. However, noted percentage of respondents could recognize the mental problem as a disease rather than 'illness' because mental illness is more visible as they opined.

More than that, some of the respondents opined Typhoid, Malaria, Jaundice, and Cholera are both diseases as well as illness too. They also opined diseases and illness or intertwined and one cannot exist without the other.

The explanations and descriptions for classifying diseases or illness by the studied sample were not in line with the scientific and the biomedical aspects of health or illness. This classification will have close association of philosophical, historical and the spiritual aspects along with the socio-economic aspects of the respondents. The constructed meaning about disease or illness as expressed by the studied samples depicts in a larger social context involved in 'meaning construction'.

If we go through the basic notion behind classification of diseases /illness by the studied rural people it looks that in the multifaceted and changing world of health seeking behaviour, it is obligatory to understand actual association between an individual and his/her society where firmly attaching to the definite and established social rules or norms that comes out as the vital sense around which other philosophical concepts are being prearranged in a leisure system or network (Dixit, 2009),

Further, it is equated that absence of illness and forces to accept the sick role and social exclusion due to the sickness and the gap between clinically established illness/diseases and the original status of the patients' have a certain role in the meaningful construction of classifications of various health problems into disease and illness. This is also applicable with respect to the communicable or non communicable diseases. Because in this study we have found that patients' having certain diseases as established by the valid medical investigations are leading to a normal life without showing any sign of illness or problems.

In some case studies, illnesses are broadly categorized by the study population as mild and severe. However, the perception varied from the community members to the traditional healers. Severe illnesses are those that are thought to require medical treatment, and mild illnesses are those that do not need any medical treatment. Thus, illnesses that need urgent bio-medical intervention and those of long duration are considered to be severe illnesses. However, there are a few exceptions. For example, the Measles and the Jaundice are considered to be severe illnesses; however, modern medical treatment is not sought for these illnesses; instead it is believed and feared that if modern medical treatment is taken, the illness may recur and may even lead to death too. Hence, only the traditional treatment by the traditional healer is sought for these illnesses. In the case of Measles, seeking modern care is even a punishable

offence in many social groups. Few traditional healers reported that Measles will recur if modern medical treatment is sought. It may also be noted here that for other illnesses the traditional healer himself advise people to go to the modern medical facility. Illnesses with less pain and which occurs usually like cold, cough, and headache are considered as mild illnesses. The evil-eye-related illness is also considered to be a non-medical type of illnesses, as it can only be cured by a traditional healer. People reported on the transmission of some illnesses. The concept of the transmission of diseases is gained from biomedical knowledge people gained through different sources. Thus, illnesses are also classified as transmissible illnesses (such as Measles, Diarrhoea, Leucorrhoea, Scabies, etc.) and non-transmitted illnesses. It may be noted here that Jaundice is considered to be a non-transmitted illness by the respondents.

It is found that normally diagnosis and causing of the illness starts at the family level in the majority cases. Family elders normally will do the initial diagnosis based on their previous experience and other villages elders, relatives and friends will contribute in their own way in this issue. After an initial diagnose by the family elder they will visit a traditional healer. If a traditional healer could not solve the problem or diagnose, then only people visit the western doctors and by that time it would be too late for the treatment. It is also found that visiting a traditional healer or western doctors depends on the severity and duration of the illness/disease.

This study has found that reasons for different ailments or diseases as attributed by the studied samples are (in the ranking order):

1. Angry deities;
2. Cosmology;
3. Breaching taboo;
4. Scientific reasons

Based on reasons and the types of illness, respondents will name and classify the responsible agent/agency for causing particular type of disease/illness. It is also found that respondents classify three types of illness. They are

1. Temporary illness;
2. Permanent illness
3. Adhoc illness(rare)

This study also found respondents' normally will classify illness or health problems into 4 groups based on their etiology they are

1. Body linked illness;
2. Deity linked illness;
3. Spirit linked illness and
4. Pathogenic linked illness.

According to the respondents if the disease/illness is curable within a short duration of time, respondents will classify it as a temporary illness/disease. If the same problem continues for a longer period or if not curable at all it will be classified as permanent disease/ illness (ex. mental illness).

In some case studies we found the co-existence of cultural and biomedical concepts regarding health and illness. These findings are somewhat in contrast to the earlier studies that were carried out during 1970s and '80s in which causes of illness are classified into three categories: supernatural, preternatural or mystical, and natural forces by the people (Erinosa, 1978; Oke, 1995). It appears that in the course of time, certain concepts have undergone change while the other cultural concepts continued; the acceptance of biomedical concept may not replace the cultural concept of illness and often both concepts co-exist. Perhaps it may be a part of the acculturation process. This continuity and the change in the cultural concepts regarding health and illness are clearly seen among certain social groups in the rural parts and has a considerable bearing on the treatment seeking behaviour. While certain illnesses such as Measles and Jaundice are purely seen through the cultural lens and led to the deterring of biomedical treatment; some other illnesses are thought to be treated only by the modern medicines. However, often people follow traditional treatment for several illnesses, sometime biomedical treatment is sought, if the traditional treatment fails, or sometime they follow both the types. The perceived causes of diseases have a considerable bearing on determining the choice of treatment, which leads to delay in seeking the modern health care system.

This study has found that respondents' concept about 'health' is quite general. Respondents believe health is a status to perform normal duty of a human being without any disturbances. If people cannot do his/her normal work then it will be termed as an ill health/sickness'. However, a notable percentage of respondents opined that health is a good physical and mental status of the body. Those respondents who believe in the western theories of etiology have given categorization

of performance orientation. The majority of the respondents opine illness causes due to the supernatural power and a notable percentage of the respondents opine diseases causes due to humeral imbalances. Also a considerable percentage of the respondents opine diseases or illness causes due to the pathogenesis or due to the biological reasons. It shows they still under traditional way of health behaviour.

Further, it is found that the respondents are having some sort of modern concepts regarding causes of diseases/illness. It is the strongest witness for interpreting some sort of changes in their health culture in the recent times. This study has also found that respondents partially could differentiate diseases from illness. In-depth study has revealed that respondents don't have a clear cut idea and definite concept about what is illness and not. They don't have any holistic idea about this concept. Though they believe illness is more or less a psychological one, they are not ready to accept illness is a separate entity. Respondents believe illness will be normally because from the unknown powers that cannot be explained, but can be experienced.

Respondents could not scientifically differentiate between 'health' and 'ill health'. The majority of the respondents believe health means 'without diseases or illness'. Certain respondents(33%) opined health means 'who can tolerate hot and cold weather and having a long life span'. Some respondents also felt health means absence of any sort of worry. Regarding the concept about unhealthy status, the majority of the respondents opined unhealthy means it is a status of 'either complete illness or complete diseased'. However, a notable percentage (16%) opined unhealthy means one who always depends on life saving medicines. In the same way notable percentage of the respondents opined illness means one who cannot fight against evil forces and 5% respondents opined who cannot withstand against the attack of the pathogenesis and it leads to have an unhealthy status with this reply we can assume respondents are partially aware about what is illness and what is diseases. Thus, the concept of health refers only to the physical health. Broadly, the concept of health and illness varied according to the gender owing to the physical structure of the body, in addition to gender-related roles in the society. According to them, illness is attributed to more than one cause and, hence, they seek different types of treatment from different sources, depending on the type of illness.

It seems that changes from the illness to healthcare seeking behavior can be mainly multidimensional one if the illness is not a life intimidating. For instance, cost of the medical care is a real concern for the poor people in the rural parts. Also, there must be a co-relation with the stipulation of primary health care services as resolute by

the interactions of all the people within the health care systems. Perceptions about illnesses/diseases can be described as an individual shared beliefs, views and traditions that characterize illness, its causes, signs and symptoms (Helmam, 1985). Respondents believe since the patients' cannot perform social responsibilities that behaviour will be viewed as a deviant. Respondents opine diseases and illness not only linked to the patients' biophysical conditions but also to the supernatural entities. Respondents also opined failing in performing in divine rights, breaching taboo, cures of deities are also causes different diseases and illness. Respondents opined that 'disease invokes certain process of the body system rather than a conception of body anatomy' (Sujatha, 2003).

Respondents could not relate a diseases or illness to a specific organ rather they felt disease or illness is a completely relating to the certain pre-established properties of an entire body system. It is found that Illnesses/diseases have been conceptualized differently in rural societies resulting in a range of different terms and categorization. a variety of local terms and concepts are being used to classify malaria according to the level of harshness and apparent causes. Respondents also think ecology, climate conditions and environment play a role in causing various diseases, and their role is subsumed under more inclusive and decisive internal body factors (Sujatha, 2003). In the rural areas incapacitation or absence from works also a general index of an illness or unhealthy condition/s. People expect a healthy person should work normally without having any problem/s. Hence, it is concluded in the rural areas illness is more related to the functional rather than a clinical or biological. Consequently, sometime respondents' having Mild fever, Headache, Cough, Wounds, Giddiness will not be considered as a health problem. Symptoms of these health problems will not normally hamper their normal routine work. The response to illness and illness behaviour is the way in which symptoms are perceived, evaluated and acted upon will vary from one individual to another in many a times.

Respondents have some cultural beliefs about natal, neo natol, antenatal and child health care. Respondents have opined special care is required for natal and infants. Respondents are also aware about the role of immunization and the essentials of hygienic conditions. However, notable percent of respondents (23%) opined natal and infants need to be secured from the evil spirits. Respondents felt natal, neonatal and infants care seeking can be done by visiting faith healers are traditional healers while 38% of the respondents opined infants care needs to be at the hospitals only. It is also found that weaning of the children normally start between 4 to 8 months.though they know the value of feeding milk immediately after the birth

respondents did not show much interest in that issue. The majority of them have opined first milk would have some contaminating items which is not good for the newborn babies. However, certain respondents opined feeding first milk is actually good for the babies. This awareness might be due to the health education through the medias' it seems. Also some respondents opined because of anticipating bad effects due to spirits and bad eye first milk should not be feed to the babies.

Further, this study has found that the proximity of illness is a strategic social style for the perpetuation of the effective social order. Concept about wellbeing and ill being has been located in the cultural understanding of the respondents' about different health practices'. Village people felt social relationships are the most vital in the smooth maintenance of the social order including the health and illness. We found in this study that 'diagnosing and healing are having the most vital role in the cultural interpretation of the illness ideology'. This study found that the illness ideology of the rural respondents is embedded with social, cultural, historical, philosophical context of the community and Illness concept goes beyond the individual body and medical diagnose (Saran, 1995).

We also found that illness with less pain and which occurs usually like cold, cough, and headache are considered to be mild illnesses. The evil-eye-related illness is also considered to be a non-medical type of illnesses, as it can only be cured by a traditional healer. People reported on the transmission of some illnesses. The concept of the transmission of diseases is gained from the biomedical knowledge which people gained through the different health sources. Thus, illnesses are also classified as transmissible illnesses (such as mMeasles, Diarrhoea, Leucorrhoea, Scabies, etc.) and non-transmitted illnesses. It may be noted here that Jaundice is considered to be a non-transmitted illness.

Some time respondents' concept about health and illness depends based on their position in the societal hierarchical structure. An interesting aspect found in this study is '**caste based illness ideology**'. Respondents belonging to the certain higher caste will perform various rituals regularly seeking blessings of the good to keep them in good health status always. They spend a considerable amount of money for that purpose only whereas illness ideology is quite different among the respondents belongs to the lower castes. This study has established that lower caste respondents (more illiterate if) more strongly believe in the cosmology or evil forces responsible for causing various diseases/illness. However, a notable percentage of them also believes in the scientific theory of illness and disease and denies traditional beliefs. It is noted that the lower caste people will seek help from the priest belonging to the

higher caste to perform any health related rituals. However, in the majority cases priests' from the higher caste will not accept this offer. In that case, the lower caste respondents will choose a person amongst them to conduct required rituals.

We attempted to determine whether the health and illness concepts and prescriptions of the community change along gender lines. It was found that that as men and women possess sex differences, and as they differ in their physical characteristics, certain illnesses occur in only women while certain others occur in men only as opined by the respondents.

It is revealed that the majority of the higher caste respondents will not participate in any health related rituals normally organized by the lower caste people except in some cases. It is prejudiced among certain sections of the society that higher caste people are more privileged to access to the wellbeing whereas lower caste people are indented to being ill-health. It is interesting to note that a notable percentage of respondents belonging to the lower caste believe in the western theory of etiology and they perform health related rituals to come out of any specific illness/diseases and they dont like to visit hospitals!. This study found that illness ideology varies caste to caste. Caste based illness ideology study would be very ideal in this moment.

This study has found that in few occasions' illness ideology changes from one geographical area to another geographical area and one social context to another social context. The illness ideology of any community must be studied with in the ambit of that particular social context only. It is well established that the role of society in conceptualizing illness and sickens/ well being are normally articulated within the force any community. It is also found that understanding health behaviour of the villager's and the health culture goes beyond the individual body and particular etiology into the context of the general culture. However, gender prospective of health and illness is also a significant part in studying the rural health culture. It is evident that understanding social relationship between the community members is very significant in understanding health behaviour and illness ideology in the any rural parts.

Respondents have classified different Gods, Goddess and Evil forces as causer /s for the different types of illness and diseases based on their historical background and experiences. They worship specific types of God and Goddess to cure various diseases and illness including for mental illness, digestive problems, breathing problems, and children's health problems etc. The style of worships differs from caste

to caste, area to area and culture to culture. The essential explanatory theory is that in serious illness, there is a reinforcement of the supernatural power. The majority often evoked agency is ancestor spirit anger. Ancestor spirits constitute part of the ordered configuration of the rural cosmology it seems. People believe hurtful the ancestors results a trouble of this order and therefore dissonance and illness. Types of family and its historical background also play a significant role in shaping illness ideology and the health behaviour amongst the young siblings. In this study it is found that in the majority cases senior members of a village will perform a key role in diagnosing diseases or illness and in opting appropriate treatment plan also. It seems respondents sometime seek first advice from the village elders using their social network rather than approaching a healer/Doctor!.

Further eating of banned/unseasonal food, contaminate water, contaminate environment, are the key factors causing body linked illness as they opined. Breaching taboo, forgetting to perform regular worships, would be considered as major causative factors for deity linked illness in rural parts. Also different deities are connected for the onset of various types of diseases/illness. Sometime the single spirit may cause different health problems whereas many spirits or deities may be responsible for causing a single disease/illness. Few responds also felt pathogenis present in air and water causes pathogenic linked illness or health issues. It is established that illness or any health issues may be an individual affair in that majority cases or sometime it may be a familial or more sometime a community level affair. Rurals' concepts on angry deities', spirits, cosmology etc also differs from caste to caste irrespective of their economic status. Also concepts about body symbolism, the hot and cold notion of food, ritual healings, ethos, body physiology also differs from caste to caste among the rural people as this study found.

Few studies have found that the local healers will play a decessive role based on the psychological aspects of the patients' during the healing process. Though the healers knows about the psychology of the patients' curing process has some sort of social touch too. Here an immense faith on the healers by the patients' play very significant role always. This kind of strong emotional attachment of rural people towards the local healers correlates socio-psychological aspects of the every patient's. Viability, availability and easy accessibility of the local medical system are very vital in case of opting suitable health care system by the rural people(Sujatha, 2008)

Further, it is within the social sphere of the family that diseases/illness occurs and its management is resolved. Family helps a patient in coping with the stress and difficulties due to illness/disease. Emotional bonds between the patients' and his/her

family members would be very crucial in case of stress, pressure and strain on the part of the patients' during sick role. It is also found that patient's sick role cannot be isolated from his/her familial circumstances. It is more in case of the joint families. It is found that familial relations' and obligations sometime leaves a major role in influencing the patients' to accept the sick role. Also family only bears the expenditure of the health care because the family is recognized legally as the decision making authority in opting th suitable health care on behalf of the patients'.

The notion of hot and cold nature of food also some time causes diseases and illness indirectly. Respondents believe certain combinations of food items should not be consumed in at a certain time or in a given season. Here hot and cold concept of food varies from caste to caste too. Higher caste respondents use more nutritious foods because of strong economic background. Respondents belonging to the lower caste uses low food items which leads to them malnutrition problem. Respondents' believe there should be a balance among consuming various food items the season. Respondents believe during cold season hot food should be taken to avoid humeral imbalance and vice versa. Respondents widely believe super natural powers can contaminate food items. And they believe consuming unseasonal food items may lead to have some health problems (Nagala, 2007).

Respondents also partially believe in pathogenesis causing contamination of food. It is found that even educated respondents believe in the contamination of food items by the evil spirits. We also found that a discrimination in case of serving food items between male and female members in a family. Respondents opined since male member works outside and since he is the main bread winner he must serve more to get a lot of energy. On further probing, respondents opined food serving must be inside the home only to avoid being contaminated by the evil eyes. At any cost, especially children must always be served inside the home respondents added. Probably this might be due to an inherited food cultural or socialization pattern of the respondents.

Differentiation between good and bad blood is a fundamental notion in explaining health seeking behaviour. Respondents believe good blood leads to having good health. Good blood will generate by eating good seasonal food items with. They said Gods' blessings are also must. Also respondents believe evil spirits or pathogenesis will not penetrate into a human body having good blood so that no health problems. Respondents believe patient having bad blood takes a long time to recover from any type of illness and diseases and any medicine does not impact on that patient. Respondents believe blood may get impure by taking prohibited fluids/ food

items etc. In total respondents believe good food generates good blood and bad food generates bad blood in the human body.

Respondents' concept about sickness is quite general. The majority respondents did not distinguish between sickness and illness. However, respondents opined every patient has rights to have a sick role and he/she has to try level best to come out of that sick role soon. In-depth probe also revealed some respondents' opined both illness and sickness are one and the same and both of them cause due to the same reason/s. Some respondents felt sickens is a kind of social sanction and illness is a kind of a curse. Sick role behaviour largely depend on how community expects its sick member to behave like. These social aspects of health shape as a strong base for adopting informal systems of health care. Respondents also felt though in some cases patients' cannot recover completely at least they can establish a relatively normal social role.

In-depth analysis has also proved that respondents have a concept about 'health culture' that has some interesting notion. Certain respondents' opined health culture is a part of their general culture but it has a set of specific dos' and donts' which should be followed during the period of illness or disease by a every patient. Notable percentages of respondents have also opined since the time immemorial, society has fixed certain procedures/norms to be followed during the time of ill health and this gradually become the 'health culture'. About 16% of the respondents opined health culture means the performance of established norms/ethos to be observed /performed during illness. Next, 11% of them opined health culture is nothing but a document of illness episode or narrations which is a guiding principle for the next generations to handle any adverse health problems. Also notable respondents opined health culture means a collective venture in sharing and interaction involved in the healing process. We think respondents have have reasonably understood the concept 'health culture' though it is an integral part in their lifestyle.

Respondents strongly believe diseases and illness is quite a natural phenomenon and it happens when the disturbance happens between the man and the environment. Majority of the respondents also opined humeral imbalance (wind/bile and flagon) causes communicable health problems like Typhoid/Jaundice/ Cholera etc. Few respondents also strongly believe bacteria, water, and air also responsible for causing various diseases and illness (19%). It means respondents are gradually getting some kind of awareness about modern etiology because of various external influences. However, respondents are not in the position to differentiate between communicable

and non-communicable health problems exactly. For causing non communicable health problems, respondents believe strongly in cosmology powers.

Various studies have proved that established rurals' health behavior should not be underestimated citing them as illiterate or superstitious (Helmance, 2001; Hardon, 2001). Even today the major sections of the rural respondents are not ready to accept the modern health system. Because of stiff resistance within and out, many rural targeted health programmes by the Govt. have not been succeeded. Medical Anthropologists felt modern health programmes, do not have any space to respect peoples inherited health culture, emotions and spiritual meaning associated with health and diseases. It is believed that respondent's health behaviour depends on the particular culture, particular geographical area and the particular eco-system. Here general culture and eco-system plays a vital role on respondent's health seeking behaviour and in opting particular type of health care approach. Moreover it is found that health seeking behaviour varies according to the type of illness, causation of illness, gender and age of the patients'. It is found that perception of illness and sickness directly affects on the health seeking behaviour and health care seeking behaviour of any particular community.

Before people seek medical help they try to interpret the symptoms themselves and often consult other people. These common illnesses were examined not because of their seriousness but because of their occurrence of frequency which disturb their normal life. The five possible triggers that people seek medical aid includes "1- occurrence of an interpersonal crisis 2- perceived interference with social and personal relations 3- perceived interference with & physical activity 4- sanctioning by other people 5- sufferers ideas about how long certain complaints should last". These models are part of the method that people use to build socio-medical culture. They give meaning to illness and health, answering questions about personal responsibility about health and most importantly are part of the dialogue between patients' and professionals' illness explanations. It can help explore why some patients will follow a doctors directions and others pay no attention to them totally. A patient's clarification or understanding of their illness can be much broader than a physician's and this dynamic has become a major criticism of modern medical practice since it normally excludes the "social, psychological and experiential dimensions of illness" (Punamaki, Raija-Leena, 1995).

It is found that there is much extreme diversity in the demographic behaviour of rural people. Further, ethically, socially, economically, culturally rural people are very different in various ecological, and developmental settings. Hence it is found

that health behaviour is much controlled by the social traditions and family based frame of mind rather than social and economic status some time. In certain rural parts both traditional and modern medical health behaviour continuous to be antagonistic to each other as opined by Singh (2008). This is why rural people have pharmacopeia of their own for various types of illness/disease they face normally.

Broad and specific geographical pattern of health behaviour can be seen across the villages and in some cases similar health culture also can be seen across the villages irrespective of caste/social groups. Also one of the great strength of the rural health culture is the involvement of blood relive/others in therapy management. Kins, friends, and other villagers will also help in the therapy management. We found that this social support network in the treatment process including sharing, suggestions and counseling to the patents will boost the morality of the concerned patient. If the patient suffers from any pain normally the whole group shares the agony. Hence, healing process will be a type of a shared experience. In this case rehabilitation of a patient will not be a problem. Also we noticed that the overall impact of various economic development processes, modern developments causes some positive or some negative effect on the rural health. Continuous migration has done sever changes in the health culture of the rural folk(Joshi ,2004) .

in rural settings health and treatment normally reflects the community's solidarity. if something health related happens to any person in a village entire village will come forward to observe certain norms. Hence up to certain extent choosing a specific therapy some time will be decided at the community level only. in certain cases the whole community will take the responsibility of the patient until he/she gets cured. Gradually this would be an illness episode of that community in that particular geographical area. Gradually these kinds of illness narrations will keep on adding to the health culture of that community over the period of time and space. Also this social solidarity through social network will also play an indirect role in educating other people to be cautious about the illness/diseases in the future(Chaudhuri ,2004).

Respondents have various notions for why certain diseases are not permanently curable? The majority of them opined it might be due to irreparable damages to the internal system of the body. They felt when internal system has been damaged by the external medicines some time permanent curing is not quite possible. Also 7% of them opined there is no such disease which cannot be permanently curable in the traditional medical care system and 4% of them felt failure of the existing health care system is the main reason in this issue. However, some of them have interpreted that the nature has specifically created some type of health problems to check the

population. Whereas 40% of them opined permanent curing is not possible because of dysfunctioning of the different organs by the spirits evil eyes. Further probe also revealed that modern food and ecology has been polluted and it is causing more non curable diseases.

Pattern of treating an ill person starts from social isolation in certain cases. In majority cases T.B, Leprosy and Mental illness patients' will be badly treated by the other fellowmen. Sometime respondents don't even touch these patients' because of fear of transmission of diseases. Even family members don't like to touch those patients' suffering from Leprosy and T.B. However, more than 30% of them opined patients' should be treated fairly and 27% of them opined support for the speedy recovery of the patients should be extended. In majority cases treating an ill person depends on type of illness/disease.

Regarding baby delivery, the majority of the respondents would like to visit government hospitals whereas the notable percentage of the respondents depends on traditional midwives. They opined treatment and the medicines will be free at the Govt. hospitals. Also fear of operation, pain, and the distance factors counts a lot in not choosing institutional deliveries. Due to the some customs and the traditions the notable percentage of the pregnant women normally chooses delivery at home only. However owing to the various Govt health schemes today rural people is showing much interest in opting Govt. hospitals.

Regarding immunization concerned the majority of the respondents have immunized for their children which are freely available in the government hospitals like BCG, DPT and Polio vaccine. In some cases the parents have not shown interest in getting vaccinations for their children. Some of the respondent's opined vaccination may cause some kind of internal health problems for the child. Moreover, the noted percentages of the respondents are not aware of the significance of the vaccinations. However the respondents are of the opinion that the medical powers of the vaccines will lost after sometime and it is a wasteful exercise and there after the child may frequently prone to the various diseases. They felt rather than vaccinating the child should allow to grow with a natural immunity. Better economic and social groups have positive opinion about the usage of various modern vaccines.

Various types of mortalities have become the problem among rural people. Neonatal and post natal mortalities are little bit prevalent among the low socio-economic status people. An In-depth study on this issue found that the majority of them are opined mortality and morbidity is due to the various unknown medical and

non medical reasons. More than 18% of the respondents opined child mortality is due to a bad household ecology. Respondents are showing much interest in keeping the house clean if any infant lives in that house. This kind of attitude will be helpful in keeping the hygienic environment so that new born babies can be saved from various types of infections. Further, the aged in the family strongly believe angry deity or evil spirits and the pathogenesis also leads natal, infant and other types of mortalities. Few respondents also opined various physiological problems controlled by the various external agencies also causing the death of natal's and neonatal in many cases. Due to the various external interventions like NGOs/media it is found that the respondents have some awareness regarding other reasons for various types of mortalities including conjugal marriage, non-vaccinations, baby deliveries at home etc. It is a kind of good sign that rural people are awaking about modern etiology.

Regarding weaning (start feeding solid food to the infants) for the children majority of them starting between 3 to 4 months followed by 23% of them felt it must be start between 6 and 8 months. Respondent's opined that weaning should start only after 10 months after birth because at this stage every internal organs will be well developed and babies can digest hard food stuff. Regarding health seeking pattern of the natal and neo natal and infants respondents prefers the local healers and faith healers only during the first few days. Respondent's opined that some cosmological powers affects on the infants at this stage. However, 38% of them have shown interest to get treatment only at PHCs only. Few respondents opined that western medicine at this stage may cause future effect on the health of the baby. However, 12% of the respondents would like to visit private hospitals for treatment of their babies because they said private doctors will take care of babies well than Govt. hospitals with all required facilities. Few parents opined that they take a decision as suggested by the family /village elders. However due to the interventions of various health programmes, trained health workers (ASHA), Doctors and NGO's are making more positive influence on the health seeking pattern.

Further probing about the primary requirements for good health of the children respondents has both traditional and modern concepts. Respondents believe children health generally depend on the blessings of the deity or fate. They opined cosmological powers will effect more in the first few years of the child's life. Hence, if any health problem in the early years, normally respondents would like to visit only faith healers / local healers or traditional healers for the treatment. Whereas more than 22% of them have opined hygienic environment and good nutrition's are very essential for keeping babies healthy. These two factors show how concept among the

respondents about children's health gradually is being changed. However only 11% of them opined regular vaccinations and health checkup are required for the good health of the infants/children. Every caste has their own concept about infant and child healthcare here. Lower caste people have more traditional concept about child immunization. Respondents with the higher caste and income have shown more improved health care seeking behaviour with respect to their children. This study has shown that level of education and good income also significantly influence on the childrens' health.

Regarding opinion about taking the injections for any health problem/s it is revealed some interesting facts. Generally the respondents are not showing much interest to take the injections for any health problems. Only 51% have opined an injection directly induces the medicines in to the blood so that patients' may get quick healing. Whereas 20% of them opined the injections would affect on the nerve system in the future and they only prefer tablets. Probably this is due to the strong previous influence of the traditional medicinal system where there is no provision for any injection/s. More than 8% of the respondents opined taking the injections means a kind of invitation for the pain and the side effects in the future. Generally children are not being allowed to take the injections and they would like to get the treatment in tablets/tonics forms only. In-depth probe also has revealed that the traditional healers and family elders are also oppose for taking the injections for any health problem.

Most interesting issue is the duration/time between falling sick and the treatment seeking. This study has found normally the respondents in the first instant would follow 'wait and see technique'. They prefer natural healing if they get ill/sick for the first instance. Only 19% of the respondents visit traditional healers or doctors immediately when they fall ill and more than 9% of the respondents will seek medical help after the problem really gets serious. In majority cases respondents uses just home remedies to cure their health problems. In some cases patients' will seek elder's opinion of the family and visit local healers only. If the local healers could not solve the problem, next, people will seek the help from the other village elders using social network. Since normally the respondents seek medical care few days after falling ill, it leaves more health expenditure because by that time the health problem will be more serious or aggravated and the doctor may order more tests/advanced treatment to cure the disease at that stage. respondents belonging to the higher caste and having good education though having low income normally will seek the medical help immediately after being ill. This study also proved that the level of education and the level of

income have a direct relation with that of the duration between falling ill and seeking the valid medical help. These two factors are most vital in health care behavior.

This study has also found some interesting features about the respondent's attitude towards the hereditary diseases. The majority of them have opined that the hereditary diseases don't have any medications at all. Whereas 17% of them have opined that traditional medicine has a solution for the hereditary diseases. They are citing how mental illness will be cured by the faith healers. Next, 12% of them opined it is the fate of the patients whereas 14% of them opined the cosmology and the spirits leave more impact regarding the hereditary diseases. Probe also revealed the respondents have cultural specific attitudes toward the onset, symptoms and curing of various hereditary diseases whereas notable percentage of them opined normally hereditary diseases causes due to the side effects of modern medicine and the ecological pollutions. While 9% of them opined hereditary diseases cause due to the internal damages. They opined consuming hot and the cold food items are also responsible for these kinds of health problems. Regarding the congenital deformities 18% of them opined the congenital deformities cause due to the superhuman causation, whereas 30% of them opined the congenital disorders causes due to the bad weather, bad food and internal damages. Some of the respondents opined these kinds of deformities are the hereditary in nature and it causes due to the conjugal marriage, cosmology, bad blood etc. Still some respondents are conducting marriage among their own relatives for various social reasons. However, social groups having the high level of education and income opined it causes due to the medical or biological reasons.

Our study also found that the rural respondents are less aware about the incidence of STDs. Normally the patients' would not reveal their problems to anybody because of shy. The majority of them are not considering the STDs as a very serious health issue and they feel it will get away naturally. It may be probably due to the low socio-economic status which may impact on their health behaviour. The majority of the rural respondents believe STDs can be cured by the local healers. Our study has found that that rural men visit cities finding jobs. Also sometime they visit the commercial sex workers in cities. In this way some rural men would get STDs from the sex workers and transmits to their wives. Since, it would be normally costlier to treat any type of STDs, people are not showing much interest in seeking western health care. People will get treatment only if any STD continuously troubling them for a long time and severely hampering their day to day life. Due to the absence of the women physicians some time the rural women don't like to visit local PHC's .

In addition, many local PHCs don't have any preventive programme because of lack of human resources and financial crunches. We found in certain cases STD had resulted in severe effect on social and economical aspect of the patients'. Also it may cause severe burden on the health expenditure on the patients' family. More pathetic issue is people visit local healers for the STD problem but the local healers cannot diagnose the STDs on time. Only few rural respondents visit urban based private clinics to get proper treatment. Because, they think they can hide the problem away from their neighbors, friends etc in the villages. If they got treatment in the local PHCs, patients' generally think this issue may get leaked out through any hospital staff and it is a kind of an insult/emarrassing and it may severely hampers the personal image of the patient in the village and sometime friends and relatives will avoid him/her in general and in majority cases patients may have to face a kind of social isolation.

Apart from social, cultural and religious practices there are some other factors which may play a vital role in developing specific health behaviour towards origin, cause and treatment plan for the STDs. The continuation of poor health culture, unawareness, poor health infrastructure, unspecified barriers, misleading, and domination of local healers are some of the vital structural barriers which prevent the patients' in getting the proper and timely treatment for the STDs. In the same way in some cases we found that losing faith on the local medical system, paradoxical changes in the rural life style, level of education and income are strongly associated and acting as pushing factors to seek modern health care for STDs by the rural respondents belonging to the higher income groups.

Approaches of socialization and health behaviour are most vital parts in conceptualizing of various disease and illness as we found. Respondents are not actually in the position to exactly differentiate between communicable and non communicable disease. Only handful of the respondents rightly defined characteristic feature of communicable and non-communicable diseases. Majority of the respondents opined communicable and non-communicable diseases means it leads to death only. It is found that due to the absence of proper medical care some patients were died in villages because of various communicable and non-communicable diseases. Hence, based on this example respondents might have developed this kind of notion like communicable diseases means death ultimately. The meaning of construction about onset and symptoms of various diseases appears to be related to their membership in the social normative behaviour and social acceptance. Respondents are not appropriately classifying diseases into communicable and non-

communicable one. This might be because of inherited health culture and the health illiteracy. In-depth study has shown some changing trends here where level of education and income has more link with disease classifications.

Respondents have variety of concepts regarding reasons for the onset of certain diseases like Measles, Polio, Leprosy, Food poisoning etc. Majority of them opined all these problems causes from humeral imbalances, super human causation, breaching taboo, spirits, sorcery etc. Also noted percentage of the respondents opined all these diseases causes due to the biological reasons. However, their income level, occupation and level of education is high and they have enough health information resources and referral system and they have modern outlook because of their social network. Respondents strongly believe malnutrition and metabolic disorders causes due to an internal physiological problems. They also opined intake of unseasonal food items causes malnutrition and metabolic disorders. However, respondents also believe due to the polluted whether, unhygienic food also leads to have these kinds of health problems. For those health problems which cannot be given any reason for causing, respondents opined those disease causes due to the super human causation bad eye etc. However, noted percentage of respondents opined certain health problems like Polio, Leprosy causes due to the pathogeneses as well as angry deity etc. Respondents also citing difficult terrain, lack of good water, climatic conditions are the responsible in the onset of these kinds of problems. Even though the above mentioned health problems are relatively very less, respondents have cultural and geographically specific concept about these diseases it seems.

Regarding the onset of the most common communicable disease like Typhoid, Jaundice, Diophrea, Cholera and Malaria, the respondents again have opined all these causes due to the humeral imbalance, super human causation, and the breaching taboo etc. Since these diseases are most common in villages respondents have little bit scientific idea relating to the causative factors. However the majority of them opined all these diseases causes due to the pathogenesis and unhygienic conditions. The most important fact is that everyday knowledge about the onset of the most common types of diseases like Typhoid, Jaundice etc is socially constructed having lay explanations. The routine knowledge regarding onset of these diseases is not in line with the scientific approach. Respondents reply clearly shows that people's opinion are clearly overlapping between the traditional and modern concepts(or changing?). Their belief and concepts are in a transitional stage. Though respondents still believe about the impact of cosmology, noted percentages of them having a good education, social network have rightly cited the exact reasons for causing these various communicable

diseases. This study clearly demonstrates that social meanings given to the commonly occurring communicable diseases mainly drawn on day to day social experiences and practical knowledge of the respondents. The 'commonly understood idea of communicable diseases relates to other social activities and it cannot be viewed as individualized , biological or psychological phenomena'.

Further this study has found that some interesting factors about a treatment option for the communicable diseases. For Typhoid 14% of them seek medical care from Ayurvedic whereas 23% of them are seeking help from the folk medicines. Some respondents believe Typhoid normally causes due to the intake of contaminated water /food and hence cosmology/deity should be worshiped to solve the problem. The majority of the respondents are seeking allopathic health care for Typhoid and they believe Typhoid causes severe internal disorders quickly. Hence they felt Typhoid should be cured very soon otherwise it may causes more internal damages. Hence majority of them seek western health care which has quick healing power for this problem. Regarding Jaundice more than 26% of them are going for Ayurvedic system whereas more than 30% of the patients are seeking help from the traditional healers. All these because of the established family traditions. Interestingly respondents believe clinical establishment of Jaundice and the majority of them go for traditional medicine only. Respondents generally believe Jaundice causes due to the intake of certain specific food items excessively and they believe Jaundice directly affects on liver and other organs. Respondents opined modern medicines are not suitable in case of curing jaundice because it affects liver. Respondents have strongly believed that only herbal medicine can cure jaundice.

It is also found until curing during treatment stage patients' should observe some sort diet and patients' have to take only cold food items which keeps the body cool. Patients' will not be allowed to have hot food items for any reason. They prefer liquid items as much as possible because both intestine and liver will not be in the position to digest any hard food substances. It shows a clear cut overlapping of both traditional and modern health outlook. Regarding Cholera which is widely prevalent in rural areas during summer 13% of them seek help from Ayurvedic healthcare while 28% of them seek help from traditional medicine, However 45% of them seeking allopathic healthcare for Cholera. Respondents normally believe Cholera causes due to the intake of contaminate food items and water they believe in worshiping cosmology powers and folk medicines.

For Malaria problem 24% of the respondents seek traditional medicine and more than 48% of the respondents seek help from the western medicine. However it

is noted that 11% of them inclined to have Homeopathy medicine for Malaria because of its success rate. Respondents believe Malaria cause due to the insect biting and noted percentages of people also believe pathogens causes Malaria. Since Malaria causes more fever, respondents some time confused with that of Typhoid. Hence, in the majority cases respondents just buy medicines from the drug seller assuming just it is a common fever only. Respondents have the opinion that Malaria affects the blood and during this point of time patients' should have more cold foods and fruits to keep the blood cool. They also opined patients' should not go out of home because the cosmological power attacks the patients'(he/she will be very weak to fight back) and the problem will be more serious. Also villagers opined along with the treatment, worshipping deity is also vital to cure the problem as soon as possible.

Treatment for selected non-communicable diseases has revealed that respondents showing more faith on traditional medicine followed by the biomedical system. For notable percentage of the respondents first choice would be the folk medicine. For the bone related problems, more than 30% of the respondents will not take any treatment whereas, 15% of the respondents for Gastric and 30% for different pains will not take any treatment at all as they wait until natural healing. If not they will go for different medical systems based on the advice given by the family /village elders. Interestingly except for respiratory diseases respondents will try home remedy for certain non-communicable disease. More than 23% of the respondents will seek the over the counter (directly from the medicals hop) medicine for bone related and 18% of them for worm infection consult the drug seller for the medicine. Further for bone related and ENT problems notable percentage (19%) of the respondents, seek Ayurvedic medicines because of its success rate in curing these problems. Treatment seeking behavior of the villagers shows prevalence of strong faith on medical pluralism or different therapeutic behaviors. People always choose the type of treatment mostly based on the advice given by the known people. Respondents are not sticking on to a single medical system rather in many cases they keep changing the treatment pattern. They will use the different medicinal system for a single problem or some time multiple health problems will be treated with a single medical system. In the same way some respondents due to the various external interventions today would visit PHC for cost effective treatment .

Preventive measure is an indicator for the health care seeking behaviour of any community. This study has found that respondents widely believe in conducting health rituals, festivals, satisfying cosmological powers etc. However 16% of them opined self hygiene is more important in the preventive measure while 25% of them

proper health education is crucial in avoiding various diseases. Though in certain cases respondents are aware of health education they are not ready to come out of their age-old cultural beliefs about the onset of the various diseases. This study has found that preventive measure differs according to the caste, income and education level. The respondents belonging to the higher caste shows the higher level of health care seeking behavior (preventive measure) when compared to the other caste people. As the level of education and income increases the respondents are willing to take more preventive measures. Television, presence of educated children, strong social network also plays a role here. Respondents though believe in the traditional medical system they have the strong faith in the western theory of etiology. Though the few respondents are capable for paying more, they are showing more interest in taking the preventive care only. Also irrespective of the level of education and income, some of the respondents strongly believe in conducting various health rituals to satisfy the deities, cosmological powers etc as a precaution.

Further, it is found that the poor health outcome of the rural community needs to be reed within in the context of rapid urbanization, medicalization, growing health infrastructure, rising treatment cost etc. However, in a multicultural society like India, changing rurals' health cultre cannot be analyzed in a contextual vacuum. Instead, they need to be looked in the light of larger changing socio economic changes and migration experienced by rural community over the period of time due to the interventions of various external agencies.

In rural society health, diseases and medicine are in-extricable linked to the area of social relationships and to the magical-religious world. Certain diseases, psychology related disorders illnesses are mostly thought of as a result of the problems of the human beings with the nature and the effect of super natural powers. Only a few types of illness are viewed as being independent of the any cosmological powers. Respondents strongly believe health and illness is a total sum of the social, ethical and cosmic equilibrium etc. Diseases and illness according to respondents causes a kind of disequilibrium in the human body system and in the surrounding societies. This study has found respondents have classified and categorizes the causation of diseases/illness as follows;

1. Diseases/illness caused by the super human causation/cosmology;
2. Diseases caused by the physiological problems(like Humeral imbalance);
3. Diseases caused by the pathogenesis

Because of this classification by the respondents various disease/illness have a particular origin and curing technique in the nature.

It is found that the most vital fact that emerging of everyday knowledge about mental health, Leprosy and T.B is socially constructed and respondent's explanations do not match with the bio medical and psychological orientations. The everyday meaning of the diseases is based on the common domain of the behavior and it can only be judged with respect to the social context in which it occurs.

Respondents opined about the onset of Mental illness, Leprosy and T.B very close to the western etiological view. Respondent's opined, physiological dysfunctions of the body may lead to have mental illness. Respondents not understood mental illness is a part of psycho biological but a social experience and performance of conformity. Respondents have understood mental health means a social problem and cannot be viewed as an individualized (Dixit, 2009). It is found that social behavior on Leprosy and T.B are mostly understood in terms of individual and the society. The lay explanations have important attitude and behavior implications with respect to the individual and the society. Villagers opined there are many types of Mental illness, and they believed erratic and obsessive behavior is explained as mental illness. Regarding Leprosy respondents opined it is a curse given by the deity for the wrong deeds. Villagers also felt problems in upbringing and the socialization of the children/youths only lead to the deviant behaviour which is the main reason for the Mental illness problem in the later stage of the life. Respondent also opined Mental illness is a partially curable whereas T.B and Leprosy can be cured only by satisfying deities or the other types of treatment.

Regarding the impact of certain diseases on different human body parts have revealed few interesting facts. Respondents have a variety of notions influenced by their health culture. It is found that 14% of them opined Cholera affects Morphology of the body whereas 10% of them opined it affects both on the Physiology and Anatomy of the body. Next majority of respondents opined Typhoid leaves more impact on Physiology of the body because they think it largely affect on the intestine. Further, 22% of them opined Jaundice affects on Physiology of the body as it is affects on the Liver. Next more than 19% of them said Malaria affects both on the Physiology and Anatomy of the body. Respondents opined since Malaria affected patients' normal will be physically weak it shows something wrong inside the patients' body. Respondents believe Mental illness affects either on Morphology or Psychology of the patients'. Next, 34% of them opined Leprosy affects largely on Morphology of the body. This view is probably because leprosy leads degeneration of

external organs. All these perception arises out of various socio, cultural and modern education .

It is found that respondents have different notions of etiology and how different disease/illness leaves an impact on different human body organs. In-depth probe has found that a close relationship between respondent's knowledge about the disease and its target organs. As respondents believed Jaundice affects on Liver and respondents think it affect Anatomy of the patient, Next based on the symptoms of the Cholera majority of them opined it affects on the Physiology of the body as vomit/dysentery are the most common symptoms of Cholera. This is a clear cut example to say that symptoms of a particular disease and its target organ/s are based on which respondents themselves experienced or the basis of the family member's experiences or hearing illness narrations of the other patients'. Some time it also depends on the deviant behaviour by the patient in the society. If the patient appears normal, respondents think he/she has no problem with the Morphology but they think might be with the Physiology. If the patient looks weak or tired respondents think specific disease is affecting on the Morphology and not on the Physiology and vice versa. It is found that when disease/illness is first experienced its labeling will be done at the family level and some time by the other village members through the social network. These affects a lot on the part of the individual in developing such a notion in a border social context.

Singh (2009) writes

“the health needs are connected to the respondents social structure and it varies according to the changes observed within the structure. The heath behaviour of a community depends on the attitude, motive and normative outline frequently predisposed by the social, culture and economic issues working within and without the social structure of the community or society. The ethno methodology of the responds therefore goes a long way in providing shape to the working of the health and medical services. It is the ethno methodology which provides motivational aspects linked to the precautionary or remedial health care. Interactions of diverse factors with the physical and cultural environment are crucial in understanding health culture of any community with respect to the changing social structure of the community”.

Health rituals are the part and parcel of any community as a tool for preventive measure. Even in urban and tribal community people perform various health rituals to avoid different diseases. In the rural parts, health rituals will be taking place at community level. Even today in rurals' interference of supernatural agencies is

particularly strong in the context of health and diseases. In rural area each and every caste has particular deity in connection with the various types of diseases and illness. This study has found that during health rituals all village people have to observe norms and the sanctity and normally women will not perform any health rituals. This study has also found that normally health rituals will be conducted by the faith healers belonging to the higher caste only. This study has an observation that higher caste/more educated people will not now show interest to perform any health rituals. People believe once health rituals performed, evil forces causing health disorders will not enter into village any more. Normally health rituals will be conducted to satisfy the different illness causing agencies, including village deity/cosmology etc, we found that lower caste people often performe different rituals worshiping local unknown deities.

MEDICAL PLURALISM

“Growing reputation of complementary medicine in current years is in part owing to people's displeasure with western system. Consumers have a right to choose from the pool of various types of therapies, each of which is unique in its own right. The second kind of meaning refers to pluralism within a particular system. For example, with orthodox medicine, a client has a choice to go to a private or public hospital or to a doctor practicing in a village, or a town, or a distant city. It is this ongoing process of fighting over the better financial reward that misleads the public into thinking that medical pluralism is well and truly pervasive”. Han (2002)

Medical pluralism is an inseparable part of any society. Medical pluralism is a part and parcel of any community too. Understanding the scope and significance of medical pluralism could be required at least from two major levels: 1.individual and 2.societal. Patient's health seeking behavior is enabled and constrained by the medical systems in the social context, but the action, in turn, reproduces or transforms the different medical systems. Availability of more than one type of healthcare /treatment/healing system is normally termed as medical pluralism. Ayurvedic, Sidda, Unaani, Chinese, Tibetans, Homeopathy, Naturopathy etc together constitute medical pluralism as a part of the health care system. It is generally opined that the existence of the strong medical pluralism and its success rate is the main reason why rural respondents even today hesitate to use bio-medicines. Though the validity of a different healthcare system is in question, availability of the different therapies has given more opportunity for the patients' in terms of both cost and quality. Regarding definition It is evident that 18.2% of the respondents said medical pluralism means availability more than one type of medicine while 12.7% of them said using different

medical systems at a time where as 11.8% of them said availability of different medical care system in a given place while 7% of them said different therapeutic treatment whereas majority of them(50%) said no idea about this. It shows only few people knows the exact concept of medial pluralism. regarding Reasons for using different medical systems at a time it is found 16.3% of the respondents said as advised by the traditional healers and faith healers while, 20.8% of the respondents said that they are taking a chance and 27% of them said as advised by the village or family elders. Next 10.8% of them said previous good experienceS is the reason why they prefer to use more than one type of medicinal system while 20.5% of them said as advised by the medical doctors and 4% said hoping either one may cure the problem. It also shows rural people are not very sure why they are opting different medical care. Regarding opinion about quality of medical pluralism available 22% of the respondents said more options for the patients is possible while 11% of them said no such quality in certain system of medical care. Next, of them 21% of them are happy with the Quality of the Homeopathy and Ayurvedic while 22.4% of them Sidda and Unani systems are the best while 5% of them said traditional medicines are only reliable whereas 5.2% of them said no idea at all.

Caste and religion also remarkably affects in accepting different medical care system in rural settings. For example, right from the history Muslim community are using the Unani medical system, whereas Hindus use Ayurvedic system more when compared to the other religion since time immemorial. This study has found respondents have a fair knowledge about the availability of different medical systems in a given area, but have a pale idea about the quality of different medical systems (medical pluralism) in the rural parts. It is revealed only 12% of them opined medical pluralism means availability of more than one type of medical systems or different therapeutic treatments. In the majority cases, respondents in the rural parts knowingly or unknowingly are using more than one type of health care system to cure various diseases or illness. This study has found that different social stratifications have a close association with the different types of healthcare system in the rural society.

Class and caste also significantly play a vital role in accepting or rejecting different kinds of medical systems here. Respondents belonging to the different caste in a multicultural society use a different medical system to cure their health problems. Also we found that Ayurvedic and folk medicine has a substantial base in rural parts. Also Siddha and Unani medical systems exist in the same area. However, it is found that people have more faith in Ayurvedic system rather than another type of systems. It is revealed that based on the previous examples (cost/ duration etc) available, people

normally choose a particular type of medical care in the rural parts. Also respondents felt each disease has a specific type of medical care.

We found that in rural area people will not completely depend on any one type of health care system at all. Some time they go for more than one type of medical care for the speedy healing. Regarding reason/s for using different medical systems, 16% of them opined family elder/healer normally suggests the patients to try with another system of medicine for the safer reasons. If the patient could not afford the expenditure than he/she may look other different option which costs him/her less when compared to the other care. This is also one of the reasons why a patient normal opt a low cost medical care like folk system or a traditional system. For example if the treatment cost in western system is more than the patient's financial capacity, he/she may go for the medicine which is affordable (ex. folk/traditional etc). Some time respondents may not intentionally use pluralistic therapies and people would take a chance thinking either one may cure their health problem as soon as possible. In most of the cases because of low cost, easy to access, and because of cultural sensitivity people would like to use different medical systems. Respondents also opined often opting pluralistic therapies will be based on the advice given by the villagers or family elder members. It is found that Biomedicine and other types of medicinal system actually consider the social genesis and constraints on health and well-being. All types of medieval care system rely on medicines, rather than on social, political and economic transformation to bring about improvements in health and well-being of the people.

In-depth probe on medical pluralism found that, rural sick respondents would like to locate illness events in the total context of once own life and resort to multiple therapeutic system for the speedy recovery which is not a necessary part of the clinical establishment. Regarding pluralistic treatment opted by the respondents most of them opted the combination of Ayurvedic and Homeopathy, Ayurvedic and Allopathic, Folk medicine and Allopathic for various diseases. It is also found that usage of Sidda and Unani system is very rare in many rural parts. For Jaundice respondents use Ayurvedic with another type of Indian system of medicine/bio medicine for speedy treatment. For Malaria 30% of them use both Folk medicine and Allopathic medicines whereas for the viral fever majority of them are used Ayurvedic and Allopathic system of medicine. This shows that respondents have strong belief either in Ayurvedic and Folk medicine and they are using Allopathic also for the safer side. In most of the cases this would be based on the advice through social net work. Probably this kind of changing therapeutic behavior shows respondents are gradually

developing faith in Allopathic medicine. Also due to the strong age-old customs and cultural barriers, respondents are not ready to omit either traditional medicine completely or not ready to accept Allopathic system absolutely.

Regarding quality of available medical pluralism in the study area majority of them have opined Folk and Ayurvedic system along with Bio medicine have a good success rate whereas 21% of them opined Homeopathy and Folk system has a better result. In rural area the majority of the Muslim respondents are using the Unani medical system only for certain diseases. However, respondents gave a mixed opinion about the quality of different medical systems. This study has found some of the respondents were conscious about the safety and side effects of different medical systems co-existing in the same area and it is due to health literacy. Also it is found that rather than the cultural factors, patients' are using the system of medicine having low cost and high success rate of healing. It is found that "always there is a competition, not only within each medical tradition to better demand to, or treat, the patients, nevertheless also between diverse medical services in order to improve each of its reputation against other types" (Unschuld, 1975). Thus, majority rural patients from the low class /caste backgrounds are virtually left with much more limited options except opting low cost medical system. Here socio-economic status of a patient plays a vital role in choosing and accessing competent Physician/ local healer.

Further, probe in the study has revealed that there is no such co-operation among various health care providers and more professional rivalry can be seen. More than that in the name of medical pluralism added fake healers have been emerged in many rural areas. Respondents have opined different healers have their own network having inside adjustments to get more money from the patients. Even though the availability of therapeutic pluralism is affordable to the rural poor across the economic status somewhere different system are creating more confusion to the patients in opting suitable healthcare. It is nothing short of "Forced Pluralism". This study has also found certain medical system have low standard being practiced by less qualified and less competent people in the rural areas. They are not having any license from any medical board/agency. This kind of inappropriate, unethical medical practice may leave a dangerous effect on the patients health and faith. Plan for regulation and action against the unqualified medical practitioner is the need of the hour here.

From the respondents' opinion it seems that rural people still have a complete faith in the ethno medicinal system. However, the majority of them opined though ethno medicine is being used since time immemorial, time has come to use other medical system for the good and valid result. They felt rural society is fast changing.

Tradition, culture and health behavior is also fast changing and pattern disease/illness has also changed in the rural parts. Hence, we need to have new health culture and medical care system. In the race of different medical systems, the ethno medicine gradually losing its prevalence in many rural areas according to the respondents. However, it does 'not mean that respondents have completely shifted to the other medical health care system but they are showing more interest and faith in using western medical care which yields good and speedy results within a short span of time. More than 30% of respondents opined ethno medicine is a reliable health care system, affordable, side effect free and a boon for the poor but it is disappearing day by day. Though western medicine is fast spreading in rurals' life ethno medicine has intervened within the people's health culture and has played a significant role in shaping communities, health seeking and health care seeking behavior since time immemorial. Respondents are not ready to forget the glory of the ethno medicine and its impacts on their life.

TRADITIONAL AND FAITH HEALERS

This study has found different opinions about traditional and faith healers. Respondents have strong faith and respect on both traditional and faith healers. They are the valuable resources as primary health care provider and are readily accepted by the community too. In rural areas there are different healers like Priest, Shaman, Diviner, Herbalist, Bone setter, Midwife etc. These traditional healers play a powerful role in shaping health seeking process of the rural community. They are widely respected and believed by the respondents. Respondents opined they are skilled and experienced in the health care management of the community. Traditional healers are less researched and less exposed today. Healers' have different diagnostic techniques and therapeutic models also. In-depth interview with the traditional healers have found they have a variety of notions and concepts about health and illness. And traditional healers strongly believe diseases and illness are causes due to the humeral imbalance and also noted the numbers of traditional healer opined breaching taboo, angry deity and different pathogenic agents also cause diseases and illness for the human beings. The Reasons for conducting various health rituals, traditional healers opined this would be conducted to neutralize evil effects, pathogenic agents, recreation of disturbed cultural orders, bringing back humeral imbalance and the bodily equilibrium etc.

some specialist healers who have been mastered in a particular healing technique and these specialists treat a number of cases every day and charge much from the patients when compared to other type of healers. They are just like general

practitioners (just MBBS) and specialists (MD/MS) in Allopathic settings. Such specialists are very few in number in rural parts and having own healing model and techniques. These specialist healers will normally handle complex health issues and can give some instant relief for the patients. Once the patient/s' got cured the same patient gradually will act as a spokesmen to propaganda about him and his healing capacity to the other patients' and gradually it spreads across the villages. Normally, traditional healers employ a variety of healing techniques to cure health problems by listening illness narrations, studying the etiology, symptoms etc. Healers treat the patients using holy water, thread, chanting, feeding herbal juice, and medicines using animal and mineral extracts etc.

It is found that traditional healers normally diagnose the problem/s largely based on the external symptoms and the visible bodily changes and the body language of the patients. A healer normally use the medicines which are extracted from the herbs, shrubs, leaves, roots available in that region. Healers administer the medicine based on the severity of the health problem including the gender, age etc. If the problem is due to the humeral imbalance healers normally use the herbal extracts. If the illness/disease is due to an angry deity or spirits or sorcery they will perform the certain rituals including offerings to the deity or satisfying spirit in cash/kinds. In some cases, healers ask the patients' to wear certain holy threads until curing. Different healers use distinct methods in diagnosing, preventive measures and the therapeutic pluralism within an established pattern for the different health problems. Since the different specialist healers available in a given area some time they act as a complementary and some time as a hurdle to each other's therapeutic modes. Female traditional healers are particularly skilled in doing massage and deliveries the babies also.

For certain illness, rural communities exclusively depend on the traditional healers irrespective of caste and class etc. For snake bite, childlessness, bone setting, menses problems, and spermatorrhea people belonging to the different castes and class seek the treatment from the local healers only. In fact, religion and caste "purity" do not seem to be an issue for the patients' to get treatment from any healer. Consultation of Muslim healers does exist by the Hindu patients' and vice versa in many cases. The sick person belonging to the upper caste frequently approaches and receives the treatment from the lower healers belong to the lower caste 'and vice versa if there is no other way. Some time it creates caste clashes among upper, low caste and ethnic minorities in rural parts. Women patients' always prefers to consult a lady traditional

healer with whom they can communicate with ease. To get lady healers they are ready to travel distant places.

Female traditional healers (specialists) have a sex specific role. 'They are generally confined to the lower castes, especially the black smith caste. Female traditional healers are also skilled in handling displaced womb, abdomen, menstrual problems etc. The native theory explains infertility is caused due to the dislocated abdomen. Navel dislocation is another sphere of the female specialists. The abdominal cramps are believed to be caused due to stretch in the abdomen and the female specialists have the ability to skillfully treat these conditions by their massage therapy. The actual practice of a female specialist is very stylish; she has a working knowledge of the pulse through which she diagnoses the problems of the humeral imbalance in the body. The massage involves treatment by stroking, pressing; tapping and kneading (rub) the affected parts. They felt women need to stay out of home during menstrual period.

Local healers are also consulted for the certain social problems for the solutions. For instance, the upper class respondents consult 'local healers about their children unemployment problems, low level or poor crops in their field, childlessness, marriage issues, regular quarrel in the family etc. some time poor people consult the healers to get a solution for their economic hardships. This indicates that traditional healers act as life-mediators for the local communities in ventilating and addressing 'uncertainty' in their life situations.

Regarding the medical pluralism, healers opined it is a good phenomenon and it gives more opportunities for the poor patients'. They promptly opined chances of healing are more in cases of availability of more than one type of medical care system in a given area. Also they opined emerging of fake healers also a big problem in the name of medical pluralism. Some of the healers feared the medical pluralism will create a kind of confusion and using more than one type of medicine may cause some kind of side effects to the patient. Also they admit the traditional healers use some sort of the pluralistic therapy to cure the patients' health issues. Some of the healers also opined Folk medicine; Ayurvedic and Homeopathy are the best medicines for any kind of health problems. Regarding degeneration of traditional healing system, they opined domination of the western medicine is the main reason. And also they admitted due to the slow healing nature of the folk medicines, some time patients does not like it . Due to the strong medical pluralism, today the rural people are showing must interest about the medicinal care which has the more rapid healing power. However few healers confident that since, people are aware of the importance of the traditional

medicines, this medicine would not degenerate so easily. They felt strong Gov't support is required for the sustainability of the traditional medicines in the rural society.

The difficulty has multiple facets making it very significant for the sociologist to unravel the issues. We need to clarify the meaning of medical pluralism in India, and separate its various mechanism. There is need to divide the political from the economic scope of health and medical problems, and to cut off the only medical from the non-medical interventions in health care. One has also to analyze the community's reply to medical pluralism too. Also the misdistribution of biomedical services creates a dilemma among Indian patients. They meet a confusing division of medical services, starting from qualified traditional medical practitioners to untrained, local healers. Research on Indian healthcare has proved that unequal distribution of quality health services in rural and urban areas. It is revealed that ground reality of the consequences of limited choices for patients, widely known as "forced pluralism," with no Govt. regulation of type of care, quality of care, or qualifications of practitioners.

Regarding the scientific training for the traditional healers the noted percentages of them agreed to get a scientific training. While the majority of them denied getting any sort of training and they claimed that they have the mastery of the knowledge about all the diseases and 29% of them opined any scientific training would be kind of breaching ethics and they fear professional sanctity will spoil. Regarding the opinion about the western medicine they felt this health system has more side effects and the poor people cannot afford/accesses it. Also they opined all types of the disease/illness cannot be cured in the western medical system and the western medicine is preferable for the certain cases only. It is found that the traditional healers have a reasonable appreciation towards the western medicine in the mind but they are orally expressing negative opinion about the allopathic system.

Surprisingly it is noted that some traditional healers depend on the clinical establishment of a disease based on that only they will treat the patients'..!. Further, in-depth study has revealed that healers are aware of indigenous medicines are not very safe though it is being used form the generations. Indirectly they admitted that the folk medicines are not standardized and not so safe. However, they opined when compared to the western medicine, the folk medicines are the safest one. They argue that so-far they never come across any safety complaints from the patients'. However, it is found that the usage of raw herbal juice, raw plants, minerals and animal extracts leaves side effects on the patients' in the long run as opined by the some traditional

healers. Hence, we can say rural patients' knowingly or unknowingly taking toxic materials in the name of folk medicinal system.

Focus group interview has revealed many interesting opinions of the community regarding the various health issues. Deeper investigations have revealed about socio-cultural barriers in introducing the modern healthcare facility. Community opined mind set of the rurals' has to change first. Rural people have to develop a positive attitude towards the modern medicines. Also the community opined age-old health beliefs, culture and behavior are not allowing the rural respondents to come out of their pre-mindset. Even though certain respondents are ready to come out of age-old caste and religion taboo, surrounding environment and the local people are not supporting them. It is found that each caste and religion have their own norms in visiting or not to visiting the hospitals for various health issues. The strong influence of general customs and traditions has interlined in the rural' health culture where they are not ready to come out of that influence.

The social organization of the village life itself is a kind of barrier for the widespread usage of modern medicines. Strong informal social network, social organization, low level of education, poverty is playing a complex role as vital barriers in adopting the modern health practices. Moreover, Informal network among the villagers have strongly controlled and obligated the members some time in getting or not to getting the modern medicines. The low level of income and insignificant occupation has created a kind of problems among the rural people in approaching the modern health care. Community opined modern health care system must find a suitable position in the rural society to win the confidence of the rural people. Rural, people will accept the modern medicine if it is very close to their social life, culture and the tradition etc.

Also community opined doctors' and the patients' relationship play a vital role in the rural settings. Western doctors should have more tolerance towards poor, poverty ridden, illiterate rural people. Rural patient's expectations towards the western doctors will be somewhat completely different unlike in the urban areas. In-depth discussion with the community has revealed that formal and informal conflict between the traditional and the western practitioners has become a big barrier in the rural areas in adopting the modern medical services by the local people. Since traditional healers have a strong historical root and background support they are avoiding the villagers in getting modern medicine as opined by the community members. In the same way, poor socio-economic background, the absence of the

health infrastructure, development behaviour, lack of proper health education also become some of the standing barriers in accessing the modern health care facilities.

Though the media have penetrated into the cultural life of the rural people, beliefs, attitudes, values which are the core component of the rural health culture and health seeking behavior have not been completely changed yet. Nevertheless people are positively responding to it. Cretan respondents are adopting modern concept, elements in their age- old health culture and health seeking behavior too despite resistances. Also in certain cases it is evident that family elders are forcefully asking the first and second generations children to follow the same health culture and health behavior. Prevalence of the strong caste systems in rural areas has also become a crucial issue in introducing the modern medicine. Dominant caste people are still influencing various health rituals in many villages for the material gaining. Since each and every caste has their own health culture and behavior, it is next to impossible to bring uniform health education across the community. Failing in understanding social-cultural frame work of the medicine and its relationship with that of the society by the policy makers is also a kind of hurdle in introducing western medicine.

The strong religious belief, strongly rooted concept about super natural power/cosmology, relating to the health issue needs a different understanding and sociological interpretations. Also more vital is socialization possessed which is normally taken place in rural settings. Cultural and traditional history of the families strongly influences in the early stage of any child's development and socializations and it will largely determine the health culture and health behavior of that child in the due course of time. Internalization of health culture also takes place through the process of socialization only. This also significantly counts in accepting and developing a positive attitude towards the modern medical system. Rural' unique social, cultural and economic background in contextualizing the modern medicine in their specific social realm is the need of the hour in understanding the cultural barriers in accepting the modern medical care. Also the role of social institutions, politico – economic and ecological dimensions relating to the rural health issue has many interrelations and constantly interacting as domains rather than as separate realms in accepting modern health care by the rural people today.

Further this study has revealed about how particular caste and religion selects the particular treatment plan. It is found that 45% of SC/ ST community will opt folk medicine whereas only 21% of them opts western medicine while 15% of them opts ISM for their variety health problems. In case of OBC 24% opts folk medicine whereas 47% opts western medicine. In case of others only 19% opts folk medicine

whereas more than 63% opt western medicine. It shows deprived communities still depend on the folk medicine for their health care needs whereas communities or social groups having good socio-economic background have adopted western medical care system.

Regarding the factors focusing in the selection of treatment pattern it is revealed that 18% of them opined it is depend on income while 22% opine it is an education, and 50% opined it is the type of an occupation and 23% said it is the social network which affects a lot in selecting or not selecting the western medical care system as the first choice. Further, 25% of them felt it depends on the income and occupation, whereas 15% with respect to education, while 13% with respect to gender and 11% with respect to social network is largely affect while selecting folk medicine as a first choice. It shows respondents having good occupation, education and social network normally opt modern health care facilities. Gender discrimination is more while opting modern healthcare facility.

This study further probed percentage distribution of the treatment factor by health seeking behavior. Based on the severity of problem more than 14% would like to opt folk medicine while 76% respondents will opt the western medicine. Based on the types of health problem, 28% wil opt folk medicine. Based on the cost factor 55% will opt folk medicine and 39% will opt the western medicine. Regarding the quality health care wise 37% will opt folk medicine whereas 57% of the respondents opt the western medicine for the variety health care issues. Regarding the health beliefs 66% opt the folk medicine whereas 30% opts the western medicine care. Regarding the decision making in choosing a health care system the majority of the respondents followed the family traditions while they selecting the folk medicine whereas more than 61% of the respondents took their own decision while choosing the western healthcare system.

Regarding the relationship between an educational level and the treatment option the majority illiterates have opted Ayurvedic and the folk medicine while 30% of the respondents with the primary education opted Ayurvedic and 20% of them opted the folk medicine. In case of the higher primary level 13% opted the folk medicine and 27% opted the western medicine. High school level and college studied respondents have mostly opted only the western medicine for their health needs often.

We found the level of education significantly affects on the healthcare choices. As the level of education increases, the respondents are trying to opt the western medical care only. Regarding the gender and the type of the treatment seeking

behavior, only 12% of the females have opted PHC's as the first choice whereas 20% of the male respondents opted PHC's as a first choice. Next 64% of the female opt PHC's as a second choice where as 32% male opt the PHC as second choice. Regarding the gender wise decision about the health seeking behavior women mostly will try with the folk medicine than if the other permits they will shift to the western health care system. In many cases they would like to try with a low cost home medicine because of the gender dissemination. While the majority male respondents directly approach the PHC's for the treatment.

Occupational wise selection has revealed some vital issues. The majority of the primary level occupant respondents choose the folk medicine/ home remedy as a first choice. Secondary level occupants have mostly chosen partially the western medicine where as the majority of the tertiary level occupants have chosen the western healthcare only. Since the tertiary level occupants are socially and economically sound they choose only a modern health care system. Whereas the poor formers (primary level occupants) are still depend on the folk medicine only for health needs. The Social, environment and the personal health practices will play an imperative role in selecting the required medicinal care system for their health needs.

Regarding the economic Groupwise opinion about the reasons for causing illness and diseases the respondents belonging to a low economic group opined cosmology and humeral imbalance causes diseases whereas the middle class respondents opined that pathogenic agents and an unhygienic condition causes illness and diseases among the humans. Further, high economic group and the elites have opined the pathogenic agents basically cause various health problems. It shows the level of economic status leads more health education, awareness and attitude can be seen whereas the low economic group respondents still believe in the traditional theories of the health and illness. Regarding the caste wise opinion, the majority SC and ST community people strongly believes the humeral and super natural cause of illness and diseases. However, notable percentages of them opined pathogenic and unhygienic conditions causes' the various health problems. It shows gradually they are keep changing their health concepts(**Tab 167**).

Different economic groups have expressed interesting features about the medical pluralism. The low economic group respondents felt medical pluralism may give an opportunity for the poor patients because of the cost factor. The Elites' also expressed the same view. The majority of the respondents opined the medical pluralism will give more success rate of healing. However, all the respondents opined the medical pluralism has quality problem and eh fake practitioners. The respondents

opined in the rural area, the patients' are being cheated in the name of the medical pluralism. Also the noted percentage of them opined the medical pluralism may lead a kind of confusion among the patients'.

Level of education and the preventive measure have a close association it seems. The Illiterates still stick on to the traditional concepts of the preventive care. Still they believe the worshipping deity/cosmology to solve their health problems. However, the gradual change also seen in their overall attitude due to the various efforts. It is found that as the level of education increases, more inclination towards the modern etiology noticed. Also it is noted that the level of education has not done much impact on certain percentages of the respondents yet. Surprisingly respondents having higher level of education still believe in the deity/cosmology theory to keep healthy. External interventions have made the less educated respondents to believe in immunizations and health education in keeping healthy. Regarding economic group opinion about folk medicine has found some interesting facts. As economic situation improves the respondents are raising issues of safety, standardization with respect to the ISM. Respondents are more cautious about the reliability and the skill of the folk healer/s. The elites opined guarantee of healing in folk medicine is low whereas poor are more confident with ISM like Ayurveda. Even the lower middle class respondents also showed more faith on ISM.

Further awareness about the side effects is more among the elites. It decreases as the economic situation keeps going down. Also the elites opined ISM is only for minor problems and it does not suites to the major and emergency health problems. However, the lower and poor respondents opined ISM is more acceptable because of the low cost. Hence we can derive that low-cost and easy accessibility are some of the reasons why the respondents are more attracted towards ISM. Economic group wise opinion about the modern healthcare found that the lower economic group opined modern health care system has more side effects and only useful in the emergency cases. Also the majority (55%) of the low economic group respondent's opined the modern healthcare is very costly and poor cannot access it. The Elites' opined the modern healthcare facilities safe and easily available. The Respondents belonging to the higher economic group opined that the government should provide generic medicine to the poor at low cost. However, few elites also felt the modern medicine must have more side effects. It shows that the elites and the higher and middle economic group respondents have a positive opinion about the modern health care system, whereas the lower and middle income group people are more concern about cost factor.

Respondents opined modern medical care is a nightmare for the poor people. Private Doctors are exploiting the rural people misusing their health illiteracy weakness in the name of medicalization. It is also found that the rural people are not completely aware of the various free health care facilities available and how to access it. Distance factors and other overhead charges also a key reason why normally the rural poor are disinterested in accessing modern healthcare today. Some time due to the cultural norms rural women do not visit PHC/private clinic. It is found that the respondents belonging to the marginalized sections are facing more socio- cultural resistance in getting modern health care facility. Respondents also opined now-a-days over medicalizations is quite rampant and it is a big barrier in getting the modern health care is. Some of the respondent's opined the modern healthcare is not culturally sensitive and it is not adjustable to the local culture.

From this it is evident that the respondents have mixed and changing opinion about the modern medicines and its usages. It is because of the changing socio-economic background, social network etc. Also respondents opined best an allopathic doctor must be culturally sensitive and he/she must have an open mind in understanding rural patients' socio economic back ground. Doctors must have a nice behavior and must be a patient's friendly. The majority (25%) of them opined the Doctors must be available whenever required. Villagers opined accessing a qualified Doctor on time is becoming a big problem in rural areas and for any emergency some time doctors will not be available to the patients' at rural hospitals. Also villagers' opined the Doctors should charge less consultation and other types of fees.

Respondents opined the best medicine should have certain features. It should be easily available like traditional medicine and whereas 27% of the respondents opined it should be easy to use. There should be no complex procedure and no diet norms. Some of them opined it should be less bitter and should be no side effects. This study has found that respondents are false aware about the side effects of modern medicine and it is due to the rumors spreading by the traditional healers for their survival. In total, best medicine should be a low cost one and must have quick healing power also as opined by them.

Availability of low cost generic medicines at selected rural locations is required and creating awareness against traditional healers falls rumors about modern medicines is need of the hour. People are little bit aware about over medicalizations. Over 50% of them opined because of medicalizations respondents cannot access to the modern health care where factor cost is a vital issue. People were worried about spreading medicalizations. Some of them alleged this situation is created by the

western Doctors to earn more money. Drug sellers also have joined with the Doctors they said.

An attempt has been made to examine the perception of the rural beneficiaries about the quality of healthcare in the local village PHCs. This study has revealed a number of critical problems: normally doctors are not available on time at the PHCs. There is a high vacancy rate for medical personnel's, especially in case of Nurses (43 per cent), Pharmacists (52 per cent), and Lab technicians (23 per cent). Patients' must purchase the drugs from outside the medical shops even though they are entitled to get the free medicines at hospitals. It is found that the patients' are prescribed drugs in quantities below the standard prescribed size. Required fund for the purchase of the drugs is circuitous. Delay in the receipt of funds for drugs by the district health office and in the procurement and delivery of the drugs to the PHCs has many problems.

The majority of the respondents felt they visit PHC's to get their children free vaccinations and 11% of them visit PHCs for the natal and neonatal health care issues whereas 12% of them visits PHC for the treatment of the minor injuries, while 19% of them visit PHC's to get the free medicines only. Female visit PHC rarely because of non availability of the lady doctors. If the traditional healer could not solve the problem then only the patients' visit the PHC's. It is found that only 12% of the respondent visit PHC's on their own decision. Otherwise in the majority cases respondents visit PHC's when they are forced to visit or as suggested by the healers/ friends/ relatives etc... It shows the respondents in the majority cases don't like to visit PHC's for any health problems because of the various socio-cultural reasons. Regarding the acceptance of the treatment in PHC's, it is found that 37% of them have opined they are accepted with full confidence/willingness. Some of the respondents have opined they are uncomfortable with PHC's but they are accepted the treatment half mindedly. Some of the respondents opined that they have no option except visiting local PHC's because of failure of the traditional medicines or ISM in solving their health problems. Some of them also strongly opined rather than the government hospitals today the rural areas need more private hospitals.

It is found that 26 percent of the rural respondents prefer to visit nearby private health centers because of the non-availability of the regular staff, equipment, medicines and diagnostic facilities at local Govt. PHCs. It is also found that the factors like rude behaviour of the staff, distance factors, transport problem, long waiting hours, and the non availability of the women physicians are some of the other reasons why rural beneficiaries do not show interest in visiting village PHCs. These findings are corroborated with another study conducted in Karnataka on PHCs which

concluded that non availability of adequate man power; finance and equipment were some of the prime reasons why rural people have negative perceptions about the local PHCs. Also they opined indifferent attitude towards rural people by the medical staff largely impacts on the mindset of the rural patients'. Further, doctors don't like to be deputed to the rural areas. On the other hand, PHCs staff members also expressed their problems including lack of proper accommodation, lack of amenities at PHCs, poor quality buildings, transport problem, inadequate supply of both medicines and the equipments, and the bureaucratic issues delay in transferring the physicians and other staffs frequently, insufficient or untimely supply of medicine etc .

In India where the rural people were significantly altered socially and culturally by the British colonization, it is the crucial and very important to understand the social and cultural consequences of the colonization and how these have altered the health culture and the health behaviour of the rural respondents historically and thereby (Marrone, 2007). Community perceptions using the focus group technique found that cultural heterogeneity has the strongest influence on the health culture and health behavior of the rural respondents than religion. The regional specific cultural health model may be presented in a culturally, linguistically and regionally appropriate format by the health policy makers in introducing the modern health care facilities. The rural areas will be normally predominated by the different marginalized social and cultural groups. These groups are living with the other major cultural groups i.e living with the other major cultural influence and surrounding beliefs about the health may account for liking or disliking the modern health care system.

It is interesting to note that since the rural marginal groups always under the huge influence of the other major culture it will try to retain their age-old health culture and health behaviour against the major culture. The major culture always uses the modern medicine for their any health problems because of the power. The illness ideology of the lower caste will be differing from the major always. Low caste or marginalized groups will be treated for illness from a major ideology/theory of illness derecognizing their health culture. Although the established castes have facilitated inter linkages across the rural areas, caste specific cultural variations have occurred whereby respondents belonging to the particular caste in the same region share the similar elements of the health culture. As Murthy (1996) opined '*a similarity between different caste groups from the different rural areas but also similarities of the local health culture that may be more deeply rooted and shared by the other caste groups living in the local region*'.

Further, this study felt more probe about changing health norms, values and ideologies among various social groups due to the various modern interventions in the rural areas and what are the factors causing them to be this in accepting or rejecting modern health care facilities is urgently required. Hence, health culture and health behaviour expressed as a social construction such as gender, kinship, rules, rights and rituals can be better analyzed sociologically. Also in understanding how this construction embodied in their daily health care, health behaviour, and its relationship to the emerging health problems can be better interpreted and can be incorporated in the new health care policy.

Community also expressed its concern about the various health communication barriers. Effective health communication between the patients' and the healthcare providers is very vital in a rural setting where majority of the rural people are illiterates. Effective language or lack of good communication is the major obstacle for the rural people in accessing the modern healthcare system on time. The language problem is also a socio-cultural barrier. It is found that the language barrier between a medical doctor and patients' play a vital role in understanding the health problem and the feedback from the Doctor. Some of the patients' in this study have expressed their opinion how they have been underestimated and discriminated by the modern healthcare providers because of their illiteracy and the lower social status. They had to face the discordance, weak identity, less preference, negligence etc both in the Govt. and in the private hospitals. Hence, it is a vital importance that the medical doctor must be in the position to understand the patients' problem, beliefs, ethics etc in the local language. Since the modern health care system needs to work in a cultural diverse setting like rural parts, physicians are increasingly confronted with the patients from the different cultural back ground. Hence the doctors must be culturally sensitive.

Sometime differing in cultural values between the patients' and the Doctor has a significant effect on accessing or continuing the modern healthcare. This is the most common among the patients' belonging to the margin and minority community having experience of the health discrimination in the rural society. Some of the respondents opined they would have received the better medical care if they would have had the better communication skill and the socio economic background. The medical staff in Govt. PHC's will disrespect the rural patients' based on their socio economic, caste and health illiteracy some time. Probably the best solution would be to post /depute culturally diverse doctors having a substantial rural background to rural the PHC's. It can decrease the cultural gap between the patients' and the Doctor.

Further, this study has found that the low health literacy in the rural area also one of the barriers in introducing the modern health care system. Because of illiteracy rural people cannot understand the instructions given by the medical doctors. This leads the confrontation between them so that the same patient may deny visiting him again. Later on the Doctor would realize due to the health illiteracy patients' could not understand the complex medical instructions. This health illiteracy causes due to the lack of educational opportunity, proper awareness, interest etc... Hence in the rural areas Doctors need to explain everything in layman's /local terms.

Community opined some other factors for the poor health status other than the socio-cultural is the poor health infrastructure in the rural parts. It has become a major problem in the rural areas where the majority of the PHC's doesn't have the necessary facilities. Also we found absence of health education and the health participation among the local people also major a reason for their poor health status also their pre-occupation with other work like agriculture, rain crops, etc where health issue is a lost topic to be focused on. Also majority rural areas today are facing various infrastructure problems like, road, power and communication and other health infrastructure. etc. Apart from these factors, the community opined the long standing poverty and illiteracy also causes more health problems in the rural areas. Government ignorance and corruption in the various health programmes counts a lot in the poor health status of the rural people too.

Due to the poverty and illiteracy the respondents are not aware of the significance of the modern healthcare facilities. Community has given a variety of suggestions about the western medical system for the rural people. Establishment of the multi doctor centers at the rural locations is highly recommended. Community also opined rural PHC's must have sufficient facilities. Community also opined the modern health education especially through the folk media can be done (drama/dance/street play). The Community is in favor of providing government support for the medical pluralism including the safety and the standardization of the various indigenous drugs and the healing techniques. Further, community opined that medical practices among the rural people have been changing in its basic ideology and treatment procedure in the recent times. It is probably due to the rapid medical pluralism and its easy availability and increasing success rate. This medical pluralism has done tremendous changes in the basic ideology of health and illness among the rural people. It is evident that the socio-economic status of the majority of the rural people have changed because of good occupation, income, education, interventions of mass media, awareness, globalizations et. All these have considerably contributing for

the changing health culture and behavior of the rural respondents today. Nowadays some rural people are not sticking to any one type of medical system. They have a variety of therapeutic choices which are affordable and easily accessible now. Community opined that overlapping the different healthcare systems in a given area are the vital issue today. Though the variety of therapeutic choices gives variety options to the patients' at the affordable cost quality is a more vital issue today for the few people.

Community felt people are aware of the side effects of the various medical system and the untrained practitioners. Fake doctors practicing the different medical system exploiting rural' innocence has become a big problem. Regarding suggestion for improving health behavior of the rural respondent's community unanimously opined creation of proper health awareness, health infrastructure and patient's friendly Doctors are in the need of the hour. This health awareness creates preventive measures. Also culturally suitable western medical model is very essential.

The most core part of this study was to elicit community opinion about the impact of the socio-economic factors on health seeking behavior. Respondents have strongly agreed economic factors shapes health culture and health behaviour of any community. Economic factors are the vital issue in accessing various healthcare systems due to lexicalizations. patients' need to pay more money for the quality health service today. Even folk healers also more /less charge much equal to a western Doctor. Economic factors like good income and occupation decides in opting quality healthcare service . Community also opined various social factors like gender, caste, education, and social network also play a crucial role in shaping health seeking and healthcare seeking behaviour of the community. Due to the lower economic vulnerability, women are not in the position to seek any required quality health care. Many health norms and the regulations imposed on women in the rural society so that women cannot get any required healthcare facility without the due permission of either husband/ in-laws. Community also felt caste is a decisive factor in getting any required healthcare in rural settings even from the PHCs. Community opined even traditional healers also discriminates between the different castes today. Respondents belong to the lower caste opined higher caste people forcefully applying their health norms on the lower caste people.

The community also opined level of education is crucial, general education leads health literacy so that more health education is possible. Educated people can get more knowledge on various health care issues including his/her family members will also be benefited. The social network is a very vital issue today in the rural side

because of various communications devise. Good social network brings exchange of information accessibility to quality health care etc. Community opined due to the strong network among the community members preventive health care is always possible today.

Further, community opined about remedial measure to improve the health behaviour of the rural people. Around 24% said create awareness using media is most vital so that people may adopt more preventive healthcare measure. Also we need to focus on inventing culturally suitable western medical system whereas 26 % the community opined scientific training for the traditional healers is must. Also they opined various health programmes and its awareness can be effectively implemented with the help of these healers where they have been widely respected in villages. Also they opined more research on effective interventions in their health culture. Further community opined about new health policies for the rural people. They said efforts made to devise new systems or patterns of institutions by which the access of rural to modern care should be enhanced.

Also provision for synthesis of Indian systems of medicine with the western medicine is need of the hour. Further, they viewed proper planning, implementing and monitoring of rural health programmes is required otherwise real beneficiary may not get enough service. Community asserted a lot of scope for decentralization of the health care policy is very essential today. Regarding the new health policies for the rural people, 42% of the community opined efforts should be made to devise new systems or patterns of institutions by which the access of rural to modern care should be enhanced while 20% of them opined synthesis of Indian systems of medicine with the modern medicine should be integrated so that cultural framed health care model may be provided also they felt all modern facilities should be available at all PHCs and the scope for the scientific training for the traditional healers is must. Regarding NGOs strategies for the rural health promotion 25% of the NGOs felt people are working collaborating with the local self help groups and PHCs whereas 20% of the NGOs are doing action research and giving policy suggestions to the Govt. while 35% of them acting as real implementing agency while 20% of them running mobile health units, awareness creation work .

Also scientific training for the traditional healers will give an edge. Since the traditional healers are widely respected in the rural areas some sort of health awareness programmes can be implemented through them. More involvement of the local NGO's also can bring more positive results because NGOs can understand ground culture and the problems of the rural respondents. Community also opined

there should be an immense scope for people's participation in the upcoming health policies including programmes to remove barriers in accessing modern health care. Synthesis of Indian system of medicine with the western medical system might yield more good result. Community also concerned about proper implementation and monitoring of the various rural health programmes. The Government has brought so many health programmes for the rural areas. However, absence of proper implementation and the monitoring system has become a major reason for the failure of many programmes. Probably more effective decentralization of the health care programmes is highly required so that the people can manage their health issues more effectively.

Respondents have mixed opinions for not accepting the modern medicine. It seems respondents don't have either complete faith or complete unfaith on the modern medicine system. They have the variety of notions around the modern medicine. It is found that 21% of them opined modern medicine has more side effects and this causes future health problems. Some of them rejected modern medicine stating it doesn't suits to the nature of their body system. Villagers opined modern medicines are violating our traditional medical system.

Respondents are not showing much interest to use the modern medicines because they are very costly, not easily accessible and modern medicines have more formalities in the usage. Hence, respondents might reject the modern medicines. Reason for accepting traditional medicine or folk medicine is because they are low cost and have no side effects. It is found that the respondents have some traditional beliefs about folk medicine. Folk medicines are easy to use and easily available and low cost too. Unlike the western medicine there are on formalities in using folk medicines. Since folk medicines have a strong history in its existence and usage, the respondent's opined folk medicine is highly reliable. Also folk healers always available in the village and they can be contacted at any time unlike the western doctors who are have having a particular visiting hours at hospitals.

We interviewed some of the respondents who are not having faith in folk medicines and who does not visit traditional healers. These respondents opined traditional healers are not the experts actually. Their knowledge is purely based on some traditional beliefs/texts. Respondents are not ready to believe traditional healers for a variety of reasons like they are illiterate, lack of specific medical knowledge, illiterates, fear of side effects, fear about the mode of their treatment etc. Some villagers have had bad experiences with the irrational healing system following by the traditional healers. These respondents have a strong belief about the western theory of

origin of the diseases and illness and they visit PHC's or the private health clinics and they have a good socio economic background, income, educational level and referral system.

It is also remarkable to note that some of the respondents showed interest about allopathic treatment only for the specific diseases. Where, there are no specific medicines available in the folk system then only respondents will go with allopathic treatment. They opined certain diseases need speedy recovery otherwise they may create more problems. Also sometime traditional healers suggest patients' to get the allopathic care only. In some cases, respondents' sought allopathic care as suggested by the friends and other relatives. It shows that good social networks also affect on the health seeking behavior of the rural people.

It seems rural people have gradually realizing not all diseases or illness cannot be cured by the folk medicine alone today. It seems villagers are gradually recognizing significance of the modern health care system and showing more interest in it. Regarding the western medicine, respondents gave a mixed opinion. the majority of them said modern medicine is highly costly, whereas 40% of the respondents opined allopathic medicines are more reliable and has no side effects and but it is only for the rich people. Respondents opined a common man cannot afford any modern medicine today. Some of them strongly felt the modern medicine has no side effects. They felt today Doctors have become the money mongers and they charge heavily even for the small health problem. Those respondents who had previous bad expressions with the modern healthcare system also add their voice to this. Those who had to face the side effects are generalizing that the western medicine has more side effects and it should not be used frequently. Majority of the respondents have opined they had to lose a lot of money but the health problem/s could be solved. Hence they have more negative opinion about the modern medicinal care.

While interviewing with the PHC staff it is found that the villagers don't visit PHCs because of lack of knowledge, shyness, fear etc. They visit PHC when the problem gets serious/worst. They also opined since PHC have certain fundamental problems normally some time villagers would like to visit nearby private clinics only. Also they felt villagers don't visit PHC unless the problem is serious. Regarding the usage of the traditional medicine, PHC staff opined these medicines have not been standardized and found unsafe in many cases. It may lead some types of side effects on the internal organs of patients'. PHC staff opined an integration of both the traditional medicine and the western medicine has more advantages in the rural areas. Due to these phenomena, the overall cost of the medicine would be low and it will be

more affordable to the every rural poor. PHC staff opined traditional healer's need some training so that they can identify the problem/s correctly in time. Regarding the opinion about the new referral system between the hospitals and the traditional healers, PHC staff opined more structured framework and full involvement of the traditional healers are required in this case. And more awareness about the use of modern health care must be created among the rural people.

Barriers and Challenges for Implementation of Health programmes from the Gender Perspective

It is found that over the last two decades, a large number of new programmes have been adopted focusing gender approaches with respect to the health care aspects in India stressing the better reproductive and maternal health care. Most of the programmes have been implemented focusing rural women because of their vulnerability status. For example Janani Suraksha yojana (for safe baby delivery) and some other also such a type of the programme designing and implemented focusing the gender issue. This JYS has been endeavor within current normative structure to improve outcomes for women's reproductive health in a conservative society like India. We found that there are various socio-cultural barriers including health behaviour and health care seeking behavior, health culture, assets ownership, financial autonomy, household decision making and freedom of movement have become some kind of hindrance in the successful implementation of various health polices (Thansia and Seemanth, 2009). We felt that effects of financial status and household autonomy invariably affects on institutional or home based delivery especially in rural parts of the country. Further, it is found that low literacy level among young rural mothers also one of the biggest challenges in implanting various women health programmes. Remoteness, traditional health seeking behaviors, socio-cultural factors, occupation, lack of publicity about the scheme, complex procedure, castes factors are some of the other barriers and challenges Further, it is revealed the level of education and health behaviour of the husband and the mother- in- law also very crucial factors in implementing the various women related health programmes and have been failed gender point of view in rural part of the country (Mutharayappa, 2010;Guptha,2011).

Influence of traditional healers, traditional birth attenders', allocation of duties between the men and women in rural society, existing gender inequalities, lack of sufficient numbers of women health workers, lack of training for the health personals etc are some of the critical issues in case of implementing various modern health schemes. In the majority cases pre natal and postnatal care will be largely depend on the decision and attitudes of the husband and in-laws, without their permission a

pregnant women cannot take own decision regarding place of delivery too. Hence, more social mobilization and pro-active interventions are required focusing the traditional health culture of the rural people to get better result in case of various modern health programmes. Apart from the gender transformative maternal health programme, there is a need for study on how assets, women empowerment, occupation and decision making power will play a role in accepting modern health care system among the traditional families.

Women's active participation in tackling healthcare issues is offering new views on how women's educational level plays a vital role in accessing and accepting health programmes. Illiterate women are least bothered about anti-natal and post natal care in the rural parts. Also women occupation and income have a positive effect on the maternal health and it is connected with the reduced rate of maternal mortality and morbidity in the rural areas. Since women face more discrimination and the concept of "male child " is more prevalent among the rural people, health scheme should have many more benefits including free health insurances for the both mother and the female baby. Further, evidence of the association between the maternal health and the violence against women has been accumulating since the early 1990's. Also psychological / emotional abuse on youth mothers in traditional families deprives her from getting a modern health care facility.

The sub-ordinate status of women in the Indian society deeply influences her health status. Emphasis is being given the biological aspect (child bearing) leads to an early marriage, unwanted pregnancies, abortions poor pre-and post natal maternal problems. Jha, (2012) opines "the gender dimensions has often been absent and epidemiological approach missing. The social and gender pedigree of maternal health do not ever register". The sustained prejudice against women, social exclusion, high illiteracy rate, ignorance in accessing free services, low health awareness, low motivated development behavior, societal denial in accessing to resources as well as to quality health services has unconstructively distressing as barriers for a rural women in accessing the modern health schemes.

The age old cultural-temporal sequencing of the various naturally occurring reproductive processes among the women residing in traditional set-up is severely altered by the compulsive intervention of the excessively medicalized technologies of the day. These technologies are more often governed by the policies and programmes which are target driven, top-down and completely torn apart from the cultural contexts of their clients. The western biomedicine which runs as the common thread encompassing all the levels of public healthcare in India seriously impinges upon the

existing notions of gender relations and motherhood. This has resulted in a kind of medical governance characterized by a highly structured and systematic “othering” or “marginalization” or the “exclusion” of women’s reproductive healthcare at the grass roots. In order to counter this kind of challenge, which was more systemic in nature, an initiative strongly backed by the civil society, NGOs, feminist organizations and various other subaltern and indigenous communities led to the emergence of a new approach called “Reproductive Health” in the field of Population Development. The approach was thought to be more innovative, inclusive and holistic in its outlook. However, serious anomalies still exist that have relegated the women’s reproductive healthcare when it comes to the actual implementation of this approach.

In fine, few author tried to focus more on the interaction between women and the medical personnel’s wherein the former are more dependent on the latter vis-à-vis medicalization making way for the women’s exclusion. Normally it has been observed that, shifting occupational patterns, formal education and institutional healthcare itself have affected the reproductive healthcare at the grass roots. However, there are very few studies to illustrate the opposite, that is, the mechanisms through which the indigenous beliefs and practices of reproductive healthcare have in turn affected the above stated domains of life. The central focus of any study should stress on the governance based systemic exclusion of women is not an extraneous phenomenon, it is as much an internal phenomenon as is the traditionally based social exclusion. And to view it as a separate one way process would only lead to unrealistic conclusions. Jha, (2012) further writes *“there is a requirement to place women’s health in the overall macro parameter gender divide in the access of health care and health cost is so sharp that women have to access informal providers and informal care”*.

The status of women health in India has been subject to many great changes over the past few millennia. From equal status with men in ancient times through the low points of the medieval period to the promotion of equal rights by many reformers, the history of women in India has been eventful. Woman of our country have faced the discrimination from the ages and still continue to exist in various forms .Any denial of equality in health care, gender and opportunity on the basis of gender discrimination in health care. Nature does not discriminate men from women but women in Indian not only in terms of social or political rights but also on the ground of their basic essential needs. Due to this Indian women faces many challenges during their childhood for their survival and they are faces many medical problems from their early child hood. Gender discrimination in health care very much widespread in

uneducated social backward class group in India. So it needs more efforts to remove from the roots.

Finally we can say there are numerous political, cultural, social, economic and educational problems of this rural community, but the important problems are related to health and nutrition development. The main problem is their ignorance and illiteracy. As they are coming in contact with outsiders, they are being treated like a commodity. Their social and cultural structure is being disturbed and disorganized and hence their health culture is being changed now. To improve the rural health status many health related development programmes (ex, NRHM)) have been introduced but the result is zero. Although, much work has been done in the fields of economic, social and political spheres, yet there is a great need to work on the various health issues focusing rural folks in India.

We think rurals' health culture and its impacts on health is insufficiently understood and studied in India (Nanjunda, 2016). It is established that some of the ways that culture has been considered in (rural) health, and states that culture is either used vaguely and broadly. For example, there is a rural culture, or hardly - certainly maybe interchangeably with ethnicity. It is known factor that although culture is a vibrant social concept, it has been adopted into a biomedical research paradigm as though it is fixed. Culture is often treated as something that can be addressed through cultural sensitivity/compatibility health education. It is suggested that culture is like an unaddressed 'elephant in the room' in the rural health issue, that exploring and emerging soci-cultural differences and beliefs. Cultural differences are critical in truly understanding and addressing the rural health and health system challenges today.

Culture determines to a large extent not only the type and frequency of disease/illness but also the way people perceive, explain and treat diseases as well as the manner in which they respond to the modern medicine. Thus, culture is an invariable determining factor of a community understands of health and illness. Every culture, regardless of its simplicity or complexity, has its own conception of health, illness and health seeking behaviour, which is referred to as 'health culture' – a component of the overall culture of the community (Kar and Gogoi, 1993). The socio-religious medical responses to illness in various forms-including the belief forms recognized, conducts approved – make the health culture. As a part of this health culture, members of each community tend to build up a specific concept relating to several illnesses /diseases recognized by them. The symptom recognition, assessment and health decisions associated to retrieval of health recuperation are

predisposed by belief frames connecting to disease caution, multiply, diagnosis, and cure of each of the a lot of categories of diseases recognized.

This study has shown that poverty, illiteracy, malnutrition, lack of potable water , sanitary conditions, poor mother child health services, problems in covering national health and nutritional services, etc. have been found most vital causative factors for the prevalence of sever childhood mortality and morbidity amongst the studied rural communities. Despite the marvelous development focusing preventive and curative medicine, the child healthcare delivery services in several rural parts is still in poor and unscientific and needed to be further strengthened in order to achieve the goal of health for all in the country by 2020.

CHAPTER VIII

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The **Introductory chapter** briefly explains the importance of the topic, the statement of the problem, objectives, methodology, conceptual framework of the study, limitations of the study

The **Second** chapter deals about research methodology

The **Third chapter** provides a review of the literature related to the study. The related studies are classified into four groups namely,

- (i) Studies relating to health status, consisting of studies related to the socio economic and other factors that determine the health status of rural people,
- (ii) studies relating to health culture, health behavior
- (iii) (studies relating to medical pluralism, consisting of different systems of medicine
- (iv) Other related health studies focusing rural health issues.

The **Fourth chapter** deals about solid background on health culture, health behavior and medical pluralism in the rural context.

The Fifth chapter discusses about theoretical perspectives on sociology of health illness. It provides an over view about various health belief models, approaches and theories including medicalizations and other factors affecting on rural health culture

The **Sixth chapter** deals about result and discussion. It is the major chapter of the study and has been divided into four sub chapters ;

- i): Social, Economic, Demographic factors of the respondents
- (II) General Health status, practice of the respondents
- (III) Health concept, culture, medical pluralism and health behavior towards various illness/diseases
- (v) Relationship between various social determinants and health behavior

The **Seventh chapter** gives a picture of summary and conclusion and

The Eight chapter deals about major findings and policy suggestions

White (2002) opines

“Sociologists show how diseases could be differently understood, treated and experienced by demonstrating how disease is produced out of social organization rather than nature, biology, or individual lifestyle choices only”

Health and illness are two antagonistic concepts, one defined as the lack of the other. It can be said that these two concepts lie on two opposite poles of the continuum. Health in general is understood as absence of illness. Illness is a socio-culturally defined exit from health and it can be differentiated from disease, which is a biomedical category. Anthropologists' concern would be more towards illness rather than disease since illness is a prejudiced occurrence related the social and cultural factors, where as disease is an objective phenomenon defined purely in bio-medical terms by the medical professionals. The response to illness – illness behaviour – is the way in which symptoms are perceived, evaluated and acted upon. This may vary from one individual to another. However, this behaviour is also greatly influenced by the culture, of which the sick person is a member.

The aid of the medical sociologists so far is mostly with regard to illness, though sickness involving disease and /or illness is their actual field. In the final analysis, there is substantial interdependence and interpenetration between the sphere of individuals or persons and that of people and their culture. When sickness is defined as the process through which worrisome behavioral and biological signs, predominantly ones originating in disease, are given socially familiar meanings, the importance shifts more to culture and society. After all, it is the exact culture which provides a specific group of socially bound people with ways of thinking and creates a significant existence for them. Cultural manifestations imitate the human ability to widen behaviour patterns in the milieu of each and every ecological niche.

Health and disease is the two noteworthy dimension of behaviour. If the former is characterized by a sense of well-being, the latter, by a feeling of distress. During the life-time, every individual traverses through health and disease. It is not an all-or-none type of occurrence but a relative location that explains whether the individual is healthy or un healthy. The individual perception of health status is largely a psychological phenomenon. In spite of the beginning of disease process, an individual may not even perceive it at a point of time. An organic disorder may not at all involve an individual until it is perceptible. Conversely, without any organic disorder, an individual may report himself to be unhealthy. Thus, logically, disease

and health may co-exist in the same individual. These two are not just equally exclusive entities

The study of rural health culture is very significant due to the various reasons. The study of changing dynamics of medical pluralism and health seeking behavior among the rural people from the medico sociological point of view is very significant because of various health problems and practices to cure it are largely influenced by the complex inter play of social, cultural, economical and political factors . Studying health culture from the sociological point has certain dimensions. The first one is sociology and medicine which focus on the contribution of sociological knowledge to the diagnosis and treatment options to cure disease. Next, sociology of medicine focuses itself within sociological study of the medical profession. An in-depth study of health culture of any rural community will help in understanding complete knowledge of etiology, onset of the various discuses/illness healing procedure etc.

We conclude that disease or illness is made of social responses rather than an organic malfunction. Illness or sickness largely determined by the historical, cultural, social and geographical context in the rural parts. Also health behaviour some time might be of hereditary/customary. Sickness behaviour will be normally used as a tool to differentiate between diseases as a pathogenic category and illness as a social aspect. Today rural people are gradually showing significant adoption to the modern medical system for their any health issues and hence the sociologists are closely monitoring these adaptations with respect to the health seeking behaviour and the health care seeking behaviour in a given society. Even though there are several scientific reasons behind disease and illness, sociology assumes society significantly determines sickness as well. In the past society and culture had some informal criteria's to legitimate an illness. This does not hold good today. We feel some time misunderstanding happens regarding the ideology about diseases between the physician and the patients'. i.e. patient will think disease/illness might have been occurred due to the folk reasons. Doctors opine it is due to some other scientific reasons. Here rural doctors lack cultural sensitivity. Doctors normally believe approval of any disease/illness as a legitimate if it is diagnosed duly by the scientific methods only today.

All these factors have vital significance in every rural health culture. The significance will depend on the nature of collectivism adopted for different health

culture. Sometime this significance will be linked to the history, origin and philosophy of a particular health culture which helps in shaping his/her behaviour with other fellow men and physical world [Usku,1990]. There are some health cultures which promotes separation of individuals from their social and physical environment completely. In this case psycho-sociology process of illness will get much focus. In the same way health culture that focus or promotes good relationship between an individual or his/her fellowmen in the society. In some cases physiological process of illness will be given low priority. It is found that concept on health and illness will be based on the collective surrounding environment, spiritual background, history of the family etc. have found true in this study also (Uskul, 2000; Duric 1994).

We found that some of the development activities in the rural areas determine the economic status of the people and finally leads to adopt a new changing socio-cultural pattern. This aspect also impact on the health system and health culture of that community. Hence this issues needs to be studied from the sociological view point. Since the rural society is multicultural one, understanding socio-cultural and socio-economic condition plays a vital role in framing locally suitable health care module but this module must be present within their cultural milieu only (Bir,2002 and Banerji,1990). At the more practical level, scientific study on beliefs and practices will play a vital role in framing culturally acceptable health care interventions for the rural people at the doorsteps. Any study on health cultural is very important because.--

A, Interplay of different factors about the onset and healing of certain diseases.

B. It is highly impossible to implant the scores within getting knowledge of peoples' health culture.

Even through different types of medical system available in the society, choosing of particular type of medical system is largely governed by the socio economic status and gender. In majority cases diagnose of illness and its seriousness would be the crucial factors in choosing specific therapy. If the problems are minor, patients' may likely to visit local healer only in rural settings. If it is of multiple syndrome people would like to visit biomedical system. Normally long standing culture and beliefs directly or indirectly intertwined with the peculiarities of the illness and health decision depends on social, economic and cultural factors. In the rural areas, in most of cases, patients satisfaction and skill of the healer would be very vital in determining any type of health behaviour (Ahmed, (2000); Sadiq,(2002);

Ndyomogyenyi, (1998). However, Rahman and others(2001) have found that no such big variations in using various medical health care facilities with reference to class and caste in the rural areas can be seen because of social mobilizations. They felt poor people will normally go for traditional healing and well off people will use modern facilities.

Background of the household head and types of diseases are some vital factors in choosing modern health care system in rural parts. Educational and Occupation and level of the household head normally will be deceive (Rahman, 2011; Ahmed, 2003). Existence of medical pluralism in a single cultural domain will be significant factors in rural areas also as we seen. It is found that any community will accept and treatment/system when it is low cost, easily available and based in the types of disease patient will decide about choosing better medical system. Before selecting any type of therapy patients' will evaluate all different medical system having above mentioned features. All this process gives an edge to any disease and relevant treatment as societal acceptable out comes. After having an effective curing each individual patient will narrate his/her own illness experience (Bode, 2011). Finally it would be publicly accepted, recognized and approved. Traditional coated notions of distress also play a vital role in forming disease into illness. This will also help in understanding, labeling and healing a particular type of disease/illness and it's how health culture gradually constructs/evolves /develops in a society.

The study has found many interesting factors. In case of educational qualifications 35% of the respondents have studied up to primary level whereas 23% have studied up to higher primary level. Next, 9% have studied up to high school and 22% of them are illiterates, regarding occupational status it is found that 49% of them are working in agricultural sector while 4% of them are working in various factories and 20% of them are working in non-form sectors while 6% of them working in unorganized sector and 12% of them are working as daily wage laborers in cities.

In case of monthly income of the respondents more than 40% of them are earning between Rs. 2,000-3,000/- where as 31% of them are earning Rs.3,000-5,000/. while 15% of them are earning between Rs. 5,000-7,000/- It is found that monthly income of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health concept, health care choice and allied issues of the respondents. In case of Caste classification 24% of the respondents belong to Scheduled Caste and 20% of them are

Lingayaths(a caste) while 33% of them are Gowda(a caste) where both of them are very dominant caste group in the studied villages. Caste of the respondents has got a statistically significant influence over the health concept, behavior and allied issues of the respondents. In case of family structure it has been found that only 41% respondents belong to the families having 4 members while 43% of the respondents belonging to families of having 5 to 7 members. Villages are moving from joint family system nuclear families. It is very significance in case adopting new health culture in the absence of elders.

General expenditure pattern of the families shows that up to Rs.2000/- is being used by the respondents for various purposes including 72 of the respondents are using it for livelihoods, 5% for using it for health, 3% for education and 10% for loan repayment. Social expenditure pattern of the families shows that up to Rs.10,000/- is being used by the respondents for various purposes including 10% of the respondents are using it for marriage 20% for using it for birthday celebration 2 % for death ceremony and 55 % for celebrating festively. Regarding break up details of house hold health care expenditure with upper sealing limit of Rs. 5000/ it is found that 51% are spending it for Surgery , 6% of them for Lab testing 12% of them for surgery 10% of them for Consultation fees 8% of them for Hospital charges and 6% of them Transportation. It is shows people are spending more for social issues and less for health care.

In case of using fruits and vegetables it is raveled that 33% of the respondents are using it twice/thrice a weak where as 2% are using frequently. Regarding food pattern it is found that 43% of them are pure vegetarians where as 27% of the respondents are purely non-**vegetarians only**. Food pastern also play vital role in the health status of the rural community. In case of additions It is quite evident that 36% of them have smoking habits whereas 25% of them are use alcohol regularly while 5% of them are having both the habits whereas 50 % are not having any addictions. It is revealed that food pattern and addictions among the respondent's is significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues. Next, it is found that 25% of the respondents aware the consequence of addiction while 16% of the respondents don't have any awareness about the health consequences of addictions. Regarding sources of health information 26% are getting health education through their educated children while 12% are getting information through their relative and friends and 13% are getting through folk media only. This factor is also very important to find out the

role of social networks in creating health awareness. Regarding preventative measures to keep healthy 7% of the respondents said it is only possible through vaccinations and 15% of them said regular health checkups are must. Next, 11% of them said celebrate festivals and fairs or worship regularly, where as 42% said clean food, water and shelter will keep us healthy. This shows people are gradually moving from traditional concept to modern concept.

In case of factors affecting women's health issues it is quite evident that 29% of them said it depends on socio cultural status of the family where as 37% of them opined economic background of the household play a vital role while 27% of them viewed that educational level of the parents /in law or husbands is also an important issue affecting on the women's health issue in rural part. Regarding contamination of food items 14% said it is because of spirits and bad eye while 17% said food contaminates when others watches our eating and 43% of them said it is because of pathogenesis. Food norms is also vital issue in case health behavior of the traditional societies

Concerning concept about pure and impure blood 16% of the respondents held pure blood leads health and impure blood causes illness where as 16% said good food leads good blood and bad food leads bad blood. Regarding reason for serving different foods for the family members it is found that 26% of the respondents opined males are hard workers hence they should feed more whereas, 30% said females work inside home only hence they should feed less. Regarding possible social deterrents affecting the health status it is revealed that 18% them opined it is level of income and 26% of them opined nature of occupation also plays a vital role. Next, 25% said educational level of the households whereas 12% said it is poverty which affects a lot on the household's health status. These also count s as socio-economic factors affecting health of the rural people.

About source of advice for referral 37% of the respondents said elder family members, where 19% said friends or relatives while 11% said awareness through media are the source of advice for referral. Further In case of reasons for the poor health status other than poverty related issue around 11% of the respondents said it is due to lack of awareness among the rural people whereas 13% said it is due to illiteracy and 25% said it is due to ignorance plus 1% of the respondents said all these reasons are the responsible for the poor health status in the rural parts.

For the question of who is being healthy 37% of the respondents said person without any disease /illness. Next, 13% of their said who can digest anything whereas 13% of them said who can tolerate hot/cold weather while 14% of them said who have long life span are being considered as healthy. Next, 10% of them said one can work always without any problem and 3% of them opined people who are having the above qualities should be considered as healthy. Concept about health and wellbeing shows people are defining in from their day to day social context.

For the question who is a person being unhealthy? It is found that 43% opined one who always suffers from illness/diseases where as 9% opined who can't work as usual and whose physical body normally would be pale and weak. Next, 16% of the respondents opined one who always depends on medicines and 16% of them said one who cannot fight against evil forces/cosmology easily can be considered as unhealthy. It is evident that 17% of the respondents opined healthy life is needed for our wellbeing whereas 13% said health required discharging our duty effectively and promptly and 20% said to earn livelihood. For keeping healthy 15% of the respondents opined proper diet and absence of worry is essential, while 19% of the respondents said hygienic environment is essential and 16% said proper health education is must for keeping healthy.

As regards reasons for causing disease 16% held due to the effect of sprits/angry deity/cosmology power where as 16% said it is due to absence of good food/water/shelter etc and 6% alleged failure to perform health rituals. For the enquiry why human beings would get illness 26% of the respondents held the view that it is due to pathogens where as 20% said angry deity or cosmological power while 9% said it happens because of failure to perform divine rites. Concept about reasons causing illness by the respondents is significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents. Regarding reasons for sickness 45% said sickness and illness both are same whereas 1% said it is due to cosmology/spirits while 1% held the view that it is due to medical or biological reasons. Regarding differences between sickness and wellbeing 40% of the respondents held the opinion sickness is ill health and wellbeing is another name of being healthy where as 26% held the view that sickens is just not feeling well while 12% opined wellbeing is general status of health. Regarding sick role 40% of the respondents did not understood the concept whereas, 26% opined sick person has certain role to play in the society, Further, 12% held the view that sick person cannot pay any role while 15% said sick person should try to get

it cure and come of the ill health soon while 6% gave some other reason. This is very crucial in understanding sick role behavior and its social contexts in the Indian rural settings.

On the subject of the concept about health culture 12% of the respondents held the view it is a set of fixed principles to be followed during illness or diseases while 14% of them said it is age old procedures or traditions to follow when we get ill or sick. Next, 16% of them said that it is a set of rules we need to perform during at the tile illness while 11% said illness experience or illness episode whereas 4% gave some other reason and 40% said don't know what is health culture is . Regarding health seeking behavior 26% of the respondents held it is about patients behavior starting from illness stage until its cure while 21% said health behavior means rules and regulations patients needs to follow during the stage of illness or disease while 23% of them said health behavior includes occurrence of dieses/ illness, etiology, diagnose and treatment etc. Regarding health **care** seeking behavior, 18% of the respondents felt health **care** seeking behavior means doing specific measure to keep healthy in the future where as 19% said it is some sort of preventive measures. Next 3% of them held, it is about post curing measures. Next 15% opined it is about occurrence of disease /illness and its cure while 29% said no idea while 13% gave some other response. It clearly shoes people are opined their views with in their socio-cultural framework.

About who takes major decision when any one fall sick in family 27% of the respondents said decision will be taken based on the experience by the elders whereas 16% of them opined decision will be taken at the capacity of once own cognitive level and 18% said decision will be taken consulting family members or friends while 25% said decision will be taken based on the previous illness experience if any. On the subject of concept about treating an ill person 8% of the respondents said ill people should be socially isolated while 5% of them said ill persons should be treated as untouchables. Next, 23% said ill person should be treated with sympathy whereas 30% said we should treat them equally like others.

For the question who diagnose when any one fall sick in a family? It is found that 27% of the respondents said family elders diagnose the health problem first whereas 16% said traditional healers will diagnose the health whereas 4% of them said self

diagnose whereas 4% said faith healers will diagnose the health problem. Regarding common diseases found among the children (8-12 age group) in the area as opined by the respondents 9% of them said it is Typhoid, 10% of them said Malaria, 16% of them said Jaundice and 12% of them said Cholera,.

Concerning common diseases found among the adolescents, it is found that 12% of the respondents said Typhoid, 10% said Malaria, while 22% said Jaundice and 19% said Cholera whereas 8% said all these diseases found common among adolescents in the studied areas. In case of elders 28% of the respondents said Heart problem. Whereas 18% opined Liver disorder and 12% said Lungs disorder (due to excessive alcoholism and smoking addictions) is most common among the aged. Also 9% said Bone disorders whereas 10% of them opined all these or either problem is common. All these shows communicable disease are most common among children and adolescents. Regarding immunized it is quite revealed that 87% of the respondents have immunized their children against BCG and DPT whereas 8% have not immunized their children. For Measles 79% have been immunized for the children whereas 20% not immunized their children. About reasons for not taking immunization for their children 5% of the respondents held it is against customs while 9% said it is because of our negligence. Next,7% said no idea about immunizations , whereas 57 % said their children have been immunized while 9% said immunizations causes future side effects.

About types of self-reported health problems during the preceding 60 days it is revealed that 2% of the respondents had surgery related issues while 9% of them had Communicable diseases 3% of them had ENT problems. Next 7% of them had had gastric related problems while 5% had respiratory problem and 3% had other type of health problem. **About** respondents' suffered from the following diseases in the last One Year it is found that 23% of the respondents have suffered from Typhoid while 18% of them have suffered from Malaria and 22% have them suffered from Jaundice whereas 9% from Cholera and 4% of them had Dengue. Regarding mortality indicator in the studied samples it is revealed that 30% of the respondents have had Neonatal, while 36 % have had Infant mortality where as 16% have had childhood mortality and 12% of the respondents have had maternal mortality problem. About reasons for miscarriage 10% of the respondents' said it might be due to heredity whereas 29% of them said it is due to medical reason while 6% of them said it might be due to the supernatural power. About reason for mortality or morbidity; It is

revealed that 13% of the respondents said medical reason may be the prime causes for mortality or morbidity; whereas 11% said it would be due to conjugal marriage. Next, 20% of them opined it is due to evil eye or spirit, and 19% of them said it is due to heredity factors..

In case of special care for keeping healthy 17% of them said they concentrate on good food, hygienic health care. While 36% said they are not doing much to keep healthy but they are doing something to keep healthy, whereas 38% of them said they are not doing any special measure to keep healthy at all. Regarding initiatives taken for disease or illness at the family level it is found that 28% of the respondents will consult senior members the village while 17% said family elders will decide about treatment plan where as 15% said worshipping deity will be done. This is also very vital in studying inherited health culture of the rural people

Regarding perception of the causes for the emergency of disease /illness it is found that 27% of the respondents opined emergency of disease /Illness causes due to differences in the food, water etc while 18% of them said evil eye and angry deity and 18% of them said it causes due to spirits and cosmology forces. Regarding choice of treatment for any sudden health problems 5% of the respondents will visit medical shop if any sudden health problem where as 46% would like to visit traditional healers only. Next it is found that 15% of the respondents would like to use home remedy where as 14% would like to visit private doctors only. It is found that 42% of the respondents will use traditional medicine, 28% would like to use home remedy where as 17% use modern medicine for cough and cold. While 50% said they will use only self medications for cough and cold. For the common fever, 24% of them would like to use traditional medicine, where as 25% would like to use home remedy and 28% would like to use modern medicine while 17% use self medications. This clearly shows people are using both traditional and modern health care for their various health problems

Common social behavior towards TB, Leprosy and mental illness it is quite evident that 8% opined to follow Taboo, while 9% of them said isolate the patients for the society where as 16% said to ex -communicate the patient. Regarding views on mental illness it is revealed 19% of the respondents said it causes due to medical reason whereas 10% of them said it causes due to fate or evil forces and 19% said mental patients need to be socially isolated and treat. Next, 29% of them said no folk

medicine to health mental illness and only western medicine should use to heal the patients.

Regarding reason for causing HIV/AIDS and STD 8% of the respondents said it is because of heredity while 18% said it is due to migration and 11% said it is because of breaching taboos. Regarding perception about STD symptoms 13 % of the respondents said white discharges while 12% said itching at gentiles where as 15% said pain at sex organs. It shows people are gradually getting more aware about HIV/STD due to the strong media and NGO present. Regarding preference of conducting child delivery 5% of the respondents prefer traditional midwife, whereas 50% prefer Govt. PHCs, while 29% prefers private hospitals. Next 9 % prefers NGO doctors and 1% people did not reply and 0.8 prefer at home. It shows people have some sort of belief over the western medical care system.

. Regarding age range of sick individuals who used self-medication 20% of them belong to the age group of 25-35 while 16% of them belong to the age group of 34- 45 whereas 18% belongs to the age group of 45-55 whereas 10% of them are above 55 age. Regarding duration between onset of disease and seeking treatment 19% of the respondents' claimed they would visit right away while 40% said after 2-3 days where as 37% said we follow wait and see technique while 3% we visit hospital only when it get serious

Regarding cultural attitude towards hereditary diseases it is revealed that 19% of the respondent held hereditary diseases no medicine at all while 12% it is due to the side effects of modern usage of modern medicines. Next, 17% opined traditional medicine has solutions forhereditary diseases. For congenital deformities problem 16% of the respondents said it is because of humeral imbalance while 18% said congenital deformities might be due to super human causation and as punishment for bad deed where as 8% said it is because of internal damages deed while 25% said it is because of medical reason.

With regard to hot and cold concept of food items, 23% of the respondents' said all vegetables are cold while 33% said few vegetables are hot. Next 24% of them said all pulses are hot, where as 18% are said few pulses are cold. Next, 42% said all cereals are cold, while 45% said few cereals are hot, 8% said milk products mutton, chicken are hot food items. This also very vital in allying onset of various diseases /illness in the vivews of the rural people

About Concept about communicable diseases it is found that 8% said communicable disease does not spread while 29% of the respondents said it spreads, where as 8% said patients will die out of these kinds of disease and 30% of them said patients will suffer for a long time from any communicable disease. Regarding concept about Non-communicable disease 11% of the respondents opined it has spreading in nature while 36% said that it will not spread but some time it spreads and 24% said non-communicable disease diseases means from which patients dies normally. Regarding classifications knowledge 12% of the respondents have classified Malaria as communicable where as 22% as non-communicable. Next 15% have classified Typhoid as communicable whereas 12% as non communicable. Next 12% have classified Cholera as communicable whereas, 21% as non communicable. Also 19% have classified Gastric as communicable while 13% have classified Gastric problems as communicable .Next 7% have classified Bone problems as communicable where as 6% as non communicable. concept about communicable and non-communicable disease classifications of the respondents have significant influence over the health behavior, culture and allied issues of the respondents .

In case of treatment behavior it is revealed that for common fever majority of them will not prefer any type of treatment where as only 25% would visit PHC and 23% would visit private hospitals. Next for gastric problem 18% use traditional medicine whereas 8% visit Govt. PHC and 11% of them seek Ayurvedic medicine. For respiratory problem 13% use traditional therapy whereas 19% use Govt. PHCs and 9% Of them visit faith healer. For ENT problem 21% visits traditional medicine 21% use Govt. PHC where as 14% use faith healers. Regarding preventive measure 7% held the view that communicable diseases can be avoided satisfying deity while 9% said celebrating festivals regularly, 16% said more preventive measures needs to be taken while 31% said by maintaining hygienic conditions, 13% alleged due to have health education while 8% said using safe food and water. It is shoes people are having mixed method preventive measure.

About respondent's opinion about how certain diseases affects on the human body 14% of them said Cholera affects on morphology of the body while 19% of them opined Choler affects Physiology of the body 10% oof them opined Malaria affects on Either Anatomy or Physiology. Further 12% of the respondent's opined Typhoid affects on morphology of the body while 14% of them opined Jaundice affects on Anatomy of the body etc. Opinion about health ritual's it is revealed that 15% of the

respondents opined it is a procedure to satisfy health deities where as 13% of them opined women cannot perform rites while 10 % of them opined during ritual rites all village people have to observe norms and sanctity.

Opinion about medical pluralism it is evident that 18% of the respondents said medical pluralism means availability more than one type of medicine while 12% said using different medical systems at a time where as 11% said availability of different medical care system in a given place while 7% said different therapeutic treatment where majority of them(50%) said no idea . Reasons for using different medical systems at a time 16% said as advised by the traditional healers and faith healers while, 20% of the respondents said that they are taking a chance and 27% said as advised by the village or family elders. Regarding opinion about quality of medical pluralism available 22% of the respondents said more options for the patients is possible while 11% said no such quality in certain system of medical care available.

Regarding opinion about ethno medicine and their impact on health 29% held that it is really good but disappearing day by day while 25% said it still exist and we need to preserve ethno medicines whereas 20% said ethno medicine is our asset and only hope for the poor. Regarding belief in the existence of supernatural/cosmology 15% of the respondents are partially believe in supernatural/cosmology while 9% of them said they believe in that but can't say more. Next 14% said up to certain extent they effects on health while 8% of them opined it is responsible for various diseases/illness and we should respect them while 12% of them felt we ignore because no proof for their existence and 39% of them don't believe at all

On the subject of reasons for **not** accepting the modern medical treatment for diseases 10% of the respondents said they don't have any faith in the modern medicine while 21% of them said it has more side effects. Next 11% said it may effects on health in the future whereas 21% said it is against our tradition and 6% said because of bad previous experiences. Reasons for accepting only traditional/folk medicine 13% of the respondent said because of quick healing while 26% of them said because of low cost and absence of any side effects , while 15% said it is easy to use and easily available. Reasons for accepting allopathic treatment only for specific diseasesit is evident that 41% of the respondents said because of speedy recovery they opt allopathic treatment where as 10% said allopathic has guarantee of cure while 15% of them said no medicine in traditional system for some diseases.

Regarding influences of the socio-economic status on the health seeking behavior it is revealed that 33% admitted influences of social and economic status has strong impact whereas 25% of the respondents just ignored it. Next, 24% of them partially admitted and said it is up to certain extent only. Next 7% of them opined it does not affect very much whereas 7% said they don't have any idea while 2% gave some other reasons.

Economic group wise opinion about causing illness/diseases it is found that 31% low, 8% medium, 10% high income, and 3% elites believe in cosmology forces for causing illness/ disease while 11% low, 45% medium, 47% high income and 61% elites believe pathogenesis for causing health problems whereas 22% low, 21% medium 21% high income and 11% elites think unhygienic conditions are the reason for causing various health problems. Caste wise opinion about causing illness/diseases. It is found that 21% SC/ST, 18% OBC, and 12% others believe in humeral causation whereas 22% SC/ST, 41% OBC, 28% others and 37% believe pathogenic causes while , 18% SC/ST , 16% OBC, and 25% others believe in super natural power causes various health problems. Next, 19% SC/ST, 12% OBC, and 12% others believe unhygienic conditions causes illness and diseases while 17% SC/ST, 10% OBC, 22% others, 12% converter believe in either above reason in causing illness/ diseases.

Regarding economic group wise opinion about medical pluralism it is found that 51% of low, 32% of medium , 25% of high income and 30% elites feel medical pluralism is more useful to the poor patients' whereas 14% of low, 19% of medium, 24% of high income and 23% of elites said medical pluralism give more option to the patients. Regarding economic group wise opinion about of modern health care it is found that 6% of low, 19% of middle, 33% of high income and 52% of the elites opined that modern health care is reliable, safe, and easily available. Whereas 33% low, 31% of middle, 13% of high income and 30 % of the elites opined that modern health care has more side effects and only useful in emergency.

Relationship between preventive measures and educational status of the respondents it is found that 21% illiterates, 29% Primary, 21% High School and 32% College and 29% Neo literates opined good food and shelter is a basic items for any preventive care . Next, it is found that 15% Illiterates, 22% Primary, 16% High School and 32% College and 17 % Neo literates opined good health practices and hygienic

conditions is the most vital preventive care. It is found that high socio-economic status of the community enables them to obtain the obtainable health care facilities and get better health status. Supplementary, better educational level gives greater health consciousness and thus develops the health status unswervingly. Thus health status is prejudiced not only demographic, socio-economic and environmental issues, but also by the accessibility and use of different types of medicines.

Opinion about Govt. effort for quality rural health care 12% said it is because of lack of infrastructure, corruption Govt. efforts failing while 19% said there is a lack of political will while 16% said there bureaucratic disinterest and 19% said unnecessary delay are more common in Govt programmes. Regarding cultural barriers in introducing new health care in the rural areas 19% of the respondents said developmental behavior of the rural people is a main barrier while 28% said age old beliefs and traditions where as 11% said general ignorance on health issues.

It is found that continuous changes in the medical technology, development etc., will change the attitude of the people towards medical care. It also affects on the health seeking behaviour of a community. Since people change their attitudes towards medical care often, defining health and illness within social life would be a big task some time. Research and analyzing sociological study of health and illness now-a-days is very difficult and it is because of rapid change in the health culture and behaviour across the societies, Sociology expects healthy people only will construct healthy society. Healthy people will only play a vital role in the holistic development of society. Medical sociologists felt on one hand efforts needs to create more awareness about the modern health facilities on other hand cultural training for the formal doctors is need of the hour. Next they felt in a pluralistic health system private/ public/ qualified/ unqualified systems and personal need gender sensitive trainings. Traditional healers should be given at least basic training in the bio-medical health care system. Certain sociologists have also criticized about nature of studies. They felt sometime research methodology and samples and a political economy of the research process under questionable. Sometime the researchers will be under pressure to give positive or favorable results. Sometime funding agencies and government also seeks to hide the real facts (Albrecht, 2011) .

Sociologists have revealed that the development of health culture of the rural environment should be examined as a sub cultural complex of the entire way of life

focusing rurals' health behavior and well-being in the changing scenario. There are a number of forces percolated from the larger socio-economic environment and directed through the attributer of historical, social and political dimension to the development of the pattern of their health culture in the given rural settings

The socio-religious medical responses to illness in various forms-including the belief, forms etc will be recognized and gets approval – over the period of time and build the health culture. As a part of this health culture, members of each community tend to build up a specific belief frame relating to several illnesses /diseases recognized by them. The symptom recognition, assessment and health decisions associated to retrieval of health recuperation are predisposed by belief frames connecting to disease caution, multiply, diagnosis, and cure of each of the a lot of categories of diseases recognized.

Normally rural folk believe diviners would have special super natural power and experience in diagnosing and curing different discuses with a reasonable time. Diviner's extraordinary behavior and knowledge and power will be greatly respected and found a place in the rural health culture. It is also a normal phenomenon that such persons pass through a phase of experiencing non-ordinary behavioral symptoms. This whole system is methodically connected to the stress and strains which society and culture induces over its member, thus the method of becoming a diviner is also a therapeutic action where a person with inner conflict finds a culturally agreed medium for channelizing his preventions and hostility (Joshi, 1990). Rurals' concepts of prevention of various health problems and keeping themselves away from the diseases causing elements have become part and parcel of their social life. Life style, food habits preventive measures will be in accordance with the local customs, norms and values. “ *All these micro-level cognitive cultural information floccus towards broad based cultural ambiguity, micro level interest, norm configuration and their intermeshing with the wider political-economic structures of interests in order to understand even the institutionalized medico-curative systems in their complete societal contexts*” (Maharajan, 1990) .

Studies conducted in various parts of the village India have shown that acts, words, songs chants, worship, statues, suggested and reveal cultural realities other than themselves further natural, supper natural, cosmological, spiritual are symbolically

and meaningfully ordered. Also any domain of health culture will have implicit meanings

Rural's concept of prevention of various health problems and keeping themselves away from the diseases causing elements have become part and parcel of their inherited health culture. Life style, food habits preventive measures will be in accordance with the local customs, norms and values only. The current study has found that health seeking behavior of one family may affect the entire village. Life style of a particular person, how seriously he /she considers health problem and frequency of occurrence of the particular health problem plays a significant role here. Also beliefs and practices traditional healer , treatment pattern, and hurdles in accepting the modern health care facilities would be significantly vital in shaping common or similar pattern of the health seeking and health promoting behavior among the entire rural group. Further, it is found that socio, cultural, ecological, political and physical dimensions shapes health culture of the given the rural community.” (Maharajan, 1990) .

This study opines that established rurals' health behavior should not be underestimated citing them as illiterate or superstitious. Even today the major section of the rural people is not ready to accept the modern health system because of their cultural background. Because of resistance, till today many rural targeted programme have not been succeeded. It is believed that rural healthbehavior depends on particular health culture, geographical area and particular eco-system. Medical Anthropologists felt that the modern health programmes, failed to respect peoples' inherited culture, emotions and spiritual meanings associated with health and disease. Moreover it is found that the health seeking behavior of the rurals' varies according to the type of illness, causation of illness, gender and age of the person affected by a particular disease and illness. Further, this study has found that poverty, illiteracy, policy problem are some of the reasons for health inequalities in case rural people in India. Uneven distribution of the modern medical facilities,hospitals, lack of awareness, lack of effective prevention measures, development behavior of certain communities, absence of strong political will, bureaucratic negligence, poor medical infrastructure, malnutrition, transport system, people ignorance are some of the hurdles in the way providing quality delivery of health care service to the rural people which is largely influenced by their socio-economic and other institutional factors(Guotha,2001).

This study has revealed that rural populations have suffered from numerous communicable and congenital diseases. Typhoid, Malaria, Jaundice, Cholera, TB, Scabies and Mental illness are highly prevalent. People believe strongly believes cosmological powers causes disease and illness. Changing socio-economic process will also influence **on** the pattern of the health culture and health care seeking behaviour. When change happens in the health culture, health seeking behavior of a particular community will also get change. Hence, perception and attitude of the rural community towards different health problems will get new shape and frame in the due course of time. Finally, it leads to the formation of new health care seeking behavior when they face such health disorders in the future. When the health culture is strongly influenced by the external organics (level of education, migration, media etc) in a particular geographical area rural people will may develop new health behaviors. This adoption will lead to have new health seeking behavior to resolves the health problems within the given ecological settings. This type of forced change in the health behavior of a particular community sometime will be explicit and some time will be implicit also. Govt. and NGO needs to look in to the cultural fabrics of the rural health for speedy social inclusion before framing any new health policies.

Rural areas in general are marked by poor implementation of health facilities. Government has implemented many rural specific health programmes however high concentration of infectious diseases absence of effective health education, lack of fundamental facilities are adversely affecting the rural's health. Even today there is no good road facility to many remote villages across the country due to this factor new medical technology has not yet reached to the villages. Rural's health today has two important dimensions;

1. Some of the communicable diseases which are most common among prevalent among the rurals including malaria, cholera, diarrhea, malnutrition, etc..... require good health education, grass root level interventions and hygienic environment.
2. Some of the non-communicable diseases including metal illness, neurological problems, require good medical interventions; also there is a dearth need to have some special programmes
3. Focus also be on alcoholism, smoking and drug addiction.

It is found that current health culture reflects the norms and values of the wider community within which the household/s is located and the social and economic possibilities, which local contexts offer different categorized of households. It seems community has not understood health culture and health behavior is a social construction. A new paradigm is required which attempts to ground explanation and interpretations in the contexts of community and culture is embedded within normal lives. Health culture is not static, nor is it narrowly prescribed. It is found that each generation reconstructs structuring patient's experiences and channeling health culture to reflect values, social networks, self-esteem and identity in society. On the contrary, there are some key features of health culture and behavior which are being reconstructed in the most economically advanced communities as a result of rigorous external interventions. The emergence of the new paradigm, and the extent, to which it has universal versus local application, will depend greatly on the approaches, philosophies and the ideology with respect to the health, illness and the medicine. Local culture more or less considers the modern health care as economic entities, thus ascribing medicine with an economic rather than simply a social value. Marginalized community find themselves establishing a separate illness ideology

People's concept about health and illness some time based on their position in the societal hierarchical structure. An interesting aspect found in this study is caste based illness ideology. People belonging to the higher caste will perform various rituals regularly regarding seeking good health status spending considerable amount of money. Illness ideology is quite different in case of lower caste people. This study also found that lower caste people will strongly believe in the cosmology or evil forces etc in causing various diseases/illness. However, notable percentage of them also believing scientific theory illness and disease and deny traditional belief. This is a good sign also. Lower caste people will perform health related ritual to the lesser known gods and the deities. Low caste people will seek help from the priest belongs to the higher caste to perform the rituals. In the majority cases higher caste priest will not accept this offer. In that case, low caste people will choose a person amongst them to conduct the rituals.

Further, it is found that majority higher caste people will not participate in any health related rituals normally organized by the lower caste people except in some cases. It shows that higher caste people are more privilege to access to the well being whereas lower caste people are more prone to the ill-health. Even though cretin

notable percentage of respondents belongs to the lower caste believe in the western theory of etiology they perform only rituals to come out of the any specific illness/diseases. This study found that illness ideology varies based caste to caste. Caste based illness ideology study would be very ideal in this moment.

It is also interesting to found that in few occasions' illness ideology changes from one geographical area to another geographical area and one social context to another social context. Illness ideology of any community must be studied with in the ambit of that social context. It is well established that the role of society in conceptualizing illness and sickens/ well being are normally articulated within the force of different social structures which constructs the health culture and health seeking behavior of a community. It is also found that understanding villager's health behavior and health culture goes beyond the individual body and particular etiology into the context of general culture(Joshi ,1990).

However, gender prospective of health and illness is also a significant comport in studying the rural health culture. It is evident that understanding social relationship and degree of personal relationship between the community members is very significant in understanding health behaviour and illness ideology of the rural parts. People have classified different god, goodness and evil forces to different types of illness and diseases. Family also plays significant role in shaping illness ideology and health behavior.In the majority cases family elders' or other family member will play a key role in diagnosing diseases or illness. In some cases family members only decide in opting appropriate treatment plan.

Emotional bonds between the patients' his/her family members would be crucial in case of stress, and strain on the part of the patients' in playing a sick role, patients sick role cannot be isolated from his social settings and familial circumstances. It is within the social sphere of the family that disease occurs and its management is resolved, family helps the patients' in coping with the stress and difficulties due to the illness. Familiarly relations and obligations sometime leaves a major role in influencing the patient' to accept the sick role, also family only bear the expenditure of the health care of the patient and family is recognized legally as the decision making authority in opting suitable health care on behalf of the patients'.Joshi (1990).

Studies are badly required to incorporate vital socio-cultural factors in introducing advanced healthcare system for the rurals to know how illness cognitions constructed or health care behavior will be developed. There are certain studies to show that how respondents' cope up with the existing health deciders. It would be interesting to know that how social networks and social support play a role to the patients' to handle the sock role positively, and how cultural difference in seeking social support. Some culture will provide social support to the patients for certain health problems. However, patients' will not show interest in getting that support because of fearing of criticizing or spreading health issues to others which is a insult or embarrassing. This will discourage the patients' in getting social support from the social network. Some time patients' may like to have unsolicited support to cope up (Kim et al 2006). In some culture, patients' may not show in interest to share true pain with the fellowmen. They will seek social support from the social network without discussing his/her problems. Studies also shown that culturally driven social support has done positive impact, and cultural will help the patients' to get back to the normal life at the earliest (Kim, et. al 2008)

The strong beliefs or faith of the respondents' on the healing technique do matter a lot. Also role of family members , village members, and others plays a vital role in opting a particular type of medical assistance within the given context of medical pluralism including hakims, local traditional healers, nomadic vaidy's, Ayurvedic and allopathic etc . It is found that some time medical practice among rural respondents' will be highly pluralistic in the days to come. Only in certain parts of the rural areas both traditional medicine and bio-medicine co-exists side by side.

Government has opened allopathic and ayurvedic medicines, in certain rural areas so that rural people can select any type of medical system regarding prevention curative and rehabilitative measures. Hence we can opine that health seeking behavior of rural people is gradually becoming flexible today. Exports opined that there is a dearth need of new sociological studies about dynamics of changing rural health culture focusing philosophy system of medicine. The typology of traditional medical practice classified for describing the legal role of traditional medicine in different medical systems by showing that.

Today in few rural areas (nearing to city) modern medicine or cosmopolitan medicines are being dominated. In practice an exclusive system is pluralistic and, an

integrated system may include many aspects of the traditional medicines. Furthermore, in practice the inclusive and integrated system form a continuum, just at the exclusive tolerant system are coterminous with each other. The context of medical pluralism is now being changed because of new socio-economic, medicalization, globalization and political development etc. Accessibility and availability of the different medical practices also plays a vital role in diffusing health culture and fulfilling health needs of the rural people. Due to all these one day traditional medicinal system may be dislocated from its originality. Emphasizing health behavior issue from the perspective of the rural cultural fabrics towards refusal or accept of various medical system needs a fresh date. Western sociologists say future of traditional medical system is in question because of inclusion of consistent inter generational contents by the traditional societies (Kim, et. al 2008)

Rather than any one form of medicine/s, it would be significant if we must focus the place of medicine occupied in the every day life of the rural people and it should be studied deeply. Some time doing cross-cultural analysis of the practice of different healing techniques, health behavior in different culture would be very vital in generalizing the pattern of the health culture across the rural society. The psycho-therapeutic elements and strong faith on the local healer or local vaidya plays highly significant role in curing diseases and sickness. It is found that diviners also significant in the traditional medical system. As Joshi opined ‘diviners are the healers who plays an intermediate role between the culturally postulated super human and the society’, (Joshi, (1990). The healing techniques used by the diviners would be a very vital for the further sociological study (Choubey, 2000; Pandry, 2000; Sharma, 1999).

One patient and multiple health providers like Ayurvedic, Unani, Sidda, doctors, herbalist etc is a current phenomenon today. This pharma health seeking behavior indicates how medical pluralism is moving (direction) in a given society. The medical system of the society will be normally composed of different medical sub systems found in a co-operative or competitive manner. Usually complex societies include all types of medical systems in a parallel and sometime overlapping manner in rural areas. Also medical pluralism in a society is sometime based on hierarchical relation, socio-political and economical control etc. However, all these factors sometime could not interpret the local notion about illness. Sometime in a pluralistic health care system, the very basic interpretation of illness may get change over the period of time due to the various external factors. Usually patients’ do not essentially mind the

illness details and the healing approaches as they need immediate cure. “The real issue is that usually sick person and different healers consider various underlying medical logics don’t necessarily undermine treatment” (Salvador, 2009).

Also it is found that the hierarchical principle of high and low caste system is not only exist with the social groups. It exists even with that of medical pluralism also. Gov’t will also support modern health care along with other medical system and traditional medicines. The broad variety of medicinal system co-exists along side of traditional medicine in the rural societies now. This was established that in some case local healer will follow certain diagnostic technique available in the modern medicine. In urban setting people are showing interests in ayurveda and homeopathy rather than allopathic today as per the ICMR report.

Much effort can be seen in India to incorporate ISM in to the main stream. It is only can be possible through the usage of various social institutions. Drug industry is also plays vital role in creating more networks among different susyem of medicines. Also ISM has psychological and spiritual dimensions. However, we must focus on the efficacy, standardized of medicine and safety also. Because some types of traditional medicines are not safe to use in the original forms. Moreover, it is also found that numbers of trained practitioners are also growing with respect to ISM in India. As Sara(2003) opined ‘Multiple health seeking’ should be recognized and incorporated into a wider co-ordination across the health system, with better co-operation between the public and private providers’.

This study has proved that availability, acceptability and accessibility of the modern medical care depend on the community, culture, and economy, political and moral values. If patients gets treatment in a government hospital will share his experience with a traditional healer. In some cases respondents will seek help from the traditional healers and visit PHC and in some cases vice versa. Patients’ may accept the western medicine or reject based on his experience in the future. He/she may deny to visit the hospital in the future if he is not satisfy with the quality of the service including duration took to solve the health problem and other issues. It is not so easy to introduce the western medicine system in the area where traditional system exists from a long time. People will normally compare among the various medical systems available at the door steps with respect to quality, history, cost, duration to heal, degree of efficacy etc. However all these issues varies from context to context.

Rural people always expect medicines should solve their problems as soon as possible. They only bother about immediate consequence. Hence, now sociologists are focusing phenomenology and political economy exists with medical pluralism and the role of social relations in health care management. A perfect understanding of medical pluralism in diverse cultural settings is need of the hour.

Finally it can be noted that due to the influence of changing social, economic and political issues, particular health culture will get frame and reframe continuously over the period of time. To reveal the psycho-sociological compliant of health culture first we need to take into account of the overall culture of the community. It is known fact that certain health cultural practices leads to have certain health disorders too!. Hence it is very vital to study the rural health issue because certain cultural practices by the community will get either by diffusion or new local innovations. Social science in general and Sociology in particular plays a vital role in understanding both qualitative and quantitative changes in the various domain of health culture of the rural people. Then any empirical study will come out with new and unique findings and contributes to the theoretical understanding and research domain of the subject more precesisly.

CHAPTER-IX

**MAJOR FINDINGS AND POLICY
SUGGESTIONS**

- It becomes imperative to focus on troubles of rural health because it differs from a particular area to another area due to their historical background, geographical location, and the influence of external agencies on processes of social change etc.. For this, there is a need for proper understanding of sociological insights of health care and its dynamics specific to time and place
- This study has found that even though rural people's health culture and health behavior is largely based on traditions and customs gradual change can be seen where rural people also gradually accepting western theory of disease causational and treatment (modern healthcare concept)
- In the context of rural settings a number of vital factors play their role in health seeking behaviour, including people's beliefs regarding the origin and cause of illness; economic status, gender bias in health care, advice lend by family elders etc.
- The customs, beliefs, perceptions and practices, focusing health and diseases are in a constant process of modification and re-modifications (adjustments) with respect time and space. The socio cultural factors that affect the health of the rural's include their customs and practices, religious beliefs, norms, values and taboos in the case or control of certain commonly occurring diseases. Hence, we can opine that health seeking behavior of rural people is gradually becoming flexible because of new elements in their health culture.
- Health seeking behavior of the ruals' varies according to the type of illness, causation of illness, gender and age of the person affected by a particular disease and illness.
- Significant difference were observed in occupation, education level and land ownership of the respondents and the health seeking behavior. Most of the beneficiaries were non-literates and primary level educated. Caste composition and the health seeking behavior varies depending on the level of education
- It is found that age and sex has no such effect on health seeking and health care behaviour Family size has no significant impact on health seeking behavior and willingness to pay for better services but has impact on awareness and purpose of visit. Income, poverty level have significant impact on all aspects of health seeking and health care seeking behavior. Occupation of the respondents has impact on the health seeking behavior but not on knowledge and readiness to pay for improved medical services

- It cannot be denied that the economic status of a household plays a crucial role in influencing health behavior. It is important to distinguish between the direct costs of health and the indirect cost. The direct cost of health on the other hand, do impose a substantially burden on families especially if there is more than one chronic patients in the same family.
- When changes happen in the health culture, health seeking behavior of a particular community will also get changes. Hence perception and attitude of the rural community towards different health problems will get new shape and frame in the due course of time. Finally, it leads to the formation of new health care seeking behavior when they face such health problems in the future.
- The socioeconomic context, especially along the development dimension, is an integral part of health programme effectiveness. On the other hand it is difficult to ensure good quality health care in the rural area because of their unique culture.
- Further, it is found that majority higher castes people will not participate in any health related rituals normally organized by the lower caste people except in some cases. It shows that higher caste people are more privilege to access to the well being whereas lower caste people are more prone to the ill-health.
- It was noted during the study that though rurals' spend significant amount of money and time, their level of health education is extremely poor. Due to the lack of knowledge, they visit traditional healers and ill-qualified medical practitioners rather than visiting the modern health care. These practitioners take full benefit of the chance and exploit the poor and uneducated
- More over it is found that health seeking behavior of the rural people varies according to the type of illness, causation of illness, gender and age of the person affected by a particular disease and illness.
- Cost effective health care measures must be put in operation, seeking in particular reduction in infant mortality rates that will reduce the social pressure on families to have many children as possible as way to insure against high rate of child mortality. More over family planning service must be made available to all at easily and affordable cost
- It is established that the involvement local self governments in framing and implementing of health plan is relatively weak. Even when there is

involvement, the quality is below desired level. Significant difference across the districts can be seen in quality of involvement various executive agencies

- In the same way It is also found that gradual diminishing in the faith of the local medical system, paradoxical change in the rural life style, education and income level are strongly associated as pushing factors to seek modern health care for various diseases by the certain section of the rural people belongs to the higher caste and income groups.
- Due to rapid economic development, migration and expansion of the cities, rural people are gradually prone to various modern STD diseases unknowingly.
- When the health culture is strongly influenced by the external organics (level of education, migration, media etc) in a particular geographical area tribal people will develop new health behaviors also. This adoption will lead to have new health seeking behavior to resolves the health problems within the given ecological settings (Parson 1963).
- The findings of this study indicates that other enabling factors such as proximity to the health facility and availability of funds were also important in determining health-seeking behavior.
- Contrary to changes in health seeking behavior patterns of the rural people one also notices marvelous changes, which have occurred with respect to philosophy, knowledge, and practices of indigenous systems such as Ayurveda, Homeopathy, etc.
- Hierarchical principle of high and low caste system is not only exist with the social groups. It exists even with that of medical pluralism also.
- This study has found that health seeking behavior of one family may affect an entire village. Life style of a particular person, how seriously he /she considers health problem and frequency of occurrence of the particular health problem plays a significant role here. Also beliefs and practices in local vidya, treatment pattern, and hurdles in accepting modern health care facilities would be significantly vital in shaping common or similar pattern of health seeking and health promoting behavior among the entire rural group.
- There is much diversity in the demographic behavior of rurals including ethnically, socially, economically in various ecological, environmental and developmental settings. It is found that health behavior and medical pluralism are much controlled by the social tradition and family based frame of mind

rather than social growth and economic status. In certain rural part traditional and modern medical system continues to be antagonistic to each other. This is why rural people have 'pharmacopeia of their own for their common diseases'.

- The success rate of some of the health education programmes of both Governmental and NGOs are very disappointing because it seems to be framed by only officials without any involvement of the concerned local people. Thus, there are some discrepancies between what is appropriate and useful and what is actually implemented to a relatively less than successful outcome.
- Few studies found the traditional medicine system may be dislocated from their past golden days due to the popularity and success rate pluralistic therapy. Emphasizing health behavior issue from the prospective of rural cultural fabrics towards refusal or accept various medical system needs now fresh date as noted by the western sociologists that the future of the traditional medical system because of inclusion of consistent inter-generational contents is also a big question in developing societies.
- Different economic groups have expressed interesting features about the medical pluralism. The low economic group respondents felt medical pluralism may give an opportunity for the poor patients because of the cost factor. The Elites' also expressed the same view. The majority of the respondents opined the medical pluralism will give more success rate of healing.
- However, all the respondents opined the medical pluralism has quality problem and the fake practitioners. The respondents opined in the rural area, the patients' are being cheated in the name of the medical pluralism. Also the noted percentage of them opined the medical pluralism may lead a kind of confusion among the patients'
- Availability of the low cost generic medicines at selected rural locations is required and creating awareness against traditional healers falls rumors about modern medicines is need of the hour. Respondents are little bit aware about over medicalizations. Over 50% of them opined because of medicalizations respondents cannot access to modern health care where factor cost is a vital issue. Respondents were worried about spreading medicalizations. Some of them alleged this situation is created by the western Doctors to earn more money. Drug sellers also have joined with the Doctors they said.

- Choosing a PHC to seek health care and treatment depends upon several criteria among rural people. Most often, why the beneficiary families do not visit the primary Health Centers coming under their jurisdiction have several reasons. The common causes for the low level of the choice of PHCs for health care treatment are the lack of knowledge among the beneficiary families at PHCs, lack of funds at PHCs to provide efficient service, and the repeated absence of Doctors at the centers. When all these factors come together, people prefer to go to private hospitals instead of PHCs.
- A majority PHCs lack even such a basic element of infrastructure as electricity. The government should consider providing either solar panels or diesel generators (depending on a cost-benefit analysis) connected to batteries for uninterrupted electric power for computers. Additionally, each PHC should have a full time staff consisting of a lady doctor, a paramedic to perform initial screening test, a trained nurse or physicians' assistant, and a laboratory technician.
- It is found that that poverty, illiteracy, malnutrition, scarcity of potable water, sanitary conditions, poor mother child health services, problems in covering national health and nutritional services, etc. have been found the most vital causative factors for the prevalence of several health issues among rural communities in the country.
- The doctor-patient relationship can potentially be used to endorse better health seeking behavior and fulfillment with treatment, and is an subject of vital issue reflected across the study
- The study reveals that majority of the people gradually preferring allopathic medicine. Since direct and indirect cost is competitively high in allopath medicine only some respondents are using Ayurvedic and homoeopathy and folk medicine. It is also found that cost connected factors and the option of the system of medicine invariably propositional to the economic background of the respondents. In contrast, cost linked factors pressure rural people more in choosing a particular system of medicine. The study found that the independent variables like age, sex education, occupation, socio economic status, etc. plays a very significant role in choosing particular system of medicine in rural areas. However some respondents choose folk medicine for minor health problems

- Before implementing community health programmes there is a need of understanding different medical system found in the same society. If we consider all practitioners of different health care system taken in to account health care providing proper health care personnel's is not a problem. Lay man concept on various medical system is vital in framing suitable health programmes for the rural respondents'.
- Practitioners belonging to the various medical systems will use only theoretical knowledge from the different medical systems and try with patients' that may leave the patients' to danger.
- Normally rural respondents' depend on any traditional medicine if they could not get the modern medicine on time. Some time some simple medicines will not be available in the rural the government hospitals
- Further, it is found that influence of traditional healers, traditional birth attenders', allocation of duties between the men and women in the rural society, existing gender inequalities, lack of sufficient numbers of women health workers, lack of training for the health personals etc are some of the critical issues in case of implementing various modern health care schemes.

POLICY SUGGESTIONS

- Attempt is needed to comprehend health culture as a sub culture complex in developing a model of culturally suited health module programmes especially for the nation's rural people with their different castes and class. There is dearth need to provide locally setting health education. Mass media can play a vital role in this aspect
- In Indian family system, a traditional woman is a real living force of the family. She is the strength of the family. She plays a major role in every household's decisions. Hence, there is a need to create awareness and consciousness among the women about household preventive measures
- Since social and cultural background of the family plays a vital role in taking household decision on health care. Hence women need more awareness about various health issues
- Culturally sensitive and situated understanding of health seeking behaviour may improve treatment compliance and shorten delay to diagnosis.
- Health education programmes must be based on sacred values so as to make them culturally acceptable, An in-depth study of indigenous medicine from an emic prospective will help in through understanding the cultural symbols and meanings and their integration with the culture. The findings of this study will also help in clear understanding the most vital reasons for the resistance encountered or refusal to accept different medical system including modern medicine.
- Primary health care services in rural parts need consideration by planners and healthcare providers. PHC s must be upgraded.
- The first step is to provide adequate facilities and equipment for the existing PHCs (land, building, equipment, and supplies) previously set up by the government. Every PHC should consist of a preliminary screening room with a computer, an examination room for the doctor, a laboratory for medical tests and supplies, and toilets. A majority PHCs lack even such a basic element of infrastructure as electricity. The government should consider provising either solar panels or diesel generators (depending on a cost-benefit analysis) connected to batteries for uninterrupted electric power for computers. Additionally, each PHC should have a full time staff consisting of a lady

doctor, a paramedic to perform initial screening test, a trained nurse or physicians' assistant, and a laboratory technician.

- This study has found requirement of an extensive community-based sexual and reproductive health education focusing rural adults.
- Some of the communicable diseases which are most commonly prevalent among the rurals including malaria, cholera, diarrhea, malnutrition, etc..... require good health education grass root level interventions and hygienic environment.
- Some of the non-communicable diseases including mental illness, neurological problems, require good psychiatric social work; also there is a death need to have some special programmes for alcoholism, smoking and drug addiction.
- Rural health culture is a part of social system and an adaptive system also. Understanding their health behavior always must be within the boundary of various societal factors which is helpful in providing modern medical health care system also would be very vital in planning any new health care planning.
- Also in certain part of the rural area government has to open allopathic and ayurvedic medicines, so that rural people can select any type of medical system regarding prevention, curative and rehabilitative measures.
- Patients visiting PHCs should also be provided health education by the staff through posters and through audiovisual demonstrations. Every PHC should consist of a preliminary screening room with a computer, an examination room for the doctor, a laboratory for medical tests and supplies, and toilets. Staff should try hard to create awareness about family planning and communicable diseases amongst the rurals. Community programmes in collaborations with Non-Governmental Agencies (NGOs) and social workers will complement these activities.
- More social mobilization and pro-active interventions are required focusing the traditional health culture of the rural people to get better result in case of various modern health programmes. Apart from the Gender transformative maternal health programme, there is a need for study on how assets, women empowerment, occupation and decision making power will play a role in accepting modern health care system among the rural traditional families.
- Poor health outcome of the rural community need to be read within in the context of rapid urbanization, focusing poor health infrastructure, costly

treatment. However, in a multicultural society rural childhood mortality in India cannot be analyzed in a contextual vacuum. Instead, they need to be looked at in the light of larger socio economic changes experienced by the rural community over the period of time. We felt that lack of good primary health care, perceived and personal risks, lack of awareness have lead in failing health improvements programmes:

CHAPTER-X
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Appendices-I
(Reprints of the Published Papers)

Appendices-II
(Interview schedules)

SCHEDULED QUESTIONNAIRES

Not exhaustive

- **Not necessarily be in the same order**

1. What is the normal size of a household?

- a)2-4 b) 4-6 c) 6-8 d) more than 10

2. What is the frequency distribution of age groups

- a) bellow 12 months b)1-5 years c)6-14 d)15-25 e)Above 25

3. What is the total number of deliveries so far

4. What is the total Number of live births:

5. What is the total Number of still births/miscarriage:

Frequency distribution of age groups of menopause

- a) 40-45 b) 45-50 c)50-55 d) more than 50

6. Distribution of woman according to age at first conception

- a)12- 15 b) 16-20 c) 21-25 d) more than 25 year's of age

7. Normal life expectancy

- below 25 years b) 25-35 c)35-45 d)none of these

8. Age specific fertility rate

- a) up to 14 b) 15-19 c)2- 25 d) 25-30 e) 31-40

9. Marital status of the informants?

- a) Married b) Unmarried c) Widow/widower d) separated

10.Total number of the consanguineous marriages

11.Total number of death occurred during delivery

12. Proportions of female addicts

- a) NO
- b) Yes
- c) occasionally
- d) other

13. Number of child (6-14) addicts

- a) NO
- b) Yes
- c) occasionally
- d) other

14. Total amount spent on health (per year)

a) Less than 500 b) Less than 500-1500 c) 1000-1500 d) More than 15000

15. Total amount spent on foodstuff and education (per month)

a) Less than 500 b) Less than 500-1500 c) 1000-1500 d) More than 15000

16. General Economic status of the informants

a) Very poor b) poor c) not so poor d) well off

17. What is the education level of the informants?

a) Up to Primary b) up to Higher Primary c) High School d) College

18. Type of the family?

a) Nuclear family b) Joint family c) Extended family

19. What is the other social behaviour?

a) TV watching b) radio c) reading newspapers d) spending leisure time

20. Choice of female patients (age wise also) for their health problems

a) midwives b) lady medicine specialist c) male medicine men d) other

21. How many of the households are working?

a) 1-2 b) 2-3 c) 3-4 d) more than 4

22. What is the occupations of household members:

a) Daily wage b) agriculture c) skilled d) semi skilled e) none

23. What is the total number of savings of household (p/m)

500 Rs. b) 1000 c) 1500 d) above 1500

24. Number of the households living in

a) Hut b) pucca c) semi pucca d) other type

25. What is the total household debit?

a) 1000-2500 b) 3000-5000 c) 6000-10000 d) above 10000

26. What are the sources of drinking water

- a) tap water, b) well water c) hand pump d) pond water

27. Types of latrine available

- a) Pucca sanitary b) pucca borehole c) mixed scavenging d) open field

28. Main reason behind performing rituals when a girl child attains puberty

- a) it is a custom b) to please the God c) for her long fertility period d) other

29. Number of informants suffering from

- a) Cancer b) heart problem c) bone related d) other internal problem

30. What is the reason for menopause

- a) left to the god b) due age c) our food style d) other

31. Informants are getting information about health from

- a) Through their educated children b) TV c) Radio d) News papers e) village nurse
- e) other resources

32. What action will be taken for Dog, Snake and Scorpion bite

- a) Home remedies b) medicine men c) religious leaders d) allopathic

33. What action taken for Diarrhea problem

- a) home remedy b) eating fruits c) drinking juice d) ORS e) PHCs

34. Why people die

- a) Past deeds b) witchcraft c) sorcery d) evil force e) short life span f) don't know

35. Total number of cases of Measles, Chicken Pox and Leprosy reported since last 5 years

- a) less than 5 b) 5-10 c) 10-20 d) more than 20

36. Reasons for Measles, Chicken Pox and Leprosy

a) Curse b) bad deeds c) heredity d) food items e) other

37. Number of children died below 6 years due to Typhoid, Malaria, Jaundice and Cholera

a) less than 10 b) 10-20 c) 20-30 d) more than 30

38. How common Typhoid, Malaria, Jaundice, Cholera among the children below 6 years old

a) rare b) very common c) very frequent d) no idea

39. What is the total income of the informants who does/visit home medication/medicine men/religious leader/Govt. PHCs and private clinic

a) 750-1000 Rs. b) 1000-2000 c) 2000-3000 d) 3000+

40. Total Number of the informants suffering from Congenital Deformities

a) less than 5 b) 5-10 c) 10-20 d) more than 20

41. Distribution of age frequencies of above mentioned diseases

a) 1-6 b) 2-10 c) 10-15 d) more than 15

42. What is the number of the informants who believe disease and illness is normally due to

a) Evil spirit, b) evil eye c) witchcraft d) sorcery e) no idea

43. What is the number of the informants who believe disease and illness is normally due to

a) Sexual intercourse with evils and menstruating woman b) relationship with other rural c) failure to perform divine rite d) other

44. What is the opinion regarding Govt. Doctors?

a) Duty to serve to the people b) serves only to rich people c) exploiting people d) not regularly coming to the duty e) other

45. What is the opinion regarding Govt. PHCs

a) Good b) not so good d) bad e) worst e) not visited so far

46. Number of visits in the last 6-8 months to PHCs

a) one time b) twice c) thrice d) more than thrice e) not visited

47. What is the Reason Visiting PHCs during last one month?

a) Typhoid b) Malaria c) Jaundice d) Cholera e) other

48. How many of them been to PHCs specially for

a) Abortion b) Mental illness c) TB

49. Reasons Visiting to the District Hospital

a) Major surgery b) heart problem c) bone related d) internal problems e) STD/AIDS

50. Propagation of the people who don't like family planning?

a) Fear of God b) it is against the custom c) fear of operation c) desire to have more children d) no idea

51. Nutritional awareness of the informants

a) Yes b) No c) just heard d) no idea

52. Opinion about establishment of more multi-doctors centers at central locations

a) Good idea b) not good idea c) may be good d) no reply

53. What are the common causes of mortality?

a) Fever b) Diarrhea c) infection disease d) other reason

54. What are the border framework of health needs of the informants?

a) Economic condition b) cultural framework c) educational level d) cleanness e) hospital service f) don't have any idea

55. Do you go for allopathic medicine with full desire?

- a) Yes always
- b) Not always
- c) Some time only
- d) No way
- e) Other

56. What are the Basic requirements of healthy persons?

a) Food cloth and shelter b) skills and training, c) as awareness and ideas status and d) living standard

57. How common Typhoid, Malaria, Jaundice, Cholera, TB, Abortion, Scabies and Mental illness is

a) Very frequent b) regular interval c) very common d) not so for e) rare f) very rare

58. Number of households/informants suffered/ing from in the last 1-2 years by

a) Typhoid b) Malaria c) Jaundies d) Cholera a) TB b) Scabies c) Menatl Illness

59. Who is a person being healthy

a) Can with stand cold and hot b) who can walk a long distance c) who can digest any thing d) who lives for a longer time e) other

60. Who is a person being unhealthy?

a) Whose body is deformed b) who has no red blood c) always depend on medicine d) cannot resist and fight against forces other

61. Do you agree cost for treatment influences on healthcare choice?

a) Yes b) No c) may be d) no idea

62. What are the other Common traits of a health person?

a) Like other individual beliefs and norms b) fulfillment of personnel or groups social requirements c) both of the above d) no idea

63. What is keeping health in good condition?

a) without any medicine b) only with allopathic medicine only with traditional medicine d) proper diet e) hygiene environment f) health education g) no idea

64. Are some habits of older causing ill-health to young people

a) Yes b) No c) may be d) no idea

65. What are the cultural norms on diet pattern?

a) For children only b) for pregnant mothers c) for girl children d) for working children d) no idea

66. Ailments such as arthritis and cough and cough is believed to be caused due to

a) excess heat of the food b) cold food items c) taking excess water/air d) no idea

67. What is the Common care for ones own health

a) Nothing special, b) for health regularity of cleanliness c) proper diet only d) hygienic environment e) no idea

68. What is the initiative taken for illness at the family level

a) Watching common symptoms of sick person b) consulting with family members about treatment c) going for treatment according to the local beliefs d) other

69. What is the type of drinking water

a) Nothing special b) Filtering water c) Boiling water d) Keep in to covered mud pot e) Not known

70. Primary reason for good child development

a) Parent's proper attention b) neighborhood c) left to the god d) education e) immnisation

71. What are the primary requirements for good health of the children?

a) Boon of the Good b) based on pervious generation deeds c) economic and education of the parents d) school f) no idea

72. What is the type of contraceptive adopted

- a) Tubectomy b) Vasectomy c) Pills d) Nirodh e) other

73. What is the preference of conducting delivery in different places

- a) inside the forest b) at home c) Govt. PHCs d) private clinic

74. Knowledge about Abortion law

- a) God decides b) legal c) illegal d) don't know

75. Normally who does Abortion service

- a) Senior member of the family b) midwives c) hospital d) other

76. What is the reason for spontaneous abortion?

- a) Heredity b) deeds c) good for mother d) good for family e) religious reason f) totally bad

77. Methods followed in abortion

- a) traditional method b) modern surgical methods c) other

78. Why abortion is only with traditional method

- a) Safe b) custom c) no side effects d) god would get angry e) other

79. Why abortion only with modern method

- a) Safe b) to keep the matter secret c) no side effects d) no choice e) other

80. From whom informants are getting assistance for delivery cases

- a) Old lady of the family/neighbor b) midwives c) lady medicine specialist d) PHCs

81. Reason why a patient does not go to PHCs for delivery cases

- a) No lady doctors b) no round the clock service c) fear of pain f) fear towards doctors g) God would get angry g) other

82. Reason why a lady patient does not go to PHCs for Gynec problem

- a) No lady doctors b) shyness c) would like to keep it secret d) other

83. Main reason for still birth/miscarriage

- a) Heredity b) God curse c) ancestral spirit d) no idea

84. What are the reasons for not recommending breast milk

- a) Shyness b) slight evil c) lack of lactation d) bad for both mother and child e) No idea

85. Reasons why rural mothers will not feed babies immediately after the birth

- a) Impurity of breast milk b) against the custom c) poor lactation d) other

86. Number of household's children undergone for the immunizations

- a) All children b) few children c) No response d) no idea

87. Number of informants taken vaccines for

- BCG b) DTP c) Typhoid d) TT e) Polio f) Measles g) Hepatitis

88. Reasons for taking immunization for them/ for their children

- a) Good for health b) force by the health workers c) green signal by the medicine men/religious leaders d) other

89. Reasons for not taking immunization for them/ for their children

- a) Not acceptable b) child gets suffer c) energy will be loosed d) cultural factors e) other reason

90. Reasons for fear of injections

- a) Not acceptable b) against custom c) pain and side effects c) not aware f) other reason

91. What is the Number of Prevalence of addiction?

- a) smoking b) alcohol c) tobacco d) beeda and jerdae) other

92. Who initially diagnosis the health problem?

- a) At family level b) self indicator c) medicine men d) religious leader e) PHC doctor

93. Disease and illness is same /different

- a) Yes b) No c) no idea

94. Season of occurrence of Typhoid Malaria Jaundice Cholera Scabies and Mental illness is in

- a) Summer only b) Winter only c) Rainy only d) Autumn e) no season

95. Type of disease increasing in prevalence in the last five years?

- a) Typhoid, b) Malaria, c) Jaundice, d) Cholera, e) TB, f) Scabies g) Mental illness

96. Typhoid, Malaria, Jaundice, Cholera, TB, Spontaneous Abortion, Scabies and Mental illness/diseases causes due to close relationship with the animals

- a) Yes b) No c) chances are there d) no idea

97. Reasons for accepting allopathic treatment for TB, Scabies and Mental Illness

- a) Speedy recovery b) c) reliable and guarantee d) no special diet/ pooja e) other

98. Reasons for accepting allopathic treatment for Typhoid, Malaria, Jaundice, Cholera,

- a) speed recovery b) short term of treatment c) guarantee of cure
d) other

99. Reasons for not accepting allopathic treatment for Typhoid, Malaria, Jaundice and Cholera

- a) Western medicine is dangerous b) allopathic has some side effects c) will be dangerous for fertility capacity d) against the custom e) other

100. Reason for not accepting allopathic treatment for TB, Scabies and Mental illness

- a) cost factor b) side effects c) not acceptable d) fear towards long term drugs e) other

101. General reasons for visiting Govt. PHC

a) Good treatment b) free/low cost treatment c) doctors respects the patients d) normally treatment will be painless e) no idea

102. General reasons for not visiting PHCs

a) Western medicine is not acceptable b) cost factor c) doctors are not capable d) not for illiterates e) not for poor people f) side effects g) no idea

103. Why western medicine is not good

a) Our God does not permit b) advice by the medicine men /religious leaders c) fear d) other

104. In your idea how a best medicine should be

a) Should be easy to take b) no diet rules c) should be bitterless and painless d) other

105. In your idea how a PHCs should be

a) don't know b) free medicines c) pharmacist should respect us d) should work round the clock e) other

106. In your idea how a best allopathic doctor should be

a) Should respect our deity b) should have patents c) should be very nice d) other

107. Number of deaths occurred due to Typhoid/ Malaria/Jaundice/Cholera,/TB/ Abortion/Scabies / Mental illness in the last three years

a) 1-5 b) 5-12 c) 12-18 d) more than 20

108. Informants who believe Typhoid/ Malaria/Jaundice, Cholera,/TB/ Abortion/Scabies / Mental illness is due to

a) unhygienic b) dirty environment c) not cleanliness d) contaminate food and water

109. Informants who believe Typhoid/ Malaria/Jaundice, Cholera,/TB/ Abortion/Scabies / Mental illness is due to

a) low intake of certain food b) Not eating certain food c) excess of eating of some food items d) malnutrition

110. Informants who believe Typhoid/ Malaria/Jaundice, Cholera,/TB/ Abortion/Scabies / Mental illness is due to excess / low intake of

- a) Vegetables b) Grains c) low intake of water d) using forest fruits

111. Informants who believe Typhoid/ Malaria/Jaundice/Cholera,/ TB/ Abortion/Scabies / Mental illness is due to

- a) visiting urban areas b) watching movies c) brothel d) stepping on certain objects

112. Informants who believe Typhoid/ Malaria/Jaundice, Cholera,/TB/ Abortion/Scabies / Mental illness is due to

- a) for blaming the God b) cutting certain trees c) not fulfilling the promise d) not attending certain pooja's e) ignoring elders advice

114. Informants who believe Typhoid/ Malaria/Jaundice, Cholera,/TB/ Abortion/Scabies / Mental illness is due to

- a) Environmental b) food habits c) seasonal d) other cultural influences

115. Informants who believe Typhoid/ Malaria/Jaundice, Cholera,/TB/ Abortion/Scabies / Mental illness is due to

- a) Heredity b) standard of living c) natural calamities d) illiteracy

116. What preventive measures can be taken to control the outbreak of Typhoid, Malaria, Jaundice, Cholera, TB, and Scabies

- a) Worshipping the God b) regular celebration of fairs and festivals c) sacrificing animals d) respect our tradition/custom e) maintaining sanctity of few things f) other

117. Knowledge regarding TB and Leprosy

- a) Heredity b) untouchable c) social isolation d) for poor people f) no idea

118. Knowledge regarding leucoderma and STD/AIDS

- a) Heredity b) untouchable c) social isolation d) for poor people f) curse of the God g) no idea

119.STD/AIDS is causes only among women beacuse

a) God curse b)due to menstrual cycle c) dont think so d) other

.STD/AIDS is causes only in men

a) God curse b)due to regular outside contacts c) dont think so d) other

120.Informants who believe Typhoid, Jaundice, Cholera and Malaria is due to

a)Humaroyal imbalance b) cosmology c) superhuman causation d) immoral behaviour

e) punishment for deed f) fate g)breach of taboo h) no idea

121Number of informants believe TB, Menatl illness and Scabies is due to

a)Humaroyal imbalance b) cosmology c) superhuman causation d) immoral behaviour

e) punishment for deed f)fate g) breach of taboo h) no idea

122.Number of the informants who believe congenital deformities is due to

a)Humaroyal imbalance b) cosmology c) superhuman causation d) immoral behaviour

e) punishment for deed f) fate g) breach of taboo h) no idea

123.Informants who think an ill person should not utilize different kinds of healers for the same health problem

a) Mixed medicine is harm to the body b) against the custom c) god will get angry d) other

124.Informants who think an ill person can utilize different kinds of healers for different health problems

a) Heeling chances are more b) not against our custom c) previous experiences d) other

125.Typhoid, Jaundice, Cholera, TB, Abortion, Scabies and Mental illness is only curable at

a) Local medicine men only b) religious leaders c) Govt. PHCs only d) private PHCs only e) natural heeling only f) other

126 .Reason for visiting a medicine men only

a) Reliable b) used to c) low cost d) no way e) easy to follow f) no body can f)other

127. Reason for non-visiting to a medicine men

a) not capable b) not updated c) not good enough d) no good rack record dealing these problems f) difficult to follow the instructions

128.Why you like medicine men/religious leaders so much

a) Representative of the God b) immediate availability c) he will respects us c) chief and flexible d) only one who can cure e) our custom

129.Reason for visiting religious leaders only

a) Reliable b) used to c) low cost d) no way e) easy to follow instructions f) no body can other then him g) other

130.Reason for non-visiting to a religious leaders

a) Not so capable b) not updated c) not good enough d) no good track record f) difficult to follow g) other

131.Other medicine system Informants used for Typhoid, Jaundice, Cholera, TB, Malaria, Mental illness and Scabies

a) Ayreurvedic medicine b) homeopathy c) naturopathy d) Yoga

132.Reasons for not go for any modern medicines for these health problems

a)Modern medicine is not so capable b) Doctors dont know any thing about these problems c) tablets and injection are not good for the body d)no pervious examples e) local deity will get angry f) other

133.Reasons for accepting new medicine technology for Typhoid and other diseases etc.

a)These diseases should be cure very fast b) doctors are only capable c) suggestions made by others d) local medicine cant cure with these disease e)other

134.Reasons for home remedy

- a) Previous experience b) safe and hygienic c) cost factors d) experiment e) not known

135.Who is the first choice of the rural to treat these health problems (order of preferences)?

- a) medicine men b) religious leader c)priest d)other

136. Classify the following disease into communicable & non-communicable

- a) Malaria b) Jaundies c) Cholera d)Typhoid e)Malaria f)TB g)Scabies f)Menatl Illness

137.Common behaviour towards TB, Leprosy and Mental illness patents

- a) taboo b) isolation c) ex-communication d) deporting

138.Why TB, Leprosy and Mental illness is permanently not curable?

- a) no medicine is available b) no body is capable including PHCs c) fate d) pervious experience e)other

139. Awareness about health effects due to addictions

- a)Yes b) no c) not completely d) no idea

140.The longer the period of illness, greater are the chance of searching for meanings related to the original and cause of the illness

- a)Yes b) no c) may be d) dont know

141.How many informants classify Malaria, Jaundies, Cholera d Typhoid, Malaria, TB, Scabies Menatl Illness is due to

- a) Bacteria b). vectors c) other pathogens

142.Informants who believe Typhoid, Jaundice, Cholera, TB, Malaria, Mental illness and Scabies affects on

- a) Morphology of the body b) anatomy of the body c) physiology of the body

143. Informants who visit the Govt. PHCs (based on the suggestions made by others) for Typhoid, Jaundice, Cholera, TB, Malaria, Mental illness and Scabies

- a) when referred by the other relatives
- b) suggested by the medicine men
- c) religious leader
- d) self
- e) other

144. Major reasons for performing healing rituals for specific type of disease

- a) To neutralize the evil effects
- b) satisfy the demands of pathogenic agents
- c) patching up/recreating disrupted cultural order
- d) to drive away the evil spirit
- e) all

145. Other associated reasons for performing healing rituals is

- a) Re-balancing of the bodily equilibrium
- b) excommunicate the soul of a person from the community
- c) to ex-communicate a patient from social circle
- d) all

146. Consuming of indigenous medicine with the modern medicine is OK because

- a) Speedy recovery
- b) no side effects
- c) kind of new one
- d) other

147. Consume of indigenous medicine with modern medicine is Not OK because

- a) Fear of impurity of body/blood
- b) against the custom
- c) deity may get angry
- d) chances of the side effects
- e) no specific reasons

148. Number of informants who would like to take drugs made out of

- a) plants extracts
- b) animal extracts
- c) made out of soil and stones
- d) mantra/chant/song/conception
- e) other

149. Number of informants who perceived etiology between impact of development or lack of development and the disease

- a) God might get angry
- b) due to entry of new people
- c) custom does not permit
- d) environmental

150. Number of Informants who have taken any preventive measures

- a) Immunization
- b) maintaining good surroundings
- c) awareness about various diseases
- d) other

151.Number of informants who have the concept of digestive, respiratory nervous, and circulatory systems of the body.

a) controlled by the god b) controlled by the evil force c) not under control d) no idea

152.Do you think there is a cooperation between different types of healthcare providers

- a) medicine men does recommend us to visit religious leaders
- b) religious leaders does recommend us to visit medicine men
- c) here is no such cooperation among medicine men/religious leaders
- d) there is a good relationship among various healers
- e) we don't think so

153.Informants, who use rituals that promote good health, prevent specific diseases

a) Special worship b) sacrifice animals c) other

154.Informants not using family planning methods because

a) Against the god will b) not in the custom c) fear of evil spirit d) no idea e) other

155.Type uncommon practices in curing some particular diseases

a) fire shock b) cuttings c)beating with sticks/tree branches d)other

156.General health problem informants got (assumed) due to breach taboos?

a) physical problem b)menatl problem c)not visible d)not known

157.Medicine men who believes Typhoid, Malaria, Jaundice, Cholera, TB, Abortion, Scabies and Mental illness causes due to

a)Humaroyal imbalance b) cosmology c) superhuman causation d) immoral behaviour
e) punishment for deed f)fate g) breach of taboo

158.Medicine men who believes Typhoid/Malaria, Jaundice/Cholera/TB/ Abortion/ Scabies and Mental illness affects on following part of the body

a) morphology, b)anatomy c) physiology d) other

159.Reason why .Medicine men who recommends a patient to seek allopathic care because

a) Not capable himself b) peasant is in critical stage c) peasant is poor d) speed recovery e) other

160. Number of medicinal men/lady medicine men who treat STD or HIV/AIDS so for?

Medicinal men who believes healthcare-seeking behavior vary according to the their religion or caste?

a) different custom b) different deity c) different rituals d) other

161. Midwives who follows scientific procedure during delivery

a) safe to both the child and mother b) no after effects c) training d) other

162. Reasons medicine men/religious leaders not suggesting allopathic treatment for the patients

a) fear of lose of customers b) not aware of the advantage c) not acceptable d) side effects f) personal reasons g) prestige f) other

163. Medicine men who believe ritual healing and health behaviour differs by caste and tribe

a) Due to different deity b) dont c) our custom does not permit to treat them d) other

164. Proportion of medicine men's willingness to take government-sponsored training

a) OK no problem b) Sorry I don't like it c) It is unacceptable d) They can't teach any thing e) other

165. Medicine men who rejects allopathic medical treatment

a) fear b) against our culture c) side effects d) other professional reasons

166. Number of medicine men who believe healthcare-seeking practices of the people here changed over the last 5 –10 year's because

a) Awareness b) development programmes c) education d) other

167. Educated rural youths who believe Typhoid/ Malaria,/ Jaundice/Cholera/TB/Abortion/ Scabies and Mental illness disease Causes due to

a) Humoral imbalance b) cosmology c) superhuman causation d) immoral behaviour
e) punishment for deed f) fate g) breach of taboo h) other

168. Rural youths who believe Typhoid/ Malaria,/ Jaundice/Cholera/TB/Abortion/ Scabies and Mental illness disease Causes due to

a) water born b) contaminate food c) due to non-hygienic d) heredity e) other

169. Rural youths who believe treatment for Typhoid/ Malaria,/ Jaundice/Cholera/TB/Abortion/ Scabies and Mental illness disease with

a) Home medication b) medicinal men c) religious leader d) allopathic

170. Rural youths who believe their local medicinal men/religious leaders are good enough to cure diseases

a) No side effects b) chief and best c) previous experience d) other

171. Number of rural youth's who believe allopathic medicine is good when compare with ayurvedic and local herbal medicine in terms of

a) Efficacy b) safety c) speed of recovery d) other

172. Number of rural youth's aware of safe reproductive health availability, quality, and price of family planning services in their community.

a) Yes b) No d) No idea

173. Number of rural youth's who believe child mortality affect family fertility decisions of the community

a) Yes b) No d) No idea

174. Proportion of educated rural youths that received health education during their schooling

- a) We had b) we did not had c- not remember d) no idea

175. Religious leaders who believe Typhoid/ Malaria,/ Jaundice/Cholera/TB/Abortion/ Scabies and Mental illness disease Causes due to

- a) Humaroyal imbalance b) cosmology c) superhuman causation d) immoral behaviour
- e) punishment for deed f) fate g) breach of taboo

176. Number of religious leaders who believe change in health beliefs and behavior amongst the local rural people in the last 5 years?

- a) Effect mass media b) education c) local PHCs d) other

177. At what stage normally rural people would visit PHC

- a) At the very beginning b) at the mid stage c) when medicine/religious leaders gets fail d) at the chronic stage

178. Normally who is suggesting the patients to visit PHCs?

- a) Family members b) relatives c) medicine/religious leaders d) others

178. Proportion of midwives that have received health training from government/private

- a) yes b) no c) other

179. Proportion of midwives treating women for STDs and AIDS

180. Rural patients' degree of acceptance of PHC medication/treatment recommendations

- a) they are accepting with full confidence
- b) basically they are feeling un-comfortable with allopathic medicine
- c) they are feeling like no other way for particular type of health problem
- d) for other pressure they are accepting
- e) other

180. Doctors who think patients don't like to visit PHCs because
a) Illiteracy b) fear c) against their culture d) no awareness e) other

181. How awareness can be created about usage of PHCs
a) Through their educated children b) by providing good treatment at PHCs c)
regular contacts with hamlets d) creation of awareness e) other

182. What are the specific factors affecting child mortality/morbidity as thought by a
doctor

a) Consanguineous marriage b) non vaccination c) carelessness d) extreme belief in
god/fate f) negligence g) other

185. Doctors think medical practice among the rural has undergone tremendous
change in its basic idea, technology and treatment procedure in the context of
medical pluralism because
a) success rate of different systems of medicine b) low-cost, and easily accessible c)
awareness of side effects d) improvements in social economic status e) effect of
mass media f) other

186. NGOs involved in goal setting, planning, implementing and monitoring of rural
health programmes
a) Collaboration with the local self Govt. b) report to the policy makers c) own
research units d) evaluation of the programmes e) other

187. NGOs who have devised a plan for mobilization of natural resources having
bearing on the life style of the rural communities in the matter of health and
medications.
a) Encourage to grow more medicinal plants b) conservation of forest resources c)
establishment of local drug units d) other

188. Measures taken by the DHO (District Health Office) to attract rural patients
towards PHCs

a) Respect rural patents b) respect their culture c) using more advanced type of diagnosis system d) be highly sympathetic e) other

189. Measures taken to control the out break of Typhoid, Malaria, Jaundice, Cholera, TB, and Scabies by the district health office

a) Awareness creation b) immunization c) mobile health unit d) round clock service of PHCs d) other

190. How community feels (focus group interview) about rural medicine system

a) Good b) no side effect c) it doesn't cure all the medicine d) scientific research is required d) other

191. How community feels about improvising health behaviour of the rural?

a) Create awareness using media b) invent cultural suitable medical system/s c) scientific training of medicine men d) more research in effective interventions in their cultural fabrics

192. How community feels about convincing rural to visit PHCs for their health problem?

a) Establishment of more multi-doctor centers at central locations b) treatments must be free of cost c) should try to develop confidence among the patients d) doctors should know the socio-economic background of the patients e) road network as well as transportation to the surrounding villages should be improved

193. How community feels about new model Health Policy for the rural?

a) Efforts should be made to devise new systems or patterns of institutions by which the access of rurals to modern care should be enhanced.

b) A synthesis of Indian systems of medicine like Ayurveda and Siddha with the rural system and modern medicine should be promoted.

c) Empowering them to plan, implement, operate and maintain their own water supply and sanitation systems.

d) All modern facilities to the PHCs and scope for the scientific training for the medicine men

Appendices-III

Bio data of the Researcher

CURRICULUM VITAE

Dr. D.C.NANJUNDA

Associate Professor Cum. Dy. Director
Centre for the Study of Social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy,
Humanities Block, University Of Mysore
Mysore 06, Karnataka State, India
Email: anthroedit@ymail.com Phone (0) 0821-2419637 Cell 09880964840

1. Personal Data

Date of Birth: 18.04.1976
Gender: Male
Nationality: Indian
Religion: Hindu
Marital Status: Married
Aadar ID 6453 87327704

2. Current Affiliation:

Associate. Professor (**Plan post**)
Centre for the Study of Social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy,
Humanities Block, University of Mysore, Mysore 06-India

3. Brief Synopsis

- Post doctoral degrees-
- Accredited Pre doctoral Research Experiences: Four Years
- Post doctoral Research Experiences: Ten Years
- Teaching Experience : M.Phil Level (Two Years)
- Fellow Membership : Indian Academic Researchers Association (F.I.A.R.A)
- National Senior Fellowship Awardee (ICSSR)*
- Publications: More than 165 articles (Journal and Edited books)
- RTI officer (by virtue of the Acting Director)
- Vigilant officer (by virtue of the Acting Director)

**Has raised over Rs. 80,00,000/- (Rupees Eighty lakh and above) external grants from the various funding agencies in total as a main applicant for the purpose of research, conference, etc purpose till date

Publications:

1	No. of articles published in international journals	28
2	No. of articles published in national journals	120
3	No. of edited volumes	15
4	No. of articles in Edited volumes	50
5	No. of general articles in Kannada	65
6	No. of books authored	8

7	No. of special issues of journals edited	1
8	No. of course materials wrote for different universities	1
9	No.of books under publication	1
10	No. of articles published in other Journals	35
11	No. of Occasional Papers /Monograph/ Working Book	4
12	Media coverage of the research study	5

Research Projects

1	No. Fellowships awarded	4
2	No. Research Projects conducted	10
3	No. Collaboration Research Projects conducted	2
4	No. of workshop grants conducted	6
5	No. seminars conducted with grants	12
6	No. Training Fellowship	2

Papers Presented in the national and international seminars/conferences et

1	No of papers presented in the national seminars	40
2	Papers presented in the international seminars	5
3	Number of sessions chaired	3
4	No of lectures/ special lectures or talks delivered	7
5	Journal board member	10

Community Service

1	NGO founded	1
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Languages: English, Kannada, and Hindi (Speak)

4. Academic Record---(from the Latest)

Degree Obtained	College And University	Year	Subjects	Division
(D. Litt)	Srinivas University, Mangalore	2018	Sociology	Thesis under submission
M.A	Karnataka State Open University	2010	Sociology	Second Division
Ph.D.	University of Mysore	2007	Social Anthropology	-----
M.Sc.	University of Mysore	2002	Anthropology	First class
B.Ed	St. Josephs' College of Education Mysore	1998	General	Distinction
B.Sc.	JSS College, Ooty road, Mysore	1997	Chemistry, Botany, Zoology	High Second Division-

5. Other Diploma/PG Diploma Courses

Sl, No	Name of the Diploma	Name of the University	Year	Mode	Grade
1	P G Diploma In Higher Education	Karnataka State Open University (KSOU)	2011	Distance Education	I st Class
2	P G Diploma In Business Administration	KSOU University	2012	Distance Education	2 nd Class
3	Diploma in Statistical And Operation Research	KSOU University	-----	Distance Education	Could not complete

* NET (for Lectureship) Exam Qualified in 2002 in Anthropology with the First attempt

Specializations :

- Public Health,
- Medical Sociology and Anthropology
- Neuro Sociology
- Development Anthropology,
- Social Exclusion/inclusion
- Applied and Clinical Sociology

Subject of Interest

- Ethnography
- Community development

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6. Professional Experience

Sl, No	Position	University/ Institute	Duration	Nature of Job
1	Associate Professor <i>cum</i> Dy. Director (Plan post)	Centre for the Study of Social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy, University of Mysore, Also In charge Director from Feb 2015 to till date	From June 2013-	Research and Administration
2	Reader <i>cum</i> Dy. Director (Plan post)	Centre for the Study of Social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy, University of Mysore,	June 2010 to June 2013	Research and Administration
3	Assistant Professor <i>cum</i> Asst. Director	Centre for the Study of Social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy, University of Mysore,	May 2010 to June 2010	Research

4	Post doctoral Research Associate (ICMR)	Department of Anthropology, University of Mysore	Sept 2008 to May 2010	Research
5	Project Fellow(UGC funded Major Research Project)	Department of Political Science, University of Mysore	July 2006 - July 2008	Research
6	Co-ordinator	Rural Organization for Appropriate Development Trust® Mysore based NGO*	Jan 2005- July 2006	Administration
7	Research Assistant (Accredited)	To an American Researcher (Department of Anthropology, University of Arizona-USA) in Mysore district	Sept 2002 -March 2004	Research
8	Field Staff – Research	MDS TRUST®, Bangalore based NGO	1998(Oct)-1999(May)	Field Assistant

***Founded by this Candidate**

7. Teaching and other Experiences

Sl,No	Level	Topics Covered	Duration
1	M.Phil (in Area Studies)	Community Development and Research Methodology	Two Years (2013-2014) (2016-2017)

7(a) M.Phil (Area Studies)

Sl,No	Level	Course	Duration
1	Board of Examiner	M.Phil (Area Studies)	(2012-2013)
2	Course co-ordinator	M.Phil (Area Studies)	(2016-17)

8.PUBLICATIONS (NATIOANL /INTERNATIOANL /STATE)

Sl no	Title, Journal with volume, Year and Page Nos	First/Corresponding author	Co-author	ISSN/ ISBN No.
1	Promotion of Rural Health: Experience of an Indian NGO, <i>Asian Social Work and Policy Review(Blackwell pub)</i> 2, (2) 2008	Nanjunda	-----	
2	Dropouts Problem among Karnataka (India) Tribal Children: Where Rubber hits the Road? <i>Journal Of Educational Research (Pakistan)</i> , Vol.11, No 2 2008 Pp 107-118	Nanjunda	-----	1027-9776
3	Commercialisation of Medicinal Plants and Issues of Rural Economic Transformation in Karnataka (India): A Suggested Model”, <i>Afro Asian journal of rural development</i> , Vol. 41, No. 1, January –June 2008. Pp83-90	Nanjunda	---	0972-3021
4	Compulsory Education And Child Labor Issue In India: A Paradox or Nexus, <i>Socio Economic Development Panorama (Nepal)</i> , 1(4) Jan –June 2009 pp 56-59	Nanjunda	--	1999-3536
5	Natives ethno veterinary practice in Coorg Dist Karnataka Some Preliminary Observations, <i>Africa Journal of Animal And Bio Medical Sciences</i> 4(2) 2009	Nanjunda	Venu .G	2251-7310
6	Child Labour In India: A Multilevel Disciplinary Approach, <i>Kasetstart Journal Of Social Sciences, (Thailand)</i> .31 (2) May-Aug,2010.pp 263-270	Nanjunda	--	0125-8370
7	NGOs And Rural Poverty Eradication In Karnataka-India: Tracing The Root of The Difficulty And Solution, <i>Bodhi (Nepal)</i> 4 (1), 2010. 71-80.	Nanjunda	Mohapatra	2091-0479
8	Ethno-Medico-Botanical Investigation of Jenu Kuruba Ethnic Group Of Karnataka State, India, <i>Bangladesh Journal Of Medical Science</i> , Vol. 9, No 3 (July 2010).	Nanjunda	----	1607-0755
9	Role of Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) Interventions On Tribal Health: Some Annotations From Grass Root Level, <i>International NGO Journal</i> , 6(9), Sept, 2011,	Nanjunda	Dinesha,	1993-8225
10	Re-Examination of Child Labor from few Unnoticed Perspectives, <i>Academic Research International (Pakistan)</i> , 1(2) September 2011.	Steven	Nanjunda	2223-9944
11	Thoughts on Redesigning to Eliminate Child Labor Problem: Some Concepts, <i>Pakistan Journal Of Applied Social Sciences</i> , Volume 1, Issue 1, July 2011. Pp 6-10	Nanjunda	--	2220-5756
12	From the High End of Society: Elite Perceptions of Poverty And Social Exclusion In	Nanjunda	---	0125-3689

	Karnataka State – <i>NIDA Development Journal</i> , (Thailand) Vol.53 No 2 April-June 2013)			
13	Health Scenario In Rural Karnataka- South India: An Ethnographic Review On Interactional And Situational Analysis And The Language Of Efficacy, The Kasetsart Journal of Social Sciences, Thailand Volume 36 No 2.2014	Nanjunda	--	0125-8370
14	Academic Growth And Integrity: How Do Institute Of Higher Learning Academicians Understanding It? <i>Bangladesh Education Journal</i> , 13(2) June 2014 .	Nanjunda	Anu Bhawana	1811-0762
15	Corporate Social Responsibility And Sustainable Development: A Review On Challenges And Opportunities, <i>Pakistan Business Review</i> , 16(4) July 2014 pp 960-964	Williams	Nanjunda	1561-8706
16	Perceptions And Knowledge About Sexually Transmitted Diseases (STD) Among Rural People: Some Ground Realities, <i>South East Asian Journal Of Public Health (Bangladesh)</i> 4(1) 2013.	Nanjunda	---	2220-9476
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5	Mid day Meals for children: A Retrospection	In Narashimsrao (Edt) Rural Development, India	Serial Publications New Delhi National	Rajendra	Nanjunda
6	Development of Primitive Tribal Groups(PTG) In Karnataka : Some Preliminary Observations	In Krishnamurthy And Others (Edt) Indian Health Scenario: Perspective And Dimensions ,	Serial Publications New Delhi National	Nanjunda	-
7	Education Gender and Class of Gender Dalit Children Accessing to Schooling In Karnataka Evidence from HD report	In Nanjunda and Others (Etd) India Development: Issues And Prospects,	Anmol Publisher, New Delhi, National	Nanjunda	Mahadevailh, Muruali Mohan,
8	Does Child Labour Displace Child Rights? Issues and Prospective	In M.S Gupta (Edt) Child Labor: Different Dimensions,	Madhav Books, Haryana (Edition :2011) National	Nanjunda	---

9	Rights to Compulsory Education Act 2009 And Inclusive Education: Where Rubber Hits the Road ?	In (Edt) Rajive Kumar Narendra Kumar Elementary Education in India	Gyan Publications New Delhi National	Dinesha	Nanjunda
9	Financial Inclusion And Microfinance: A Perspective.	In Siddaraju (Edt) Financial Inclusion In India: Issues And Challenges,	Gyan Publications, New Delhi National	Dinesha	Kiran Kumar and Nanjunda
10	Empowering Small And Marginal Farmers For Inclusive Agriculture Growth: An Overview	In Siddaraju (Edt) Inclusive Agricultural Development	APH Publishing New Delhi. National	Dinesha	Nanjunda
11	Rural Cultural Transformations and Changes In Health Behavior: Some Annotations	In Nanjunda and Dinesh (Edt), New Public Health Topics in India 2014	Spring Leaf, Publications, Mysore Local	Nanjunda	
12	Reservation for Dalith Muslims: What We Know An What We Don't Now:	In Ramesh (Edt) Religious Conversion: Constitutional Perspective	Mysore University Publications Local	Nanjunda	Dinesha
13	Situational Analysis Of Children In Mysore City –India: Some Preliminary Annotations	In S. Jyothi Lakshmi and Sunitha (Edit) Redesigning Of Inclusive Development,2014	Gyan Publications New Delhi National	Nanjunda	Dinesh
14	The Self Is More Than Its Body And Much More Than An Illness: Health Culture And Conditions Of The Soliga Tribal Population In Karnataka	In Kedarnath Dash (Edit) Health And Tribes In India: Challenges And Opportunities	SARUP BOOK PUBLISHERS (P) LTD.	Nanjunda	---
15	Social Dynamics And Cultural Frontier Of Health Care In Rural India: A Medico-Sociological Review	In Lancy Dsouza (Edit) Public Health And Psychology,2014	Discovery Publications National	Nanjunda	Anu bhawan
16	Intra-Rural Ecology Of Primary Health Care: Socioeconomic Characteristics, Accessibility , And Utilization Pattern	In Jyothi Lakshmi and Nameetha (Edt) <i>Growth, Inequality And Social Development,2015</i>	Discovery Publications, New delhi National	Nanjunda	-----

17	Eco Tourism And Tribal Development: Some Empirical Evidences	In Ramakrishan Madal (Edt) Poverty, Inequality And Food Security,2015	Discovery Publications –New Delhi	Nanjunda	Jyothi Lakshmi
18	Constriction Of Identify And Social Development In Social Culture Land Scape	in S. Jyothi Lakshmi and Sunitha (Edit) Redesigning of Inclusive Development,2014	Discovery Publications National	Motaleb azari	Nanjunda
19	Pattern in Growth and Financing of Higher Education in India: Does Quality Responding To it	It Dinesha (Edit) Inclusive Higher Education, Between quality and reservation,2014	Kalpaz Publications, New Delhi National	Nanjunda	Jyothi Lakshmi
20	Psycho Socio Statsu of The Child Laborers	In Lancy D Souza (Edt) Readings In Development Psychology	Discovery Publisher, New Delhi National	Nanjunda,	Mahdeviah
21	Gender Symmetry In Domestic Violence In India: What We Know And What We Don't Know?	In Huche Gowda (Edt) Gender Studies in India	Current Publications. Agra	Mamata Kyatannana va	Nanjunda,
22	The Changing Socio- Economic Profiles of Kadar Tribes of Kerala– Where Rubber Hits The Road?	In Sidda raju (Edt) Women and Inclusive Growth	ROAD Publications, Mysore	Priya.K.R.	Nanjunda,
23	Influences Of Socio-Cultural Factors On The Health Of The Elderly Population Of Tribes – A Case Study Of Kadukuruba	in Swati Chakraborty(Edt) Inclusive Development of The Tribes	Anmol Publisher; New Delhi National	Nanjunda,	---
24	Tracing Corporate Social Responsibility In Rural Development: Evidences From India	India In Siddraju And Ramesh (Edt) Rural Development And Inclusive Growth,	Gyan Publication New Delhi National	Nanjunda,	Appaji gowda
25	Features Of Medical Pluralism and Health Seeking Behavior of Karnataka Tribes	In Nanjunda (Edt) Tribal Development: Issues and Challenges (Kannada)2014,	Deeksha Publications, Mysore Local	Nanjunda,	---
27	Devaraja Nayaka and Nanjunda NGOs, Microfinance Institutions and Social	In B.T Ramappa (Edt) Micro Finance and Inclusive growth Kalpaz books, New Delhi	D.Nayaka	Nanjunda	--

	Intermediation				
28	Social empowerment of Rural Women: How Information Technology Has a Decisive role?	In Divya and others (Edt) Transforming India in the 21 st Century , Perspectives, Challenges and Policy Implications, 2015	Spring leaf publications	Nanjunda	---
29	Women and the Unorganized Sector: An exploratory Study on Domestic women Servants in Mysore city -India	in Swathi chakraborty and RB Upadhyay(editors) Gender Development In India:- Retrospect And Prospect, Aavishkar Publications, 2015	Aavishkar Publishers	Nanjunda ,	---
30	Prevalence of Common Mental Health Problems among Rural Community: A Case of Kodagu Districts -Karnataka State	In Lancy dsouza (Edt) Emerging Issues in Social Psychology, Discovery Publishers, New Delhi	Discovery Publications	Nanjunda ,	---
31	Breaking the Barriers?: Inclusive Development of Rural Women Through ICT,	In the National Seminar (Edt) Huchhe gowda and Talwarsabanna		Nanjunda	----
32	Role of good governance in economic growth : An outlook	Leela appaji and Divya (Edts) in Changing India: Objectives Challenges and Policy Implications,	Spring leaf publications, Mysore	Nanjunda ,	---
33	Rural Poverty and Regional Disparity in Karnataka: Some Unrevealed Truth.	In Leela appaji and Divy B.S(Edts) Rural Infrastructure Development- Issues and Challenges in India,	Spring leaf publications, Mysore	Nanjunda	---
34	Voice for the Voiceless ?: An Examination of the Potential of Community radio in Local Social Inclusion Process	In John (Edt) Media and Development	Dominant Publications, National	Nanjunda	---
35	Approaches for Social inclusion of Farmers: Multi-dimensional Perspective	In Ragavendra and Others(Edit) The Problems and Prospects of Sustainable Agriculture	Nayana Publisher,mysore	Nanjunda	---
36	Genesis of Untouchability and Social Exclusion: Human rights Perspective	In Ramesh and others(Edt) Issues and Changes Of Human Rights In Contemporary World	Nayana Publisher,mysore	Nanjunda	---
37	Rural Development And ICT : An Inclusive Structure For E- Governance	In Kumarand Panchanatham(Edt) the book E-Governance – Current Scenario	Archers & Elevators publishing House,	Nanjunda	----

			ISBN:978-93-85640-12-5 (e-book)		
38	ICT-Driven Social Sciences and Humanities Research: Issues and Challenges	In the book ICT and Social Science Research (Edt) Kumar D Dr.N.Panchanatham Published by	Archers & Elevators publishing House, ISBN: 978-93-85640-13-2 (e-book)	Nanjunda,	---
39	Women and Advertisement Sector	In Divya and Ramachandra (Edts) Women Empowerment –Dimensions and Challenges	Deeksha Publications, Mysore	Nanjunda	----
40	Women Empowerment and Maternal health	In Divya and Ramachandra (Edt) Women Empowerment: Issues and Concerns	Deeksha Publications, Mysore	Nanjunda,	---
41	Rural poverty and Unemployment problems : Some Emerging Thoughts	In Nagaraja and others (Edit) Poverty Alleviation Programmes Problems: Prospects and Remedial Strategies	Deeksha Publications, Mysore	Nanjunda,	---
42	Rural Migration and Exclusion in India: Some Perspectives	In Pavithra (Edt) Contemporary Issues in Empowerment of Weaker Section	Bharahti College Mandya	Nanjunda,	--
43	Health Schemes for the Weaker Sections; A Case Study Of Caste Discrimination among Jananai Suraksha Yojana beneficiaries)	In Pavithra (Edt) Contemporary Issues in Empowerment of Weaker Section	Bharahti College Mandya	Prasad	Nanjunda
44	A Review of Schemes For Women Empowerment And Maternal Health	Empowerment Of Indian Women Through Skill Eco System Organized	Kristu Jayanti Collge Bangalore	Nanjudna	Surendra
42	Inclusive Scheme for Unorganized Sector Workers Will It Really Serve The Purpose : Will It Really Serve the Purpose?	In siddaraju (Edt) Social Security and Social Inclusion	ROAD Trust Publications Mysore	Nanjunda,	---
43	CSR in Rural India: Some Perspectives;	In Siddaraju (Edt) Social development in India: Emerging Debates	Deeksha Publications, Mysore	Nanjunda,	---
44	The Issue of Farmers Suicides in Karnataka	In Swathi and Nanjunda(Edts) Multidisciplinary Handbook of Social	Aayu Publications, New delhi	Nanjunda	---

		Exclusion And Human Rights			
45	The Language Barrier And Education of Tribal Children: Some Issues	In Sucismitha and Nanjunda (Edts) Tribal's and Inclusive Growth in Between Culture and Development	Aayu Publications, New Delhi	Nanjunda	----
46	Decentralization and Health Care Policy Reform in India Focusing NRHM	In Dr.Swathi (Edt) Inclusive Development and Sustainability	Bharathi Publications, Newdelhi	Nanjunda	---
47	Public -Private And People Partnership Initiatives in Skill Development: A CSR Prospective	In Dinesha (Edt) skill India and development: emerging debates ,	NCIGDR Publications, Mysore	Nanjunda	--
48	Women Resource Centre; A Key Step For Empowering Through Skill Development	In Dinesha (Edt) Rethinking Skill Development and Women Empowerment,	NCIGDR Publications, Mysore	Nanjunda	Srikanth
49	Agri tourism and Inclusive growth : A Case of Coorg Dist Karnataka	In Chandrashekar and Manu (Edt) Agribusiness and Rural Management-Towards Sustainable Development (accepted)	ROAD Trust, Mysore	Nanjunda	--
51	Integrating Youth Into the Main Stream: Some Inclusionary Prospective [	In Divya (Edt) Youth Development : Dynamics and Discourses	Deeksha Publications Mysore	Nanjunda	--
52	Role of youths in Nation building	In Divya and others (Edt) Social Development and Youth	Deeksha publications Mysore	Nanjunda	--
53	Inclusive Health Care and Maternal Benefit Programmes	In Nanjunda and M.Arwin (Edt)	Aayu Publications, Mysore	Nanjunda	
54	Urban cooperatives for Social inclusion : Some thoughts	In Dinesha (Edt) Urban Poverty and Social Exclusion	Spring leaf Publications, Mysore	Nanjunda	---

55	A bird view on the health status and health infrastructure in Mysore districts India	In Dinesha and R. Murthy (Edts) Rediscovery of Inclusive growth	ROAD Trust Pub, Mysore	Nanjunda	
56	Impact of National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) on Health Status in Karnataka-South India	in Dr. Naveetha (Edts) Emerging Developmental Issues: A Debate	Aayu Publications, New Delhi	Nanjunda	
57	Fake or Faith? A Study on Traditional Faith Healers in Rural South Karnataka	In Nanjunda (Edts) in Emerging Public Health Issues in India.	Aayu Publications, New Delhi	Nanjunda	
58	Education and Globalization	In Dr. Ramesha and Bhvya (Edt) Contemporary Social Thoughts		Nanjunda	
59	The lonely society? Mental health of Indian elderly living single in apartments	In Lancy D'souza (Edt) Emerging Trends in Clinical Psychiatry	Upcoming	Nanjunda	---
60	Some retrospection on birth rate by residence in India	In Smitha and Nanjunda (Edt) in Contemporary Public health Scenario in India	Aayu Publications, New Delhi	Nanjunda	
61	Socio-economic Conditions of Women Workers in Match industry: An examinations	In divya			
62	Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) : Between The Market and the Search for A Sustainable Growth and Development,	Infrastructure and sustainable development issues and challenges in Mahadevaiah and others (Etdt)	SPRING LEAF		

19.DETAILS ABOUT RESEARCH PROJECTS UNDERTAKEN

B. Sponsored Research Projects

	Title of The Project	Position	Level	Name of the agency	Outlay (Rs. in lakhs)	Status
1	Situation Analysis of Protection Issues Relating to Children In Mysore District-India And District Protection Action Plan	Principal Investigator	District	UNISEF And Women And Child Development, Govt. Of Karnataka	3,58,000/-	Completed
2	A Baseline Assessment Of Extent Of Unemployment In Three Border Districts (Rural) Of Karnataka State, India	Principal Investigator	State	UGC (Minor Project)	1,35,000/-	Completed
3	Extending Financial Assistance To SC/ST Nursing Students Studying In Schools/Colleges Other Than Government Schools/Colleges – An Evaluation Study	Joint Principal Investigator	State	Dept Of Social Welfare, Govt. Of Karnataka	5,55,000/-	Completed
4	Moving From Philanthropy To Inclusive Growth: An Empirical Investigation Of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Practices In Selected Companies In India.	Project Director	National	Indian Council of Social Science Research	5,00,000/	Completed
5	An Evaluation Study On Janani Suraksha Yojna (JSY) Assisted Under NRHM Programme In Karnataka, Tamilnadu And Andra Pradesh States of South India	Principal Investigator	South India	Indian Council of Medical Research- (ICMR)	19,68,669	Completed
6	A Benchmark Assessment of Capacities of Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRI) to Administer The Grass Root Health System In Karnataka State	Principal Investigator	State	Indian Council Of Medical Research- ICMR	13,45,273	Completed
7	Voice for the Voiceless?: An Empirical Examination of Role of Community Radios in Social Inclusion Process Juvenile Justice System: An	Principal Investigator	State	UPE-II Project ,Mysore University	1,00,000	Completed

8	Juvenile Justice System (Protection and Care) 2016: Measure to Improve (In 10 Indian states)	Project Director	National	Bureau of Police Research and Development (Ministry of Home Affairs, Govt. of India).	19,0000	Approved
9	Situating Social Justice In The Indian Political Process: Karnataka 1880-1947	Principal Investigator	National	Indian Council of Historical Research (Under Study cum Contingency grants)	45,000	Completed
10	An Evaluation Study of Administration and Functioning of One Stop Centers (OSC) in Karnataka Tamil nadu and Andra Pradesh states of South India	Project Director	National	National Commission for Women (Govt. of India)	4,97,000	Running

H. Research Projects' as a Co-investigator

	Title Of The Project	Position	Level	Funder	Status
1	Missing Girls And Women: Issues And Concern	Co investigator	District	Karnataka State Commission Women	Completed
2	Effectiveness of Ayurveda & Allopathic Medicine On Iron Deficiency Anemia In Children Of Hassan District, Karnataka	Co investigator	State Level	Dept of Ayuesh /Govt Of Karnataka	Project Windup Abruptly
3	A Benchmark Assessment of Dalith Muslims In Karnataka	Co investigator	State Level	UGC	Completed

D. Collaborative Research Projects

	Title of The Project	Position	Collaboration	Funder	Outlay(Rs. in lakhs)	Status
1	Household Catastrophic Health Care Expenditure In Two Backward Districts of Karnataka	Project Director (Hon.)	National centre for inclusive growth and development Trust@, Mysore	Indian Academe Research Association	Rs.50,000	Completed

2	An Evaluation of The Impact Of Human Resource Interventions On Motivation And Retention Of Health Care Workers In Remote And Rural Areas	Joint PI	National centre for inclusive growth and development Trust®, Mysore	Indian Academe Research Association	Rs. 50.000	Completed
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E. Fellowships Related Research Projects/Study (Awarded/ Completed)

	Title	Position	Funder	Status
1	Medical Pluralism and Health Seeking Behaviour Of Jenu Kuruba And Koraga Tribal Groups Of Karnataka : A Medico Anthropological Study	Research Associate (Post Doc)	ICMR	Completed
2	A Study on China Policies to Promote The Social Inclusion of Aged And Disabled Groups And Lessons For India	Visiting Fellow (to visit China)	ICSSR	could not accept due to the technical reason from the China end
3	Health And Inclusive Development: An Investigative Study On The Impact Of NGOs Interventions On Tribal Health In Karnataka State	National Senior Fellowship	ICSSR	Not accepted because University refused to sanction lien
4	An Evaluation Study On Bala Sanjeevini (Child Health Programme) In Vijayapaua Dist of Karnataka	Research Fellowship (For Six Months)	Karnataka Child Development Academy (Govt. Of Karnataka)	Completed (Rs.50,000/-)
5	To visit Jharkhand state to write a travelogue	Travel Fellowship	Karnataka Literature Academy (Govt. Of Karnataka)	Completed

C. University of Potential of Excellence (UPE) Project, Mysore University (funded by MHRD/UGC)

Title	Position	Level	Funder	Amount	Status
1. Media And Social Development: A Case Study Of Karnataka'	Core Member	State	UGC/MHRD	5 CRORES	Completed

Training Fellowship awarded

	Category	Host Institute	Funding agency *
1	Short term Training Fellowship	National Centre for Disease Informatics and Management	Dept of Health Research (Govt. of India)

could not avail because of no lean

F. Travel grants Received

	Title	Position	Funder	Outlay(Rs. in lakhs)
1	To visit Jharkhand state to write a travelogue	Travel Fellowship	Karnataka Literature Academy (Govt. of Karnataka)	50,000
2	To visit Sri lanka for a seminar presentation	Under Consideration	UPE-II Project , Mysore University	60,000*

* could not visit

G. Fellowship/grants applications submitted/under consideration*

	Project Title	Category	Funding agency *
1	Representation of CASTE issue in Kuvempus'(national poet) short stores	Short term research Fellowship	Betageri Krishnasharma Trust, Belagavi Karnataka

20. Grants Received to Conduct National Seminars

	Title Of The Seminar	Position	Level	Sponsored Agency	Amount(In Rs)
1	Ethno- Historical Development of De-Notified Tribes: Issues And Prospects (Dec 15 th -16 th 2010)	Organizing Secretary	National Level	Indian Council of Historical Research, New Delhi	40,000
2	Multilevel Interventions For Health Care: Framing New Inclusive Health Policies	Organizing Secretary	National Level	ICMR New Delhi	30,000/
3	Regional Imbalance, Banking Industry And Inclusive Growth In India: A Focus on 12 th	Organizing Secretary	State Level	NABARD Bank ,Bangalore	75,000

	Five Year Plan,				
4	Social Exclusion And Inclusion In India: Self Governance, Development Politics And Autonomy Movement	Organizing Secretary	National Level	ICSSR (Hyderabad)	25,000
5	Denotified, Nomadic and Semi nomadic Tribal groups in India: Contemporary Scenario	Organizing Secretary	National Level	Anthropological Survey of India	75,000
6	Globalization And Its Impact on Tribal Culture	----	-----	Indira Gandhi Rashtriya Manav Sangrahalaya, Bhopal	25,000*
7	Inter religious and Inter Cultural Dialogue on Human rights and Peace	Organizing Secretary	State (In collaboration)	KAICIID, Vienna, Austria (an intentional NGO)	40,000
8	Social Media for Digital and Social Inclusion: Cultural, Technological and Economic Implications	Organizing Secretary	National Level	UPE-II	75,000
9	Corporate Social Responsibility and Tribal Development	Organizing Secretary (NGO collaboration)	National Level	Anthropological Survey of India	75,000
10	Make in India and Digital India: Empowerment and Transformation for Inclusive growth	Organizing Secretary	National Level	ICSSR New Delhi	150000

***Grants received: seminar could not conducted**

21.Grants Received to conduct International Seminar

	Title	Position	Level	Sponsored Agency	Amount
1	Ethnicity, Discrimination And Social Exclusion Of Minorities And Margins: Post Colonial Debates	Organizing Secretary	International	ICSSR	2,00,000

22.Grants Received to Conduct National Workshops

	Title	Position	Level	Sponsored Agency	Amount (In Rs)
1	New Public Health Issues In India	Coordinator	National Level	National Academy for Medical Sciences - New Delhi	75,000
2	Developments In Statistical Methods or Data Analysis Of Excluded Groups	Coordinator	National Level	Ministry Of Statistics And Programme Implementation	1,51,000
3	New Human Development Index For Tribal Healthcare	Coordinator	National Level	ICMR ,New Delhi	40,000
4	Primitive Tribal's in Transition An Ethno Historical Re look	Coordinator	National Level	ICHR ,New Delhi	1,00,000
5	Health and Gender Disparity	Coordinator	National Level	Medial Council of India	50,000*
6	Universal health coverage	Coordinator	National Level	National Academy for Medical Sciences - New Delhi	
7	Interdisciplinary Research Methodology In Social Sciences				

*Could not conduct

23.Grant Received for Training Programmes

	Title	Level	Sponsored Agency	Amount(in Rs.)
1	Human Rights And Social Exclusion	State	NHRC	50,000
2	Advanced Research Methodology In Social Sciences	National	ICSSR	5,40,000
3	Research Methodology for SC/ST research Scholars in Social Sciences	Regional	ICSSR,Hyderabad	75,000/-

24. Joint Organizing Secretary of the Seminars /workshop

	Title	Position	Level
1	Inclusive Higher Education and Marginalized Sections : Dynamics and Discourses	Joint Organizing Secretary	National Level
2	Social Exclusion And Reservation Policy In India : A New Debate	Joint Organizing Secretary	National Level
3	Agricultural Communication for Formers	Member(committee)	State level

25. Publications Assistants /Grants Received*

	Title of the Book/manuscript/Monograph	Funder	Amount in Rs.
1	Rural Unemployment issues in Karnataka: A Study	UGC- UPE II Project- Mysore University	Rs.72,000/-
2	Impact of Janani Suraksha Yojana on Maternal Health Care in South India	UGC 12th Plan Publication grant (University of Mysore_	Rs.50,000/

***All grants released directly to the publisher**

Grants Received to conduct Awareness Programme (Joint Applicant)

1	Title	Funder	Amount
1	Building Models on Biodiversity Conservation	Karnataka State Council for Science, Bangalore	Rs. 6700*

* Programme did not conducted

26.Convener for the Following Seminars

	Topic	Position	Level	Sponsored Agency
1	Reservation and Inclusive Growth	Coordinator	State	University Of Mysore
2	Women And Work: Policies Towards Economic Inclusion (Conducted By Centre For Women's Study) (21 st And 22 nd March 2011)	Coordinator	National	(CSSEIP And Centre For Women's Studies
3	Dr. B. R. Ambedkar's Vision On Social Exclusion And Inclusion (27 th March 2011).	Coordinator	State	University of Mysore, Mysore
4	Missing Girls And Women: Issues And Implications	Coordinator	State	State Commission For Women

27.Joint Director /Co-ordinator of the Seminars

.	Topic	Funder	Position	Level
1	Inclusive Development Of Marginalized Groups In Contemporary India: Issues And Challenges	ICSSR	Joint Director	National

2	Financial Inclusion India: Issues And Prospects	ICSSR	Co-ordinator	National
3	Inclusive Agricultural Growth In India: Issues And Challenge	ICSSR	Co-ordinator	National
4	Rural Development And Inclusive Growth: New Debates	ICSSR	Co-ordinator	National
5	Social protection schemes and Inclusive growth	ICSSR	Co-ordinator	National
6	Empowering women through skill development: challenges and opportunities.	ICSSR	Co-ordinator	National
7	Dynamics of Poverty, Inequality and Exclusion in Urban India.	ICSSR	Joint Organizing Secretary	National
8	40 th Indian Social Science Congress	-----	Executive committee member	National
9	Constitution-Democracy and Equality: Karnataka A Role Module	Govt. of Karnataka on Account of Dasara State fest)	Organizing Committee Member	National
10	Emerging Rural Health issues in India	ICMR	Co-ordinator	National
11	Food Security in India	ICSSR	Co-ordinator	National

Other Small Grants

	Particulars	Year	Sponsored Agency
1	Field work grants:	2011	Rural Organization from Appropriate Development Trust @Mysore
2	Library fellowship:	2012	NCIGDR Trust
3	Pilot study grants	2014	Karnataka Kidney health Foundation
4	Institutional grants	2015	Anthropology Observatory
5	Paper writing grants:	2016	Rural Organization from Appropriate Development Trust @Mysore
6	Book writing grants		IARA Tirchy

12. SELF AUTHORED BOOKS

1. **Nanjunda**, Child Labor and Anthropology , Mittal Publications, New Delhi 2009
3. **Nanjunda**, Rural Unemployment Issues in Karnataka (Published by UPE II- Mysore University, Mysore)
4. **Nanjunda**, Corporate Social Responsibility and Inclusive growth, Aayu Publications, New Delhi
5. **Nanjunda**, Impact of JSY on Maternal Health Care in South India (Published by Indian Academic Researchers Association, Tamil nadu)
6. **Nanjunda**, Panchyathi raj System and Public Health: Aayu Publications, New Delhi
7. **Nanjunda**, Changing Health Culture and Medical Pluralism in Rural India, Aayu Publications, New Delhi
8. Nanjunda Urban and Rural Public Health; An Introduction
9. **Nanjunda**, Medical Care for Malnourished Children: Role of Bal Sanjeevani Scheme (**In Kannada**)
10. **Nanjunda**, Politics, Higher Education and Development Politics: Contemporary Debates (**In Kannada language**)

11. BOOK PUBLICATIONS: (EDITED VOLUMES)

1. Rethinking Indigenous Knowledge: New Deal for Rural India (**Edited**) D C Nanjunda, RBSA Publishers, Rajasthan (**2008**)
2. Contemporary Anthropology (**Editor**) D C Nanjunda, Discovery Publisher, New Delhi (2009)
3. Social Anthropology in India : An Ethnography of Policy and Practice, (in 3 Volumes) (**Editor**) D C Nanjunda, Discovery Publisher, New Delhi (2009)
4. India Development: Issues and Prospects , (**Editor**) D C Nanjunda, Anmol Publisher, New Delhi,(2010)
5. Multidisciplinary Handbook of Social Exclusion and Human Rights (**Editors:** Swathi Chakrabrothy and Nanjunda), Aayu Publications, New Delhi 2015
6. Towards inclusive growth :Between Equity and Development (Edited: Nanjunda and Mak Arvin (Canada) Aayu Publications, 2016
7. Culture, Cognition and Schooling: A Reassessment, (**Editors** :B.R Ghosh, Nanjunda and others) Discovery Publication, New Delhi (2011)
8. Emerging Public Health issues in India, (**Editor:** Nanjunda) Aayu Publications, New Delhi 2016
9. Tribal Social Inclusion: Between Culture and Development (**Editors:** Suchismitha Mishra and Nanjunda), Aayu Publications, New delhi ,2016
10. The New Public Health Paradigms, (**Editors:** Nanjunda and Smitha), Aayu Publications, New delhi ,2017
11. Emerging Issues in Development Anthropology, (**Editors:** Nanjunda and Shukla Skidher), Aayu Publications, New delhi ,2017 -
12. Ignored claim: Gender and Inclusive development, (**Editors:** Divya and Nanjunda), Aayu Publications, New delhi -
- 13: Tribal Development: Issues and Challenges (in Kannada language) (**Editors:** Nanjunda)

14. A short book on urban public health, United Publisher, Mangalore(Karnataka)
(Editors: Nanjunda and Dinesha) UNDER PRESS

OTHER BOOKS

1. **Nanjunda**, 'Unique Jharkhand' (Travelogue on Jharkhand State-India, Published by Karnataka Literature Academy (Govt of Karnataka) , Bangalore
2. Translated a book When breath becomes air (Random house, USA) in to Kannada

13.Reference Work Brought

Sl.No	Titles	ISBN	Publisher
1	Annotated Bibliography on 'Developmental Issues In India'	978-81-923619-2-5	Spring Leaf Publications
2	Bibliography on 'Child Labour' (Joint Work)	978-81-923619-0-1	Spring Leaf Publications
4	Bibliography on 'Health Dynamics In Rural Context'	-----	Spring Leaf Publications

Other Article of Interest

1. Nanjunda, (2006) Panchayath and Rural Labour, *Third Concept*, No. (ISBN1470-482x)
2. Nanjunda (2009), NGOs And Education Of Tribal Children, *Third Concept*, 22(3)
(ISBN 1470-482x)
3. Nanjunda and Annapurna (2010) Perception And Curative Measure; A Case Study Of Koraga Tribe of Karnataka India, *Vanya jathi* 58(1) (ISBN 0975-0647)
4. Nanjunda Venu Gopal(2011) Use Of Various Bio-Fencing Plants to Cure Human Diseases by the Yarava Ethic Group Of Coorg District Karnataka *AfroJournal Of anthropology And Social Policy* , 2(1) (January-June)(ISBN 2229-4414)
5. Nanjunda,(2015) Eco Tourisem As A Long-Run Economic Growth Factor For Tribes; Some Empirical Evidences, *Vanya jathi*,Vol.63 No 1 (ISBN 0975-7307)
6. Nanjunda, (2010) Ethno- Medical Plant Record Of Soliga Ethic Group of Karnataka, *Vanya jathi*, Vol.LVIII,july (ISBN 0975-7307)
7. Nanjunda(2009) Economic Reforms Of Karnataka Natives; Evidences Form Human Development Report, *Vanya jathi*, 3(3) (ISBN 0975-7307)
8. Nanjunda (2014), Social Inclusion of Small and Marginal Formers, *Kissan World* 42(5)May
9. Nanjunda Education Status of perimitive Tribes Groups of Karnataka, *Edu research*, 6(2) Oct 2015 (ISSN:0976-1160)
10. Nanjunda (2015) A Medico-Sociological Review on Health Behaviour and Therapies among Rural people, e-journal of JSS College Of Nursing, July-Sept(Vol.11) ISSN; 0277-1830 -

11. Nanjunda (2017) Ignored Claims; Prolific Investigation on Trafficked Women (rescued) in Mysore city-India, *Pearls-Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 2(1) (ISSN;2229-4414)
12. Nanjunda (2015) The Plight of Tribal Migrants; A case of Mysore Dist, *Al, shodhana* 3(2) ISSN:2320-6292
13. Nanjunda (2014) A bench mark assessment of yearava tribes in Karnataka *Tui journal of tribal Studies* ,28(2) (ISSN 2319-7382)
14. Nanjunda (2014) Corporate social responsibility (csr) and social inclusion : a number of indistinct Pictures ? *Aarhat multidisciplinary education research journal* 3(5) (ISSN :2278-5655).
15. Nanjunda and D.Nayaka (2015) Corporate social responsibility (csr): a case study of adithya birla group, *Samzodhana* 2(1) (ISSN :2347-4270)
16. Nanjunda (2013) Evaluating the influence of culturally specific and standard risk factors on the changing health behavior: the case of kadu kurubha tribe of Karnataka , *journal of tribal research and cultural institute (govt.Tripura)* 36(2).
17. Sunitha ganiger and Nanjunda(2015) managerial challenges and critical analysis of india “s most ambitious technological project Aadhar :EPR international journal of economics ,business and management studies ,1(1) (ISSN ;2347-4378).
18. Nanjunda(2016). A quick look on new companies act 2013 act, focusing Corporate social responsibility *journal of management and research* ,Sankalpa *journal of management research*, 6(2),ISSN ;2231-1904
19. Nanjunda (2016) Corporate Social Responsibility Social inclusion: Few Thoughts, *KAIM Journal Of Management and Research*, (ISSN;0974-9462)
20. Nanjunda(2017). An analysis on Health Infrastructure in Mysore District-Karnataka *BODHI International Journal of Research in Humanities Arts and Sciences* 2(1) (ISSN; 2310-7382)
21. Nanjunda(2017). Prevalence of health Problems Among the Tribal people; A case of Betta Kuruba Tribe of Karnataka, *Tui Journal on Tribal Life and culture* (Govt. of Tripura) Vol. 20(2) ISSN; 2310-7382
22. Nanjunda (2012) Poverty, Inclusive Growth And Regional Disparities in in Northern Karnataka; Where Rubber Hits The Road? *Radix International Journal Of Social Sciences*, 1(8) (ISSN;2250-3994)
23. Nanjunda (2013)Revisiting Constitutional Measures For Child Labors, *Legal Opus* 8(2) ISSN;0978-9381
24. Nanjunda (2014)Voluntary Action And Alternative Development Of Tribes; Contemporary Debates, *Tui Journal on Tribal Life and culture* 18(1) (ISSN; 2319-7382)
25. Nanjunda(2015) Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)and Inclusive Development Of Tribes; Myth or Reality? *JSS Journal Studies And Research* (online),31(2). (ISSN; 2321-4171)
26. Dinesh and Nanjunda (2012), Structuring Socio-Capital through Micro finance tool for reducing urban poverty, *AJRBEM Journal* 2(10) (ISSN;2249-7307)

27. Nanjunda(2016)Appraisal of Janani Suraksha Yojana (JSY) in Bidar Districts (Karnataka): Knowledge, Attitude and Utilization pattern of Beneficiaries PEARL Multidisciplinary Journal 2(1) Feb 2016 pp 23-35,(ISSN:2394-0352).
28. Nanjunda(2012). Forging New Grounds for Ecotourism And Financial Inclusion: A Case Study of Coorg Dist Of South Karnataka, Man And Life, Vol.38 No 3-4 July-Dec 2012 pp. 59-67-
29. Nanjunda(2015). Community Perception About Risk Associated With The Child Occupations: A Case Of Bangalore City-India-Al-Shodhana, 3(1) ,(ISSN:2320-6292)
30. Nanjunda (2014). Community Perception About Risk Associated With The Child Occupations: A Case Of Bangalore City-India (Journal of Management Research)3(1)
31. Nanjunda (2014) Changing Medical And Related Ritual Practices: Health Status of Elderly Population Of Jenukuruba Tribe Of South Karnataka, India Tui Journal Of Tribal Studies, Vol.17 No.2. Oct-13-March 2014, ISSN:2319-7382
32. Nanjunda (2015) Tracing Historical Development of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Practices In In India: Retrospection And Future Action, *Sugyam Journal Of Siva Sivani Institute Management*, 7(2) (ISSN; 0975-4032)
33. Nanjunda(2014) Retrospection On Corporate Social Responsibility: A Review Of Shifting Focus And Parasigms, *Shrinathji Journal Of Business And Research* 5(1) Jan-June 2014, ISSN: 0975-7996
34. Nanjunda and Venugopal(2018) Awareness, Perception and Practice Of Stakeholders about National Rural Health Mission (NRHM)- A Case Of Karnataka, *journal of Social and Economic Research*, (8) 1

14.Seminar Presentations

1. A Survey of functioning of Ashram Schools In Karnataka, Paper Presented in the National Conference Of Tribal Societies In Transitions, organized by Kannada University, Hampi held on Nov. 14th And 15th 2008
2. Tribal's Health In Karnataka Presented in the Seminar Population Health And Generic Diversity: Perspectives And Issues organized by Department of Anthropology SV University, Tirupathi held on 25-26 March 2009
3. Inclusive policy and tribal development in the national seminar on *culture of social exclusion, identities and inclusive policy: Dalits, minorities and tribal, India/Karnataka* conducted by CSSEIP, held on 11th and 12th march 2009
4. Role of NGO's in Rural Development – A Review at the National conference *Triology of Non-governmental Organization, Community Engagement and Development ethos* organized by Institute of Development Studies at University of Mysore, Mysore held on 12th and 13th December 2008.
5. Social Workers and Rural Health in the National Seminar *HR Paradigms in the 21st Century: A Social Work Perspective*, Organized by P G Department Of Social Work. JSS College Of Arts, Commerce And Science,Mysore held on 27-29 Oct 2010

6. Ignored claims of DNTS : How and why? Ethno- Historical Development Of De-Notified Tribes: Issues And Prospects conducted by CSSEIP Mysore Universty held on Dec 15th -16th 2010
7. Regional Imbalance in the Growth Of Self Help Groups: Problems And Suggestions in The State level Conference **Regional Imbalance, Banking Industry And Inclusive Growth In Karnataka/India: A Focus On 12th Five Year Plan** held At UGC-CSSEIP, Mysore University held on December 15th And 16th 2011.
8. Social movement and social inclusion in the national seminar *Social Exclusion and Inclusion in India: Self Governance, Development Politics And Autonomy Movement* conducted by CSSEIP, Mysore University held on 22nd and 23rd August 2012.
9. Women development and economic inclusion in the National Seminar on *Women and Work: Policies Towards Economic Inclusion* Conducted By the Centre For Women's Study, Mysore University held on 21st And 22nd March 2011(**Joint paper**)
10. Tribal health and inclusive growth in the national seminar *Multilevel Interventions For Health Care: Framing New Inclusive Health Policies* organized by CSSEIP, Mysore University held on 8th and 9th September 2011
11. Three sociological perspectives of human trafficking in the National Seminar *Missing Girls And Women: Issues And Implications* organized by CSSEIP Mysore University held on 23 and 24 2012
12. Empowering small and marginal farmers for inclusive agriculture growth In The National Seminar *Inclusive Agriculture Growth In India: Issues And Challenges* organized by UGC-CSSEIP, Mysore University held on Jan 30 -31st 2013
13. Social Exclusion Among Muslim Beedi Workers , in the National Seminar *Social Inclusion – Challenges And Strategies* Crosland College, Udupi District (**In Absentia-22nd Feb2013**)
14. Regional Imbalance in the Growth of Self Help Groups Problem And Suggestions In The national Seminar *Financial Inclusion In India: Issues And Challenges* organized by UGC-CSSEIP, Mysore University held on 15-16th Dec 2011.
15. Financial inclusion and micro finance: A micro perspective in the national seminar in the national seminar *Financial inclusion in India: issues and challenges* organized by CSSEIP on 9th and 10 October 2012
16. Nanjunda and Naveen, Socio-Cultural Dimensons Of Tribal Health: Case Of Elderly Population of Kadu Kuruba Tribe Of Karnataka In The National Seminar *Health And Disease: Exploring Genomics And Cultural Globalization In 21st Century* , Department Of Anthropology SV University, Tirupathi. 26th And 27th June 2013 (**Joint Presentation**)
17. Inclusive Higher Education: From Half- Baked Public to Half-Baked Privatesem in the National Seminar *Inclusive Higher Education And: Dynamics And Discourse*, Conducted by CSSEIP, Mysore University held on Aug 1st And 2nd 2013.

18. New approaches for including disadvantaged section in social research in national conference *Inclusive development of marginalized groups in contemporary India: Issues and challenges* organized by CSSEIP, Mysore university on 27th and 28th September 2013
19. Corporate Social Responsibility Initiatives Of Non Nifty Companies: Some Ground Realities in the National Seminar *Ethics, Corporate Governance And CSR- The Changing Landscape* Conducted National Seminar By MS Ramaiah College Of Arts, Science And Commerce held on 22nd March 2014
20. Conceptual issues in measurement of rural migration in India in national conference on *Rural development and Inclusive growth: New Debates* organized by CSSEIP on 21st and 22nd August 2014
21. Decentralization And Decision Space: Panchayats Raj Institutions And Grass Root Health System in the National Seminar *Gandhian Concept Of Ideal Villages And Its Contemporary Relevance* Organized By Dept Of Gandhian Study, University of Mysore held on 28th 29 March 2014**(Joint paper)**
22. Corporate Social Investment For Inclusive Development Of India: Implicit Or Explicit? In The National Seminar *Business Sustainably Through Social Value Addition* Organized By St. Aloysius College(Autonomous), Mangalore held on 7th April 2014
23. The Public Value And Public Interest In Promoting Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) And Human Rights in the *National Seminar Recent Trends In Indian Politics* Organized By Indian Academy Degree College, Bangalore held on April 30-2014
24. Public Health Problems And Climate Change: A Contingent Analysis In The Seminar *Population, Environment And Sustainable Development – Issues And Challenges* Conducted By R.P.D. College, Tilakwadi, Belgaum – Karnataka on Sept 13 /2014 . **(Joint paper)**
25. Rural Development And Decentralization: New Equations And Challenges In the 10th Kannada Science Congress held on Sept 15-17th 2014
26. Rural empowerment and food security act: promise and perils in the National seminar *Rural empowerment India through initiatives and innovations in agricultural* sectors conducted by Taitham institute of Management Coimbatour Jan on 23 and 24 2015
27. Role of Youth Organizations in Social Inclusion Process of Minority Youth, in the National Seminar *Banking upon Youths*, conducted by St. Philomena P.G. College, , Puttur, Dakshina Kaanada Dist-On 3rd February 2015
28. Breaking the Barriers?: Inclusive Development Of Rural Women Through ICT, In The National Seminar '*Sustainable Rural Development Challenges and Opportunities in India*' conducted by Rani Channamma University, Belagavi held on 27th and 28th Feb 2015
29. Nanjunda and Ramesh, Governance and Representation: A Study on Social Exclusion Of Dalith Woman In Local Self Government In the national seminar on *Social Exclusion of Daltih Women in 21st Century* conducted by CSSEIP Gandhigram Rural University Tamil nadu on 12th and 13th March 2015 **(Joint paper)**

30. Financial Inclusion: and Nationalized Bank: Subject And Scenario in the National Seminar *Financial Inclusion A Policy Perspective for an Egalitarian Society* in the national seminar Conducted By JSS College for Women, Chamraja nagar-Karnataka on 27th March 2014
31. CKD-A public health problem in India in national workshop on *New public health issues in India* organized by CSSEIP, Mysore University on 27th and 28th December 2014
32. Dalith Women in Panchayath in the State Level Seminar *Gandhian Concept of Decentralization and Model Village* Conducted By Dept. Of Gandhian Study, University Of Mysore on 18th July 2015
33. Rural migration and exclusion in India Some prospective in the State level seminar on *contemporary issues in empowerment of weaker section* held on 6th Oct 2015
34. An Gandhian concept of inclusive growth in the State level conference *Gandhiji and world peace* organized by Gandhian study centre, University of Mysore, Mysore on 22nd September 2015 **(Joint paper)**
35. Health schemes for the Weaker Sections: A Case Of Caste Discrimination Among Janani Suraksha Yojana Beneficiaries in state level seminar *contemporary issues in empowerment of weaker sections* held on 6th oct 2015 Bharathi college and KSOU university Mysore
36. Empowering Excluded People and Driving Change, in the National seminar on *Social Innovation and change making : A way forward* conducted by St. Philomena P.G. Dakshina Kaanada Dist-held on 3rd and 4th December 2015
37. Rural empowerment and food securing act: The promise and perils in national seminar on *Rural empowerment in India through initiatives and innovations in Agriculture sector* organized by Rathinam Institute of Management, TamilNadu on 23rd and 24th January 2015 **(Joint paper)**
38. Skills development and poverty reduction: contemporary reviews in the National Seminar on *Role of higher Educational institutions in reinventing skills for global competency* conducted by Kristu Jayanti college, Bangalore held on 21st and 22nd January 2016
39. Women and Health Care Issue: Some untold Insights from Janani Suraksha Yojana (JSY) Scheme In National Seminar *Strategic Issues And Challenges In Health Economics: An Economic Perspective* Organized by Maharani Women's Arts And Commerce College, Bangalore held on 5th April 2016.
40. Role of Panchayath Raj: A Key System for Improving Child Health In National Seminar *Strategic Issues And Challenges In Health Economics: An Economic Perspective* Organized by Maharani Women's Arts And Commerce College Bangalore held on 5th April 2016.
41. Panchayatiraj participation in access to health service among differently abled women in the national seminar on *Constraints faced by differently bled women in their access to services and education in India* organized by Holycross Institute of Management and Technology, Kozhikode on 10th June 2016. **(Joint paper)**

42. Women resource centre: A key step for empowering women through skill development in the National seminar on *empowering women through skill development: Challenges and opportunities* conducted by CSSEIP, Mysore University held on 1st and 2nd July 2016.
43. Panchayath and health problems of young people; A key concern in the National seminar *Suitable development for revitalizing India –Prospects and Challenges for the Youth* conducted by Jyoti nivas College, Bangalore August 9th and 10th 2016
44. Community radio: A Key to propel Health education in the National seminar *Literature, Media and Politics* conducted by Marymatha Arts and Science College, Mananthavady –Kerala(6th and 7th Feb 2017) **(Joint paper)**
45. Financing Panchayath Raj Institutions for Inclusive Health Care in *Panchayath Raj Institutions and Politics* conducted by PES college Mandya (Feb 2017)

15. International Seminars (Conducted in India)

1. Nanjunda, Mainstream Inclusion of Minorities in India in the international seminar titled *'Discrimination and Social Exclusion of Minorities and Margins: Post Colonial Debates'* conducted by CSSEIP Mysore University on Dec 18th 19th Dec 2014 **(Joint presentation)**
2. Nanjunda, Social Work Practices and Health Care Management: A Case Of Janani Sureksha Yojana (Scheme for Institutional Delivery) in the international seminar titled *'Bridging the gap between the theory and practice of social work'* conducted by P G Research Department Of Social Work, Sree Narayana Guru College, Coimbatore, T.N on Aug 14th 2015
3. Nanjunda, *Impact of Human Resources Management On Healthcare Quality : Some Issues In the seminar titled 'The Global HRM Strategies For Sustainable Development'*, conducted by PKR Arts, college for women, (Gobichettipalayam), Tamil nadu on 15th Sept 2015
4. Nanjunda, Total Quality Management of Health Care System in India : In seminar *Competency building strategies in business and technology for sustainable development* 19th Feb, 2015 organized by Sri Ganesh School of Business Management, Salem, Tamilnadu, India **(Joint presentation)**
5. Nanjunda, *Social Inclusion – A Way to Integrate Differently Challenged Youth In Democracy?* In the Seminar *Youth Led Sustainable Development: Opportunities And Challenges* conducted by P.G and research department of Social work, Sacred heart collage (P.G), Tirupattur, Tamil nadu on 19th Jan 2016 **(Joint presentation)**
6. Nanjunda, Changing relation between community development and social work: Some thoughts in the National Seminar *social work contribution to sustainable development* conducted by Loyola college Chennai held on 12th and 13th Feb 2016
7. Change and Mobility in Contemporary India : Re thinking M N Srinivas, conducted by ISEC Bangalore Aug 29th and 30th 2017 **(Attended)**

18.(a) Session Chair (Seminar)

- 1.Finnaicla Inclusion India (national seminar) on March 22nd and 23rd 2014
- 2.Skill development and women empowerment(national seminar) on 12 and 13th 2017
January
3. Rural health issues Jan 10th and 11th (CSSEIP, UOM)
- 4 Indian constitution (Dept of Law , UOM)

28.A.Provided Accredited Academic Support for Ph.D/Post Doctoral Studies

1. Socio Economic Survey of Handigodu Syndrome Affected Population of Shimoga District of Karnataka –August,2008 (Mr.Venugopal P N , Anthropological Survey Of India-Mysore)
2. Human Trafficking In Mysore City, India: An Anthropological Study (Dr.Mahadeviah V N, UGC-PDF , Dept of Anthropology, University Of Mysore, India) –**Post Doctoral Study**
3. Role of Non-Governmental Organizations in the Prevention and Rehabilitation Of Juvenile Delinquency in Bangalore City: An Anthropological Study (Mr. Krishnappa Research Student, Dept of Anthropology, University of Mysore)
- 4.Changing Cleanliness Practices: An Intercultural Perspective, (Ms. Jack Tullia, Dept of Sociology, Lund University, **Sweden**)
5. Assisted in writing a chapter in ‘Mysore Districts Human Development Report’ - 2015

29.Invited Lecturing

- 1 Culture and Conservation of Water, Chinathana Foundation –Periyapatna, Mysore
- 2.Basics In Proposal And Technical Paper Writing In The Research Methodology Workshop Held at KSOU University -Mysore (5th May 2013)
- 3 Qualitative Research Design in the National Research Methodology Workshop Conducted By the Department Of Commerce, Mysore University (Jan 20st And 30th 2014)
- 4.E-Resources and the Funding Agencies for Research in Social Sciences in the National Research Methodology Workshop Conducted by the Department Of Economics Mysore University (Mandya PG Centre) (March 24th 2014)
5. Data sources and the Funding Agencies in Orientation Course in the topic Research Methodology workshop for college teachers conducted by the Academic Staff College, Mysore University (Jan 23rd 2017)
6. Preparing for Karnataka Administrative Service Examination (general studies),
7. Right to food in Karnataka and Poverty in Dasara State Fest in Mysore on 25/9/2017 organized by the Mysore district administration

8 e resoeruces

ENGAGED SCHOLARSHIP

KNOWLEDGE TRANSLATION WITH POLICY MAKERS, INDUSTRY AND RESEARCH STAKEHOLDERS

(Only meetings and consultation sessions that)

1.State child rights commission (Govt. of Karnataka)

30.Provided Accredited Logistic Support for Ethnographic Studies

1. An Ethnographic Study of Kadugolla’ Community in Karnataka (PI: Prof. Annapurna, Dept of Anthropology University of Mysore-funded by Directorate of Tribal Welfare, Govt. of Karnataka)

2.An Ethnographic Study on Washer men community in Karnataka (PI: Prof. Annapurna, Dept of Anthropology University of Mysore-funded by department of Social welfare, Govt. of Karnataka)

31 Filed work Experiences

1. Mysore Districts (Child labor issues): 2 years
2. North and South Karnataka Districts (Tribal school issues): 2 years
3. Bangalore (Child labor issues/Ph.D): 1 year
4. Kodagu and D.Kannada Districts (Tribal health /PDF): 22 months

31.M.Phill Guidance (one)

32.Self Instruction Materials written for MA classes (open university)

Sl No	Class	University	Subject
1	M.A (Previous)	Karnataka State Open University	Anthropology (Kannada)

32.Other Publications

a.Occasional Papers

1.Rural Health Scenario And Management In Karnataka

b.Monograph

2.Child Labour and Sectoral Exclusion: Community Perception and Government Policies

c.Working Book

3.Bibliography on Medical Pluralism And Health Seeking Behavior

33.Academic/Social Related Popular Articles in the State and District Level News Papers and Reputed Magazines in Vernacular (Kannada) Language

Sl No	Title	Newspapers Magazines/Periodicals	Vol /Date /Issue
1	Financial Crisis In Universities	Prajavani State Daily	3/4/2010
2	Status Of Deemed Universities	Prajavani State Daily	13/4/2010
3	Quality In Higher Education	Prajavani Daily	3/6/2010
4	Problems In State Intelligence Department	Prajavani Daily	2/7/2010
5	Reformation Of Pre Primary Education	Prajavani Daily	13/4/2010

6	Plight Of School Teachers In Karnataka	Prajavani	3/6/2010		
7	Religious Conversion And Communal Harmony	Prajavani Daily	2/7/2010		
8	Quality Education For Tribal Children	Prajanudi Daily	13/5/2010		
9	Problems Of The State Universities	Prajavani Daily	3/6/2010		
10	The quality of distance education	Vijaya vani state daily	2/7/2010		
11	Higher Education And Private Universities	Prajavani State Daily	3/4/2010		
12	Tough Legislature Required For Rape Crime	Anupama Periodicals	3/6/2010		
13	Good Governance And Economic Development	Ananya	12/4/2010		
14	The Plight of Tribal People	Mysore Mithra Daily	23/4/2012		
15	Does India Need New Agricultural Policy?	Agri Work - Periodicals	13/5/2012		
16	Feticide And Infanticide issues	Vijay Karnataka, State Daily	12/4/2012		
17	Health Behavior and Medical Pluralism Among Tribes	Samshodana Vemershe,		--	2277-811x) 2015
18	The Plight Of Primary Education System In The State	Vijay Karnataka, State Daily	13/4/2013		
19	Universities And Quality Higher Education	Ananya Magazine	3/6/2013		
20	Quality Of Journalism Education In India : Issues And Prospects	Ananya Periodicals	2/7/2013		
21	Concern Need on 'Went Missing' Issue of Women And Children	Vijaya Karnataka State Daily	16/4/2015		
22	USA—Pak Nuclear Deal And Impact On India ,	Ananya monthly	4/5/2015		
23	Free Economy, Participation And Social Development	Ananya monthly	April 2014		
24	CSSEIP : An Unique Research Centre in Mysore University	Andolana daily	13/5/15		
25	Rural Health Sector: Issues And Challenges	Sowrabha	3(3)2014		
26	The Politics Of Food Shortage	Kannada Jana Mana Dialy	5 th July 2014		
27	New Hopes In The Budget-2014	Rajya Dharma Daily	8 th July 2014		

28	Higher Education: With New Possibilities And Challenges	Kannada Jana Mana Dialy	28/8/14
29	UGC: Towards a Drastic End?	Prajavani State Daily	13/4/2015
30	Anthropology and Sociology: Never Ending Confusions	Andolona daily	24/5/2015
30	Changing Scenario of Indian food culture	Andolona daily	19/6/2015
31	How to Prepare Anthropology For IAS /KAS Exams	Prajavani State Daily	3/5/2011
32	How to Prepare for NET exam	Prajavani State Daily	2/4/2010
33	Research begins After Ph.D., Degree	Prajavani State Daily	1/5/2011
34	Beneficiaries as parterres in Govt. schemes	Ananaya monthly	3/5/2012
35	Tribal Development Schemes : Where went wrong	Prajavani State Daily	12/8/2015
36	Comprise With the Rape Accused?: Critique On Court Verdicts	Ananaya monthly	8/4/2014
37	Women's' participation in PRI	Anupama monthly	Vol. 6 Issue 9 Oct 2015
38	Societal thinking towards disabled people	Rajya dharma daily	Jan 20 - 2016
39	Displacement of BINA beach Kannadigas	Karve nalnudi monthly	3(3) 2014
40	Changing face of women in Advertisement	Rajya dharma daily	2(1)2015
41	Climate change	Karnataka sowrabha monthly	March 2016 (Vol 11, No 4)
42	Disabled need help not sympathy	Rajya dharma daily	26 th Jan 2015
43	Essentials health reforms in India	Rajya dharma daily	24/Feb 2016
44	Women and Advertisement	Mysore mithra daily	3/5/2016
45	Child health insurance: Balasanjeeveni scheme	Anupama monthly	Vol. 7 No. 4 May 2016
46	Tribals' in transition	Karve nalnudi monthly	3(3)2016
47	Constitution and the Dalith Muslims	Nairutya monthly	Aug 2016
48	Falsie Tribal development plans ?	Mysore mithra daily	7/8/2016

49	Tribal development plans deviated?	Prajavani state daily	10/8/16
50	Peace and sustainable development	Mysore mithra daily	17/9/2016
51	Where is intolerance	Nairutya monthly	Oct 2016
52	Infant mortality	Anupama Monthly	April 2017
53	Malnutrition among infants	Health sciences magazine	2(4)2015
54	Civil service reforms in India	Viswavani daily	27/12/16
55	Tourism and Development	Nairuthya magazine monthly	Jan 2017
56	Issues in freelance writings	Nairuthya magazine monthly	2 (9) 2017 April
57	Disability and Paralympics	Samshodhana Veemershe	2 (2) 2106
58	Women and political empowerment	Nairuthya magazine monthly	June 2017
59	Different Govt. scheme for the safe motherhood	Anupama Magazine monthly	Upcoming
60	Tribal development at cross road	Mysore Mithra Daily	6/8/17
61	Schemes to prevent maternal mortality	Anupama monthly	2/5/17
62	Plight of UGC funded research centers	Ambedkar voice monthly	5/4/17
63	Tribal development at cross road	Praja nudi dialy	29/10/17
64	Women's participation in PRIs	Anupama monthly	Jan 2018
65	Securing minorities rights	Mysore Mithra daily	3/7/18
66	Save girl child	Mysore mithra daily	2/6/18
67	Dalith study centers in crisis	Ambedkar voice	12 Dec 2017
68	Social justice for all	Praja nudi daily	2/6/18
69	Safety of online data	Samaj mukhi monthly	1/4/18
70	Community Participation, Decentralization And Development,	Hosathu (Feb 2014)	2/4/15
71	Community Participation, Decentralization And Rural Development,	Hosathu (Sept 2015)	3/4/15

34. Founder of the Academic Journals (www.indianjournals.com)

1. Asian Journal of Development Matters (Print and Online ISSN/UGC approved) Chief Editor: Dr. Steven Wind (UGC approved)
2. International Journal of Social and Economic Research (Online ISSN) Chief Editor: Prof. Mak Arvin-Trent University Canada
3. Samshodana Veemershe (Critique Research) a Kannada Quarterly, Academic Research Journal

Editor –In –Chief

1. Samshodana Veemershe (Critique Research) Kannada Quarterly, Academic Research Journal

35. Founder Of ----

1. Rural Organization for Appropriate Development -Trust®-(An NGO)
2. Karnataka Kidney Health Foundation (www.kkhf.org) ® (An NGO)
3. National Observatory for Anthropological Research
4. National Association of Social Scientists
5. Founding co-Director: Karnataka Association of Professional Anthropologists ®

36. Founder of a Research Centre

1. National centre for Inclusive growth and Development Research Trust®

16. Award/Honors Received

1. Social Scientist Award (2012), Indian Academic Researcher Association, Tamil Nadu
2. Shikshan Rathna (2013) (Karnataka Cultural Academy, Bangalore)
2. Best Researcher Award (2016) SELP Trust, Tamil Nadu

Educational Documentary Movie/Short film Made

1. Endangered language -the Koraga (15 min documentary on Koraga tribal lang)

Special Lectures Organized

1. Anthropology: Our Life: Our Feature (3rd December 2011), KSOU Mysore
2. Honour Killings and Gender Anthropology (12th Feb 2010) Continues Education Centre, KN Pura, Udayagiri, Mysore
3. How to Save Your Kidneys (Jnana Deepa Degree College, Mysore)

17. Other Awards

1. Cash Award for the Highest Score in M.Sc., First Year in Dept. Of Anthropology, University Of Mysore, 1999)
2. Junior Research Fellowship-2007 (National Institute of Rural Development - Hyderabad) (Could Not Accepted)

18. Research collaboration

1. Centre for Contemporary Indian Studies (University of Colombo, Sri Lanka)
2. Center for Advanced Development Studies, Bhopal
2. International Childhood and Youth Research Network (ICYRNet), Cyprus (Member)’’

37. Editorial Board Member-

1. Journal Of Social Exclusion
2. SELP Journal of Social Sciences
3. Journal of Media and Development
4. City University Research Journal²-Pakistan
5. Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences (Italy/ceased)
6. Pakistan Journal Of Applied Social Sciences (Asso Editor)
7. Asian Journal Of Social Sciences, Arts And Humanities Pakistan)
8. International Journal of Research in Economics and Social Sciences
9. International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)
10. Katmandu University Journal of Medical Sciences –Nepal
11. International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development (Pakistan)

38.Ph.D Thesis Examiner

Title: A Comprehensive Study on the Rehabilitation Measures and Coping Mechanism of Leprosy Afflicted Patients. (Thesis from the Department of Sociology, Madurai Kamaraja University, Tamil nadu)

39. Forwardal Wrote for the Books

- 1.Housing Finance And Banking Sector In India' By Ganaraja K, And Others, Lambert Academic Publications, Germany,
2. Empowerment Of Women Through Self Help Groups: Karnataka Experience', Prasanna Kumar and H. D. And Dinesha P. T., Lambert Academic Publishing, Germany,
3. New Public Health Issues In India, Dr. Lancy D Souza Others (Edt), Spring Leaf Publications, Mysore
4. S. Jyothi Lakshmi And Suneeta Ganiger (Edt), Dynamics Of Inclusive Development: New Discourses, Discovery Publications, New Delhi
5. S. Jyothi Lakshmi (Edt), Growth, Inequality And Social Development, Discovery Publications ,New Delhi
- 6.Mrs.Swathi (Edt) Inclusive Development Of India Tribes: Anmol Publications, New Delhi
- 7.Dr.Umesha D (Author) Gandhi Concept on Economics

40.Book Reviews

- 1.Aging: An Interdisciplinary Approach, Edited: Sarjoo Patel And Veena Gandotra, First Edition (2012), Rawat Publications (Pp:268 *International Journal of Social and Economic Research* Vol.4. No.2 2014
2. 'Population Anthropology:- A Study Of Wearers Community, P.M .Sandhya Rani B.R Publishing Corporation', Delhi :First Published In 2012, *Afro Asian Journal Anthropology And Social Policy* Year : 2014, Volume : 5, Issue : 2

41.Health Awareness Related Articles in News papers

1. Behavior Of Kidney Disease (Mysore Mithra Daily)
2. Behavior Of Cancer (Vijaya Karnataka Daily)
3. Behavior Of Brain Tumors (Andolana Daily)
4. Why Kidney's Are Important? (Andolna Daily)
5. Behavior Of Heart Problems (Andolana Daily)
6. Behavior Of Kidney Disease (Prajavani Daily)
7. Behavior Of Kidney Disease (Mysore Mithra Daily)

8. Issues on Hemophilia (Andolana Daily)
9. Behavior Of Asthma disease (Mysore Mithra Daily)
10. Nutritional food care (Andolana Daily)

(Written More Than 30 Letters to The Editor/S on Various Social Issues for Reader's Column In Daily's

42. Extracurricular activities

1. Actively Participated in 'Suvarna Manasa-2011' University level Exhibition Conducted by the University of Mysore, Mysore as a part of the Golden Jubilee Celebration of the Mysore University Campus.

2 Acted as a Judge for Inter-college debate competition at Somani Degree College, Mysore

42. Member to the Professional Organizations;

- A. Anthropological Association of India
- B. Indian Sociological Association
- C. Indian Social Science Association

44. Policy Planning Document (Co- Authored)

A. Eco-Tourism Opportunities In Coorg Dist (Karnataka): A Guide For Planners, Administrators, Submitted to Group for Nature Care (R) Reputed NGO in D K Dist (Karnataka)

Other Professional Association

1. State President, Indian Academic Researchers Association- (Karnataka chapter)

43. Radio Programme Aired

1. Child Labour Issue' Aired By All Indian Radio – Mysore (May 4th 2009)
2. Definition of the Term 'Change' in Anthropological Perspective (Mysore AIR)
3. Dengue and Chikjken gueny and how to overcome

43. Other Professional Activities

a. Discussant: In Two national seminars

b. Committee Member

1. Solution Exchange (Platform For Discussion) Running By Karnataka State Resource Centre On Child Labor (KSRCCCL) Of Karnataka State Child Labor Eradication Project Society (KSCLEPS) ,Ministry of Labour, Government Of Karnataka.

3. Culture And Society: Transformation, Challenges And Strategies
Department Of Studies And Research In Sociology
Tumkur- University, Tumkur-(8th December-2012)

4. M/Phil PhD Thesis Evaluation : One Ph.D thesis in Sociology from Bharatiya
University (Topic: Medical sociology)

d. Proposal Reviewing: Reviewed 3 proposals for funding

e. Consultant: NCIGDR Research centre, Mysore

f. Independent Research Consultant: NCIGDR Research centre, Mysore

g. Online certificate program (free) enrolled
Center for Global Health (Colorado School of Public Health, University of Colorado –
USA)

h. Poster Presentations: One poster presentation in a seminar

I. interview board member: For 5 different research projects to hire research assistants

44. Research Impact on News And Articles:

1. Indigenous Medicine and Safety Needs , Covered In Prajavani State Daily
- 2 In Times of India Daily
3. In Indian express Daily
4. In Hindu Daily

45. Community Service /Social Awareness Rallies Organized

1. Three Rallies organized on Account of World Kidney Day
2. Rally Organized on Account of World Heart Day
3. Rally Organized on Account of World Cancer Day
4. Free Eye Checkups And Operation Camp Organized In Association Mysore
Rice Club Eye Hospital (2009 July)

46. Research Methodology Related Workshops Attended

1. Research Methods In Social Sciences (Ugc Academic Staff College, University
Of Mysore) One Week Programme
2. Advanced Research Methodology (Part-1) –Mahajana College, Mysore
3. Research Methodology, Organized By Kannada Development Authority,
Bangalore And Karnataka Research Union (R), Bangalore,
4. Advanced Research Methodology (Part-2) –Mahajana College, Mysore
5. Advanced Research Methodology On Social Exclusion, National Law School,
Bangalore

6. One Day Research Methodology Course (Centre For Social And Cultural Growth (An NGO) Bangalore
7. Organized Advanced Research Methodology Workshop In Social Sciences (Ugc-Csseip Jan 16th Jan 26th 2013)
8. Orientation Programme On New SPSS And Descriptive Statistics Awareness Programme (16 Hours) Organized By The Iranian Student Association, Mysore
9. Application Of SPSS In Research Data Analysis, Mahajana College, Mysore (4/3/14)
10. Digital Qualitative Research workshops (V.V Institute Of Engineering And Technology Mysore)

Dissertation details

Level	Dissertation Titles
M.Sc	Alcoholism and its Consequences: Case of among Kodva Community in Coorg dist
Ph.D	Child labor in Bangalore Dist: An Anthropological Study
D.Litt	Nature and Dynamics of Health Culture: A Sociological Examination on the Changing Health Seeking Behavior and Medical Pluralism of the Rural Population in the Selected Districts of Karnataka state, India'

47. Shortlisted Concept Proposals; but could not send the full proposal on time

	Title	Funder
1	An Investigation of the Administration and Functioning of Primary Health Centers (P.H.C.s) in Rural Areas of Karnataka- INDIA	ICMR
2	An Empirical Study on Prevalence of Childhood mortality and Morbidity in Two Primitive Tribal groups of Karnataka	ICMR
3	A Study on Japans' Policies to Promote the Social Inclusion of Disadvantaged Groups and Lessons for India	Japan Foundation, New Delhi

48. Research Proposals did not selected

	Title	Funder
1	Assessing the Linkages between Changing Socioeconomic Status, Perceived Personal risk, and Risk Factors for Certain Communicable Diseases in Primitive Tribal's of Karnataka Tamil nadu and Kerala of South India	Dept of Health Research (Govt of India) (2017)
2	An Assessment of Availability and Utilization Pattern of Existing Facilities for Post-Crash Emergency Management	ICMR

	Care along Golden Quadrilateral and National highways in South Indian States	(2017)
3	Inclusive health care: An Investigation of the Administration and Functioning of Primary Health Centers (P.H.C.s) in Tribal Areas of Karnataka- INDIA	UGC (2014)

49.Seminar /workshop proposals did not selected for the technical reasons

	Title	Funder	Reasons
1	Cultural Tourism and Tribal Development in India: Dynamics and Discourses	Ministry of Culture Govt. of India	Rejected because of inadequate documents (originally short listed)
2	Law, Urban poor and Social Exclusion (One day work shop)	National Human Rights Commission, New Delhi	Rejected because of the technical issues in the utilization certificate (UC) of the previous programme (originally short listed)
3	Faculty Development Programme (10 days workshop)	ICSSR, New Delhi	Rejected because Three years was not lapsed from the previous award
4	Research Methodology workshop for Ph.D Students (Seven days workshop)	Association of Indian Universities ,New Delhi	-----

50.Other Competencies

IT	Well versed With Computer Operations, PPT, Mini Tab Statistical Software, Basics In SPSS
Research Project Management	Research project management: Drafting research proposals, experienced at managing research projects with single or multiple participating institutions. Skilled at Providing logistical support to projects including checking on and managing the Budget, Scanning through applications and communicating with partners.
Running Journal/s	Handling And Publisher Edited Printing (Done Since Last 9 Nine Years)
Communication	Adept at Communication At Multiple Levels, Experienced at Communicating With Multiple Participants And Project Partners. Campaigned for Various Health Issues
Organizing events	Well Experienced in Organizing Seminars/Workshops/Walkathon /Camps etc

In the interview panel	Was a Member in 4 Different Interview Sessions for the Selections of The Candidates for Different Research Projects
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48. Volunteer Service

A..UNESCO On-line Volunteer

B. Volunteering Member for Peace & Harmony, National Foundation for Communal Harmony (Ministry of Home Affairs, Govt, Of India)

C. Voluntary Member for Two NGOs

49. **Hobbies:** Freelance writing, Photography, Armature Radio

50. Reference

1.Prof. Douglas Anderson

Dept of Anthropology

Brown University -USA

Email; douglas_anderson@brown.edu

2.Prof. Mak Arvin

Department of Economics

Trent University Canada, Email: marvin@trentu.ca

3.Prof. M. Assadi

Special officer

Raichur University India

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Research Brief

Health Culture, Health Behavior and Medical Pluralism in Changing Rural Context in India: Some Perspectives

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It is generally felt that modern health programmes do not have any space to respect people's inherited health culture, emotions and spiritual meanings associated with health and diseases. It is believed that respondent's health behavior depends on the particular culture, particular geographical area and particular eco-system.

Moreover, it is found that health seeking behavior varies according to the type of illness, causation of illness, gender and age of the patient; and that perception of illness and sickness directly affects health seeking behavior and health care seeking behavior of any particular community and health behavior is much controlled by the social, cultural and the family-based frames of mind in rural parts. In certain rural parts of India both traditional and modern medical health behavior continuous to be antagonistic to each other. This is why rural people have pharmacopeia of their own for various types of illness/disease they face normally. This paper is based on the author's field work experience in many rural parts of south India.

One of the leading themes of medical Sociology has been the conceptualization of health behavior and its cultural meanings. The growing number of publications in Sociology on health behavior issue in the underdeveloped countries has raised a renewed interest in the family context of health culture. Central to some of the notable work has been "how health behavior among marginalized sections is constrained by hierarchies based on age, caste and gender—a constraint that results in its typically rural, flexible and personalized character, rather than a widespread form of medicalizations".

To some extent different medical system can co-exist as separate arenas in the same geo-graphical areas. There is a persistent belief, which finds its origin in the neoclassical approach, that medical pluralism is the best antidote to rapid medicalizations, at least with special reference to the rural part. This notion suggests that availability of a different medical system decreases health

expenditure on the family. The articulation of gender, age and kinship of the patients plays an instrumental aspect in opting for a particular type medical system. Culture determines to an extent not only the type of disease or illness, including frequency of its occurrence, but culture plays a vital role in the way people perceive, explain and treat various illness and diseases. Hence it is generally found that culture determines community understanding of health and illness. Because of this, community develops specific belief, towards several health problems including causation, spread and diagnosis.

Health culture, health behavior and medical pluralism in the rural context play an ultimate role in determining the health status of the rural people. Health culture and health behavior are like two faces of a coin, one cannot exist without another. The exposition of health culture in case of the rural context has been attributed to some of its determinant factors. In rural settings, an availability and accessibility of different health care agencies are the vital components of health culture. The co-existence of various health care agencies becomes the outcome of social changes including socio-political development. With such health institutions and their services, rural people have inter-oriented themselves in fulfilling their required health needs.

Though the process of socialization of health culture is an internal aspect of any individual, health behavior manifests in accordance with the valve of norms. Hence health culture presents stimulating forces to produce the required health behavior. In the majority of cases, the cultural attitudes towards health are largely boosted by current socio-economic conditions. However, health culture in rural areas has undergone tremendous changes due to various new technologies, varying social needs, and the influence of a variety of pressure groups and institutions. Various studies have shown that a sick person while making decisions on his/her own will be largely influenced by age, income, occupation, religion and other factors. Also, health behavior is found to be a complex phenomenon

because it is influenced by a range of factors ranging from psychological to biological and economic (Bir, 2001).

Different beliefs and practices indirectly reveal the causation of diseases as they provide the framework for one's reasons and expectations for seeking treatment. We find that, in rural areas at least in the case of India, health behavior is found to exist alongside western medicine; yet, many people are failing to acquire proper medical treatment on time. Apart from the socio-economic factors, there are some other vital issues that help shape health culture and health behavior in rural centers. Cultural factors like ethnicity, religion and gender also produce differential health behavior in case of rural residents. Certain Anthropologists have introduced different health models in order to understand health behavior in rural communities, including the etiology of diseases, symptoms, responses, communication and management (Banerji, 1981). Rural residents' perception of the severity of the diseases coupled with previous experience and faith in the success of particular type of healing technique is imperative to seeking suitable initial choice. In remote rural areas, people are wise enough to differentiate different diseases which can be cured by western doctors and those by local healers. In some rural parts, modern medicine is being used to cure severe health problems (Duggal, 1994).

Health seeking behavior is contingent upon people's perception of illness or disease and on available health services. Health seeking behavior involves taking a pragmatic decision in order to deal with health problems within available resources. Income, occupation and level of education also play a vital role in selecting appropriate treatment. Higher-income groups in rural area normally approach good health care whereas lower-income groups look for subsidized health care, or would visit only government hospitals where poor health infrastructure exists. Sometimes, in rural areas, the distance factor also counts a lot. The structural and functional changes in the rural societies are taking place over the period of time, hence health culture and behavior are spontaneously brought in and some are induced in the context of several health institutions.

We found that, over the last decades, awareness has increased regarding usage of medical pluralism and role of modern medicine with reference to rural areas. Even today, a variety of healing treatments exists alongside western medicine in rural areas. Rural communities have local medical systems, based on traditional and customary beliefs. However, in the fast changing rural society due to globalization, local medical system has been under the influence of other medical systems.

The medical system in rural India consists of a variety of practices including those related to magic, faith healing and herbal, among others. Both orthodox and non-orthodox therapeutic pluralism, which reflects domestic political economy, has been widely available today in rural communities. Experts feel that the demand for pluralistic therapy is increasing in rural areas due to the changing concept regarding health and illness. Due to external influences, usage of more than one type of medical care for the same health problem is gradually increasing (Minocha, 1990). In rural areas, the patients showing interest in therapeutic pluralism include those who suffer from the side effects of allopathic medications; would like to avoid excessive medications; and those who want to avoid surgery.

In rural areas, patients evaluate the therapies in terms of costs and benefits with reference to various types of treatment. Here, cost means not money, but rather the long-term impact of a particular

type of therapy on health and duration of healing. It is found that people in rural areas today are very careful regarding the standardization of traditional medicines and are more aware about side effects, with the help of various social networks. In fact, some of the sidelined medical system likes Unani and Sidda are also quite popular in rural areas at present, because of their low cost and absence of side effects.

Medical pluralism in rural communities thus opens up new possibilities of gaining insights into the interplay of social, economic, political and cultural domains of health behavior. Efficiency of treatment is determined differently by various actors and class of people when several systems of medicine are available in the same area. Pluralism is not just a therapy but substantive definitions of what constitute a disease and how efficiently it can be cured soon (Mechanic, 1989).

Selecting a type of therapy in rural traditional health system has a bigger impact than curing a disease. Rural health culture believes that the beginning of any health disorder has a direct resultant impact on social solidarity. Choosing the right medical system to heal the problem will play a vital role in cementing existing social ties. Experts opine that medical pluralism has various dimensions and dynamics including philosophy, ideology and social diversities (e.g., caste, class and religion). Traditional healers basically use this philosophy in their treatment in order to preserve their role and status within the wider society and culture. Only the holistic concept of health culture provides a structural insight about rural communities' changing health seeking behavior nowadays (Turner, 1967).

We feel that the option for a multiple system of relief is basic to human in broader need and cannot be analyzed as a cultural obduracy neither ignorance on the part of rural residents. It is not just because of the absence of proper allopathic facilities nor general ignorance. Rather, it is argued that the co-existence of traditional and modern medicine had therefore to be seen not as dichotomies but as overlapping instrumentals (Sujatha & Abraham, 2012).

Health beliefs are changing according to different geographical areas especially in rural context. Broad and specific geographical patterns of medical knowledge across villages in India have been reported, some of which are disparate while others are similar. One of the great strengths of the Indian rural medical system is the involvement of group in therapy, where kin, affine and other villagers help in therapy management. This social support network in the treatment process, in which suggestions and counseling are involved, help boost the morale of the concerned patient. If the patient suffers from any pain, normally the whole village group shares the agony. Hence, healing process is a shared experience here. In this case rehabilitation of the patient is not a problem at all. The overall impact of various modern and economic development processes is also impacting effect on rural health. Continuous migration also has done severe damage to the natural humanity of the rural folk (Joshi, 2009).

We find in rural settings health and treatment normally reflects community solidarity. He writes if something happens to a single village's person like illness the rest of the village will come forward to observe certain norms. Choosing a healing therapy will be sometime at community level. In certain cases the whole community will take the responsibility of the patient until cured. This social solidarity through the social network will also play an indirect role in

educating other people to be more cautious about the illness. He also highlights that social scientists have done enormous work on the rural health culture and committed about their blind health beliefs but they have focus on in-depth study on the basic forces behind that belief. Further, he opines the current traditional method available to the rural people needs more scientific study. There is a dearth need to encourage and support the traditional healing system to the tune of modern medical coverage. Traditional healers should be trained at least in the field of identifying diseases exactly in earlier stage where is burden on the patient can be substantially reduced (Choudhuri, 1989).

The medical system of the rural society is normally composed of different medical sub-systems found in a co-operative or a competitive manner. One patient and the multiple health systems (e.g., Ayurveda, Unani, Sidda and Western doctors) are the features of medical pluralism, which is based on hierarchical relations and socio-political and economical controls. In a pluralistic health care system the very basic interpretation of illness may get changed over time. Usually patients do not essentially mind the illness details and healing approaches coming from different health care systems that may be contradictory. We find that modern world should not ignore the entire traditional medical system, including the diagnostic and healing techniques prevalent among rural folks. Further, we feel that both indigenous and modern medicines have certain common platforms and hence it is better to study the rural health culture from the context of both differences and similarities within these two systems of medicine. Expert said it is high time to find out the cultural factors affecting the acceptance of traditional medicine and cultural issues related to non-acceptance of modern medical care by rural folks.

It is proven that the acceptability of traditional or western system by communities depends on cultural, economic, political and moral values. It is not so easy to introduce the Western medical system in rural areas where traditional systems strongly exist for a long time. People will normally compare among the various medical systems available at their door steps with respect to quality, cost and effectiveness. All these factors vary from context to context. Rural people normally expect medicine/s should solve any health problems as soon as possible, and they just bother about the immediate consequences. Hence, now Sociologists are focusing on the phenomenology and the political economy that exist within current medical pluralism and social relations in health care management. A perfect understanding of medical pluralism in diverse cultural settings is a need of the hour.

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Sujatha V., & Abraham, L. (2012). *Medical pluralism in contemporary India*. New Delhi: Orient Black Swan.

Turner, V. (1967). *The forest of symbols: Aspects of Ndembu rituals*. Ithaca, New York: Cornell University Press.

PhD in SOCIOLOGY

The De La Salle University offers a 3-year PhD in Sociology (PHDSOC). The program aims to produce, professionals who are able to critically comprehend, integrate, and apply the sociological perspective in three tracks: family, health and population dynamics; organizational and social systems development; and educational Sociology. To be admitted into the program, students should:

- 1) Hold a master's degree. The master's degree may be in any social science discipline. If applicant has no such master's degree, her/his university degree should be in social science. If applicant has no social science degree, either at the master's or university level, he/she should have at least three years of social science-related work experience; and
- 2) Submit admission requirements (<http://www.dlsu.edu.ph/admissions/gao/requirements.asp>):
 1. Application form with 2x2 picture,
 2. Original copy of transcript of records,
 3. Original copy of NSO birth certificate,
 4. Transfer credential (for non-DLSU graduate),
 5. Two (2) letters of recommendation (downloadable at above URL),
 6. Updated curriculum vitae/resume,
 7. Personal statement containing academic and career objectives,
 8. Two (2) pieces of 2x2 picture for testing permit,
 9. Certificate of good moral character from previous school/employer at least six months from date of issuance,
 10. Photocopy of sample research outputs, and
 11. A concept paper of the proposed dissertation research (include a statement of the research problem; the potential contribution of the research to theory and/or policymaking; and of the data collection methods).

Upon admission, the student will be assigned a faculty member as mentor/adviser.

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Inclusions of Social Determinants for Public Health Care Approach: Does it Really Matter?

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Abstract

The National health policy accepted by the honorable Indian parliament in 1983 states health care as the main device for achieving sustainable development of the community. It is a known factor that development of any society depends on the healthy people only. Without good health even we cannot think appropriately and act properly and expect the society to keep moving smoothly. It is a known fact that without proper health we cannot expect the proper social inclusion of any community in any way. An in-depth study of social determinants on health culture of any society will help in understanding complete knowledge of etiology, various health issues and policy drawbacks etc of nay society. Understanding social determinants on health would be more useful in planning geographic and cultural specific health care programmes for the rural people in the county. Holistic knowledge of social determinates will be helpful in understanding health seeking behavior of the people and this will provide valuable insight in framing ground level public health policies in the country. With this background this paper is to reveal various social determinants affecting on health .This paper concluded various social determinates of public health care needs to be focused urgently

Keywords: Determinants, Health, Inclusion, Public, Social

1. Introduction

Leslie, writes "All systems of medical belief of practice are empirically self confirming. People everywhere live until finally die and they only die once, while in the process of living they undergo various, physical and mental health illness, episodes. In brief, a lot of people will recover from their health problems no matter what the healers they met, say or do, and they will mostly would like to give credit to their recovery to what was done" (Leslie, 1986 : 79).

Health is not only a stable state of physical and natural well being but also in a true sense it involved the various other complex issues. As it is widely known fact that, health is one of the imperative indicators shimmering the excellence of human life since time immemorial. Healthy community is very vital because it can set the destiny of the any society or country. Also healthy human resources lead to have any type of development or any kind of achievement. Health is a very vital integrated component of an

individual/a community. Sometime collapse of health may even lead an individual towards an early death. Also unhealthy community may be a hinder for the holistic growth and development of any society. Poor health status of any community may isolate that community from the mainstream of the society.

What is Health?

Scientific definition of the term 'HEALTH'

WHO definition of health: The present definition of health was originally created during framing a preamble to the aims and objectives of the world health organization in 1946. According to the WHO definition "Health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity". In 1986, the WHO said that health is "a resource for everyday life, not the objective of living. Health is a positive concept emphasizing social and personal resources as well as physical capacities". (WHO, 2001).

*Author for correspondence

Today every government is intended to bring many health programmes. Quality health care has become a key indicator of social inclusion. Providing health care to the disadvantaged sections of the society has become a challenged task before any government, rather than just medical care, health is a very important constituent in every social development programmes. Generally quality health system depends on existing strong politico-economy of the state. Today health sector is a potential long term investment marketing potential. Excellence in the delivery of health care service mainly predisposed by the various socio-economic and other situational issues. We found that poverty, illiteracy, housing are some of the factors causing health inequalities in India. Uneven allocation of modern medical facilities, lack of effective prevention measure, development behavior of certain communities, absence of strong political will, bureaucratic negligence, poor medical infrastructure, malnutrition, transport system, people ignorance are some of the hurdles in the way of "Health for all".

There are some studies to show that changing socio-economic process will also influence on the pattern of the health culture and health seeking behavior. This is very common and true in case of rural folk. It is found that when changes occur in the given health culture the health behavior will also get changes slowly. Thereby health status of that particular community will get changes. Hence perception and attitude of the community towards different health problems will get new shape and frame finally it leads to the formation of new health behavior when they faces such health disorders in the future¹. When the health culture is strongly influenced by the external organics (level of education, migration, role of media etc.) in a particular geographical area people will develop new health behavior. This adopted a new health seeking behavior will resolves the health problems within the given ecological settings². This type of compulsory modification in the health behavior of a particular community for a moment will be overt and some time will be implied also.

As we are aware socioeconomic and cultural issues have long been considering influencing factors on individual's health. These factors includes an individual-level (e.g. individual socioeconomic status, sex, caste, class) and neighborhood-level dimensions (culture, community, demography composition, social and physical environment) operating both separately and through various interactions. Current spatial research has found that

in rural communities, economics, caste and class status are furthermost fundamental factors influencing on their health status. On the other hand, rural communities also face supplementary problems connected with access to, and utilization of quality health care³.

Public Health Agency of Canada has given 12 Social and Economic Determinates of Health⁴

- (1) "Income and Social Status
- (2) Social Support Networks
- (3) Education
- (4) Employment
- (5) Social Environments
- (6) Physical Environments
- (7) Personal Hygiene and Coping Skills
- (8) Proper Child Development
- (9) Biology and Genetic
- (10) Health Services
- (11) Gender
- (12) Culture"

The World Health Organization (2008) views that the following health determinants has a pivotal role in determining the better health and standard of living of the people in general. The major health determinants are as follows:

1. Income
 2. Education
 3. Social Network
- (Sources: official website of WHO) Quoted

2. Social Determinates of Health

"what really moves the health of whole societies, adding to or subtracting from the sum of total health, may be factors which account for only a very small part of the individual variation in health and so escape detection" (Wilkinson:1996;16)

A not only biological factor, health is also determined by both social and cultural environment. Various studies have established this link. Some of the social variables like income or poverty, occupation, educational status social network etc.... plays a vital role in determining the health behavior of a community. Throughout the life course social determinants influences health at multiple levels. For example, income of a person influences the health at different levels. This influence may co-occur and interact with each other to produce health status. Further, various social -cultural factors independently influences the health of an individual at different stages

of the life. As we are aware socioeconomic and cultural issues have long been considering influencing factors on individual's health. These factors includes an individual-level (e.g. individual socioeconomic status, sex, caste, class) and neighborhood-level dimensions (culture, community, demography composition, social and physical environment) operating both separately and through various interactions. Current spatial research has found that in rural communities, economics, caste and class status are furthestmost fundamental factors influencing on their health status. On the other hand, rural communities also face supplementary problems connected with access to, and utilization of quality health care³. It is found that throughout the illness period social determinates will play a role in choosing specific health care system (Aurvdeic, western etc). It helps in choosing affordable treatment.

India can be divided into urban, tribal and the rural, social determinant issues also plays vital role on various social sections of the society like SC/ST/OBC. Rural people are most valuable to difference kinds of diseases. Their social economic conditions normally will be poor some time they have to live in a most remote area. Their income, educational level and occupation type will be also plays a vital role while determining the health cultural

1. Broader socio culture environment
2. Civil society
3. Intimate sources and economic realm

Table 1.

Category	Determinants	Details	Sphere
Cultural	Status of Women	Elements of Patriarchy	Cultural property
Social	Age and Sex		
Socio-Economic	Households Resources	Education Level; Maternal occupation; Marital Status; Economic Status	Informal
Economic	Cost of care	Treatment, Travel, Time	Physical
	Type and severity of illness		
Geographical	Distance and physical access		Infrastructure
Organizational	Perceived quality	Standard of drugs, Standard of Equipment, competence of staff, Attitudes of Staff Interpersonal process	Technical, Staffing Interpersonal formal

Source: Sara Mackiam (2003:4): A review of health seeking behavior: problem and Prospects (University of Manchester)⁴

Figure 1. Bullseye Model of social determinants of health³.

3. Breaking Down Determinants of Health Care Seeking Behavior

3.1 Income

It is found that the income of any family may decide the echelon of the poverty in that family. However the connection between income and the health is not up till cleared it is not so easy to make known the relationship between heath and income. A little bit income may be highly recurring. Or in some case we may need to focus on individual income or total household income. As we know Income also stands on various independent factors like employment status, salary, pension, household size etc... it is revealed that squat income at all times acquaintances with little accessibility for high-quality health care. The relationship among low income, mortality and

morbidity tempo in a meticulous family proves poor health status itself. In addition it is established that person of having good health will have more possibility to get better income for himself. It has been established in quite a few studies. In the similar way owing to unhealthy, an individual may misplace occupation and decreases in the usual income. owing to the drop of the normal income not only influence on the individual including other house hold members. It clearly know factor that good income enables one person to purchase a variety of health related items like, nutritious food, health insurance etc. In adding to it gives rather good mental health also. Good income too escalates tan individuals from poverty connected pressure. Since income is a type of flow of resource, while other shape of wealth can be extremely helpful to maintain the good health at any stage of the life. Some studies have shown that people with high income live longer when contrast to the people of having little income. Infant mortality tempo would low in the high income people whereas it would be higher in the squat income group as we seen. Also "higher income people more likely to report having seen a physician regularly where as lower income group people are not". All these result shows that marginal income or low income levels tends to be more powerfully connected with condensed prospect of poor health than augment the possibility of brawny health status. Reports have proved that elites of the population are spending lofty on health care. In addition poor people do not have a propensity to over consume health care relatively to their level of social status. MacInnes and Milburn (1994) writes "however not all research shows an independent effect of income dissimilarity on health social problems since there is a less concord about whether income inequality causes health and social problems independent of these factors or not".

3.2 Education and Health

Educational level has a close association with health over the period of time. Various research works have shown that echelon of education unswervingly or circuitously impact on health issue. It is found that low level of education leads towards in dangerous health behavior. Education is an informal variable in improving the health status. Experts have established that advanced level of education is coupled with healthy lifestyle. It is found that linkage between level of schooling and health shows two issues;

- a. Causal role of education on health.
- b. Interface between the level of educational attainment and inherited features.

It is recently found that level of schooling is an indicator of improved health literacy. Educationists opined significance of giving pre-school education will, really augment the health scenario of the children and of the concerning family members. It is revealed that physical and as well as mental health of the educated people will be normally good and they will spend a smaller amount on health problems than others. Recent study found that low level of education is greatly connected with the poor psychological status of an individual. Certain studies shows that low level of education is associated with poor biological conditions bad habits and unscientific health practices also. Interestingly a better educated people though they had bad habits previously but they gave them up more readily because of feature health care.

Since education is also a major determinate in the health care low educated people have experience, a shortened life expectancy than higher educated. Also a high rate of crimes and violence can be seen among a low educated people. More education obviously leads to have a higher income. This higher income access to have high quality health care. It also is found that good education provides individuals to make better health related decisions himself /there self related to the other family members. In rural area level of education may not impact on health separately from other variable factors. Income and occupation also have good linkage with education as influential factors on health. Finally education is a vital for increasing the healthy life style of an individual. Due to better education, family members can practice good health behavior and low health expenditure (MacInnes, and Milburn,1994).

3.3 Poverty

It is widely known fact that poverty is a key role in determining health status of any community. It may be urban, rural or tribal. It is found that poverty ultimately results in unhygienic housing, poor nutrition, increased risk of infections etc. Poverty as on ultimate impact on any community particularly vulnerable and poor health status might be a best parameter to measure poverty. Experts felt increasing states health expenditure not only improves the health status of the community unless reducing

poverty level we cannot expect any improvement in the health status of the population.

Poverty is a multidimensional aspects it affects on good food, shelter, un employment and low income that all work together and affects on individual health due to this an individual will be in risk of getting depression, anxiety any type of chronic disperse. Due to poverty poor people may not visit a doctor unless it is a serious disease. First he/she will try with local traditional or self medication. Sometime due to poverty patients will buy medicine over the counter (From the medical shops with prescription). Recent Human Development Report (2005) opines that poverty and health each influence each other directly and indirectly. Sociologists felt poor people often describe illness and disease as fate, hunger, pain, fear, anger etc... poverty not only affects the adults it also affects severely on the health status of the children and aged people of the family. Due to poverty poor people visits only government hospitals where there will be no modern equipments and highly specialized physicians to diagnose the problem in the early stage.

Due to poverty only people cannot visit private practitioners or hospitals where one can get high quality of health care. Educationists felt due to poverty sometime children could not attend schooling; hence, children and parents cannot get any awareness about simple day, to day health related practices. Poverty not only affects on physical health but also affects on the mental health. Poverty related stress may even provoke to commit any crimes in the society. This poverty related stress also lards to severe depression, lack self esteem which finally affects on mental health of an individual⁸.

3.4 Occupational Status

Rather than income, occupational status of an individual or family is more reliable and static criteria to measure socio-economic status and its effect on the general health. Good occupational status or decent occupational status leads to have more quality healthy life. It is found that occupational status has a close link with access to good health care. Flow of income some time fluctuates, where as good occupation promises more reliable and regular income flow. Hence they can take right decisions regarding their health care planning. Sometime ill health may be a major reason for downward occupational mobility few studies have also proved that casual effect of occupational status on health behavior. Some time health disorders may be a constrained for up word occupational mobility.

Higher occupational status is less likely to be explosion to various occupational disorders. Also higher occupational status gives more peaceful mental health. Since employment status is more strongly associated with health than income. Experts left it play a vital role to access more economic resources. This may help to an individual for upward social mobility. Sociologist have founded on objection and subjective indicator of health and occupational status. Also it is observed that unscientific health practices and unhealthy habits can be seen more among unemployed people. This association has been found younger adults older adults and people with various disabilities also. However some of the studies have observed that income and health are independently associated. Even after the food employment status the health problem of the lower income people were still increased. This might be due to an effect of material factors on health care.

4. Social Support and Social network

Social connections play a vital role as in major social determinant of health. Social supports not only give material recourses but also they provide love, emotions and attachments to an individual. Social support is a type of assistance that people will normally receive through their established social network. Social network provides vital information's about healthy life style or hospital care. Certain studies have shown that good social network, results in positive impact on physical and mental health. Social networks predict the risk of all causes and cause specific health disorders. Social network also has a history in providing good mental health care to the rural folks. Social network and social support have also helped in survival of some major illness.

Certain epidemiologists felt social connections may help in avoiding on set of various infectious diseases. On other hand good social network can also be a negative impact on health outcomes. Sometime people may use their social network for bad health behavior (during users). Also few studies are going on association between social supports and give environment interactions. Social network and support may together use as social capital, member of the community can make use of social capital system for betterment of their health needs. Studies have also proved that there is a close association among social capital, health outcomes and communities social

economic characteristics. It is also proved that that withdrawal from the social network resulted in some type of mental issues among the youths. Modern social network system in rural area has proven useful in providing culture specifics role in adopting western health care. Through social network support people will get influential, emotional and informational support to keep themselves away from both short term and long term consequences of various health problems.

In a currently varying social order it is proved that relationship between a range of socio-economic distinctiveness and the health is very vital. It is established that education, poverty and income are the three main indicators of the healthy society. Each of the indicator acts through diverse mechanisms on health issues. "Socio-economic characters in health are wide spread, distinctive, dynamic across multicultural societies and for a diverse range of health issues. These social variables play a vital role. Also through this variables we can enhance our knowledge in understanding how biological pathways for some health disorders shaped by local culture" (Nanjunda, 2013). accepting the contribution of social and cultural factors on health reveals a new edge to get an idea on dynamics by which these variables participates as a major role concerning the beginning of disease and sequence until adopting a positive health behavior. All social-economic indicators act internally and externally to impact on health.

4.1 Sense of Personal Efficacy

It relates to People's ability to control over their emotional part of the life. People with a higher ability of controls of emotional will escape from stress related health disorders Experts also felt 1. Social gradient 2. Early life experience 3. Social exclusion also plays a vital in health issue rural people.

5. Conclusion

Healthy community is the future asset or capital for the development of the any society. Health is a substance of apprehension to all spear of the society. It is a high order to foresee a society which is free from the recurrent struggle against diseases. The development of good health is conditioned both by heredity and environment. If the society burdened by ill health people it would be a kind of overburden and it may be a curse for the any society

for that matter. Poverty, income, education level are some of the vital and major pushing factors for the poor health status of any community in India. In the same way, it is revealed that existing social determinants with respect to the public health problems are viewed as a major hurdle to the overall development of an Indian economy. It is also known that poor health actually minimizes the human capital accumulation, which is a prerequisite for the national development. Govt need to address to overcome various social determinants soon.

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International Journal of Basic and Applied Medical Sciences

ISSN: 2277-2103 (Online)

An Open Access, Online International Journal Available at
<http://www.cibtech.org/jms.htm>

2014 Vol. 4 (3) September-December

SOCIAL CONSTRUCTION OF HEALTH AND ILLNESS: A THEORETICAL REVISITING ON DIVERGED DIMENSIONS

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ABSTRACT

The sociology of health and illness has a long history. Over the last 100 years many concepts, theories, findings have been explored for the better understanding of health behavior of human being and the role of the society. Majority theories and approaches relating to the health and illness have been originally propounded by the western sociologists only. Even today researchers in developing countries are heavily depending on western theories to explain health culture and behavior of the rural community. In developing countries social class, caste, gender etc play a vital role in accessing suitable healthcare facilities. More than these the underlying social, political and economic forces are also counting a lot. It is found that sociology of health and illness significantly helps us in better understanding of people's concepts about onset of various diseases and its cure in a cross cultural framework. Health and illness are a universal concept in all societies. Each community organizes itself through experience, through different means, through different elements and finally will develop different approaches to fight against illness and diseases. In this way each and every society develops specific medical institutions called health care system in a relevant social context. This health care system will have origin, symptoms, development, process and curing of various diseases/illness. This system will have different symbols expressed through the means of practices, interactions and institutions. This paper is bas don the review of various secondary materials.

Keywords: Health, Illness, Sociology, Institutions

INTRODUCTION

Health is an elusive concept. We have numerous definitions to define the term health. Good health can be some time positive or sometime negative or more precisely absence of any kind of health related problems like physical or mental. Herzlich (1973) said "health is to feel well, in good form, happy content, with a good appetite, sleeping well wanting to be up and doing; it is to feel well and strong; that's what good health is". Parson (1951) defines health is a good status of physical body which can perform any task. He said 'healthy person can do any social role which is a normal part of his/her societal responsibility. Health disorder may reduce the capacity of the human being'. We can also opine the cultural setting of any given society regarding, 'perception, preference, evaluation and satisfaction about 'health' is more vital while generalizing term' (Nagala, 2007). The health of any society is intimately related to its value, system, philosophical and political and ecological organizations (Singh *et al.*, 2008). Moreover health is subjective in its basic nature.

"Sociological research deconstructs such discourses and highlights their implications on the notion of agency of the patient, meanings of informed consent, patient participation in different cultural contexts and notions of health and illness as doing. Health becomes an everyday moral duty" (Mishra, 2010).

Sociology brings two different focuses of analysis to the study of health and illness:

1. At the first instance it focuses to 'make sense of illness', by applying various sociological perspectives both to a scrutiny of the understanding of illness, and to the social structuring of health and disease. Further, sociology makes an imperative input to multi-disciplinary and multi faceted assessment into issues of interest to health care providers and helps in the development of new appropriate health policies;
2. At a second level, sociological enquiry can give more options to an understanding of the effect of wider social and cultural phenomenon upon the health of individuals or the community and various social

groups. Such processes include social inequalities, health culture, behavior, change, knowledge, medicalizations and power.

Albrecht (2000) writes "An massive body of work in the sociology of health and illness is not so patently realistic but is intention on understanding what it means to be sick, to have a chronic illness or disability, to be a woman, to experience fertility and menopause, to be poor, a member of a minority group and in need of health care and social services" (Albrecht *et al.*, 2000; Bird *et al.*, 2000).

Since communities' perception on health and illness varies from culture to culture sociologists have given various theories and approaches to study about health and illness over the period of time using longitudinal studies. Truly speaking the very basic concept of sociology of health and illness is to enlighten about the social origin and influence on the onset and choosing suitable medical care of any diseases or illness and role of different components of the society relating to that issue. Sociology of health and illness also explains how different social groups have come up with the specific diseases over the period of time and what other culture can learn from their experiences. Also concept on health and illness of the society is based on the cognitive orientation of a particular social group and cure will also follow the same cultural logic.

Culture is a shared concept of the specific social groups. The concept of health, hygiene, illness, well being, and sickness are the fundamental issues present in all types of culture across different societies. Every culture will have its own notions, concepts about health and illness. Culture is a vital concept and an instrument to conduct health studies among the rural population as patients' belongs to different social groups. These people express unique health behavior and medical pluralism to cure their health problems. People's construction of illness is a focal point in sociology. The Influence of religious belief and social network on the health culture is a vital issue studying health and illness from the sociological point of view. Every culture has its exact clarification and justifications for all types of ill health. Culture provides people with ways of thinking that are "concurrently models of and models of actuality".

The health care system is also a part of general culture. There will be no much differences between socio-cultural experiences and episode of illness with respect to a particular social group. Each and every individual through his/her personal episode of illness will keep on adding his/her prospective to the society's health culture. We cannot neglect health and illness episode of a lay person. Health culture will develop according to the social, economical, legal and political development etc. of the society. In this matter various medical institutions and the systems will also play a vital role in the maintaining of the "state of health" (Langdon and Wikinson, 2010; Kleinman, 1980; Langdon and Wilk, 2010).

Health care system normally will have two components.

1. Social component;
2. Cultural component

Social Component: In case of social elements it consists of different health care institutions, healers, health culture, health behavior etc., It also includes traditional medicinal system like folk system, faith healers, quacks herbalists etc., Apart from these we can also witness for the growth of other medical system like Unani, Sidda, Tibetan and Chinese medicinal system side by side. Also we can see the concentration of different specialist practicing different therapeutic models based on different health culture and care. Each and every social group will have their own reservations, perceptions in accepting or acknowledging or rejecting these any type of medical system/s. This acceptance or rejection will be largely based on the socio-economic background, caste, family history, religion etc. we cannot isolate all these vital factors while studying the health culture of a community from a sociological point of view.

Cultural Component: The cultural system of health will help us with different knowledge and cognitions to identify perceive and explain disease/illness. Each and every culture will have their own concept about symptoms, classifications about various types of diseases/illness. However they are not universal. Every health cultures give etiological theories about multiple causes of disease and illness. Certain health culture theories provide us logic behind both preventive and curative knowledge of the people. Some theories enlighten us about various reasons for using more than one type of medical system (Medical pluralism) and how medical pluralism shapes communities' health behavior and health culture.

Truly speaking health care system has been just a conceptual model to understand society's different health culture and behavior. This will help us to understand the different sets of elements and experiences involved in the health culture and behavior. Since the health care system is a cultural system, sociology will also help us in understanding medical pluralism operating concurrently in different social groups and cultural response for various health problems.

Sociology of health and illness specifically also deals about

- Various medical and healing agencies ;
- Social role;
- Symbols, power and the healing;
- Structure, process and outcome

Sociology of health and illness basically deals about the inter relationship between 'health and society' and 'medicine and society'. Study about health and illness in the society is not a new phenomena. From time immemorial, people are doing official or unofficial research study about societal reaction and responsible towards health and illness. Even during the Egyptian period also there were some intelligent people doing research on medicine and its connection with the society. Essentially there is a clear cut differentiation between medical sociology and sociology of health and illness. In medical sociology focus will be concerning health and illness delimited by a range of social institutions. Nevertheless in case of sociology of health and illness researchers by and large studies concern a) various social and cultural factors causing diseases and illness, b) health seeking behavior, c) health care seeking behavior and d) inherited health culture of the society.

It also focuses how health culture and behavior varies based on the socio-economic status of the community. Sociological concept about illness gives a fair idea how external determinants causes health problem to an individual and how he/she responds to it in a given social context. It is a well known truth that the influence of socio-cultural factors varies across the globe. Normally these social factors demonstrated through various discourses on important diseases /illness and its outbreak in a specific geographical area. Basically experts' focus about the issues comprising society and medicine, socioeconomic setup, general cultural issues which are geographically specific while studying specific health culture of a community. Sometime a common disease may affect the larger population whereas a major disease may affect smaller population only. Medical anthropologists basically studies about these discrepancies.

It is found that basically sociology of health and illness study takes place in three vital doamins. They are-

1. Conceptualization of health and illness of a particular society or culture;
2. Measurement and distribution of health and illness;
3. Reason behind choosing particular type of healing approach

As we are aware different culture responds differently to different illness/diseases. Based on this study about how an illness affects social regulations or controls over the time would be worth for study. Measuring and distribution of various dieses/ illness will help how community is using various existing health services. It also helps in getting patients' perception about his/her illness and reason for that. Sociologist tries to study the various data to analyze the distribution pattern of disease and illness in a given society.

As new medical health care facilities discovered, health status of the communities across the world has started considerably improving. Gradual changes in the socio economic status of the people also led to have quality medical care. Diagnose and treatment also started to affect positively on the health care seeking behavior of the community. Now rural people are showing much interest to adopt modern health care facilities whereas certain sections are not yet. This change in the health culture of the community causes the issue of health and illness within given societal life to be highly volatile in definition. Hence studying health and illness from the sociological point of view continuously needs to be updated.

Wilkinson (1996) has opined society having poor health will tolerate high inequality in every aspect. Differences in health practices between various social groups would be more vital for sociological analyzations. Even in the same society, disparities in health status and health behavior can be seen among

different social classes/castes. The wide income gap, material deprivation and psychological issues invariably effects on health and illness of an individual/community in a society. Wide gap between rich and poor people results in low social cohesion which finally affects the health of all members. It is found that vital differences in case of mortality and morbidity continuously increasing between low income groups and the elites of the society. However the research is on the way to find out how poverty and deprivation effects on general health issues and behavior among the members of developing societies.

Health seeking and health care seeking behavior of an entire family will be largely influenced by the social and cultural factors. Poor income means poor health. Finally it leads to have various effects on family causing various health problems. Income and health are closely related to life expectancy of any community. High income inequality also leads to have a big gap in the health disparity between different social groups. This health disparity is due to material deprivation and socio-psychological effects. Due to social exclusion (class and cast) certain sections of society may not get equal health benefits. Various social, cultural, developmental and psychological factors finally leave an impact on health condition of an individual irrespective of his/her class and caste. Moreover it is found that social capital like education, housing, social networks also places an imperative factors causing health and illness (Crision, 2007; Wilkinson, 1996; Marmot, 2004).

Social Construction of Illness

Bhasin (2007) writes "every culture has its particular explanations for illness. Frake (1961) during his research among Subanum of Mindanao, explained illness as a vehicle for pursuing other interests. He wrote "illness is fundamentally semantic or meaningful and all clinical practice is inherently interpretive.....".

According to Good (1977) "semantic illness network is the network of words, situations, symptoms and feelings which are associated with an illness and give it meaning for the sufferer".

Health, illness and cure are realities in everybody's life across the societies. Therapy, practices and results normally evolve over the period of time within the socio-cultural contexts. It provides different insights about health culture, behaviour, traditions; customs in the medical health care system. Through the personal experiences patients' and the doctors/ native healers will also add on to the knowledge of society's health belief system continuously over the period of time. All cultures consist of vital information's about how disease occurs, what makes illness and how to choose suitable healing approaches. This would be a health culture of each and every community. In each health culture there will be different concepts, ideology philosophy and thinking and planning in handling various diseases and illness appropriately (Bhasin, 2008). Obeyesakere (1976) has given a term called "cultural diseases" because some diseases are created partially because of "cultural" definition of the "situation".

Regarding social construction of disease and illness Rose (1992) has evolved an argument for analyzing 'behavior determinants of the health of individuals at the societal level'. Rose writes "concerning the social distribution and determinants of disease and illness cut across the view of disease as an autonomous individual affliction. It focus that new disease and the discloser to the range of possible risk factors are a result of the norms of any given society". Hence it is opined that beliefs held by the community/individual within a society about on set of disease and curing is critical always.

It is generally opined that illness has three domains:

1. Illness as Sanction (punishment for doing wrong)
2. Illness as Deviance(a form of social control)
3. Illness as an Indicator of Social System Performance (indicative of the performance of an existing social system)

It is well known truth that health and illness is a 'socially constructed concept'. Each and every society will interpret the term 'health and illness' differently in its own way. This would be depending largely on history, culture, religion, gender role etc. of that society. Moreover it depends who has the final authority to apply the label of 'illness' within a given society. Also it depends on the context or the circumstances in which illness occurs. Truly speaking social construction of illness means how society shapes illness

behavior of an individual in which he/she normally live. Here one question arises what does really construct an illness?

Steven (2001) writes "clearest example of illness as a socially and culturally shaped through a similarity of eastern medicine system and description of illness versus western medicinal system and description of illness".

Illness has three historical origins:

1. Few illness notions are originally rooted historical and cultural meaning;
2. Most of all illness are socially constructed at the empirical level;
3. The true medical concept about illness is mostly framed by the vested interest

Social construction of illness depends on how people differentiate between illness and the disease. Social construction of illness has developed through an interaction in a social context. Meaning and the experience of illness will be largely framed by the historical and existing social system. Scholars say illness is not 'given' rather actually conferred by dominating social groups in a given society. They say society will confer illness as a part of the control/sanction (short term). Scholars who support 'symbolic' interactionism felt illness is an experience within the framework of daily social interactions of an individual.

Few sociologists are showing interest to work on how 'symptoms' or 'symbols' are being labeled or identified as an 'illness'. It is also interesting to look what is accepted as "Illness or what is not accepted as not an 'illness' and what are the factors which play a vital role in differentiating illness from any biological framework. However, few scholars also say an argument over illness and its societal construction approach as something 'Mixed' i.e. Illness has both medical and social deviance. Some time illness varies or may not have independent factors of effect on patient and health care system. Illness has also cultural symbolic domain.

Some illness has been labeled as stigma, while some illness is not stigmatized in society. For example AIDS will be severely stigmatized where as polio not some time. Illness stigmatization varies society to society based on the type, duration and severity etc. It may have less noticed in urban society whereas more serious in case of rural society. Some time due to stigmatization people may not come forward to take suitable medical care as all.

It is known fact that sociologists are studying 'patient perspective of illness' since 1950 onwards. Strauss (1975) opined that since patients' will spend only few days 'with illness (if is a minor problem) patient's personal experience/narrations may not same as the illness experiences of a patient having long term health problems' Hence it is necessary to focus on 'patients life's before illness, during the stage of illness and after the illness got medically cured'. This helps us in the social construction of illness based on patients' experiences in a given society. Also it helps us to know how the different components of the society helped him/her to come out of illness stage soon.

During the stage of illness patients' will be normally worried about their personal and social relationships and other day to day activities which could not be performed well. Sometime during the stage of illness patients will review their previous life and in some cases it may create new illness identification (ex. patients under dialysis) also.

Banks and Prior (2001) opined in this situation patients will create their own illness ideology based social context and their own illness narrations and parameters to measure their illness notions.

Truly speaking sociological study on health and illness mainly focus on two prospective:

1. Sociological analysis of different societal factors causing health and illness;
2. Social structure and how different segments of a society responsible for the current illness and how a patient responds to it.

Studying health and illness from the societal perspective will yield some diverse dimensions and discourses. This would be completely different when examining health from an individualistic prospective because social determinants and individual determinates are quite different. Social, cultural and economic conditions are some of the strongest determinants while studying illness in rural society.

Theories about Origin of Diseases and Illness

There are various theories about origin, cause and cure of diseases and illness. Also theories explain how particular health behavior and health culture evolved in the society. Theories about diseases and illness may mainly divided into two groups they are: 1. Personalistic 2. Naturalistic 3. Folk Concept

1. Personalistic theories argue illness or disease causes due to supernatural powers including spirits, sorceries, souls, witches etc. According to this theory illness causes due to moral or spiritual violation by human beings. Violated social and religions taboos also cause illness as believed in many traditional cultures. This theory further believed that illness is a type of sanction by the super natural powers due to the immorality or breaching taboos in the life. This theory also opines failure to carry out certain rituals may also end up with illness. According to this theory recovery can be had by worshipping deity through ritual or through a trained healer. This theory also explains about sick role in the society and society can help him/her to come out of sick as spoons as possible. Also it explains the space of the sick person in the society and effect of sick role issue on the stability, continuity and cohesion of the society.

2. According to Naturalistic theory illness causes due to impersonal terms. This theory assumes illness causes due to disturbance of cultural order of human beings with his/her surrounding eco-system. This theory says harmony between human beings and eco-environment should be properly maintained without which it causes severe may harm of the health of a person. Humeral concept is a vital concept of naturalistic theory. Proper balance of various human systems would be a vital component for being healthy. According to this theory Indian system of medicine is also based on naturalistic theory. In India 'Prana' (vital energy) concept exists since time immemorial, Prana is essential in keeping the human being alive. If the vital energy is disturbed human being may get sickness.

Folk Concept: This is one of the ancient concepts of explaining causes of illness and cure which is prevalent in many parts of India and other Asian continents. Folk concept's on illness and diseases ranges from the social world to the supernatural world. These symbols have cultural significance in explaining health behavior and health culture. Folk concept presumes illness and disease may cause due to evil eyes, imbalance of body fluids, hot and cold diet, sorcery, violation of taboos, improper behavior also. It also opined an individual failed in performing rituals regularly may get various health problems. Folk concept has a lot of symbolic meanings. This theory also explains how human body normally functions (humeral), and how it causes symptoms and the meaning of illness and its moral, social and cultural significance. Also it thrives to explain about illness within the individualistic perspective.

Sociological Approachs: Sociological theories of health and illness relatively based on imbalances inside the human body. Certain sociologists argue illness causes due to problems in the social relationship. Also they argue that illness causes due to broken relationship between the human being and the eco-system. Indian system of medicine is based on the same belief that the human body is made-up of three basic substances called 'spirit, phelam and bile'. Chinese's medicine is also based on the belief that the body is made-up of five elements including 'water, metal, earth, fire, and wood'. In addition Greek system of medicine opines that human body has four different of forces. Expert says any imbalances among these basic elements would cause illness and disease among human beings. Certain sociologist's proposed their theories about illness and diseases based on natural and super natural causations. Theories of natural causation focus on disturbance of health as a physiological consequences including infection, germs, mental trauma (Murdock, 1980).

There are three vital theoretical modules to get into the in-depth understanding of health and illness from the perspective of Medical Anthropology.

1. Epidemiological approach
2. Interpretive
3. Critical Medical Anthropology

1. Epidemiological Approach: In case of epidemiological approach, normally researchers studies health and illness from the prospective of social and cultural factors. The core part of this theory deals how ecology and environment affect causing various health problems in the society. In this approach, normally focus would be on various risk factors which cause diseases and illness and how it relates to the

environment. This theory also propounds the relationship between urbanization and new public health problems. According to these theory social interactions, food habit, and household ecology also play a vital role in causing health disorders. This theory adds urbanization and migration invariably causes new social pattern of health problems in the society.

This approach further divided into three more divisions;

a. Retrospective Approach: it conducts reasons for various diseases and illness which are occurred already.

b. Prospective Approach: informs us whether the diseases occur or not? More precisely we can say prospective approach gives an idea of possibility about future occurrence of some diseases. Epidemiological approach will not avoid the occurrence of any diseases but gives a hint in advance.

2. Interpretive Approach: Basically this approach studies diseases/ illness from the micro prospective. Interpretive prospective further elaborates how specific cultural factors cause disease/ illness. It also focuses how health behavior and health culture evolved over the period of time in a given society/community. This study would be useful in analyzing health behavior and health culture of small communities.

Critical Medical Anthropology here researchers would focus on how economics and political issues of the society play significantly in the development or underdevelopment of various human health issues. Economics and politics are the major factors in the development/underdevelopment of human health. Also this approach deals about various social problems and effects of the media on the prevailing health care system in the given society. This theory further focuses how dominant western biomedicine discriminates poor and powerless in the society with respect to health. This approach also sheds light on pseudo-medicalism, medical exploitations, cost of treatment, Doctor's behavior, medicalizations process etc. This approach strongly believes in the notion that political and economical structure of the society basically responsible in establishing good/ bad health status of a community. Finally this approach criticizes the western health care system for being de-humanized. This theory also strongly criticizes about 'over medicalizations'.

Further sociological study also revealed how different social process and functions affects on health status of different social groups. In addition it helps to reveal how different social groups are experiencing health and illness. Supplementary it reveals layman's health beliefs, and illness behavior. Many studies have proved that layman's health beliefs vary according to social and cultural background. How a layman experiences, describes, justifies health and illness would be a vital point in understanding general conceptions of health and illness of the people. However certain medical sociologists have opined there will be a big difference in case of general societal opinion than an individualistic opinion about socio-cultural aspects of health and illness. Because individualistic determinants for health and illness cannot be simply generalized or add up to become the general social determinants in a border way (Crimson, 2007).

Conclusion

A lot of changes have also occurred in the basic theory of illness ideology and sick role because of the availability of speedy healing techniques/treatments. The significance of the "sick role" has also been diluted because of globalizations. Globalization has affected even on the concept of traditional or folk medicine today. Today public health communication has been effective due to the availability of new and upcoming formal and informal channels. However, because of globalization western bio-medicine acting as a system of social control ruling out the role of sociological argument pertaining to health and illness. Report says today western part of the globe turning to use the non-biomedical healing system rather than modern medicines which leads sociology of health lines to aside.

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PUBLIC HEALTH *and* PSYCHOLOGY

NEW DEBATES

LANCY D SOUZA

24

Social Dynamics and Cultural Frontier of Health Care in Rural India A Medico-Sociological Review

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Anu Bhawana**

ABSTRACT

Health is one of the vital indicators reflecting quality of human life. Today majority of rural people are suffering with various communicable and non-communicable diseases. It is found that there is a positive correlation between the health status of rural people and their social, economic and cultural dynamics. Over the last few decades various governments have developed plans to achieve long-term goals to provide a comprehensive health care programme for the rural people, and have increasingly emphasized the more immediate need to provide essential basic primary health care and scientific management of rural the rural population through rural system. Experts have conducted various studies on culturally bounded health behaviour among various rural settings. Still, they have not yet completely understood the dynamics of health behaviour of rural people. It is found that poverty, illiteracy, malnutrition, scarcity of potable water, sanitary conditions, poor mother child health services, problems in covering rural health and nutritional services, etc., have been found the most vital causal factors for prevalence of several health issues among rural communities in

the country. This paper concludes that as far as an organic linkage with the rural health concerned, there is no basic service for a comprehensive health intervention attempt to understand health culture as a sub culture complex in developing a model of culturally suited health care delivery system specially for the rural people of the country yet. Hence we need to rethink in having more culturally suitable health policies for the rural folk. This paper is based on the author's field experiences working on various health related projects.

Background

In all human society irrespective of its simplicity and complexity and no matter how small or big, no matter how advanced or traditional there exists some sort of simple or complex health issues. The world health assembly in 1977 started a movement for health and well-being for all by the year 2000. A. D. India was also committed to achieving 'Health for all to her citizen'. The National health policy accepted by the honorable Indian parliament in 1983 states health care as the main device for achieving sustainable development of the community. It is known factor that development of any society depends on the healthy people only. Without good health even we cannot think appropriately and act properly. It is known fact that without proper health we cannot expect proper social inclusion of any community.

Experts felt that Health can be more precisely viewed as an index of human adaptation to 'micro-ecological niche'. Even though western system of medicine has many advantages over the traditional, it has not totally been accepted by the majority rural Indian masses till today. It is because of their unique age old health behaviour consistently influencing by their inherited culture, tradition, beliefs, values, norms and practice etc. All these play a very vital role in shaping health behaviour of that particular community. Invariably it keep shapes the perception and attitude towards the onset and curing of different health problems in a given community over the period of time. Finally it determines to select a particular type of treatment to solve the particular type of health problem. Sociologists felt that every community (may be urban/tribal/rural) normally develops their own health needs and curing approaches after motivating by their changing levels of socio-economic conditions. In this process, health of the rural's as subsystem will be mainly infused by the above attributes of entire social system. Experts felt cultural response of the community to the health problems confronted by it determines the way individual members perceive different ways of dealing with various health problems.

Right from the time immemorial health-seeking behaviour of the Indian rural population is greatly governed by cultural values, beliefs and traditions etc. However now it is open for gradual change because continuous

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interventions of the different kinds of external agencies. Further in the changing process of health seeking behaviour patterns of the rural people one also can notice incredible fresh air which have occurred with respect to philosophy, knowledge, and practices of indigenous systems such as Ayurveda, Homeopathy, Allopathic, etc. Nevertheless, it becomes important to work on problems of rural's health because it differs from a particular area to another area owing to their remote geographical setting. Historical milieu and the processes of social change (Bulliyya, 2009). Geographical isolation and limited interactions with other communities has become an obstacle to know the degree of prevalence of certain dangers diseases including HIV/AIDS among rural communities in India (Arlappa, 1999; Basu, 1992; Kerketta, 2008).

In rural setup people believe illness is due to supernatural power, angry deities trouble from the ghosts, ancestors, etc. According Tribhuvan (1998) generally rural believes illness is a kind of social sanction. People from rural or tribal background have perception that illness is a punishment for doing wrong deeds. This kind of attribution is an early form of social control in the more regular way on the development of human society. Polar (1966) and Cromble (1969) have opined that today in non-western society major mass will felt illness is a type of fate or punishment by the unknown cosmological power. Further, Persons and Fox (1952) have opined that illness can also be seen as a form of deviance in its own right, they point out that a high occurrence high rate of illness is dysfunctional for any kind of social system. Lieban and Richard (1973) have opined that illness as an indication of social system performance. Camaroff (1981) and Foster (1976) have opined that rural people believe illness is curse due to the disturb of cultural order and every society has its own explanations and reasons for illness. Certain medical sociologist felt even though sickness or illness is basically individual or personal issue or phenomenon it will be largely influenced by the surrounding social groups. Generally existing socio-economic structure will play a vital role in shaping specific type of health belief or behaviour in a particular society.

Truly speaking health behaviour would be a kind of interpersonal behaviour, care, and sympathy about the sick person amongst the villagers. Normally in rural settings social group shares basic concept about health and illness in a more organized way. Lewis (1993) said illness pertains to "those corresponding choose to identify as underside called abnormal, the experience and meaning of perceived disease". It is found that indigenous concept and beliefs are completing associated and may be more precisely say intertwined regarding various dimensions and angles of the illness itself. Also diversity in circumstantial and other strong related social factors. Particular illness shapes in having simpler or complex health seeking behaviour among the rural folk which leads to have proper selection of the treatment.

Any domain of health culture will have implicit meanings. Studies conducted in various part of the village India have shown that acts, words, songs, chants, worship, statues is very vital in healing process. Further natural, supper natural, cosmological, spiritual power also play significant role in causing illness as believed by the villagers. It is found that illness will be classified into four groups based on their etiology they are:

1. Body linked illness.
2. Deity linked illness.
3. Spirit linked illness.
4. Sorcery linked illness.

Eating of banned food, bad water, contaminate environment, are the factors causing body linked illness. Breaching taboo, forgetting worship, festival would be considered as causative factors for deity linked illness. Further it is found that different deities, spirits are connected with a single type of diseases and single spirit may cause different health problems.

Though India is a heterogeneous culture society there are certain elements which are common in all types of societies. This is because over the period of time each society and culture will exchange certain elements through Sanskritisation, Universalisation. This is an example of how cultural elements travel from one society to another. Sometime due to the uneven spread of culture similar set of health traditions and customs can be seen across the country and sometime only in a particular geographical area. In India medicine and culture are inseparable. Medical pluralism found across the country can be studied like other elements of culture.

What is Health Culture?

- *Culture*: Culture is a core part of any human civilization; whither culture we cannot assume this human society. We cannot study human behaviour with out knowing the cultural background. Health culture is the core concept of Medical Sociology or medical Anthropology and it may significantly helpful in deepening our insight into the vital inter-relationship between culture and health. In Medical Sociology more precisely we have two approaches to study the health culture. (i) Realistic and (ii). Idealist approaches. In realistic approach "looks upon health culture as an attribute of social life of man". According to this view health culture is in separable from the real human behaviour in society and it is standardized social procedure. However experts felt individual differences and variations within the concept and perception of health culture need to be concluded without fail. Regarding idealistic view health culture is conventional understanding of health behaviour of the community towards specific diseases or illness. In this approach particular health behaviour of a particular community passes through the generations as social heritage (Suter and other 2002).

There are some studies to show that changing socio-economic processes will also influence on the pattern of the health culture and health seeking behaviour in rural part. This is very common and true in case of rural India. When changes happen in the health culture health behaviour will also get changes. Thereby health status of that particular community will get changes over the period of the time. Hence, perception and attitude of the community towards different health problems will get new shape and frame finally it leads to the formation of new established health behaviour when they face such health disorders in the future (Banerji, 1986). When the health culture is strongly influenced by the external organics (level of education, migration media etc.) in a particular geographical area people will develop new health behaviour also. This adopted new health seeking behaviour will resolve the health problems within the given ecological settings (Parson 1963). This type of forced change in the health behaviour of a particular community sometime will be explicit and some time will be implicit also.

Social Support, Social network and Health

Social connections play a vital role as major social determinant of health. Social supports not only give material recourses but also they provide love, emotions and attachments to the patients. Social support is a type of assistance that people will normally receive through their social network. Social network provides vital information's about healthy life style or hospital care. Certain studies have shown that good social network, results in positive impact on physical and mental health in rural settings. Social networks predict the risk of all cause and cause specific health disorders. Social network also has a history in providing good mental health care to the community. Social network and social support have also helped surviving from major illness.

Certain Epidemiologists felt social connections may help in avoiding on set of various infectious diseases on other hand good social network can also be a negative impact on health outcomes. Sometime people may use their social network for bad health behaviour (during users). Also studies found an association between social supports and environmental interactions, Social network and support may together use as social capital. Member of the community can make use of social capital system for betterment of their health needs. Some studies have also proved that there is a close association among social capital, health outcomes and communities social economic characteristics in shaping specific health behaviour. Studies have also shown that withdrawn from the social network resulted in some type of mental issues among the patients. Modern social network system in rural area have proven useful in providing cultural, instrumental, emotional support and informational support to save him/her from long term health problems. In a changing rural society education, poverty and income are the three main

indicators of the health of a particular society. However each of the indicator acts through different mechanisms affecting health issues. Socio-economic characters in health care is wide spread, distinctive, dynamic across multicultural societies and for a diverse range of health issues. These social variables play a vital role in enhancing our knowledge in understanding how biological path ways for some health disorders have been shaped by local culture. Understanding the contribution of social and cultural factors on health gives a new edge to get an idea on mechanisms by which these variables play a role about the onset of disease and its progression.

Health Culture and Medical Pluralism in the Rural Contextual Process

India is a home to many medical system (pluralism) like: Ayurveda, Unani, Sidda, methods date back to 5,000 B. C. Even today they remain a vital source of every day health care in curing common diseases. There are many instances to demonstrate significance of various indigenous knowledge's in curing various health and sickness problems by the rural folk. However, rich ecological and cultural diversity cannot completely highlighted if we confined our knowledge to conventional scientific concepts on health and illness. These different kinds of medicinal system are culturally familiar, technically simple, locally available and effective. Since indigenous knowledge is culturally and spiritually very near to the people traditional beliefs this medicine plays a vital role, as a part and parcel income of rural health culture.

It is widely known fact that health status of the rural people will be poor because of isolation, habitat, difficult terrain, poor understanding of their health behaviour etc. Hence Medical Sociologists suggest following an integrated multi disciplinary approach to understand rural health concepts, focusing traditional diagnostics, curative and preventive health care is must. Since rural's may have to face some communicable diseases like malaria, T. B, Typhoid, STD, Jaundice etc., their traditional medicine system may get fail in diagnosing and curing the problem soon. Hence prevailing culturally and geographically specific health care system should be studied deeply. In rural part socio-cultural dynamics will be very complex and also it plays a major role in adopting different kinds of treatment to cure any health problem. Perception of illness and sickness directly affects on health seeking behaviour of the particular community. In rural setup health and diseases are more related to practice humeral medicines. Since in certain rural parts trained doctor's available humeral medicine co-exists with modern medicine. In this concept changing rural health culture may be more perceived in the context of knowledge of health problems, health beliefs, new healing techniques and norms and values related to health and disease and limitations of different types of medicines.

Reasons for Health Problems as Believed by the Villagers

Sl. No.	Problems	Frequency	%	X ²	P
1.	Humoral imbalance	4	4.00	21.186	.000*
2.	Superhuman causation	34	34.00		
3.	Cosmology	32	32.00		
4.	Pathogenic	11	11.00		
5.	Punishment for deed	19	19.00		
Total		100	100.00		

*Highly Significant.

Truly speaking health culture is an existence of its own (more precisely) an autonomous and independent system. During the process of socialisation health culture will be an integrate part of an individual and it helps in shaping the once own health seeking behaviour or action in due course of his life time. As Bir (2002) opined, "In fact, the organic needs that operate the internal environment or system of an individual such as needs for food, sex, protection etc... are sources of stimulus force or motivation for independent action of the system of health culture". Further Hassan (1967), felt "The level of satisfaction of these needs takes place in accordance with the values of health culture acquired by man as a member of community or society".

Systemic investigation on rural's health culture has gain with consideration in medical sociology. It is found that health seeking behaviour varies according to the type of illness, causation of illness, gender of the ill person and age of the person affected by a particular type of illness. Studies have been conducting to get the core concept of rural's health behaviour focusing illness ideology and its relation with cultural perception, culture experience and cultural communication, and finally cure. However certain studies found that socially constructed medical roles to enhance particular health behaviour and cross societal similarities and changing patterns in such behaviour. It is found that medical pluralism and health seeking behaviour of a family may affect an entire village. Also similarities and variables with respect to health seeking behaviour of an rural individual may be a lesson to the rest of the villagers. Sometime life style of the particular person, and how seriously he/she considers his/her health problem and frequency of occurrence of the particular health problem plays a significant role. Hence every society has developed certain methods to cure such type of diseases by using different kind of medicines. Nature, application, control of any type of medical system depends on every cultural pattern. Largely we can say it depends on the pattern itself with in a given community. All beliefs and practices of local medicinal or religious leaders (priest, etc.) in accepting modern health care facilities significantly vital in shaping common or similar pattern of health seeking and health promoting behaviour.

Hence experts felt study should focus on how medical aspects influenced by the social cultural issues and in turn how given socio-cultural issues influence by the medical aspects. Further experts opined that both indigenous and modern medicines have certain common platform. It is better to study the rural health culture from the context of both differences and similarities focusing available medical system and it must be to find out cultural factors affecting in accepting indigenous medicine and cultural inhibiting factors in accepting modern medicines. Established health behaviour of the rural folk should not be underestimated just citing them as illiterate or superstitious. Even today major sections of the rural people are not ready to accept modern health system. Because of their cultural resistance, many rural targeted health programmes have not been succeeded yet. Medical Anthropologists felt modern health programmes, don't have any space to respect people inherited culture, emotions and spiritual meaning associated with health and diseases.

The strong beliefs on faith of the people regarding in the relating of healing technique does matter a lot. Also role of family members, village members, and others plays a vital role in rural health culture seeking a particular type of medical assistance within the given context of medical pluralism including hakims, local traditional healers, nomadic vaidy's ayurvedic and modern allopathic etc. It is found that medical practice among rural people is highly pluralistic. Only in certain part of the rural areas both traditional medicine and bio-medicine co-exists in India. Also in certain part, the rural areas government has opened allopathic and ayurvedic medicines, so that rural people can select any type of medical system regarding prevention curative and rehabilitative measures. Hence we can opine that health seeking behaviour of rural people is gradually becoming flexible or changing. Experts opined that there is a dearth need of new sociological studies about dynamics of changing rural health culture focusing philosophy of changing traditional system of medicine.

Today in some rural part local medicine system are being dislocated from their past golden days. Health behaviour issue from the prospective of rural cultural fabrics towards refusal or accepting various medical system needs new and fresh date as felt by the western sociologists. Also they says traditional medical system because of inclusion of consistent inter-generational contents is also a big question in traditional societies. There are some extreme diversities in the demographic behaviour of rural's with respect to ethnically, socially, economically in various ecological, environmental and developmental settings. It is found that health behaviour is much controlled by the social tradition and family based frame of mind rather than social growth and economic status of a community. In certain rural parts traditional and modern medical system continuous to be antagonistic to each other (Singh, 2008). This is why rural people have pharmacopeia of their own for their common many fold discuses.

Normally illness causes high rate of social, economical, psychological cost on any human being. The set of medicines composing various cultural practices, methods, traditions are embedded in a matrix of values, traditions, beliefs and pattern of ecological adaptation. Rural's health concepts revolve around gods and spirits and they think super natural power will normally controls the human health behaviour. Since rural society is a multicultural one in certain cases health seeking behaviour differ from caste to caste, and people belongs to twice born caste will also observe a dual type of health behaviour. Religions also greatly impacts on determining the type of treatment plan. Sometime Hindu patients will visit Muslims quacks and where as Muslim patients visits hindu quacks. Sometime nomadic quacks are also found significant in curing various illnesses. In some cases rural people will also visit tribal medicinal men. In rural setting caste plays a vital role. In some cases low caste people will not visit quacks who belongs to higher caste and vice-versa.

It is found that in rural settings concepts on angry deities, ghosts and spirits whiches also differs from caste to caste irrespective of socio-economic status concepts about body symbolism, hot and cold concept, ritual healing ethos, concept on body physiology also differ from caste to caste in rural settings. Experts felt that local healers will play on the psychological aspect of the patient. Here faith on the healer by the patient play very momentous role. This kind of strong emotional attachment of rural's towards local healer correlates socio-psychological aspect of the illness. Also it completely depends on viability, availability and easy accessibility of any medical system.

Indian sociologists have done in-depth study on social character of health and sickness. Truly speaking local medicine comprises number of individuals interacting with each other which is influenced by the local culture and society. In this way concept of health, illness and medicine will be largely influenced by the particular type of culture. Hence health and illness should be studied in a holistic way from the lens of social cultural factors. Each and every individual will develop/her own health seeking behaviour over the period of time due to the influences of economy, religion, politics health and illness are part and parcelary society. Sometime the health seeking behaviour may be similar or different. In this background sociologists will try to study social dynamics of health and illness and response of the society to it.

Conclusion

In rural society concept about health and illness changes from culture to culture, caste to caste, class to class and one geographical area to another. People will normally presumes illness may be due to angry of the god because of sins and crime committed in the life. Sometime people will connect health problems in the current birth may be related to the previous life. Sometime

people think some disease is internal due to the three humors (Tridosas) of the human body, i.e., Air, Bile and Phlegm. In a rural setting people normally visit local Vidya as a healer to get rid of any health problem. Before visiting the healer people normally practice certain home treatments. In some rural part local healers who are well experienced in curing certain disorders have been monopolized by certain specific families. Also the secret behind curing techniques will not be leak out to the any other person. During curing session a healer may use one technique or mixture of more than the technique to cure the health problem.

Various conventional approaches for the rural health development implemented have mixed result. Hence, sociologists felt sustainable and culture specific health development model should be introduced. It is known that health seeking behaviour of a community involves both beliefs and practices about health and sickness. Hence indigenous knowledge must be the basis for any new health development programme focusing rural people. Normally these beliefs and practices are based on inherited and deep-rooted traditions. Probably these traditional based health behaviours are more prevalent in the rural area because a minimal influence of urbanisation education, including Illiteracy, lack of modern health facility, ignorance and many more factors.

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Evolving Perspectives on Intelligence

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ABSTRACT

Intelligence is one of the most highly debated topic. In psychology there is no standard definition of intelligence. Over the last 100 years some psychologists have suggested that intelligence is a single, general ability, others believe that it encompasses a wide variety of aptitudes, skills and talents. In the middle some psychologists even confirmed that, the intelligence quotient can be measured through psychometric techniques. As the controversy over how reliable the IQ tests are, how well these pen and paper measurements of IQ can be extrapolated to success in everyday life. Slowly evolution towards the development of more than one kind of intelligence i.e., the concept of Multiple Intelligences began. The view on human intelligence has broadened during the past 30 years. Various researchers from various fields from cognitive psychology to neurobiology have contributed to the theories that give explanation on the evolving perspectives of intelligence. In our paper we have attempted to portray the emerging perspectives of intelligences along with an account on the past in brief.

Keywords: Intelligence, Multiple Intelligence, Emotional Intelligence.

An electrocardiogram (ECG) strip with a grid background, showing a regular rhythm. The text is overlaid on the right side of the strip.

**EMERGING
PUBLIC HEALTH
ISSUES**

Editor

Dr. D.C. Nanjunda

TABLE 4
Comparison of energy intake and energy expenditure for different activities performed by rural adolescent girls in 900 minutes of time

RDA	13-15 years energy	Energy intake	R util. uses	Energy balance	RDA kcal	16-18 years energy	Energy intake	R value	Energy balance
2060 kcal	1532.36 ± 44.156	1429.98 ± 200.21	0.23	+102.28	2060	1956.62 ± 330.02	1964.8 ± 102.02	0.5307	0.84

*0.5% significant, **0.1% significant
Primary survey

CONCLUSION

Hence suitable intervention programmes and nutrition education, nutrition counselling centres, mothers should be given importance in preventing under nutrition and malnutrition in future coming children and mother, life cycle needs to be strengthened.

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Fake or Faith? A Study on Traditional Faith Healers in Rural South Karnataka

—Dr. D.C. Nanjunda

Abstract: Background—Faith healing is from time immemorial. It is of the opinion that the faith healings largely depends on the subject of the healing technique/s. In many societies traditional healers performs healing rights (faith healing) sometime as a family doctor also. Healers' here normally focus on the weak psychology of the patient. In most of the cases this job would be like a family occupation passing from generations. Traditional healers have got a holy position in the mindset of the village people. Objective—To study the murals opinion about faith healing and perception of the tradition and faith healers about their profession.

Methodology—This paper is based on a study conducted in rural parts of south India using focus group technique on different prospects of the traditional healing phenomenon and content analysis method.

Result—Usually traditional healers will be respected by everyone in the village. He/she will be honored on many occasions. Normally people do not want to cross his words/advice. Traditional healing normally would be a familial healing and its secret will not be leaked to anyone outside of his/her family.

Conclusion—Healers will try to convince the patients' that his/her illness has caused due to the supernatural/deity power only. Hence, only supernatural powers can cure or heal the illness through the healers only.

Keywords: Health, traditional, faith healers, illness, rural

BACKGROUND

Medicine men or the traditional healers' role in administrating or practicing ethno-medicine will be more vital in rural parts of the globe. Even though

the traditional healers are scientifically untrained they would normally have more knowledge about the local's concept on disease, illness and people's social psychology etc. Hence, some time they will have more successful healing rates. Also these healers are more informal, approachable and easily accessible and patients friendly. However, in modern medicine, patient-doctors relationship is quite formal, hierarchical and nowadays it has become more depersonalized. Qualifications to be a traditional healers or quacks need some sort of formal or informal training or strong family background. In some cases, more than two years of apprenticeship may be required. In a village side every therapist will be specialized in handling different types of illness and diseases. Women healers also can be seen who is specialized in solving women related disease in the rural areas. A religious leader like a priest, quack etc, also plays a significant role as faith healers. People believe the supernatural authority is bestowed upon him by a cult or organization. Rural folk normally believes a religious leader who receives power directly from the cosmological sources (Bhardwaj and Paul, 1986).

As we know some of the development activities in the rural area determine the economic status of the people it finally leads to have adopt a how changing socio-cultural pattern. This aspect also impact on the health system and health culture of that community. Traditional healers' or faith healing also plays a vital role in traditional rural settings. Hence this issues needs to be studied from the sociological view point since rural society is multicultural one and understanding socio-cultural and socio-economic conditions plays a vital role in framing locally suitable health care module led by the traditional healers. Experts felt practical level of the scientific study on the existing faith healing system will play a vital role in framing the culturally acceptable health care interventions for the rural people at the doorsteps at the affordable cost. (Bury, 1991).

Joshi (1986) has classified traditional healers found in the rural areas in the following five categories:

1. Diviner or Thantri / Va dya
2. Astrologer, Priest and the Healer
3. Pulse specialists and Herbalists
4. Midwife / Gynecic specialist

In rural parts people choose the healer based on the following parameters:

1. Caste background of the faith healer;
2. Cost he/she charges per case;

3. Friendly behavior of the faith healer;
4. The personal attention towards the patients;
5. His/her past experience;
6. Success rate of the healer

TRADITIONAL HEALERS

Dala (2007) writes "In most of the folk practices healers are mediators between the physical and the metaphysical. One can regularly find healers who are recognized for their ability to host a deity or spirit and under whose spell they acquire supernatural powers to manage the minds of their visitors and to heal them." (Dala, 2007)

Anthropologists and Medical sociologists have written largely on traditional healers. The majority of the writings are on the psycho-social role of the healers because they are specializing in psycho-pathological treatment. Experts have opined that traditional healers sometime manipulate current social symbols they can repair the broken social ties from the patient's point of view. Some time in a rural multi cultural society, caste of the patients and the caste of the healer also play a vital role in the broader social context. Some time patients belonging to the upper caste may ignore the healing skills of the Vidya belonging to the lower caste. (Turner, 1967)

Table 1
Types of Healers Commonly Found in Rural Settings

<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Indigenous <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Midwives • Shamans • Curers • Spiritualists • Witches • Sorcerers • Priests • Diviners • Herbalists • Bone setters • Massagers 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Other Medical Systems <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chinese medical system • Practitioners • Chemists/herbalists • Acupuncturists • Ayurvedic practitioners • Taoist priests • Pluralistic • Injectionists • Indigenous health workers • Western-trained-birth attendants
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(Source: Adnan Ali Hyder And Richard H. Morrow, from the book *Culture, Behaviour, and Health*, 2005)

TABLE 2
The Choice of Healer in Relation to Various Possible Characteristics
 (After Kroger, 1983)

Explanatory variables	Subject characteristics	Disorder characteristics	Service characteristics
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age • Sex • Marital status & position in household • Ethnicity • Formal education • Occupation • Resource (land, cash, etc) • Interaction with family, Community, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chronic or acute • Severe or trivial • Etiological model • Expected benefits from treatment • Psychosomatic vs somatic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessibility • Appeal (opinions and attitudes towards traditional and modern healers) • Acceptability • Quality • Communication • Cost 	

Source: Rapid Assessment of Health seeking behaviour in relation to STD SER/PRR/STD (GPA/WHO June 1995 (draft protocol))

INDEPENDENT VARIABLES

Characteristics of the subject

- Age, sex, status in the household, Household size, formal education, occupation,

Characteristics of the perceived illness

- Chronic or acute, severe or trivial, expected benefits of treatment, psychosomatic or somatic, aetiological model (natural or supernatural)

Characteristics of the health service

- Accessibility, acceptability, quality of care, cost of care

DEPENDENT VARIABLES

Figure 1: The Choice of Healer in Relation to Various Explanatory Variables
 (Source: Kroger, 1983)

Figure 2: Ritual Process Associated with Traditional Healers to Collect Medicinal Plants.

Source: Robin D Tribhuwan (1998), Medical world of the Tribes, (Discovery publisher, New Delhi)

Objectives and Methodology

1. To reveal the perceptions of the rural people about the traditional faith healers
2. To study about the opinion of faith healers towards traditional medical system

METHODOLOGY

Data collected conducting 10 focus group studies on the patients' and faith healers carefully selected using snowball sampling technique in two districts (Coorg and Mysore) of Karnataka

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This study has found different opinions about traditional and faith healers. Respondents have strong faith and respect on both traditional and faith healers. They are the valuable resources as primary health care provider and are readily accepted by the community too. In rural areas there are different healers like Priest, Shaman, Diviner, Herbalist, Bone setter, Midwife etc. These traditional healers play a powerful role in shaping health seeking process of the rural community. They are widely respected and believed by the respondents. Respondents opined they are skilled and experienced in the health care management of the community. Traditional healers are less researched and less exposed today. Healers' have different diagnostic techniques and therapeutic models also. In-depth interview with the traditional healers have found they have a variety of notions and concepts about health and illness. And traditional healers strongly believe diseases and illness are causes due to the humeral imbalance and also noted the numbers of traditional healer opined breaching taboo, angry deity and different pathogenic agents also cause diseases and illness for the human beings. The Reasons for conducting various health rituals, traditional healers opined this would be conducted to neutralize evil effects, pathogenic agents, recreation of disturbed cultural orders, bringing back humeral imbalance and the bodily equilibrium etc (Bullyya,2009).

This study has also found some specialist healers who have been mastered in a particular healing technique and these specialists treat a number of cases every day and charge much from the patients when compared to other type of healers. They are just like general practitioners (Just MBBS) and specialists (MD/MS) in Allopathic settings. Such specialists are very few in number in rural parts and having own healing model and techniques. These specialist healers will normally handle complex health issues and can give some instant relief for the patients. Once the patients' got cured the same patient gradually will act as a spokesmen to propoganda about him and his healing capacity to the other patients' and gradually it spreads to the nearby areas. Normally, traditional healers use a variety of healing techniques to cure health problems by listening illness narrations, studying the etiology, symptoms etc. Healers treat the patients using holy water, thread, chanting, feeding herbal juice, and medicines using animal and mineral extracts etc.

It is found that traditional healers normally diagnose the problem/s largely based on the external symptoms and the visible bodily changes and the body language of the patients. A healer normally uses the medicines which are extracted from the herbs, shrubs, leaves, roots available in that region. Healers administer the medicine based on the severity of the health problem

including the gender, age etc. If the problem is due to the humeral imbalance healers normally use the herbal extracts. If the illness/disease is due to an angry deity or spirits or sorcery they will perform the certain rituals including offerings to the deity or satisfying spirit in cash/kinds. In some cases, healers ask the patients' to wear certain holy threads until curing. Different healers use distinct methods in diagnosing, preventive measures and the therapeutic pluralism within an established pattern for the different health problems. Since the different specialist healers available in a given area sometimes they act as a complementary and some time as a hurdle to each other's therapeutic modes. Female traditional healers are particularly skilled in doing massage and delivers the babies also.

For certain illnesses rural community exclusively depends on the traditional healers irrespective of caste and class etc. For snake bite, child illness, bone setting, menses problems, and spermatorrhea all social groups belonging to the different castes and class seek the treatment from the local healers only. In fact, religion and caste "purity" do not seem to be an issue for the patients' to get treatment from any healer. Consultation of Muslim healers does exist by the Hindu patients' and vice versa in many cases. The sick person belonging to the upper caste frequently approaches and receives the treatment from the lower caste healers belong to the lower caste and vice versa if there is no other way. Some healers belong to the lower caste and vice versa if there is no other way. Some time it creates caste clashes among upper, low caste and ethnic minorities in rural parts. Women patients' always prefers to consult a lady traditional healer with whom they can communicate with ease. To get lady healers they are ready to travel distant places.

Female traditional healers (specialists) have a sex specific role. They are generally confined to the lower castes, especially the black smith caste. Female traditional healers are also skilled in handling displaced women, abdomen, menstrual problems etc. The native theory explains infertility is caused due to the dislocated abdomen. Navel dislocation is another sphere of the female specialists. The abdominal cramps are believed to be caused due to stretch in the abdomen and the female specialists have the ability to stretch these conditions by their massage therapy. The actual practice of a female specialist is very stylish; she has a working knowledge of the pulse through which she diagnoses the problems of the humeral imbalance in the body. The massage involves treatment by stroking, pressing, tapping and kneading (rub) the affected parts. They felt women need to stay out of home during menstrual period.

Healers are also consulted for the certain social problems for the solutions. For instance, the upper class respondents consult local healer about their

children unemployment problems, low level or poor crops in their field, childlessness, marriage issues, regular quarrel in the family etc. some time poor people consult the healers to get a solution for the economic hardships. This indicates that traditional healers act as life-mediators for the local communities in venturing and addressing 'uncertainty' in their life situations.

Regarding the medical pluralism, healers opined it is a good phenomenon and it gives more opportunities for the poor patients'. They promptly opined chances of healing are more in cases of availability of more than one type of medical care system in a given area. Also they opined emerging of fake healers also a big problem in the name of medical pluralism. Some of the healers feared the medical pluralism will create a kind of confusion and using more than one type of medicine may cause some kind of side effects to the patient. Also they admit the traditional healers use some sort of the pluralistic therapy to cure the patients' health issues. Some of the healers also opined Folk medicine, Ayurvedic and Homeopathy are the best medicines for any kind of health problems. Regarding degeneration of traditional healing system, they opined domination of the western medicine is the main reason. And also they admitted due to the slow healing nature of the folk medicines, some time patients does not like it. Due to the strong medical pluralism, today the rural people are showing must interest about the medicinal care which has the more rapid healing power. However few healers confident that since, people are aware of the importance of the traditional medicines, this medicine would not degenerate so easily. They felt strong Gov't support is required for the sustainability of the traditional medicines in the rural society.

Regarding scientific training for the traditional healers the noted percentages of them agreed to get a scientific training. While the majority of them denied getting any sort of training and they claimed that they have the mastery of the knowledge about all the diseases and 29% of them opined any scientific training would be kind of breaching ethics and they fear professional sanctity will spoil. Regarding the opinion about the western medicine they felt this health system has more side effects and poor people cannot afford/accesses it. Also they opined all types of the disease/illness cannot be cured in the western medical system and the western medicine is preferable for the certain cases only. It is found that the traditional healers have a reasonable appreciation towards the western medicine in the mind but they are orally expressing negative opinion about the allopathic system.

Surprisingly it is noted that some traditional healers depends on clinical establishment of a disease based on that only they will treat the patients'. Further, in-depth study has revealed that healers are aware indigenous

medicines are not very safe though it is being used form the generations. Indirectly they admitted that the folk medicines are not standardized and not so safe. However they opined when compared to the western medicine, the folk medicines are the safe. They argue that so-far they never come across any safety complaints from the patients'. However, it is found that the usage of raw herbal juice, minerals and animal extracts leaves side effects on the patients' in the long run as opined by the some traditional healers. Hence we can say rural patients' knowingly or unknowingly taking toxic materials in the name of folk medicinal system.

CONCLUSION

The strong beliefs on faith of the respondents' regarding healing technique do matter a lot. Also role of the family members, village elders, and others plays a vital role in rural health care seeking behavior. Further, a particular type of medical assistance within the given context of medical pluralism including hakims local traditional healers, nomadic vaidy's Ayurvedic and modern allopathic counts a lot. It is found that medical practice among rural respondents' is highly pluralistic. Experts opined that there is a dearth need of new sociological studies about dynamics of changing rural health culture focusing philosophy system of medicine and faith healings.

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ACFT • BANGALORE

VOI, JUNE 8 • NUMBER 3 • JUL - SEPT 2015
ISSN: 0974-1143 • CODEN: AAJMBC

Al Ameen Journal of Medical Sciences

Al Ameen Medical College
Bijapur- 586108, Karnataka, India

<http://ajms.alameenmedical.org>

minor problem) patient's personal experience/narrations may not same as the illness experiences of a patient having a long term health issues. Hence, it is necessary to focus on 'patients life's before illness, during the stage of illness and after the illness got medically cured'. This helps us in the social construction of illness based on patients' experiences in a given society. Also it helps us to know how the different components of the society helped him/her to come out of illness stage soon. During the stage of illness patients' will be normally worried about their personal and social relationships and other day to day activities which could not be performed well. Sometime during the stage of illness patients will review their previous life and in some cases it may create new illness identification (example: patients under dialysis) also [8].

It also focuses how health culture and behavior varies based on the socio-economic status of the community. Sociological concept about illness gives a fair idea how external determinants causes health problem to an individual and how he/she responds to it in a given social context. It is a well known truth that the influence of socio-cultural factors varies across the globe. Normally these social factors demonstrated through various discourses on important diseases/illness and its outbreak in a specific geographical area. Basically experts' focus on the issues comprising society and medicine, socioeconomic setup, general cultural issues which are geographically specific while studying specific health culture of a community. Sometime a common disease may affect the larger population whereas a major disease may affect smaller population only. Medical anthropologists basically studies about these discrepancies [9].

In rural areas, incapacitation/absence from work is the general index of an illness. Even though the basic concept of the illness changes from caste to caste a person will be declared as a diseased if he/she could not perform day to day work. They expect a healthy person should work normally without having any problem. Consequently, sometime if people have mild fever, head ache, BP, depression, giddiness etc, will not be considered as a part of disease/ illness because these symptoms will not hamper their normal routine day to day work. Usually peoples don't bother for these simple health issues. Hence,

sociologist has concluded that in rural areas illness is more related to 'functional rather than clinical or biological'.

Delton's (1970) Model as to How People Perceive Illness.

	Clinically	
Clinically Ill	D	C
Clinically Ill	B	A

- *Category - A:* People think that they are not ill both culturally and clinically;
- *Category - B:* People think that they are not culturally ill but are clinically ill;
- *Category - C:* People think that they are culturally ill but not clinically;
- *Category - D:* People think that they are ill both culturally and clinically.

It is opined that response to any type of illness by a patient will be mainly depends on how he/she perceives/ belief concerning health and illness. In the next stage, he/she seeks assistance from various social components (including, friends, relatives, people who suffered from the same health problems previously....etc) to get a proper outlet to come out from the current health problem.

Also medical anthropologists feared during this entire process of seeking assistances make the delay in getting proper treatment in time and patient' will get suffer [9]. It is found that the communities' reaction to symptoms is dependent on their cultural values / beliefs concerning health. That is, their perception of what is 'normal'. Therefore, the choice to seek proper medical help was either promoted or delayed by various social factors. Zola's (1973) model identified five diverse types of occurrence which 'triggered' the judgment to seek medical care, incidents which intimidate people's philosophy of customariness" [10].

As new medical health care facilities are being discovered, health status of the underserved communities across the world has started considerably improving. Gradual changes in the socio economic status of the people also led to have the quality medical care. Diagnose and treatment also started to affect positively on the health care seeking behavior of the

community. Now rural people are showing much interest to adopt modern health care facilities whereas certain sections are not yet. This change in the health culture of the community causes the issue of health and illness within given societal life to be highly volatile in definition. Hence studying health and illness from the sociological point of view continuously needs to be updated as societies are dynamic in nature [11].

It is generally opined that society having poor health will tolerate high inequality in every aspect including health care. Differences in health practices between various social groups would be more vital for sociological analyses. Even in the same society, disparities in health status and health behavior can be seen among different social classes/castes. The wide income gap, material deprivation and psychological issues invariably effects on health and illness of an individual/community in a society. Wide gap between rich and poor people results in low social cohesion which finally affects the health of all members. It is found that vital differences in case of mortality and morbidity continuously increasing between low income groups and the elites of the society. However the research is on the way to find out how poverty and deprivation effects on general health issues and behavior among the members of developing societies [12].

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Conclusion

The thoughts of illness and health are socially constructed inside each society of every culture. These widespread languages cover up a varied choice of connotations for which there has been no universal conformity over their denotations. The main role of social, cultural, psychological, family relationship, social capital social network, epidemiology and other issues plays vital role in the etiology of disease and illness. Current theories of health and illness are relatively based on the various perspectives of humoral imbalance. Certain Sociologists argues illness causes due to the problems in case of social relationships in the changing scenario [13].

Also, they argue that illness causes due to the broken relationships between the human beings and the eco-system. Again, certain sociologist's proposed their theories about illness and diseases based on natural and super natural causations. Theories of natural causation focus on disturbance of health as a physiological consequences including infection, germs, mental trauma [14]. Hence Health and illness are socially constructed and cannot be considered as a separate entity from other elements of any given society for any time.

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ISSN 0975-9727

Vol 8 | Issue 1 | January-June 2017

Muller Journal of Medical Sciences and Research

Official Publication of Father Muller Charitable Institutions
www.mjmsr.net

Medknow

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Beyond the rational choice: The social dynamics of the changing nature of the rural people's health concept

Devaajna Chinnappa Nanjunda Sr

ABSTRACT

Culture creates an exclusive prototype of the beliefs and perceptions as to what "health" or "illness" actually means. Health culture is the basis for health-seeking and health-promoting behavior. There are institutional arrangements within which health behavior occurs and the impacts of socioeconomic, political, and physical background for their specific health beliefs and health institutions counts a lot. Further, this prototype of beliefs mainly influences how symptoms are documented, to what they are accredited, and how they are interpreted and how it also affects how and when modern traditional health services are sought by the people. Cultural differences in the recognition and interpretation of symptoms and in the use of health services are the topic of wealthy literature. This paper is based on the author's fieldwork experiences in different occasions about the various cultural aspects of the rural health-care issues in southern Karnataka, India. The fieldwork was done in certain rural parts of Karnataka, South India, using participant observation and data also synthesized using content analysis technique. It concludes that cultural differences among the rural people seeking health care are related to the social structures and relationships and the quantity of belief/disbelief in concerning traditional or Western medical care system. We found that the impediment in seeking suitable and timely health care were indifferently found among the individuals belonging to the various sociocultural groups characterized by the cultural exceptionality and customary and family authority.

Key Words: Concept, health, illness, medicine, rural

Introduction

All the rural areas are unique with extensive geographic and economic variations when compared to the urban areas. However, the rural populations are frequently characterized as follows:

1. Being innocent and less educated;
2. Living in the most remote areas;
3. More likely to be covered by unhygienic environment;
4. Having high rates of poverty, chronic diseases, and deaths from unintentional injuries and motor vehicle accidents;
5. Having no or little access to transportation; and
6. Having limited economic diversity.

All of these issues create big challenges and opportunities to improve the health of those living in the rural parts/ marginal sections and they play a role in understanding

some of the underlying causes associated with the issues related to the rural health workforce, health services, and special populations.^[1]

It is found that the majority of the rural people believe in the following causes of ill health:

1. Displeasure of supernatural entities,
2. Breach of taboos,

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How to cite this article: Nanjunda DC. Beyond the rational choice: The social dynamics of the changing nature of the rural people's health concept. Muller J Med Sci Res 2017;8:1-5.

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DOI:

10.4103/0975-9727.199368

3. Nonfulfillment of obligations toward their gods,
4. Influence of occultism, and
5. Environmental and physical ones.

Further, nutritional deficiencies are more in young rural children and reproductive health care is also poor. The health of the rural people is prejudiced by a number of factors such as adequate food, housing, sanitation, healthy lifestyles, protection against environmental hazards and communicable diseases. Experts have identified variety of issues related to rural people's health that are as follows:

1. Food habits and environment,
2. Medicine and community (modern),
3. Fertility and mortality,
4. Interaction of traditional and modern systems of medicine at various levels; and
5. Reasons for nonadoption of modern practices.^[2,3]

It is a well-known truth that infectious diseases are common among the people in various rural parts of the country because of their habitation in remote areas and other hygiene-related reasons. Most of the rural people as studied by the anthropologists/sociologists and nongovernment organizations appear to have a few common traditional practices regarding maternal and childcare that cause child mortality in the future. Among most of the rural people, it was found that gastrointestinal disorders, particularly dysentery and parasitic infection, are very common leading to the morbidity and malnutrition, diarrhea, dysentery, skin diseases, and respiratory diseases.^[9] Further, nutritional problems, such as anemia, food taboos, wrong infant feeding practices, increasing postpartum mortality, neonatal mortality, postnatal mortality, perinatal mortality, poor life expectancy, are some of the vital health issues and people still believe that all these are caused due to various nonmedical factors such as supernatural powers.^[4]

Materials and Methods

This study had a main objective to find out the rural peoples' changing health concepts in recent days. The fieldwork was done in certain rural parts of the Karnataka state, South India, using participant observation and data are also synthesized using the content analysis technique. Relevant data have been extracted from various literature and synthesized through a narrative review that included descriptive characteristics.

Socioeconomic status (SES) plays a vital role as one of the major determinants of health of any community including health care, environmental exposure, and

health behavior. In addition, constant pressure connected with the lesser SES may also augment the morbidity and mortality as found in a few studies.^[4,5] Reducing the socioeconomic disparities among various social groups in health-care issue require policy an initiative addressing the components of SES focusing income, education, and occupation etc. Also the suitable channel by how these issues affect the health behavior needs to be studied deeply. One can say that today health-seeking behavior of majority of the rural people is greatly governed by the existing cultural values, beliefs, and traditions. However, it is open for the gradual change because of different kinds of external interventions such as media. Contrary to changes, in health-seeking behavior patterns of the rural people, one also can notice tremendous changes, which have occurred with respect to philosophy, knowledge, and practices of indigenous systems, such as ayurveda, homeopathy, allopathic, in recent days.^[9]

However, it becomes an important issue to work on problems of rural people's health because it differs from a particular area to another area owing to their geographical location, historical background, and processes of social change. Geographical isolation and limited interactions with other communities have become obstacle to know the degree of prevalence of HIV/AIDS among rural communities. However, some studies have shown that rural people are emerging as a high-risk group for human immunodeficiency virus infection/acquired immune deficiency syndrome (HIV/AIDS) while they migrate driven by displacement for employment opportunities. Their study have pointed out that the differences between the points of view of the physicians and the village folk with regard to the theory of etiology, techniques of curing, and conceptions of the roles of the physicians resulted in misunderstanding between the physician and the client.^[6,7]

A study done in a village named Kishan Garhi in Aligarh district of Uttar Pradesh (India) found that there are vital problems of introducing the Western medicine in an Indian village community. Experts have shown that how the contracts and conflicts between the roles assumed by the indigenous and Western medicinal practitioners resulted in obstacles to the acceptability of the Western medicine.^[7] Medical sociologists have tried to distinguish between two types of social and natural factors that affect the health status of any community's as factors that directly affect the health of the community. Factors (a) that directly affect the health of the community because of certain customs, practices, beliefs values, religious taboos etc., create an environment that helps in the spread or control of certain disease and b) Factors that indirectly affect the health of the community as they are

related to the problem of medical care to the sick and the invalid^[8,9] Some experts have done an extensive study on sickness, healing, and culture among certain Indian tribes. They have classified illness into four categories as follows:

1. Illness caused by supernatural power,
2. Illness due to disturbance of social system,
3. Illness due to angry of spirits and they have felt that rural people are the strongest believers in the magico-religious type of treatment.^[10]

A few experts have opined that the diagnose and treatment of disease lie in the cognitive domain of culture of any particular community. Each and every culture has its own interpretations toward health illness. However, due to acculturation, the trend of health culture keeps changing. A unique study done in a village of Rajasthan has revealed that the health belief system of the rural people is very deep-rooted in their lives controlling certain rules of conduct of health behavior. A study done in Nainital district (Uttarakhand) has found that different communities in a village follow different indigenous medicines to cure different diseases. Their health culture seems to be interwoven with their day-to-day lifestyle. Their health culture is influenced by their inherited social and cultural background.^[11,12]

Health Perception of the Rural People

Right from the history, sociologists are attempting to find out how social and cultural factors influence understanding of illness and diseases, people's responses to illness and its relevance in the health-care policies. Sociologists are also probing how social, economic, and cultural factors impact the choice of different health-seeking behaviors. Medical sociologists and anthropologists have given a wide range of findings on health and illness based on the various empirical studies conducted in the different rural settings across the globe. Particularly, sociologists have written more on the sick role, the social construction of health and illness, influence of the local culture and tradition in defining and treating diseases, and how health and illness concept may affect the different segments of the society.

A number of child health and reproductive studies have revealed that rural people's health seeking behavior and other issues have found that traditional beliefs and values play an important role in determining the reproductive health-seeking behavior of a woman. This is more so in the case of adolescent women who do not have any autonomy in decision-making with regard to even her own health care. "It is not enough to educate adolescent women as they do not have any decision

making authority. The target should be their parents and elders in the society who are required to be educated and made aware about these issues." Even adolescent women also suggested that the health program should target on real decision-makers such as husbands and mothers-in-law in a household.^[13] Next, knowledge and awareness regarding source of health care is also a hindrance in seeking health care. Most of the adolescent women reported that they did not seek reproductive health services due to the lack of money and family support. Moreover, daughters-in-laws get least priority in the household with regard to health care especially in rural areas. The providers were also of the opinion that economic factors are also a factor because of which a woman shows delay in seeking any urgent medical treatment. In addition, in rural parts an adolescent women singly cannot visit a hospital and always need of having the male relatives or husband's accompaniment that is also a causative factor in delaying the required medical treatment.^[14,15]

Undernutrition and childhood mortality have become serious problems for the rural children. It is found that their social-cultural background, health, behavior, and health culture dynamics play a significant role as vital determinants of the health status of a particular community. Hence, undernutrition and childhood mortality are more common in the rural areas.^[16] The World Health Organization (WHO) report (1985) has found that 57% of the death of under-five children in the developing countries are accompanied by undernutrition thereby low weight for their age. For this issue, anthropologists have attributed that the development of health culture of the rural environment should be examined as a subcultural complex of the entire way of life stressing food culture. There are a number of forces percolated from the larger socioeconomic environment and directed through the attributer of historical, social, and political dimension to the development of the pattern of their health culture in the given rural settings. Under-five children need good nutritional diet that is scanty in many rural settings in the country and this causes mortality and morbidity among rural population.^[17]

Further, experts have opined that the poor health outcome of the rural community including the children need to be read within the context of rapid urbanization, focusing on the factors such as poor health infrastructure and costly treatment. However, in a multicultural society, rural childhood mortality in India cannot be analyzed in a contextual vacuum. Instead, they need to be looked at in the light of larger socioeconomic changes experienced by the rural community over the period of time. Till now, various governments have implemented many programs

to improve the nutritional status of the preschool children through various innovative schemes. Corers of money have been spent. Still the country experiences severe rural child mortality issues.^[18] Health experts opined that lack of good primary health care, perceived and personal risks, lack of awareness have lead in failing health improvement programs. Also, it is found that traditional health-seeking behavior toward certain diseases severally hampering their health status. It is found that the prevalence of respiratory tract infection, anemia, typhoid, and deficiency of vitamin A and B are more common and it might be due to their food culture. Poor household ecology, personal habits, cultural practices, traditional beliefs, child delivery system, and childrearing and breast-feeding also place a vital role.^[19]

As India strives toward becoming a more egalitarian society, the health of a marginalized section of the society has become a significant issue and the lack of health education become a serious factor in reaching its goal. Some noted that developmental agencies and NGOs have developed the concept of innovative Health Modernity' to be implemented in the rural areas of Karnataka, India. The problems of accessibility, remoteness, and poor transport system in the rural areas are the most common problems to be faced by the health workers. It is because of difficult terrain and sparsely distributed rural population in forests and hilly regions. Next, the lack of appropriate man power policy, inadequate funding mobilization, lack of government support, absence of proper and suitable approaches, and lack of trained and committed staff also play a vital role in the accomplishment of the NGOs' interventions. Sometimes services will not be client friendly in terms of timing and cultural barriers, inhibiting utilization etc. Noninvolvement of rural people and weak monitoring and supervision systems also count.^[20]

Certain studies have suggested that the lack of an optimal utilization of health services by the rural people may be due to a variety of reasons. Some services are inappropriately used, whereas others, such as the preventive health programs, are underutilized due to the lack of awareness. In addition, one of the main problems identified with the rural people was communication difficulty to interact with external forces. Sociologists said what is required to improve the awareness about basic health concepts of rurals is culturally appropriate health instructions, better and easily accessible medical services with a sympathetic, and understanding attitude of the doctors and health staff.^[21] It expressed by the experts that the effects of health-care interventions of various health schemes should not be limited to the improvements of rural people's health status. The interventions should have a broader intention,

such as empowerment of rural beneficiaries to get more control over health determinants, health behavior and to find out their own solution/s for their health dilemma and the solidarity with vulnerable segments of that population. It is required for a holistic way of health development and system management. In general, this suggests that the development of socioeconomic status plays a vital role assuming significance for the best utilization of the services and the strategy by the targeted people. It has been pragmatic that though various India governments have done tremendous efforts to set up a vast system of health network across the country in remote areas of the country health infrastructure is declining due to lack of strong political will, negligence, corruption, less peoples' participation etc.^[22]

Conclusion

Despite the availability of modern preventive and curative medicine, the health-care delivery services in several rural areas are still poor and largely unscientific. Within the current comprehensive health intervention services, there has been no attempt to understand health culture as a subculture complex. But this is precisely the perspective necessary to develop a model of a culturally suited health-care delivery system specifically designed for the rural people of the country. Experts have lamented on the dearth of microlevel data among such rural populations and have suggested that an effective solution to the health-related problems of rural society must situate the problem within the larger contexts of changing health culture. The aim of the current research study was to understand how different forces and approaches to health culture are determined in the larger and changing socioeconomic conditions of the rural people.

Financial Support and Sponsorship

Nil.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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● Volume 2, No. 2, July-December 2015

● Print · ISSN : 2322-0414

● Online · ISSN : 2322-0422

Annals of Health and Health Sciences

Indian Journals.com
A Product of Diva Enterprises Pvt. Ltd.

Review Article

Changing Framework of Sociology of Health and Treatment: Few Retrospections

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ABSTRACT

The sociology of health and illness has a long history. Over the last 100 years, many concepts, theories, findings have been explored for the better understanding of health behaviour of human beings and the role of the society. Majority of the theories and approaches relating to the health and illness have been originally propounded by the Western sociologists only. Even today researchers in developing countries are heavily depending on the Western theories to explain health culture and behaviour of the rural community. In developing countries social class, caste, gender and others play a vital role in accessing suitable healthcare facilities. More than these, the underlying social, political and economic forces are also counting a lot. It is found that sociology of health and illness significantly helps us in better understanding of people's concepts about onset of various diseases and its cure in a cross-cultural framework. This paper gives a solid platform to discuss about changing phenomenon of sociology of medicine in India.

Keywords: Sociology, Health, Illness, Globalisation, Rural Caste, Medicalisation

INTRODUCTION

Like economy, religion and politics health and illness are the part and parcel of any society. In sociology, the relationship among magic, religion and medicines has been discussed deeply. Indian sociologists have done in-depth study of the social character of health and sickness. Truly speaking, the field of medicine comprises a number of individuals interacting with each other which is influenced by the local culture and society. In this way, concept of health, illness and medicine will be largely influenced by the particular type of culture. Hence health and illness should be studied in a holistic way from the lens of socio-cultural factors. Each and every individual will develop health-seeking behaviour or health-care-seeking behaviour over the period of time. Sometime the health-seeking behaviour may be similar or different. In this background, Indian sociologists have tried to study the social dimension of health and illness and response of the society.

In Indian society, people's concept about health and illness varies from culture to culture, caste to caste, class to class and one geographical area to another. In rural area, people will normally presume that illness may be due to angry deity or cosmological effects because of sins and crimes committed in the life. Sometime people in rural part will connect their health problems in the current birth might be due to the sins of the previous life. For example, if a person is suffering from blood-related problems, people think that person might have killed a holy cow in the previous life. Also sometime rural people think diseases are normally due to some internal factors that is three humours (tri-dosh) of the human body: air, bile and phlegm (vaata/pitta/khata). Sociological studies conducted in many rural parts of the country have generalised that rural people normally classify diseases or illness into two categories, they are

1. Illness which can be curable by the local healers (folk medicine)

2. Illness which can be cured by the western medicine.

This classification will be based on the previous experience of the patient or advice given by the family or village elders from time to time. Some noted studies in rural parts of India and narrated about people believing in health and illness. People were really against the Western theories of etiology and curing techniques because of a strong belief in local health culture⁶¹. Though India is a heterogeneous-cultural society, there are certain elements which are common in all types of health culture. This is because of exchange of certain health elements over the period of time between different cultures for the reason of Sanskritisation. Universalisation and transfer from one society to another. Sometime due to the uneven spread of culture, certain traditions and customs can be seen across the country and sometimes only in a certain specific geographical area. This is also applicable to health culture.

Normally in the rural area, diagnosis of any health disorders would take place initially at the family level. Before visiting the healer, people in rural parts usually practice certain home treatments. Elder people in a particular family will extend their opinions, suggestions and the possible healing treatment for the illness or disease of the family members. Thereafter, it will be cross-checked with the other experienced people of the village or friends or relatives through their own social network. In many parts of the rural areas, healing approach or theory will be largely decided based on the collective opinion⁶². If it doesn't work then they will visit local healers to get rid of his/her health problem. In rural areas, we can see some local specialists who are well experienced in curing certain disorders. These local healers use different system medicines to cure the problem. Sometime this would be monopolised by some families belonging to the higher caste.

Certain studies conducted in rural areas have provided some valuable notions about the illness ideology of the Indian rural folk. Sometime illness will be handled in non-magical and non-religious way because diagnosing and curing of the various illnesses differ from culture to culture. People would believe that shamans or priests only can interpret the supernatural phenomena. Sometime rationale and his treatment approach must be suitable to the cultural

Even today, established contrasts and conflicts exist between the local and the Western medical system in rural settings. Experts opined rural India need medicinal system having the best understanding of social life of the Indian villages. Also, it is found that in rural settings doctor and his treatment approach must be suitable to the cultural

background of the patient. Introducing any new medical system should be in a position to meet the cultural expectations of the rural patients. Since the Indian villagers are more conservative in nature, emerging medical pluralism needs to focus on social organisation and the institutions in the rural settings.

RELIGION, CASTE AND THE MEDICINE

It is rightly recognised that health is not the restricted sphere of medical science, because each and every health culture, irrespective of its simplicity and complexity, has its own beliefs and practices relating to diseases. No culture works in a worthless fashion in its treatment of diseases⁶³.

Every culture evolves its own classification and structure of medicine in order to treat diseases in its own way. Thus, treatment of disease may differ among various social groups. To comprehend health and health-related problems in an accurate viewpoint, it is extremely significant to think the socio-cultural factors surrounding the health issues. This is an extra relevant factor in the rural areas. Studies conducted on sociology of health and illness in India have used an existing social structure as the basic unit for the reference. Caste and class will play few specific roles, and in rural area sometime people belonging to the higher caste will be the power centric and even they can control the money flow. Even though the Western medical system has an edge over the traditional once, its success depends on how good it gets a reliable space 'between the realm of outsider and the inner realm of kinship'⁶⁴.

Caste and religion has close similar/dissimilar associations in using specific/different kinds of medical system in rural settings. Also few studies have shown religion has no connection in using specific type of medicinal system. In one study, the author has opined the usage of Unani system which is quite universal in Kerala, whereas people belonging to other religion in Uttar Pradesh and other states are sparingly using Unani in all walks of life. Siddha system is relatively rare among Muslims and Christen where it is quite common in case of low caste Hindus especially among tribal people. Faith healing is common with the Hindus and Muslims and most uncommon among the Christens. It raises some important question regarding

the relationship between religious background and usages of specific type of medicine available in the society⁶⁵. Ayurvedic is one of the oldest systems, and it is more prevalent among all the religions. It is found that in some parts of the world, people would like to differentiate between the religion and medicine based on the procedure involved in the curing sessions. Otherwise, any identification of any types of medical system would lead to the communal issue.

It is opined, caste and medicine relationships especially in post-industrial society are a significant sociological issue. Certain castes in rural areas have dominated on traditional medicines. It has become a family business. Also it is found that certain traditional healers would like to extend the treatment only for the patients belonging to his/her community only. It is opined that in British regime, traditional medicinal system was an important tool for the caste mobilisation in rural parts. It is felt that caste comparison and caste-based treatment have been plagued in traditional medicine system in rural parts of the country today. It is also found, because of caste and class conflicts and medicalisation, socially excluded communities are suffering a lot in rural parts of the country⁶⁶.

Sociologists from the long back are showing interest in studying between different segmentation of the society and emerging medicines. Also sociologists are doing some comparative studies between medical pluralism among various castes and ethnicity also acts as a strong indicator/parameter in evaluating health inequalities. It is also found, each and every caste in India has its own health culture, tradition, ritual and diet in a given society. Also, it is noted in a multi-caste society that health culture and health-seeking behaviours vary significantly under the changing social system due to various external factors. Lower caste people mostly prefer only traditional medical care for any health problems, whereas higher caste people will opt quality medicines. Their economic conditions also play a vital role too⁶⁷.

In rural areas, each and every caste has its own healer some time, and the caste factor of a local healer would be a significant issue even today. Caste-based medical skills are also an important issue for the debate. Though female traditional healers are available in every society, they are not getting enough importance. Next, it is opined

that religious/caste-based offers will play a vital role in meaning positive and mental health in the area of onset of a disease, cure and general well-being. These authors say some religion and caste-based health practices will be used in the psycho-biological and in cultural healing practices in many rural parts of the country.¹¹⁰

MEDICAL KNOWLEDGE AND POWER

Crisson (2007) writes 'Power is essentially relational rather than something that is possessed by individual doctors or the medical profession as a part of social group'¹¹¹

The development of medical knowledge has a long history. Bio-medical science helps us to reveal cause and affect issues with special reference to health and illness. The scientific understanding of health and illness can only be applied through material practices. Medical knowledge has evolved as an organisational system of formal health care system in this universe. This formal health care system through material practices has become socially embedded now. Medical knowledge, education and power are the core parts of modern healthcare system. Earlier, experts were used to define the medical knowledge as 'Medical Cosmologies'. This itself shows that medicine has a close relationship with society or the part and parcel of the society. The evolution of medical knowledge has its roots within societal domain. Medical knowledge is composed of both science and social spheres. Before the industrialisation, doctors were used to judge sick person based on personal attributes of the patient¹¹². Institutional (hospital) based medical system developed in association with the continues phase of social changes. Medical knowledge evolved along with industrialisation, urbanisation, capitalist society and so on. Along with this, doctor and patient balance of power begins to change. Medical knowledge gradually has started to pass from patients to doctors.

New medical discoveries and improvised treatment started to emerge. In 1977, an expert coined the term 'Clinical Gaze'. Also he showed an importance of social relationship of medical knowledge between the physicians and the patients¹¹³. Power is a kind of an approach or discursive practices which is the core part of emerging or social systems. Power exists at all level which controls

the different segments of the society including the health issue. In the case of medicine, power is nothing but scientific knowledge associated with modern medical health care systems including hospitals, physicians, medicines and so on. Since any health care system needs to work within the society this is often referred as bio-medical discourses. Power and knowledge are the most vital for both development of new health care system and its sustainability in the society.

It has opined, understating the traditional medical system may not promote bio-medical therapy in rural areas all of a sudden. We cannot just overlook into the efficacy of traditional medicine because it is being used by the people over the centuries. Rapid expansion and promotion of the medical system and knowledge could not affect the popularity and avoiding in using traditional medicines. She opined, experts should work on reducing complexities and problems involved in using bio-medical system. Normally, rural folk does not want any new medical system to be encroached into their traditional health culture. Any new medical system should commensurate with their socio-cultural systems. There must be an understanding of the diverse cultural traditions in medicines and health to any sociologists who would like to work in this field focusing the rural folk¹¹⁴.

MEDICALISATION

It is nothing but an expansion of medical jurisdiction in the areas normally thought to non-medical. Defining the term medicalisation is quite complex because we cannot clearly separate medical from non-medical domains from the societal perspective. Because there are so many factors which affect separately on both medical and non-medical domains including power and knowledge, professional objectives, political economy, socio-cultural issues, patients' interest and so on. It is opined that 'day-by-day more and more segmentation of human life has been brought into the bio-medical influence'. The concept of medicalisation reflects both interactions and Marxist approach focusing on health and illness. It is an extended part of social domain of medicine¹¹⁵.

It is opined that medicalisation has undermined people's ability to take care of their own health, and medicalisation has dual roles to play:

Changing Framework of Sociology of Health and Treatment. Few Retrospections

1. It discloses and eradicates diseases.
2. It negotiates diseases into sickness.

It is found that establishing what is medical and non-medical will be the base for medicalisation and is the result of the functional connections between curing diseases and the function performed by the sick role. Sickness according to person is a social fact between physician and the patient corresponding to their wider social roles¹¹⁶.

An expert has opined that medicine acts 'as a tool to control the society and medicine is a vital agency or force in medicalising society'. Medicine has become legitimate control over people's health. Sometime medicine expands its influence unnecessarily even on healthier individuals too. It is found that 'political aspects act as a powerful process in society taking forward the expansion of medicalisation process rapidly'. It is observed that 'new medicine is basically capital oriented forming the basis of modern society and which is narrowing down the definition of health and illness'. Medicalisation has its roots in the sick role. It is driven largely by the social control aspirations having implications on day-to-day life of an individual. Medicalisation is a kind of social construction¹¹⁶. Indeed, not only medicine, however, sociology of medicine also produces medicalisation thought:

- a. It produces knowledge about medicine.
- b. Indirectly expands the nature of medicalisation.

It is generally opined that social construction is the core part to reveal the role of medicine in the medicalisation of society. The social construction process moves through the sociological frame of references. Indirectly, sociological components of medicine are playing a vital role in various social constructions of medicalisation. Today, the medicalisation has expanded to cover bio-technology, consumers and the insurance sector also. At present, commercial domain of medicine is fast expanding. Now-a-days every human problem is being considered as a medical problem and is trying to solve it medically only. Sociologists are now focusing on how a disease normally develops, considers medically valid and treats the patients accordingly.

Some of the natural phenomena's which are common in

the human life are also being labelled as medically valid for some type of treatments¹¹⁷. Sometime problems in human relations will also be treated medically¹¹⁸. It seems that it has become a tradition that human problems are being treated scientifically rather than addressing the real underlying socio-culture cause for the actual problem. On the other hand, it is found that medicalisation plays a vital role in providing advanced and scientific health care system. Some sociologists opined, lay knowledge about illness/disease may decrease the relationship between doctors and patients, and thereby medicalisation expands in the society rapidly. The processes of medicalisation are of vital issue to be debated in a new health care sector focusing on rural folks¹¹⁷.

GLOBALISATIONS AND HEALTH

Globalisation has spread its tentacles everywhere. It has not even left the health sector. As globalisation intensifies, new medical technologies and new disease are emerging which is a major challenge to the health care system today. It has led to new paradigm called 'Development of Diseases'. Due to the socio-economic development process, day-by-day various types of the disease are emerging, mainly due to the changes in ecology, environment, changing life style and so on. In this context, we also should note that transferring Western bio-medicines care system to the non-Western traditional area is a vital change due to the rapid globalisation, privatisation and liberalisations focusing on rural people. Hence, today we can witness for the rapid medical pluralism in each and every country as new drugs are being developed, and new diseases are also emerging simultaneously.

It is also noted that globalisation is the major responsible in creating awareness about medical education and more improved health behaviour in any society. Today, people are largely using over the counter medicine (without prescription by the doctor) as a part of self-medication. Biologists opined that today new drug-resistant diseases are emerging like mushrooms. Because of knowledge explosion in medical science, the lay concept about health and illness is also changing rapidly. Both formal and informal medical care institutions are rapidly emerging in the society. Today, people can choose any medical caring system to prevent any type of health problems¹¹⁸.

A lot of changes have also occurred in the basic theory of illness ideology and sick role because of the availability of speedy healing techniques/treatments. The significance of the 'sick role' has also been diluted because of globalisations. Globalisation has affected even on the concept of traditional or folk medicine today. Today public health communication has been effective due to the availability of new and upcoming formal and informal channels. However, because of globalisation Western biomedicine acts as a system of social control. Report says, today Western part of the globe turning to use the non-biomedical healing system rather than modern medicines⁽⁹⁾.

CONCLUSION

Within the context of sociology of health culture, health has been considered less as an abstract state and more as a means to an end which can be expressed in functional terms as a resource which permits people to lead an individually, socially and economically productive life. Health is a resource for everyday life, not an object of living. It is a positive concept emphasising social and personal resources as well as physical capabilities. Understanding the role of health culture should be examined as a sub-cultural complex of the whole way of life. Rural health cultural will normally have a lot of dimensions including changing social, economical, political and historical and so on. Rural health culture is a part of their social system as well as an adaptive system. Understanding their health beliefs, it always should be within the boundary of holism which is illuminated by their local medical system. Anthropologists felt health culture is a product of actions adopted by the pool of people over the period of time. It is argued that rural health culture should not be underscored as just superstitious.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

It is declared that this manuscript has no financial or other substantive conflict of interest that might be construed to influence the results or interpretation of their manuscript.

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How to cite this article: Nanjunda DC. Changing Framework of Sociology of Health and Treatment: Rev Neurosciences Ann Health Sci Res 2015;2(2):57-72

Research Article

Impact of Language Proficiency on Academic Achievement among Nursing Students

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ABSTRACT

Background: In preparing future nurses who are competent to provide safe care, nursing education has an important role in updating current knowledge, skills and attitudes of patient care. As students progress through the grades, the academic tasks they are required to complete and the linguistic contexts in which they must function become more complex. As language is socially situated, it is described as only one of many complex features that may affect academic progress. **Objectives:** To assess the impact of language proficiency on academic achievement among nursing students. **Methods:** A total of thirty one nursing students in a medical college were administered with written Test of English as a Foreign Language (TOEFL) paper test after getting consent to assess their language proficiency. The cognitive domain which represents the knowledge acquired during the course was evaluated by formative assessment as per university norms. Strength of association between language proficiency and academic achievement was measured using Pearson correlation coefficient using medical software. $P < 0.05$ was considered as statistically significant. **Results:** Correlation with Pearson correlation test between academic achievement and language proficiency showed statistically significant association. **Conclusion:** Language proficiency plays an important role in the academic achievement among the nursing students. Inculcating English language course in to the curriculum of nursing programme will uplift the standards of nursing education and thereby nursing care.

Keywords: Language proficiency, Cognitive domain, Knowledge, Nursing students, ESL, Nursing students, Curriculum development

INTRODUCTION

Children hear and learn from the sounds of speech even while they are still in the womb. Language learning accelerates once infants are born. Children's language instils inspire them to learn the syntax of their native language and a vocabulary of approximately 5,000 words over their first 5 years of life. This language learning affects cognitive development in many ways. Some effects are specific to language, whereas others are more general. As per the national language policy (or strategy) in India for school education, the three-language formula recommended by the National Commission on Education 1964-1966, was incorporated into the national Education policies of 1968 and 1986. Accommodating at least three languages in school education has been seen as a

convenient strategy, but concerns have also been expressed from various quarters about its 'unsatisfactory' implementation. India's pluralism is reflected in its linguistic diversity. According to Rao two decades ago the number of languages used as media of instruction was about 60, but by the time Rao's study was carried out the number had dropped to 47^(1,2).

Traditional taxonomies (e.g., Bloom's) have been used to outline the domains of learning. Bloom's taxonomy makes three important distinctions in the domains of learning namely cognitive (knowledge), psychomotor (practical skills) and affective (attitude). Cognitive domain is further sub-classified into six hierarchical domains, beginning with knowledge of the subject and ending with evaluation of knowledge⁽³⁾.

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Journal of
Research Volume 2

1993

all clinical practice is inherently interpretive”.

Health, illness and cure are realities in everybody's life across the societies. Therapy, practices and results normally evolve over the period of time within the socio-cultural contexts. It provides different insights about health culture, behaviour, traditions; customs in the medical health care system. Through the personal experiences patients' and the doctors/ native healers will also add on to the knowledge of society's health belief system continuously over the period of time. All cultures consist of vital information's about how disease occurs, what makes illness and how to choose suitable healing approaches. This would be a health culture of each and every community. In each health culture there will be different concepts, ideology philosophy and thinking and planning in handling various diseases and illness appropriately (Bhasin 2008). Obeyesakere (1976) has given a term called “cultural diseases” because some diseases are created partially because of “cultural” definition of the “situation” .

Regarding social construction of disease and illness Rose (1992) has evolved an argument for analyzing ‘behavior determinants of the health of individuals at the societal level’. Rose writes “concerning the social distribution

and determinants of disease and illness cut across the view of disease as an autonomous individual affliction. It focus that new disease and the discloser to the range of possible risk factors are a result of the norms of any given society”. Hence it is opined that beliefs held by the community/individual within a society about on set of disease and curing is critical always.

It is generally opined that illness has three domains:

1. Illness as Sanction (punishment for doing wrong)
2. Illness as Deviance(a form of social control)
3. Illness as an Indicator of Social System Performance (indicative of the performance of an existing social system)

It is well known truth that health and illness is a ‘socially constructed concept’. Each and every society will interpret the term ‘health and illness’ differently in its own way. This would be depending largely on history, culture, religion, gender role etc. of that society. Moreover it depends who has the final authority to apply the label of ‘illness’ within a given society. Also it depends on the context or the circumstances in which illness occurs. Truly speaking social construction of illness means how society shapes illness

Review article

A Conceptual Revisit to Sociology of Health and Illness :Does it Matters?

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Abstract

The sociology of health and illness has a long history. Right from the history, Sociologists are attempting to find out how social and cultural factors influences understanding of illness and diseases. people's responses to illness and to the relevant healthcare policies. Sociologists are also probing how social, economic, and cultural factors impacting about choosing a different health seeking behaviors. Medical sociologists and anthropologists have given a wide range of findings on health and illness based on various empirical studies conducted in different rural settings across the globe. Particularly sociologists have written more on the sick role, the social construction of health and illness, influence of local culture and tradition in defining and treating diseases and how health and illness concept may affect on the different component of the society. Sociologists have also found that the health culture of each and every community will have different concepts, ideology philosophy and thinking and planning in handling various diseases and illness appropriately..this paper is based on the review of various secondary resources.

Key words: sociology, health, illness, concepts

Introduction

“Sociological research deconstructs such discourses and highlights their implications on the notion of agency of the patient, meanings of informed consent, patient participation in different cultural contexts and notions of health and illness as doing. Health becomes an everyday moral duty” (Mishra, 2010).

Sociology brings two different focuses of analysis to the study of health and illness:

1. At the first instance it focuses to 'make sense of illness', by applying various sociological perspectives both to a scrutiny of the understanding of illness, and to the social structuring of health and disease. Further, sociology makes an imperative

input to multi-disciplinary and multi faceted assessment into issues of interest to health care providers and helps in the development of new appropriate health policies:

2. At a second level, sociological enquiry can give more options to an understanding of the effect of wider social and cultural phenomenon upon the health of individuals or the community and various social groups. Such processes include social inequalities, health culture, behavior, change, knowledge, medicalizations and power.

Health is an elusive concept. We have numerous definitions to define the term health. Good health can be some time

positive or sometime negative or more precisely absence of any kind of health related problems like physical or mental. Herzlich (1973) said "health is to feel well, in good form, happy content, with a good appetite, sleeping well wanting to be up and doing; it is to feel well and strong: that's what good health is". Parson (1951) defines health is a good status of physical body which can perform any task. He said 'healthy person can do any social role which is a normal part of his/her societal responsibility. Health disorder may reduce the capacity of the human being'. We can also opine the cultural setting of any given society regarding, ~~perception: preference~~, evaluation and satisfaction about 'health' is more vital while generalizing term' (Nagala, 2007). The health of any society is intimately related to its value, system, philosophical and political and ecological organizations (Singh ~~et al~~, 2008). Moreover health is subjective in its basic nature.

The sociology of health and illness has a long history. Over the last 100 years many concepts, theories, findings have been explored for the better understanding of health behavior of human being and the role of the society. Majority theories and approaches relating to the health and illness have been originally propounded by the western sociologists only. Even today researchers in developing countries are

heavily depending on western theories to explain health culture and behavior of the rural community. In developing countries social class, caste, gender etc., play a vital role in accessing suitable healthcare facilities. More than these the underlying social, political and economic forces are also counting a lot. It is found that sociology of health and illness significantly helps us in better understanding of people's concepts about onset of various diseases and its cure in a cross cultural framework.

Since communities' perception on health and illness varies from culture to culture sociologists have given various theories and approaches to study about health and illness over the period of time using longitudinal studies. Truly speaking the very basic concept of sociology of health and illness is to enlighten about the social origin and influence on the onset and choosing suitable medical care of any diseases or illness and role of different components of the society relating to that issue. Sociology of health and illness also explains how different social groups have come up with the specific diseases over the period of time and what other culture can learn from their experiences. Also concept on health and illness of the society is based on the cognitive orientation of a particular social group and cure will also follow the same cultural logic.

Culture is a shared concept of the specific social groups. The concept of health, hygiene, illness, well being, and sickness are the fundamental issues present in all types of culture across different societies. Every culture will have its own notions, concepts about health and illness. Culture is a vital concept and an instrument to conduct health studies among the rural population as patients' belongs to different social groups. These people express unique health behavior and medical pluralism to cure their health problems. People's construction of illness is a focal point in sociology. The Influence of religious belief and social network on the health culture is a vital issue studying health and illness from the sociological point of view. Every culture has its exact clarification and justifications for all types of ill health. Culture provides people with ways of thinking that are "concurrently models of and models of actuality".

Health and illness are an universal concept in all societies. Each community organizes itself through experience, through different means, through different elements and finally will develop different approaches to fight against illness and diseases. In this way each and every society develops specific medical institutions called health care system in a relevant social context. This health care

system will have origin, symptoms, development, process and curing of various diseases/illness. This system will have different symbols expressed through the means of practices, interactions and institutions.

The health care system is also a part of general culture. There will be no much differences between socio-cultural experiences and episode of illness with respect to a particular social group. Each and every individual through his/her personal episode of illness will keep on adding his/her prospective to the society's health culture. We cannot neglect health and illness episode of a lay person. Health culture will develop according to the social, economical, legal and political development etc. of the society. In this matter various medical institutions and the systems will also play a vital role in the maintaining of the "state of health" (Langdon and Wikinson , 2010; Kleinman, 1980; Langdon and Wilk, 2010) Health care system normally will have two components.

1. Social component;
2. Cultural component

Social Component: In case of social elements it consists of different health care institutions, healers, health culture, health behavior etc., It also includes traditional medicinal system like folk system, faith healers, quacks herbalists etc.. Apart from

these we can also witness for the growth of other medical system like Unani, Sidda, Tibetan and Chinese medicinal system side by side. Also we can see the concentration of different specialist practicing different therapeutic models based on different health culture and care. Each and every social group will have their own reservations, perceptions in accepting or acknowledging or rejecting these any type of medical system/s. This acceptance or rejection will be largely based on the socio-economic background, caste, family history, religion etc. we cannot isolate all these vital factors while studying the health culture of a community from a sociological point of view.

Cultural component: The cultural system of health will help us with different knowledge and cognitions to identify, perceive and explain disease/illness. Each and every culture will have their own concept about symptoms, classifications about various types of diseases/illness. However they are not universal. Every health cultures gives etiological theories about multiple causes of disease and illness. Certain health culture theories provide us logic behind both preventive and curative knowledge of the people. Some theories enlighten us about various reasons for using more than one type of medical system (Medical pluralism) and

how medical pluralism shapes communities' health behavior and health culture.

Truly speaking health care system has been just a conceptual model to understand society's different health culture and behavior. This will help us to understand the different sets of elements and experiences involved in the health culture and behavior. Since the health care system is a cultural system, sociology will also help us in understanding medical pluralism operating concurrently in different social groups and cultural response for various health problems.

Further sociology of health and illness focus on

1. What should be the actual theories of health and illness?
2. How theory should be constructed focusing health and illness;
3. How health theories changes from culture and culture;
4. How body, mind and spirit careered each other;
5. Connections between theory of health and theory of healing;
6. What is meant by healing and who is the actual healer;
7. Relationship between medicine and society

8. How health culture and health seeking behavior changing over the period of time:
9. How quality health care \ can be delivered to all
10. Why people rejects/accepts modern medicines

Sociology of health and illness basically deals about the inter relationship between 'health and society' and 'medicine and society'. Study about health and illness in the society is not a new phenomena. From time immemorial, people are doing official or unofficial research study about societal reaction and responsible towards health and illness. Even during the Egyptian period also there were some intelligent people doing research on medicine and its connection with the society. Essentially there is a clear cut differentiation between medical sociology and sociology of health and illness. In medical sociology focus will be concerning health and illness delimited by a range of social institutions. Nevertheless in case of sociology of health and illness researchers by and large studies concerning a) various social and cultural factors causing diseases and illness, b) health seeking behavior, c) health care seeking behavior and d) inherited health culture of the society.

It also focuses how health culture and behavior varies based on the socio-economic status of the community. Sociological concept about illness gives a fair idea how external determinants causes health problem to an individual and how he/she responds to it in a given social context. It is a well known truth that the influence of socio-cultural factors varies across the globe. Normally these social factors demonstrated through various discourses on important diseases /illness and its outbreak in a specific geographical area. Basically experts' focus about the issues comprising society and medicine, socioeconomic setup, general cultural issues which are geographically specific while studying specific health culture of a community. Sometime a common disease may affect the larger population whereas a major disease may affect smaller population only. Medical anthropologists basically studies about these discrepancies.

It is found that basically sociology of health and illness study takes place in Three vital domains. They are-

1. Conceptualization of health and illness of a particular society or culture;
2. Measurement and distribution of health and illness;
3. Reason behind choosing particular type of healing approach

As we are aware different culture responds differently to different illness/diseases. Based on this study about how an illness affects social regulations or controls over the time would be worth for study. Measuring and distribution of various diseases/ illness will help how community is using various existing health services. It also helps in getting patients' perception about his/her illness and reason for that. Sociologist tries to study the various data to analyze the distribution pattern of disease and illness in a given society. Since history, thousands of people had been dying due to the outbreak of various endemics which led to think about the necessity of having good a public health strategy in the society. Studies shows concept of good health was only among the elite sections (rich people) of the society. Slowly concepts and significance about good health and reason for illness among other people were also starting to develop. People started to have a notion that good health leads to have a good social status in the society. Gradually marginalized sections of the society started showing interest towards sanitation and precautions in their personal life to keep healthy.

As new medical health care facilities discovered, health status of the communities across the world has started

considerably improving. Gradual changes in the socio economic status of the people also led to have quality medical care. Diagnose and treatment also started to affect positively on the health care seeking behavior of the community. Now rural people are showing much interest to adopt modern health care facilities whereas certain sections are not yet. This change in the health culture of the community causes the issue of health and illness within given societal life to be highly volatile in definition. Hence studying health and illness from the sociological point of view continuously needs to be updated.

Wilkinson (1996) has opined society having poor health will tolerate high inequality in every aspect. Differences in health practices between various social groups would be more vital for sociological analyzations. Even in the same society, disparities in health status and health behavior can be seen among different social classes/castes. The wide income gap, material deprivation and psychological issues invariably effects on health and illness of an individual/community in a society. Wide gap between rich and poor people results in low social cohesion which finally affects the health of all members. It is found that vital differences in case of mortality and morbidity continuously

increasing between low income groups and the elites of the society. However the research is on the way to find out how poverty and deprivation effects on general health issues and behavior among the members of developing societies.

Health seeking and health care seeking behavior of an entire family will be largely influenced by the social and cultural factors. Poor income means poor health. Finally it leads to have various effects on family causing various health problems. Income and health are closely related to life expectancy of any community. High income inequality also leads to have a big gap in the health disparity between different social groups. This health disparity is due to material deprivation and socio-psychological effects. Due to social exclusion (class and cast) certain sections of society may not get equal health benefits. Various social, cultural, developmental and psychological factors finally leave an impact on health condition of an individual irrespective of his/her class and caste. Moreover it is found that social capital like education, housing, social networks also places an imperative factors causing health and illness (Crision, 2007 : Wilkinson, 1996 : Marmot, 2004).

Further sociological study also revealed how different social process and functions affects on health status of different social groups. In addition it helps to reveal how different social groups are experiencing health and illness. Supplementary it reveals layman's health beliefs, and illness behavior. Many studies have proved that layman's health beliefs varies according to social and cultural background. How a layman experiences, describes, justifies health and illness would be a vital point in understanding general conceptions of health and illness of the people. However certain medical sociologists have opined there will be a big difference in case of general societal opinion than an individualistic opinion about socio-cultural aspects of health and illness. Because individualistic determinants for health and illness cannot be simply generalized or add up to become the general social determinants in a border way (Crimson, 2007).

SOCIAL CONSTRUCTION OF ILLNESS

Bhasin (2007) writes "every culture has its particular explanations for illness. Frake (1961) during his research among Subanum of Mindanao, explained illness as a vehicle for pursuing other interests. He wrote "illness is fundamentally semantic or meaningful and

all clinical practice is inherently interpretive”.

Health, illness and cure are realities in everybody's life across the societies. Therapy, practices and results normally evolve over the period of time within the socio-cultural contexts. It provides different insights about health culture, behaviour, traditions; customs in the medical health care system. Through the personal experiences patients' and the doctors/ native healers will also add on to the knowledge of society's health belief system continuously over the period of time. All cultures consist of vital information's about ~~how disease occurs~~, what makes illness and how to choose suitable healing approaches. This would be a health culture of each and every community. In each health culture there will be different concepts, ideology philosophy and thinking ~~and planning~~ in handling various diseases and illness appropriately (Bhasin 2008). Obeyesakere (1976) has given a term called “cultural diseases” because some diseases are created partially because of “cultural” definition of the “situation”.

Regarding social construction of disease and illness Rose (1992) has evolved an argument for analyzing ‘behavior determinants of the health of individuals at the societal level’. Rose writes “concerning the social distribution

and determinants of disease and illness cut across the view of disease as an autonomous individual affliction. It focus that new disease and the discloser to the range of possible risk factors are a result of the norms of any given society”. Hence it is opined that beliefs held by the community/individual within a society about on set of disease and curing is critical always.

It is generally opined that illness has three domains:

1. Illness as Sanction (punishment for doing wrong)
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~~It is well~~ known truth that health and illness is a ‘socially constructed concept’. Each and every society will interpret the term ‘health and illness’ differently in its own way. This would be depending largely on history, culture, religion, gender role etc. of that society. Moreover it depends who has the final authority to apply the label of ‘illness’ within a given society. Also it depends on the context or the circumstances in which illness occurs. Truly speaking social construction of illness means how society shapes illness

behavior of an individual in which he/she normally live. Here one question arises what does really construct an illness?

Steven (2001) writes “clearest example of illness as a socially and culturally shaped through a similarity of eastern medicine system and description of illness versus western medicinal system and description of illness”.

Illness has three historical origins:

1. Few illness notions are originally rooted historical and cultural meaning;
2. Most of all illness are socially constructed at the empirical level;
3. The true medical concept about illness is mostly framed by the vested interest

Banks and Prior (2001) opined in this situation patients will create their own illness ideology based social context and their own illness narrations and parameters to measure their illness notions.

Truly speaking sociological study on health and illness mainly focus on two prospective:

1. Sociological analysis of different societal factors causing health and illness;
2. Social structure and how different segments of a society responsible for the current illness and how a patient responds to it.

Studying health and illness from the societal perspective will yield some diverse dimensions and discourses. This would be completely different when examining health from an individualistic prospective because social determinants and individual determinates are quite different. Social, cultural and economic conditions are some of the strongest determinants while studying illness in rural society.

SOCIOLOGICAL APPROACHS:

Sociological theories of health and illness relatively based on imbalances inside the human body. Certain sociologists argue illness causes due to problems in the social relationship. Also they argue that illness causes due to broken relationship between the human being and the eco-system. Indian system of medicine is based on the same belief that the human body is made-up of three basic substances called ‘spirit, phlem and bile’. Chinese’s medicine is also based on the belief that the body is made-up of five elements including ‘water, metal, earth, fire, and wood’. In addition Greek system of medicine opines that human body has Four different of forces. Expert says any imbalances among these basic elements would cause illness and disease among human beings. Certain sociologist’s proposed their theories about illness and diseases based on natural and

super natural causations. Theories of natural causation focus on disturbance of health as a physiological consequences including infection, germs, mental trauma (Murdock, 1980)

There are three vital theoretical modules to get into the in-depth understanding of health and illness from the perspective of Medical Anthropology.

1. Epidemiological approach
2. Interpretive
3. Critical Medical Anthropology

1. Epidemiological Approach: In case of epidemiological approach, normally researchers studies health and illness from the prospective of social and cultural factors. The core part of this theory deals how ecology and environment affect causing various health problems in the society. In this approach, normally focus would be on various risk factors which cause diseases and illness and how it relates to the environment. This theory also propounds the relationship between urbanization and new public health problems. According to these theory social interactions, food habit, and household ecology also play a vital role in causing health disorders. This theory adds urbanization and migration invariably causes new social pattern of health problems in the society.

This approach further divided into Three more divisions;

a. **Retrospective approach:** it conducts reasons for various diseases and illness which are occurred already.

b. **Prospective approach** informs us whether the diseases occur or not? More precisely we can say prospective approach gives an idea of possibility about future occurrence of some diseases. Epidemiological approach will not avoid the occurrence of any diseases but gives a hint in advance.

2. Interpretive Approach : Basically this approach studies diseases/ illness from the micro prospective. Interpretive prospective further elaborates how specific cultural factors cause disease/ illness. It also focuses how health behavior and health culture evolved over the period of time in a given society/community. This study would be useful in analyzing health behavior and health culture of small communities.

3. Critical Medical Anthropology here researchers would focus on how economics and political issues of the society play significantly in the development or underdevelopment of various human health issues. Economics

and politics are the major factors in the development/underdevelopment of human health. Also this approach deals about various social problems and effects of the media on the prevailing health care system in the given society. This theory further focuses how dominant western biomedicine discriminates poor and powerless in the society with respect to health. This approach also sheds light on pseudo-medicalism, medical exploitations, cost of treatment, Doctor's behavior, medicalizations process etc. This approach strongly believes in the notion that political and economical structure of the society basically ~~responsible~~ in establishing good/ bad health status of a community. Finally this approach criticizes the western health care system for being de-humanized. This theory also strongly criticizes about 'over medicalizations'.

Experts felt health expenditure, resources, health policies all come under the domain of economic factors causing health disorders in a society. Social and developmental policies, political will, political stability, decision, participation etc also affect on human health culture and behavior. Social exclusion is also a major factor in accessing well quality health care facilities to the marginalized sections of the society. Because of Social

exclusion certain sections of the society is away from the health rights today.

Theories about Origin of Diseases and Illness

There are various theories about origin, cause and cure of diseases and illness. Also theories explain how particular health behavior and health culture evolved in the society. Theories about diseases and illness may mainly divided into two groups they are:- 1. Personalistic 2. Naturalistic . 3.Folk Concept

1. Personalistic theories argue illness or disease causes due to supernatural powers including spirits, sorceries, souls, witches etc. According to this theory illness causes due to moral or spiritual violation by human beings. Violated social and religions taboos also cause illness as believed in many traditional cultures. This theory further believed that illness is a type of sanction by the super natural powers due to the immorality or breaching taboos in the life. This theory also opines failure to carry out certain rituals may also end up with illness. According to this theory recovery can be had by worshiping deity through ritual or through a trained healer. This theory also explains about sick role in the society and society can help him/her to come out of sick as spoons as possible.

Also it explains the space of the sick person in the society and effect of sick role issue on the stability, continuity and cohesion of the society.

2. According to Naturalistic theory illness causes due to impersonal terms. This theory assumes illness causes due to disturbance of cultural order of human beings with his/her surrounding ecosystem. This theory says harmony between human beings and eco-environment should be properly maintained without which it causes severe may harm of the health of a person. Humeral concept is a vital concept of naturalistic theory. Proper balance of various human systems would be a vital component for being healthy. According to this theory Indian system of medicine is also based on naturalistic theory. In India 'Prana'(vital energy) concept exists since time immemorial, Prana is essential in keeping the human being alive. If the vital energy is disturbed human being may get sickness.

Folk Concept: - This is one of the ancient concepts of explaining causes of illness and cure which is prevalent in many parts of India and other Asian continents. Folk concept's on illness and diseases ranges from the social world to the supernatural world. These symbols have cultural significance in explaining health behavior and health culture. Folk concept presumes illness and disease may cause due to evil

eyes, imbalance of body fluids, hot and cold diet, sorcery, violation of taboos, improper behavior also. It also opined an individual failed in performing rituals regularly may get various health problems. Folk concept has a lot of symbolic meanings. This theory also explains how human body normally functions (humeral), and how it causes symptoms and the meaning of illness and its moral, social and cultural significance. Also it thrives to explain about illness within the individualistic perspective.

Social construction of illness depends on how people differentiate between illness and the disease. Social construction of illness has developed through an interaction in a social context. Meaning and the experience of illness will be largely framed by the historical and existing social system. Scholars say illness is not 'given' rather actually conferred by dominating social groups in a given society. They say society will confer illness as a part of the control/sanction (short term). Scholars who support 'symbolic interactionism' felt illness is an experiences within the framework of daily social interactions of an individual.

Few sociologists are showing interest to work on how 'symptoms' or 'symbols' are being labeled or identified as an 'illness'. It is also interesting to look what an accepted as "Illness or what is not

accepted as not an 'illness' and what are the factors which play a vital role in differentiating illness from any biological framework. However, few scholars also say an argument over illness and its societal construction approach as something 'Mixed' i.e. Illness has both medical and social deviance. Some time illness varies or may not have independent factors of effect on patient and health care system. Illness has also cultural symbolic domain. Some illness has been labeled as stigma, while some illness is not stigmatized in society. For example AIDS will be severally stigmatized where as polio not some time. Illness stigmatization varies society to society based on the type, duration and severity etc. It may have less noticed in urban society whereas more serious in case of rural society. Some time due to stigmatization people may not come forward to take suitable 'medical' care as all.

It is known fact that sociologists are studying 'patient perspective of illness' since 1950 onwards. Strauss (1975) opined that since patients' will spend only few days 'with illness (if is a minor problem) patient's personal experience/narrations may not same as the illness experiences of a patient having long term health problems' Hence it is necessary to focus on 'patients life's

before illness, during the stage of illness and after the illness got medially cured'. This helps us in the social construction of illness based on patients' experiences in a given society. Also it helps us to know how the different components of the society helped him/her to come out of illness stage soon. During the stage of illness patients' will be normally worried about their personal and social relationships and other day to day activities which could not be performed well. Sometime during the stage of illness patients will review their previous life and in some cases it may create new illness identification (ex. patients under dialysis) also.

Conclusion

A lot of changes have also occurred in the basic theory of illness ideology and sick role because of the availability of speedy healing techniques/treatments. The significance of the "sick role" has also been diluted because of globalizations. Globalization has affected even on the concept of traditional or folk medicine today. Today public health communication has been effective due to the availability of new and upcoming formal and informal channels. However, because of globalization western bio-medicine acting as a system of social control ruling out the role of sociological

e-Journal of JSS College of Nursing

July-September Issue (Volume 11) 2015

(<http://www.jsscon.org/ejournal/volume11.html>)

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A Medico-Sociological Review on Health Behaviour and Therapies among Rural people

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Abstract

It is opined that the exact role of social determinants in the health care seeking behavior is not completely cleared yet. The Health beliefs sometime more closely relates to the both psychology and sociological issues with the broad influences of the socio-economic conditions. Also various social networks play a vital role in framing the vital behavior determinants. Moreover, the neighborhood environment also largely influences on the people with reference to their health behavior and the health culture. It is found that poverty and the health are closely related in every society. Poverty effects on the health in many ways. The authors have found that heavy cost for the quality health care might be one of the reasons for the poor health status in the rural parts. It is Opined that poverty and other issues mainly effects on the health status including lifestyle, social exclusion, malnutrition, mental problems etc., this paper is based on the review of various literature on health behaviour and therapies focusing rural people.

Background

Since time immemorial health-seeking behavior of the rural population is greatly governed by the cultural values, beliefs and traditions. However now it is open for the gradual change because of continuous interventions of the different kinds of external agencies in the rural part. Further, in the changes of patterns of health seeking behavior of the rural people, one also can notice incredible fresh ideology which has occurred with respect to philosophy, knowledge, and practices of indigenous systems such as Ayurveda, Homeopathy, Allopathic, etc in rural settings. However, it becomes important to work on problems of rural's health because it differs from one area to another area owing to their remote geographical setting, historical milieu processes of social change and the cultural diffusion (Bulliyya,2009). Geographical isolation and limited interactions with other communities have become an obstacle to know the degree of prevalence of various communicable and non communicable diseases including HIV and STD among rural area and the community's response

Nancymun (1973) found that "ritual is a common medium of social interactions which becomes a vehicle for framing messages through iconic symbols (acts, words, chants and other things) that convert the load of importance of complex socio-cultural meanings embedded in and generated by the ongoing process of social existence into common currency. In other words, shared socio-cultural meanings constituted, which are symbolically transacted through the medium of ritual action". Medhiano and Hassan (2002) have found that introducing western medicine may be a reason for the emergence of medical pluralism. In some village, people use both the traditional and modern type of medicine to cure different types of diseases/illness. Some time people will themselves choose a particular type of therapy for their different health

problems. In certain cases both the local healers and the patients; are being well aware about various biological & non-biological substances as medicines to cure various health problems.

Carpa (1991) has narrated that Shamanistic idea of illness is based on the concept that every human being is a part & parcel of the certain cultural order. It is found that diseases or illness causes whenever there is a disturbance with the cosmic order. Hence, 'curing illness means restoring the good harmony with the spirit world again'. He also opined that 'shamans will not treat a patient based on his/her conscious rather an entire social-unconscious shared by the universe'. The main objective behind the ritual healing is to satisfy and surrender to the cosmic powers. Dauglas (1975) has written every human being will have both social body experiences and physical body experiences. However, physical experiences of the body always changes by various social categories. Throughout the life course of an individual, there will be an exchange of meanings, exchange of perceptions and other consciousness between these two types of bodily experiences. Further, this author has explained about the relationship between symbols and its meanings associated with the communities' perception or expression about illness theory and body image. He also said a different healing technique in various contexts represent the cultural whole.

Chilivumbo (1977) wrote "diagnosis and therapeutic measures acquiring meanings through subjective perceptions and the defined symbolic world view in which irrationalities assume meanings. Illness experience is shaped by cultural symbols and meanings in a defined cultural context or situation". Tribhuvan (1998), Sten and Mazonde (1999) have opined health seeking behavior has no place in the modern medical text books. The modern doctors should aware of the health seeking behavior of the both urban and rural patients' for an effective treatment under the context of medical pluralism.

Tipping and Segall (1995) have found health seeking behavior depends on gender, personality, types of occupation etc. Also he opined in rural area parents' are not providing nutritional food for both infants and minor children as per the nutritional requirements because of various cultural reasons. As a result, the level of malnutrition among infants and children would be very high. Ahmed et al (2001) has found rather visiting modern Doctor rural people would like to visit a traditional healer normally for the required treatment. Because the traditional healer can be visited any time and he/she will be more a patients' friendly. People have more faith on the traditional healers not on allopathic doctor because the traditional healers are very close to their social and cultural realm.

Outwater, et-al (2001) has found few vital facts about the traditional healers and their knowledge about the modern health techniques. He opined today traditional healers use more inputs from the modern medicines. Also the author felt traditional healers should be given enough scientific training to handle simple health problems of the rural people. Because, people have more faith on the healers who are not trained enough than the trained doctors due to the various cultural reasons. Murdock (1980) has felt illness perceptions of the various societies' can be obtained based on their opinion about the natural and super natural causation of various health

issues. Normand and Bennet (1996) study has found that people who can have control on their health can have more knowledge on promoting self-health behavior normally. He felt today due an explosion of various modern media' people are aware more about their health needs.

Macphail and Campbell (2001) have studied how individual's medical knowledge in social and cultural contexts developers. They opined that there is a slight conflict between the modern and local medical knowledge over the period of time. People strongly believe the modern medical technology has originated basically from the traditional system only. Campbell and Mzaidume (2001) have opined peoples' participation in health related projects may increase more positive health care seeking behavior among them'. Also health projects will give more therapeutic options to the people. The author also found high rates of various infectious diseases in the rural areas is due to the poor socio economic status, health illiteracy, unhygienic conditions etc.

Bedri (2001) has opined women have limited opportunity in accessing good health care facilities in the rural areas because of their vulnerable position. The significant higher fertility rate among the rural people is mainly due to the high infant and child mortality rate facing by the rural population. They also showed that simple awareness about the infant and child morality influences the real family size of those who recognize the current level of infant and child mortality as the same or worse than before. Radley (1994) ; Dalal and Ray (2005) have opined health and sickness are often limited in natural terms, referring to the bodily conditions, as assessed by the medical professionals. This distinctive expert-oriented approach fails in delivering the health care services. In the first instance, rural patients' will approach the health professionals only when they find their illness symptoms threatening and understand that they need some urgent medical attention. Thus, it seems significant to understand the health and illness issues from the patients' viewpoint especially in the rural settings.

Uzma et.al (1999) opines that people's decision about choosing a suitable healthcare involves multiple steps. We can't give any set models generalizing the health behavior of the rural people. It requires trial and error method to fix a specific or more accurate health behavior model focusing rural people. Courad (2000) found advancement in medical technology is a kind of curse for the rural people. Because more medicalization of human problems cause more economic consequences for the people having different socio-economic backgrounds. This may lead to have more conflicts at the societal level causing other sever problems.

Basavanagouda, (2004) opined that availability of pure water, sanitation, traditional beliefs play a vital role in shaping the health behavior of the rural folks. Partnership with the NGOs and civil society, Govt. may try to provide the high-impact, cost-effective health and nutrition interventions to decrease the neonatal and child mortality causing due the various infectious diseases in the rural areas. The Govt. should frame the programmes to create awareness about the importance of the nutritious food items and the breast feeding among the rural folk. Media can also play a vital role in the success of the various immunization programmes.

Shaika (2004) has opined that the health seeking behavior of the rural people in the developing societies is changing today. This is because of the changing physical, socio economic, cultural and political scenario due to the globalization. He opined that the utilization of any type of health care system normally depend on the socio-demographic factors, existing social structure, gender discrimination and ecology. He writes 'health policy making should be supplementary to the pluralistic health care system'. More focus should be given to the socially excluded people through an inter-sectoral collaboration. Martorell (1999) has opined that malnutrition and childhood mortality became a serious problem among the rural community in many south Asian countries. It is found that the rurals's social-cultural background, health seeking behavior and dynamics of the health culture play a significant determinants indicating the health status of the rural community in a multi cultural society like India. Because of a unique health seeking beliefs and behavior, malnutrition and the childhood mortality issues are more common in the rural areas.

Gaidas (2005) opined that the health seeking behavior differs in both men and women. Men belonging to the different socio-economic background and ethnicity normally may have to suffer with the various health inequalities. He opined that heterogeneous sample is required to reveal the factors which place a vital role regarding the health decision making among rural men. Deepa (2005) has opined that Ayurvedic and Homeopathy should be treated as a complementary rather alternative to the western medicinal system. In US it will be considered as a food supplement. Since the more medical pluralism is available today in the rural areas, people some time may get confusing over accepting an appropriate health care system.

Conclusion

The review of existing literatures on the health culture and health behavior reveals that an extensive research is required to fill up some of the gaps related to changing different perspectives of the rural health problem. It is found that there is a rising socio-economic inequality between rural and urban population. Essential inequality in health care reimbursement between rural and urban is augmented by the fast but uneven economic expansion that rural India has witnessed in the last few years. The high occurrence of illness cuts into the financial plan of rural people in two dissimilar ways i.e.

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วิทยาศาสตร์

สาขาสังคมศาสตร์

เกษตรศาสตร์

KASETSART JOURNAL

Social Sciences

ISSN 0125 - 8370

<http://www.rdi.ku.ac.th>

<http://kasetartjournal.ku.ac.th/>

ปีที่ ๓๖ ฉบับที่ ๒ พฤษภาคม - สิงหาคม ๒๕๕๘
May - August 2015 Volume 36 Number 2

ความเต็มใจจ่ายเพื่อคุณลักษณะในการบริหารจัดการห่วงโซ่ทางจักรยาน
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ABSTRACT

Rural health development in India traces its history to the seventeenth century when voluntary efforts to serve mankind were initiated by the then rulers. The rural health development functions were assumed by the government in the context of recurrent famines, but in the beginning, they did not have any legal sanctions behind them. We can divide health in India into two divisions: 1) high quality medical care in urban India; and 2) low health infrastructure in rural India. Reports indicate that more than 63 percent of rural people do not have access to modern curative and preventive health care facilities in various part of the country and that only 24.6 percent of doctors are serving in rural areas. Furthermore, there is a large disparity in the presence of government hospitals between rural and urban parts of Karnataka state. Illiteracy, unhygienic health conditions, malnutrition, and a scarcity of potable water from wells are some of the reasons why rural people make up such a large proportion of those suffering from various health disorders. Normally, people with low economic status such as rural folk are the victims of various epidemics and endemics. The major section of rural society is either small land holders or marginal holders having very limited resources. Clearly, their socio-economic status is very low and they cannot spend more money on health. It is stated that there is a positive correlation between the health status of the rural people and their social, economic, and cultural background. This paper is based on a careful review of various reports, secondary data, and experts' opinion pertaining to the health situation in Karnataka state, South India.

Keywords: health, rural, diseases, health infrastructure, health culture

บทคัดย่อ

การส่งเสริมสุขภาพในชนบทของประเทศไทย เป็นที่ยอมรับมาช้านาน ซึ่งไม่ได้แยกตัวออกจากกันกับปัญหาความแออัดของเมือง ซึ่งเริ่มศตวรรษที่ 17 ซึ่งผู้ปกครองในเมืองขณะนั้นริเริ่มงานอาสาสมัครเพื่อรับใช้มนุษยชาติ โดยในระยะแรกมีการดูแลสุขภาพนอกออกของผู้คน ซึ่งไม่มีบริการด้านสุขภาพแผนกต่างๆเป็น 2 ประเภท คือ

บริการระดับคุณภาพในเมือง และบริการระดับต่ำในชนบทที่มีรายงานกันว่าร้อยละ 63 ของชนบทในภูมิภาคต่างๆของอินเดียยังไม่สามารถเข้าถึงบริการทางการแพทย์ขั้นสูงได้ ในด้านการป้องกันและการรักษา อีกทั้งมีแพทย์เพียงร้อยละ 24.6 ของอินเดียที่ทำงานในชนบท เฉพาะในรัฐ Karnataka นั้นพบว่ามีความเหลื่อมล้ำสูงของสภาพโรงพยาบาลรัฐในระหว่างเขตเมืองกับเขตชนบท ทั้งนี้ ปัญหาพื้นฐานต่างๆ ได้แก่ การไม่รู้หนังสือ ความไม่เพียงพอ

ไม่ถูกสุขอนามัย การขาดการดูแลสุขภาพของตนเอง ต้นตอจากปัญหาเหล่านี้ เป็นปัจจัยที่ส่งผลให้ชาวชนบทมีปัญหาด้านสุขภาพเป็นส่วนที่สูงของประเทศ โดยทั่วไป กลุ่มคนที่มีความเสี่ยงต่อโรคต่างๆที่คาดคิดและโรคไม่ติดต่อ ก่อตัวส่วนใหญ่ในชนบทที่มีท่ากิมและทรัพยากรจำกัด จึงมีฐานะทางเศรษฐกิจที่ไม่สามารถรับภาระค่าใช้จ่ายด้านสุขภาพได้ สามารถกล่าวได้ว่า มีความสัมพันธ์ระหว่างภาวะสุขภาพของชนบทและสถานะทางเศรษฐกิจ สังคมและวัฒนธรรม สาเหตุที่นำเสนอมานี้มีความเกี่ยวเนื่องกันระหว่างสุขภาพและชีวิตที่หนึ่งของผู้ที่ชาวชนบทที่เกี่ยวข้องกับสุขภาพของประชาชนในรัฐ Karnataka เขตอินเดียตอนใต้

คำสำคัญ: สุขภาวะ ชนบท โรค ป่าเขี้ยวสุขภาพด้านสุขภาพ ภาวะสุขภาพ

INTRODUCTION

In all human society, irrespective of its simplicity and complexity and no matter how small or big, no matter how advanced or traditional, there exist simple or complex health issues. Strasser (2010) wrote, "In all developing countries, accessibility to rural and remote communities is exaggerated by the physical topography, with mountains, deserts and jungles creating difficulties for transportation, at times complicated by varying climatic conditions. As a result, in some areas, at least some of the time, there is no means of transportation, and evacuation of critically ill or injured patients is impossible. The standard and quality of communications between diverse rural and remote areas and between those communities and the urban centers is also very variable."

Health is not only a stable state of physical and natural well being but also in a true sense it involves various other complex issues. It is a widely known fact that health is one of the imperative

since time immemorial. A healthy community is vital because it can set the destiny of the any society or country. Healthy human resources allow any type of development or any kind of achievement. Health is a vital, integrated component of an individual or a community. Sometime the collapse of one's health may even lead toward an early death. Furthermore, an unhealthy community may be hinder the holistic growth and development of any society. Poor health status of any community may isolate that community from the mainstream of the society. There are some external determinants which can decide the health status of the rural people including socio-economic, environmental, and the availability of hospitals, doctors, and health infrastructure. It significantly depends on some internal factors including one's health culture, education, health practices, *et cetera*.

Basically, India is a land of villages. Since independence, the government of India has implemented several programs to improve the health conditions of rural people. However, growing regional and gender disparities have become a big challenge for the rural health sector. Today, Indian rural people are frequently facing both communicable and non-communicable health disorders. A scientifically based primary health care center is still a distant dream, even though HIV/AIDS is also gradually spreading among rural folk. Life expectancy among rural folk is also gradually decreasing. The infant mortality rate is 85 per 1,000 live births and the maternal mortality rate is around 445 per 100,000 live births. Reports indicate that more than 73 percent of the rural people in south Karnataka do not have access to modern, curative, and preventive health care facilities (Health and Family Welfare Survey Report, 2000). It was found that only 24.6 percent of doctors are serving in rural areas and a large disparity in the presence of government hospitals between rural and urban parts of the country can be seen. For the period 1905 to 2000, the life expectancy at birth was 60.36 years

1991, the sex ratio was 920 females for 1,000 males in rural parts of Karnataka. After introducing the National Rural Health Mission Programme, maternal and child health programs have been improved significantly in rural areas and an immunization program in rural areas has progressed. Some of the programs, like the upgrading of primary health centers and sub centers, are underway. Today, almost all public health centers are working all day every day. Strong measures have been taken to control endemic diseases. Regular, free health checkups are undertaken.

However a reasonable disparity in rural health can be seen today in most rural parts because of: 1) a lack of cultural-specific rural health policies; low expenditure on the health sector in the budget; 3) the absence of rural infrastructure; and 4) a low participation rate by rural people in developmental issues (Health and Family Welfare Survey Report, 2008).

Experts have observed that poor living standards and unhygienic conditions are the factors responsible for the frequent outbreaks of various communicable diseases in rural areas. Nowadays, due to the usage of more pesticides and chemical fertilizers, there are increased health hazards for rural people. Mother and child healthcare practices in rural areas are pathetic. However, in certain cases, the young, educated, rural generation is showing more interest toward modern healthcare. Discrimination against women in health care normally exists in rural areas and it is often studied only as a part of the overall pattern of discrimination against women. As far as women's health is concerned, these experts have opined 'what has been observed is that most of the parameters are often defined in such a manner that discrimination is not even apparent'. Studies have revealed that in rural areas, women run the household, doing cooking, collection of water, fuel, fodder, agricultural work, and looking after the children among other tasks. Such activities invariably affects the health of

Furthermore, Kathathrya (2004) has written, "It may be worthwhile to state that at least one component of health is universally seen among the rural societies, and that is, committing or omitting certain acts, in other words a breach of trust is thought to bring upon some kind of affliction on the individual or a family as a whole. Measles, tuberculosis, diarrhea, cholera may cause some diseases where individual's action may cause some concern to the family, clan or the village".

In rural areas, people normally think that being unable to work is the general index of illness. Even though the basic concept of illness changes from caste to caste in rural areas, a person will be declared as diseased if he/she cannot perform day-to-day work. It is expected that a healthy person should work normally without having any problems. Hence sociologists have concluded that in rural areas, illness is more related to functional rather than clinical or biological factors. Hence, sometimes people having a mild fever, headache, cough, wounds, or giddiness will not be considered as ill because their symptoms will not hamper their normal routine work. Usually people don't bother with such symptoms.

In the majority of cases, people normally do not consider that health status depends on sanitation. Rather, rural people connect their illness problems to fate and thereby to supernatural powers. People believe there are some benevolent and malevolent supernatural powers. Benevolent supernaturals do good things to human beings while the latter harm mankind. People believe continuous worshipping of benevolent powers brings good deeds to the family. Beard, Tomaska, Earnest, Summerhayes, and Morgan (2009) have opined that 'socioeconomic and cultural factors have long been thought to influence an individual's health and they suggested a framework for characterizing these factors that comprises individual-level (individual socioeconomic status, sex, race) and neighborhood-level dimensions (population composition, social environment,

and through interaction'. Recent spatial research suggests that in rural communities, socioeconomic disadvantage and indigenous status are two of the greatest underlying influences on health status. However, rural communities also face additional challenges associated with access to and utilization of health care (Beard et al., 2009).

Health issues in rural people are many and diverse; they vary from fever to acute respiratory tract infection and sometimes cholera and cancer. *Post partum* illness also causes maternal mortality in rural India. Rural people in Karnataka have traditional belief toward health and illness. Some rural people are still practicing traditional healing approaches with other types of established medical systems because of their unique social, economic, and cultural background is also responsible for the onset of various communicable and non-communicable diseases. Various infectious diseases are reported to cause morbidity in rural areas. In addition, 0.30 million deaths occur in rural areas because of water-borne diseases in rural Karnataka and typhoid, cholera, and warm infections are common in rural areas causing 0.60 million deaths. About 1,000 malarial deaths occur annually in rural India. Only 26 percent of rural pregnant women had an antenatal checkup. Furthermore, health issues were related to snakebites, dog bites, and mishandling pesticides among others. Rural folk face oral problems, respiratory infections, addictions, and gynecological problems, with some of these being highly seasonal (Advani & Akram, 2007).

Strasser (2010) has opined that 'with the concentration of poverty, low health status and high burden of disease in rural areas, there is a need to focus specifically on improving the health of people in rural and remote areas, particularly if the urban drift is to be reversed. The WHO International Development Programme has highlighted this, with specific objectives for policies and action which promote sustainable livelihoods including access for

better education, health, and opportunities for rural people'. These objectives seek to contribute to lowering child and maternal mortality, and to improving basic health care for all, including reproductive services. Achievement of this is linked to the protection and better management of the natural and physical environment.

Objective

The major aim of this study was to review the current health issues and health infrastructure in rural parts of south Karnataka State, India.

METHODOLOGY

This study has been carried out in two stages, using two different methodological approaches.

Documentary analysis

In the first phase, a review of relevant policy documents reflecting India's health policy from the past 15 years has been carried out utilizing a literature review, analysis of policy documents, and some secondary data analysis. The search strategy involved contacting general libraries and university libraries, leading non-governmental organizations, and government offices. In addition, a search was conducted of electronic databases for relevant studies conducted from 1990 to 2012. Relevant data have been extracted from each paper and synthesized through a narrative review that includes descriptive characteristics as well as more substantive issues such as the budget for the health sector, the outbreak of various diseases, the impact and failure of certain health policies, and gaps in the research.

Interview/Consultation

In the second stage, key informant interviews were conducted with rural stakeholders and individuals knowledgeable about public health policies. Such interviews were very useful for

factors, public debate, and variation in health infrastructure in rural areas. The interviews were semi-structured.

Interviews or consultation involved three groups of stakeholders: 1) experts from the leading health research institutes, health policy makers, and other developmental agencies; 2) senior academic experts in the health field; and 3) directors and executives from local and national statutory and volunteer bodies.

About Karnataka State

Karnataka state is situated in South India and is the eighth largest state of the country covering 74,122 square miles. The capital city of the state is Bangalore which is an information technology hub of the world and is also known as Silicon Valley. Karnataka is bordered by the Arabian Sea to the West. With 61,130,704 inhabitants, more than half of the population is rural (Health and Family Welfare Survey Report, 2000).

FINDINGS

In general, rural areas are marked by poor implementation of health facilities or health infrastructure. Various governments have implemented many rural specific health programs. A high concentration of infectious diseases, the absence of

effective health education, a lack of fundamental facilities, and problems in implementation are adversely affecting rural health. Even today, there are no good road facilities to many remote villages across the country and thus, new medical technologies have not yet reached the many villages in the country.

The plight of rural people has drawn increasing policy attention since 1960. Even so, today, the majority of rural people are suffering with various communicable and non-communicable diseases (Tables 1 and 2). It is stated there is a positive correlation between the health status of the rural people and their social, economic, and cultural background. In India, where rural people have been significantly altered socially and culturally by the British colonization, it is crucial to understand the social and cultural consequences of colonization and how these have altered the health culture and health behavior of rural dwellers historically and currently.

According to the various studies, there are numerous public health issues with respect to the rural Karnataka, including: malnutrition, various communicable diseases, failure of family planning, a high infant mortality rate, issues of sanitation and hygiene, a shortage of safe drinking water, cultural health beliefs, and poor health infrastructure (Kshathrya, 2004).

Table 1 Infectious diseases in rural areas in Karnataka (Annual base)

Indicator	Percentage
Typhoid	14.67
Jaundice	12.70
Cholera	15.80
Diarrhea	17.80
Malaria	23.00
Viral fever	19.20
Dengue	7.10
Plague	3.10
...	...

Malnutrition

The World Health Organization (1985) found that 57 percent of the deaths of under-five-year-old children in developing countries were accompanied by malnutrition and a low weight for their age. Furthermore, 47 percent of rural children today are facing severe malnutrition problems and this figure is even greater than in many African countries. Due to malnutrition, social and cognitive development is impeded. Malnutrition and childhood mortality have become a serious

problem among rural children and their social-cultural background, health, behavior, and health culture dynamics play significant roles as vital determinants of the health status of a particular community. Hence, malnutrition and childhood mortality are more common in rural areas as good health requires a balanced diet (Verbrugge, 1985). The under-five-year-olds need a good nutritional diet which is rare in many rural settings in the country and this causes mortality and morbidity in rural areas.

Nearly 3 million rural children in India die before the age of five due to various health issues. The infant mortality rate and the under-five mortality rate are good indicators of health and the quality of life of any given community. Reports shows that various child health indicators of the country have improved considerably and infant mortality has declined from 78 to 57 deaths per

1,000 live births and under-five mortality from 109 to 74 deaths per 1,000 live births. However, the under-five mortality level among rural children is still shockingly high (at 97 deaths per 1,000 live births). Rural people constitute 60 to 62 percent of the total population, but account for about 19 percent of all under-five deaths, and 23 percent of deaths are in the one- to five-year age group (Health Family Welfare Survey Report, 2006).

Reports have shown that poverty, illiteracy, malnutrition, scarcity of potable water, sanitary conditions, poor mother-child health services, and problems in providing national health and nutritional services, among others are the most important causative factors for the prevalence of severe childhood mortality and morbidity amongst rural communities in India. Despite marvelous development focusing on preventive and curative medicine, the child healthcare delivery services in several rural communities are still poor and unscientific and need to be further strengthened to achieve the goal of health for all in the country (Health Family Welfare Survey Report, 2006).

Various communicable diseases

Rural people are more prone to have many communicable diseases such as malaria, jaundice, tuberculosis, cholera. In many parts of rural India, diarrhea is the prime cause of early childhood mortality. It has been reported that more than 7,000

Table 2 Other types of health problems in rural areas in Karnataka (Annual base)

Disease	Percentage
Infants	34.5
Heart and kidney problem	13.6
Cancers	7.9
Abortions	11.8
Mental problems	9.5
Snake and other bites	21.6
Chemical manures	16.8
Skin related	11.8
Bone and liver related	17.8

rural people die annually because of various communicable diseases. Malaria and jaundice has become common in rural areas because of poor sanitation (Health Family Welfare Survey Report, 2006).

Failure of family planning

Due to the various social and cultural beliefs, family planning programs have failed in many rural areas of the country. Poor contraceptive materials also become a problem in rural areas. Rural people are still using traditional types of family planning which have mixed results.

High infant mortality rate

It was found that 0.7 million rural children die each year before reaching their first birthday. Under-five mortality and infant mortality are also big issues in rural health care. Due to cultural beliefs, rural people are not showing much interest in immunization and prevention care. Diarrhea and respiratory infections are also responsible for high infant mortality in many remote parts of the country (Health Family Welfare Survey Report, 2006).

Issues of sanitation and hygiene

Even today, considerable numbers of rural households have no toilet facilities. Only about 21 percent of Indian rural families use a closed toilet whereas nearly 80 percent of the population are still using open spaces. Open air defecation also spreads infections which is also a major issue in rural parts (Health Family Welfare Survey Report, 2006).

Shortage of safe drinking water

This has caused a severe problem in rural areas as some time people have to walk long distances together to get safe, potable water and the use of contaminated water also causes various infectious diseases in rural areas. The ground water level is also decreasing due to the repeated failures in the monsoon rain. The presence of arsenic and

rural health.

Cultural health beliefs

It was found that the social-cultural background, health behavior, and health cultural dynamics plays a significant role as vital determinants of the health status of particular rural communities. Malnutrition and childhood mortality have become a serious problem among rural children in India and they are more common in rural areas. More than 57 percent of deaths of under-five children in developing countries are accompanied by under-nutrition, low weight for their age and this is largely due to the various cultural health beliefs with respect to diet. Anthropologists have revealed that the development of health culture in the rural environment should be examined as a sub cultural complex of the entire way of life. There are a number of forces percolating from the larger socio-economic environment and directed through the attributes of historical, social, and political dimensions to the development of the pattern of their health culture in given rural settings (Banerji, 1986).

Poor health infrastructure

Modern healthcare facilities and hospitals are being concentrated only in urban areas (Table 3). Even today, most villages don't have enough primary health centers as sub centers. The majority of rural hospitals are lacking doctors and other paramedical staff. Some of hospitals in rural areas don't have enough health infrastructure.

TRENDS IN HEALTH STATUS IN

RURAL INDIA

In 2000, the life expectancy at birth was around 62.36 years for males and 64.39 for female. In 1991, the sex ratio was 920 females for 1,000 males in rural areas. Action has been taken to

applying a war footing to rural health infrastructure. Maternal and child health programs have been improved in rural areas. Immunization programs in rural areas have also increased. Some of the programs involve upgrading primary health centre and sub centers. Today, almost all rural public health centers (PHC) are on an all-day, every-day schedule; however, the majority have insufficient infrastructure. Strong measures have been taken to control endemic diseases through PHC, however, such diseases have not been eradicated. Regular, free health checkups are being undertaken through NGOs with some success (Advani & Akram 2007).

Mortality

It was reported that the infant mortality rate was 65 in every 1,000 live births in 1994 and in 1998, and the maternal mortality ratio during 1998 was estimated at 415 per 100,000 live births. Furthermore, around 0.54 million children under five years were dying from diarrhea in 2010 with around 0.32 million dying from acute lung problems and the same number from cholera. In addition, around 0.2 million children are affected every year by malaria in rural areas, while 0.5 million people die from heart-related diseases, 11,675 in traffic accidents and 1,143 from occupation-related accidents (Advani, & Akram 2007).

The crude death rate has been slowly decreasing. In 1998, infant mortality was 112 per 1,000 live births and now it has declined to 32 per 1,000 live births. It was reported that the following diseases are the most common causes of death in rural areas (in descending order as at 2009): cholera (63%), jaundice (57%), malaria (41%), typhoid (62%), and dengue fever (22%) (Rural Health Statistics in India, 2010). Deaths due to non-communicable diseases (in descending order as at 2009) were: heart problems (blockage of veins), acute lung problems (due to smoking), liver damage (due to alcohol), kidney problems (due to modern life style), and oral cancer (due to using Jarda and Beeda) according to Rural Health Statistics in India (2010). Other causes of death in rural areas include: severe injury (32%), poisoning by snake bite (31%), and parasitic diseases due to using pesticides (13%) according to Rural Health Statistics in India (2011).

Morbidity

Mortality and morbidity are good indicators of the health status of any community. Morbidity focuses on the death of people due to various problems after certain years. In 1999, around 0.6 million leprosy cases, around 0.2 million tuberculosis (TB) cases and around 0.27 million malaria cases were reported which indicate that as a

Table 3 Comparison of health care services in rural and urban areas

Indicators	Total	Urban	Rural
Infant mortality rate	42.00	36.00	48.00
Birth rate	22.80	18.50	24.40
Death rate	7.40	5.90	8.00
Total fertility rate	2.70	2.10	3.00
Pure drinking water	89.00	96.00	86.00
Sanitation	28.00	18.00	52.00
Under weight children	40.40	30.10	43.70
Adult education	66.00	80.30	59.40
Immunization	43.50	52.60	38.60
AWL treatment	50.70	73.80	42.80
Health care service	40.80	40.40	40.40

result of an intensive vaccination program, the death rate in under-five children is declining in rural parts of Karnataka. However, even today, there are 0.3 million deaths in rural areas every year due to tuberculosis even after implementing the DOTS scheme (a special program to curb TB) to eradicate the problem. However the rate has dropped to 0.2 million and the problem is declining. The prevalence rate of leprosy is also decreasing due to the limited success of multi drug therapy. After introducing some awareness programs in rural areas of the state, the number of people dying from various life threatening diseases has decreased gradually. (Karnataka Glance Report, 2012).

Disability

Reported disability statistics for every 1,000,000 people in rural areas of Karnataka state in 2004 include: physical disability (7,571), visual disability (2,110), hearing disability (900), speech disability (650), and locomotive diseases (1,041). In addition, 3.3 million were blind due to cataracts and eye-related issues (Karnataka Glance Report, 2012).

HEALTH INFRASTRUCTURE IN

RURAL KARNATAKA

Rural health infrastructure has been

Table 4 Infrastructure facilities

Sl no	Facility	Number per 1,000,000 population
1	Public health centers	38
2	Sub centers	140
3	Community health centers	6
4	Rural hospitals	8
5	Urban hospitals	8
6	Total hospitals	16
7	Total beds	1096
8	No. of doctors at public health centers	48
9	No. of health assistants at public health centers	34
10	No. of health workers at public health centers	703

neglected for a long time as governments have given low priorities to rural health issues (Table 4). Even after introducing the NRHM program, the situation has not improved completely (Tables 5 and 6).

Reducing funds for rural health issues in India is also a big issue in recent times. Many rural areas are facing a shortage of qualified doctors and other paramedical staff. In some rural areas, untrained doctors and under-trained doctors are practicing which is a great threat to the rural community. Various studies have found that lifestyle-related diseases and illnesses are more common in rural areas where the low economic status also creates more stress on these communities (Sinha, 2000). The absence of mental health care facilities has also increased the severity of the rural problem. Moreover, smoking, alcohol, shortages of medicines, and low nutrition foods have also contributed to the poor health status in rural India. The World Health Organization has also advised developing countries to decentralize health issues and strengthen the health surveillance system, especially in rural areas. Emerging technologies can be used to serve the needs of rural people. There is a need for an area-specific, innovative health education program as a part of preventive measures. There is a requirement in new program guidelines to create awareness even at the school level on health issues, health NGOs, and health workers to co-ordinate

Table 5 Selected health indicators in Karnataka and India

Sl. No.	Items	Karnataka	India
1	Life expectancy at birth	65.30	63.50
2	Infant mortality rate	41.00	50.00
3	Under-five mortality rate	54.70	74.30
4	Percentage of persons not expected to survive beyond the age of 40 years	14.60	17.70
5	Percentage of women adult population with BMI < 18.5	35.50	33.00
6	Percentage of men adult population with (Body Mass Index) BMI < 18.5	33.90	34.20
7	Percentage of women with anemia	51.50	55.30
8	Percentage of children (0-5 years) with anemia	70.40	69.50
9	Death rate	7.20	7.30
10	Public expenditure on health as a percentage to Gross Domestic Product	0.87	2.02
11	Per capita public expenditure on health	233.00	1014.00
12	Per capita private expenditure on health	597.00	1639.00
13	Public expenditure on health as a percentage to total health expenditure	71.90	58.30
14	Private expenditure on health as a percentage to total health expenditure	28.10	41.70

Source: Health and Family Welfare Survey (Round 3) Report (2011)

Table 6 Division-wise selected health infrastructure facilities in Karnataka, 2010

Facility	Belgaum					Gulbarga					Bangalore					Mysore					North					South					Karnataka				
	Per 100,000 population					Per 100,000 population					Per 100,000 population					Per 100,000 population					Per 100,000 population					Per 100,000 population									
District and other hospitals	0.9	(4)	1	(3)	1.2	(2)	1.4	(1)	1	(1)	1.3	(1)	1.1	(1)	1.1	(1)	1.4	(1)	1	(1)	1.3	(1)	1.1	(1)	1.1	(1)	1.1	(1)	1.1	(1)					
Community health centers	5.5	(3)	6.5	(2)	3.4	(4)	7.4	(1)	5.9	(3)	4.8	(4)	5.3	(3)	5.3	(3)	7.4	(1)	5.9	(3)	4.8	(4)	5.3	(3)	5.3	(3)	5.3	(3)	5.3	(3)					
PHCs and Sub centers	154	(2)	142	(3)	135	(4)	271	(1)	149	(2)	184	(4)	169	(2)	169	(2)	271	(1)	149	(2)	184	(4)	169	(2)	169	(2)	169	(2)	169	(2)					
Total beds	764	(3)	789	(2)	737	(4)	1196	(1)	775	(3)	901	(4)	847	(2)	847	(2)	1196	(1)	775	(3)	901	(4)	847	(2)	847	(2)	847	(2)	847	(2)					
District and other hospitals	2.6	(3)	2.5	(4)	5.4	(1)	3.9	(2)	2.5	(4)	4.7	(3)	3.6	(2)	3.6	(2)	5.4	(1)	2.5	(4)	4.7	(3)	3.6	(2)	3.6	(2)	3.6	(2)	3.6	(2)					
Community health centers	14.9	(4)	16.6	(2)	15.5	(3)	21.4	(1)	15.6	(3)	18.2	(4)	16.9	(2)	16.9	(2)	21.4	(1)	15.6	(3)	18.2	(4)	16.9	(2)	16.9	(2)	16.9	(2)	16.9	(2)					
PHCs and Sub centers	418	(3)	365	(4)	614	(2)	783	(1)	394	(4)	693	(3)	539	(2)	539	(2)	783	(1)	394	(4)	693	(3)	539	(2)	539	(2)	539	(2)	539	(2)					
Total beds	2070	(3)	2019	(4)	3337	(2)	3455	(1)	2047	(4)	3392	(3)	2701	(2)	2701	(2)	3455	(1)	2047	(4)	3392	(3)	2701	(2)	2701	(2)	2701	(2)	2701	(2)					

Note: Figures in the parentheses are rankings
Source: Karnataka Glance Report (2012)

Per 10,000 square km area

activities. There is general awareness that the rural population has inadequate access to health care, and the poor placement of medical and paramedical staff in rural districts is also under question while maternal and child mortality rates in Karnataka are also under scrutiny. All these factors play a role in the diminishing rural health care service in many rural parts of Karnataka. It was found that at least six to seven births take place every day without the supervision of any doctor at many general hospitals in the state. Sometimes one sub center must cater for around three to five villages at a time. Proper documentation on patients is also a large problem due to inadequate human resources (Health and Family Welfare Survey, 2011).

When the health culture is strongly influenced by the external organics (level of education, migration, media *et cetera*) in a particular geographical area, rural people will develop new health behavior. This adoption will lead to new health seeking behavior to resolve the health problems within the given ecological settings (Parson, 1963). This type of forced change in the health behavior of a particular community sometimes will be explicit and sometimes will be implicit. Government and NGOs needs to look into the cultural fabric of rural health for speedy social inclusion before framing any new public health policies (Wilkinson, 1996).

CONCLUSION

Anthropologists have revealed that the development of the health culture of the rural environment should be examined as a sub cultural complex of the entire way of life. There are a number of forces percolating from the larger socio-economic environment and directed through the attributes of historical, social, and political dimensions to the development of the pattern of the health culture in the given rural settings. The general health status of rural people is worse than in urban

areas. The infant mortality rate in rural areas is 1.5 times that of urban areas. Poverty, low health status, and the high burden of diseases are rampant in rural areas. The World Health Organization in its program

has specifically advised developing countries to focus more on sustainable development including the regeneration of agricultural activities, natural resources, and quality health care. Achievements in these issues might lead toward better management of the natural and physical environment. Good health is a way out of poverty. Good health status may contribute to producing economic assets. Poor health may also decrease the productive capacity of rural people. The rates of avoidable deaths in rural areas are higher than in cities. It was found that work injuries are higher in rural areas and people will normally ignore the consequence of these injuries which may some time lead to losing an organ or body part. Unlike in urban areas, rural communities have different cultures and a particular sense of behavioral norms. Social roles and functions among rural people are supported by historical religious practices. Good rural medical healthcare has become a nightmare. In many parts of the country, the poor transport system and the underdeveloped medical infrastructure also cause delays in shifting patients to good hospitals. Sometime it is impossible to evacuate patients because of remoteness and the bad communication system.

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วารสาร รัฐประศาสนศาสตร์
THAI JOURNAL OF

PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION

Volume 14 • Number 2 • July-December 2016

ISSN: 0859-418x

บทบรรณาธิการ

The Growth and Development Effects of Public Education, Health, and Welfare Spending in ASEAN

Ponlapat Buracom

Intergovernmental Transfer in Thailand: A Test of Horizontal Equity

Darunee Punkaew

Caste, Discrimination, and Social Exclusion in Public Health Administration

Untold Indian Experiences

Devajana Chinnappa Nanjunda

กระบวนทัศน์ใหม่ในการบริหารท้องถิ่น

อำนาจ บัญญัติ ปันนิตวี วัฒนา นนทชิต และ อภินชัช งามนัครี

การศึกษาร่วมมือด้านการจัดการสาธารณสุขขององค์กรปกครองส่วนท้องถิ่น:

กรณีศึกษา เทศบาลเมืองร้อยเอ็ดและองค์การบริหารองศาพื้นที่งันข้างเคียง

สุนทรชัย ชอบยศ

การย้ายถิ่นอย่างไม่ปกติของคนต่างด้าวชาวพม่าสู่ถิ่นในเขตพื้นที่ภาคใต้ของไทย

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Caste, Discrimination, and Social Exclusion in Public Health Administration: Untold Indian Experiences

Devajana Chinnappa Nanjunda*

Abstract

Caste, poverty and social exclusion are closely interrelated to health in any prismatic society. Caste and social exclusion have a multidimensional consequence on the social determinants of health and bear an elevated threat of various diseases among the margins. Also this issue has a likelihood of being excluded from the quality health care services. The issue of social exclusion and public health has received wide attention in India in the era of globalization. It is argued that poverty leads to poor health, and poor health is also one of the major factors for social exclusion and poverty. In a prismatic society like India, the caste plays a predominant role in causing social exclusion and thereby various types of health inequalities. Some socially excluded groups are living in extremely poor conditions in rural parts even today. In India SC (Scheduled Castes), ST (Scheduled Tribes), OBC (Other Backward Castes), and minority (Muslims, Christians, etc.) groups are considered as socially excluded groups and have been deprived of good health status for various reasons. This current study has been conducted in South Karnataka-India on selected socially excluded groups to obtain their opinion and experiences through the use of a questionnaire.

The conclusion is that caste and social exclusion are vital factors accounting for the fact that certain sectors of society even today cannot access quality public health care services in India.

Keywords: Health, caste, discrimination, social exclusion, poverty

วรรณะ การเลือกปฏิบัติ และการกีดกันทางสังคมในการจัดการ สาธารณสุข: ประสบการณ์ที่ถูกปิดบังในประเทศไทยอินเดีย

Devajana Chinakappa Nanjunda*

บทคัดย่อ

การแบ่งชั้นวรรณะ ความยากจน และการกีดกันทางสังคมมีความสัมพันธ์อย่างใกล้ชิดกับสุขภาพของประชาชนในทุกการเปลี่ยนแปลงผ่านของสังคม วรรณะและการกีดกันทางสังคมส่งผลต่อการตัดสินใจสุขภาพตามกาลเวลาชีวิต ท่ามกลางช่องว่างทางสังคม ประเด็นนี้ทำให้โรคภัยต่าง ๆ ที่ความเลวร้ายมากยิ่งขึ้น นอกจากนี้ ประเด็นดังกล่าวยังมีแนวโน้มอย่างมากรอคอยการแบ่งแยกคุณภาพการบริหารสาธารณสุข ซึ่งเป็นผลพวงจากโลกาภิวัตน์ในรูปแบบเฉพาะของอินเดีย ในสังคมเปลี่ยนผ่าน เช่น อินเดีย การแบ่งชั้นวรรณะเป็นต้นเหตุสำคัญของารกีดกันทางสังคมและความไม่เท่าเทียมเกี่ยวกับสุขภาพของประชาชนจนถึงปัจจุบัน กลุ่มทางสังคมที่ถูกแบ่งแยกบางกลุ่มถูกปฏิบัติอยู่ในสภาพที่เลวร้ายในภาคชนบท แม้ในปัจจุบัน ในอินเดีย นั้น จัณชาติ กลุ่มชนเผ่าที่ถูกปฏิบัติ วรรณะชั้นต่ำอื่น ๆ และชนกลุ่มน้อย เช่น มุสลิม คริสเตียน เป็นต้น ต่างถูกมองเป็นว่าส่วนเกินของรัฐคณาฎกะตอนใต้ (South Karnataka) ของประเทศอินเดีย มีการเก็บรวบรวมข้อมูลโดยใช้คำถามแบบมีโครงสร้างกับกลุ่มทางสังคมที่ถูกละเลย เพื่อสอบถามความคิดเห็นและประสบการณ์จริง และสรุปได้ว่า การแบ่งชั้นวรรณะและการกีดกันทางสังคมเป็นปัจจัยสำคัญที่ทำให้บางภาคส่วนของสังคมในปัจจุบันไม่สามารถเข้าถึงการสาธารณสุขที่มีคุณภาพในประเทศไทยอินเดีย

คำสำคัญ: สุขภาพ วรรณะ การเลือกปฏิบัติ การกีดกันทางสังคม ความยากจน

Background

India is extremely multiracial, multilingual, multicultural and mainly a caste based prismatic society. Ethical or caste based social exclusion is commonly found and persistent in Indian society, especially in rural regions. Poverty, socioeconomic, politics and other issues are obviously connected to caste and cultural-lingual character. Poverty and social exclusion in India have roots in India's historical divisions between castes and tribes. Many socio-culturally entrenched old age systems have brought health inequality among margins. Poverty creates inequality and prevents these groups from getting quality healthcare in the country.

The significance of good health cannot be minimized and it has been considered as one of the significant components of human capital. Good health is an indication of strong mind. Due to its vital importance, health economics is attracting researchers and policy makers more speedily in current decades. It is well said in the theory of human capital that people should invest themselves in terms of education, health and skill development programs. If the quality of human capital is not good, physical capital and natural resources cannot be utilized properly and growth can neither be sustainable nor be qualitative (Mohapatra et al., 2008).

The issue of margins' health has drawn increasing attention both at the national and international level today. Criticism has been focused on poor health infrastructure and health inequalities and its impact on physical, mental, social, moral and spiritual health of excluded groups. Since 1990, the World Health Organization (WHO) has emphasized improving the health status of the margins across the developing countries and stressing promotion of public health administrations. Also some health scientists are focusing on how communities evaluate the risk associated with health discrimination on future generations and the socio-cultural barriers in getting modern medical healthcare facilities and how to overcome this issue (Kesterton et al., 2010).

What Is Social Exclusion?

This term is being used in different countries in different ways, including:

In India:

“Social exclusion is the denial of the basic welfare rights which provide citizens positive freedom to participate in the social and economic and political life and which thereby render meaningful their fundamental negative freedoms.” (Gore & Figueiredo, 1997: 17-18)

In Thailand:

“Social exclusion is a process through which citizenship rights on which livelihood and living standards depend are not recognized and respected. This involves relationships between people, in which rights are challenged and defended through negotiations and conflict.” (Gore & Figueiredo, 1997: 17-18)

Issues of exclusion and discrimination assume particular significance in the Indian context. In India, the list of social groups experiencing some form of inequality or social exclusion is immense, although possibly most frequently mentioned, and most numerous, are the *Dalits* or *Untouchables* (Constitutionally declared as Scheduled Castes/SC) and *Adivasis/Natives* (Constitutionally declared as Scheduled Tribes/ST). Other Backward Castes (OBCs) and Minorities (Muslims, Christians etc.) who together make up about more than sixty-eight percent of the total population of India and are facing severe exclusion and discrimination in various sectors including health. Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes are the major excluded sections in Indian society. “Scheduled Castes” is a term given to the section which have usually occupied the lowest status in Indian society, and the Hindu religion provides the religious and ideological basis for an “untouchable” group outside

the caste system and inferior to all other castes (web based). Scheduled Tribes/ST are also at the lowest status in Indian society. They mostly live in the forests of remote parts of the country. Backward Castes (OBC) is a combined word used to categorize castes that are socially and educationally deprived in India. However, the total number of STs are very small when compared to all other groups. Despite widespread economic growth and prosperity in current times, these communities have traditionally been deserted and left out of the process of development, including health. Their exclusion can be witnessed in a lack of access (or unequal access) to various institutions, to public services (education, healthcare, etc.), to public places, including temples, and to many income-earning assets, particularly land. Their socioeconomic status is very distressing, and they are denied quality public healthcare services (Kulkarni & Baraik, 2003).

Achary (2010: 34) writes,

“As an attribute of individuals, caste-based discrimination focuses directly on the health status of SCs and disadvantages their experience. Discrimination in access to health care service can thus, be understood through three basic forms.. a) Complete exclusion or complete denial of health care services, b) Partial denial or selected exclusion of health care services.”

Data from the 2005-2006 National Family Health Survey (NFHS-3) reports the caste differentials with respect to health status in India. This regular survey stresses the reduced or low access to quality maternal and child healthcare among the SCs and STs. Accordingly, infant and under-five mortality among the SCs and the STs are quite high. The prevalence of anemia is also very high among the lower castes. Also it is quite apparent that the level of ante-natal and post-natal care is very low among these margins. Furthermore, it is found that institutional deliveries and essential vaccination coverage among these excluded groups are also very low. In addition, it shows a low level of contraceptive usage among the excluded groups (Iaroh, 2009). The NFHS-2 (1995-96) had similar results

Table 1. Poverty Incidence by Socio-Religious Groups and Household Types in India (2004-2005)

Religions	Rural			Urban					
	Social Groups	SENA	AL	OL	SEA	SE	RW/SE	CL	OTH
Hindu	ST	39.03	61.92	46.24	46.39	49.84	15.93	71.15	17.16
	SC	33.91	49.07	35.08	27.41	47.36	24.35	65.67	28.07
	OBC	21.73	43.70	29.30	21.31	30.99	16.87	54.57	18.60
Muslim	OTH	9.53	31.21	14.81	11.00	11.72	7.33	37.00	7.60
	ST	1.84	62.88	-	26.67	25.76	0.35	83.75	9.59
	SC	45.65	62.34	-	46.38	46.51	46.31	39.86	63.13
Christian	OBC	30.42	49.72	28.86	26.78	46.88	32.99	57.67	40.20
	OTH	26.39	42.56	32.18	19.77	37.41	33.34	62.05	25.90
	ST	12.42	35.10	32.90	23.00	17.37	5.98	40.30	7.70
Sikh	SC	40.54	26.31	42.63	52.00	28.68	10.86	64.70	6.35
	OBC	5.02	32.23	9.27	10.83	11.70	5.17	39.88	12.00
	OTH	-	21.67	5.49	3.32	8.74	3.57	20.06	5.24
Buddhist	ST	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	SC	3.31	11.66	7.53	-	18.28	16.53	50.98	1.08
	OBC	3.89	13.09	15.29	-	6.20	7.10	7.25	9.95
All	OTH	-	17.69	0.26	-	1.07	2.85	22.11	0.10
	ST	5.40	2.26	27.24	8.65	0.94	0.30	-	0.79
	SC	28.14	57.66	50.05	20.95	36.91	11.97	55.10	20.97
All	OBC	57.70	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	OTH	-	-	27.07	2.96	56.14	90.10	-	-
	ST	36.33	60.81	45.29	42.98	42.03	13.57	69.70	14.96
All	SC	32.87	47.84	33.76	27.27	46.01	23.28	64.59	27.26
	OBC	23.02	43.70	28.45	21.42	34.37	17.84	54.59	22.20
	OTH	15.51	35.27	19.71	11.98	17.57	11.00	48.44	10.51

Source: Estimated from National Sample Survey Organization, (NSSO) 61st Round.

Note: SENNA = Self-employed in Non-agriculture

AL = Agricultural Labour

SEA = Self-employed in Agriculture

SE = Self Employed

RW/SE = Regular Wage and Salary Earners

Table 2. Different Types of Mortality over the Five Years Prior to the Survey

Excluded groups	Neonatal mortality	Post neonatal mortality	Infant mortality	Percent of Under Five deaths (Urban)	Percent of Under Five deaths (Rural)
SC	35.0	15.8	50.7	28.1	24.6
ST	29.0	14.9	43.8	23.0	13.9
OBC	26.4	15.8	42.2	35.1	38.6
Minorities	21.6	13.9	35.5	33.0	21.9

Source: National Family Health Survey (NFHS), 2005.

Table 3. HIV Prevalence Rate (15-49 Age Group) by Social Group

Excluded groups	Percentage of HIV positive (Women)	Percentage of HIV positive (Men)	Total percentage
SC	0.23	0.34	0.28
ST	0.12	0.36	0.25
OBC	0.24	0.34	0.30
Minorities	0.06	0.21	0.13

Source: National Family Health Survey, 2005-06.

Table 4. Percentage of Children Under Age Five Years Classified as Malnourished According to Three Anthropometric Indices of Nutritional Status by Social Group

Indices	Weight-for-Age		
	Percentage below -3SD	Percentage below -2SD	Percentage below +2SD
SC	18.5	47.9	0.3
ST	24.9	54.5	0.4
OBC	15.7	43.2	0.3
Minorities	15.6	41.8	0.4

Source: National Family Health Survey, 2005-07.

SD: standard deviations

Mean anthropometric distribution of studied children (according to weight against age, height against age and weight against height) has revealed that thirty-two percent (average) of SC children are between -3SD to -2SD and thirty-nine percent (average) of ST children are between -3SD to -2SD. In the case of OBC children, twenty-nine percent are in a group of between -3SD to -2SD. Also, in the case of minorities, twenty-eight percent of children are in a group of between -3SD to -2SD. All of these facts prove children from the disadvantaged groups are more vulnerable to malnutrition problems.

Table 5. Households Who Do Not Get Safe Drinking Water Throughout Year (Per One Thousand)

Household Social Group	Rural	Urban	Rural+Urban
ST	237	157	228
SC	131	107	126
OBC	120	87	111
Others	130	80	108
All	138	89	124

Source: NSSO Housing Conditions & Amenities in India, 2008-09.

This table quite clearly shows a lack of accessibility to drinking water for disadvantaged groups. In the case of those who reside in rural areas, 237 of the ST population and 131 of the SC population (per thousand) are not getting safe drinking water throughout the year. Also it is quite clear that in urban areas 157 of the ST population and 107 of the SC population (per thousand) are not getting safe drinking water throughout the year. For the OBC, 120 rural-based populations and 87 urban-based populations are not getting safe drinking water throughout the year. It proves that these sections of the society are deprived from receiving safe drinking water due to the caste system.

It is well known that poverty and social exclusion are significant socioeconomic variables in the health status of any social group in India. Historically, Scheduled Caste and Scheduled Tribes, Backward Castes and certain minorities are considered as socially marginal groups and these groups are living under unfavorable conditions and poverty for the past few centuries. The current health status (as depicted) and usage patterns of such disadvantaged groups is an obvious indication of their deprivation and social exclusion. There is undoubtedly a close connection between poverty and health (Nayar, 2007).

Methodology

The current study is undertaken among the selected members of the social excluded groups. This study was conducted in low profile areas of Mysore and Hassan districts (South Karnataka-India) among 87 community members from Scheduled Caste (Dalits), Scheduled Tribes (Natives), OBC (Other Backward Castes) and Minorities (Muslims, Christians, etc.) from various sections of society. These members were randomly selected and structured questionnaires were administered.

Tools for Data Collection

1. Survey
2. Interview
3. Content Analysis

Other Data Resources

Apart from the members of the socially excluded groups, the sample also covered people associated with the various health programs such as state and district health program officers, block-level health providers, health educators, government officials, NGO members, etc.

Table 6. Respondent Characteristics

Variables	Frequency (N=87)	Percentage
Age		
Just above 20	23	26.44
22-25	21	24.14
26-30	43	49.42
Educational Level		
Primary education	51	58.62
High school	23	26.44
College	10	11.49
Illiterates	3	3.45
Annual Income (In Rs.)		
50,000-75,000	23	26.44
Above 1,00,000	11	12.64
Below 25000	53	60.92
Social Group		
SC	31	35.63
ST	9	10.34
OBC	20	22.99
Minorities	27	31.04
Domicile		
Local	62	71.27
Inter district	15	17.24
Inter state	10	11.49
Occupation		
Government sector	12	13.79
Private sector	14	16.10
Informal sector	51	58.62
Other	10	11.49

Table 7. What Are the Different Health Issues among Socially Excluded Groups?

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Increasing infant, child and maternal mortality	12	13.79
Severe anemic issues	11	12.64
Different types of communicable diseases	7	8.05
More lifestyle disorders (caused because of poverty)	31	35.63
Different types reproductive health issues/HIV	17	19.54
Health issues caused because of their unique socio-cultural background	9	10.35
Total	87	100.00

Table 8. Why Is Health Inequality More Prevalent among Socially Excluded Groups?

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Social isolation and social alienation	32	36.78
Cultural and linguistic barriers	12	13.79
Poor social healthcare protections	13	14.94
Low healthcare delivery for the socially excluded	21	24.14
Poor health programs and policies	9	10.35
Total	87	100.00

Table 9. How Is Caste-Based Politics Responsible for Poor Health Outcomes?

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Castes lead to social exclusion and unfair economic arrangements	23	26.44
Caste-based distribution of power, income, goods and services	12	13.80
Caste is inextricably linked and is a proxy for socio-economic status	31	35.62
Lower castes populations are restricted from clean water, sanitation, nutrition, housing, education, health	6	6.90
Discrimination at health institutions	11	12.64
	4	4.60

Table 10. How Is Social Exclusion Responsible for Poor Health Outcomes at Public/Private Hospitals?

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Negligence of the hospital staff because of caste issues	12	13.80
Indifferent treatment because of caste issues when compared to others	31	35.62
Denying quality/health service, citing various unwanted reasons	21	24.14
Lack of information from the service agency	11	12.64
Abuse, intentional delay, carelessness, etc.	12	13.80
Total	87	100.00

Table 11. How Are Government Health Policies Responsible for Poor Health Outcomes for the Margins?

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Isolation or remoteness, including poor health infrastructure and poorer access to health markets and services	21	24.14
Service delivery is not being customized to undertake the "differentials" that marginal populations face	32	36.78
Decreasing Government budget for healthcare sector	12	13.79
Vulnerable groups are more exposed to adverse living conditions leading to health inequities	18	20.69
Low transparency and responsibility of health financing for the marginal population	4	4.60
Total	87	100.00

Table 12. What Would You Suggest to Combat Public Health Discrimination?

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Societal mind set should change	33	37.93
Living standards of the margins must be improved	22	25.29
More policy reform and budget required for rural health infrastructure	3	3.46
Social determinants to healthcare must be emphasized in health policies	10	11.49
Representation of various castes and classes in the government health institutions is a must	9	10.34
Active role of NGOs and civil society is required	10	11.49
Total	87	100.00

Discussion

The structural determinants of daily life contribute to the social determinants of health and fuel the inequities in healthcare among caste groups. Viewing health in general as an individual or medical issue, reducing population health to a biomedical perspective, and suggesting individual medical interventions, reflect a poor understanding of issues. Social interventions should form the core of all health and prevention programs, as individual medical interventions have little impact on population indices that require population interventions.

The socioeconomic profile of respondents shows that the mean age of the respondents was 25.1 years old. Of the caste groups, thirty-seven percent were SCs, STs ten percent, OBC twenty-three percent and the Minorities were thirty-one percent. Next, three percent of the respondents had no formal education and fifty-eight percent had studied up to a primary level and high school level (twenty-six percent). The majority (sixty percent) of the respondents are in an income group of below Rs. 25000/p.m. Regarding occupation, thirteen percent are in the government sector, one hundred and sixty-five are in the private sector and fifty-eight percent are in the informal sector. Around seventy-one percent were the local respondents.

are even more pitiable with old age service delivery channels. This has created havoc among the margins. Also, the government's budget does not currently give enough funds for all health sectors in India. Because of these factors, the death rate among the margins, even from the various curable diseases, is rising.

Conclusion

The key blockade to mainstreaming healthcare and scaling up successful interventions is caste inequality based on socio-cultural issues, especially in rural regions. The methodical favoritism and nepotism by the higher caste and the mistreatment of the lower caste populations based on culture, tradition and religion, needs to be avoided at all costs if interventions are to be effective. Omnipresent and overriding associations between caste and culture which have key effects on health outcomes of the margins must be overcome even in public policy matters. The Public Health Administration should be very sensitive of this issue. Failure to recognize this relationship and the refusal to tackle these issues results in poorer health standards for the marginal people in the country. In India customs, norms, culture, and tradition continue to promote inequality in every walk of life.

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ความร่วมมือระหว่างภาครัฐกับภาคเอกชนในโครงการ *Yeshasvini* (โครงการบริการ

สุขภาพสำหรับผู้ยากไร้): คำตอบสำหรับการประกันสุขภาพแบบองค์รวมของรัฐ กรณีศึกษา ประเทศอินเดีย

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บทคัดย่อ

Yeshasvini (ภาษาท้องถิ่นแปลว่า ความสำเร็จ) เป็นโครงการที่พัฒนาขึ้นมาจากความร่วมมืออย่างมีประสิทธิภาพระหว่างภาครัฐและภาคเอกชนในรัฐकर्णाฏกะ (Karnataka) ซึ่งอยู่ทางตอนใต้ของประเทศไทย เป็นโครงการประกันสุขภาพซึ่งรู้จักกันในชื่อหนึ่งว่า “โครงการกองทุนสุขภาพชุมชน” โดยมีวิสัยทัศน์ในการสร้างหลักประกันสุขภาพการบริการสุขภาพสำหรับสมาชิกของสหกรณ์ในรัฐ โครงการดังกล่าวเริ่มต้นในปี พ.ศ. 2545 นับตั้งแต่ก่อตั้งมา ความเข้มแข็งของโครงการกลายมาเป็นที่นับแบบให้กับหน่วยงานอื่น ๆ ในประเทศ ในทางกฎหมายแล้ว “สหกรณ์สุขภาพชวาวนา *Yeshasvini*” จัดตั้งขึ้นตามพระราชบัญญัติว่าด้วยทรัพย์สินของโครงการจะได้รับจากผลความสำรับของโครงการในแคละวี โครงการสุขภาพ *Yeshasvini* ดำเนินงานผ่านเครือข่ายเอกชนและโรงพยาบาลของรัฐที่ได้รับการคัดเลือกเพื่อให้บริการสุขภาพที่มีคุณภาพและมีต้นทุนที่ เหมาะสมสำหรับสมาชิกสหกรณ์ของรัฐกรณีศึกษา บทความนี้ใช้ข้อมูลศึกษาภูมิในการศึกษาเพื่อแสดงให้เห็นถึงผลกระทบของโครงการดังกล่าว

Keywords: *Yeshasvini* สาธารณสุข ประกันสุขภาพ โครงการ โรงพยาบาล

Background

Any health issue/s creates problems in the income earning capacity of the person who is in below poverty line but that family also traps in debt. India runs the world's one of the largest network of basic medical insurance through rural cooperative system. In today's world, out of pocket expenditure is growing like anything. Today medical technologies are fast spreading and become more costly as poor or marginal sections of the society cannot afford medical cost. Financing health care issue has a long history. Normally relationships between poverty and health insurance have usually focused in many developing countries as these countries will be having poor GDP and lack of required resources. Still many governments have brought community based low cost health insurance for the poor and this has succeeded in many low income nations across the globe (Devadasan et al., 2004). Through community based low cost health insurance schemes, families can be saved from any financial trap and health shocks as well. A well designed such health care programmes may be a highly quality oriented one over the period of time. Instead of completely free, a nominal user pay based insurance programme may create much more impact. Such success stories/programmes may be a model for many other low income countries. Expert felt any govt health insurance programme must be low cost, cash less, comprehensive and must be a provision for the quality health care services. The article demonstrates that community insurance presents a practical replica for providing high-end quality oriented health services in resource-poor scenario stressing on responsibility and effective co-operative management system (Onwujekwe et al., 2009). Majority rural and informal sector workers in India do not have any form of health insurance. In India, ninety-two percent of India's families earn their livelihood mainly from the unorganized sectors only. The poor are predominantly susceptible to the lack of health safety. It is noted that the poor and margins normally spend 1/4 of their total income on health connected spending only.

Yeshasvini Health Care Scheme

Karnataka-south India has most vital percentage of rural population primarily engaged in agriculture and related activities. State is known for medical tourism. Plenty of hospitals and medical colleges available across the State. However, the bed occupancy rate has been as low as forty-seven percent in the state. It is found that large number of poor rural people is dying, simply because they cannot afford required hospital treatment on time (Devadasan et al., 2004). The main challenge before the government is to provide these sections of the population an easy access to reasonably priced healthcare service in a sustainable and continues mode (Kuruvilla & Iju, 2007). In this background *Yeshasvini* (community based health care scheme) scheme has been a model in the healthcare for the poor in the Karnataka state-south India (Hindu Daily, 2013). Recently Govt.

Table 2. The Progress of The Yeshaswini Scheme during the Past Twelve Years Is Detailed Below.

Sl NO	Scheme Year	Members Enrolled under the Scheme	Amount Collected (in Lakh)	Amount Released from the Govt.	No. of O.P.D	No. of Surgeries Done	Amount Spent on Surgeries
1	2003-04	160,000	969.00	450.00	35,814	9,047	1,065.35
2	2004-05	2,021,661	1,197.00	357.00	50,174	15,326	1,847.23
3	2005-06	1,473,576	1,634.00	1,100.00	52,892	19,682	2,616.94
4	2006-07	1,853,966	2,156.00	1,985.00	206,977	39,602	3,851.00
5	2007-08	2,318,000	2,775.00	2,500.00	155,572	60,668	5,409.00
6	2008-09	3,047,000	3,610.00	3,000.00	191,109	75,053	6,108.00
7	2009-10	3,069,000	4,136.00	3,000.00	134,534	66,796	5,305.00
8	2010-11	3,047,000	4,168.00	3,000.00	157,480	73,963	5,723.00
9	2011-12	3,070,000	4,508.00	3,000.00	116,690	77,526	6,000.00
10	2012-13	3,036,000	5,888.00	3,500.00	110,842	80,401	7,412.00
11	2013-14	3,751,000	5,272.00	4,500.00	123,205	86,359	8,456.00
12	2014-15	3,872,000	6,940.00	7,100.00	172,442	134,742	15,000.00

Source: Department of Cooperation, Government of Karnataka Various Annual Reports.

Table 3. Distribution by Social Groups of Yeshaswini Users (2011-2013)

Social groups	2011-12		2012-13		Total	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Above poverty line	632	0.7	0	0.0	632	0.4
Below poverty line	1,178	1.4	0	0.0	1,178	0.8
Economical backward class	11,625	13.6	5,227	9.3	16,852	11.9
Minority	828	1.0	0	0	828	0.6
Others/General	69,604	81.3	49,971	88.8	119,575	84.3
Scheduled caste	1,234	1.5	791	1.3	1,974	1.4
Tribes	520	0.6	313	0.6	833	0.6
Total	85,630	100.0	56,242	100.0	141,872	100.0

Sources: Study Report of Centre for Budget and Policy Study, Karnataka (2012)

Table 4. Age-wise Distribution of Gender of Yeshaswini Users (2011-13)

Age	Female		Male		Total	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
0-18 years	3,943	38.9	6,203	61.1	10,146	100
19-36 years	38,350	78.7	10,400	21.3	48,750	100
37-54 years	17,810	49.1	18,464	50.9	36,274	100
55-75 years	15,940	33.7	31,295	66.3	47,235	100
>75 years	3	33.3	6	66.7	9	100

Table 5. Expenditure per Package in Yeshaswini Scheme (2011-13)

Package	Frequency	Mean Expenditure (in Indian Rupees)	Total Expenditure (in Indian Rupees)	Percentage
CVS (cardio vascular)	18,035.0	23,478.6	423,436,209.0	32.9
END	345.0	9,027.0	3,114,315.0	0.2
ENT	6,743.0	6,419.0	43,288,659.0	3.4
GNI.	19,111.0	6,641.4	126,923,462.0	9.9
GST	1,913.0	12,496.9	23,906,566.0	1.9
ME	99.0	1,846.5	182,800.0	0.0
NEURO	2,075.0	19,959.1	41,415,129.0	3.2
NICU	2,042.0	2,714.8	5,543,657.0	0.4
OBC	40,987.0	6,425.8	263,373,469.1	20.5
ONCO	591.0	23,774.9	14,050,947.0	1.1
OPHTHO	43,423.0	4,322.7	187,704,032.4	14.6
ORTHO	6,552.0	10,689.2	70,035,836.5	5.4
PED	1,148.0	8,541.9	9,806,087.0	0.8
THR	88.0	18,342.5	1,614,136.0	0.1
URO (Urology)	7,429.0	8,981.9	66,726,195.8	5.2
VAS	192.0	24,379.2	4,680,800.0	0.4
Total	150,773.0	8,528.1	1,285,802,300.8	100.0

Source: Department of Cooperation, Government of Karnataka Various Annual Reports (2013)

Table 6. Performance of the Surgery Cases and Amount Sanctioned over a Period of Time (2003-04 to 2011-12)

Name of the Districts	Total Surgery Cases (in Numbers)	Percent Share of Cases	Total Amount Sanctioned (In Indian Rupees)	Percent Share of Amount
1. Belgaum	16,683	5.62	167,115,771	6.32
2. Bijapur	11,854	3.99	96,741,892	3.66
3. Bagalkot	15,571	5.25	116,546,579	4.41
4. Dharwad	3,567	1.88	40,460,270	1.53
5. Gadag	6,380	2.15	47,591,860	1.80
6. Haveri	12,930	4.36	98,591,754	3.54
7. UK	5,792	1.95	52,579,700	1.99
8. Raichur	7,104	2.39	67,192,540	2.54
9. Koppal	3,439	1.16	33,361,315	1.26
10. Gulbarga	8,400	2.83	91,668,465	3.47
11. Bidar	4,280	1.44	43,690,990	1.65
12. Bellary	4,123	1.39	51,082,502	1.93
13. Bangalore (Urban & Rural)	17,460	5.88	192,050,813	7.27
14. Kolar	14,849	5.00	147,196,796	5.57
15. Tumkur	17,425	5.87	167,671,421	6.34
16. Chitradurga	12,001	4.04	113,658,242	4.30
17. Dargare	19,172	6.46	163,476,512	6.19
18. Shimoga	7,390	2.49	74,167,302	2.81
19. Mysore	11,112	3.74	128,043,570	4.85
20. Chamrajnagar	5,539	1.87	57,669,250	2.18
21. Mandya	34,536	11.64	279,639,153	10.58
22. Hassan	17,536	5.91	147,286,710	5.57
23. Chikmagalur	8,294	2.79	79,330,332	3.00
24. Kodagu	2,600	0.88	31,025,266	1.17
25. D K	5,080	1.71	56,711,070	2.15
26. Udipi	21,670	7.30	108,234,957	3.91
Total	296,787	100.00	2,642,784,432	100.00

Source: Department of Cooperation, Government of Karnataka Various Annual Reports (2013)

Discussion

Visibly indicates that total number of members enrolled under the scheme under the Yeshaswini health care scheme in the state from the beginning from the year 2008-09 onwards the members enrolled under the scheme is gradually increasing. This is mainly because of Cooperative Societies, Self Help Group and Government progressive policies and their active role in the scheme. The highest number of surgery done in the year 2013-14. Between 2003 to 2005 poor performance can be seen because of less awareness about the scheme (Table 1) This table indicates that different social groups availed the service under Yeshaswini health care scheme in Karnataka state. Economical backward class have obtained highest usage of the scheme scheduled caste and tribes (highly marginalized group in India) have not availed this scheme up to the mark (Table 2). Regarding age group highest number of users comes between nineteen to thirty-six. In case of performance of the surgery cases and few districts have some good result because of presence of good numbers of private hospitals and awareness. It is found that the current programme has got a vital success and found to have augmented use of health-care services, abridged out-of-pocket spending and has almost reached to the every needy person of the society.

Also it is found that this scheme is giving better health behavior and economic outcomes. In addition this particular programme has special effects across different socio-economic groups in the state. It is also known that this programme has brought down the direct and indirect charge of health-care down but the degree to which this successfully occurs across medical cases as a more pragmatic issue (Mahal, 2002). Supplementary to this, the effects of this particular programme are more marked for the better-off population. Also this community insurance programme is providing high-end services for the resource-poor settings through solid responsibility and proper local health care management (Ron, 1999). Because of this scheme today any poor person can get a reasonable good health care treatment even in the private hospitals. Despite having more vital issues it is still not a comprehensive scheme because it covers cost part surgery only. Patients have to bare the other cost of the treatment like diagnostic, lab charge, medicine etc. this is highly impossible for poor income families. This is a big issue here. More problems is that few network hospitals have already started talking to get way out of this scheme because of alleged non-payment of dues by the Trust on time. Trust says releasing matching grant on time from the Govt. is a big issue. It shows private-public partnership will survive only if the interests of all stakeholders are taken into account.

However the other part of this scheme has some questionable substantiation. Low enrolment is usually observed in many districts of the state through this study. We suspect numerous socio-

and outcome among various social groups. In Some cases elevated enrolment do not associated with the better result. However, a number of evidences found that this scheme has helped in reducing out-of-pocket expenditure (Mahal, 2002). Since it is a cashless scheme it is highly helpful in various ways. However, it is also noted that few hospitals are showing discrimination about these insured people while providing various health services treating them just as free beneficiaries. Few big and reputed hospitals also denying services citing unrelated reasons and many rural illiterates and patients' belonging to the lower castes are being treated badly as we found. Moreover there is an obvious confirmation of augmented use of private health services for primary health care among the insured people.

Trivial changes in accessing to quality medical services and the geographically varied effect of this scheme on service utilization points and health seeking and health care behaviour of the insured found very promising. Further, concrete strategies required for reducing claims and managing utilization as much as possible. Impartial effect of this low cost insurance programme and enhanced monetary guard, particularly for the poor and marginalized sections of the society. The role of other public and private insurance agencies as monetary mediators of the widely funded and supported by the Govt. needs additional assessment before moving forward

Conclusion

The major limitation of the study is largely this article is based on the secondary data. Numerous low- and middle-income nations endorse low cost community-based health insurance (CBHI) to get better admittance to health care for the poor and margins. It is largely indicated that the scheme has been proven useful to all sections of society, especially poor people, margins, middle or low income people, laborers, taxi drivers, domestic servants, construction and factory workers to those who are not having regular income. The scheme is meant for middle and lower middle class are the highest beneficiaries till now. However, more awareness among the people is still required because of widespread coverage. Though it provides health security for the poor it is depend on the government subsidy. We suggest that this scheme must be a more quality health care oriented and easily accessible to the poor at the door step. For this we found an effective public-private bond is required. Attempt is needed to comprehend health care culture as a sub culture complex in developing a model of culturally suited health care module programmes especially for the rural people with their different castes and class. There is a dearth need to provide locally setting health education about this scheme. Mass media can play a vital role in this aspect. For become self-sustained one, policy makers must have some other ideas to improve the scheme soon.

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Perceptions and knowledge of sexually transmitted diseases among rural people in India: Some ground realities

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Abstract

Sexually Transmitted Diseases (STDs) have become a serious public health issue among the rural people in India because of a unique health culture and health seeking behavior. Most rural people are suffering from different types of STDs because of cultural fabrics, poverty, illiteracy, ignorance and poor access to effective treatment. The World Health Organization has also warned that India could be the next nation with the highest number of unreported STD cases, resulting in devastating consequences. This current study, conducted in a rural part of the Hassan district of Karnataka, South India, examined the perceptions and knowledge regarding STDs among rural people. A focus group study conducted among selected purposive samples of both infected (with STD) and non-infected rural people. This study has found that STDs were more prevalent among people in the age group of 25-28 years (50.6%) male respondents (62.6%), people with a low level of literacy (42.2%), professional truck drivers (38.6%), people in the lower income groups (64%), and unmarried people (56%). This study also found vaginites and herpes are the most common types of STDs found among the respondents. The majority of the respondents were not aware about the onset and symptoms of the STDs. People were too shy to seek treatment even from the local healers. Effective public health policies and health promotion programs should be developed regarding the holistic and inclusive health development for the rural people with special references to STDs.

Keywords: STDs, Knowledge, Perception, Health Behavior, Rural people, India.

Introduction

Sexually transmitted diseases (STDs) are a major global cause of acute illness, infertility, long-term disability and dying of millions of men, women and infants.¹ According to World Health organization, approximately 499 million new cases of curable STDs (syphilis, gonorrhoea, Chlamydia and Trichomoniasis) occur in 2008 throughout the world in adults aged 15-49 years.¹ This estimate is 11% higher than the estimate for 2005 (498.9 million vs. 448.3 million).¹ In the WHO South-East Asia Region, total incidence of selected curable STDs is 78.5 million: 7.2 million cases of *C. trachomatis*, 25.4 million cases of *N. gonorrhoeae*, 3.0 million cases of syphilis and 42.9 million cases of *T. vaginalis*.¹

STDs have become a serious public health issue in India.² There are some social factors which play a vital role in increasing the risk of STDs including socio-economic status, occupation marital status, sexual disharmony etc.³ According to the National Behavioural Surveillance Survey, Karnataka is the state of having the fourth highest incidents of STDs in India.² The current estimates national adult HIV prevalence in India is approximately 0.36%, amounting to between 2 and 3.1 million people.² If an average figure is taken, this comes to 2.5 million people living with HIV and AIDS, almost 50% of the previous estimate of 5.2 million.³ Several STDs prevalence studies^{4-6,7} among female sex workers in India have shown widely varying rates across different parts of

Practice Points

- STDs have become a serious public health issue among the rural people in India because of a unique health culture and health seeking behavior.
- STDs were more prevalent among following categories of rural people: people with age group of 25-28 years (50.6%); male respondents (62.6%); people with a low level of literacy (42.2%); professional truck drivers (38.6%); people in the lower income groups; (64%) and unmarried people (56%).
- It was also noted that vaginites and herpes are the most common types of STDs found among the rural people.
- The majority of the rural people were not aware about the onset and common symptoms of the STDs and they were too shy to seek treatment even from the local healers.
- There is an urgent need to implement cultural-sensitive and community-based sexual and reproductive health education programs focusing rural people, especially adolescents.

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the country including Gonorrhoea 0-19.1%, Chlamydia 0.9-22.6%, Syphilis 1.2-51% and Trichomoniasis 2-54.1%.^{8,9}

It has been observed in India that change in the epidemiological trends particularly speedy increasing rate of STDs occurrence being noted in the high risk groups, specifically different drug users and commercial sex workers.³ Several studies⁸⁻¹² found long distance truck drivers, middle class businessmen and construction workers are belongs to the high risk groups focusing rural region of the country. In India more than 70% of the populations reside in rural areas and increasing urban-rural migration is the major factor for the high prevalence of STDs in rural areas.¹² High risk groups being in rural areas may spread HIV to the other general population as cautioned by various studies.^{7,13,14}

Rural people are more vulnerable to the rapid spread of STDs. Urban and semi-urban area attracts more rural people, especially people who usually migrate searching for short-term and well-paid jobs. The DFID (Department for International Development, UK) report made clear that extensive travelling men may cause contact with multiple commercial sex workers¹⁵ and they spread STDs to their wives when they returned homes.¹⁶ Rural men, who are always mobile, may serve as a bridging population even for HIV not only between two genders, but also for two geographical locations.¹⁶

A number of studies^{9,14} have found that STDs are more commonly transmits from men to women in India. It is found that biologically women are more susceptible to STDs than men.¹⁷ One of the movements may be men have more decision-making power than women in relation to reproductive health in India.¹⁸

The important causes of increased incidence of STDs in rural areas include: unsafe sex, lack of awareness, illiteracy and strong social and ethnic factors, supernatural beliefs.⁵ Medical sociologists found that health care seeking behavior of the rural people also responsible for spreading STDs.¹⁶ Unprotected pre-marital and extra-marital relationship also causes more incidences of STDs/HIV in rural areas.¹⁹ Among the other key issues associated with STD are disagreeable sexual behavior, teenage pregnancy, sexual annoyance and growing rate of prostitution which may hamper the health of the society.²⁰

It is also found that various types of STDs are causing high rate of morbidity and mortality among rural women and that they frequently present lacking any clinical symptoms.²¹ Experts have cautioned that because of lack of adequate knowledge about curable STDs the prevailing rate of HIV may increase among the rural folk.²⁰

The current aim of this study is to examine the perceptions and knowledge about STDs and to measure the rate of prevalence of STD in rural parts of Hassan district of Karnataka, South India.

Materials and methods

The study was conducted in three selected villages of Hassan districts of south Karnataka state, India. The villages were selected based on the Reproductive and Child Health (RCH) Survey Report 2011.²² These villages have shown poor performance in the RCH Survey. This study has been conducted among 75 infected adolescents (25 adolescents from each village) and adolescents were selected using purposive sampling technique based on self-reporting and after verifying their medical records with the help of a local physician and assistance from the local health workers. A survey questionnaire was used to collect quantitative data and the same has analyzed using *Minitab* software.²³ For some socio-cultural reasons unmarried women and girls, pregnant and puerperal women were excluded from the study. The symptoms related to the various STDs were followed as recommended by the Government of India, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare guidelines.³ An interview schedule was also prepared using WHO interview schedules for diagnosis of STDs.¹ Adolescents were interviewed in a private place. Data have verified for completeness and consistence.

Results

Table 1 shows the detailed background information of the respondents. This study has found that STD is more prevalent among the age group of 25-28 years (50.6%). More than 29% of the age group of 18-19 and 20% of the age group 20-24 years were suffering from STDs. It was also found that male members were more prone to STDs (62.6%). Majority of STD cases found among illiterates (42.2%) followed by the high school educated group (25.3%). In case of occupation, 38.6% of professional truck drivers, 24% of migrant laborers, 12% skilled labors and 10.6% unemployed adolescents were found to suffer from different types of STDs. This study also revealed that the low income group (64%) is more prone to STDs followed by the middle income group (30.6%). In case of marital status, unmarried and widow/widower are at more risk of being infected by STDs (56% and 26.6% respectively).

The common prevalence of various cases of STDs among the respondents included gonorrhoea (12%) syphilis (9%), herpes (15%), and vaginitis (18%). HIV infection was found to be less common among the studied groups (1%) (Table 2). It is found that 29% of the respondents felt swelling genitals whereas 19% of them felt pain in the genital area, while 11% of them reported smelly discharges whereas 12% felt losing interest in sex were some of the vital symptoms of STDs (Table 3).

While asked about the main reasons of contracting STDs, the respondents mentioned the following: effects of sprits/breaching taboo (28%), sex with strange people (14%), eating/doing religions prohibited foods/deeds (10%), unprotected sex (11%) and sex with an infected person (9%) (Table 3). For the treatment of STD problems, 29% of the respondents received treatment from the local traditional healers, 21% used home/self-

Table 1: Background characteristics of the study population

Variables	Respondents (%)
Age (yrs)*	
18-19	22 (29.3%)
20-24	15 (20%)
25-28	38 (50.6%)
Gender*	
Male	47 (62.6%)
Female	28 (37.3%)
Educational level*	
Primary education	18 (24%)
High school	19 (25.3%)
College	4 (5.3%)
Illiterates	32 (42.2%)
Professional education	2 (2.6%)
Occupational Status*	
Migrant labors	18 (24%)
Drivers	29 (38.6%)
Skilled labor	9 (12%)
Unemployed	8 (10.6%)
Business	7 (9.3%)
Garments	4 (5.3%)
Income level (In Rs.)*	
3000-5000	48 (64%)
5000-10000	23 (30.6%)
Above 10000	4 (5.3%)
Marital Status*	
Married	8 (10.6%)
Unmarried	42 (56%)
Widow/widower	20 (26.6%)
Others	5 (6.7%)
Employment status*	
Currently working	33 (44%)
Not working	42 (56%)

*Values are significant $p < 0.05$.

Table 2: Prevalence rate of STDs

STDs	Respondents (%)
Gonorrhoea	12 (16%)
Syphilis	9 (12%)
Herpes	15 (19%)
Vaginitis	18 (24%)
HIV	1 (1.3%)
No such cases	20 (26.7%)

remedy, 26% got treatment from the faith healers and only 12% were treated by the modern medicine.

Regarding source of information about STD, 23% of the respondents received information from the local health workers, while 17% from the friends/relatives and 9% obtained information through various media. While asked about the non-treatment of STDs, the respondents mentioned the following reasons: shyness to seek treatment (40%), cost (20%), and time constraints (8%). Regarding preventive measure (after being diagnosed

Table 3: Perceptions and knowledge of respondents

Variables	Respondents (%)
Perceived symptoms of STDs*	
Swelling in genitals	29 (38.7%)
Pain in genital area	19 (25.3%)
Smelly discharges	11 (14.6%)
Not interested in Sex	12 (16.0%)
Other symptoms	4 (5.3%)
Perceived Reasons for STDs*	
Effects if sprits/ breach of taboo	28 (37.3%)
Sex with unknown people	14 (18.6%)
Religion prohibited foods/deeds	10 (13.3%)
Sex with an infected person	9 (12%)
Unprotected sex	11 (14.6%)
Others	3 (4%)
Sources of Treatment*	
Traditional healer	22 (29.3%)
Home/ self remedy	21 (28%)
Faith healer	20 (26.6%)
Western medicine	12 (16%)
Source of information about STDs*	
Local health workers	23 (30.6%)
Friends/ Relatives	17 (22.6%)
Media	9 (12%)
Others	14 (18.6%)
Reasons for not taking treatment*	
No time	8 (10.6%)
Low priority/cost factor	20 (26.7%)
Fear/shy	30 (40%)
No idea	8 (10.7%)
Under-treatment	9 (12%)
Preventive Measure*	
Nothing	18 (24.0%)
Using Condoms	21 (28.0%)
Never sex with infected person	30 (40%)
Early treatment	6 (8.0%)

*Values are significant $p < 0.05$.

with STDs), 18% of the respondents didn't take any preventive measures, 21% used condoms, and 30% avoid sex with infected persons.

Discussion

This study has found that STD is more prevalent among the age group of 25-28 years (50.6%), male (vs. females) (62.6%), illiterates (42.2%), professional truck drivers (38.6%), low income group (64%) and unmarried people (56%). It is generally reckoned that even though young people aged 18-23 years represent only 27% of having pre-material sexually experienced, they acquire more or less nearly half of all new STDs in various parts of the globe.¹⁶ It has been found that majority rural men visit cities in searching well-paid jobs and they were in contact with the commercial sex workers in the cities. In this way, men were infected with STDs and in turn infections were transmitted to their wives. Some studies have found that young people having multiple sexual partners, having unprotected sex,

or involved in other high-risk sexual behaviors which are potential risk factors for acquiring various types of STDs.⁸ It is found that in majority cases rural community will not consider STDs is a serious health problem.¹⁵ They will get treatment only if STDs continues for a long time and severely hampering their daily life. Due to non-availability of lady physicians, rural women some time reluctant to visit local primary health care centres.¹⁹ Further it is found that poor access to healthcare, lack of awareness, the asymptomatic nature of certain STDs have also immensely contributed to increased prevalence of STDs among rural female adolescent.¹⁶ We also found that adolescents often discussed among the peer groups about STDs/HIV and the usage of contraceptives. Among the female adolescents, irregular menstrual cycle and urinary tract infection was the common topic of discussion with their friends.¹⁷

Moreover, it is found that majority primary health care centers in rural part do not have any preventive programs because of lack of human and financial resources.⁵ We found that STDs had implications on social and economical aspects of the patients and his/her family.¹⁶ Infected people usually seek treatment from local/faith healers cannot diagnose STDs and reluctant to visit health centers for social and financial reasons.^{9,17} Once they are diagnosed with STDs, this may hamper patients' personal image in the village and sometime friends and relative will avoid him/her or may have to face a kind of social isolation.⁴

The patients also reported that once they identified with STD they cannot attend any social functions in the village. Even today rural people in India are more interested to seek low-cost traditional treatment for STDs.¹³ The continuation of traditional health culture, unique health seeking behavior, poor health infrastructure, socio-cultural and religious barriers, and domination of local healers are some of the main barriers which prevent the STD patients in getting proper and timely treatment.^{8,12}

The health culture and changing the reproductive behavior of the rural people in the studied village have been largely influenced due to contact with various external agencies including media and NGOs. Due to rapid economic growth, migration and expansion of cities, rural people are gradually prone to various STD diseases. Our study also found that rural people are less aware about the incidence of STDs and implications/consequences of the diseases in their life. STDs has become a lifestyle-related disorder in rural areas.¹⁵ One of the worrying fact is that majority of the patients would not disclose their problems to anyone until it gets worse. The majority of them are not even considering STD is a very serious health issue and they are holding the perception of natural healing. It is probably due to the lower socio-economic conditions which may impact on their health seeking behavior. Moreover, the majority of the rural people have strong faith on the local healers for curing STDs.¹⁴

Conclusion

This study has found adolescents are more prone to various STD and majority of them are illiterates. It is also revealed that the majority of the infected respondents belong to the low-income group and most of them are unmarried adolescents. Moreover the long distance truck drivers are more prone to the STDs because of their nature of profession. This study found vaginites and herpes are the most common types of STD found among the respondents. Responds opined swelling in the genitals and pain are the most common symptoms of STD. Despite the availability of modern medical facilities, the incidence rate of STDs is increasing in rural areas, which may be due to socio-cultural and economic reasons.

There is an urgent need to implement cultural-sensitive and community-based sexual and reproductive health education programs focusing rural people, especially adolescents. Involvement of the village leaders and traditional healers is also essential for successful implementation of the programs. The traditional healers and local health workers should be properly trained in diagnosing and treatment of STDs.

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A SHORT BOOK ON URBAN PUBLIC HEALTH

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**RURAL CULTURAL TRANSFORMATION AND CHANGES IN HEALTH
BEHAVIOR: SOME ANNOTATIONS**

Dr. D.C. Nanjunda

Abstract

Health is one of the vital indicators reflecting the quality of human life. World Health Organization (WHO) describes health as a state of complete physical, mental, social and spiritual well-being and not merely as absence of diseases or infirmity. The plight of rural people has drawn increasing policy attention since 1960. Over the last few decades various Indian governments have planned long term goal of providing a compressive health care programme to the rural people, increasingly emphasized the more immediate need to provide essential basic primary health care and scientific management of rural's traditional system. Today majority of the rural people are suffering with various communicable and non communicable diseases. It is stated there is a positive correlation between the health status of rural people and their social, economical and cultural background. This paper is based on the filed work conducted in the selected villages in Karnataka and reveals about various soci-cultural factors affecting rural's health seeking behavior

Introduction

Health is one of the vital indicators reflecting the quality of human life. World Health Organization (WHO) describes health as a state of complete physical, mental, social and spiritual well-being and not merely as absence of diseases or infirmity. Today majority of the rural people are suffering with various communicable and non communicable diseases. It is stated there is a positive correlation between the health status of rural people and their

social, economical and cultural background. The plight of rural people has drawn increasing policy attention since 1960. Over the last few decades various Indian governments have planned long term goal of providing a compressive health care programme to the rural people, increasingly emphasized the more immediate need to provide essential basic primary health care and scientific management of rural's traditional system. Experts have conducted various studies on culturally bounded health behavior among various rural settings. Still they did not understand completely the dynamics of health behavior of rural's.

Health seeking behavior in terms of illness behavior refers to those activities undertaken by individuals in response to symptom experience. Health seeking behavior is influenced by a large number of factors apart from knowledge and awareness. This behavior among different populations, particularly in the rural communities, is a complex outcome of many factors operating at individual, family and community level including their bio-social profile, their past experiences with the health services, influences at the community level, ~~availability of alternative health care~~ providers including indigenous practitioners and last but not the least their perceptions regarding efficiency and quality of the services. Belief systems prevalent in the communities i.e. how people conceptualize the etiology of health problem and how symptoms are perceived is an important factor in deciding the first step of treatment seeking behavior of rural population (Tones,2004). Culture creates an unique pattern of beliefs and perceptions as to what "health" or "illness" actually mean. In turn, this pattern of beliefs influences how symptoms are recognized, to what they are attributed, and how they are interpreted and affects how and when health services are sought. Cultural differences in the recognition and interpretation of symptoms and in the use of health services are the subject of a rich literature. conducted a classic study on the effects of culture on pain: although pain was considered a biologic phenomenon, he found that sensitivity to pain and attributing significance to pain symptoms varied by culture and ethnicity. It is said that cultural differences among rural people seeking health care as related to social structures and relationships and the degree of skepticism about professional medical care. Delay in seeking care was found among individuals belonging to cultural groups characterized by ethnic exclusivity, traditional family authority, and high skepticism about medicine. More recently, level of acculturation has been shown to account for differences in

social, economical and cultural background. The plight of rural people has drawn increasing policy attention since 1960. Over the last few decades various Indian governments have planned long term goal of providing a comprehensive health care programme to the rural people, increasingly emphasized the more immediate need to provide essential basic primary health care and scientific management of rural's traditional system. Experts have conducted various studies on culturally bounded health behavior among various rural settings. Still they did not understand completely the dynamics of health behavior of rural's.

Health seeking behavior in terms of illness behavior refers to those activities undertaken by individuals in response to symptom experience. Health seeking behavior is influenced by a large number of factors apart from knowledge and awareness. This behavior among different populations, particularly in the rural communities, is a complex outcome of many factors operating at individual, family and community level including their bio-social profile, their past experiences with the health services, influences at the community level, availability of alternative health care providers including indigenous practitioners and last but not the least their perceptions regarding efficiency and quality of the services. Belief systems prevalent in the communities i.e. how people conceptualize the etiology of health problem and how symptoms are perceived is an important factor in deciding the first step of treatment seeking behavior of rural population (Tones,2004). Culture creates an unique pattern of beliefs and perceptions as to what "health" or "illness" actually mean. In turn, this pattern of beliefs influences how symptoms are recognized, to what they are attributed, and how they are interpreted and affects how and when health services are sought. Cultural differences in the recognition and interpretation of symptoms and in the use of health services are the subject of a rich literature. conducted a classic study on the effects of culture on pain: although pain was considered a biologic phenomenon, he found that sensitivity to pain and attributing significance to pain symptoms varied by culture and ethnicity. It is said that cultural differences among rural people seeking health care as related to social structures and relationships and the degree of skepticism about professional medical care. Delay in seeking care was found among individuals belonging to cultural groups characterized by ethnic exclusivity, traditional family authority, and high skepticism about medicine. More recently, level of acculturation has been shown to account for differences in

the use of health services within ethnic groups after control-ling for age, gender, health status, and insurance coverage (Nandan ,1984).

METHODOLOGY

This study has been conducted in Hassan and chamaraja nager district of Karnataka State India based on the pilot survey conducted by this author selected a total of 100 (50 each) rural families having different socio-economic background for the current study. Data collected from, the patients, community members, PHC staff and NGO's through survey questioners. This research had Two major components 1 Households Case study , 2 Community norms study, The qualitative data has been analyzed in the NUD*IST database and quantitative data analysis using SPSS software.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table: 1 Factors Affecting Health Behavior

<i>Response</i>	<i>Men</i>		<i>Women</i>		<i>Total</i>	
	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Social and Cultural Factors	28	28.00	19	19.00	47	23.53
Gender roles	23	23.00	23	23.00	46	23.10
Social networks	21	21.00	28	28.00	49	24.51
Religion	17	17.00	16	16.00	33	16.50
Traditional belief	7	7.00	6	6.00	10	5.00
Others	4	4.00	3	3.00	10	5.00

$X^2=30.418$; $X^2=22.310$; $X^2=48.376$;
 $P< .000$ $P< .001$ $P< .000^*$
 $X^2(\text{Male*Female}) =9.754$; $P<.135$

Tab-2
Types of Treatment Preferred First for Certain
Types of Conditions

<i>Response</i>	<i>Traditional</i>		<i>Modern</i>	
	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Tetanus	58	58.0	41	41.00
Pneumonia	67	33.0	33	33.00
Cholera	51	51.0	49	49.00
Malaria	67	67.0	33	33.00
Diarrhea	63	63.0	37	37.00
Fever	47	47.00	53	53.00
Miscarriage	60	0.00	40	5.00

$X^2=29.418$; $X^2=21.310$; $P<$
 $P< .000$ $.001$
 $X^2(\text{Male*Female})=9.740$;
 $P<.125$

Tab-3
Reasons for Preferring Different Types of Medicine

<i>Response</i>	<i>Traditional</i>		<i>Modern</i>	
	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Adequate availability of healers	53	53.0	40	40.00
Good-diagnosis	55	55.0	31	30.00
Satisfaction over prescription	47	47.0	41	41.00
Quality of drugs	61	61.0	29	29.00
Recovery/cure	63	63.0	37	37.00

Sufficient time to patients	41	41	48	48.00
Payment arrangements	57.0	57.0	41	41.00
		0		
	X ² =29.418; P<.000		X ² =21.310; P<.001	
	X ² (Male*Female) =9.704; P<.115			

Discussion and Conclusion

It is found that majority of these rural believe the causes for ill health are (i) displeasure of supernatural entities, (ii) breach of taboos,(iii) non-fulfillment of obligations towards their gods, (iv) Influence of occultism and (v) Environmental and physical ones. Further, nutritional deficiencies are more in young rural children and reproductive health care is also poor. Health of the rural is prejudiced by a number of factors such as adequate food, housing, sanitation, healthy lifestyles, protection against-environmental hazards and communicable diseases. Experts have indentified variety of issues related to rural's health that is: health culture-including, (1) health, food habits and environment,(2) medicine, health and community-modern, (3) fertility and mortality, (4) interaction of traditional and modern systems of medicine at various levels (Naidu, 2008; Sawin, 1994)..Most of the rural's have high prevalence of many infectious diseases because of their habitation in remote areas. Most of rural's studied by anthropologists/sociologists and NGOs appear to have a few common practices regarding maternal and child care. Among most of the rural's, gastrointestinal disorders, particularly dysentery and parasitic infection are very common leading to morbidity and malnutrition, diarrhoea, dysentery, skin diseases, respiratory diseases. Nutritional problems, anemia due to food taboos, wrong infant feeding practices, fertility, neo-natal mortality, post-natal mortality, peri-natal mortality, poor life-expectancy etc. are some of the vital health issues and it requires and urgent scientific interventions in this regard (Dobe, 2002). Culture creates a unique pattern of beliefs and perceptions as to what "health" or "illness" actually mean. In turn, this pattern of beliefs influences how symptoms are recognized, to what they are attributed, and how they are interpreted and affects how and when health services are sought. Cultural

**Indian Journal of Public Health Research &
Development**

Year 2015, Volume-6, Issue-1 (January–March)

Print ISSN : 0976-0245

Online ISSN : 0976-5506

DOI:10.5958/0976-5506.2015.00032.7

Under Nutrition and Childhood Mortality: A Public Health Problem among Rural Under Five Children of South Karnataka, India

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ABSTRACT

Infant and under five mortality rates are reliable indicators of health status of the children. Despite accelerated growth, prevalence of hunger, under nutrition and mortality in rural part of the country is still persists. While under nutrition among children is very pervasive child mortality is rather high in rural India. The current study is conducted in Two remote villages of Hassan and Kodagu districts of South Karnataka-India. Study was conducted on (Boys 160, Girls 140) preschool children, selected through stratified sampling design technique. This study was found that stunting in 75.0 %, wasting in 81.7% and underweight in 87.6% of both Boys and Girls of preschool children. In case of Anemia, 48% of Girls and 56% of Boys were severely affected while 47 % of Girls and 41% of Boys were modestly affected. 10% of Boys and 28% Girls were observed mildly affected. It is also found that clinical sign of Anemia among 62% of the studied children. Next, 21% children found Vitamin A deficiency and 22% children found vitamin B complex deficiency. Study also found that only 67% children were put on breast feeding within Three hours after the birth. It is also noted that income poverty, bad personal habits, changing health seeking behavior, cultural practices regarding delivery, childrearing and breast feeding also plays a vital role in case of mortality problem where Government and NGO should focus on these issues immediately.

Keywords: Mortality, Nutrition, Health, Rural , Children

INTRODUCTION

Under nutrition and childhood mortality have become a serious problem among rural children. It is found that their social-cultural background, health, behavior and health culture dynamics plays a significant role as vital determinants of the health status of a particular community. Hence, under nutrition and childhood mortality are more common in rural areas. WHO report

(1985) has found that 57% of death of under Five children in developing countries are accompanied by under-nutrition thereby low weight for their age. Anthropologists have revealed that the development of health culture of the rural environment should be examined as a sub cultural complex of the entire way of life⁶. There are a number of forces percolated from the larger socio-economic environment and directed through the attributer of historical, social and political dimension to the development of the pattern of their health culture in the given rural settings. A good health required a balanced diet. Under Five children need good nutritional diet which is scanty in many rural settings in the country and this causes mortality and morbidity among rural population. ¹

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It is found that Nearly Thirty (30) lakhs children in India die before the age of Five due to various health issues. Infant mortality rate and under Five mortality rates are the finest indicators of health and quality of life of any given community. Reports shows that various child health indicators of the country have shown considerable improvement and infant mortality has declined from 78 to 57 deaths per 1000 live births and under-five mortality from 109 to 74 deaths per 1000 live births. However, under-five mortality levels among rural children are still shockingly high (at 97 deaths per 1000 live births). Rural's constitutes 60 to 62 percent of the total population, but accounts for about 19 percent of all under-five deaths, and 23 percent of deaths in the 1-5 age group.³

Studies have shown that poverty, illiteracy, malnutrition, scarcity of potable water, sanitary conditions, poor mother child health services, problems in covering national health and nutritional services, etc. have been found most vital causative factors for the prevalence of sever childhood mortality and morbidity amongst the rural communities in the country. Despite marvelous development focusing preventive and curative medicine, the child healthcare delivery services in several rural communities are still poor and unscientific and need to be further strengthened in order to achieve the goal of health for all in the country.⁶

Further, experts opined that poor health outcome of the rural community and their children need to be read within in the context of rapid urbanization, focusing poor health infrastructure, costly treatment. However, in a multicultural society rural childhood mortality in

India cannot be analyzed in a contextual vacuum. Instead, they need to be looked at in the light of larger socio economic changes experienced by the rural community over the period of time. Till now various Governments have implemented many programmes to improve the nutritional status of the pre-school children through various innovative schemes. Corers of money have been spent. Still country experiences sever rural child mortality issue. Health experts opined that lack of good primary health care, perceived and personal risks, lack of awareness have lead in failing health improvements programmes⁴. This present study is to assess the extent and prevalence rate of mortality among under Five rural children in the Two districts of south Karnataka, India.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

This current study conducted in two remote villages of Hassan and Kodagu districts of south Karnataka. Study had 300 (Boys 160, Girls 140) preschool children, selected using stratified sampling design technique. Household survey was carried out in Two villages covered by two primary health centers(PHC). Anthropometric measurements were taken using standard techniques. Infant meter was also used to measure below 1 year old children. Date of birth were obtained from the village directory for cross checking. The indices of nutritional status have been mentioned in Standard Deviation(SD). Household socio-economic data were collected through survey & analyzed using SPSS software and NSIUD data base. Nutritional deficiency and morbidities were recorded under the supervision of the dieticians. Children have been classified after simple clinical test for Anemia and mean anthropometric measurements.

FINDINGS

Tab-1 Mean Anthropometric Measurement of Studied Free School Children

Age	NUMBER	SEX	HEIGHT (cm)	WEIGHT (cm)
0-1	60	M- 35	5.1 + 1.38	56.9+1.7
		F- 25	5.3 + 1.61	51.3 + 1.5
1-2	60	M - 30	7.5 +1.38	68.2 +20
		F - 30	7.1 + 1.03	65.3 +1.0
2-3	60	M -38	8.5 + 1.13	70.5 +2.1
		F- 22	8.1 + 0.71	71.3 +1.8

3-4	60	M-32	11.5 + 1.81	82.1 +1.7
		F-28	10.3 +1.70	79 +1.3
4-5	60	M-37	12.5 + 1.60	82 +1.0
		F-23	11.3 +1.50	81 +1.1

Tab-2 Distribution of Pre-School Children according to SD (standard deviation) Classification of Pre-School Children.

Parameter	-3S D to -250	-2S D to -1SD	- Median
Weight/ age	106 (35.3%)	96(32.0%)	114(38.0%)
Height/ age	102 (34.0%)	103(34.3%)	108(36.0%)
Weight/Height	92 (30.6%)	101(33.3%)	78(26.0%)

Tab-3 Nutritional Status of Pre-school Children

Sex	Stunting _W	Wasting	Underweight
Girls	107 (35.6%)	137 (45.6%)	141 (47.0%)
Boys	118 (39.3%)	106(35.3%)	122(40.6%)
Total	225 (75.0%)	243(81.0%)	263(87.6%)

Tab-4 Occurrence of Anemia in Pre-school Children

Level	Girls	Boys
Severe	77(48.12%)	84(56.75%)
Modesty	47(29.3%)	41 (27.70%)
Mild	28 (17.5%)	15(10.13%)
Total	160	140

DISCUSSION

A Total of 300 rural pre-school children (Boys 160, Girls 140) were examined through this study. It is found that Boys were slightly taller and heavier than Girls for their ages (Tab-1). In case of distribution of pre-school children according to standard deviation, 33% (average) of children are between -2SD to -3SD and 30% (average) of children are between -2SD to -1.5SD (Table 2). This is about weight and height according to their age. In case of nutritional status of pre-school children, stunting in 75.0 %, wasting in 81.7 and under weight 87.6 were observed in both Boys and Girls (Tab-3). Further, in case of Anemia ,48% of Girls and 56% of Boys were severely affected; while 47 % of Girls and 41% of Boys were modestly affected (Tab-4). However 10% of Boys and 28% Girls observed mildly affected in this study. Further, it is also found that clinical sign of Anemia among 62% of studied children. Next, vitamin A deficiency was found in 21% children while vitamin B complex

deficiency found in 22% children. In depth study found that only 87% children were put on breast feeding within 3 hours after the birth. Our study also found majority of the children did not receive pre-local feeds. It is found that supplementary feeding started after 8 months in majority of the studied children. The socio-economic data reveals that majority of them are living in poverty and illiteracy. Still they are depending on traditional healers to solve their various health problems. Normally they will not visit PHCs. Local PHCs lack infrastructure facilities. Doctors rarely visit the Hospitals. Absence of the lady physicians also one of the reason why rural women's don't like to visit PHCs. Availability of clean potable water is very rare. It is found that age old traditional health seeking behavior towards certain diseases severely hampering their health status. We learn that high mortality of the children is causing due to various types of infectious diseases. Morbidity rate (32.5%) is considerably high in the studied children it is due

GROWTH INEQUALITY AND SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT

S. JYOTHI LAKSHMI
NAVITHA THIMMAIAH

Intra-Rural Ecology of Primary Health Care Socio-economic Characteristics, Accessibility, and Utilisation Pattern

Dr. Nanjunda

ABSTRACT

Health is one of the prime concerns of mankind, since his emergences on the earth. Health is a pre-requisite for human development and is essentially concerned with the well-being of the common man. Quality of health care, health orientation and social protection of health in a population affects the development status of any nation. Health is not only related to medical care but an integrated development of an entire human society. Normally the context in which an individual lives is of very vital and significant for his/her health status and quality of life. There are some external determinants which can decide the health status of any person including social environment, health culture, hospitals, doctors etc. Also it significantly depends on some internal factors including his/her health culture, education, health practices, etc. As far as an organic linkage with the rural health is concerned, there is no basic service for an inclusive health interference effort to understand health culture as a sub-culture complex in developing a model of culturally suited health care delivery system especially for the rural people of the country. With this background this paper is to reveal various health related problems of the village folks in two villages of Kodagu districts of Karnataka. This paper concludes that health culture of the villages are largely being influenced by the social and cultural factors.

INTRODUCTION

Health is one of the vital indicators reflecting the quality of human life. World Health Organization (WHO) describes health as a state of complete physical, mental, social and spiritual well-being and not merely as absence of diseases or infirmity. The World Health assembly in 1977 started a

movement for health and well-being for all by the year 2000 A. D. India was also committed to achieving 'Health for all to her citizen'. The National health policy accepted by the honorable Indian parliament in 1983 states health care as the main device for achieving sustainable development of the community. It is known factor that development of any society depends on the healthy people only. Without good health even we cannot think appropriately and act properly. It is known fact that without proper health we cannot expect proper social inclusion of any community. The health is not only a stable state of physical and natural well-being but also in true sense it involved the various other complex issues. As it is widely known that Health is one of the imperative indicators shimmering the excellence of human life. Healthy community is very vital because it can set the destiny of the any society, country, any type of development or any kind of achievement etc. Health is a very vital integrated component of an individual. Sometime collapse of health may even lead an individual towards an early death. Like this unhealthy community may be a hinder for the holistic development of any society. Poor health status of any community may isolate that community from the national main stream.

Experts felt that health can be more precisely viewed as an index of human adaptation to 'micro-ecological alcove'. Even though western system of medicine has many advantages over the traditional, it has not totally been accepted by the majority rural Indian masses till today. It is because of their unique health behaviour consistently influencing by their inherited culture, tradition, beliefs, values, norms and practice etc. All these play a very vital role in shaping health behaviour of that particular community. Invariably it keep shapes the perception and attitude towards the onset and curing of different health problems in a given community over the period of time. Finally it determines to select a particular type of treatment to solve the particular type of health problem. Sociologists felt that every community (may be urban/tribal/rural) normally develops their own health needs and curing approaches after motivating by their changing levels of socio-economic conditions. In this process, health of the rural's as subsystem will be mainly infused by the above attributes of entire social system. Experts felt cultural response of the community to the health problems confronted by it determines the way individual members perceive different ways of dealing with various health problems. As far as an organic linkage with the rural health is concerned, there is no basic service for a comprehensive health intervention attempt to understand health culture as a sub culture complex in developing a model of culturally suited health care delivery system especially for the rural people of the country. Very little work, however, has entailed an in-depth analytical study of comparative emic perspectives of different factors influencing rural people's health behaviour in India. With this background this paper is to reveal various health related problems in two villages of Kodagu districts of Karnataka state.

Objectives

1. To find out the different health problems facing by the studied rural population.
2. To identify the factors influencing health seeking behaviour of the studied population.

Methodology

- *Area Under Study:* Selected Two villages in Chamaraia anger districts.
- *Sampling:* Data has been collected from the 100 village members using simple random technique.

Tools for Data Collection

1. *Survey:* Primary Data has been collected through questionnaires.
2. *Interview:* Carefully designed structured interview has been conducted to collect data.
3. *Focus Group Study:* Data has also been collected through Two focus group (each group had 5-7 members) studies including common public teachers, religious leaders, and others).

Analysis of Data

The qualitative data has been analysed using NUD*1ST statistical softwares and the quantitative data has been analysed using SPSS software.

Result and Discussion

Discussion

Health-seeking behaviour of the rural population is greatly governed by cultural values, beliefs and traditions. However Now it is open for gradual change because continuous interventions of the different kinds of external agencies. Further in the changes of health seeking behaviour patterns of the rural people, one also can notice incredible fresh air which have occurred with respect to philosophy, knowledge, and practices of indigenous systems such as Ayurveda, Homeopathy, Allopathic, etc. However, it becomes important to work on problems of rural's health because it differs from a particular area to another area owing to their remote geographical setting, historical milieu and the processes of social change (Bullyya, 2009). Geographical isolation and limited interactions with other communities has become an obstacle to know the degree of prevalence of certain dangerous diseases including HIV/AIDS among rural communities (Arlappa, 1999; Bose, 2006; Kerketta, 2008).

Rural's exhibit a far less health modernity, as compared to the rest of the population. Their own beliefs, illiteracy, poverty, non-access to scientific information contribute to this low Health Modernity status. The widespread

Table 15.1: Common health problems facing by the children

Sl. No.	Problems	f	Count	X ²	P
1.	Typhoid	32	32		
2.	Diarrhoea	24	24		
3.	Malaria	21	21	23.671	0.000
4.	Cholera	12	12		
5.	Scabies	11	11		
	Total	100	100		

Table 15.2: Common health problems facing by the men

Sl. No.	Problems	f	Count	X ²	P
1.	BP/Diabetics	18	18		
2.	TB	23	23		
3.	Jaundice,	23	23	13.794	0.000
4.	Stomach upset	10	10		
5.	Lungs problem	26	26		
	Total	100	100		

Table 15.3: Common health problems facing by the women

Sl. No.	Problems	f	Count	X ²	P
1.	Skin Problem	15	15		
2.	Asthma	23	23		
3.	Gynec.problems	25	25	11.566	0.000
4.	Arthritis	24	24		
5.	Abortion	13	13		
	Total	100	100		

Table 15.4: Common health problems facing by the aged

Sl. No.	Problems	f	Count	X ²	P
1.	Paralysis	11	11		
2.	Mental health	31	31		
3.	BP/Sugar	23	23	18.940	0.000
4.	Heart and Kidney problem	33	33		
5.	Other	2	2		
	Total	100	100		

Conclusion

The plight of rural people has drawn increasing policy attention since 1960. Today the majority of rural people are suffering with various communicable and non-communicable diseases. It is stated there is a positive correlation between the health status of rural people and their social, economical and cultural background. Over the last few decades various Indian governments have developed plans to achieve long term goals to provide a compressive health care programme for the rural people, and have increasingly emphasised the more immediate need to provide essential basic primary health care and scientific management of rural the rural population's traditional system. Experts have conducted various studies on culturally bounded health behaviour among various rural settings. Still, they have not yet completely understood the dynamics of health behaviour of rural people. It is found that that poverty, illiteracy, malnutrition, scarcity of potable water, sanitary conditions, poor mother child health services, problems in covering national health and nutritional services, etc., have been found the most vital causative factors for the prevalence of several health issues among rural communities in the country. Attempt is needed to comprehend health culture as a sub culture complex in developing a model of culturally suited health module programmes specially for the nation's rural people with their different castes and class.

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Inclusion Far Away Scrutinizing the Factors Contributing to Further Exclusion of Tribes in Kerala

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Dr. M. S. Jayakumar

ABSTRACT

Social Exclusion is the process/situation by/in which a section of a society is excluded from the requirements and necessities of normal life. There could be numerous determinants for this state of affairs, the major one being nothing other than poverty. Exclusion creates its own culture and this culture in turn, sustains and perpetuates exclusion. Though Kerala is an exception among the states in India in the matter of equitable social development, there is inequity between the layers of social strata, most visible in the lower ones including the tribal communities. The exclusion experienced by these communities is manifest in all walks of their life ranging from education to health and to employment and this in turn acts as effective impediment to their advancement in all spheres. The present study reveals that reservation policy in education and job opportunities over the years has failed to make an effective intervention in improving the overall development of tribes in the state. Moreover, the social sector developments the state has achieved made little impact on most of the tribal communities in the state. Bottlenecks in the effective implementation of various welfare programmes are also obstructing their development. Residence in difficult and remote terrains, poor connectivity to basic amenities including water, medical facilities, educational institutions and lack of effective financial assets has resulted in their deprivation. This very culture of exclusion hinders their social and economic development. This paper analyses the varied and complex dimensions of the perpetual social exclusion experienced by the tribal communities in the state.

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Putting People First: Inclusive Health Care through Primary Health Centers

NANJUNDA

ABSTRACT

In India, Primary Health Centers (PHCs) are the keystone of healthcare. PHCs play a vital role as the first level of contact and a connection between individuals and the health system, bringing healthcare delivery as close as possible to where people live and work. Primary health care services are incomplete if they lack appropriate and efficient referral systems to secondary and tertiary care hospitals. Also PHCs have to provide precautionary, remedial and rehabilitative care. Even though there are numerous reasons for a meager performance of PHCs, almost all of them stem from weak stewardship of the sector, which results in a deprived inducement structure. Primary healthcare being crucial, it is based on sensible, systematically sound and culturally appropriate methods. Information about it is made available to individuals in the community through their full involvement and at a cost the community and country can afford to sustain. This helps self-reliance and self-determination. This paper is based on the author's experience in various health care issues and provides a solid platform for discussion about the role of PHC in inclusive health care for the marginalized section of society.

Key words: Health, PHC, Inclusion

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BACKGROUND

Health is one of the vital indicators reflecting the quality of human life and it is a well-established fact that there is a positive correlation between health of the population and the economic development of the country. Alma Ata Declaration of 1978 by WHO adopted Primary Health Care (PHC) Programme as a strategy for 'Health for All'. Primary health care forms an integral part of the country's health care system and is the driving force behind determining policies. Primary health care can be defined as: socially appropriate, universally accessible, scientifically sound first level care provided by a suitably trained workforce supported by integrated referral systems and in a way that gives priority to those most need, maximizes community and individual self-reliance and participation and involves collaboration with other sectors. It includes the following:

- health promotion,
- Illness prevention, care of the sick, advocacy, community development etc (Kumar, 2009).

Long before the Declaration of Alma Ata, India adopted a primary health care model based on the principle that incapacity to pay should not put people off from accessing health services. Based on the recommendations of the Health Survey and Development Committee Report (the "Sir Joseph Bhore Committee Report") of 1946, the Indian Government decided to focus services on rural people. This with programmes such as the national family planning program, launched in 1952, and the policy of one community health worker per 1,000 people in the 1970s. India had already committed to most of the Alma Ata principles when the global primary health care movement began.

Studies show that the strength of a country's primary care system is associated with improved population health, decreasing all-cause mortality, all-cause premature mortality, and cause-specific premature mortality, from major respiratory and cardiovascular diseases. This relationship is significant at the macro-level and micro-level. Unfortunately, in India, not only is there

pre-existing inequality in healthcare provisions, but this is further enhanced by difficulties in accessing it, which is due to geographical, socio-economic or gender distance. Studies from developed countries demonstrate that an orientation towards a specialist based system enforces inequity in access. Health systems in low income countries with a strong primary care orientation tend to be more pro-poor, equitable and accessible (Sharma, 2009; Anand, 1993).

Recent National Health Policy (2006) has laid stress on people centered primary health care approach. Few ICMR reports have revealed that more than 80 percent of the population has no access to any form of health care. However, curative service, people perception about functioning of PHCs, preventive activities and attitude of the health staff need to be properly evaluated through various research approaches yet. In 2005, the United Progressive Alliance Government launched the National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) to improve access to quality health care, especially for poor rural women and children, to strengthen primary health care institutions, increase equity and the decentralization of services, and encourage states to generate alternate sources of financing. While the mission covers the entire country, its emphasis is on 18 states with the poorest infrastructure including Karnataka state. It is found that NRHM is very effective in certain states and fairly failed in certain states.

Primary care services are incomplete if they lack appropriate and efficient referral systems to secondary and tertiary care hospitals. Primary health care services considerably affect the rural population; however many factors weaken the excellence and effectiveness of primary healthcare services in rural areas. In India, although there are many reasons for poor primary health care performance, almost all of them stem from weak stewardship of the sector, which produces a poor incentive framework. The World Health Organisation (WHO) specifically points out that to some extent, the deterioration in health status is attributed to inadequacies in primary health care implementation, neglecting the wider factors that have

been responsible for this deterioration such as lack of political commitment, inadequate allocation of financial resources to primary health care and stagnation of inter-sectoral strategies and community participation in rural areas. The main ones being bureaucratic approach to healthcare provision, lack of accountability and responsiveness to the general public and incongruence between available funding and commitments (Jones 2009).

PRIMARY HEALTH CENTERS (PHC)

The PHC concept implied delivery of integrated health services through an appropriate institutional framework to the smallest unit of population possible. The PHC in itself embodies an integrated approach to health services development through Curative, Preventive and Promotive service. The operational responsibilities of the PHC are to cover medical care, maternal and child health services, family welfare, nutrition, health, education school health, control of communicable diseases, protected water supply, environmental sanitation and collection of vital statistics. In spite of the criticism they have faced regarding quality of care and poor infrastructure, they continue to be the major primary care provider for the majority of India's population in rural areas (Banerji, and others 2004).

A typical Primary Health Centre covers a population of 20,000 in hilly, rural, or difficult areas and 30,000 populations in plain areas with 4-6 indoor/observation beds. It acts as a referral unit for 6 sub-centers and refer out cases to Community Health Centers (CHC) (30 bedded hospital) and higher order public hospitals located at sub-district and district level. In each Community Development Block, there is one primary health centre and eight or seven sub-centers at present. An average primary health centre in a community development block covers a geographic area of 400 sq km, with a population of 1,00,000 to 1,20,000 persons living in about 100 to 125 villages. Medical relief in primary health centers is designed as an institutional service. PHCs and Sub Centre's (SC) are designed to make primary health care services available throughout the rural areas. Mudaliar

Committee (1955) Chadha Committee, (1963) Arthar Singh Committee (1973) and Shrivatsva Committee (1975) Bajaj Committee, (1986) have also highlighted the importance of upgradation of PHCs (MHFW, 2006)

The National Health Policy (NHP) 1983 envisaged a three-tier structure of primary, secondary and tertiary health-care facilities to bring health care services within the reach of the rural population. The whole concept of infrastructure for primary health care services in our country revolves around two major components of static service centers in the form of the PHCs and SCs (sub centers) and providing of extension services to villages and individual families through planned and continuous visits to show infrastructural facilities should be adequate to accomplish the multiple tasks (curative, preventive and promotive health care), family welfare, and material and child health service assigned to the PHCs for the successful implementation of the programmes. Performance of PHCs will be greatly affected due to the absence of material resources like building, equipment, vehicle, medicines, and vaccines etc (Varatharajan, 2004).

PHC's are functioning as peripheral health service institutions with little or no community involvement. Increasingly, these centers came under criticism, as they were not able to provide adequate health coverage, partly, because they were poorly staffed and equipped and lacked basic amenities and plagued with corruption. Various high level committees have found both rural and urban PHCs are not spared from issues such as the inability to perform up to the expectation due to (i) lack of man power (ii) scarce physical infrastructure and facilities; (iii) deficient quantities of drugs; (iv) lack of accountability to the public and lack of community participation; (v) lack of set standards for monitoring quality care etc.

Experts felt the performance of any health care delivery organizations can be assessed against the set standards. Standards are a means of describing the level of quality those health care organizations are expected to meet or aspire to. Key aim of these standards is to underpin the delivery

of quality services which are fair and responsive to client's needs, which should be provided equitably and which deliver improvements in the health and wellbeing of the population. Standards are the main driver for continuous improvements in quality.

Studies have also shown that, in the improved access to primary health centers and its timely function, lead to less hospitalization, less utilisation of specialist and emergency centers and less chance of patients being subjected to inappropriate health interventions. In low-income settings, the cost effectiveness of PHCs compared to other health programmes has been reinforced by World Bank findings; selected primary healthcare activities such as infant and child health, nutrition programmes and immunization appeared as 'good buys' compared to hospital care. Such interventions could avert a large number of deaths and it is demonstrated that even in resource-poor settings, it is possible to implement and sustain basic PHC services. Few debates also stressed about handing over the responsibility of PHCs gradually to Panchayats (local self Govt.) with technical support, guidance and leadership from State Health Services. However, there are several problems and shortcoming in the PHC system of many states which the district Panchayat has not been able to address effectively (Ranga Rao, 1993; Laveesh, 2009).

Primary care services are incomplete if they lack appropriate and efficient referral systems to secondary and tertiary care hospitals. Primary care referrals in India have not received as much attention. In one study (Patro, 2008) concluded that the referral system was availed of by most of the patients and that longer distances to the referral institution reduced favorable outcomes. Next, referrals depended primarily on issues related to the diagnosis and availability of adequate treatment resources. It is also suggested that appropriate referrals had to be necessary for the patient, appropriate in the course of the disease, successful in reaching its aims and cost effective at PHCs. It is also reported that referrals were more common

when the specialist hospitals were located closer to the general practice. Some time the closest referral hospital would be more than 15-20 kilometers away, which is as well the case with the majority rural sub centers/primary health centers in rural parts of India. It could be thus assumed that the referrals that were made would more likely have been out of necessity than otherwise (Raghvan, 2005).

PHC AND RURAL HEALTH SERVICES

The differences in urban-rural health indicators are a harsh reality even today; infant mortality rate is 62 per thousand live births for rural areas as compared to 39 per thousand live births for urban areas (2007). Only 31.9% of all government hospital beds are available in rural areas as compared to 68.1% for urban population. When we consider the rural-urban distribution of population in India, this difference becomes huge. Based on the current statistics provided by the Government of India, It is found that at a national level the current bed-population ratio for Government hospital beds for urban areas (1.1 beds/1000 population) is almost five times the ratio in rural areas (0.2 beds/1000 population). Apart from this shortfall in infrastructure, shortfall in trained Doctors enthusiastic to work in rural areas is also one of the factors responsible for poor health care delivery systems in the rural areas. The rural areas are still unable to access the services of the qualified Doctors. There's shortfall of 9% doctors in all Primary Health Centers (Ajit, 2005).

Rural health services in India are provided through a network of integrated health and family welfare delivery system. These are mainly dependent upon networking of PHCs which involve in both curative and preventive activities as well as promoting family welfare services. The PHCs are the first contact point between the village community and the medical officer, whereas sub-centers are the most peripheral contact point between the PHC and community. Lack of access to these institutions is a reflection of an overall deprivation and it results on many health indicators. Many

studies indicated that the health services are inaccessible or poorly accessible for the poor and disadvantaged communities of the society.

Some noted studies have highlighted rural PHCs suffered from a variety of limitations (both institutional and financial) and shortcomings across the country. Limitations to rural health infrastructure and services include (a) Inadequate of medical and paramedical staff (b) lack of amenities in PHC buildings; (c) Scarcity of construction materials causing delay in creating infrastructure, especially sub-centre buildings; (d) Unsatisfactory supply and maintenance of drugs and equipments (e) lack of set standards for monitoring quality care (f) Poor maintenance of vehicles at the PHCs etc. These problems throw up several issues that need to be immediately examined. Prominent among these is the funding and maintenance of rural health infrastructure. Scarcity of trained manpower is another major problem. Moreover, qualified medical and paramedical staff is not willing to work in rural areas because of professional, personal and social reasons. Regarding management of health services at the primary health centre level, various problems relating to suitability of the personnel, coordination of work of different health functionaries (CHC/SC), field logistics and facilities, infrastructural support and services, sectoral coordination with organizations related to health, etc., have been noticed (Umamani,2010; Srinivasan 1994). This problem was further compounded by bureaucratic procedures and practices relating to postings and transfers of medical and paramedical staff. Even when we judge from the point of view of government expectations, the overall performance of PHCs has been greatly wanting (Mavalankar, 2009; Rajesh,2006; Srinivasa, 2001).

ADEQUACY AND ACCESSIBILITY OF THE PHC SERVICE

In the rural areas, a large number of rural people seek medical treatment and health care by the PHCs. In terms of ratio of population and availability of services the rural areas have inadequate services, particularly in some specific PHCs. However, in urban areas the PHCs rendering

various services seems to be adequate enough because the people of the higher rungs of the society do not depend upon PHCs at all. Hence, PHCs are more needed in rural than urban areas. Urban areas have many favorable conditions (availability of multi-specialty hospitals etc) leading to less dependency on PHCs by the people. Therefore, more number of PHCs and sub centers are needed in rural areas in a developing country (Smith, 2009). Sometimes certain services are available in PHCs but people do not get these services due to various reasons. In rural areas, certain services are available and medicines are supplied in plenty. However, the benefits of these facilities do not reach the beneficiaries. This may be due to the factors like lack of propaganda, awareness and education, lack of hygiene, wrong notion about the quality of medicines provide in PHCs, lack of transport system etc (Aldana, 2001).

Ganguly (2008) opined that some time rural PHCs are usually under-utilized because they fail to provide their clients with the desired amount of attention and medication, inconvenient locations, and long waiting time. Utilization of health services is a complex phenomenon, which is affected by various factors like people's perception about illness, severity of illness, need for health care, knowledge about healthcare services, economic and social accessibility of health system, and biases of the healthcare providers. The economic viability of the PHCs solely depends on the visit by the patients. This is dependent on the basic conditions of the Centers. The government invests more money every year for medicine, staff, bed and other logistics but neglects the variables that affect the annual turnout of patients. It is at this point the PHCs fail to attract beneficiaries. Therefore, they remain economically not viable (Jones and others, 2009).

Approximately one-third of the people of our country, particularly living in the rural, hilly and arid as well as feudal areas have critical health status. Active participation of the people in managing their own health and that of the communities where they live, are associated with the issues of food security, hygiene and underdevelopment. The health of this population

is directly linked to their economic, social and political status and all of them directly depend on PHCs for their health needs. Major thrust should be to help them reverse the situation through a well-planned, adequately financed community-oriented Integrated Health and Development Programmes with substantial participations from voluntary organizations. There have been several efforts in the Planning Commission in identifying these vulnerable areas. Interventions for enhancing community participation in health and family welfare services were designed and implemented. The interventions mainly focused on the active participation of Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRIs) and non-government organisations (NGOs). Dynamic participation of voluntary organisations in the scheduling, supervision and completion of health programmes, mainly in the susceptible areas is more necessary than ever (Kamat, 1995).

PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP (PPP) AND PHCS

Public-Private Partnership (PPP) has emerged as one of the important strategies for health sector reforms in the country. Various states have taken Initiatives by NRHM, Health & FW Dept to undertake effective PPPs in health services including RCH-II and other national health programmes like Malaria, TB etc. Studies found that the quality of PHCs service have improved considerably after an effective PPP in many rural areas of the country. In Many states through PPP, PHCs have initiated variety of activities including Community Health Insurance, Telemedicine, Tele-agriculture and farmer advisories (with ISRO), Mainstreaming of Traditional Medicine in Primary care with herbal gardens at PHC, Integration of mental health care, Improved community participation, Health Management Information Systems, stipulation and administration of necessary drugs, accomplishment of normal treatment strategy and drugs and therapeutics board in all-PHCs-etc. Further, to augment the PPP initiatives, it is proposed to have Regional Resource Centre (RRC) to provide technical support for PHC- PPP – NGO activities in various States.

Moreover For an unrestrained development of PHC, flexibility and adaptation in long established bureaucracies are essential at both within the administration and at community level and emphasis on preventive approaches (Dipankar, 2005; Laveesh, 2009).

Till date, hardly one or two studies (Srinivasa,2001; Nanjunda, 2011) have been conducted on primary health care and found that in rural areas, health services provided by the PHCs suffer from quality degeneration because of non-availability of emergency services in time, absenteeism and lack of laboratory facilities or equipment. Difficulties in communication and information usage of expired drugs etc are the causes for low quality service by the PHCs in rural areas of Karnataka. Sometimes, staff of the PHCs have to work in an unsecured zone. Situation in many rural pockets are really bad where PHCs are working in rented congested spaces. News paper report says there are delays in the receipt of funds for drugs by the district government and in the procurement and delivery of drugs to PHCs; and PHCs do not conduct proper accounting. Corruption exists in purchasing medicines. Communities and NGOs lack access to pertinent information on health services, and they are not involved in supervising the programmes and the service providers. Hence, it is essential to look further into the problem .Also no such systematic and holistic study undertaken so far in understanding the effective functioning of primary health centers in the rural areas of the country. The present attempt may go a long way in bridging the gap between the philosophy of working of primary health centers and the reality of the situation.

CONCLUSION

It is essential to get an insight into the functioning of the PHCs which were established with the objective of minimizing the hardships of the rural people arising out of lack of specialized medical services in the nearby areas or to district and other rural referral hospitals which are already

overcrowded. Evaluating the scheme will make available useful pointers to the policy makers and the implementers for taking corrective measures on bottlenecks, disparities, etc., if any, in the functioning of rural PHCs.

Note: The author acknowledges the support of ICMR for this project.

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SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGY

Lancy D Souza

Social Psychology

Edited by: Dr. Lancy D' Souza

Edition: 2016

ISBN: 978-93-5056-771-5

Published by: Discovery Publishing House Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi (India)

4

Prevalence of Common Mental Health Problems among Rural Community A Case of Kodagu Districts - Karnataka State

Dr. Nangunda

ABSTRACT

Mental Health is one of the prime concerns of mankind, since his emergence on the earth. Health is a pre-requisite for human development and is essentially concerned with the well-being of the common man. Quality of Mental health care, health orientation and social protection of health in a population affects the development status of any nation. Mental Health is not only related to medical care but an integrated development of an entire human society. Normally the context in which an individual lives it is of very vital and significant for his/her Mental health status and quality of life. There are some external determinants which are decide the Mental health status of any person including social environment, health, culture, hospitals, doctors etc. Also it significantly depends on some internal factors including his/her health culture, education, health practices, etc. As far as an organization with the rural Mental health is concerned, there is no basic service for an inclusive health interference effort to understand. Mental health as a sub culture complex in developing a model of culturally suited health care delivery system especially for the rural people of the country. With this background this paper is to reveal various Mental health related problems of the village folks in two villages of Kolar districts of Karnataka. This paper conclude that Mental health issues of the villagers are largely being influenced by the social and cultural factors.

INTRODUCTION

The world health assembly in 1977 started a movement for health and well-being for all by the year 2000 A.D. India was also committed to achieving 'Health

for all to her citizen'. Health is one of the vital indicators reflecting the quality of human life. World Health Organization (WHO) describes health as a state of complete physical, mental, social and spiritual well-being and not merely as absence of diseases or infirmity. The National health policy accepted by the honorable Indian parliament in 1983 states health care as the main device for achieving sustainable development of the community. It is known factor that development of any society depends on the Mental healthy people only. Without good health even we cannot think appropriately and act properly. It is known fact that without proper mental health we cannot expect proper social inclusion of any community. The health is not only a stable state of physical and natural well-being but also in true sense it involved the various other complex issues. As it is widely known that Mental Health is one of the imperative indicators shimmering the excellence of human life. Healthy community is very vital because it can set the destiny of the any society, country, any type of development or any kind of achievement etc. Health is a very vital integrated component of an individual. Sometime collapse of Mental health may even lead an individual towards an early death. Like this unhealthy community may be a hinder for the holistic development of any society. Poor Mental health status of any community may isolate that community from the national main stream.

Experts felt that Mental health can be more precisely viewed as an index of human adaptation to 'micro-ecological alcove'. Even though western system of medicine has many advantages over the traditional, it has not totally been accepted by the majority rural Indian masses till today. It is because of their unique health behaviour consistently influencing by their inherited culture, tradition, beliefs, values, norms and practice etc. All these play a very vital role in shaping Mental health of that particular community. Invariably it keep shapes the perception and attitude towards the onset and curing of different mental health problems in a given community over the period of time. Finally it determines to select a particular type of treatment to solve the particular type of mental health problem. Sociologists felt that every community (may be urban/tribal/rural) normally develops their own health needs and curing approaches after motivating by their changing levels of socio-economic conditions. In this process, health of the rural's as subsystem will be mainly infused by the above attributes of entire social system. Experts felt cultural response of the community to the Mental health problems confronted by it determines the way individual members perceive different ways of dealing with various Mental health problems. As far as an organic linkage with the rural health is concerned, there is no basic service for a comprehensive Mental health intervention attempt to understand health culture as a sub-culture complex in developing a model of culturally suited health Mental care delivery system especially for the rural people of the country. Very little work, however, has entailed an in-depth analytical study of comparative emic perspectives of different factors influencing rural people's Mental health behaviour in India. With this background this paper is to reveal various health related problems in two villages of Kolar districts of Karnataka state.

Objectives

1. To find out the different health problems facing by the studied rural population.

- To identify the factors influencing health seeking behaviour of the studied population.

Methodology

- Area under study:* Selected two villages in Kodagu districts.
- Sampling:* Data has been collected from the 100 village members using simple random technique.

Tools for Data Collection

- Survey:* Primary Data has been collected through questionnaires and checking and medical documents.
- Interview:* Carefully designed structured interview has been conducted to collect data.
- Focus group study:* Data has also been collected through two focus group (each group had 5-7 members) studies including common public teachers, religious leaders, and others).

Analysis of Data

The qualitative data has been analyzed using NUD*IST statistical software's and the quantitative data has been analyzed using SPSS software.

Result

Table 4.1: Age and Sex of the Respondents

Age in Years		Sex		Total
		Male	Female	
25-35	Count	30	20	50
	%	30.0	20.0	50.0
35-45	Count	11	25	36
	%	11.0	25.0	36.0
Above 45	Count	10	4	14
	%	10.0	4.0	14.0
Total	Count	51	49	100
	%	51.0	49.0	100.0

Table 4.2: Common, Mental Health Problems facing by Men

Problems	f	Count	X ²	P
1. Anxiety	23	23	4.640	0.326
2. Depression	18	18		
3. Sleep disorder	23	23		
4. Homeless stress	10	10		
5. Social deprivation	26	26		
Total	100	100		

Table 4.3: Common Mental Health Problems facing by the Women

Problems	f	Count	X ²	P
1. Sleep disorder	15	15	3.328	0.505
2. Anxiety	23	23		
3. Depression	25	25		
4. Homelessness	24	24		
5. Social deprivation	13	13		
Total	100	100		

Table 4.4: Common Mental Health Problems facing by the Adults

Problems	f	Count	X ²	P
1. Anxiety	11	11	13.111	0.000
2. Suicide	31	31		
3. Self-harm	23	23		
4. Depression	33	33		
5. Sleep disorder	2	2		
Total	100	100		

Table 4.5: Common Mental Health Problems facing by the Aged

Problems	f	Count	X ²	P
1. Social-deprivation	11	11	23.111	0.000
2. Homelessness	31	31		
3. Sleep disorder	23	23		
4. Depression	33	33		
5. Self-harm	2	2		
Total	100	100		

Table 4.6: Reasons for Mental Health Problem as Believed by the Samples

Problems	f	Count	X ²	P
1. Humoral imbalance	4	4	19.704	0.001
2. Superhuman causation	34	34		
3. Biological/genetics	32	32		
4. Immoral behaviour	11	11		
5. Personal problems	19	19		
Total	100	100		

Discussion

Mental Health-seeking behaviour of the rural population is greatly governed by cultural values, beliefs and traditions. However Now it is open for gradual change because continuous interventions of the different kinds of external agencies. Further in the changes of Mental health seeking behaviour patterns of the rural people, one also can notice incredible fresh air which have occurred with

Table 4.7: Villager's Perception about Curing Various Mental Diseases

Problems	f	Count	X ²	p
1. Local/traditional healers	34	34		
2. Home remedies	22	22		
3. Worshipping deity /spirit	30	30	22.452	0.000
4. Modern medicines	12	12		
5. Others	2	2		
Total	100	100		

respect to philosophy, knowledge, and practices of indigenous systems such as Ayurveda, Homeopathy, Allopathic, etc. However, it becomes important to work on problems of rural's Mental health because it differs from a particular area to another area owing to their remote geographical setting, historical milieu and the processes of social change (Bulliyya, 2009). Geographical isolation and limited interactions with other communities has become an obstacle to know the degree of prevalence of certain mental health issues among rural communities (Arappa, 1999; Bose, 2006; Kerketta, 2008).

Rural's exhibit a far less Mental health modernity, as compared to the rest of the population. Their own beliefs, illiteracy, poverty, non-access to scientific information contribute to this low Health Modernity status. The widespread poverty, illiteracy, malnutrition, absence of safe drinking water and sanitary living conditions, poor maternal and child health services and ineffective coverage of national health and nutritional services have been traced out in several studies as possible contributing factors to dismal health conditions prevailing among the tribal population in Karnataka (Karnataka Human Development Report-2005). Mental Health services provided by the rural PHCs suffer from quality degeneration because of non-availability of emergency services in time, absenteeism, lack of laboratory facilities or equipments, difficulties of communication and information usage of expired drugs etc. are the causes for low quality service. Mental health by the PHCs in rural areas of Karnataka. Some time, staffs of the PHCs have to work in an unsecured zone. The Situation is worst in many rural districts of northern Karnataka where PHCs are working in rented tiny space without having good basic facilities. News paper report says there are delays in the receipt of funds for drugs by the district government and in the procurement and delivery of drugs to PHCs. Because of these problems rural folk don't want to visit PHCs in majority cases. Corruption also exists in purchasing medicines. Communities and NGOs lack access to relevant information on health services, and they are not involved in monitoring the services and the service providers.

Conclusion

The plight of rural people has drawn increasing policy attention since 1960. Today the majority of rural people are suffering with various mental diseases. It is stated there is a positive correlation between the health status of rural people and

their social, economical and cultural background. Over the last few decades various Indian governments have developed plans to achieve long-term goals to provide a comprehensive mental health care programme for the rural people, and have increasingly emphasized the more immediate need to provide essential basic mental health care and scientific management of rural the rural population's traditional system. Experts have conducted various studies on culturally bounded mental health behaviour among various rural settings. Still, they have not yet completely understood the dynamics of mental health behaviour of rural people. It is found that poverty, illiteracy, malnutrition, scarcity of potable water, sanitary conditions, poor mother child health services, problems in covering national health and nutritional services, etc., have been found the most vital causative factors for the prevalence of several health issues among rural communities in the country. Attempt is needed to comprehend Mental health as a sub culture complex in developing a model of culturally suited health module programmes specially for the nation's rural people with their different castes and class.

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**Journal of Liaquat University of Medical and Health
Sciences (JLUMHS)**

ISSN: 1729-0341.

VOLUME 13 NUMBER 01 - JAN - APRIL 2014

Missing Doctors? An Investigative Study on the Absenteeism among Medical workers in Community Health Centers (CHCs) in Rural South Karnataka, India

Nanjunda

ABSTRACT

OBJECTIVE: To find out unauthorized absenteeism among the various staff of Community Health Centers (CHCs)

STUDY DESIGN: Cross Sectional

Settings: This study was conducted in 30 selected Community Health Centers (CHC) in southern Karnataka, India

METHODS: Simple random technique and data collected through unnoticed visits.

RESULT: In this study we observed that unauthorized absenteeism is most common and it would be very hard to find different medical workers in the CHC's even during working hours. Some doctors were making adjustments among the colleagues for being absent by turns. Mainly absent rate of Physicians are more. Absent rate is more on Fridays' and Mondays'.

CONCLUSION; Unauthorized absence of the Doctors has resulted in rural health care system even worst for the poor. This paper suggests that strong accountability and commitment is required on the part of the doctors. Also Govt should provide proper fundamental facility, specialist doctors, and provide emergency medicine and equipments.

KEYWORDS: CHS, Doctor, Absenteeism, Weeks, Staff, Health.

INTRODUCTION

From the 5th Five year plan (1974-1979) onwards government of India noted regarding disparities in accessing quality health service for rural areas. Hence from 6th Five year plan onwards government took major decision to increase the total number of CHC's (Community Health Centers) across the country. (Planning Commission, 2001). In India, Primary Health Centers (PHCs) are the foundation of rural healthcare. In the second stage CHCs have been established. CHCs play an imperative responsibility as the second level of contact and a connection between individuals and the health system, bringing healthcare delivery where people live and work. Further these CHCs are charged with providing advanced promotive, preventive, curative and rehabilitative care also. Various health experts suggested integrating and intensification of the rural PHCs and CHCs through proper standard and functional linkages¹

Various research studies have concerned about the functioning of CHC's including large coverage of geographical area which is practically impossible. Even today CHC's are lacking required fundamental facilities. Some CHC's even don't have adequate power and water supply. More than 70% of CHC's are running either with one specialized or without any specialists in many rural areas. Hence CHC's are not in the position to act as an effective referral center. In

addition to that now a day's CHC's are facing insufficient medical and paramedical staffs². Availability of required specialists in CHC's also become a vital problem in the rural parts. Frequent absenteeism among the medical staff has become a major problem today (HDRK Report, 1999-2005).

Absenteeism is the frequent absence from work, especially without good reason. It is more commonly occurring both in developed and developing countries. It is a source of concern in view of the weak national economy and health system. Absenteeism leads to have defeat in main working hours, finance, productivity, jobs in the health sector³. According to World Bank's Global Monitoring Report-2008 (GMR) Absenteeism among health care workers is the utmost in India, A survey carried out in 2002 -03, has found that rate of absenteeism among healthcare workers in India is 42%. Absenteeism has become a big problem for the CHC's. Both medical and paramedical staffs of the CHC's are not attending CHC's regularly. They visit CHCs if they have some free time! Still they receive a huge Govt. salary and are taking undue advantages. They have a nexus with the higher authority and are escaping without being punished⁴.

In a study conducted in Uganda found that "The average rate of absenteeism was 47.9% and after desegregation of key health cadres, the absent rate of clinical officers was around 47.5% Medical doctors were

Missing Doctors?

at 44.2%, Enrolled midwife were at 43.4%, registered nurses were at 38.1% and Registered Midwife were at 44.7%. Further, the important determinants of health workers absenteeism found from this study were working culture, supervision, Job satisfaction, facility available in hospitals, salary package, etc" (UNHC0,2010). Experts opined that opined absenteeism in case of CHCs is very high in rural India. If doctors are absent from the work either the community or the higher authority do not ask any question. In some cases instead of the Doctors nurses treat the patients' in many CHCs!. Because of absenteeism of the Lab technicians some time patients' has to get the blood test in the private laboratories paying more money⁶. Further it is opined that "Doctors with housing and other facilities at the CHCs are less absent than other health providers. Doctors in Community Health Centers (CHCs), which are having greater facilities, shows more work progress and commitment"⁵. This pattern may reflect the improved infrastructure at each CHCs" This current study has been conducted to find out the prevalence rate of absenteeism of medical workers in the rural CHC's of southern Karnataka, India.

METHODOLOGY

Study Design: Cross sectional

This study was conducted in Mysore, Hassan and Coorg districts (both city and rural) of South Karnataka-India. Districts were selected based on the Health and Family Welfare Survey Report 2011.

Method

A total of 30 CHCs were selected through random sampling as follows;

Districts	Total Number of CHCs in the districts	Selected for the study
Mysore,	23	13
Hassan	30	10
Coorg	10	7
Total	63	30

A total of 55 medical officers, 60 male and female nurses and a total of 35 lab technicians were included in this study. Frequent un-announced observations through visits were made over a period of Four weeks in the selected CHC's in the above mentioned districts. Data collected during unannounced visits made by the previously selected local informants only. Unnoticed visits were to avoid alertness among the

medical staff. Informants physically verified the presence or absence of each designated staff at CHC. Informants visited more than 4 times over a period of time to the each selected CHC. Repeated visits were made to calculate more accurate measure of absence rate.

Tools for data collection

1. Survey
2. Informal Interview
3. Participant Observation

Analysis of Data

Collected data has been analyzed using minitab software.

RESULTS

GRAPH I: ABSENTEEISM RATE IN THE STUDIED DISTRICTS

TABLE I: ABSENTEEISM RATE OF KEY MEDICAL SERVICE PROVIDERS

Category	Absent rate in Percentage		X ²	p
	N	%		
Medical Officer	27	27.0	6.391	0.381
Lab Technician	17	17.0		
Female nurse	13	13.0		
Pharmacist	12	12.0		
Lady Health Vision	11	11.0		
Male nurse	9	9.0		
Adult nurse Midwife	11	11.0		
Total	100	100		

TABLE II: DAY WISE ABSENTEEISM

Days	Absent rate in percentage		X ²	p
	N	%		
Monday	17	17.0	4.967	0.420
Tuesday	11	11.0		
Wednesday	13	13.0		
Thursday	12	12.0		
Friday	21	21.0		
Saturday	26	26.0		
Total	100	100		

TABLE III: NUMBER OF TIMES ABSENT FROM THE WORK

Designation	Number of Times Absent from the Work			
	Present all the Times	Absent 1 Time	Absent 2 Times	Absent 3 Times
Doctor	19.5%	17.6%	44.6%	17.9%
Pharmacist	16.9%	20.8%	43.7%	18.5%
Female Nurse	27.3%	14.0%	31.2%	27.1%
Lab Technician	18.8%	21.9%	42.7%	17.8%

DISCUSSION

In case of absenteeism rate of key medical service providers it is found that 27% of medical doctors are being absent regularly followed by 17% of lab technician and 13% of female nurses are also absenting from the duty regularly. In case of day wise absenteeism 17% of the staff are absenting only on Mondays whereas 13% of them are absenting only on Wednesdays only. In case of day wise absenteeism majority of the staffs are absenting only during afternoon session. In case of service wise absenteeism 36% of the staffs are absenting who have joined recently and 14% of the staffs are having more than 12 years of service. Regarding reasons for absenteeism 26% of them cited personal work whereas 19% of them said it is because of official duty whereas 16% of them said it is because of field visit.

Among the studied districts Hassan (36%) has witnessed a high absent rate of medical workers followed by the Kodagu district (33%). Coorg is predominantly a hilly area. During monsoon time it is almost impossible to stay there. Majority of the CHCs are run-

ning under very difficult circumstances with minimum facility only. Posted doctors won't ready to work in Coorg districts because of its remoteness. Hence majority of the posts have been left unfilled and more prevalence of absenteeism is common here. Some-time weeks together Doctors and other staff wont turn-up. Chamaraja nagar districts is a comparatively a backward district in the state. Transport system is not so good and number of CHCs are also very less. Absenteeism rate is also high in these districts. Further, since Mysore districts is more politically influenced than other two districts CHCs in Mysore rural area have reasonably good facilities. It is found that local self governments, health committees and NGOs are very active here and hence absent rate is comparatively low⁸.

It is found that absent rate by designations, Doctors are 29% followed by the lab technicians (17%). In case of reasons cited for absenteeism, 26% of them staff cited 'personal work'. Even though 19% of them cited official work as a reason for absenteeism it is found actually untrue, 76% of them are engaged in private practices (running their own clinics). Some time they are working as consultant in high paying private hospitals. They get both Government salary and high remuneration from the private hospitals. This is also one of the vital reason for absenteeism and hence they are visiting CHC's only twice a week for the name sake only. Further, absent rate is more common on Saturday's. If they absent on Saturday they will turn only on Monday because of Sunday (holiday) in-between. It is also found that usually medical staffs will be more absent during afternoon session/s. Medical staffs having more than 12 years of experiences have shown highest rate of absenteeism with respects to length of service. These people have good relationship with the higher authority. It is found that persons having more experience are deep-rooted in the system and have good connections with the high officials. Hence they are escaping is unpunished. In case of number of times absent from the work, again Doctors and Pharmacist have occupied first and second position respectively. In some CHCs staffs remain absent on an understanding basis among themselves⁷.

This kind of absenteeism indicates major accountability problems. Absence level might be high because of lack of supervision and monitoring by the higher authority. Karnataka government has brought a rule that the medical students who have been graduated from the government medical colleges (under free seat quota) should work at least three years in any rural part of the state. If not, they have to pay a huge fine. Still amazingly young doctors are not showing interest to serve in rural areas and they are paying fine!. Big

CHC buildings and assigning staff (on record) doesn't mean doctors are available in rural areas 24/7. Some time due to shortage of the staff single Physician might have to manage both PHCs and CHCs. Our study also found that majority of the CHC's are facing lack of fundamental facilities. Some CHC's don't have enough medicines, equipments, power, and water facility and are located in remote areas (NHPR, 2002). Suitable staff and residential houses are not available. This is also a reason why staff members not staying in the head quarters⁸.

CONCLUSION

This study documents the overall absenteeism rate, the reasons for absenteeism and the a range of factors influencing absence rates among the studied samples. This study had found that absenteeism rate is more common among the Physicians which leads to poor medical facilities in rural part of the country (NRHM, 2006). Government should take initiative to provide required fundamental facilities including staff residences and extra perks, for the rural health staffs. A flying squad need to be initiated to give surprise visit to CHCs³. District health officials should take strong actions to punish irregular staff of the CHCs⁹. Also Govt. can focus on introducing community based monitoring system for tracking the medical staff. It is better to train local community health workers scientifically to handle emergency medical needs. Moreover Doctors also should introspect their accomplishment towards the society.

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JSSCM Journal
May - 2013
Volume 2, Issue 1
ISSN : 2277-145X (Print)
www.jsscacs.edu.in
Email : jssautonomous@gmail.com

JSSCM JOURNAL

Published by :
JSS COLLEGE OF ARTS, COMMERCE AND SCIENCE
(Autonomous)
Ooty Road, Mysore-570 025
India

An Epidemiological Investigation on Health Conditions and Health Culture of the Rural People in the Selected Villages of Kodagu districts, Karnataka (INDIA)

Dr. Nanjunda

Abstract

Health is one of the prime concerns of mankind, since his emergence on the earth. Health is a pre-requisite for human development and is essentially concerned with the well being of the common man. Quality of health care, health orientation and social protection of health in a population affects the development status of any nation. Health is not only related to medical care but an integrated development of an entire human society. Normally the context in which an individual lives it is of very vital and significant for his/her health status and quality of life. There are some external determinants which can decide the health status of any person including social environment, health culture, hospitals, doctors etc. Also it significantly depends on some internal factors including his/her health culture, education, health practices, etc. As far as an organic linkage with the rural health is concerned, there is no basic service for an inclusive health interference effort to understand health culture as a sub culture complex in developing a model of culturally suited health care delivery system especially for the rural people of the country. With this background this paper is to reveal various health related problems of the village folks in two villages of Kodagu districts of Karnataka state south India. This paper concludes that health culture of the villagers are largely being influenced by the social and cultural factors.

Key words: Health, Disease, Cure, Hospital, Beliefs, Rural

1. Introduction

Health is one of the vital indicators reflecting the quality of human life. The plight of rural people has drawn increasing policy attention since 1960. World Health Organization (WHO) describes health as a state of complete physical, mental, social and spiritual well-being and not merely as absence of diseases or infirmity. The world health assembly in 1977 started a movement for health and wellbeing for all by the year 2000 A.D. India was also committed to achieving "Health for all to her citizen". The National health policy accepted by the honorable Indian parliament in 1983 states health care as the main device for achieving sustainable development of the community. It is known factor that development of any society depends on the healthy people only. Without good health even we cannot think appropriately and act properly. It is known fact that without proper health we cannot expect proper social inclusion of any community. The health is not only a stable state of physical and natural well being but also in true sense it involved the various other complex issues. As it is widely known that Health is one of the

imperative indicators shimmering the excellence of human life. Healthy community is very vital because it can set the destiny of the any society, country, any type of development or any kind of achievement etc. Health is a very vital integrated component of an individual. Sometime collapse of health may even lead an individual towards an early death. Like this unhealthy community may be a hinder for the holistic development of any society. Poor health status of any community may isolate that community from the national main stream (Venkataratham, 1989).

Health culture is a very wider concept as it includes various health problems, occurrence, medicine, healing, beliefs, norms values side effects, habits, rituals all these issues works in a given set of system which together known as health culture. Banerji defined 'health culture means health behavior of the people in the context of the availability and accessibility of health institutions and health care facilities and their cultural meaning and cultural perceptions of several health problems existing in a given socio-economic condition' (Banerji, 1982)

Experts felt that health can be more precisely viewed as an index of human adaptation to 'micro-ecological alcove'. Even though western system of medicine has many advantages over the traditional, it has not totally been accepted by the majority rural Indian masses till today. It is because of their unique health behavior consistently influencing by their inherited culture, tradition, beliefs, values, norms and practice etc. All these

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play a very vital role in shaping health behavior of that particular community. Invariably it keeps shaping the perception and attitude towards the onset and curing of different health problems in a given community over the period of time. Finally it determines to select a particular type of treatment to solve the particular type of health problem. Sociologists felt that every community (may be urban/tribal/rural) normally develops their own health needs and curing approaches after motivating by their changing levels of socio-economic conditions. In this process, health of the rural's as a subsystem will be mainly infused by the above attributes of entire social system. Experts felt cultural response of the community to the health problem confronted by it determines the way individual members perceive different ways of dealing with various health problems (Choudhari, 1986). As far as an organic linkage with the rural health is concerned, there is no basic service for a comprehensive health intervention attempt to understand health culture as a sub culture complex in developing a model of culturally suited health care delivery system especially for the rural people of the country. Very little work, however, has entailed an in-depth analytical study of comparative emic perspectives of different factors influencing rural people's health behavior in India. With this background this paper is to reveal various health related problems in two villages of Kodagu districts of Karnataka state

Objectives

1. To find out the different health problems facing by the studied rural population
2. To identify the factors influencing health seeking behavior and culture of the studied population

2. Methodology

Area Under study: Selected Two villages in Kodagu districts of Karnataka, south India
 Sampling: Data has been collected from the 200 village members (100 men and 100 women) using simple random technique

2.1. Tools for data collection

1. Survey: Primary Data has been collected through structured questionnaires
2. Interview: Carefully designed structured interview has been conducted to collect data
3. Focus group study: Data has also been collected through Two focus group (each group had 5-7 members) studies including common public teachers, religious leaders, and others)

2.2. Analysis of Data

The qualitative data has been analyzed using NUD*IST statistical software's and the quantitative data has been analyzed using SPSS software

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Health Problems of Men and Women in the Studied Population

	Problems (women)	Frequency	Count	Sl. No	Problems (Men)	Frequency	Count
1	BP/Diabetics	18	18	1	Gynecological Problems	36	36
2.	T B	23	23	2	Arthritis	34	34
3	Jaundice,	23	23	3	Lungs problem	13	18
4	Kidney/Heart	10	10	4	Anemia	13	3
5	Stomach upset	20	20	5	Asthma	4	4
6	Other	6	6	6	Other	5	5
	Total	100	100		Total	100	
		X² 18.6	P .000	Highly significant			

Table 2. Reasons for health problem as believed by the villagers

Sl.No	Problems	Frequency	%	X ²	P
1	Humoral imbalance	4	4.00	21.186	.000*
2	Superhuman causation	34	34.00		
3	Cosmology	32	32.00		
4	Pathogenic	11	11.00		
5	Punishment for deed	19	19.00		
	Total	100	100.00		

*Highly significant

Table 3. Villager's perception about curing various diseases

Sl.No	Problems	Frequency	%	X ²	P
1	Local/traditional healers	34	34.00	23.694	.000*
2	Home remedies	22	22.00		
3	Worshiping deity/sprit	30	30.00		
4	Modern medicines	12	12.00		
5	Others	2	2.00		
	Total	100	100.00		

*Highly significant

Table 4. What preventive measures you would like to take to control the outbreak of any diseases?

Type	Frequency	%	X ²	P
Satisfying deity	21	21.00	21.542	.000*
Celebrating fair and festivals	27	27.00		
Follow customs	17	17.00		
Maintaining hygienic conditions	15	15.00		
Surrender to cosmology powers	20	20.00		
Total	100	100.00		

*Highly significant

4. Discussion

It is widely known fact that health status of the rural people is poor because of isolation, habitat, difficult terrain, poor understanding of their health behavior etc. Hence medical anthropologists suggest to follow on integrated multi disciplinary approach to understand rural health concepts, focusing diagnostics, curative and preventive health care, Since sometime rural may

have to face some advance diseases like malaria, T.B, Typhoid, STD, Malnutrition, anemia, sometime their traditional medicine system may get failed in diagnosing and curing the problem. Hence it is found that culturally and geographically specific health care system is need of the hour. All above tables shows how rural people are still believe in the age old traditions

Perception of illness and sickness directly affects on health seeking behavior of the rural community. In rural area socio-cultural pattern will be very complex and also it plays a major role in adopting different kinds of treatment to cure any health problem. In rural setup health and disease are more related to practice of traditional medicines. Since in certain rural parts trained Doctors available some time traditional medicine co-exists with modern medicine. In this concept changing rural health culture may be more perceived in the context of knowledge of health problems, health beliefs, new healing approach, norms and values, related to health and disease and limitations of different types of medicines.

Out study found that Health-seeking behavior of the rural population is greatly governed by cultural values, beliefs and traditions. However Now it is open for gradual change because continuous interventions of the different kinds of external agencies. Further in the changes of health seeking behavior patterns of the rural people, one also can notice incredible fresh air which have occurred with respect to philosophy, knowledge, and practices of indigenous systems such as Ayurveda, Homeopathy, Allopathic, etc. However, it becomes important to work on problems of rural's health because it differs from a particular area to another area owing to their remote geographical setting, historical milieu and the processes of social change (Bulliyya, 2009). Geographical isolation and limited interactions with other communities has become an obstacle to know the degree of prevalence of certain dangers diseases including HIV/AIDS among rural communities (Arlappa, 1999; Bose, 2006; Kerketta, 2008).

In this study it is found that Health culture is a product of actions adopted by the pool of changes over the period of time it is original that rural health culture should not be under scored as, superstitions our of lock of various external agencies including lack of education. Many rural focused health programmes have not been successful because of lack of local cultural component in the programme. The biggest problem in room for emotions, proactive behavior

associated within various diseases since beliefs, under strolling and experience plays a vital role culturally accepted and culturally meaningful health programme for the rules in essential today (Ref Tab-3 and 4).

Rural's exhibit a far less health modernity, as compared to the rest of the population. Their own beliefs, illiteracy, poverty, non-access to scientific information contribute to this low Health Modernity status. The widespread poverty, illiteracy, malnutrition, absence of safe drinking water and sanitary living conditions, poor maternal and child health services and ineffective coverage of national health and nutritional services have been traced out in several studies as possible contributing factors to dismal health conditions prevailing among the tribal population in Karnataka (Karnataka Human Development Report-2005). Health services provided by the rural PHCs (Primer health centers) suffer from quality degeneration because of non-availability of emergency services in time, absenteeism, lack of laboratory facilities or equipments, difficulties of communication and information usage of expired drugs etc are the causes for low quality service by the PHCs (Primer health centers) in rural areas of Karnataka. Some time, staffs of the PHCs have to work in an unsecured zone. The Situation is worst in many rural districts of northern Karnataka where PHCs are working in rented tiny space without having good basic facilities. News paper report says there are delays in the receipt of funds for drugs by the district government and in the procurement and delivery of drugs to PHCs. Because of these problems rural folk don't want to visit PHCs in majority cases. Corruption also exists in purchasing medicines. Communities and NGOs lack access to relevant information on health services, and they are not involved in monitoring the services and the service providers.

5. Suggestive Conclusion

Today the majority of rural people are suffering with various communicable and non communicable diseases. It is stated there is a positive correlation

between the health status of rural people and their social, economical and cultural background. Over the last few decades various Indian governments have developed plans to achieve long term goals to provide a comprehensive health care programme for the rural people, and have increasingly emphasized the more immediate need to provide essential basic primary health care and scientific management of rural the rural population's traditional system. Experts have conducted various studies on culturally bounded health behavior among various rural settings. Still, they have not yet completely understood the dynamics of health behavior of rural people. It is found that that poverty, illiteracy, malnutrition, scarcity of potable water, sanitary conditions, poor mother child health services, problems in covering national health and nutritional services, etc. have been found the most vital causative factors for the prevalence of several health issues among rural communities in the country. Attempt is needed to comprehend health culture as a sub culture complex in developing a model of culturally suited health module programmes especially for the nation's rural people with their different castes and class. There is dearth need to provide locally setting health education. Mass media can play a vital role in this aspect

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Vol.3, No.2

July-December 2016

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Panchayat Raj Institutions and Rural Health Care System in Karnataka

Health is one of the vital elements of human development in any society. The Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRIs) are the Constitutional set up in India for grass roots development in rural areas. Health is one of the subjects transferred to the PRIs in India. PRIs are implementing State and centrally sponsored schemes under the direct supervision of the Health and Family Welfare Department of the State. Government of Karnataka has given a large amount of funds and other assistance to PRIs for up-gradation of rural health care system, but it is not reaching the beneficiaries due to the lack of active involvement of officials and corruption at PRIs. This paper tries to analyze the role and fund flow mechanism of Panchayati Raj Institutions in Rural Health Care System in Karnataka.

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1. Introduction

The process of decentralization was set into motion through 73rd and 74th amendments to the Indian Constitution. Many analysts thought that this was a panacea for all the ills of local administration. Basically, with these amendments, it was visualized to deepen the democratic foundations of the India. Studies done on NRHM suggested that for the improvement of rural health care system, there is a need for an effective implementation of health care programmes through PRIs, controlling of corruption at the managerial level, political commitment, active involvement of public, strengthening of public-private partnerships and NGOs. (Gandhi, 2016; Rao, 2003). It is usually understood that decentralization of health services would result in greater community participation. However, there were mixed reactions both from the legislatures and bureaucracy assuming that PRIs may deprive them of hitherto enjoyed power. However, with regard to the transfer of power, responsibilities and funds, the states have taken very lukewarm steps. These are very essential ingredients for the smooth functioning of PRIs. PRI needs strong human resources which transfers the ideas into action. Karnataka (where the current study is conducted) it is observed that the Government has transferred all the 29 subjects listed in the 11th schedule of the Constitution (Vyasulu and Vijayalakshmi 2015).

Both the National Health Policy (2002) and National Population Policy of Government of India (2000) emphasized the role of PRIs in Rural health care system. Even the National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) recognizes the critical role to be played by the PRIs in planning, implementation and monitoring of the NRHM. PRIs have a central role to play in improving the health status of the rural poor. The functionaries play a pivotal role in providing quality health care to the rural poor and disadvantaged and this can succeed if the functionaries are accountable to the PRIs.

2. Objective and Methodology of the Study

The present study was carried out with the objective of gaining insight into the small picture regarding role and fund flow mechanism to the PRIs system for the effective implementation of NRHM. The present study is based on various secondary data.

Karnataka is frequently quoted as a State which has introduced the health decentralization system for the first time in the country.

An event of almost epochal significance in the recent history of local government institutions in India is the performance of the 73rd and 74th Constitutional amendments. At the outset, these acts performed upon Panchayati Raj Institutions/PRIs and Urban Local Bodies/ULBs constitutional status for which a demand had been being articulated for several decades. This is generally due to the preceding legislation passed by the state in 1983 that was considered as a landmark step. Later 73rd amendments to the Constitution, Karnataka were the first State to pass the Karnataka Panchayati Raj Act, 1993, as per the 73rd Amendment and conducted to Gram Panchayat in December that year. This was the commencement of a full-fledged three-tier arrangement of Panchayati raj in Karnataka, to decentralize local governance in effective manner, through the Zilla Parishad and Talooka Panchayats. Politically, there is a broad consensus in favor of decentralization that finds a place in the ideologies of all political parties in the State. The process of making PRIs accountable for their specific roles is also tied up with the initiative on the rationalization of schemes.

3. Financial Assistance to Panchayati Raj Institutions

There is a need of high financial assistance for an effective implementation of health care programs under PRIs in Karnataka. The quantum of assistance provided in the form the grants to PRIs during the year 2013-14 have been analyzed here. Panchayats receives funds from both the consolidated fund of the state as well as from the central government to implement various health schemes. With regard to the implementation of fiscal transfers, it is known that the transfers are devolved in the form of schemes. Further, the 13th Finance Commission has earmarked Rs 68,895 (crores) as a general development grant to the state government. The required amount has been transferred to the various tiers of PRIs with the district, block, and village Panchayats. The assistance to PRIs increased from Rs. 11,407 crores in 2009-10 from previous Rs. 90345. Next, in 2010-2011 from 12,554.65 crore it is again increased to Rs. 13,856.32 cr.. A small increase portion when compare to 2011-12 can be seen. Next, in the year 2012-2013 Govt. allotted Rs. 18,532.58 crore for the effective implementation of new health care programs through PRIs. There is a significant outlay of total fiscal devolution of Rs. 20,513 crores to PRIs during 2013-14 (Source: Government of Karnataka report, 2015).

4. Allocation of Funds to Karnataka from Government of India under NRHM

The average annual rise in GOI fund allocation for the year in 2005-2006 towards RCH flexi pool is Rs. 72.26 cr. and for infrastructure & maintenance it was Rs. 110.88 cr. whereas for immunization it is Rs. 4.66 cr. and for National Disease Control Programmes (NDCP) Rs. 25.94 cr. In 2006-2007, the RCH flexi pool was Rs. 85.43 cr. which was less than NRHM flexi pool of Rs. 714.28 cr. For infrastructure & maintenance the allocated fund was Rs. 108.76 cr. and for NDCP it was Rs. 23.75 cr. Next, in the 2007-08 the RCH flexi pool was Rs. 69.25 cr. and NRHM flexi pool was Rs. 125.48 cr. whereas when comes to the Immunization programme it was Rs. 7.35 crore. We can say it has been increased when compared to the previous year. Next, for NDCP programme it has been increased up to Rs. 31.71 cr.

In 2008-09 the RCH flexi pool was Rs. 129.92 cr. and Rs. 9.99 cr. was earmarked for immunization programme and in the same year Rs. 36.34 cr. was allocated for NDCP programme. In the year 2009-10 the fund allocation was increased when compared to the year 2008-2009 whereas the total amount of Rs. 505.17 cr. was allocated for the various sub programmes under NRHM. Next, RCH flexi pool and NRHM flexi pool was slightly different in the year 2009-10. In the same year for rural infrastructure & maintenance a total of Rs. 177.58 cr was allocated.

However, during the year 2011-12, the level of allocation of fund to infrastructure & maintenance was Rs. 11,11.17 cr., which has increased when compared to the previous year whereas the total grant for RCH Flexi Pool and NRHM flex pool were Rs. 163.60 cr. and Rs. 201.42 cr. respectively as compared to the previous year. Also the allocation of the fund to NDCP programme was high when compared to the previous year of expenditure. The GoI fund allocation under NRHM has increased three fold the national level. In 2013-2014 State Zilla Panchayats have received Rs. 58,890 cr. whereas Talook Panchayats have received Rs. 13,779 cr., village Panchayats have received Rs. 48,226 cr. and District Panchayats have received Rs. 6,601 cr. of proportion. The ZP & TP grants are used for the developmental works as per the guidelines of the 13th Finance Commission of funds allocated to Grama Panchayats.

Development grant allocation is based on the basis of population and the geographical area of the district. In 2014-2015 the total

amount of Rs. 976.47 cr. was distributed to all Panchayats in the form of basic grants and performance grants respectively. Further, in 2014-2015 districts Panchayats have received Rs. 75.30 cr, block Panchayat have received Rs. 150.61 cr. and village Panchayats have received Rs. 527.12 cr. under basic grants. In the same way, in case of general basic grants, District Panchayats have received Rs. 22.34 cr. Talook Panchayats have received Rs. 44.69 cr. and village Panchayats have received Rs. 156.41 cr. respectively. We can find the reduction in the grants when compared to the previous year.

5. Plan and Non-plan Allocations for PRIs

Here we shall discuss about the plan and non-plan allocations under each tier of PRI. For the effective implementation of health care programmes under PRIs, the responsibility of the preparation of performance report and monitoring of all plan and non-plan schemes are being implemented by the health department now. During the year 2002-03 the plan allocation was 37.9% and non-plan allocation was 62.1% for Zilla Panchayats out of the total grant. In case of Taluk Panchayats, 14.5% was under plan allocations and 85.5% was under non-plan allocations. Next, in the year 2003-04, the ZP had a plan allocation of 37.7% and non-plan allocations of 62.3%. In case of Taluk Panchayats, 14% was for plan and 86% was for non-plan schemes. During 2004-05 ZP had a plan allocation of 41.5% under plan and 58.5% was under non plan scheme and for TP 16.3% was plan allocation funds and 83.7% were non-plan funds. In 2007-08 and 2008-09 there was a marked change where the State allocations to the Panchayats were very less when compared to the 2010-2011 and 2012-13 (Source: GoK 2001-2008).

The positive role of PRIs is quite evident in improving the quality of health care services, especially through ensuring enhanced turnout of health workers at the local level as well as exerting ethical and moral force on ground health staff not to evade from work when it comes to extra work in various components of NRHM. Also observant contribution and participation of needy local communities have played a vital role in a number of gauges in loopholes in the supplies of various materials, drug and other equipments by supplementing the local health workers by bringing the deficiencies in the valuable materials to the attention of higher authorities. Moreover, the PRIs are also able to key in significant roles by assuming vital duties of monitoring and supervision and

The Journal of Community Health Management

Publisher: Innovative Publication

Print ISSN: 2394-272X

Online ISSN: 2394-2738

Web: indianjournals.com

Downloaded IP: 128.128.128.169

A RETROSPECTION ON THE HEALTH INFRASTRUCTURE IN KARNATAKA

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ABSTRACT

Public health and hospitals fall in the State list, others such as population control and family welfare, medical education, and quality control of drugs are included in the Concurrent list. The Union Ministry of Health and Family Welfare (UMHFW) is the central authority responsible for implementation of various programmes and schemes in areas of family welfare, prevention, and control of major diseases. In the case of health the term infrastructure takes on a wider role than mere physical infrastructure. Healthcare centres, dispensaries, or hospitals need to be manned by well trained staff with a service perspective. In this chapter we include medical staff health infrastructure is an important indicator for understanding the health care policy and welfare mechanism in a country. It signifies the investment priority with regards to the creation of health care facilities. India has one of the largest populations in the world; coupled with this wide spread poverty becomes a serious problem in India

Key words: Health, Infrastructure, Development , Hospital

Introduction

The health infrastructures have been neglected since a long time. Various Governments also are giving low priorities for the health issues. Even after introducing NRHM and NUHM (National Urban Health Mission) programme situation has not completely improved. Reduction of funding for rural development in India in the budget also can be seen. Also rural and urban areas are facing the shortage of doctors and other paramedical staff. In some part of the rural areas none of the PHCs are having any good facility.

A striking feature of India's healthcare system is the significant and growing role of the private sector in healthcare delivery and total healthcare expenditures. Public health expenditure accounts for less than 1 percent of GDP compared to 3 percent of GDP for developing countries and 5 percent for high income countries. The private healthcare sector in India accounts for over 75 percent

of total healthcare expenditure in the country and is one of the largest in the world. An estimated 60 percent of hospitals, 75 percent of dispensaries, and 80 percent of all qualified doctors are in the private sector. However, private healthcare delivery is highly fragmented with over 90 percent of private healthcare being serviced by the unorganized sector, according to a recent consulting firm report.¹ Some 2 to 3 percent of hospitals are 200-bed plus, some 6-7 percent are 100-200 bed size hospitals, and the bulk 80 percent of private sector hospitals are very small, less than 30 beds.

Studies by the Central Bureau of Health Intelligence² have shown that a majority of Indians trust private healthcare despite a higher average cost of US\$ 4.3 compared to US\$ 2.7 in government-owned healthcare agencies. Only 23.5 percent of urban residents and 30.6 percent of rural residents choose government facilities, reflecting the widespread lack of confidence

in the public healthcare system. The private sector's role is expected to grow in the future. It is estimated that out of the 1 million beds to be added by 2012, the private sector will contribute 896,000 beds. Government spending on healthcare infrastructure (excluding land) is projected to rise only marginally, by 0.12 percent of GDP and is expected to meet only 12 percent of the huge investment required in

the healthcare sector, with the private sector providing some 88 percent of investment requirements.³ Hence, the private sector will be a key player in driving the future growth of India's healthcare sector, including in segments such as hospitals, wing demand and to compare favorably with international standards.

Table-1: Bird view of Rural Health Care Service in Karnataka

Sl. No.	Availability of Man power Resources in Rural Health Centers	%
1	Sub Centers	24.6
2	PHCs	66.8
3	Resident ANM	54.2
4	Male Health Workers	6.9
5	Female Health Workers	62.5
6	Availability of Additional ANM's	37.5
7	Deficit of ANM's	53.9
8	24×7 Delivery Services	37.5
9	Trained ANM	95.9
10	Estimated Expenditure on Primary Health Center	83.3
11	Availability of Total Specialists	8.9
12	AYSUH Facility	10.0
13	Total Number of Primary Health Centers	250
14	Availability of Surgeons	10.0
15	Availability of General Specialists	25.0
16	Gynecics	4.0
17	Pediatrics	25.0
18	Doctors in Sub-Centers	25.0
19	Anesthesia	1.0
20	General facility	8.0

Source: NRHM Report, 2009

Table- 2: Division wise Selected Health Infrastructure Facilities in Karnataka, 2010

Item		Belgaum	Gulbarga	Bangalore	Mysore	North	South	Karnataka
Facilities								
Per 10 Lakh Population	District and other Hospitals	0.9 (4)	1 (3)	1.2 (2)	1.4 (1)	1	1.3	1.1
	Community Health Centres	5.5 (3)	6.5 (2)	3.4 (4)	7.4 (1)	5.9	4.8	5.3
	PHCs and Sub Centres	154 (2)	142 (3)	135 (4)	271 (1)	149	184	169
	Total Beds	764 (3)	789 (2)	737 (4)	1196 (1)	775	901	847
Per 10 thousand sq KMs area	District and other Hospitals	2.6 (3)	2.5 (4)	5.4 (1)	3.9 (2)	2.5	4.7	3.6
	Community Health Centres	14.9 (4)	16.6 (2)	15.5 (3)	21.4 (1)	15.6	18.2	16.9
	PHCs and Sub Centres	418 (3)	365 (4)	614 (2)	783 (1)	394	693	539
	Total Beds	2070 (3)	2019 (4)	3337 (2)	3455 (1)	2047	3392	2701
Status								
Infant mortality rate		47.6 (1)	47.3 (2)	38.4 (4)	42.7 (3)	47.5	40.4	43.3
Life expectancy at birth		65.6 (4)	66.6 (3)	68.6 (1)	67.4 (2)	66.0	68.1	67.2

Note: Figures in the Parenthesis are Ranks

Source: Computed from the data available from Karnataka at a Glance, 2011

Table- 4: District wise Normalized Indicators on Health Infrastructure Facilities in Karnataka, 2010

Name	District & other Hospt's	CHC*	PHCs & Sub Centres	Total Beds	District & other Hospt'	CHC*	PHCs & Sub-Centres	Total Beds	Index	Index Rank
Bagalkot	0.47	1.20	0.85	0.69	0.42	1.08	0.76	0.62	0.76	25
Belgaum	0.19	0.95	0.85	0.71	0.21	1.06	0.95	0.79	0.71	29
Bellary	2.10	0.97	0.80	1.26	1.98	0.91	0.75	1.19	1.24	11
Bidar	0.52	1.11	0.99	0.85	0.51	1.09	0.97	0.84	0.86	22
Bijapur	0.81	1.04	0.95	0.80	0.53	0.68	0.62	0.52	0.74	27
Dharwad	1.92	0.31	0.67	1.22	2.63	0.42	0.92	1.66	1.22	12
Gadag	2.50	1.06	1.16	0.95	1.79	0.76	0.83	0.68	1.22	13
Gulbarga	0.24	1.51	0.80	0.90	0.17	1.09	0.58	0.65	0.74	28
Haveri	0.56	1.31	1.34	0.84	0.57	1.34	1.37	0.86	1.03	17
Koppal	1.27	1.49	0.97	0.76	0.66	0.77	0.50	0.39	0.85	23
Raichur	0.46	0.88	0.76	0.75	0.50	0.96	0.83	0.82	0.75	26
Uttara Kannada	1.23	1.71	0.82	1.59	0.54	0.75	0.36	0.70	0.96	20
Bangalore	1.11	0.12	0.16	0.61	15.23	1.62	2.18	8.40	3.68	1
Bangalore Rural	0.90	0.57	1.42	0.73	2.97	1.90	4.71	2.42	1.95	2
Chamaraja Nagar	0.87	1.11	1.75	1.20	0.49	0.62	0.99	0.68	0.96	19
Chikkaballa- Pura	0.71	1.05	1.13	0.89	2.10	3.13	3.36	2.65	1.88	4
Chikmagalur	1.56	1.66	2.20	1.53	0.77	0.82	1.09	0.76	1.30	10
Chitradurga	0.53	1.70	1.28	1.11	0.33	1.06	0.79	0.69	0.94	21
Dakshina Kannada	1.28	0.91	1.41	1.14	1.72	1.22	1.90	1.54	1.39	8
Davanagere	1.37	0.87	1.19	1.27	1.39	0.89	1.21	1.29	1.18	14
Hassan	0.50	2.23	1.81	1.85	0.41	1.82	1.48	1.52	1.45	7
Kodagu	3.19	2.72	2.34	2.57	1.36	1.15	0.99	1.09	1.93	3
Kolar	2.88	0.73	1.00	1.31	1.69	0.43	0.59	0.77	1.18	15
Mandya	0.98	1.15	1.58	1.26	1.12	1.31	1.80	1.44	1.33	9
Mysore	1.18	1.07	1.12	1.40	1.77	1.61	1.68	2.10	1.49	6
Ramanagara	0.82	1.22	1.60	0.87	0.78	1.17	1.53	0.83	1.10	16
Shimoga	1.01	1.18	1.33	1.21	0.66	0.77	0.87	0.79	0.98	18
Tumkur	0.33	0.91	1.35	0.92	0.26	0.73	1.07	0.73	0.79	24
Udupi	1.50	1.60	1.83	1.02	1.55	1.65	1.88	1.04	1.51	5
Karnataka	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	---
North	0.85	1.11	0.88	0.91	0.70	0.92	0.73	0.76	0.86	---
South	1.11	0.92	1.09	1.06	1.31	1.08	1.28	1.26	1.14	---

Note : * CHC = Community Health Centre

Source: Karnataka at a Glance, 2011

DECENTRALIZATION OF HEALTH GOVERNANCE

Primary Health Centers: The primary health centre should have a building with water, electricity, and toilet facilities. In addition, it must also have a labour room, telephone connection, one vehicle, and at least one bed. As compared to the sub-centres more than 70 percent PHCs have own buildings in the states except for Uttar Pradesh where only about 60 per cent of the PHCs have own building. From Table 8 it is observed that the infrastructure is poor with respect to availability of water, labour room, and to a certain extent vehicle also. Comparing the facilities of infrastructure in PHCs in all states, all four southern states, Gujarat and Maharashtra are well equipped with all the necessary facilities. The percentage of PHCs with labour room, telephone, and vehicle facility is very low in the low income and high poverty states namely Bihar, Chattisgarh, Jharkhand, M.P, Orissa, Rajasthan, and U.P. PHCs with at least one bed account for more than 70 per cent of total in all states except Assam, Bihar, Chattisgarh, M.P., and West Bengal.

Community Health Centres (CHC): Community health centers are located at the Block or Tehsil level head quarters. The infrastructural facility at each CHC is larger as compared to PHC. This includes electricity generation, operation theatre, specialized OPD, and linkage with blood bank. By and large, we observe that the CHC are equipped with basic facilities such as water, electricity, telephone, and vehicle. They however, lack the other specialized facilities such as operation theatre, specialized OPD, and linkage with blood bank. This is true across all the states irrespective of their levels of development

India at presently undergoing for two developed paradigms having the potential to considerably get better the health of its people. The first is the mounting identification of drawbacks' in

public delivery of health services is in catastrophe. And the second is India's massive hard work to reinforce rural health care through the decentralization to local Governments Panchayat Raj Institutions (PRI). It is argued that that these two presumably separate trends can converge to generate real reform in the health sector in India through the potential for increased accountability that local government scan provide.⁴ The real concept is that decentralization brings governments closer to people thus allowing them to act in response additional efficiently to local health needs and preferences. Studies on rural decentralization even argued that decentralization is a misnomer in Karnataka. In the health sector, decentralization has been clearly played a vital role in the chain of service delivery under the National Rural Health Mission (NRHM). Thus efforts at rural decentralization (73rd Amendment) have been undertaken within the context of strengthening accountability in governance structures. "Moreover, proximity encourages better monitoring and enforcement. In the specific context of the health sector, a decentralized institutional structure that emphasizes a bottom up, participatory approach can indeed help to redress some of the key failings in the sector such as absenteeism and corruption by strengthening accountability through NRHM programme".⁴ Experts felt there is a need of having more research study to find out capacities of Panchayatraj Institutions to manage the grass root health system in Karnataka state and to find out does the degree of decentralization under the NRHM correlate strongly with perceived decision space of Health officials and PRI members at the District level and below .

The PRIs are seen critical to the planning, implementation, and monitoring of the NRHM. The success of NRHM significantly depends on the well

functioning Gram, Block and District level Panchayats. A village health committee is an integral part of every Panchayat. The PRIs through village health committees to create a link between the Gram Panchayat and the community. The village health committee is expected to prepare a village health plan and maintain village level data supervised by the Gram Panchayat. Engaging the Gram Panchayat and other smaller groups in the planning and monitoring of the Village Health Plan enforces transparency and accountability within the programme.

Indian health care delivery system has a long history which can be traced back to British era. It looks very sound on paper in terms of policy formulations and health programme planning. But a careful evaluation of impact of these policies and programmes show that the results are far from satisfactory. Indian health system is ranked 118 among 191 WHO member countries on overall health performance. The key issues are availability, access, affordability, quality, equity and efficiency. Health is a priority goal in its own right, as well as a central input into economic development and poverty reduction. India's health system is at crossroads today. The

third wave of healthcare is upon us. The first wave was the government run healthcare delivery model. The influx of private players defined the second. Now a discerning and interconnected nation demands a new incarnation, that will transform the very ground rules of healthcare and that will catalyze its participants to engage with a billion plus people across the length and breadth of our diverse nation.

Conclusion:

Key factors that adversely affect the functioning of the public health system are poor management of resources and centralized decision-making, low budgets, irregular supplies, large-scale absenteeism, corruption, absence of performance-based monitoring and conflicting job roles making accountability problematic. There is a real need for HRD policies related to recruitment, promotion, transfer and training. The demoralization and deionization that exists among the workforce must be countered by enhancing professional competencies and career opportunities. The neglect in developing the required skill mix and in particular public health expertise is hindering us from achieving national health goals

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ISSN-0976-0245 (Print) • ISSN-0976-5506 (Electronic)

Volume 3 Number 1 January - March, 2012

Indian Journal of Public Health Research & Development

An International Journal

Functioning of Primary Health Centers in the Selected Rural districts of Karnataka-India: Some Preliminary Observations

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Abstract

The Primary Health Centre (PHC) occupies a key position in nation's health care system. The primary health centers PHC are the principle institutions providing integrated health services to the rural population. The PHC complex constitutes the core to the rural health care services programme in the country. This present study has conducted in selected rural areas of Karnataka about functioning of PHCs. Total of 35 PHCs in Four districts of Karnataka were selected for the random study. Data were analyzed using suitable software's. These findings is corroborated with another study conducted in Karnataka on PHCs concluded that non availability of adequate man power, finance and equipment were some of the prime reasons why rural have negative perception about the PHCs. Further this study has shown that there is a dearth need of policy changes regarding PHC is concern.

Introduction

In India, Primary Health Centers (PHCs) are the keystone of rural and tribal healthcare. A first port of call for the sick and an effective referral system. It forms the first level of contact and a link between individuals and the health system, bringing healthcare delivery as close as potential to where people live and work. In addition, these PHCs charged with providing promotive, preventive, curative and rehabilitative care in urban rural and tribal areas. In India, although there are many reasons for poor PHC performance, almost all of them stem from weak stewardship of the sector, which produces a poor incentive framework. Primary healthcare is indispensable healthcare based on sensible, scientifically sound and available methods and technology made generally available to individuals in the community through their involvement and at a cost the community and country can afford to sustain at every stage of their advancement to the point of self-reliance and self-determination.

A typical Primary Health Centre covers a population of 20,000 in hilly, tribal, or difficult areas and 30,000 populations in plain areas with 4-6 indoor/observation beds. It acts as a referral unit for 6 sub-centres and refer out cases to Community Health Centers (CHC) (30 bedded hospital) and higher order public hospitals located at sub-district and district level. Primary Health Centers (PHCs) form the back bone of the public health system in rural and tribal India. Mudaliar committee (1955) Jungalwalla Committee (1965) Karthar singh committee(1973) and Shrivatsva committee (1975) Bajaj committee, (1986) have also highlighted the importance of up gradation of PHCs. In spite of the criticism they have faced regarding quality of care and poor infrastructure, they continue to be the major primary care provider for the majority of India's population who reside in rural areas (Singh 2001).

Although poverty and low levels of education are the root causes, poor stewardship over the health system bears some responsibility. India's primary healthcare system is based on the Primary Health Centres (PHC) which is not spared from issues such as the inability to detect diseases early due to lack of multi-disciplinary medical expertise and laboratory facilities and insufficient quantities of general medicines. At the same time, patients usually do not visit PHCs in the early stages of their diseases, while healthcare providers (if at all present) are forced to focus only on seriously ill patients due to the volume of cases. The lack of accountability stems from the fact that there is no formal feedback mechanism and incentive to treat citizens as clients. Patients often complain of rude and abrupt health workers that discriminate against women and minorities from scheduled castes or tribes. The lack of accountability leads to absentee doctors as it is difficult to attract qualified doctors to rural areas. In addition ANMs, inconvenient opening times and little or no community participation (Raghuwani, 1991)

Establishing of essential primary health centers (PHCs)

Change in Status of Health Facilities in Rural Karnataka, September 2005.

Sl. No.	PHC	Sub-Centre	PHC	Sub-Centre
1	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
2	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
3	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
4	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
5	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
6	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
7	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
8	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
9	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
10	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
11	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
12	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
13	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
14	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
15	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
16	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
17	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
18	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
19	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
20	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
21	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
22	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
23	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
24	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
25	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
26	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
27	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
28	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
29	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
30	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
31	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
32	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
33	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
34	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02
35	111.02	111.02	111.02	111.02

in 'rural' development blocks was an integral part of various rural programme implemented since 1947. Bhore committee report had recommended to open PHCs to cover only a population of 10000 and have 6 specialist doctors, 75 beds and other required staffs. However, each PHC complex in the rural blocks consists of 6 beds, 1 medical officer, 2 midwives and 1 ancillary persons. Various Governments have taken appropriate measurements to upgrade the PHCs based various experts' committee reports. Recent national health policy has laid stress on people centered primary health care approach. Still ICMR report has revealed that more than 80 percent of the population has no access to any form of health care. However, curative service, people perception about functioning of PHCs, preventive activities and attitude of the health staffs need to be properly evaluated through various research approaches. This current study examines functioning of PHCs has viewed by the community in the selected rural blocks of south Karnataka.

PHCs in Karnataka

In Karnataka the PHCs were started only in the Adhoc-plan years after the 3rd Five Year Plan by opening 34 PHCs with 55 Sub-Centres. During the Fourth Five Year Plan 24 PHCs with 66 Sub-Centres were further opened. Thus at the end of the Five Year Plan there were 236 P.H.C s and 141 Sub-Centres in the state. The total strength of the PHCs in the state at this time is 2164. Out of which more than half of the PHC s are working in Rural and few of them working in the tribal dominant are of the State. Recent national health policy has laid stress on people centered primary health care approach. Still ICMR report has revealed that more than 80 percent of the population has no access to any form of health care including PHC service. However, Experts feels curative service, people perception about functioning of PHCs, preventive activities and attitude of the health staffs need to be properly evaluated through various research approaches.

Objectives

1. To find out the degree of usage of the health care services accessible in selected P.H.Cs;
2. To ascertain the excellence of health care services delivered by the studied P.H.Cs;
3. To scrutinize community perception concerning the working style of PHCs

About the study areas

This current study was undertaken in three rural dominant districts of South Karnataka (Mysore, Chamaraja Nagar and Kodagu). The average literacy rate of these districts is 61 percent with the moderate fundamental infrastructures.

Methodology

A. Material and methods adopted;

1. Survey
2. Community norms study
3. Institutional Ethnography (NGOs prospective)

B. Data collection and Analysis

This study was undertaken during April 2010 to July 2010. A Total of 35 PHCs were randomly selected in the three districts for the pilot-study. For qualitative data, 100 rural beneficiaries were selected (50 men, 50 women). It collected through open-ended questionnaires using indepth interviews, matrix method and focus groups study.

C. Sources

PHCs staffs, patients, local politics leaders etc.

D. Tools for data collection

1. Survey
2. Case Study
3. Interview
4. Participant observation
5. Content analysis

Date Analysis: Quantitative data has been analyzed using SPSS database and qualitative data has been analyzed using NUD*ISD software.

Result and Discussion

1. Number of studied PHCs in the Rural Area

Districts	Total number of PHCs working	Number of studied PHCs	Mobile units
Mysore	27	13	2
Chamaraja Nagar	22	12	1
Kodagu	12	1	1
Total	61	35	4

Discussion

This study revealed a number of critical problems: doctors are not available in 45percent of the time at PHCs. There is a high vacancy rate for medical personnel, especially in positions for nurses (43per cent), pharmacists (52 per cent), and lab technicians (23 per cent); patients must purchase drugs from outside of the PHCs only. 20per

Tab 1 (a): How often does a physician visits to PHC?

Response	Men		Women		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Regular	26	26.00	48	48.00	74	37.00
often	37	37.00	39	39.00	76	38.00
Rare	21	21.00	13	13.00	34	17.00
No visit	16	16.00	-	-	16	8.00
Total	100	100.0%	100	100.0%	200	100.0%

$\chi^2=4.665; P<.198$ $\chi^2=39.059; P<.000^*$ $\chi^2=20.172; P<.000^*$
 χ^2 (Male*Female) =24.478; P<.000*

Tab 2 (b): How often does a peripheral health workers visit to PHC?

Response	Men		Women		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Regular	53	53.00	42	42.00	95	47.50
often	42	42.00	51	51.00	93	46.50
Rare	3	3.00	3	3.00	6	3.00
No visit	2	2.00	4	4.00	6	3.00
Total	100	100.0%	100	100.0%	100	100.0%

$X^2=51.243; P<.000$ $X^2=45.701; P<.000$ $X^2=96.038; P<.000^*$
 $X^2(\text{Male*Female})=2.811; P<.422$

Tab 3 (c): Do you think PHCs have all facilities?

Response	Men		Women		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Yes	46	46.00	58	58.00	104	52.00
No	49	49.00	36	36.00	85	42.50
Don't Know	4	4.00	4	4.00	8	4.00
No response	1	1.00	2	2.00	3	1.50
Total	100	100.0%	100	100.0%	100	100.0%

$X^2=51.356; P<.000$ $X^2=49.904; P<.000$ $X^2=100.102; P<.000^*$
 $X^2(\text{Male*Female})=3.706; P<.295$

Tab 4: Are u satisfied by the delivery of the service

Response	Men		Women		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Yes	54	54.00	48	48.00	102	51.00
No	41	41.00	46	46.00	87	43.50
Don't Know	5	5.00	5	6.00	11	5.50
No response	0	00	0	00	0	00
Total	100	100.0%	100	100.0%	100	100.0%

$X^2=23.561; P<.000$ $X^2=23.605; P<.000$ $X^2=49.874; P<.000^*$
 $X^2(\text{Male*Female})=0.731; P<.694$

cent of the time even though they are entitled to get free medicines; stock-outs of drugs last up to 14 weeks; it is found that patients are prescribed drugs in quantities below the standard prescription size. The flow of funds for the purchase of drugs is circuitous. There are delays in the receipt of funds for drugs by the district government and in the procurement and delivery of drugs to PHCs and PHCs do not conduct proper accounting. In this study, an attempt has been made to examine the perception of rural beneficiaries about quality of health care in their respective PHCs. This study has found that 26 percent of rural people are showing interest to visit near by private health centers because of non-availability of regular staff, equipment, medicine and diagnostic facilities. 4 percent of rural population is using indigenous medicines for their health issues as side effect in modern medicine. It is also found that factors like rude behaviour of the staff,

Tab 5 (d): Are you facing this problem at P.H.Cs?

Response	Men		Women		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Long hour of waiting	28	28.00	19	19.00	47	23.50
Distance factor	23	23.00	23	23.00	46	23.00
Absence of Doctors	21	21.00	28	28.00	49	24.50
No medicine available	17	17.00	16	16.00	33	16.50
No upgraded facility	4	4.00	6	6.00	10	5.00
Rude behaviors of Staff	7	7.00	3	3.00	10	5.00
No lady doctor	0	0.00	5	5.00	5	2.50
Total	100	100.0%	100	100.0%	100	100.0%

$X^2=30.418; P<.000$ $X^2=22.310; P<.001$ $X^2=48.376; P<.000^*$
 $X^2(\text{Male*Female})=9.754; P<.135$

Tab 6 (e): Are you satisfied with service?

Response	Men		Women		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Yes	24	24.00	31	31.00	55	27.50
No	72	72.00	68	68.00	140	70.00
No response	4	4.00	1	1.00	5	2.50
Total	100	100.0%	100	100.0%	100	100.0%

$X^2=38.632; P<.000$ $X^2=42.305; P<.000$ $X^2=79.983; P<.000^*$
 $X^2(\text{Male*Female})=2.805; P<.246$

Tab 7 (f): Reasons for not visiting PHCs

Response	Men		Women		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Lack of knowledge	45	45.00	31	31.00	76	38.00
Not felt necessary	32	32.00	48	48.00	80	40.00
Not customary	6	6.00	8	8.00	14	7.00
No time to go	4	4.00	6	6.00	10	5.00
Traditional healers is efficient	9	9.00	5	5.00	14	7.00
other	4	4.00	2	2.00	6	3.00
Total	100	100.0%	100	100.0%	100	100.0%

$X^2=41.039; P<.000$ $X^2=45.741; P<.001$ $X^2=83.924; P<.000^*$
 $X^2(\text{Male*Female})=8.274; P<.142$

Tab 8 (d): Opinion of PHCs Staff about Govt Policy

Response	Total	
	f	%
Grant is not enough	32	32.00
No facility for staffs	47	47.00
Distance factors	6	6.00
Safety factors	9	9.00
other	6	6.00
Total	100	100.0%

$\chi^2=32.899; P < .000$

Tab 9: Facility Available in the Studied PHCs

Sr. No.	Facility	PHCs (percentage available) out of studied PHCs
1	Own building	32%
2	With Labour Room	62%
3	With Operation theatre	59%
4	With 4-6 Beds	62%
5	With 24 Hrs. Delivery Facility	74%
6	Without Electric Supply	2.7%
7	With Telephone	55.9%
8	With Toilet	73%
9	Generator Functional	51.9%
10	Vehicle Functional	64.6%
12	Gynaec OPD	41.2%
14	Linkage with Dist Blood Bank	16.3%

distance factors, transport problem, long waiting time, non availability of lady physician are some of the other reasons why this rural beneficiaries not showing interest to visit PHCs. These findings is corroborated with another study conducted in Karnataka on PHCs concluded that non availability of adequate man power, finance and equipment were some of the prime reasons why rurals have negative perception about the PHCs (Srinivasan 2004).

On the other hand majority of the staff of PHCs have expressed their problems including lack of proper accommodation, lack of amenities in PHCs, buildings, transport problem and inadequate supply of both medicines and equipments and bureaucratic practice in transferring physicians and p.m staff. Regarding process of medical care, the frequent transfer of doctors and health staff, lack of their dedication, indifferent attitude towards people, lethargy, doctors lack of interest to go to rural areas, insufficient or untimely supply of medicine are observable in rural PHCs. Regarding outcome of service, there is lack of aftercare services, lack of attention towards prevention of diseases before their actual attack, lack of follow up methods are explicitly visible in rural areas of Karnataka.

Choosing a PHC to seek health care and treatment

Tab 10: Work force Available in the Studied PHCs

	Service	PHCs
1	Multipurpose Worker/ANMs (Female)	76 %
3	Doctors	45%
4	General duty doctor s(Male)	78%
5	General duty doctors (Female)	61%
6	Staff Nurse s	82%
7	Laboratory Assistant	65%
8	Obstetrician & Gynaecologist	34%
9	Paediatricians	22%
10	RTI/SSTI Specialist	62%
12	Anaesthesiologist	55%
13	Radiographers	54%

depends upon several criteria. Most often, why the beneficiary families do not visit the primary Health Centres coming under the 4th jurisdiction have several reasons. The common causes for the low level of the choice of PHCs for health care treatment are the lack of knowledge among the beneficiary families at PHCs, lack of funds at PHCs to provide efficient service, and the repeated absence of doctors at the centers. When all these factors comes together, people prefer to go to private hospitals instead of PHCs.

During the course of its research, it is discovered that policymakers, PHC users, communities, and even NGOs are not fully aware of various problems. Both communities and NGOs lack access to relevant information on health services, and they are not involved in monitoring service providers. Furthermore, local government bodies responsible for health services are not accountable to communities.

Suggestive Conclusion

The initial step is to equip the existing PHCs (land, building, equipment, and supplies) previously set up by the government. Each PHC should consist of an preliminary screening room with a computer, an examination room for the doctor, a laboratory for medical tests and supplies, and toilets. The most serious infrastructure element is electricity. Govt should think either solar panels or diesel generators (depending on a cost-benefit analysis) connected to batteries for uninterrupted electric power for computers and Each PHC should have a full time staff consisting of a lady doctor paramedic individual to perform initial screening tests , a trained nurse or physicians' assistant, and a laboratory technician. In addition to the testing capability of the on-site medical laboratory, a decisive tool for analysis (diagnose) will be the usage of computers. Govt. should provide this to every PHCs. Patients visiting PHCs should also be provided health education by the staff through posters and through audiovisual demonstrations.

Providing information and help with family planning, and awareness on communicable diseases, should be the role of the staff. Community programs in collaborations with Non-Governmental Agencies (NGOs) and social workers will supplement these activities. As a final step, we advise enhancing the diagnostic capability of PHCs through video consultations wherein the patient (through the PHC) will access a physician (and even a specialist) via a two-way video camera and screen if possible with the help of NGOs.

Acknowledgment

Author is grateful to Mr. Venu gopal P N, M Dinesh PT, and Muddu raju for their logistic support.

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